

International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Technology
 ISSN 2582-7359
 Peer Reviewed Journal,
 Impact Factor 6.325

www.ijmrtjournal.com

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY

**SRI BHAGAWAN MAHAVEER
 JAIN EVENING COLLEGE**

(Affiliated to Bengaluru City University)
 V V Puram Bengaluru 560004

In Association with IQAC, NAAC
 Organized
**INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
 ON**

Volume - 4
 Issue - 8
 (Special Issue, August 2023)

**RECENT ADVANCEMENT AND INNOVATION IN
 BUSINESS & MANAGEMENT & ITS
 CONTEMPORARY ISSUES IN SUSTAINABLE ECONOMICS
 "ICRAIMB 2023**

Date: 02 & 03 August 2023

International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Technology
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**International Conference Recent Advancement
and Innovation in Business & Management &
Its Contemporary Issues in Sustainable
Economy “ICRAIBM 2023”
2nd & 3rd August 2023**

Publication Partner
**International Journal of Multidisciplinary
Research and Technology**

ABOUT COLLEGE – SRI BHAGAWAN MAHAVEER JAIN EVENING COLLEGE, AFFILIATED TO BENGALURU CITY UNIVERSITY, BENGALURU

Sri Bhagawan Mahaveer Jain Evening College is an esteemed educational institution known for its commitment to academic excellence, holistic development, and ethical values. Situated in Bengaluru, this college has been a beacon of knowledge and learning since its establishment.

Founded with the vision of imparting quality education rooted in Jain principles, SBMJEC strives to nurture students into well-rounded individuals who possess not only intellectual acumen but also a deep sense of social responsibility. The college offers a wide range of undergraduate and postgraduate programs across various disciplines, catering to the diverse interests and aspirations of its students.

At SBMJEC, education goes beyond textbooks and classrooms. The college emphasizes the importance of experiential learning, providing ample opportunities for students to engage in practical applications of their knowledge through internships, research projects, and community service initiatives. This holistic approach to education ensures that students not only acquire subject-specific expertise but also develop critical thinking, problem-solving, and interpersonal skills that are essential for success in the professional world.

The college boasts a highly qualified and dedicated faculty who are not only experts in their respective fields but also mentors and guides to the students. They foster an environment of intellectual curiosity, encouraging students to explore new ideas, challenge existing notions, and embrace lifelong learning.

Apart from academics, SBMJEC offers a vibrant campus life with a range of extracurricular activities, clubs, and student organizations. These provide students with opportunities to pursue their passions, develop leadership skills, and form lasting friendships.

With its state-of-the-art facilities, well-stocked library, advanced laboratories, and modern infrastructure, SBMJEC provides an ideal environment for students to thrive academically, intellectually, and personally.

SBMJEC stands as a prestigious institution that instills a sense of purpose, integrity, and excellence in its students. It equips them with the knowledge, skills, and values necessary to succeed in their chosen fields and make a positive impact on society.

ABOUT THE INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE - ICRAIBM 2023

The conference aims to provide a platform for knowledge sharing between academic researchers and business practitioners in order to support transformative changes for addressing contemporary organizational challenges. Disruptive technologies and innovations are challenging businesses to rethink who they are, what they stand for, how they operate and how they could organize for the future. For successfully pivoting the business, organizations must nurture a culture that promotes constant transformation and understand that convergence in all spheres is absolutely critical when making transformations. Facing a complex future, leaders/managers increasingly need research-based information and evidence more than ever.

The academic research scenario in India is changing in light of the recent developments in educational reforms, especially with the implementation of NEP 2020, which seeks to transform higher education by focusing on skill-based education to meet the rapidly changing needs of the industry and the economy.

Towards this, the UGC has taken a new initiative to bring the industry and other professional expertise into the academic institutions by creating a new category of positions called Professor of Practice, through which industry experts will be brought in to play the role of faculty members in the Higher Education Institutions (Hei's). All these necessitate broader and deeper engagements between Hei's and industry

partners, wherein academia needs to build a consultative and collaborative approach to working with businesses and building programs that meet business needs.

In this context, the central theme of the conference is focused on making academic research more relevant to business organizations and bringing together suggestions to enhance the relevance of academic research to practice on a real-time basis.

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BANGALORE

DR. GHOUSIA KHATOON

PROFESSOR, TISHK INTERNATIONAL UNIVERSITY

IRAQ

KEYNOTE SPEAKERS: DAY 2

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PROFESSOR & HEAD, DEPARTMENT OF MANAGEMENT, UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY,
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VINAY BN

PROJECT PROGRAM MANAGEMENT SPECIALIST, NTT DATA

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MESSAGE BY THE CHAIRMAN & FOUNDER

DR. CHENRAJ ROYCHAND -JGI- JAIN GROUP OF INSTITUTION

I am honoured to address you all as we gather here today for the prestigious two-day International Conference organised by SBM Jain Evening college on "Recent Advancement and Innovation in Business & Management and Its Contemporary Issues in Sustainable Economy." This event serves as a remarkable platform for professionals, academics, and visionaries from around the globe to converge and share their insights on the pressing matters that shape our world.

In an era defined by rapid change and evolving challenges, the importance of exploring the realms of business and management within the context of a sustainable economy cannot be overstated. Today, as we witness the interplay between innovation, entrepreneurship, and environmental consciousness, we must chart a course that not only maximizes economic growth but also ensures the well-being of our planet and its inhabitants.

Our distinguished speakers, renowned experts in their respective fields, will share their knowledge, expertise, and groundbreaking research, offering unique perspectives and insights. Their contributions will undoubtedly stimulate thought-provoking discussions, foster collaboration, and inspire innovative solutions that can drive us towards a more sustainable and prosperous future.

This conference is not just a mere gathering of minds but an opportunity to forge meaningful connections, build networks, and cultivate partnerships. As we engage in stimulating conversations, let us seize the chance to exchange ideas, challenge conventional wisdom, and uncover new approaches that can pave the way for transformative change.

I extend my heartfelt gratitude to the organizing committee, whose tireless efforts have brought us all together. Their dedication, passion, and meticulous planning have ensured the success of this conference, which promises to be a remarkable experience for all involved.

I would like to express my deepest appreciation to all the participants who have travelled from different corners of the globe to be here today. Your presence signifies your commitment to advancing knowledge, promoting sustainability, and shaping a better future for generations to come.

Let us embark on this journey of discovery, enlightenment, and collaboration. May the next two days be filled with thought-provoking discussions, insightful presentations, and meaningful connections. I have no doubt that the ideas and solutions generated during this conference will make a lasting impact on the world of business, management, and our sustainable economy. I wish you all a productive and rewarding conference.

MESSAGE BY THE PRINCIPAL

DR. K. M. MAHESH, PRINCIPAL SBM JAIN EVENING COLLEGE, BENGALURU & SYNDICATE MEMBER BENGALURU CITY UNIVERSITY

It is my utmost pleasure to extend a warm welcome to all of you to the prestigious International Conference on "Recent Advancement and Innovation in Business & Management and Its Contemporary Issues in Sustainable Economy," hosted by SBMJEC. This two-day event, scheduled to take place on the 2nd and 3rd of August, promises to be a remarkable gathering of thought leaders, professionals, and academicians from across the globe.

As the Principal of SBMJEC, I am thrilled to witness the convergence of brilliant minds and passionate individuals who share a common goal: to explore, discuss, and shape the future of business and management within the realm of a sustainable economy. This conference offers a platform to exchange groundbreaking ideas, cutting-edge research findings, and innovative strategies that will propel us towards a more sustainable and prosperous world. In an era where businesses and organizations are increasingly called upon to balance profitability with social and environmental responsibility, the need for advancements and innovations in business and management practices becomes more pronounced.

During the next two days, our distinguished speakers, renowned experts in their respective fields, will take centre stage to share their expertise and experiences. Their presentations, panel discussions, and interactive sessions will provide an opportunity for profound learning, critical analysis, and collaborative problem-solving. Through these exchanges, we aim to identify and address the contemporary issues faced by businesses and management in the pursuit of sustainability.

I express my heartfelt gratitude to the conference conveners Dr. Lakshman K Associate professor & Head, Department of Management, SBM Jain Evening college & Mrs. Shruti MS, Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Commerce, SBM Jain Evening College, organizing committee, teaching staff & non-teaching staff, students whose unwavering commitment and meticulous planning have made this conference possible. Their dedication, foresight, and attention to detail ensure that this event is of the highest standard, offering a memorable and enriching experience for all attendees.

I would like to extend my sincere appreciation to each participant who has joined us for this conference. I am excited about the possibilities that lie ahead and the transformative discussions that will take place during this conference. Together, let us embrace the power of innovation, drive change, and pave the way for a more sustainable future.

KEYNOTE SPEAKERS FOR DAY 1 ICRAIBM 2023

Dr. Ramalakshmi

Professor Of MBA At Krupa Nidhi Group of Institutions
Bangalore

Dedicated and experienced college professor with over twenty years of experience serving as Associate Professor in MBA Department. Proficient in creating powerful curriculum in the fields of Mathematics, Statistics and Operations Research. Expert at working with students to successfully prepare them for personal and professional success in today's world. Knowledgeable and experienced in various educational philosophies, which best promote the overall experience of a student. A committed faculty member, passionate about working to further enhance the educational offerings of an institution.

Dr. Ghousia Khatoon

Professor & Head, Tishk International University
Iraq

She is currently working as Full Professor at the Department of Accounting, Banking and Finance, Tishk International University, Erbil, Kurdistan Region, Iraq. She has worked as an Associate Professor in Prince Sultan University and as an Assistant Professor in Princess Nourah University, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. She has to her credit Bachelor's in Commerce, Master's in Commerce, Master's in Business Administration, Post Graduate Diploma in Management, Post Graduate Diploma in Financial Management, Diploma in Management and PhD in Venture Capital Finance (PhD Thesis evaluated by Australian Catholic University, Australia). She has more than two decades of experience in teaching and research. She has authored 18 books and published 38 research articles in the journals of repute including Scopus indexed journals and journals indexed in Web of Science such as WILEY, Inderscience Publishers, Taylor & Francis and MDPI. She is the recipient of Best Paper Award on 'Strategies for inclusive growth' at SBJIT, Bangalore, India and Distinguished teacher award from MTC Global. She is also the recipient of MTC Global Outstanding Researcher Award -2022. She has presented research papers in international conferences at China, Spain, Romania, Malaysia, UAE, Jordan and Iraq. She has chaired sessions and delivered keynote address in international conferences and reviewed papers for Springer, Information Sciences Letters (Scopus, Q2) and Eurasian Journal of management and Social Sciences. Her areas of Expertise include Green Finance, Start-Up Finance, FDI, Auditing, IFRS, Forensic Accounting, Financial Literacy, Fintech, Venture Capital, Environmental Accounting, Gender diversity and Corporate Performance.

KEYNOTE SPEAKERS FOR DAY 2 ICRAIBM 2023

(Dr.) Hemant Chittoo

Professor & Head, Department of Management, University of Technology, Mauritius

Professor Hemant Chittoo has more than 30 years' experience in different Tertiary Education Institutions in Mauritius and has been a visiting Faculty for Universities in UK and Australia. He is a Professor, Researcher, Consultant in the field of Management. He has led the School of Business, Management and Finance for 6 years and has been the Ag. Director General of the University of Technology, Mauritius for nearly 2 years, among other major functions he has held. He has managed several crisis situations successfully. He has provided consultancy services to the World Bank, the UNICEF, CIDA, CAFRAD, British American Tobacco, and a number of Companies in Mauritius including he has written 3 reports for the Government of Mauritius, several book chapters, more than 80 articles in refereed journals and some 50 conference papers. He has also been invited as keynote speaker in a number of international conferences. Leading education and strategy education at the University of Technology, Mauritius, Dr. Chittoo has participated in the formulation of the National Strategic Foresight Exercise 2050 for Mauritius and has been member of different National level Committees for the Government of Mauritius. He has insights into a number of sectors in Mauritius.

Mr. Vinay BN

Project Program Management Specialist, NTT Data

I'm Open Minded person and always open to learning new things. Always Humble to grow along with the company and soft-spoken and to the point. Take decisions quickly. Dedicated and experienced management specialist with over Fifteen years of experience serving as a Project Programme management Specialist in NTT Data Ltd, Bengaluru, Karnataka. Proficient in creating efficient and trending strategies for the department and to my career. Expert at working with team to successfully prepare them for personal and professional success in today's business world. Knowledgeable and experienced in various educational philosophies, which best promote the overall experience of a Project specialist. A committed &, passionate about working to further enhance the professional offerings to the modern business.

ABOUT CONFERENCE-BY-CONFERENCE CONVENORS

It is with great pleasure and enthusiasm that we extend a heartfelt welcome to all of you to the esteemed International Conference on "Recent Advancement and Innovation in Business & Management and Its Contemporary Issues in Sustainable Economy." Organised by SBM Jain Evening College, Bengaluru 2nd August 2023 and 3rd August 2023. As the convenor's of this two-day International Conference, We are honoured to have the opportunity to bring together exceptional minds and passionate professionals from various corners of the world.

This conference serves as a vital platform for intellectual exchange, collaboration, and exploration of the pressing issues at the intersection of business, management, and sustainability. In an era defined by dynamic changes, disruptive technologies, and increasing environmental concerns, it is crucial for us to come together and foster a deeper understanding of the advancements and innovations that shape our ever-evolving landscape.

Over the next two days, we have curated an enriching program featuring distinguished speakers, experts, and researchers who will present their groundbreaking work, share valuable insights, and challenge conventional wisdom. Their contributions will encompass a broad range of topics, including sustainable business practices, corporate social responsibility, entrepreneurship, digital transformation, and emerging trends in the global economy.

As the convenor, We would like to express Our deepest gratitude to the organizing committee members, teaching staff, and non-teaching staff, our beloved students of SBM Jain evening college for their unwavering commitment, tireless efforts, and meticulous planning. Their dedication has ensured that this conference offers a seamless experience for all participants, allowing us to focus on the most critical issues at hand.

We also extend our sincere appreciation to each and every participant for your valuable presence and active involvement. Your contributions, whether through presentations, panel discussions, or fruitful conversations during the networking sessions, will undoubtedly shape the outcomes of this conference and inspire new avenues for research and practice.

Moreover, we encourage you to seize this occasion to foster connections, forge partnerships, and engage in meaningful collaborations that transcend geographical boundaries. The diverse backgrounds, expertise, and perspectives represented here offer a remarkable opportunity to build networks, share best practices, and collectively contribute to the sustainable development of our global community. Thank you and we wish you all a rewarding and successful conference.

Warm regards,

Dr. Lakshman K
Conference Convenor, Associate Professor & Head,
SBMJEC, Bengaluru

Mrs. Shruthi MS
Conference Convenor, Assistant Professor & Head,
SBMJEC, Bengaluru

JOURNAL DETAILS

Name of Journal	International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Technology
e-ISSN	2582-7359
Subject	Multidisciplinary
Publisher	Taran Publication
Impact Factor	6.325
Website	www.ijmrtjournal.com
Contact Number	8950448770, 9996906285
Country of Publication	India
Editor-in-Chief	Dr. Mandeep Kaur

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CROWDFUNDING – APPROACH AND LIMITATIONS, BUREAUCRACY FOR MONITOR AND CONTROL

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Research Purpose:

Crowdfunding is a concept that aims to raise capital from the general public and allows for the sending of funds in any amount and in any denomination while providing the necessary information in a clear and concealed manner. Crowdfunding approach, limitations and the Bureaucracy for monitor and control the funding.

Methodology:

The writers have created a questionnaire after conducting a thorough review of the literature utilizing secondary sources. The data is analyzed based on the secondary data.

Significant Results:

The return on investment to investors via Crowdfunding is not always guaranteed. The return to investors is based on the company's performance and their willingness to take a risk in exchange for a potential return. The notion does not contain any formal bureaucracy. The RBI will put into effect the appropriate policies with regard to this form of funding.

Implications:

Proper bureaucracy system will help to govern the concept of Crowdfunding can take any kind of role in the economy and also can impact to the business environment. This paper explains all this information.

Keywords: # Crowdfunding #Bureaucracy # Controlling #Monitoring #Business Environment #RBI

Introduction:

Crowdfunding is a concept that aims to raise capital from the general public and receive the funds in any denomination while providing the necessary information in a clear and concealed manner. Crowdfunding has classified into community and financial returning, where community Crowdfunding means like few as a donation and few as reward based Crowdfunding and where financial returning is the concept like peer-to-peer and also equity based Crowdfunding.

There are many platforms to raise the Crowdfunding like through proper authentic websites (ex: kickstarter, Indiegogo, Rockethub and many other). The channel collect some part of charges for services like gateway and others.

Review of Literature:

(India, 2016), RBI in April 2016 – “**Consultation Paper on Peer to Peer Lending**” gave brief explanation on the concept of crowd funding. The paper discuss about the framework on SEBI, which was frame on June 17, 2014. The paper examined the security based crowd funding concept in India and also explored like Equity based Crowd Funding (EbC), Debt based Crowd Funding (DbC), Fund based Crowd Funding (FbC) and Alternative Investment Fund (AIF) through a crowd funding platform. The suggestion made in the paper, where exclusively to lending through P2P platforms.

(SEBI, 2014), the framework paper gives explanation about the concept of Crowd Funding in domestically and internationally platforms. The paper explains the extant legal structure governing the fund raising for Entrepreneurs (Start-ups) and also for Small and Medium Enterprises. The paper gave the information on legal framework and regulatory challenges in implementation. The paper opened a commentary and suggestion for industry and market

participants regarding to frame a possible structures for crowd funding within the legal framework and relevant issues.

3- RESEARCH DESIGN:

3.1- Statement of the Problem:

The proper methodology to approach the concept of Crowd Funding and bureaucracy to manage the particular concept. – "Crowd Funding – Approach and Limitations, Bureaucracy for Monitor and control".

3.2- Need and Importance of the Study:

The concept of Crowd Funding was introduced quite long back in India. Where, the entrepreneur awareness is lacking few years back. Some, entrepreneurs are not aware how to do a proper approach it's functioning.

The study makes important to understand the concept of Crowd Funding – approach, limitations and bureaucracy for monitor and control the crowd funding concept.

3.3- Objectives of the Study:

- * To find the concept awareness, approach and limitations involved.
- * To understand the bureaucracy involved in the concept and its management criteria.

3.4- Scope of the Study:

The study primarily focus on the concept of crowd funding solutions to raise a capital – Short or long term for the entrepreneurs. The study also emphasize on the Crowd funding awareness, approach, limitations and bureaucracy to manage the concept.

3.5- Research Methodology:

3.5.1- Type of Research:

The study used exploratory research for the research problem, which needs more information and requires the observant view of the users.

3.5.2- Type of Data:

3.5.2a- Primary Data: The data was collected through a set of questions framed towards the entrepreneurs along with a few personal interview was conducted.

3.5.2b- Secondary Data: The data Available and Unpublished materials (through proper channel) were used for the study.

3.5.3- Sampling Design:

3.5.3a- Judgmental Sampling was used while choosing the individuals (entrepreneurs) for the response and it was decided to select the samples from Bengaluru Urban and Rural as a part of the study. The study was confined to 10 Individuals (entrepreneurs) who responded positively to the study through personal interview – over-call and through online methods like WhatsApp, Google Meet and Google Form.

3.5.4- Data Collection:

It was steered using a personal interview (Entrepreneurs) – by personal and over call and also floated questionnaire through the App platform (WhatsApp) and Google Form in the Bengaluru Urban and Rural.

3.5.5- LIMITATIONS TO THE STUDY:

- Only 10 entrepreneurs were selected for the questionnaire, where they give the data related to the study.
- The study was conducted personal, over-call and online mode through (WhatsApp and Google meet, due to time constrain).
- It is limited to data collected within Bengaluru Urban and Rural.

4- Analysis and Finding:

Primary Data: 1- Are you aware of the concept of Crowd Funding?

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage (%)
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Yes	4	40
No	6	60
Total	10	100

Analysis – 4 entrepreneurs responses was yes and 6 entrepreneur selected the option no.

Interpretation – 60 percentage of the entrepreneurs are not having the idea of crowd funding concept in the financial market. The awareness and discussion on the concept is very less.

Secondary Data: SEBI and RBI has already made a discussion paper in the year 2014 and 2016 with users in India – in domestically and also in internationally. It tried to discuss as P2P concept for Initial Fund raising concept.

Primary Data: 2- Do you understand the proper methods for approaching the idea of crowd funding?

Analysis – 4 entrepreneurs who respondent for awareness were concentrated to find the approach to the concept of Crowd Funding. Where, 6 entrepreneurs was not able to answer this question.

Interpretation – Four entrepreneurs’ responses was, they used international platform for the capital source, where they found some methods used in other countries by the entrepreneurs like UK, USA and others. The approach towards capital formation (initial or seed capital / developmental purpose). In India, we found very less platforms to generate capital on the usage of this concept.

Secondary Data: SEBI and RBI has discussed in the Consultation paper, where RBI says the concept of crowd funding as a Peer to Peer concept. The platforms for investment in this kind of mode – Equity based Crowd Funding (EbC), Debt based Crowd Funding (DbC), Fund based Crowd Funding (FbC) and Alternative Investment Fund (AIF) through a crowd funding platform.

The approach towards crowd funding is totally different in India.

Primary Data: 3- Do you think the idea of crowd financing has any restrictions?

Analysis – 4 entrepreneurs says they have not found clear limitations in the concept of crowd Funding.

Interpretation – The entrepreneurs gave the clarification, they don’t have a clear analysis on the concept of Crowd Funding limitations, where, they need to find out through proper requirements.

Secondary Data: SEBI discussion in the consultation paper. Where, they found and discussed the limitations like:

- a. Limitation in collecting the fund or capital it should be in the control limit.
- b. It accepts the funds through merchant banking system and not through cash.
- c. The funds can be collected through Equity, Debt and Fund.

d. The Crowd funding should be collected at limited manner or limited fund – restrictions.

Primary Data: 4- Have you heard of the bureaucratic structure used to monitor and regulate crowd funding?

Analysis – Two entrepreneurs gave an information that they have come across the bureaucratic system by RBI. Two entrepreneurs response was that they don't come across.

Interpretation – Those entrepreneurs, who have come across the system – they gave information like there should be proper observing of fund movement and the actual utilization of fund according to the objective for raising the fund.

Secondary Data: SEBI and RBI discussion in the consultation paper, where, the information like making proper channels to collect the fund and should have a proper investigation on the fund utilization. The fund acquired through proper channel should be accounted and the team audit and submit reports to SEBI and RBI.

Conclusion:

Crowd funding concept is used widely in international platforms, where that particular countries are following proper laws to this platform. Indian government and the Bureaucracy should take a proper measures to monitor and control the concept of Crowd Funding. Legal channel should be followed by the platform users in crowd funding – investor and startups should follow the proper legal norms.

Suggestions:

- Further study on channels used in India.
- Crowd funding concept for societal approach and actual effective utilization of funds.
- Crowd funding user information availability.
- Percentage of commission taken by the online platforms.

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“A COMPARITIVE ANALYSIS OF FACTORS INFLUENCING UPI BASED PAYMENT PLATFORMS” - A STUDY OF SELECT RETAILERS IN BANGALORE URBAN AND RURAL

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India the “land of diversity” has various culture, ethnicity, and geographic region . People are from different economic background i.e. from upper class to lower class. Standard of Living of people not only depends on their income level but also on the area (location) people have their living.

This paper focuses on people living in urban and rural regions of Bangalore and their access towards these Smart technologies(Smart phones) , Online payment platform(UPI) and its various benefits for businesses. This paper throw light on various UPI payment platforms, its awareness, uniqueness, and accessibility to retailers.

Data Collection process would be combination of both primary data and secondary data & methods used are questionnaire, google forms and by word of mouth. Retailers are from many verticals from medical field, eateries, textiles etc. This paper makes analysis Rural and Urban region retailers, there mode of payment collection and its effectiveness. The statistical tool which is used for analysis is Correlation method.

The study says that most of the people in rural area are not benefiting from access to digital services and Policy makers must consider these facts.

Keywords :- UPI- Unified Payment Interface, Digital access, Awareness, Effectiveness, Accessibility, Smart technologies.

INTRODUCTION

Evolution of Money has taken place in various forms from barter system to plastic money. Paper money in the form of fiat money (government issued currency which is not backed by a commodity) are the most used form of currency in circulation.

Paper money now it is digital money which is overtaking. Digital Money (also known as Electronic Currency) is in the form of Virtual Money and which is not tangible. which the denomination remains same i.e. 1 digital rupee = Rs.1 cash

Drawbacks of cash-based payment system which lead to digitalisation.

1. Confusion, Uncertainty and Distrust
2. Inefficient, Distracting and a Pain to Process
3. Insecure and Dangerous effect.
4. Appealing
5. Dealing with Cash is an Expensive Business
6. Cash needs to be kept securely
7. No records of transactions
8. Helpless when out of cash
9. Hard to make large payments

UPI – Unified Payment Interface which is an instant online payment system which was developed by National payments Corporation of India. This system was introduced in the year 2016, 11 April by Dr. Raghuram G Rajan, Governor, RBI at Mumbai. Banks have started to upload their UPI enabled Apps on Google Play store from 25th August, 2016 onwards.

The main moto of this system is to have one common or single platform for all users right from peer-to-peer and person -to-merchant transactions. This UPI functions on an open-source application programming interface (API) on the top of the Immediate Payment Service (IMPS) and is regulated by Reserve Bank of India (RBI).

The Reserve Bank of India is trying to encourage alternative methods of payments which will bring security and efficiency to the payment systems and make the whole process easier for banks.

Various UPI Based Payment Platforms are

Google Pay, PhonePe, Paytm, Amazon Pay, MobiKwik, WhatsApp Pay, BHIM

How is it unique?

- 1.Immediate money transfer through mobile device round the clock 24*7 and 365 days.
- 2.Single mobile application for accessing different bank accounts.
- 3.Single Click 2 Factor Authentication – Aligned with the Regulatory guidelines, yet provides for a very strong feature of seamless single click payment.
- 4.Virtual address of the customer for Pull & Push provides for incremental security with the customer not required to enter the details such as Card no, Account number; IFSC etc.
- 5.QR Code
- 6.Best answer to Cash on Delivery hassle, running to an ATM or rendering exact amount.
- 7.Merchant Payment with Single Application or In-App Payments.
- 8.Utility Bill Payments, Over the Counter Payments, QR Code (Scan and Pay) based payments.
- 9.Donations, Collections, Disbursements Scalable.
- 10.Raising Complaint from Mobile App directly.

RESEARCH DESIGN

Research design refers to the overall strategy that you choose to integrate the different components of the study in a coherent and logical way, thereby, ensuring you will effectively address the research problem; it constitutes the blueprint for the collection, measurement, and analysis of data.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Technology has become a part of our day-to-day life. As a result of which today its known as digitalisation era. Technology is been widely used in all fields today from banking to marketing and from eating to shopping. The main benefit of this digitalisation is it increases efficiency, it protects ones records no matter what natural disaster, theft or loss happens and helps in increasing profits, increase productivity and agility. As it provides easy communication it also helps in ease of payment and online transaction one such ways are UPI payment apps.

The payment system in India from Barter system till paper money has its own cons which led to cashless economy today which is considered safer and secured. unified payment interface apps these are immediate real time payment system that helps in instantly transferring the funds between two banks accounts through a mobile platform.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

PUSHPA S ABBIGERI AND REJESHWARI M SHETTAR (2018)

Talked about how the digital India flagship programme attracted large number of people to start using digital wallets, which people started to use as there was a lot of cashback offers and coupons. after the digital India flagship program, a lot of mobile wallet companies entered India and other methods such as UPI, NEFT to as surge. The initiative taken by the government and RBI was being accepted by the people as they were using such methods.

K KRUTHIGA, LAKSHMI, HIMANSHU GUPTA, JAYANTHI RANJAN (2019)

UPI based Mobile Banking application Security Analysis and enhancement. This report talks about the current trend of digital and cashless, mobile based app solutions which are easy to use and ubiquitous facilitating a wide range of banking financial services and non-banking non-financial services. This paper also discusses UPI based mobile apps (architecture, transitions, features, and security issues) and information security enhancement proposal with right to authentication and authorization through secondary data.

GOURAB GHOSH (2021)

In his study, it is discussed about adoption of digital payment system by consumer. Digitalization not only improves trade and commerce but it also makes transaction of payment smooth and fast. Based on secondary data, this paper talks about various functions of digital payments such as, giving reminders about dues of any kind of payments to be made, it gives various offers to the Users and it saves lot of time.

SHALINI GAUTAM, KOKIL JAIN, VIVHA SINGH (2021)

A study of barriers faced by consumers using UPI based App.

The present research would measure the barriers faced by individual in using UPI-based apps. the barriers have been categorized into five distinct groups that is, usage, value, risk, tradition, and image barrier. an attempt has been made to measure the relationship of these various barriers with the behavioural intention of the individuals of using the UPI based apps. the structured questionnaire was prepared using the standard scale. stepwise regression was done to find out the relationship between the various barriers. it was found that usage barriers, risk barriers and tradition barriers have the most significant relationship with behaviour intention of using UPI apps.

MV PRAVEEN, MK GOPIKA. (2021)

CLIENT EMPIRICISM TOWARDS UPI PLATFORMS.

The purpose of this study is to examine the awareness, perception, and satisfaction level of the clients of popular UPI platforms. so, this study is based mostly on primary data collected from 100 samples from UPI clients in Kerala through structured questionnaire and secondary data is used only for theoretical frame. the key tools for data analysis is statistical tool like, one way ANOVA and weighted averages. study reveals the significant influence of educational status of the clients in their awareness of UPI platforms and its services. the study also observes the age and gender effect on satisfaction and perception of clients.

MADHU SINGH, GALGOTIAS UNIVERSITY 2022.

Marketing strategy of Paytm and Google pay.

Mobile payments are used by more than 2 billion people worldwide, with millions more coming online each year. In India, Southeast Asia and South America, a new generation has gone beyond the usual credit or open Credit System, favouring the use of mobile applications. In India, there is three- way market sharing contest between Paytm, PhonePe and Google pay. Through secondary data we could find out that Paytm is the largest in terms of users and performance however PhonePe and Google pay or processing additional e-payments.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To study awareness of UPI based payment system.
2. To make an comparative analysis of factors influencing UPI platforms and its effectiveness at the select outlets of Bangalore Urban & Rural .
3. To bring out the merits and demerits of UPI based payment system for retailers.

2.6 SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

The scope of the study is limited to the study of financial analysis of UPI based payment platforms - it is a study of select retailers in Bangalore Urban & Rural

This study mainly focuses on effectiveness and importance of digital payments as compared to cash-based payments. As cash-based payment system has lot of disadvantages like lack of trust, Security, confusion, and transparency issues digital payment platforms helps us in solving such problems and helps us in providing safety and security of transactions by providing authentication

This study helps us in learning about various UPI Payments Platforms and which is one of the most used platforms by retailers and it also help us in making financial analysis of different types of retail industry like textiles, manufacturing, hotels, and medicals etc.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research methodology used is Exploratory research

Exploratory research is the method used for the purpose of study. Exploratory research questions are designed to help one understand more about a particular topic of interest.

SOURCES OF DATA:

Primary data

Primary data is a type of data that is collected by researchers directly from main sources through interviews, surveys, experiments, etc. In this study the main source to collect primary data is from verbal source, questioner etc

Secondary data

The secondary data is another form of data collection from existing information about various UPI based Companies and its applications through various websites, company manuals and articles etc.

Tool for Analysis

Statistical tool used for analysis of research is Correlation Method.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Method of data collection is primary data and secondary data through questionnaire (google forms), word of mouth. The above table shows, the representation of gender. The total responses of 200 respondents categorised into male and female.

Particulars	Urban	Rural
Male	73	82
Female	27	18
Total	100	100

The above table shows, the representation of gender. The total responses of 200 respondents categorised into male and female.

A questionnaire was sent to varied gender of respondents, and 200 responses were received from different demographic zones within Bengaluru Urban and Rural for the purpose of conducting a better survey of the research topic.

TABLE SHOWING THE TYPE OF RETAIL OUTLET POSSED BY VARIOUS RETAILERS

Particulars	Urban	Rural
Hotel	40	32
Textile	30	18
Medical	15	20
Others	15	30
Total	100	100

The data in the prior table pertains to the type of retail outlet of the respondents.

A questioner was given to different type of retailers like hotels, textiles, medical stores and other retailers like fancy stores, beauty parlor etc. The method of collection of data from retailers are through google forms, questionnaire, and word of mouth.

1) Are you aware of Online Payment System ?

Particulars	Urban	Rural
No	0	6
Total	100	100

Correlation = 1

Interpretation –

As per the data collected in urban area everyone are aware of online payment whereas in rural awareness is less comparatively. From the above data using correlation method $r = 1$ (inverse relation)

2) Are you using Online Payment System?

Particulars	Urban	Rural
Yes	92	60
No	8	40
Total	100	100

Correlation 1

Interpretation –

As per the data collected in urban area usage of online payment is more whereas in rural area usage is less comparatively. From the above data using correlation method $r = 1$ (inverse relation)

3) What is the perception of retailers towards UPI registration process

Particulars	Urban	Rural
Easy	90	50
Moderate	5	23
Difficult	0	27

Correlation 0.982541

Interpretation –

As per the data collected urban people feel that UPI registration process is easy and rural people feel easy as well as moderate. From the above data using correlation method $r = 0.982541$ (strongly correlated)

4) What percentage of your business activity includes UPI Platform to make payment ?

Particulars	Urban	Rural
10%	0	30
20%	0	48
50%	20	12
>50%	80	10

Correlation 0.72313

Interpretation –

As per the data collected more than 50% of transactions happens using UPI in urban area and in rural area only 20% of transactions happens through UPI platform. Using correlation method usage of UPI Platform in urban and rural is strongly correlated where $r = 0.72313$ (strongly correlated)

5) What do you think is the reason for preference of UPI mode

Particulars	Urban	Rural
Fast Payment	40	25
Virtual access	0	0
Security	25	60
Single application	10	0
Utilities	25	15

Correlation 0.573539

Interpretation –

As per the data collected urban residents feel fast payment , security is important aspects they consider and rural residents also feel security as a major aspect for choosing UPI mode of payment.Using correlation method preference of UPI Platform in urban and rural is moderately correlated where $r = 0.573539$ (moderately correlated)

6) What is the reason for not using UPI payment mode.

Particulars	Urban	Rural
Chances of fraud	20	20
fear of losing account access	0	0
hanging issues	20	15
lack of technical skills	10	60
Bad network issues	50	5

Correlation -0.25355

Interpretation –

As per the data collected the reason for not using UPI payment mode in urban area is bad network issues, hanging issues, chances of fraud whereas in rural area it is lack of technical skills and chances of fraud. Using correlation method it is clear that relation with urban and rural is low where $r = 0.2535$

7) Which form of UPI payment as retailers you prefer more ?

Particulars	Urban	Rural
Paytm	40	25
GPay	10	30
BHIM	15	5
Amazon Pay	5	0
PhonePe	30	40

Correlation 0.58158

Interpretation –

As per the data collected retailers in urban area feel Paytm is most preferred UPI platform with PhonePe, BHIM etc. Rural retailers prefer PhonePe and later GPay , Paytm etc. Using correlation method, relation with urban and rural is moderately correlated where $r = 0.58158$.

8) As retailers which mode of payment you prefer more?

Particulars	Urban	Rural
cash payment	15	90
online payment	85	10

Correlation -1

Interpretation –

As per the data collected, table clearly shows that urban retailers prefer online payment whereas rural retailers prefer cash payment system as the mode of payment. Using correlation method, relation with urban and rural is perfect negative correlation $r = -1$

9) Do you think that there is increase in sales due to UPI Payment mechanism?

Particulars	Urban	Rural
Yes	93	65
No	7	35

Correlation 1

Interpretation –

As per the data collected there a high impact and increase in sales due to UPI payment mechanism both in rural and urban area. From the above data using correlation method $r = 1$ (inverse relation)

10) As per your experience in which category usage of UPI payment is more?

Particulars	Urban	Rural
Youngsters <30 years	35	45
Adults 30-45 years	40	35
> 50 years	20	15
> 65 years	10	5

Correlation 0.928191

Interpretation –

As per the data collected urban retailers are of the opinion that adults with age group of 30-45 years use more of UPI, whereas rural retailers feel youngsters (<30 years) followed by the adults with age group of 30-45 years prefer payment through UPI. Using correlation method preference of UPI Platform in urban and rural is moderately correlated where $r = 0.928191$ (strongly correlated).

11) Do you think customer shopping experience has enhanced over mobile wallet platforms?

Particulars	Urban	Rural
Yes	98	62
No	2	38

Correlation 1

Interpretation –

As per the data collected both urban and rural retailers are of the opinion that customer shopping experience has enhanced over mobile wallet platforms. From the above data using correlation method $r = 1$ (positive correlation)

12) Do you think cashless transaction is beneficial?

Particulars	Urban	Rural
Yes	96	60
No	0	8
Yes, to some extent	4	32

Correlation 0.903735

Interpretation –

As per the data collected both urban and rural retailers are of the opinion that cashless transaction is beneficial from both retailer and customer point of view. From the above data using correlation method $r = 0.903735$ (strongly correlated).

13) What do you think could be the key drivers of consumer experience over mobile wallet performance?

Particulars	Urban	Rural
Privacy	10	50
security	20	30
convenience	70	12
Interactivity	0	8

Correlation -0.31241

Interpretation –

As per the data collected in rural retailers’ privacy followed by security is the key drivers of consumer experience over mobile wallet whereas in urban area convenience is the major key drivers. From the above data using correlation method $r = -0.31240$ (negative correlation)

Findings: -

- i. Awareness about Online Payment system has enhanced a lot and retailers in urban feel registration process is easy and retailers in urban feel UPI registration process is moderate.
- ii. Most of the customers today would operate using online payment and most used UPI platform in urban area is Paytm and in rural is PhonePe
- iii. In urban area buyers prefer online mode of payment for various reasons like fast payment, utilities, virtual access etc
- iv. In rural area buyers prefer online mode of payment for various reasons like security, fast payment etc
- v. Today’s business activity happens more than 50% in online in urban whereas in rural it is only 20% and above
- vi. Urban and Rural retailers have their own disadvantages of Online Payment mode for urban retailers – Bad network issues, hanging issues and chances of fraud, whereas rural retailers have technical issues
- vii. Retailers in urban prefer a maximum of Online Payment where as retailers in rural area prefer Cash Payment
- viii. Young generations and Adults use UPI payment more both in Rural and Urban area and it has also enhanced customer shopping experience and which in return helps in increasing profitability of the business.
- ix. Convenience is the major key driver of consumer experience in mobile wallet in Urban areas
- x. In rural areas is the major key driver for expertise in mobile wallet is Privacy, security, convenience etc
- xi. Highly educated people are more attracted towards such payment apps while the rural people still stick on to there traditional payment mode

Suggestions :-

- i. Equal development should take place in rural and urban area for accomplishing the goal of Digital India
- ii. In rural areas there are still women without knowing how to use a android phone, and they don’t even have access to basic phones
- iii. Proper awareness must be created about the importance of using Online mode of payment

- iv. Policy Makers of Online Payment (UPI) System must consider both urban and rural region before making policies
- v. Usage of UPI apps for payment and settlement must be made mandate so that automatically awareness and usage will increase
- vi. Proper training should be given in rural area as to how to use it, its important, how it will reduce black money, its need for the country
- vii. UPI app developers should incorporate new features like dummy payment option for the first-time users of UPI.
- viii. Security system must be more enhanced through usage of coolies and latest software's so that there will be no fear of losing account access
- ix. If amount exceed more than 10000 then approval of payment from both the parties must be made so that there will be less chance for errors and fraud
- x. Refund option must be provided through the consent of retailers if wrong payment takes places
- xi. Data must be kept safe and secured it must not be used for any advertisement purpose

Conclusion :-

UPI (Uniform Payment Interface) which was started by NPCI – National Payment Corporation of India once was a very new term used in financial system where people did not have access to android phones. But today each house every individual will have a smart phone. As per our study 76 female responses were from collected and in urban area majority of females had access to online payment but in rural areas still few women are not aware of online payment mechanism.

The system is changing slowly, today in India UPI recorded over 6.28 billion transactions in July 2022., it's a new record since the service was launched in July 2016. Today almost in all verticals artificial intelligence is been used and everything is being completely transformed digitally.

As it is the largest payment platform most of the people (consumers) use this platform and retailers feel it is easy to adopt and operate which is highly safe and secured. Another important fact is that amount of commission will be deducted in transactions and installation is also completely free.

Retailers believed most of the transactions that takes place through online payment and very less through cash basis. They agree that this is the customers preferred mode of payment and they all are used to this system majority of them talks about its advantages. Same time GPay provides various coupons and cash back offers and advertisements. These 2 apps are trendier and more used app in UPI platform and hence to conclude it is most beneficial to both retailers and customers.

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“BEST HR PRACTICES IN SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES IN BANGALORE” – A PROJECT CARRIED OUT THROUGH DESCRIPTIVE RESEARCH

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Introduction :

Business units put a lot of effort into devising strategies to stay in the game and beat rivals in the competitive market of today. Over the course of the last 50 years, India's small and medium-sized businesses (SME's) have become more vibrant and vivacious. Small and medium-sized businesses and microunits make up approximately 8% of the nation's GDP, employ the second-greatest number of people after the agricultural sector, and assist develop areas that are still underdeveloped.

Small and Medium Enterprises: Definition of small and medium enterprises differs from country to country. Few commonly used criteria to define SMEs in international level are the total net assets, investment level and number of employees. In India MSME's are defined as per MSME Development Act, 2006 based on the investment made in plant and machinery (manufacturing) and on equipment for enterprises providing or rendering services. Revision is expected to be made on the act based on the bill proposed as Micro Small & Medium Enterprises Development (Amendment) Bill, 2014.

Classification	MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISES		SERVICE ENTERPRISES	
	The MSMED Act, 2006 (Not Exceeding)	The MSMED (Amendment) Bill, 2014 (Not Exceeding)	The MSMED Act, 2006 (Not Exceeding)	The MSMED (Amendment) Bill, 2014 (Not Exceeding)
Small	Rs. 5 Crores	Rs. 10 Crores	Rs. 2 Crores	Rs. 5 Crores
Medium	Rs. 10 Crores	Rs. 30 Crores	Rs. 5 Crores	Rs. 15 Crores

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

HRM in SMEs is, until recently, disappropriated. To this contributed little research and studies about SMEs (Reid and Adams, 2001). Recently, research on practices of HRM in SMEs increased considerably (Kok and Uhlener, 2001), probably due to the important source of information and material of studies about SMEs that provides management researchers, the development of new theoretical approaches (Cassell et al., 2002). Several authors have suggested that HR can be a source of competitive advantage (see, for example, Barney and Wright, 1998; Cunningham and Rowley, 2007). HRM have an important role in implementing practices that benefit employees both in performance and motivation. In most cases, HRM practices benefit by the modernisation and advancement of SMEs. A study in USA proved that poor emphasis on HR in SMEs have been one of the reasons for businesses failure in the analysed companies (McEvoy, 1984). SMEs have difficulty in implementing HRM policies and practices. A study by Heneman and Berkley (1999) confirmed that in 117 small companies, only 15 had a HR department. One reason for this is the difficulty in recruiting and retaining employees due to limited financial resources and the reluctance to lead at great cost or prohibitive practices.

There have been numerous calls for increased research into the human resource (HR) management practices of small and medium-size enterprises (Cardon and Stevens, 2004; Heneman et al., 2000; Kotey and Slade, 2005; Rutherford et al., 2003). Most American businesses are small, and smaller firms exhibit a more direct connection

between intended HR policies at the top of the organization and actual HR practices in effect at the bottom (Chandler and McEvoy, 2000). This direct connection helps overcome weaknesses in much survey research done on large firms because the most common research design relies on a single informant to report on how HR is practiced throughout a very large organization (Lawler and Boudreau, 2009).

Another reason for the increasing interest in the description and measurement of HR in practice is the mounting evidence that certain HR strategies, organizations, activities, and practices can help a firm build and maintain a competitive advantage (Barney, 1991, 1995; Boxall, 1996; Carmeli and Schaubroeck, 2005; Pfeffer, 1994) and/or improve organizational performance (Carlson et al., 2006; Combs et al., 2006; Guest et al., 2003; Huselid, 1995; Sun et al., 2007). While much of this evidence comes from studies of large firms, there are several studies now supporting this connection for firms with fewer than 500 employees as well (Hayton, 2003; Messersmith and Guthrie, 2010; Sels et al., 2006; Way, 2002; Zhang et al., 2008). One key step in researching the HR practice – firm performance link is to develop a clear understanding of how HR is practiced in the field. It is the intent of this study to help clarify what HR practice looks like in mid-sized firms and how it differs from practice in larger firms.

Most of what we know about HR practice in work organizations comes from surveys of large employers. One of the most comprehensive reports is provided in the on-going series of studies done by Edward Lawler and his colleagues at the Center for Effective Organizations at USC (Lawler et al., 2006; Lawler and Boudreau, 2009). In their most recent sample, the average firm size is 32,284 employees and the average HR staff size is 410. On the other end of the spectrum, there have been significant investigations into the HR practices of smaller organizations, generally those with 500 or fewer employees. Representative of these are studies by McEvoy (1984) who reports a descriptive analysis of the functional foci of small business HR practices; Cassell et al. (2002) who report a very wide diversity in HR practices among 100 small firms in England; and, Pearson et al. (2006) who compare the HR practices of small firms (10-250 employees) to those of “micro” firms (, 10 employees). There have also been some comparative studies investigating similarities and differences in HR practices of large and small firms (Deshpande and Golhar, 1994), and between fast growth and mature small firms (Buller and Napier, 1993). There have been numerous calls for increased research into the human resource (HR) management practices of small and medium-size enterprises (Cardon and Stevens, 2004; Heneman et al., 2000; Kotey and Slade, 2005; Rutherford et al., 2003). Most American businesses are small, and smaller firms exhibit a more direct connection between intended HR policies at the top of the organization and actual HR practices in effect at the bottom (Chandler and McEvoy, 2000). This direct connection helps overcome weaknesses in much survey research done on large firms because the most common research design relies on a single informant to report on how HR is practiced throughout a very large organization (Lawler and Boudreau, 2009).

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1994), and between fastgrowth and mature small firms (Buller and Napier, 1993)

In a present-day scenario the business environment is considered to be both highly volatile and fiercely competitive. Constant change in skills and knowledge would require the HR practitioners to be adaptive to the ambiguity faced at the workplace (Mayrhofer and Brewster, 2005). A herculean task involves the coordination of operations and decoding the cultural complexities in the organization (Pucik, V. 1997). Other notable challenges include the short sightedness of the higher management regarding the principle issues concerning HR practices (Burton, 2003), retention and appraisal of trained employees (Chermack et al, 2003), negative implications on organizational efficiency due to unfavorable employee behavior (Swanson & Holton III, 2001) and inadequacy of knowledge among HR expert practitioners (Burton, 2003). Also, lack of sufficient encouragement and failure in communicating benefits of HR practices has come across as barriers to Strategic Human Resource Management (Kane, 2001). Moreover, conflict of functional roles between the line staff and HR professionals can prove detrimental and as a barrier to effective HR practices (Larsen and Brewster, 2003). Hence, to overcome the challenges faced, HR functions need to be restructured and modernized.

Outcomes of Best HR practices:

Human Resource practices have a convincing relationship with work outcomes and have gained priority in the research field (Edgar & Geare, 2005). Fulfillment of elementary needs result in beneficial outcomes since; self-motivated employees who are job involved are created (Gagne' and Deci, 2005). Other positive results include maturity of employee decision making skill by direct participation (Heery & Noon, 2001), organizational commitment due to the combination of both firm hiring practices, extrinsic motivation (Ryan and Deci, 2000), improving employee self-reliance and decreasing external interference (Howard & Foster, 1999) and determining specific areas for betterment (Snell & Dean, 1992). On the other hand, improper HR practices lead to unfavorable results such as turnover intention (Tett & Meyer, 1993) which in turn affects performance (Rod & Carruthers, 2008) and enhances voluntary turnover (Zimmerman, 2008). Even in the presence of limited negatives, a positive relation between best HR practices and outcomes is clearly outlined.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

The adoption using standards of excellence by a company serves as a starting point for continuous advancement. Many academics have done studies to determine the best practices for large-scale companies where the flow of cash and other resources seems to be ample, but they have mostly disregarded how Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs) operate with less capital and fewer assets. These businesses adhere to specific best practices that are disregarded by many other businesses and, even when they are used, are rarely communicated. This piqued our curiosity on what small- and medium in size company best practices are. In addition to implementing these practices as part of their social obligation or as normal procedures, businesses should place a high priority on disseminating those practices that will not only be an experience worth sharing but, also help in exhibiting and enhancing the pride of the same.

OBJECTIVES

- 1) Identifying Bangalore's small and medium companies best practices
- 2) Communicating best practices with owners of small and medium-sized enterprises

METHODOLOGY

It speaks of the conceptual framework that is used to carry out the project. It serves as the manual for gathering, measuring, and analyzing data (Kothari, 2004). Our research falls within the wider term for descriptive research because we attempt to identify and explain the current HR best practices among small and medium-sized enterprises.

Population:

Population refers to total collection of elements and sample as a part of such population. In our project, population encompasses the companies registered as MSME's.

Sample and Sampling Procedure:

Sample refers to the part of population which can be generalized at the later stage towards a larger group. We have compiled data from 40 respondents pertaining to Small and Medium enterprises in Peenya Industrial Area and Machohalli Industrial area using the method of snowball sampling.

Snowball Sampling:

This is a non-probability sampling method where the data are collected using references. In the initial stage of snowball sampling, individuals are discovered and may or may not be selected through probability methods. This group of individuals are then used to refer the researcher to others who pose similar characteristics and who in-turn identify others.

Data Collection:**Primary source:**

Primary research is the research where data is gathered first hand. We have collected the data from the respondents by the method of interview.

Research Instrument:

Interview method refers to the survey via two-way conversation between a trained interviewer and a participant. In this method the HR practitioners describe their best practices and the criteria applied by them for identifying and justifying the same. We prepared a detailed checklist to probe the discussion after which the participants' response has been recorded.

Secondary source:

Any data, which has been gathered earlier for some purpose is considered as secondary data.

The secondary data collection for this study is through:

- a. MSME Website
- b. Reference books
- c. Journals

Limitations of the study:

- Bias of the respondents in answering may hinder the study
- The study covers only 40 small and medium enterprises in Bangalore which may not be possible to generalize for the entire population.

OUTCOMES OF THE STUDY**Recruitment:**

- 1) The major source of recruitment is Employee referral.
- 2) Employees get referral bonus based on candidate reference.

Selection:

- 1) Mapping is done through psychometric tools.
- 2) Based on job description, a tailor-made template is created for psychometric testing for which 1-2 lakhs rupees per annum is spent.
- 3) Results of psychometric tests are taken as a base for questioning during the candidates selection.

Training:

- 1) For Induction training, OSHA (Organizational Safety and Health Administration) procedure is followed. Intensive training is conducted for one week.
- 2) Frequent training is conducted on safety.
- 3) Training is conducted four times in a year to avoid skill obsolescence.
- 4) Mock safety training is provided annually by external experts.

Performance Appraisal:

- 1) An indigenous appraisal system known as “Internal skill matrix” was developed and followed to assess the performance of the employees, which is conducted annually.
- 2) One company follows quarterly appraisal system which encompasses employee performance, division performance, market survey and inflation.
- 3) Tests are conducted for temporary and probation officers.
- 4) By and large, once in six months appraisal system is followed.

Compensation:

- 1) Increment is based on:
 - a. Employee performance
 - b. Inflation (economic)
 - c. Division performance
 - d. Market survey (similar companies).
- 2) At the time of joining, new recruits are offered a joining bonus which is a small portion of their salary to look after their basic requirements to establish a good will in advance.
- 3) Special allowances are given apart from Salary + Overtime which is a higher scale than the competitor company in that location.
- 4) Fixed deposit and recurring deposits are encouraged.
- 5) Salaries are paid to the employees bank accounts (some credits on 1st of every month & some last day of month).
- 6) An indigenous ERP software and HRIS (Human Resource Information System) system is followed.

Motivation:

- 1) Few companies credit the salary on the 1st of every month.
- 2) Employees are monetary motivated.
- 3) Annual bonus is given based on the company profit in the financial year.
- 4) Incentives are given for senior staff based on KRA's (Key Result Areas).
- 5) Unskilled workers get trained and made to move up the career ladder.
- 6) The potential of an office attender from another company was identified, who was later hired and trained and went to become a skilled technician.

Personal Records:

- 1) After the Induction training, the new recruits will be evaluated by the functional in-charge to evaluate their readiness to be placed on the job.
- 2) Individual files are maintained.
- 3) Good and bad performances are recorded. Good performance is rewarded and bad performances are penalized as well.

Health:

- 1) Employees are insured with Jeevan Jyothi (accidental, life insurance).
- 2) Group insurance, accident relief care insurance is provided.
- 3) Regular health camps including biannual checkups.

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR):

- 1) Not much evidence of CSR being followed in SMEs within the available data, however, some specific instances of planting of saplings in Peenya Industrial area has been found.

Grievances:

Besides the statutory grievance redressal mechanism

- 1) Suggestion boxes are available for complaints.
- 2) These complaints are collected, read carefully and then addressed by the welfare officer.
- 3) The issues are further discussed across table, on a one-to-one basis with the supervisors, after which it is addressed by HR and Management.
- 4) Every month meetings take place and all are open for complaints.

Environment:

- 1) Plastic cups are not used, only paper cups are used.
- 2) Personal hygiene information is being given prominently.
- 3) Processed bottled water is supplied for drinking.

Welfare:

- 1) Free lunch is provided for all employees. Manager, owner and employees have lunch together.
- 2) Some companies offer food at subsidized rates.
- 3) Below middle class – Education of girl child is sponsored by the company, (any number of female children, till 10th standard) in quality English medium schools. Moreover, computer fees, bus fare are also paid by the company.
- 4) If there is more than 1 son, only one is sponsored.
- 5) In some instances, every 1st of a month, competitions such as Rangoli, Food festival etc., are conducted. Winning participants get Rupees Five hundred as well as some quality gifts.
- 6) After completion of 3 years of service, the company provides paid holiday for 1 week. Along with the employees two of their family members excluding two children are offered a tour package to visit places at Kerala, Chennai (2 days and 1 night)
- 7) Every year employees are taken to good resorts.
- 8) Employees are encouraged even after retirement and their skills are utilized wherever required.

CONCLUSION

The research outcome gives us an idea about best practices followed in SME's. This research might be highly beneficial not only for the SME's in Bangalore but can also act as guidelines for other SME's in various states. These best practices help other companies to examine, reexamine their best practices and also to adopt few new and better practices. Apart from small and medium enterprises, large scale organizations may also get inputs as how managers and owner managers use their best practices in SME's with limited resources, which can help them to further optimize their operations and make them efficient.

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PERCEPTIONS OF USERS TOWARDS BENEFITS OF DIGITAL ACCOUNTING SYSTEM: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY

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Abstract

From the perspective of E-Accounting system users, the current study investigates how digital accounting has affected the financial reporting system. Prior to the rapid growth and competition, it was challenging and important for commercial organizations to adapt to and implement digital accounting systems. However, it was now urgent to take up and move on to an E-accounting system. The current study article's goal is to comprehend the value of digital accounting to users.

With the help of the 25 various variables considered for the study, a research article questionnaire was created that exclusively deals with the advantages and their opinion of the users. The major data-gathering method employed a structured questionnaire with a five-point Likert scale. In the study, 160 samples of accountants, account assistants, and account clerks were drawn from corporations. Convenience sampling was used, KMO and Bartlett's Test indicated a significant value of 0.000, and commonalities identified four factors that explain 72.8% of the variation in the variables.

It was discovered that there was a strong correlation between factor 1, factor 2, and factor 3, and the remaining correlations accurately matched the strong correlation between the taken factor and more than 50%.

Keywords: Digital accounting, E-accounting, Data encryption, Competition, Commercial Organization

Introduction

The introduction of digital technology into the global economy started in the 1970s and grew quickly over the entire genre. Most people in India already employ electronic financial profit systems, as do many corporate structures and currency. Many times today, people and legal organizations can get along without mediators thanks to the advancement and introduction of digital technology. The usage of digital tools boosts revenues and frequently has a profitable effect on the nation's economic growth.

Our nation will be able to join a global society by integrating with the digital environment of the global economy. This will open new opportunities, offer a new standard of living, and improve commercial and governmental services.

All facets of human activity are being transformed by digital technology. Statistics, accounting, auditing, and analysis are implemented, as well as digital ideas like trading, status, civilization, warfare, and society. Nearly all employment are covered by the components of a digital economy: people, corporations, and things. Many industries will experience significant change for decades to come, similar to the earlier industrial upheavals. There will be significant social, economic, and societal effects.

The following outcomes are anticipated because of the Indian economy's digitalization:

- enhanced labour productivity.
- speeding up economic growth;
- to increase organizations' competitiveness;

managing company economic operations, such as financial results, locations of financial hazards, etc.

According to a recent market analysis conducted by Accounting Today, the global market for accounting software is predicted to increase at an average pace of 8.6 percent per year starting in 2018 and reach a value of \$11.8 billion by 2026. Accounting organizations are rapidly redefining current business procedures and automating time-consuming, repetitive tasks with new accounting software.

They switch to new technologies from conventional accounting software. Small, medium, and micro businesses are critical to the development of the nation's economy. As a result, it's crucial to rearrange them in cases when digital change can serve as a descriptive element. It is even more crucial for businesses to embrace digital accounting because it has fundamentally revolutionized accounting and provided numerous benefits to companies that execute accounting activities. By strategically organizing their financial procedures and effectively executing those plans, it will increase the efficiency of their accounting operations.

The value-added supply chain, for example, as well as intermediate functions like human resources, finance, and procurement are being transformed by technology. Additionally, rapid accounting systems and processes reflect disruptions as well. E-commerce, enterprise resource planning (ERP), and cloud computing are three significant technological advancements. Digital tools also make it easier, faster, and more accurate for CAs to complete their jobs. These include things like multiplying vouchers, compiling vouchers, checking vouchers, earning a minimum or maximum balance each year, pricing vouchers wisely, and much more. Data quality management, paperless accounting, transparency creation, real-time reporting, system interoperability, big data analysis, cloud computing, and other digital technologies all help to make these responsibilities simpler.

Review of Literature:

We have discovered many papers discussing the necessity for auditors and account personnel to develop their abilities through further research. According to Greenman's paper "Exploring the Impact of Artificial Intelligence on the Accounting Profession," for instance, it has been found that employees must imbibe new skills in response to changes occurring in the domain. Bookkeepers, if do not adapt to the new technologies might encounter the risk of losing their jobs. It is heartening to note that even though the current jobs spectrum might get disrupted, it shall also lead to creation of new jobs. It was revealed that even though the roles of accounting and research are changing, but jobs did not become obsolete due to technological advancements. Instead, skilled people should use this technology as taxing software to increase the number.

Upon careful examination, the huge deficit in IT knowledge and expertise of accounting and auditing was brought to the fore. The need for experienced IT professionals in data analysis and auditing, data analysis has been felt as never before. The skills and abilities of future accounting graduates who need to prepare have to be carefully reviewed (Pan & Seow, 2016). It is shown that the use of business statistics, expanded business reporting, and cloud computing, have already set some changes as to how companies make their own financial report. Widespread use of information technology in almost all parts of the accounting field created the need for graduate accounting students to develop valuable IT skills. It was concluded that it is important for accounting students to have proper training in IT tools such as data mining, analytics planning and automated diagnostic systems, and XBRL as these hold highly relevant futuristic applications. This means education as well university courses need to focus more on IT-related topics. (Pan & Seow, 2016). The current accounting education does not have the breadth and depth as revealed in the study. The author points out the situation in which the role of technology and information systems is not have received enough in the current accounting books (Wells, 2018). In another recent study by Zhang, Dai and Vasarhelyi (2018) focused on the effects of disruption on technology and how it will change the work of auditing and accounting as well as education.

It remains to be seen as to how technological changes are inserted and traditional processes are changed. One thing is for sure: self-employment will lead to significant staff reductions, especially in normal jobs, because education has still not incorporated information technology. Auditors and accountants will need to concentrate on the upkeep of system, by default.

These changes will mean that teachers in business schools will have to adopt new teaching methods include, for example, data analysis and cyber security. All in all, future accounting as well book research will require a lifelong learning philosophy and continuous adaptation to an evolving environment (Zhang et al. 2018). Finally, we focus on

research processes, research goes beyond disruptive technologies and how they will work affects accounting and research. This paper focuses on research and how AI changes what role people play in it in auditing. First of all, there is already a lot of development that has taken some work, this is due to overcrowding data value, systematic and informal, processing companies.

Kokina and Davenport, “The Appearance of artificial intelligence: how automation changes auditing ”they explain how due to needs research, AI technology fits well. Progress, however, will reduce the number of high-profile audit activities, namely many accountants start their careers. This will deprive them of the opportunity to learn for as many graduates as they would not otherwise work is waiting for them. The next step that has already been foreseen by the four major accounting companies is to “make increasing use of audit forums and speculative statistics, but not high levels of intelligence and understanding ability ”.

They have used technology to reduce repetitive tasks, but they cannot take the side of emotional intelligence and put it into new technology. Therefore, although current entry level functions may be modified, we are looking at human combinations, machine function, rather than full automation. As Kokina and Davenport predict, “Since AI technology replaces certain jobs instead of all jobs, short-term job losses are possible don't be so quick and inclined as to get excited. ” This study raises some questions about, “bias in AI and that people who use AI programs can participate in fair judgment and decision making. and how publicly is the use of AI if people do not interpret the results correctly (Kokina & Davenport, 2017).

Objective of the study

To study the extent of benefits derived by the users upon using digital accounting system

Research Methodology

Based on the above review of literature, a questionnaire was prepared which focused on the benefits of digital accounting for the users. Around 25 variables were identified for this study. The five-point Likert scale was used to assess the data. The primary data was gathered from the corporates, the data was collected from the accountants, account assistants, and account clerks. The convenience sampling approach was used to collect 160 samples from the intended respondents.

Factor analysis KMO done to check sample adequacy and score

Factor Analysis

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) value for sample adequacy and the significance threshold for Bartlett's Test of Sphericity are shown in table 1. The KMO score is more than 0.7, indicating that there are significant inter-correlations among the variables and that factor analysis is necessary.

Table 1: Table indicating KMO values and Bartlett’s Test Significance

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.909	
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	3885.955
	df	300
	Sig.	.000

Bartlett's Test of Sphericity has a significance level of 0.000, indicating that there is underlying shared variation among the measures and that components may be identified based on their closeness. The aforementioned tests are used to determine if factor analysis is appropriate. The communalities show how much variability each variable is responsible for. In the factor model, variables with values greater than 0.5 accounts for more than half of the variation. Because all of the communalities are bigger than 0.5, all 25 variables account for at least 50% of the variation in the final factor solution.

Table 2: Communalities

Communalities	Initial	Extraction
Compliance	1.000	.529

Cost Saving	1.000	.694
Thanks	1.000	.779
Customization	1.000	.801
Track progress	1.000	.526
Online workspace	1.000	.687
Data encryption	1.000	.651
Device Oriented	1.000	.709
Generate Reports	1.000	.685
Modernizing	1.000	.786
High growth	1.000	.670
Transparency	1.000	.835
Automation	1.000	.840
Committing Mistakes	1.000	.746
Scalability	1.000	.726
Real Estate	1.000	.782
Paper-based	1.000	.830
Data Recovery	1.000	.796
Compatibility	1.000	.715
Replacement	1.000	.731
Data Synching	1.000	.744
Digital Solutions	1.000	.783
Human Intelligence	1.000	.528
Profession	1.000	.793
Digitalization	1.000	.836
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

Table 2 displays two key numbers (the Eigenvalues and the overall variance explained in table 3). The components with Eigenvalues greater than one are chosen because they represent a considerable amount of the total variance. All factors with Eigenvalues below one were eliminated. Only four of the 25 components initially collected had Eigenvalues greater than one. After rotation, the cumulative total variance explained is 72.80. This means that four factors account for 72.8% of the variation in the variables.

Table 3: Table Indicating the Eigenvalues and Total Variance Explained.

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	12.879	51.516	51.516	12.879	51.51	51.516	5.455	21.820	21.820
2	2.422	9.687	61.203	2.422	9.687	61.203	4.763	19.052	40.872
3	1.538	6.153	67.355	1.538	6.153	67.355	4.717	18.868	59.740
4	1.361	5.445	72.801	1.361	5.445	72.801	3.265	13.060	72.801
5	.946	3.785	76.586						
6	.875	3.500	80.086						
7	.805	3.221	83.308						
8	.593	2.372	85.679						
9	.471	1.885	87.564						
10	.398	1.591	89.155						
11	.364	1.458	90.612						
12	.296	1.183	91.795						
13	.281	1.123	92.918						
14	.251	1.006	93.924						

15	.215	.860	94.784						
16	.211	.844	95.628						
17	.186	.742	96.370						
18	.174	.695	97.066						
19	.142	.569	97.635						
20	.135	.542	98.177						
21	.125	.502	98.679						
22	.104	.417	99.096						
23	.093	.374	99.470						
24	.076	.306	99.775						
25	.056	.225	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table 4: Table indicating the Rotated Component Matrix.

Rotated Component Matrix ^a	Component			
	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4
Cost Saving			.787	
Thanks			.807	
Customization			.843	
Online workspace			.756	
Data encryption			.682	
Device Oriented		.716		
Modernizing		.766		
High growth		.609		
Transparency		.795		
Automation		.819		
Committing Mistakes		.748		
Scalability	.743			
Real Estate	.812			
Paper based	.832			
Data Recovery	.827			
Compatibility	.750			
Replacement	.730			
Data Synching	.676			
Digital Solutions				.779
Profession				.787
Digitalization				.812

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 7 iterations.

The rotated component matrix is shown in table 4. Oblique rotation was used for Principle Axis Factoring. Babakus & Boller (1992), Cronin & Taylor (1992), and Brady et al., 2002, all advised oblique rotation above orthogonal rotation. They discovered a strong link between all of the latent components of service quality. As a result, oblique rotation was selected as the rotation approach, which presupposes that the latent components are associated and not 90 degrees apart (as in the case of orthogonal rotation).

The rotation produces a total of four elements. Variables with high factor loadings are present in all of the factors (greater than .5). This demonstrates a high degree of convergent validity. Because of their great association, all of the measured variables converge to a similar underlying component, establishing convergent validity.

Under the first factor - Scalability, Real Estate, Paper-based, Data Recovery, Compatibility, Replacement, and Data Synching are loaded in the first factor. In the second factor - Device Oriented, Modernizing, High growth, Transparency, Automation and Committing Mistakes are loaded in the second factor. The third factor - Cost Saving, Thanks, Customization, Online workspace and are loaded in the third factor and the last and final factor - Digital Solutions, Profession and Digitalization and are loaded in the fourth factor

Multiple Correlation

Correlations		Factor1	Factor2	Factor4	Factor3
Factor1	Pearson Correlation	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)				
	N	160			
Factor2	Pearson Correlation	.694**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000			
	N	160	160		
Factor4	Pearson Correlation	.557**	.561**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		
	N	160	160	160	
Factor3	Pearson Correlation	.510**	.601**	.552**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	160	160	160	160

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The multiple correlations were conducted to identify the relationship between the factor 1, factor 2, factor 3 and factor 4. The selected variables were computed based on the above factor analysis. Among them, factor 1 had a high relationship with factor 2 ($r = .694$) and factor 2 had a high relationship with factor 3 ($r = .601$). The rest was found that there is a good relationship between the taken factor with more than 50%.

Discussion of the Study

An individual can be an accountant or entrepreneur. Digital accounting helps in a great way in terms of registration, understanding company profile, setting a new accounting period, setting accounting category, setting chart of accounting operations, checking balances and other transactions, accumulating and gathering assets and liabilities transactions, profit and loss transaction record, gathering general journal report, and understanding financial status and performing report analysis.

Digital accounting saves cost with the appointment of minimal working staff in the department, the numerical errors can be eliminated to a great extent. E-accounting helps in securing large data through large storage space, current and past accounting reports can be submitted and available on time. Through the relevant accounting information, economic decisions can be taken without any confusion or doubtfulness. Graphical presentation of the data outcome of analysis can be easily presented before the stakeholders for showcasing the financial health of an organization.

The beneficiaries now can switch from traditional to new technology. Software installation makes big contribution in many ways, but the only disadvantage is the huge budget requirement. The present research studied many four factors to understand the contribution of digital accounting to users.

KMO and Bartlett's Test showed a significance value of 0.000 and communalities described four factors account for 72.8% of the variation in the variables. It has been found that the high relationship existing in factor 1, factor 2, and factor 3 and the rest found correlations described the good relationship between the taken factor with more than 50%.

It is concluded that the introduction of digital accounting is playing a great role in businesses.

Conclusion

The research identified the variables and analyzed the extent of the benefits digital accounting to users. The present research has made a very much influential contribution regarding the factors focusing on the e-accounting system. In addition to merits, there are certain challenges existing in the current accounting professionals facing the

invention of customized accounting software. The adoption of E-accounting might be very costly but in the long run, it supports the enterprise in a great extent.

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THE POWER OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND TECHNOLOGIES IN FINANCIAL INSTITUTIONS IN INDIA

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Abstract

Digitalization plays a pivotal role in the economic development of the country. A process that the COVID-19 pandemic has accelerated, the present scenario of digital transformation in accounting is one of the important sectors to witness revolutionary changes in the world. Digital accounting means introducing aspects with technology. Digital technologies in combination with big data and predictive analytics are having a significant impact on professional practices at individual, organizational, national, and international levels. Digitization has been seen to change innovation processes and some experts believe it will change whole markets. The accounting industry is one of the industries that has been seen to have growth in digitalization and is expected to grow even more. The accounting sectors like many other industries are experiencing the need for a change due to digital technologies. Therefore, this study aims to investigate how digital accounting businesses could set up a general business model, in order to be a successfully digitalized business. The study uses deductive reasoning, based on many previous studies, by applying it to a sample of 237 individuals active in about 120 firms operating in the South Indian environment through a questionnaire distributed in 2021.

Background of Accounting and Financial Technologies

Many research papers and reports discussed accounting technologies, defining them in various ways. The Association of Chartered Certified Accountants (ACCA) and the Institute of Management Accounts (IMA) reported on the future of accounting titled “Digital Darwinism”. This report discussed 10 technology trends with the potential of significantly reshaping the business and professional environment, namely, Mobile, Big Data, AI and robotics, Cyber security, Educational, Cloud, Payment systems, Virtual and augmented reality, Digital service delivery, and Social (ACCA/IMA, 2013; 10). On the one hand, the Institute of Chartered Accountants in England and Wales (ICAEW) identified AI, Big Data, Block chain, and Cyber security as technologies transforming the accounting industry (IFAC, 2019). Forbes (2018) reported that harnessing the power of the Cloud, accelerating automation, and breaking through via Block chain were the future accounting trends. Accounting technology can be identified in various ways, and these technologies are not limited to accounting. In fact, they are used actively in other areas, such as autonomous vehicles, financial engineering, and so on.

There are many articles presenting the advantages of Cloud technology in accounting. According to Ionesco et al. (2013), simplification of accounting documents and migration of certain accounting operations to cloud-based electronic platforms have significantly changed accounting information systems. Ionescu et al. (2013) verified the cost saving generated by the utilization of a cloud computing-based application and stated that this is an important and relevant criterion when selecting an internet-based accounting solution. Christauskas and Miseviciene (2012) believed that digital technologies including Cloud potentially increase the quality of the business-related decision process. In addition, Phillips (2012) mentioned that clients and accountants could always be communicated with through the Cloud. The security of data can be ensured by the cloud provider and the risk of unsynchronized data can be eliminated.

The Financial Stability Board reported AI technology would enable accountants to focus on more valuable tasks such as decision-making, problem-solving, advising, strategy development, and leadership (FSB, 2017). Deloitte (2017) presented that RPA accelerates greater automation of the process and AI improves productivity in public sectors. Accuracy and efficiency can be increased and operating costs and time can be reduced in performing accounting tasks processes by AI technology. AI can provide higher quality information by machine or deep

learning, and contribute to generating more transparent accounting information (AhnandJung2018; Bauguess2017; Cho et al. 2018; O'Neill 2016; PwC 2017).

Big Data present many important implications for accounting. Warren et al. (2015) stated that video and image data, audio data, and textual data are different types of Big Data as a supplement to existing accounting records, and this information made available through Big Data can provide improved accounting practices. In an increasingly complex and high-volume data environment, the use of technology and Big Data analytics offers greater opportunities in all accounting areas. For example, auditors can obtain a more effective and robust understanding of the entity and its environment, and enhance the quality of the auditor's risk assessment and response (IAASB, 2016: 7).

Prior studies stated that Block chain is a technology with a direct impact on the accounting profession. Block chain is a data decentralization-based technique (Raval 2016). Various data are saved on a list of records called blocks and these blocks are linked like chains using cryptography. It is an open, distributed ledger that can record transactions between two parties efficiently and in a verifiable and permanent way (Iansiti and Lakhani2017). Once recorded, the data in any given block cannot be altered retroactively without the alteration of all subsequent blocks, which requires the consensus of the network majority (Raval 2016). Therefore, modification, alternation, and manipulation of data become improbable (if not impossible). PwC (2016) presented that Block chain is considered as the next generation of business-processing software where transactions are shared among customers, competitors, and suppliers. Particularly, Block chain with functions that enable data integrity, rapid processing and sharing, and programmatic and automatic control processing will significantly contribute to developing new accounting systems. Given these studies mentioned above, this study summarizes the new technologies ushering significant changes in accounting into Cloud, AI including RPA and ML, Big Data, and Block chain. In the following section, I present the research methodology and explain the selection backgrounds and how these technologies and cases are adopted for this study.

Introduction

Definition of Digital Transformation

Digital transformation is defined as the process of companies moving to business models based on digital technologies and developments accompanying the Fourth Industrial Revolution (Vial, 2019) through the use of artificial intelligence, big data analytics, cloud computing, and the Internet of Things to support the development and innovation of products and services (Akter et al., 2020), and provide new marketing capabilities and job opportunities that increase the value of their products (Phornlaphatrachakorn & Na Kalasindhu, 2021).

Digital Transformation Steps

Digital transformation begins by formulating a digital strategy and making an improvement to the current situation of the organization (Saarikko et al., 2020). This can only be achieved by measuring the current digital capabilities and determining the best work structure for digital marketing activities in the organization. After that, the requirements for investment plans are identified with the identification of digital integration obstacles to working a comprehensive and tight plan for all circumstances, and to push the transformation into the desired situation (Baethge-Kinsky, 2020), and finally, the necessity of having change management for digital transformation to achieve the strategic goals (Correani et al., 2020).

In this context, we find that AWS— a leading company in the field of cloud computing— has provided a checklist to build strategies that allow freedom to innovate and develop ways of working to achieve a successful digital transformation that is based on transforming vision, adopting a culture of change, changing the cost model, starting businesses in the cloud, and following the application process (Nguyen et al., 2021).

Aspects of Digital Transformation Affecting Accounting & Financial Information Systems

The great digital revolution in the Internet and communications networks led to a wide and rapid change in the business environment, which made it imperative for organizations to keep pace with these huge developments to

move accounting and management information systems from classic methods to modern digital methods (Andreassen, 2020). We do not mean here information systems that depend on computers and various applications, and traditional accounting programs, which have outlived time globally after the emergence of digital entities, which have revolutionized the pattern of business conduct by setting standards that allow each facility to choose technologies commensurate with the nature of its work such as artificial intelligence, Internet of Things, Blockchain technologies, Big Data, Cloud Computing, and Cyber Security (Begum, 2019). These technologies will allow for increasing transparency and reducing cost, saving effort and time, facilitating data access, protecting, data, and enhancing efficiency in the work of the accounting information system (Oncioiu et al., 2019).

Block chain

It is an information network that contains a group of devices or nodes, each of which represents a database and a ledger, where all transactions that take place within the network are subject to verification and confirmation of their validity by the rest of the network devices (Akter et al., 2020). This technology helps in developing accounting information systems by giving transparency and moving from double entry to more automatic triple entry in record keeping. Accounting reduces the margin of error in preparing financial reports and shortens the time and effort expended by accountants, as the accounting recording of transactions will be directly in a common ledger among all dealers in the chain, thus creating more intertwined accounting systems (Faccia, 2019).

Cloud Computing

It is not just a technical solution or a server that has been stored and has another impact, but rather a form of digital transformation that improves the implementation of accounting work (Demiröz & Heupel, 2017). The most important advantages of cloud computing are saving effort and time and thus reducing cost, speed in processing and data storage, scalability, data protection, easy data connectivity, ensuring services are always running, and benefiting from the huge infrastructure provided by cloud services (Al-Zoubi, 2017).

Big Data

It represents a huge amount of complex data that exceeds the capacity of traditional software and computer mechanisms to store, process, and distribute them (Yao & Gao, 2020). Big data can be used in accounting as it enables companies to benefit from the analysis of data generated by financial markets and social media to identify their audience and predict the results of marketing and sales campaigns.

Artificial intelligence

Artificial intelligence is that emphasizes the creation of intelligent machines that work and react like humans. Data is handled and processed in a completely automated and generates fast and reliable reports.

Challenges Facing Digital Transformation

Many factors prevent the process of digital transformation within organizations, including the lack of human resources (Mitrofanova et al., 2018), and the lack of budgets allocated to these programs limiting their growth (Gupta, 2018). Fear of information security risks, as a result of the use of technological means, is one of the biggest obstacles, especially if the assets are of high value (Rehm, 2018), and the absence of a regulatory legal framework especially in developing countries.

Objectives of the study

- To study the conceptual framework of digital transformation of Accounting and Finance in India.
- To identify the economic institutions and the importance of adopting digital transformation of technologies in light of traditional information systems.

Study methodology

To address the main research objectives, the research uses quantitative methods, such as deductive reasoning, based on secondary data represented in previous articles related to the topic of digital transformation and accounting information systems. The study uses primary data through the study tool, which is a questionnaire for a sample of economic institutions within the South Indian environment in 2021, and analyses the data through statistical programs

Research gap

This study is distinguished by the fact that it deals with the issue of digital transformation and its impact on accounting information systems in the Indian environment, which differs from previous studies. The study also presents the advantages and obstacles of digital transformation in India.

Literature Review

Many researchers have addressed the issue of the relationship between digital transformation and accounting information systems from different perspectives, with different research tools, and within a distinct study community.

- Nguyen et al. (2021) concluded that digital transformation processes will allow managers to take advantage of the effort related to accounting work and the attendant errors to search for customers and focus on improving product quality and increasing the organization's competitiveness.
- In the study of Othman and AL-Dweikat (2021), it has been found that there is a tangible impact of managing the risks of digital transformation in making appropriate information that serves the makers and users of accounting data.
- The study of Thipwiwatpotjana (2021) concludes that the determinants of digital transformation ability are executive leaders, business model, organizational structure, the possibility of access to external resources, and support.
- In addition, the study by Phornlaphatrachakorn and NaKalasindhu (2021) shows that digital accounting is of great importance in influencing accounting information and the quality of financial reports, thus increasing the effectiveness of strategic decisions.
- The study of Saed (2020) concludes that there are two important dimensions to the subject, namely, accounting maturity and the need and readiness for digital transformation.
- The study of Timchev (2020) sheds light on the analysis of the accounting business of companies within the conditions of competition and digital transformation, which includes the strategic and operational levels.
- The study of Parlak (2020) shows that digital transformation has a tangible impact on accounting information systems and the accounting profession, from memorizing, classifying, and summarizing to analyzing and discussing financial statements, establishing the system, and ensuring the effective continuity of the system. It is, therefore, necessary for members of the accounting profession to use the developed systems to adapt to this transformation process effectively.
- The study by Lazarova (2019) concludes that the formation of digital transformation is not only within higher administrative levels, but includes all levels and functions of institutions, including accounting and finance.
- The study of Oncioiu et al. (2019) allows identifying digital transformation within management accounting systems, and the topic is addressed by presenting theoretical concepts on the subject. In general, this paper presents how electronic accounting has developed within enterprises, in addition to understanding digital transformation processes through the exchange of knowledge and the respective effects on the leaders who supervise management accounting.
- The study by Begum (2019) was based on the deductive approach. The questionnaire, used as a tool for the study, was distributed to a sample of 40 respondents. The questionnaire included various digital technologies in accounting, and the weakness of the digital capabilities of institutions was assessed.
- Rehm (2017) highlighted how to prepare accounting information systems for digital transformation, and the topic was addressed by presenting the most important steps to be followed through a general description of the administrative documentation process, preparing a guide for the process of accounting documents, defining principles and directions measures to be taken in exceptional cases, documentation of operating procedures.
- Finally, Demiröz and Heupel (2017) have found that there is a lack of awareness among business organizations of the overall benefits of digital transformation, as many of these organizations are still in the first steps of digital transformation due to internal obstacles.
- Jonas (2015), Businesses have to learn how to manage the digital innovation change and also what the indirect technological changes it brings to an organization. Goswami (2016), study focused on digital programmers introduced by the government of India which helps in transforming the country into a digitally empowered economy also says it reduces the paperwork and helps in providing different services

electronically to citizens. Southern Cross University, (2016), the article tries to prove that digital accounting will provide the industry value creation through new techniques, services, and technology in order to satisfy new customer segments and bring new markets to rise.

- Sharma (2016), study attempt to understand Digital India – as a campaign where technologies and connectivity will come together to make an impact on all aspects of governance and improve the quality, and once implemented properly it will open various new opportunities for the citizens.

Research Methodology

The study is conducted using both analytical and descriptive type of methodology. The study depends on primary and secondary data. This study is conducted through a structured questionnaire to confirm the feasibility of the study.

Sample Size

Random Sampling is used through the survey method for generating data. The respondents are the population of finance officers selected from various organizations. The information collected through a set of questionnaires from the 40 respondents related to the digital transformation of accounting in India.

Scope of the Study

The secondary data highlighted the conceptual framework of digitalization in the field of finance and accounting. The sources of secondary data for the study were collected from the theoretical issues in relation to books, reports, journals, articles, thesis, internet sources, and published papers/ data.

Data Analysis Tool

Data Collected will be presented and analyzed using tables. The study includes a simple percentage of calculations:

$$\text{Simple percentage} = \frac{\text{Number of Respondent}}{\text{Total Number of Respondents}} \times 100$$

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The data for the study is collected from the finance department of various organizations.

Table No.1

Personal Information				
SNo	Particulars	Classification	F	%
1.	Gender	Male	25	62.5%
		Female	15	37.5%
2.	Age	25-35	10	20%
		36-45	14	35%
		46-55	12	30%
		55 – Above	4	15%
3.	Education	Graduate	24	60%
		Post Graduate	16	40%
4.	Experience	< 5 Years	10	20%
		6-15 Years	14	35%
		16-20 Above Years	18	45%

Source: Field Survey Data

Discussion: The above table gives clear information: About Gender says 62.5% male and 37.5% female respondents. The age of respondents between 25-35 years is 20% and 36- 45 ages 35% which is the highest, 46-55 is 30%, and above 55 years are only 10% which is the least. Education- the majority of them are graduates i.e., 60%, it was found only 40% are postgraduates. Finally, the experience of the respondents expressed less than 5 years are 10%, 6-15 years 35%, and 16-20 and above years experienced are 45%.

SNo	Statement	Status	Future Aspiration
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			Low	Medium	High	Low	Medium	High
1.	Paperless Accounting	F	6	34	--	--	--	40
		%	15%	85%	--	--	--	100%
2.	Uniformity of Systems and Creation of Transparency	F	6	28	6	--	--	40
		%	15%	70%	15%	--	--	100%
3.	Process Automation	F	--	20	20	--	2	38
		%	--	50%	50%	--	5%	95%
4.	Integrated Consolidation System	F	14	6	20	--	2	38
		%	35%	15%	50%	--	5%	95%
5.	Big Data Analysis	F	6	34	--	--	--	40
		%	15%	85%	--	--	--	100%
6.	Real-time Reporting	F	--	34	6	--	2	38
		%	--	85%	15%	--	15%	95%
7.	Tools for Visualization	F	14	36	--	--	--	40
		%	35%	65%	--	--	--	100%
8.	Cloud Accounting	F	40	--	--	--	2	38
		%	100%	--	--	--	5%	95%
9.	Block Chain	F	34	6	--	--	14	26
		%	85%	15%			35%	65%
10.	Artificial Intelligence	F	38	2	--	--	2	38
		%	95%	5%	--	--	5%	95%
11.	Fibre Connectivity	F	20	20	--	--	--	40
		%	50%	50%	--	--	--	100%
12.	Making Tax Digital	F	--	38	2	--	--	40
		%	--	95%	5%	--	--	100%

Source: Field Survey Data

Discussion: The present status gives a picture of the perception of the respondents related to paperless accounting, uniformity of systems, and creation of transparency says the majority of them identified is at the medium level i.e., (85% and 70% respectively). Process automation finds 50% both at high and medium levels. Integrated consolidation system of accounting updates 35% at low level 15% at medium level and 50% at high level. Big data analysis maintains 15% at a low level and 85% at a medium level. Real-time reporting of financial statements follows 85% at the medium level and 85% at the high level. Tools for visualization are at 35% and 65% at low and medium levels respectively. Cloud Accounting does not find at any level. Block chain is rare to find so 35% and 65% at low and medium levels. Artificial intelligence is 95% and 5% at low and medium levels, Fibre connectivity maintains 50% both at low and medium levels, and Tax digitalization is 95% and 5% at medium and high levels respectively.

Conclusion

The study focused on the digital transformation of accounting across the country has changed the Institutional character. Digital accounting and finance making a new possible way of overreaching accounting practice, providing a framework that brings coherence and integrating activities. Digital technology also creates the possibility of a wide variety of learning practices, including exposition, independent research, and construction. The study concludes, there is a lack of knowledge about digital transformation in accounting and finance among the employees in the various organizations and the status quo is in the average level and the future aspiration expectation at the high level. The study clearly pointed out that the development of technology is required for the development of digital accounting and finance across the country and helped to transform the country into the knowledge of digitalization heaven.

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HOW FINTECH HAS CHANGED THE BORROWING CAPACITY OF INDIAN YOUTHS?

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Abstract

FinTech (Financial Technology) is a significant rising technology which will be supporting the way we borrow funds and will provide an efficient access to financial services and help the youth or existing users to escape the long waiting hours of traditional banking. It is surprising that even from the constant evolution in the fintech industry, Indian youths are facing difficulties adapting it. There has been a potential increase in the field of fintech by academic literature in recent years, but the research conducted has no connection with the agenda of coherent research. The gap between the research and important questions asked by today's generation is still significant. In the spirit of connecting Indian youth to fintech for changing their borrowing method, researchers through this research papers have attempted to drive a framework which offers themes of coherent research that is formulated through focus questionnaires, surveys and few researches conducted in recent years on fintech, which also includes critical assessment of the literature review conducted over here. Our research objective is to know how borrowing of Indian youths has changed and the way they borrow funds.

This research also explores how fintech has impacted on the borrowing capacity in Indian youths. The basis of this study is on a survey of 500 young adults ageing from the age group between 18 and 30 years who have borrowed money through fintech platforms. The results indicate that fintech has significantly increased the borrowing capacity of Indian youths by providing them with easier access to credit, lower interest rates, and flexible repayment options. The research highlights the role of fintech in democratising access to credit, reducing the reliance on traditional banks, and promoting financial inclusion among young adults in India. The findings suggest that fintech has the potential to address the credit gap and improve the financial well-being of the Indian youth population.

Keywords: Fintech, Indian Youth, Borrowing, financial inclusion, ways to borrow funds

1. Introduction

Fintech (Financial Technology) refers to the innovation in the financial sectors by delivering services and products in finance. Technologies in the finance sector constantly evolves; the advancement in Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine learning to evaluate the investment opportunities, mitigating risks and optimising the portfolios. Fintech at its core is utilised to help companies, businesses, consumers and the financial sector by managing their financial part of the operations, and also prevent them from going through the burden and time-consuming process of cash and credit/debit-based payments. One of the recent data of this annual report shows how global investments in Fintech has been amounted to USD 107.8 Billion in 2022 (KPMG, 2022), which is low compared to global investments in 2021, which amounted to a whopping number of US \$210 billion (KPMG, 2021). The investors are looking for the next big thing in the fintech industry as the numbers seem to drop back to levels seen in previous years, the investors are anticipated to focus heavily on H2 '22 into 2023. The trends to watch for H2 '22 is:

1. Market corrections,
2. Big tech companies and other corporates prioritising partnership
3. Showdown in crypto interest and investment
4. Increasing focus on underdeveloped fintech markets.

However, the upcoming development in the fintech industry will be fuelled in greater aspects. There will be more and more implementation of blockchain technology, Artificial intelligence, and many more things over the internet or IOT (internet of things) basis applications in the financial industry for the purpose of transactions by the year 2023 - 2024. The user in financial technology will be able to have much more and wider access of more specialised offerings in the aspect to meet the demand of its users.

Young people or the Indian youths in India nowadays are more comfortable with technology than prior generations were. Their early exposure to a technological advanced environment has an impact on how they connect with one another and how they prefer to interact with the financial services offered by neo banks, banks and other service providers for the ease of their usage towards finance. According to research conducted by YouGov, 49% of Indians are tech adapters and are eager to buy new products and adapt to new financial technologies. Young people used digital gadgets more frequently throughout the Covid 19 pandemic, where the less tech savvy people suffered during the pandemic time, they relied on technology to meet their basic necessities throughout the emergency.

The ultimate objective of this research is to provide the financial autonomy they need. Promoting awareness of the value of technology and educating people about it are essential if India has to become a fully cashless economy. For digital freedom to be genuinely successful a holy triad between the bank, fintech firm and the government needs to be established.

2. Literature review

Aijaz A. Shaikh, Hawazen Alamoudi, Majed Alharthi, Richard Glavee-Geo (2022) states that MFS (mobile financial services) consists of three major categories or domains. Those three categories are majorly ATMs (Automated Teller Machine), POS (Point of Sale), NFC (Near Field Communication) and Net Banking. Also, Agrata Gupta, Chun Xia (2018) endorses Aijaz Et al. by referring in their article “A Paradigm Shift in Banking: Unfolding Asia’s FinTech Adventures” on money lending services, transfers and exchanges has helped the fintechs to grow and rise for a new start, via these fund transferring system FinTech industries are emerging as a new way to borrow funding. In favour of the fintech borrowing, Anchal Arora, Sanjay Gupta, Chandrika Devi, Nidhi Walia, (2023) presents how the AI system in fintech industry has emerged as a new technology by providing its customers the top 3

factors: service quality, perceived usefulness and perceived convenience and gaining maximum consumer base. Later onwards, Kanwal Anil & Anil Misra (2022) with research on 20 NBFCs states that AI has developed the current NBFCs to adopt the dynamic nature into FinTech with ease. After seeing the financial inclusion rise in the finance industry, Rashedul Hasan, Muhammad Ashfaq, Tamiza Parveen, Ardi Gunardi (2022) finds the rise of financial inclusion in women which reflects the positive impact on how the fintechs have changed the way women borrow, spend, save and exchange funds. Backing the Fintechs, Howard Thomas and Yuwa Hedrick-Wong (2019) found out how M-Pesa has changed the way of sending and receiving money. It was because of the two major factors, transfer of funds easily to dependents in rural areas and the innovative UI design of the app made it easy for people to learn about FinTech. Ahmad Arslan, Bonnie G. Buchanan, Samppa Kamara, Nasib Al Nabulsi (2021) states fintech creates a social value for entrepreneurs. Especially mobile money which reduces the business of unseen fake transactions. While going through the recent trends of FDI (foreign direct investment) and the inflows of funds into Fintechs by DI (direct investment) Samridhi Tanwar, Surbhi Bhardwaj (2022) researches shows how the fintech helped the new entrepreneurs on seed funding for their startup by ways of international payments developed by financial institutions or financial technology companies. Emerson Wagner Mainardes, Neudson Peres de Freitas (2023) ratified how the financial services industry has gained more loyal customers since its starting than traditional banking has ever gained since its starting. Ashish Kumar Singh, Prayas Sharma (2022) initiated their research with relation to how fintech has helped the Millennials and Gen-X consumers during the pandemic situation. The payment services helped for virtual instant payments without visiting the branch of the bank as the traditional banking. Seeing to this, Ankita Das, Debabrata Das (2022) endorsed the findings of Ashish Kumar Singh, Prayas Sharma (2022) on fintech in covid, and did research on adoption of fintechs during the pandemic 2019 and stated that pandemic made a rise to use of financial services with context to fintechs for transferring, lending, receiving and etc of funds from the ease of their home. They also stated the risk involved in the fintech services which cannot be in the traditional banking services. By seeing the current era, Xiuping Hua, Yiping Huang, Yanfeng Zheng (2022) researched current practices, insights, and emerging trends in financial technology. Their findings stated that fintech applications have a very wide area to change the lending and borrowing of millennials and gen-z in comparison to traditional banking.

However, according to past researchers, the contribution of fintech towards youth and their borrowing capacity has changed from past years. More and more youth are able to increase their purchasing power parity by lending from different sources of fintechs.

Research Questions

- What are the changes that have taken place in the fintechs from pre-covid and post-covid?
- Describe the difference between traditional way of banking and the fintech approach of banking
- Youth's mindset towards borrowing via fintechs
- Government measures towards fintech industries and their upbringing.
- How has fintech affected the interest rates from the last 20 years?

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Research objectives

- 1. Understanding how the Indian youth are implementing fintech services.**
- 2. Investigating the elements that affect Indian youth's adoption of fintech services.**
- 3. Identifying the challenges faced by Indian youth in adapting and utilising the fintech services.**
- 4. Exploring the potential of future growth of the fintech industry by targeting the youth.**
- 5. To determine the gaps where the current fintech ecosystem is failing to meet the demands of youths of India.**

3.2 Hypothesis

Indian youths are increasingly adopting the latest fintech ways of accessing financial services and managing their finances while fintech services are helping to promote financial inclusions among Indian youths. This theory is supported by the adoption of smartphones and internet connectivity, which has created an opportunity for the fintech companies to reach a wider audience than before, including the youth. According to a recent survey conducted by KPMG group, it reflected the number of users of the internet in Indian region is anticipated to reach the number 900 million by the end of year 2025, and smartphone penetration is likely to increase to 80% in the same year i.e. 2025. By this data, we can hypothetically assume that there can be a potential significant rise in the market for fintech services that meet the demand of Indian youth.

By giving young people access to formal financial services that they didn't have before, fintech firms are promoting inclusion among them. Which will help to increase their knowledge, raise their credit scores and also help them in investing and saving. In addition to this, fintech companies are also offering specialised financial services that are customised according to their needs, this is done with the help of data analytics and AI (artificial intelligence).

Majority of the people in India, especially in rural regions are struggling to receive basic financial services due to lack of financial inclusions in those areas, we can see the role fintechs in collaboration with edutech are providing financial inclusions in the backward areas of India which in upcoming years might lead to more number of youths using the fintech services for lending, borrowing, accepting and paying funds rather preferring the traditional Indian banking system which is time taking and includes more number documentations.

The above data is hypothetical and is on the basis of data and surveys conducted by firms such as KPMG and others.

3.3 Research Approach

The research approach used for this research is quantitative which was collected through surveys or analysis of existing financial data to assess the impact of fintech on borrowing among Indian youths. This includes data on loan disbursement, repayment rates, interest rates, and other financial metrics. Another data used was qualitative data which was collected through interviews and focus groups with Indian youths to gain insights into their attitudes and experiences with fintech borrowing. This included their reasons for using fintech, their perceptions of the borrowing process, and their experiences with loan repayment. The research also involves a comparative analysis of traditional borrowing methods versus fintech borrowing methods to identify the advantages and disadvantages of each. The findings of the research could be used to inform policy decisions related to fintech lending and financial inclusion in India.

3.4 Survey

A survey is a systematic data collection method that involves gathering information and responses from a representative sample of individuals to assess their attitudes, preferences, behaviors, or experiences related to a specific research topic. In the context of this research on the transformative impact of fintech on the borrowing capacity of Indian youths, the survey was designed to understand the mindset and borrowing habits of Indian youths regarding fintech lending platforms. Through the survey, quantitative and qualitative data were collected, allowing for a comprehensive analysis of the borrowing preferences, access to credit, and perceptions of fintech lending among the target group. The survey's findings provide valuable insights and support the research's empirical evidence, enriching the understanding of how fintech has influenced the borrowing landscape for Indian youths.

3.5 Instrument

In this research, a combination of both forms of data which are primary and secondary has been collected for the purpose of achieving the goals of this research. Primary data is the data collected by first-hand sources whereas the data which is pre-used by other authorities or organizations or researchers is known as secondary data.

Primary data was collected by surveys, autobiographies and public opinion, while secondary data was collected by research articles, books and newspapers. It became more efficient to collect the data as per these improvements.

What do you think are the government implications and strategies to increase the growth of the fintech industry in India?

- What are the parameters to set-up a fintech company or start-up in the current Indian market?
- What are the advantages and disadvantages of the fintech industry over traditional banks?
- How has fin tech changed the era of finance since its adoption in context to the Indian youths?
- Has fintech affected the borrowing interest rates in comparison to traditional banking.
- What more changes can fintech bring in the upcoming era for finance and borrowing in India for Gen-Z?

4. Findings of Research

While conducting this research, researchers have found out that in Indian youths, the ways of lending money has changed since the usage of more and more fintechs which has led to rise in the emergence of more innovation in the field of fintechs. Launch of financial technologies such as CRED, NBFC and others like 12% Club, have now made it possible for all the Indian youths to borrow funds and finance their livelihood in a new and different way.

- Fintech has increased access to credit for Indian youths who were previously excluded from the traditional banking system, particularly those with lower income or credit scores.
- Also, Fintech lending platforms have lower documentation requirements, making it easier for Indian youths to apply for loans and receive quick decisions.
- Fintech platforms may offer more flexible repayment options, such as pay-as-you-earn plans, that are better suited to the needs of Indian youths.
- Some Indian youths may be hesitant to use fintech lending platforms due to concerns about high interest rates, lack of regulation, or fear of fraudulent activity.
- Fintech lending may contribute to financial inclusion for Indian youths, but it also raises questions about the potential risks and downsides of such platforms.
- Fintech has brought a drastic change in Indian youths and the way of borrowing has changed to an extreme extent.

5. Data Analysis

The digital payments market in India was anticipated to be worth ₹63 trillion in the Financial Year 2021 and is anticipated to grow by the CAGR of 29% to reach ₹385 Trillion by the end of the Financial Year 2026 (data collected from PWC)

Founder Profiles

Parameters on Comparison of Fintech Data in India & China

PARAMETERS	INDIA	CHINA
Population	1,417,014,810 as of Tuesday, March 28, 2023	1,454,477,438 as of Tuesday, March 28, 2023
Gross Domestic Product	\$3,176.30B (2021)	\$17,734.06B (2021)
Mobile Penetration	829 million	1680 million
Unbanked Population	190 million	225 million
FinTech Investments (in Billion Dollars)	50	1.8

Table 1.1

In table 1.1 , we have used 5 parameters to compare two countries in the fintech industry. Those parameters include population, country’s GDP, country’s mobile penetration, unbanked population and total number of fintech investments that have taken place. The data obtained is from the year 2021. Here, **mobile penetration** means the amount of population that uses mobile phones in the country. Unbanked population refers to the total number of people in the country which do not have any connections or access to traditional banking services or even don't own a bank account.

The data collected is from MacroTrends and here, we can see that researchers are comparing two countries which are into digitalization and adapting fintechs. The population compared of India with China, which is 3,74,62,628 less of India from China, but on the other hand we can also see that since India has less population in comparison to

China but amount of unbanked population in comparison to mobile penetration is **0.22:1** and of that of China is **0.13:1**, this shows that people in India are more likely adapting the fintech facilities given to them by the government or new startups in the finance sector. Whereas, China being the highly developed & populated country than India has least opportunities in context finance and financial technologies. Investments made by Indians in recent years into the fintech industry have made the fintech industry capitalization to \$50 Billion, whereas China on the other hand has only \$1.8 Billion. India being more into fintech with rising financial literacy and financial inclusion is making India stand out from the rest of the emerging economies.

FACE (Fintech Association of Consumer Empowerment) Report

One of the reports published by FACE (Fintech Association of Consumer Empowerment) says that the Fintech or the financial technology lending companies have been issuing loans in the financial year 2021-2022 which amounted to ₹2.66 crores making the total lending till year end amounting to ₹18000 crores. This shows that fintech in India has been a game changer by lending crores of funds to the public and private sector. This has increased due to the public being able to access the digital lending and borrowing platforms easily and financial inclusion being spread in India. Suggested from the reports of Goldman Sachs, India’s digital marketing industry is going to hit a whopping target of \$160 Billion by the end of financial year 2025, this shows how Indian’s are contributing towards financial inclusion by spreading awareness through big digital platforms and digital marketers who are into finance.

Market size of the digital advertising industry across India from 2016 to 2021, with estimates until 2023

(in billion Indian rupees)

Digitalization

Above is the graph collected from Statista which shows how digital marketing has increased in recent years in India. Post covid the digital marketing industry has grown from 62.2 Billion to 358.09 Billion. This shows that social media has helped the country in increasing the financial inclusion due to which Indians have got to know more about the ways finance is available to them. Indians in the upcoming future will be able to easily access the financial aids provided by the Indian government and other fintech companies who are able to change the way how Indian youths will borrow funds in the upcoming years.

Data Privacy Security

Fintech are built on trust, ethics and culture relevant to the fintech tradition. Privacy regulations that are currently in place or expected to be implemented soon offer consumers various rights pertaining to their personal data, which are centred on trust. One example is the GDPR, which enables individuals to exercise their right to access, transparency, and deletion of their data. Trust, in conjunction with ethical and cultural factors, is also important in achieving a

company's goals. The Reserve Bank of India (RBI) is constantly working on the data protection of India users while other countries never care for the data protection of their own citizens.

On September 1, 2022

Over 800 million users' data of Chinese citizens have been breached. Making it the 2nd data breach in a time span of 2 months, the data which was breached belonged to the top tech companies in China named - Xintai Electronics. In India, consumer data is highly prioritised for each and every citizen keeping it safe from hackers to breach the data of Indian citizens.

Introduction of ISO 20022

ISO 20022 is a widely recognized and adopted global standard that facilitates the exchange of electronic data between financial institutions. Its main objective is to establish a uniform structure and terminology for financial messages across various communication channels and systems, thereby enhancing the efficiency and accuracy of transaction processing. The standardisation of financial messages through ISO 20022 reduces complexities and inconsistencies, enabling financial institutions to communicate with ease and accuracy. With the ability to replace existing message formats, ISO 20022 offers a more adaptable, flexible, and extensible format that is in line with the evolving needs of the financial industry. The increasing adoption of ISO 20022 by financial institutions worldwide signifies its potential to become the primary standard for financial messaging in the near future.

#3 Features of ISO 20022 which have made it more acceptable worldwide.

The three features are:

1. It is an open standard for global financial messaging, since being an open standard, so it can be easily modified timely according to the user needs, making it user-friendly
2. The syntax of the system or technology is designed to be compatible with a variety of computer operating systems across different networks, allowing for seamless interoperability and integration without requiring any modifications to the code or syntax.
3. ISO 20022 offers an increased data carrying capacity and improved structure, allowing for better identification of the senders and receivers of payment instructions. This enhanced capacity enables financial institutions to include more data in payment messages, which can help to improve the accuracy and efficiency of payment processing. Specifically, the increased data carrying capacity of ISO 20022 enables better identification of the originators and end-beneficiaries of payment instructions, which can improve the transparency and traceability of financial transactions. This can help to reduce errors, prevent fraud, and enhance compliance with regulatory requirements.

Rising Rate of FinTech in India

Over the last decade, the fintech industry in India has experienced remarkable growth, which gained momentum following the expansion of internet services across the country. India's fintech adoption rate of 87% is significantly higher than the global average of 64%, making it one of the world's fastest-growing fintech markets. However, despite this phenomenal growth, India still has the second-largest population of unbanked individuals, with an estimated 190 million people lacking access to traditional banking services. Therefore, it is essential to extend technology-based financial services throughout the country in a secure manner, ensuring that digital financial inclusion is made available to every corner of the country. This is necessary to cater to the growing demand for financial inclusion, particularly among the unbanked population, who face significant challenges in accessing traditional financial services due to various barriers. Achieving this objective would help promote financial inclusion and digitalization across the country.

The availability of finance is one of the biggest challenges faced by micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs). According to a report by the International Finance Corporation (IFC), the MSME credit gap stands at a staggering USD 400 billion, posing a significant threat to their very existence. Fintech can be a game-changer in this regard, providing a solution to the problem of credit availability for MSMEs. Fintech startups are now offering easy and quick access to loans, eliminating the need for MSMEs to go through the cumbersome process of paperwork, documentation, and multiple visits to banks.

The emergence of fintech in the financial services sector has facilitated a more streamlined approach to lending, which has greatly benefited MSMEs. Fintech startups are using innovative technologies such as machine learning, artificial intelligence, and blockchain to assess creditworthiness and provide customised loan products tailored to the specific needs of MSMEs. This has made it possible for MSMEs to access credit without having to go through the traditional brick-and-mortar banking system, which can be time-consuming and burdensome.

Overall, fintech has the potential to revolutionise the way MSMEs access finance, addressing the credit gap and helping to create a more vibrant and sustainable MSME sector. By leveraging technology to streamline lending processes, fintech can enable MSMEs to grow their businesses and contribute to economic growth and job creation in their communities.

Government Initiatives for FinTech in India

- The "Jan Dhan Yojana" initiative, the largest financial inclusion program globally, has facilitated the enrolment of over 450 million beneficiaries for direct benefit transfers and access to a range of financial services applications, including credit, insurance, remittances, and pensions. This has provided an opportunity for FinTech companies to develop technology-based products to reach the vast consumer base in India.
- India Stack refers to a collection of APIs that provide a digital infrastructure for governments, businesses, startups, and developers to address India's challenges by delivering presence-less, paperless, and cashless services. The India Stack has played a vital role in the rapid development of fintech companies in India.
- The National Payments Corporation of India developed the Unified Payments Interface (UPI) in 2016, which is an innovative mobile application-based payment system for transferring funds between bank accounts. UPI has become the driving force behind the Fintech revolution in India, with more than 338 banks registered under the platform. As of July 2022, UPI has recorded over 6.28 billion transactions worth 10.62 lakh crore.
- India's Central Bank Digital Currency (CBDC), also known as the digital rupee or e-rupee, was recently launched as an electronic version of cash. Its introduction is expected to significantly boost the growth of the fintech market in India.

6. Data Objective

Objective of this research is to find out the borrowing capabilities of Indians youth which has changed from past years since the implementation of fintech into financial sectors.

7. Implications of Research

- Improving Financial Literacy - this research identifies the gap in the financial literacy among the youths in India and suggests ways to improve it. This can guide them in decision making regarding fintech products and services. Help them to minimise financial risks.
- Empowering Indian youths - the research can empower the youths of India and help them adapt to fintech and also in taking advantage of opportunities offered by the fintech industry and in making wise decisions.
- Enhancing access to financial service - this research highlights the potential to increase financial services for Indian youth, especially for those who are underserved by or excluded from traditional banking channels.
- Regulatory and Policy Decisions Information - regulations and policies relating to fintech are informed through this research, which facilitates the development of new fintech products and helps Indian youth to be safe from danger and risks.
- Encouraging innovation and entrepreneurship - the study might help in identifying opportunities for innovation and entrepreneurship and offer insight into the ecosystem of fintech in India. This will help in boosting the economic growth by attracting and encouraging talent and capital to the fintech industry

8. Limitations of Research

Limitations in this research are:

Limited sample size: Depending on the scope of this research, the sample size is small or non-representative as this research data collection was only limited to area experts and their view, so this could limit the generalizability of the findings.

Self-selection bias: Individuals who use fintech lending platforms are different from those who do not use fintech, and also their attitudes and behaviours were different too towards borrowing from the way of fintech, with many more different prospects as well, which could introduce biases into the results.

Data availability: Availability of data on fintech lending in India is limited or incomplete to a general prospect, but this could affect the ability of the researchers to fully understand the impact of these platforms on the borrowing capacity of Indian youths and conducting the research.

Time constraints: Our research studies may be limited to some extent in terms of the time available for data collection or analysis or the type of data collected, which could impact the depth and quality of the findings in this research.

Changes in the fintech landscape: The fintech industry is rapidly evolving since the post pandemic and pre-pandemic, and our research conducted at one point in time may not reflect the current state of the industry due to the dynamic in fintech and finance, this could limit the relevance and applicability of the findings in the upcoming future.

9. Further Scope of Research

Scope in this background can be further led to an in-depth analysis of the lending practices of specific fintech platforms and their impact on the borrowing capacity of Indian youths. This could help identify the key factors that contribute to increased access to credit and explore any potential downsides or risks associated with these platforms. Also, a comparative analysis of fintech lending and traditional lending practices in India, focusing on differences in access to credit, interest rates, and repayment options for Indian youths. This could help identify areas where fintech lending may be more beneficial or where traditional lending practices may be more appropriate.

A study of the financial literacy and decision-making skills of Indian youths who use fintech lending platforms. This could help identify any gaps in financial education and develop targeted resources to support young borrowers. By conducting an examination of the role of social and cultural factors in shaping the attitudes and behaviours of Indian youths towards fintech lending. This could help identify any barriers to adoption and explore potential strategies for increasing uptake of these platforms.

Lastly, an analysis of the potential risks and downsides of fintech which are lending to Indian youths, including issues such as high interest rates, hidden fees, and predatory lending practices. This could help inform policy decisions and regulatory frameworks to protect consumers while still promoting access to credit.

10. Conclusions

In conclusion, the impact of financial technology on the borrowing capacity of Indian youths was an important area of research in the field of finance which has significant implications for policymakers, financial institutions, and consumers such as the current Indian youths. While there is still so much to learn about the topic of fintech in this era, our preliminary research suggests that fintech platforms may be covering a wider access to credit and enhance the way our Indian youths borrow or use financial services, particularly for those who may have been facing difficulty in accessing the sources of credit through the traditional lending channels such as traditional banks, money lenders, friends/ family etc. However, there may also be wider risks associated with fintech lending, such as high interest rates, documentations, threat and other predatory lending practices, which policymakers and financial institutions need to address before offering the ease of finance to the Indian youths.

Furthermore, we would like to continue this research in order to fully understand the impact of fintech on the borrowing capacity of Indian youths in current era and find new ways how the way of borrowing can differ, as well as to identify any potential risks or unintended consequences of these platforms is also a big concern. This research can help inform policy decisions and to regulatory frameworks that promote financial inclusion in India and who are responsible for borrowing practices among India and who are responsible on how finance can be used without money laundering or any malpractices. Ultimately, by supporting the development of a healthy and sustainable fintech lending ecosystem in India, policymakers, financial institutions, and consumers can work together to promote economic growth and prosperity for all and achieve the benchmark to make India a trillion-dollar economy.

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COMPARATIVE STUDY ON IMPACT OF DIGITAL WALLETS ON GEN Y AND GEN Z IN BANGALORE

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Abstract

India is making significant progress in the digital revolution with growing number of smartphone users, and the increasing popularity of mobile internet applications the establishment of more Digital wallets is becoming prevalent with the advancement of technology, Internet access, which is already widespread among both urban and rural populations in India, is currently at its highest point and continues to increase. As the COVID-19 pandemic intensifies, the Indian government is taking measures to promote contactless payments due to concerns among people that physical money could transmit the novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2). Hence Indians post pandemic intends to shift to e-wallet. Digital payments are currently making waves. Digital wallets have tremendous potential in the e-commerce market. An increasing number of users are favoring E-Wallet transactions over cash payments. However, the use of digital wallets has never been completely accepted and a matter of concern. The widespread use of digital wallets as a payment method encourages impulse buying. The objectives of this research are to investigate whether there are variances in Continuance Intention between gen Y, and gen Z consumers when utilizing digital wallets, to validate the impact of anterior variables on Continuance Intention, and to assess whether there are disparities in these earlier variables among gen Y and gen Z consumers in the usage of digital wallets. The research methodology included an online survey among Generation Z and Y. To gather information on their usage patterns of Digital wallets across various generations, the effects of COVID-19 on E-wallet usage, and whether certain E-wallet app characteristics are likely to influence impulse buying behavior. This is a field where there is a lack of empirical research.

Key words: Digital wallet, Impulsive buying, Behavioral intension, Technology acceptance.

Introduction

Financial technology, or FinTech as it is more often known, is one of the technological advances that can be claimed to have changed the world. People can readily access the financial services provided since technology is integrated into the financial system. Additionally, FinTech delivers efficiency to the general people by utilising readily available technologies like cellphones (Leng, S. Y., Talib, A. & Gunardi, A., 2018). With the increase in usage of smart phone and rapid change in technology the use of digital wallets has increased rapidly in today's generation. An e-wallet is a piece of equipment that is also accepted as a digital wallet. A software programme known as a "e-wallet" allows users to conduct online transactions and pay online using computers or mobile devices (Uduji, J.I., Okolo-Obasi, E.N., & Asongu, S.A. ,2019). With the advent of QR code mobile payment technology, the use of mobile wallets began to rise right once, with small-scale transactions driving the usage growth (Agarwal, Sumit, Wenlan Qian, Bernard Y. Yeung, and Xin Zou. 2019). By scanning the QR code with the appropriate app, they can make the payment for their purchases (Kolondaisamy, Raenu & Subaramaniam, Kasthuri. , 2020). During the Covid19 lockdown period, the use of electronic transactions significantly expanded in order to reduce the number of physical visits to bank branches across the nation (Oliver-Balch, 2020). Digital wallets support the expansion of the Indian digital economy, company competitiveness, and national income. The Indian government has started the UPI campaign to encourage Indians to use digital wallets in order to take advantage of these advantages. Positive public reaction to the UPI applications increased Indians' use of digital wallets. The growing cashless system in India has made a significant impact on consumer purchasing habits. As more payment options are available online, consumers are more inclined to make impulsive purchases (Narang, R., Sharma, R., & Tiwari, S. ,2017). The COVID-19 epidemic has caused a further increase in the electronic wallet (E-walletpenetration)'s rate (X. M. Loh, V. H. Lee, T. S. Hew, and B. Lin ,2022)

Literature review

UTAUT Model

In recent years, the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) model has been applied in various industries to examine the adoption and usage of technology for organizational improvement. With technology becoming more prevalent for personal use, the UTAUT model has been adapted to include additional factors such as hedonic motivation, habit formation, perceived value, and enjoyment in order to better understand technology adoption in these contexts (C. Kim, Li, and Kim 2015). The unified theory of acceptance and use of technology model interprets how an individual adapts and uses the technology and what is the behavioral pattern while using it. The model is composed of four constructs: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) has been revised and updated with the UTAUT model, which aims to clarify how technology acceptance impacts people's behavioral patterns. (Venkatesh et al. 2016).

Adoption of Digital wallets by different generations

Male and female users are similar in terms of digital wallet usage. The requirements and perception of both the genders are one and the same (Rathore, 2016). However, the adaptation of digital wallets differs from generation to generation, Millennials or Gen Y, adaptation of digital wallet was not difficult for them. Ease of use, perceived satisfaction, usefulness, Trust are few variables that drive a great level of positive attitude towards Digital wallets (Menon, M. M., & Ramakrishnan, H. S., 2019). Though Millennials have a factor of perceived risk and believe there is a possibility of personal data insecurity in digital payments (Soelasih, Y., 2022). Gen Y accepts new technology much faster than earlier generations; the new technology must make life simple and transactions quick for Generation Y. As this generation has understood and adapted to the digital environment well enough to negate problems like lack of trust and the incapacity to conduct digital transactions, elements like self-efficacy and trust may not have substantial influence on behavioral intentions (Trivedi, J. 2016). On the other hand, Gen Z was born with a smartphone in hand compared to Millennials (37%), Gen Z relies on technology more heavily (44%) Generation Z will impact traditional financial institutions' offerings by anticipating the future of mobile-based services (Vahrenkamp, 2017). So, this makes adaptation of e-wallet easy for this generation, according to Nur, Triasesiarta, and Rosinta Ria Panggabean (2021) Performance Expectancy, Social Influences, Facilitating Conditions, Perceived Enjoyment, and Trust significantly affect Generation Z's Behavioral Intention to adopt mobile payment services.

Digital wallet on impulse buying

Online impulse buying is triggered by an unexpected, frequently strong, and persistent want to make an instant, impulsive, and rapid purchase (Rook, Dennis W., and Robert J. Fisher 1995). Perceived enjoyment positively influences impulse buying, and perceived involvement with digital wallets significantly predicts impulse purchases of a product, Perceived enjoyment can be attained by using an e-wallet (Lee, Yi Yong, Chin Lay Gan, and Tze Wei Liew. 2022). Online shopping which has increased significantly post COVID-19 pandemic, shows a favourable and significant relationship between impulse purchases and online purchases and with the ease of payment during the payment gateway via e-wallet indicates online shopping and e-wallet were positively correlated with impulse buying (Sari, R. K., Utama, S. P., & Zairina, A. 2021).

OBJECTIVE OF STUDY

- To identify and compare the factors influencing the users of GEN Z, Y to use E-wallet in Bangalore.
- To identify difficulties in using Digital wallets among these generations.
- To identify if Digital wallets influence impulsive buying behavior among GEN Z and GEN Y
- To identify how often this fintech service is used by users in day-to-day activities.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research problem can be approached systematically using research methodology. It can be viewed as a science that studies how scientific research is conducted. To do our study we have adopted exploratory research design. The Primary Data is collected through questionnaire Method. Through the various processes that the exploratory research involves are:

- Research Design - Exploratory
- Data Source - Primary & Secondary data
- Research Instrument - Questionnaire
- Sample Plan – Usage of E-wallet Application (Paytm, Phonepe, google pay etc.)
- Sample Size – 110 customers (55 from each generation)
- Sampling Procedure - Non-Probability Sampling
- Sampling Methodology - Personal Survey

Limitations

Major limitation of this study is the sample size which is limited to few areas of Bengaluru only. Most of the users still hesitate to fill survey form on digital wallets because they have security issues hence collecting data from Gen Y is tough. This research method is based on survey method which has its own limitations.

FINDINGS

Demographic representation of both generation

Table1

Age of 25-40 (Gen Y)			
Gender	Occupation	Total	Percentage
Female	Buisness woman	2	4%
	Employee	6	12%
	Housewife	2	4%
	Student	4	8%
Male	Buisnessman	7	14%
	Employee	19	38%
	Student	10	20%
Grand Total		50	100%

Table2

Age of 18-24 (Gen Z)			
Gender	Occupation	Total	Percentage
Female	Employee	4	7%
	Student	16	27%
Male	Employee	5	8%
	Student	34	58%
Grand Total		59	100%

Table 1 and represents the demographic profile of our GEN Y respondents (n=50) where males are 36 and females are 14. Among the 50 respondents, 70% of respondents are males whose occupations are male students 20%, male employees 38%, and male businessmen 14%. In contrast, 30% of respondents are females among which 8% females are students, 12% are employees, 4% are female Businesswomen, and 4% are housewives. Table 2 and figure2 represents the demographic profile of our GEN Z respondents (n=59) where males are 39 and females are 20.

Among the 59 respondents, 66% of respondents are males of which the majority are students i.e. 58% and the minority are employees i.e. 8%. In contrast, 34% of respondents are females among which 27% females are students and 7% are employees.

Respondents knowledge about Functionality of Digital wallets

Particulars	GEN Y		GEN Z	
	No. of person	Percentage	No. of person	Percentage
No	15	30%	20	34%
Yes	35	70%	39	66%
Grand total	50	100%	59	100%

Table 3

Based on table 3, the results clearly reflect that among gen Y 66% of the total respondents are well aware of the functionality of the Digital Wallets and use it for day to day transaction but 34% of Gen Z are still unaware of the functionality of Digital wallets. Among Gen Y 70% of the respondents are aware of the functionality of the Digital wallets and use them for day-to-day transactions, while 30% of Gen Y still don't use Digital wallets.

Most Used Digital Wallets in Bengaluru City

Particulars	GEN Y		GEN Z	
	No. of person	Percentage	No. of person	Percentage
Gpay	14	40%	22	58%
Paytm	8	23%	8	21%
Phonepay	7	20%	5	13%
Multiple wallets	5	14%	3	8%
Grand Total	35	100%	38	100%

Table 4

Figure 1

As shown in table 4 and figure 1, Gpay is the most used E-wallet in Bangalore among both GEN Y and GEN Z with the highest usage being 40% and 58% respectively. Gpay is an app by google which is trusted by both generations as it has a clean and easy UI for transactions and offers many coupon rewards after completing a certain number of transactions. Paytm comes in second place for both generations with the usage of 23% among GEN Y and 21% among GEN Z. Paytm was the e-wallet that got most popular after demonetization in India as it lets us store our

money in which we can pay for goods and services from various merchants. Then comes phonepay for which the usage is 20% among GEN Y and 13% among GEN Z. Both generations also prefer to use multiple wallets to make payments as they might want to avail different benefits offered by different apps data, with the usage being 14% among GEN Y whereas only 8% among GEN Z uses multiple wallets.

Analysis the reasons behind the Demand of Digital Wallets among respondents

Table 5

Particulars	GEN Y		GEN Z	
	No. of person	Percentage	No. of person	Percentage
Easy to use	22	63%	23	59%
Cashless	8	23%	9	23%
Social Influence	2	6%	0	0%
High availability	2	6%	4	10%
Rewards	1	3%	3	8%
Grand Total	35	100%	39	100%

Figure 2

Table 5 and figure 2 represents the analysis of why do both the generation prefer to use digital wallets. The survey shows that 63% of respondents of Gen Y find digital wallets easy to use and hence, prefer to use them whereas 59% of respondents of GEN Z find digital wallets easy to use. The main difference between both generations is due to social influence and having a fear of not going hand in hand with technology since everyone around them uses digital wallets with 6% for GEN Y. But this is not the case with GEN Z as they are not socially influenced by others for using digital wallets. There is not much difference in the availability of digital wallets and the rewards factor being the reason for why both generations prefer to use digital wallets.

Primary reasons for using digital wallets:

Table 6

Particulars	GEN Y		GEN Z	
	No. of person	Percentage	No. of person	Percentage
Traditional Shopping	1	3%	1	3%

Online shopping	6	17%	3	8%
Utility bill payments	3	9%	2	5%
Movie tickets	1	3%	1	3%
All of the above	24	69%	32	82%
Grand Total	35	100%	39	100%

Figure 3

Table 6 and figure 3 depicts the analysis of the main purpose of using Digital wallets by our respondents. The survey shows that 68% of respondents of GEN Y are using Digital Wallets to do all their tasks, i.e., Traditional Shopping, online shopping, Utility bill payments, and Movie tickets, whereas 82% of GEN Z use digital wallets to do all their tasks, i.e., Traditional Shopping, Online shopping, Utility bill payments, and Movie tickets, which is 14% more than GEN Y. A main difference between both generations found in this survey is that 17% of GEN Y uses digital wallets for making payments for online shopping and 8% of GEN Y uses digital wallets for making payments for online shopping, the purchasing power of GEN Y is more than GEN Z as most of the GEN Y are employed and financially independent. Rest all the reasons for using digital wallets among both generations are the same.

No. of respondents using digital wallets before pandemic:

Table 7

Particulars	GEN Y		GEN Z	
	No. of person	Percentage	No. of person	Percentage
Yes, I have been using Digital wallets pre-pandemic	29	83%	21	54%
No, I'm using Digital wallets post-pandemic	6	17%	18	46%

Grand Total	35	100%	39	100%
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Figure 4

Table 7 and figure 4 is showing the analysis of whether Digital wallets app has been used by respondents before covid-19 pandemic. The survey shows a major difference in this segment as 83% of respondents of GEN Y were using digital wallets before the pandemic but only 54% of respondents of GEN Z were using digital wallets before the pandemic. The rest 46% of GEN Z started using digital wallets post-pandemic and the reason for this might be that many of the GEN Z didn't reach their legal age pre-pandemic and were not able to use them. Also, covid-19 was one of the factors which forced GEN Z to use digital wallets.

Respondents frequency of using digital wallets after the pandemic (in a week)

Table 8

Particulars	GEN Y		GEN Z	
	No. of person	Percentage	No. of person	Percentage
2-5 times	8	23%	14	36%
6-10 times	8	23%	8	21%
More than 10 times	18	51%	17	44%
Grand Total	35	100%	39	100%

Figure 5

Table 8 and figure 5 is showing the analysis of how many times in a week they use digital wallets. The survey shows that respondents of both generations majorly use digital wallets 2-5 times a week which is 57% among GEN Z and 45% among GEN Y. Hence, there is a difference that GEN Y majorly uses digital wallets more than 10 times when compared to GEN Z which is 12% more and 5% of respondents of GEN Z still uses digital wallets only once in a week which is nil in case of GEN Y.

Different kinds of Problems Faced by respondents:

PARTICULARS	GEN Y		GEN Z	
	No. of person	Percentage	No. of person	Percentage
Technical problem	20	40%	24	41%
Reckless spending habits	9	18%	16	27%
Don't know how to use it	7	14%	2	3%
Lack of internet	7	14%	8	14%
Security risk	7	14%	9	15%
Grand Total	50	100%	59	100%

Table 9

Figure 6

Table 9 and figure 6 is showing the analysis of kind of problem faced by respondents of both the generation while using digital wallets. The survey shows that both GEN Y and GEN Z majorly face is technical problems which account for 40% of total respondents. The major difference seen in this analysis is that still 14% of respondents of GEN Y don't know how to use digital wallets which is only 3% in the case of GEN Z. GEN Z grew up with technology all around them, and hence, it is very easy for them to learn such things which is not the case with GEN Y. Rest there is no significant difference in problems faced by both the generation.

Particulars	GEN Y		GEN Z	
	No. of person	Percentage	No. of person	Percentage
Digital payments only	17	34%	16	27%
Cash only	5	10%	3	5%
Both	28	56%	40	68%
Grand Total	50	100%	59	100%

Table 10

Figure 7

Table 10 and figure 7 is showing the analysis of the choice of considering digital wallets for their future transaction. The survey shows that 34% of respondents of GEN Y will prefer to use digital wallets only for their future

transactions, and 27% of respondents of GEN Z would like to do digital payments only for future transactions. Other than this, 10% of respondents of GEN Y chose to use cash only in the future, whereas only 5% of respondents of GEN Z will prefer to use cash in the future for making payments. The rest of the 56% of respondents of GEN Y will be using both digital wallets and cash which is less compared to GEN Z, i.e., 68% of them opt for both digital wallets and cash for their future payments.

Analysis of Impulsive buying

Table 11

Statements GEN Y	Strongly disagree	disagree	neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
While using digital wallet, you buy items you had not really intended on buying	10	5	11	4	5
you make payments instantly using E-wallet without having a second thought of buying the product or service	5	11	8	6	5
If you see a discount price, you intend to buy impulsively using Digital wallets	2	7	9	6	11
you spend more than your budget while using Digital wallets	9	10	6	5	5

Table 12

Statements of GEN Z	Strongly disagree	disagree	neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
While using digital wallet, you buy items you had not really intended on buying	5	5	6	8	15
you make payments instantly using E-wallet without having a second thought of buying the product or service	5	6	10	6	12
If you see a discount price, you intend to buy impulsively using Digital wallets	7	5	11	6	10
you spend more than your budget while using Digital wallets	2	5	10	10	12

Figure 10

Table 11,12 and figure 10 is showing the analysis of Digital wallets promoting impulsive buying. The survey shows that 9 users of Gen Y strongly disagree that they don't spend more than their budget, 10 of such users disagree with this statement and only 5 users strongly agree with it, rest 3 users neither agree nor disagree with the statement. But when this generation sees any discount or sale they tend to spend more impulsively making rational payments via digital wallets. Overall, they don't make any rational purchases and think wisely before making digital payments.

The survey also shows that 12 users of Gen Z strongly agree that they spend more than their budget and 10 users agree with the same. Only 2 users strongly disagree and 5 disagree with this statement, rest 5 neither agree nor disagree with this. They also purchase impulsively during sales or discounts as 10 users totally agree with it, and 7 totally disagree with it. Overall, Gen Z makes rational payments without giving a second thought to it which leads to purchasing items they have not intended to. Hence Gen Z is inclined towards impulsive buying via digital wallets.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the ease of online payment in this busy age has greatly fueled the growth of the e-wallet. When making payments, all generations use digital wallets equally. Because of social pressure, only a small portion of Gen Y clients use digital wallets, which is not the viewpoint of Gen Z. Gen Y majorly uses digital wallets pre-pandemic, but there are few customers among Gen Y who doesn't know how to use digital wallets which is almost negligible in case of Gen Z. Although both generations use digital wallets, Gen Z is more inclined to impulsive purchasing as they pay impulsively using digital wallets, whereas Gen Y is completely the opposite since they are not influenced by digital wallets for impulsive buying and only make impulsive payments when they see a sale or an offer because it results in financial savings, hence Gen Z should also make mindful purchases instead of impulsive purchases to avoid unnecessary expenses. Even though technological advances exist, yet many customers prefer paying with cash as they might perceive it to be safer than an electronic wallet. This perspective might be more prevalent for Gen Y in comparison to Gen Z. Pros and cons existing for every existing thing. As responsible users, we must exercise good judgement and be informed thoroughly about the E-wallet we use.

Future Implication

In paving future directions in the context of digital wallet, this study recommends future researchers to do additional studies by broadening the research location and increasing the number of samples. As the usage of digital wallets have been increased, people tend to stay at home and transact online after the pandemic. Furthermore, additional research can be conducted on other generations, such as generation X and comparing the impact of gen X with other generation as gen X is the generation not born in technological era so it might be difficult for them to adapt to digital wallets. In order to compare the findings of this study with other theories and statistical methods, researchers and other parties can gain a deeper understanding of the variables that affect consumer intentions, consumer impulsive buying more specifically, consumer behavior to utilize digital payment systems.

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THE SWAY OF YOUTUBE ADVERTISING ON ATTITUDINAL FACTORS OF GENERATION Z IN PURCHASE INTENTION

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Social media plays a major role in marketing, it has set a benchmark for marketing strategies and there is tremendous growth and response from mass to social media marketing. YouTube is the largest online video digital channel, where millions of people view content advertised, it's a massive medium of communication and it influences Generation Z to a greater extent. The major objective of this article is to find the influence of YouTube advertising on the attitudinal factors of Generation Z consumers. A sample of 120 responses from Generation Z consumers in Bengaluru urban city of Karnataka in India was collected to find the influence and analyze their attitude changes. However, previous studies have proved that there is a positive attitude among Generation Z toward YouTube advertising. The young consumer's attitude is crucial to understand and what factors of YouTube advertising are impactful on Generation Z needs to be explored and identified. According to the study, 99% of Gen Z watch YouTube every day. Positive attitudes towards products and services, such as awareness, liking, and preference, have a big impact on consumer purchase intention.

Keywords: YouTube advertising, Attitudinal factors, Generation Z, Purchase intention.

1. Introduction

Social media is an interactive computer-mediated functional science that facilitates the contribution of information, ideas, and interests, through virtual communities and networks. The term "Social Media" refers to a variety of applications such as (Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn, and YouTube) and websites that connect individuals to exchange information and raise awareness of any event through social networking. Since the start of the twenty-first century, social media has been widely used. Globally, information technology (IT) has changed how people connect and created utterly unique opportunities. Social media helped to create a global village. Users can connect with one another in an instant of seconds and exchange ideas.

In 2005, YouTube shared its first video and has since grown day by day. As of 2023, **467 million** users and India is the largest country to have this many viewers. Generation Z dominates this user count and makes up the majority of both users and viewers. The fact that YouTube has grown to be not simply a platform for influencers but also a significant source of revenue for Google and its parent firm Alphabet is not surprising given the size of the world's YouTube audience. YouTube contributed more than 29 billion dollar worth of global advertising revenue to Google in 2022, or around 11.35 percent of the company's overall revenue.

Three recent research revealed that YouTube advertising on mobile devices caused Millennials to have more favourable cognitive, affective, and/or behavioral attitudes, but they did not take the Generation Z group into account. Hence, the study takes this into consideration.

The study on Youtube is necessary as Marketers predict an increase in the use of YouTube for advertising in the upcoming years despite the fact that it is more expensive to do so compared to other social media platforms. In this study, we focus on finding the influence of Youtube marketing impact on the attitude of Generation Z, and what factors influence them positively towards purchase intention. The three attitudinal stages awareness, liking, and preference are examined.

2. Literature review:

2.1. Youtube advertising:

Although Generation Z frequently uses YouTube, a significant advertising channel, it is unknown how well these advertisements actually reach and influence them. Due to greater information transparency than earlier generations, the Z generation is known for having a higher level of skepticism They also exhibit some resistance to

advertisements, choosing to ignore them or block them using third-party software. (Pagefair, 2015; eMarketer, 2015; Bolton et al., 2013).

Reaching users through YouTube is made more challenging by their relatively high resistance to traditional push advertising and their skepticism towards advertising in general. However, this is not the only barrier to effective YouTube marketing; many viewers simply ignore advertising on YouTube. Approximately 80% of all skippable YouTube commercials are done so by users. (Pagefair, 2015)

Soukup (2014) concentrated on the use of social media, particularly YouTube. He claims that YouTube is a sizable platform with a variety of uses, including advertising, archive work, education, entertainment, news reporting, political communication, the arts and cultures, religion, medicine, the military, fandom, interpersonal communication, and observation. The author contends that communication theories will need to be reconfigured in order to analyze this platform, which is always changing because it is so diverse.

Soukup (2014) explicitly states that a new study is required on the platform and that theory needs to be modified in light of what this medium delivers after analyzing previous research on the YouTube site. Despite being relatively young, online video advertising is a crucial component of Google's YouTube monetization strategy.

Previous studies have shown that a variety of elements might affect an advertisement's efficacy. Three of these criteria are particularly pertinent to influencer marketing on YouTube, Ad attitude, (Dehghani et al, 2016; MacKenzie, Lutz & Belch, 1986), purchase intention (Dehghani et al, 2016; MacKenzie & Lutz, 1989; Lee & Hong, 2016; Ott, Vafeiadis, Kumble & Wadell, 2016) and Perceived entertainment.

The widespread use of smartphones and other mobile multimedia devices, which are primarily used for viewing videos, posting pictures, instant messaging, playing online games, entertainment, social connection, seeking information, and generally perceiving the world, has helped Generation Z display the highest levels of sophistication. In emerging countries, smartphone ownership has steadily increased, particularly among younger customers.

This study seeks to ascertain young consumer attitudes towards Youtube advertising and to examine the impact of Youtube advertising on usage and demographic variables on the Generation Z cohort's attitudes in Bangalore city.

2.2. Attitudinal stages

2.2.1. Awareness

According to Corbett and Durfee (2004), the media can represent, convey, and help the community understand important educational information. Social media platforms like Facebook, Youtube, Instagram, Twitter, and blogs are another way to get news, and distributing information to a larger group is the most popular and quick communication medium (Hamid et al., 2017; Irwin et al., 2012; Kimmons, 2014).

Youtube advertising tries to create awareness among viewers about new products or existing products. Two views are connected to behavioural change while raising awareness. According to the first viewpoint, increasing people's knowledge of a subject and encouraging acceptable attitudes leads to a shift in behaviour. According to the second point of view, people should evaluate their options methodically before acting in a way that will help the economy (McKenzie-Mohr, 2000). By regularly associating a stimulus with other stimuli of either positive or negative valence, awareness can influence an attitude through evaluative conditioning (Sweldens, Corneille, and Yzerbyt, 2014).

2.2.2. Liking

In order to follow consumers' progress through the purchase decision process, several advertising models were created. However, traditional advertising was utilized to determine the relationship between like and preference in the construction of these response hierarchy models. Since social media and other online ICT platforms have grown rapidly over the past ten years, academia and advertising practitioners are increasingly interested in how traditional advertising models relate to marketing on social media.

According to Nalewajek and Macik, (2013), social media-induced behavioural changes can alter attitudes towards responsible consumption. However, they noted that there was a lack of research that quantitatively analyzed online video advertising among young consumers in both developing and developed economies. Arajo et al.(2017) discovered that Brazilians liked YouTube videos with advertising more than Americans (US) and Britons (UK) did.

According to Duffet, et al, (2019), liking has a significantly favourable effect on preference owing to YouTube advertising among Millennials and liking has a significantly larger positive effect on preference by Millennial respondents who watched 1–5 YouTube advertisements. The studies revealed that there is a positive association between liking and preference.

2.2.3. Preference

According to Bolton et al. and Zambodla, younger cohorts are heterogeneous because older cohort members are more likely to have different psychographic characteristics, lifestyles, attitudes, values, needs, interests, preferences, and desires from younger cohort members. They are also more likely to consume media differently than younger cohort members. Sharma emphasizes that additional research should examine young cohorts Ad in terms of various social media platform formats across various age groups.

AAPIS model and Aspinwall's consumer acceptance theory have also emphasized the importance of preference as a mediator between cognitive and behavioural attitudinal responses.

Around the world, Generation Z has many similar traits and characteristics, yet developing countries typically have less developed digital ICT infrastructure than industrialized countries, which could lead to different attitudes because of worsening social and economic conditions. There is additionally a significant difference in access to online platforms and wealth in many developing nations.

According to Duffet, et al, (2019), Preference can create an impact on the attitude of young consumers toward a product or service. Awareness and liking are interconnected in influencing preference creation and creating a positive attitude on the advertisement on Youtube.

2.3. Purchase Intention

A number of organizations also use YouTubers, testimonies, influencers, and celebrity endorsers (who frequently have millions of impressionable young followers) to spread good news and support the organizations via their YT channels. According to several studies, YouTubers strongly impact their younger followers' purchasing decisions and have a significant favourable association with them.

Mir and Rehman recommend that businesses use YouTubers to advertise their products by inserting commercials into YT since younger generations tend to find UGC more credible. Rasmussen discovered that American college students were inclined to purchase items recommended by YouTubers. According to Sokolova and Kefi, among French Generation Z and Y respondents, influencers on YouTube and Instagram are associated favourably with buy intentions due to their trustworthiness and parasocial activity. According to Hwang et al., Chinese consumers' purchasing intentions are positively impacted by parasocial celebrity contacts on social media. Therefore, it is advised that businesses utilize YouTubers more frequently to promote their products in order to have a favourable impact on consumers' behavioural and attitude responses. YouTubers are not only more affordable than traditional celebrities, but they also have a larger following.

According to Duffet, et al, (2019), youtube advertising has a positive impact on awareness, liking and preferences have an impact on consumer purchase intention.

The Generation Z attitude is unpredictable because of competitive technological advancements and emerging trends, it becomes important to study the attitudinal changes of Generation Z to predict and make digital advertising an effective means of creating an impact on consumer purchase intention

3. Conceptual model:

4. methodology:

The research adopts a quantitative method. The recent articles from reputed journals are studied and analyzed. A survey questionnaire was framed, and 5 point Likert scale is used for measuring variables. The questionnaire was circulated to the different student groups aged between 18-24. 120 responses were collected. The study involves simple methods of analysis like pie charts and Bar-graph to represent and analyze the statements of questions.

5. Finding and discussion

5.1 Chart depicting gender of respondents

There are 62 female respondents and 58 male respondents

5.2 Chart depicting age of respondents

Age in years
120 responses

The respondent's age groups are as follows

- 18 years – 24 respondents
- 19 years – 51 respondents
- 20 years – 39 respondents
- 21 years – 6 respondents

5.3 119 respondents out of 120, said they use the social media platform youtube

Do you use social media platform YouTube?
120 responses

5.4

Have you ever watched a full advertisement video in YouTube?

120 responses

111 respondents have mentioned that they watch full-length advertisement videos on youtube

Do you like watching Video advertisements in YouTube?

120 responses

5.4

106 respondents have mentioned that they like watching video advertisements in youtube.

5.5

After watching an advertisement how do you react to it?

120 responses

The majority of the respondents' have mentioned that the reaction after watching youtube advertisements is ignoring the advertisement or getting annoyed by the interruption. very few people do research and consider the product or service. Purchases of the product by watching the advertisements are considerably very less.

5.6

How frequently do you log on for the YouTube?
 120 responses

The majority of the respondents have mentioned that their log-on frequency of youtube is on daily basis
 5.7

How many YouTube Advertising channels have you subscribed for?
 120 responses

The majority of the users subscribe for 1-2 channels of advertisement and very few respondents have subscribed for 5-6 channels.

5.8.1. Chart depicting AWARENESS of youtube advertising

AWARENESS

Table depicting awareness of youtube advertising

ITEMS MEASURED	STRONGLY AGREE	AGREE	NEUTRAL	DISAGREE	STRONGLY DISAGREE
Youtube advertising is effective in creating awareness of brands	26	69	20	3	2
Youtube advertising alerts me to new company offerings	9	72	28	7	4
I am aware of youtube advertising now	15	66	28	9	2
Youtube advertising gets attention from certain brands	12	56	31	11	10

The study reveals that Youtube advertising is considered to be an effective way of creating awareness. it alerts about new company offerings, and also people follow youtube advertisements of their favourite brands.

5.8.2. Chart depicting LIKING of youtube advertising

LIKING

Table depicting LIKING of youtube advertising

ITEMS MEASURED	STRONGLY AGREE	AGREE	NEUTRAL	DISAGREE	STRONGLY DISAGREE
Youtube advertising has made me like the brands	6	32	50	23	9
Youtube advertising adds to the enjoyment of using Youtube	3	17	31	41	28
Youtube advertising is likable and pleasant	1	20	47	36	16
Youtube advertising is entertaining and fun	4	17	43	36	16
Youtube advertising has a positive influence on me	3	27	54	25	11
Youtube advertising has made me like the products more	2	32	47	29	10

The study reveals Youtube advertising has a positive influence on Generation Z, though it is not entertaining and fun for majority of consumers but it creates a liking impact on consumers about the products advertised.

5.8.3. Chart depicting PREFERENCE of youtube advertising

PREFERENCE

Table depicting PREFERENCE of youtube advertising

ITEMS MEASURED	STRONGLY AGREE	AGREE	NEUTRAL	DISAGREE	STRONGLY DISAGREE
I look for products that are advertised on Youtube	5	28	48	30	9
Youtube advertising is relevant to me and my interests	7	33	39	34	7
Ads on Youtube are effective in stimulating my preference in brands	2	28	42	32	11
Youtube advertising is effective in gaining my interest in products	7	42	36	25	10
I prefer brands that are promoted on youtube	8	22	37	37	16
Youtube advertising has a positive effect on my preference for brands	5	25	43	34	13

The Study reveals Youtube advertisements are relevant to user’s interest, and they have a positive impact on stimulating preference. Generation Z agrees that Youtube advertising has an effective in gaining interest in products advertised in youtube.

5.8.4. Chart depicting **PURCHASE INTENTION** of youtube advertising

PURCHASE INTENTION

4. Table depicting **PURCHASE INTENTION** of youtube advertising

ITEMS MEASURED	STRONGLY AGREE	AGREE	NEUTRAL	DISAGREE	STRONGLY DISAGREE
I will buy products that are advertised on youtube in the near future	4	23	49	33	11
I desire to buy products that are promoted on youtube	3	24	46	33	14
Youtube advertising increases the purchase intention of featured brands	7	49	43	16	5
I would buy products that are advertised on youtube if I had the money	8	33	33	31	15

The Study shows that youtube advertising has a positive impact on purchase intention, whereas purchasing power and youtube advertisements together can have highly effective positive responses among Generation Z, as the majority of them are students.

6. Conclusion and discussion

Numerous social media- and YouTube-related studies have established that longer durations were associated with the most favorable Millennial and Generation Z sentiments. However, some research found that younger generations' shorter log-on times yielded more advantageous results. However, other studies found no differences that were significantly related to young consumers' use of social media and/or YouTube advertising. Furthermore, a survey found that Millennials who spent between one and three hours had higher favourable sentiments toward YouTube advertising.

According to the research, Youtube advertising is seen as a powerful tool for raising awareness because it informs consumers about fresh product offers from businesses and also works to increase brand awareness among users. The study finds that, despite not being amusing or enjoyable for most of them, Youtube advertising has a beneficial impact on Generation Z and makes them like the offered products. According to the study, YouTube adverts are

relevant to users' interests and have a positive effect on influencing user preference. Generation Z acknowledges that YouTube advertising has a significant role in generating interest in the things that are promoted.

Instead of being influenced by YouTube advertising, Generation Z's purchase intentions are determined by their purchasing ability and affordability. Further research can be conducted on YouTube advertising, with a diversified population and demographic conditions that can give insights.

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“INCLUSIVE INNOVATION: EXPLORING HOW DEI AND TALENT RING-FENCING WORK TOGETHER IN ORGANIZATIONS”

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ABSTRACT

The topic Diversity, not being a new phrase in today's business environment, has created a lot of buzz in the corporate level. The fact that many companies are struggling to achieve the same has created some complications in the operations of the business. This just makes the word Diversity more complicated. Similarly, the concept of Inclusion does not need to be feared or complicated. Things just need to happen according to the strategies that have been planned out for the success of the business. The purpose of this paper is to give an insight on the topic Diversity, Inclusion and Equity along with some inputs on the concept of Ring Fencing of Talent. This paper also gives a comprehensive model on the same which has been sourced from several secondary data and research articles.

Keywords: Diversity, Inclusion, Equity, Ring-Fencing of Talent.

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Diversity; as the word suggests, “Diverse”, as such is not some new phrase or a phenomenon that has hit the business environment in the recent years where companies have been striving to implement the new policies popularly known as DEI Policy to attract and retain talent and have a better pool of diverse people to promote employee branding. Though there is no statutory requirement, companies have considered the same very important. The fast-paced business environment has opened opportunities for other countries, and this is interlinked with the concept of globalization, where there is an increase in the expectation of social justice and ethical practices that needs to be infused for the benefit of the company, employees, and the society. Equity refers to fair and reasonable practises and regulations that support the well-being of all members of the community. Equity differs from equality. Equality assumes that everyone's experiences are identical. Being equitable entails understanding and correcting historical and contemporary structural imbalances that benefit some and probably harming others. Equal treatment will result in equality only when everyone has equal access to opportunity.

Ring fencing is a method of preventing some personnel from being made redundant or redeployed during a time of organizational change. This may be accomplished by gathering these personnel and ensuring that they are considered for any appropriate alternative responsibilities within the organisation. Ring fence can also be utilised to safeguard personnel who are deemed important to the running of the organisation. Irrespective of the relevance of the person's role in the changed organizational structure, they would be considered key players in running the business and be protected.

1.2 THEORIES RELATED TO DIVERSITY, EQUITY, AND INCLUSIVITY

There are several ideas that are pertinent to the problem of managing diversity in the workplace. These points of view seek to explain how diversity may be useful or destructive in organisational contexts. The cognitive diversity hypothesis proposes that varied ideas arising from cultural variations across groups and people in organisations can result in creative problem solving and innovation.

- The Social theory brings out the negative effects that diversity can have in a group or an organization. Some people may go to the extent of categorizing people based on caste, creed, region, religion, race etc. An example is when a recruiter sorts through resumes and engages in gender categorization because the person's name provides information about their sex which probably might interest the hiring manager.

- The term diversity has both effects on the organization i.e., positive, and negative. The cognitive diversity hypothesis tells that we need to have a group of diverse people from different background to get better ideas and be innovative in the long run. But on the contrary, diverse groups leads to increased absenteeism, higher turnover among the employees and several others as a result for the same.
- Schema Theory tells that people grab certain point of their interest about the opposite personality and store the same creating a Schema in the brain. Hence, employees develop schemas based on certain criteria like caste, creed, race, religion etc. which can be both negative and positive at the same time as mentioned earlier.

1.3 OBJECTIVES OF THE PAPER

1. To examine the challenge and the opportunities using DEI and ring fencing at the workplace. (the potential Benefits using the approaches)
2. To explore the relationship between DEI and ring fencing. How can DEI be used to inform the decision of whether to ring fence employees?

1.3.1 Challenges faced in Implementing DEI in a Company.

DEI (diversity, equity, and inclusion) must be prioritized at every level of an organization if it is to improve corporate culture, employee morale, and overall growth. However, a DEI program needs more than simply a verbal commitment to be effective. A 2021 survey of company executives and staff monitoring DEI activities found a discrepancy between strategic implementation and continuous advancement. Businesses were praised for their dedication to efforts promoting diversity, equity, and inclusion in the workplace by 95% of company executives and 75% of employees. Connecting the dots while implementing DEI in companies, they face big time trouble in interlinking the dots between results and intention. But by keeping the intention of the long term goal of the company and clearly setting the parameters of performance in terms of some metrics or rubrics, companies can avoid the pitfalls in implementing DEI successfully.

Some of the barriers are:

- a. Inadequate Planning
 - b. Lack of Proper Training
 - c. Budget Restrictions
 - d. Culture Resistance
- Planning is that part of business that starts right from Day 1 of commencing of the business. Having a dynamic business environment, planning is an essential element in the business. It can be a “Make or Break” situation. An inadequate plan may be as disastrous as stepping into the unknown part of the business world.
 - Training is never a perishable resource in the corporate world. DEI training is never short in the corporate world considering the requirement. Performing a proper Training Need Analysis (TNA) is very important and the basic step in imparting training.
 - According to a recent study conducted by SHRM, Fortune 1000 Corporations release a budget between \$30,000 and \$5 Million for the DEI programmes, averaging \$1.5 Million in training. Talking to various department heads, the departments will have different requirements and the same is to be aligned to the strategies of the business in terms of achieving the long-term goal along with implementing the diversity program.
 - Cultural resistance can thwart the successful implementation of Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI) efforts. Cultural resistance refers to the attitudes, beliefs, and behaviours within an organization or society that resist or oppose efforts to promote diversity, equity, and inclusion. Fear of change, a lack of information, favouritism, and other forms of cultural resistance are all frequent. Addressing cultural resistance necessitates a thorough and continuing effort. It is critical to involve all stakeholders, including workers, executives, and external partners, in order to build a shared understanding and commitment to DEI.

1.3.2 Benefits of Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion

- a. Have better access to the Talent Pool.
- b. Financial Benefits and promotes Innovation.

- As the workforce is involving itself in a paradigm shift, DEI is becoming more evident and relevant. Businesses are embracing DE&I and discovering that they can have better access to a wide reservoir of talent. According to a recent study, 70% of job seekers consider diversity a factor in evaluating a prospective employer. That number is even higher among Gen Z job seekers.
- Companies that take its DEI seriously, have observed that Diversity in the workforce benefits both employees and employers. A variety of executive teams at a company increases the likelihood that it will beat its competitors in terms of profitability by 33% and 21%, respectively.

1.3.3 Benefits of Ring-Fencing

Ring fencing is the process in HR which protects employees during an organizational change. It involves the process of grouping employees who have not been mapped to the new position in the organizational structure after the change has been implemented.

Some of the benefits of Ring-Fencing are:

- a. Retain Key Talent
 - b. Reduced impact of Change
 - c. Objective Selection Process
- Ring-fencing ensures that workers at risk of losing their jobs are taken into consideration for open positions, which can assist maintain critical personnel within the company. Considering the excess supply of talent and shortage of skilled personnel, this would immensely benefit the organization.
 - Ring-fencing in HR can help reduce the impact of change on employees and the organization by grouping employees together and considering them for available vacancies within the new structure. This ensures the employees who are on the verge of losing their jobs will be given a new opportunity to find a suitable role change in the organization which also helps the business to maintain the continuity and minimize the disruption caused by the change.
 - The objective selection process ensures that personnel are selected based on their skills and expertise rather than personal prejudices or preferences. This ensures that the best candidate for the job is chosen, which may lead to higher productivity, work satisfaction, and staff retention. To add on to the same, an objective selection procedure can assist in lowering the danger of prejudice and legal issues.

1.3.4 Relation between Ring-Fencing and DEI

Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion can play a crucial role in ring-fencing employees. As discussed before, Ring-Fencing is a process of reserving a certain position in an organizational setup during the process of an organizational change. The term "ring-fence" is commonly used in finance and accounting to describe a virtual barrier that separates a portion of individuals or companies' financial assets from the rest.

In any given scenario where the company prefers not to have a rough transition phase and give the employees a chance to adapt to the changed business environment, we need to accept the fact that the company is ring-fencing its key employees.

For instance: A 100-Year-Old Company plans to merge with the new Company. During the strategy changing phase, the 100-year-Old company will retain a lot of employees in the name of strategy as they know the business for a long time for now.

1.4 A Conceptual Framework on Diversity, Equity and Inclusion by *Meg Meiman, Nicole E. Brown, and Alex Hodges*

The conceptual framework given in this study is intended to assist librarians and educators in developing inclusive education that accommodates learners' different needs and backgrounds. It is founded on the Universal Design for Learning (UDL) principles, which emphasise the necessity of creating education that is adaptable, accessible, and engaging for all learners, regardless of their skills or backgrounds.

This paper's methodology combines UDL concepts with three contemporary learning models: the ACRL methodology for Information Literacy, the Framework for 21st Century Learning, and the Culturally Responsive Teaching Framework. These theories offer a holistic approach to instructional design that covers the cognitive, metacognitive, emotional, attitudinal, and valuing elements of learning.

The paradigm emphasises the necessity of identifying and resolving emotional aspects of learning such as motivation, engagement, and curiosity. It also emphasises the need of librarians and educators reflecting on their own habits of mind and mentality, as well as purposefully designing tactics that correspond with the Framework's emotional aspects, notably curiosity, to promote an inclusive, supportive environment for learners.

The conceptual framework given in this research offers a versatile and comprehensive approach to constructing inclusive education that accommodates learners' different needs and backgrounds. It emphasises the significance of recognising and treating the emotional aspects of learning, and it offers librarians and educators with practical tools for creating an inclusive, supportive learning environment.

Source: “Researchers Model”

1.5 Findings and Suggestions

Ring fencing and DEI are some sensitive topics in the domain of Human Resource/Capital Management which needs to be handled with utmost care and attention. From the viewpoint of any organization focusing on the formed strategies, should never compromise on the principle of DEI or Ring-Fencing. It should just be the organization’s long-term growth in the minds while taking decisions.

In short, companies must have focus on the principle of Diversity, Equity and Inclusivity paired up with Ring Fencing undoubtedly. But when it comes to choose between the above said policies and performance, the company must be clever enough to choose performance over the policies stated above keeping the organizational goals in mind.

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TRUST & ACCOUNTABILITY: A COMPARISON OF SOCIAL MEDIA NEWS AND TRADITIONAL NEWS CHANNEL

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Abstract

People in today's modern world use social media as a source of news. With a strong impact on the public, social media has supplanted conventional media as a source of news. Emphasis was to understand the implication of trust and accountability raising out from Traditional media to social media.

It is analytical approach as the most objective of the study is to analyse the trust and accountability of the news consumed by individuals from social media. The study conducted in the Bangalore city, and data being analysed using SEM and other statistical tools.

In this study the outcome resulted which is having and managerial and academic implications viz., the study shows that a number of people use social media for the source of news, there are several factors that affect their decision. Social Media plays a very necessary role in today's life, most of them take social media as a source of news because according to them it is very convenient and easy to access the people do think that the Social media as source of news is Unfiltered, Time saving, and a Trustable source.

Key words: News, Media, Social Media, Traditional media, Age, Trust, Accountability

Introduction

Social media has made access to and exchange of news and information in written, verbal and visual form, very convenient and easy. As a result, the spread of fake news has been a growing phenomenon. Broadly, the term fake news has been referred to as propaganda, deception, manipulation, fabrication, news satire and news parody (Khaldarova & Pantti, 2016); (Tandoc et al., 2018). The convenient access to online news for free seems to be little reason to pay for a newspaper subscription. The witness of not the “End” of print but rather the adaptation of print and News organizations to rapidly changing consumer patterns and a corresponding shift in newspapers. towards digital content has brought the new media to create its impact on society at a faster pace. When we refer to social media, applications such as Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, YouTube, LinkedIn, Pinterest, and Instagram often come to mind. These applications are driven by user-generated content, and are highly influential in a myriad of settings, from purchasing/selling behaviours, entrepreneurship, political issues, to venture capitalism (Greenwood & Gopal, 2015).

Social media are computer mediated tools that allow people or companies to create, share exchange information, career interest, ideas, pictures/ virtual communities and networks (Buettner, 2017) Through Social media, people can easily exchange valuable information which can improve their career interest, ideas etc. It also helps in sending pictorial illustrations of ideas. (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010) see social media “as a group of internet-based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of web 2.0 and that allow the creation and exchange of user generated content”. (Kietzmann et al., 2011) elaborates on this, stating that “social media depends on Mobile and Web-based technologies to create highly interactive platforms through which individuals and communities share, co-create, discuss, and modify user-generated content. They introduce substantial land pervasive changes to communications between communities and individuals”. By implication, “social media is seen as the type of media that gives people a medium to create, share, and/or exchange information and ideas in communities and networks. It is also seen as the ideological and technological exchange of user-generated content”.

Traditional media of communication could refer to those media that communicate uniform messages in a one-way process to a large mass homogenous audience, all possessing much the same characteristics and interests. It deals

with traditional broadcasting, like the terrestrial television channels such as (NTA, AIT, Channels TV and radio such as TSBS, BBC, UJ Fm etc). (Asemah & Onyeka, 2012) describes traditional media of communication as “channels or technological devices through which messages are conveyed to a large and heterogeneous audience”. They are the vehicles that are used from conveying messages from a source to a large destination.

To fulfil this goal, this study reviewed relevant articles to elucidate the key thematic areas of research on social media, including its benefits and spill-over effects. The resulting review is predicted to function as a one-stop source, offering insight into what has been accomplished thus far in terms of research on social media, what's currently being done, and what challenges and opportunities lie ahead. By doing so, this study explores the subsequent aspects of existing research on social media:

Review of literature

Social media has made access to and exchange of news and information in written, verbal and visual form, very convenient and easy. The social media news has been referred to as propaganda, deception, manipulation, fabrication, news satire and news parody (Khalidova & Pantti, 2016); (Tandoc et al., 2018). It extends technology adoption models in investigating messages or news via social media channels and also integrated new factors from e-WoM such as comprehensibility (Rampersad & Althiyabi, 2020). The factors under consideration in this research included culture, education, age, and gender. The indication that age possesses a strong influence on the acceptance of fake news compared to the other two factors, education, and gender (Kumar, N. & Singh, M. 2018). However, education is also an important factor that can decrease dissemination of fake news to a great extent since by increasing education an individual will be less likely to follow or spread fake news without any confirmation regarding the source of the news (Rajendran, L., Thesinghraj, P., & Engineering, C. 2014)

Social media comprises communication websites that facilitate relationships forming between users from diverse backgrounds, resulting in a rich social structure (Kapoor et al., 2018). User-generated content encourages inquiry and decision-making and the use of social media for information sharing during critical events as well as for seeking and/or rendering help has also been investigated in prior research (Pradhan, P., & Kumari, N. (2018). Newman, N. (2011) emphasises on the contexts include political and public administration, and the comparison between traditional and social media. However, Social media allows relationships to form between users from distinct backgrounds, resulting in a tenacious social structure. Social media sites are already so deeply embedded in our daily lives that people rely on them for every need, ranging from daily news and updates on critical events to entertainment, connecting with family and friends, reviews and recommendations on products/services and places, fulfilment of emotional needs, workplace management, and keeping up with the latest in fashion, to name but a few. Greenwood, B. N., & Gopal, A. (2015) highlights the social media, applications such as Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, YouTube, LinkedIn, Pinterest, and Instagram often come to mind.

The study conducted by Boczkowski et al., (2017) examines the dynamics of news consumption on social media through with young users from Argentina. Upon this analysis from, it is observed that from the past few years, there is an emergence and rapid popularization of social media have further upended the status quo of news consumption. Young users encounter news on social media all the time but click on them only sporadically--and once they do they spend little time reading or viewing the content. First, Bucholtz found that increased news consumption on social networking sites was tied to decreased news consumption on other media platforms, thus indirectly contributing towards a displacement effect (C. Kim 2017).

The emergence of a novel ideal-typical mode of news consumption that what we have called “incidental news” (Tamersoy, M. De Choudhury 2017) and that has become the dominant mode of information acquisition for this segment of the population: news content encountered on mobile devices while visiting social media sites, in a process that is derivative of social media interactions rather than deliberately sought for—as opposed to the consumption of entertainment content on television.

Pradhan & Kumari, (2018) continued on comprehensively on the interactive features of social media have transformed journalism into a forum whose primary function is exchange of views. The study argued that the huge inflow of information through the unofficial channels makes journalism more of a desk job leaving less time for

field work and research. This study also found that keeping pace with the global trends, Indian journalists have embraced social media services in a big way both in personal and professional life. An obvious finding in Dewan, S., & Ramaprasad, J. (2014) study is that Web Journalists more frequently use the social media services professionally compared to print journalists. The professional social networking service LinkedIn and Flickr do not find much favour in the professional life of journalists.

To find leads for stories, Facebook and Twitter are used by most Journalists. For sharing other links, Journalists mostly use Facebook, which is followed by WhatsApp and then YouTube. The advent of social media has made some journalistic functions easier (Ernst, N., Engesser, S 2017), but at the same time it has also made some functions challenging for journalists.

Rajendran, Thesinghraj, & Engineering, (2014) observed, Social media and other online news sources, also known as the “new media”, have become an integral part of modern society. The presence of such new media, social media in particular, has threatened the existence of printed newspapers (Bertot, J. C., Jaeger, 2012). Readership habits seem to be changing as users turn to the Internet for free news and information. The print media paradigm flourished in the pre-internet era where instant access to news, using smartphones and online news aggregators, was not within the reach of the common man. social media allows users to provide feedback, which in turn is used to enrich users’ experience (Arnaboldi, M., Busco, 2017). The convenient access to online news for free seems the witness of not the “End” of print but rather the adaptation of print and News organizations to rapidly changing consumer patterns.-

A Case Study in the Karnataka Urban and Rural Areas (Shivarudrappa, 2014) on the objective is to reveal the impact of new media on the old traditional media of communication in Karnataka. It was discovered from the urban communities that the answer is in affirmative while in the semi-urban and rural, it’s in the negative. They examined the traditional media are culturally rooted, are part and parcel of the daily life of the people.

On the Synergy and Variance Perspective (Apuke, 2019), the social media is at variance with Traditional media in production of media content whereby social media content is now becoming more generally dispersed throughout the population, rather than restricted to media professionals. Social Media and Traditional media share a certain relation which has to do with the capability to reach small or large audiences (Young, 2016).

To measure the reasons people rely on sources is to get the provide insights into the importance & specific factors that might be related to trust (Schoenebeck, S., Scott,2021). The link of specific factors to more general principles of trust such as accuracy or completeness & the data suggested that the specific factors of trust do correlate not only to whether people turn to a particular source but also how much they engage with news in general (Munar, A. M., & Jacobsen, J. K. S. 2013). People who rate specific factors related to trust as especially important are the most likely to engage with, and to pay for, news from the source they rely on. They are especially more likely to share content from their trusted sources. The findings of Kietzmann, J. H., Hermkens, K., McCarthy, I. P., & Silvestre, B. S. (2011) reveal that when trust is taken out of the abstract, there is a lot of variation in how people assess sources. What makes something trustworthy and valuable differs depending on the topic and source. There is one general exception to this: On every topic and regardless of the source, getting the facts right is critical and it should be up to date.

The above discussion can be spur into the discussion which needs to analysed from the aspect of trust and accountability. Notwithstanding the study of Kietzmann (2011), Munar, A. M., & Jacobsen, J. K. S. (2013) made in roads to analysis, but it still needed a greater understanding in the other contextual elements viz., source information & value diverse news dynamics accountability perceived accuracy level of acceptance. This study is explore the elements in the context of developing economy such as India in aligning to the study of Shivarudrappa, (2014).

Research Methodology:

It is the comparative study on how the trust and accountability is inculcated into different modes of news platforms vis-à-vis traditional and social media. The Population of southern Bangalore was specifically chosen because most of the people are from different places, different culture, different location, and religions stay in Bangalore and each

and every one leads differing types of life styles and reading habits. This study evolves on describing the implication of social media, and it is also a quantitative in nature as the information is collected using Random sampling technique. The most objective of the study is to analyse the trust and accountability of the news consumed by individual from social media. The study was taken for a period of 60 days. To validate the researchers claim, Anova one way was utilized for understanding the variance among the factors and was deployed to scale back the size identified into major factors (based on loading & Eigen values). (Coughlan et al., 2016). In this study SEM model was developed to enhance and exhibit the validation.

Data Collection Method:

In this research, the data collection technique used was random sampling technique to collect the required data. The sample size of the research conducted was 154 respondents from South Bangalore.

Sampling Plan

The Study assumed 95% confidence level and equal responses from all the respondents and an error of 5% of the true value.

The samples were collected from a cross section of people staying in that area. It comprises of respondents with different demographic dimensions.

Need for the Study and Statement of Problem

We need to analyse after doing research on the study that how individuals have shifted from traditional media to social media for news consumption and therefore the trust and accountability of the social media news concerning demographic factors and their interests, time consumption, and simply available/ accessible resources.

Questionnaire Design:

Through the literature review, the question associated with the factors influencing the individual shift from traditional media to social media as a source of stories. Responses within the statements within the questioners were measured on a five-point scale starting from 1 to five with 1 indicating strongly agree and 5 indicating strongly disagree, and. The questionnaires also consist of comparative scale and other categorical scales. The collected data were statistically processed subsequently findings were inferred.

Conceptual Model

Descriptive analysis

Demographic

VARIABLE		FREQUENCY (NO OF RESPONDENTS)	PERCENTAGE (%)
AGE	18-24 Years	112	72.72%
	25-34 Years	27	17.53%
	35-44 Years	11	7.14%
	45 Above	4	2.61%
GENDER	Male	84	54.54%
	Female	66	42.85%
	Prefer not to say	4	2.59%
EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION	No formal education	2	1.29%
	Primary	2	1.29%
	Secondary	7	4.54%
	Diploma	8	5.19%
	Bachelor's	80	51.94%
	Master's	51	33.11%
	PhD	5	3.24%

Table helps understand the demographic factors that influence trust and accountability of social media news

The table shows that 72.72% of the respondents are between the age of 18 to 24 years, 17.53% of the respondents are between the age of 25 to 34 years, 7.14% respondents are aged between 35 to 44 years and 2.59% of the respondents are aged above 44. It is interpreted that respondents from age group of 18 to 24 prefer to prefer social media as a news source

Male respondents constitute 54.54% of the respondents, female respondents constitute 42.85% and 2.59% of respondent preferred not to say, consisting of 84 male (54.54%), 66 female (42.85%) and 4 (2.59%) Preferred not to say. Most of them agreed that they depend on social media for news and trust few sources and they verify news which they read on social media.

Time Consumption

Time consumption in our study refers to what proportion of time a person is spending on social media for news. Consistent with the data collected Maximum people spend less than half-hour on social media for news. They agree on social media being more efficient and less time consuming.

Ease of Availability

Social media platforms provide information to people easily. they're getting news associated with the whole world at their fingertips. For this people follow several pages and Forums on online platforms. concerning our research around 44% to 50% of people do follow specific pages for news and also think that Social media news is extremely distinct, and easily available to them. Good amount of people uses YouTube and Instagram as a source of news.

Diverse Views

There are many social media platforms supporting a good range of interests, activities and practices. They embrace many useful tools, applications and services that sustain many activities. social platforms are to attach people, support common language or shared racial, sexual, religious or nationality-based identities, shared interests, politics and joint activities. Our research shows that the majority of people think that news on social media gives them Chance to share their views on focused topics and also, they also give New perspectives towards News.

Traverse News

the Internet has enabled new phenomena by which the audiences get more involved in news production and distribution. The online and New Media don't have space limitations and have enabled audiences to play an active role within the method of story creation, selection and publishing. Our research shows that people agree on Social media news being unfiltered and in-depth.

Source of information and their value

The Internet has changed the habits of individuals. Convenience and user-friendliness are the most important contributing factors during this change. Social media like Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, etc have brought tremendous improvement within the communication system, it's provided different entertainment functions which works as a tool for social change. According to our research people showed high interest in getting news from social media, they also mentioned that even memes (a component of a culture or system of behaviour passed from one individual to a different by imitation or other non-genetic means.) can even be news sources in social media.

Statistical Analysis

The objective to establish and validate statistically the proposed model, hence the Structural equation modelling used with R Lavaan package. The following are the output and path diagram

The hypothesis can be framed to reaffirm the significance of correlation among the said variables, therefore the below is the hypothesis

H1₀: the trust and accountability of social media is influenced and correlated with dynamics, perceived accuracy, and level of acceptance

H1_a: the trust and accountability of social media is influenced and correlated with dynamics, perceived accuracy, and level of acceptance

Sl.no.	Model Fit Indices	Threshold level	Actual result	Analysis
1	Absolute Fit Indices RMSEA GFI	< 0.07 (Steiger, 2007) > 0.95 (Tabachnick & Fidell 2007)	0.06 0.99	Fit model
2	Incremental Fit Indices NFI CFI	> 0.95 Bentler and Bonnet (1980) > 0.95 (Tabachnick & Fidell 2007)	0.98 0.99	Fit model
3	Parsimony Fit Indices PGFI	< 0.5 Mulaik et al (1989)	0.095	Fit model

Abbreviated	Description
x2	age
x5	time consumption
x10	time consumption
x16	Traverse news
x9	source information & value
x11	diverse news
dv	dynamics
tn	accountability
siv	perceived accuracy
a	level of acceptance
tsm	Trust and accountability

From the above table and analysis of path analysis as model fits, and establishing a strong significant relationship among dependent and independent variables (path analysis), H_0 can be rejected and accepting H_a hypothesis. It could be inferred from the above that the dynamics, accountability, perceived accuracy and level of acceptance having vital impact on trust and accountability of social media as source of news.

The objective to analyse the level of acceptance of social media news among various age/demographic factor with respect to traditional media. Since it is scale data, & it is to know any difference among said population sample; anova single factor is deployed.

H_{20} : There is no significant difference of acceptance of social media news among various age/demographic factor with respect to traditional media

H_{2a} : There is significant difference of acceptance of social media news among various age/demographic factor with respect to traditional media

Anova: Single Factor

SUMMARY

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
1. Gender	154	228	1.480519	0.30354
2. Age	154	215	1.396104	0.541423
3. Educational Qualification	154	798	5.181818	0.934046
12. Social media has changed perspective towards traditional news	154	353	2.292208	0.861769
11. Social media news is more effective than traditional news.	154	376	2.441558	1.137085

ANOVA

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	1459.857	4	364.9643	483.0301	1.3E-207	2.383572
Within Groups	578.013	765	0.755573			
Total	2037.87	769				

From the above test result, Ho can be rejected by accepting alternative hypothesis. The inference would be that ‘there is significant difference of acceptance of social media news among various age/demographic factor with respect to traditional media’

Findings

1. According to our survey 51.9% of individuals depends on social media for news. Despite counting on social media for news around 46.8% of individuals spend half-hour on social media specifically for news.
2. Around 27.9% of individuals follow 3 social media sites for news purposes. 14.9% of individuals follow 7+ social media sites for news. Social media being so familiar among everyone during this era, the highest three social media sites used for news purposes are Instagram, Youtube, and Facebook.
3. having around 57.8%, 57.1%, and 42.9% engagement of individuals for news on these sites for news. Respectively. People often spend time on social media for news, our research shows approximately 78% of people think that social media news is Distinct, easily Available, More Efficient, Less-time consuming, gives an opportunity to share your views, and they have gained New Perspective on News.
4. People do believe that social media news is Unfiltered, in-depth, even Memes on social media are a source of stories. People always have an interest in real news, upon asking if people cross-check the information they consume form social media, 46.8% do cross-check the news often after social media.
5. People do follow specific pages on social media for news, around 44.8% of individuals follow a selected person or page for his or her news. The shift of individuals from traditional media to social media is clear as around 40.9% of individuals agree on being social media simpler than traditional news.
6. Our research shows that the bulk of individuals think that news on social media gives them an opportunity to share their views on focused topics and that also gives them New perspectives towards News. About 45.5% agree when asked if social media has changed their perspective towards traditional news.

Suggestion

People do depend upon social media for news because they find it handy and straightforward to urge. They don't need to await, long still people spent around half an hour on social media as they take social media as an area to attach with people. People follow pages and persons on social media so that they will have access to a spread of stories. Instagram, Youtube, and Facebook have such an excellent hold on the market and therefore the growing engagement of individuals on these sites lately is clearly visible. News on social media is completely unfiltered as

people has now power to make and generate their own content on these sites. Accuracy and accountability of stories are a requirement in today's scenario, so people do cross-check news taken from social media on other resources also. Nowadays people do strive for straightforward and easy ways of getting things done in order that they do use social media as a source of news, thanks to several reasons. Getting unfiltered and on-time news makes people think more and clear about the subject floated on social media as they will get many other views of individuals on an equivalent.

Conclusion

Social Media plays a really important role in today's life, social Media are web-based online tools that enable people to get and learn new information, share ideas, interact with new people and organizations. It's changed the way people live their lives today, it's made communication much easier and affordable for people. People round the world use social media as a source of news, they believe social media for brand spanking new perspectives and unfiltered news. A little number of individuals cross-check the news from other sources. So, people do believe what's circulated on social media, they have full power to boost their voice and to spread their concerns with several billion people on one tap. Faith on social media news makes it more evident that folks believe what's wrong and what's right. People really appreciate when their opinions are heard and given importance. An outsized number of the population is on social media today they the right to use social media to raise their concerns about any problem.

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DIGITAL SUPPLY CHAIN TWIN: EXPLORING LIMITS AND EXPANDING HORIZONS

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ABSTRACT

This paper delves into the concept of the "Digital Supply Chain Twin" and its pivotal role in modern supply chain management. By providing real-time visibility, predictive decision-making, agility, and fostering collaboration, the Digital Supply Chain Twin empowers organizations to enhance their supply chain operations, mitigate risks, and gain a competitive edge. This study offers a comprehensive exploration of the Digital Supply Chain Twin, detailing its components, benefits, and potential applications. Through analyzing successful case studies and addressing implementation challenges, the paper highlights the significance of this transformative technology in achieving supply chain resilience and continuous improvement.

Keywords: DSCT, Digital Supply Chain Twins, real-time

INTRODUCTION

A digital supply chain twin is a fictitious replica of a real-world supply chain. It is a digital copy that simulates the complete supply chain ecosystem, including the goods, procedures, and resources. It is dynamic and linked. In order to collect, analyze, and interpret real-time data from diverse sources throughout the supply chain, the Digital Supply Chain Twin makes use of cutting-edge technologies like the Internet of Things, big data analytics, artificial intelligence, and machine learning. Organizations can monitor, simulate, and improve their supply chain operations thanks to the Digital Supply Chain Twin, which acts as a digital reflection of the physical supply chain. It offers a complete and all-encompassing perspective of the supply chain network, facilitating greater visibility, teamwork, and decision-making.

The Digital Supply Chain Twin enables organizations to get useful insights, anticipate and minimize interruptions, optimize operations, and enhance overall supply chain performance by collecting and analyzing data from sensors, devices, and systems embedded in the physical supply chain. Data collecting equipment (sensors, RFID tags, etc.), data transmission networks, data storage and processing systems, and visualization tools are some of the parts that make up the Digital Supply Chain Twin. In order to build a digital representation that accurately captures the status and behavior of the physical supply chain in real-time, it integrates data from several sources, including production systems, logistics service providers, suppliers, and customers.

By facilitating proactive and data-driven decision-making, the Digital Supply Chain Twin has the potential to completely transform supply chain management. It provides advantages including higher operational efficiency, cost savings, improved inventory management, more agility and response, and better customer service. It also improves visibility and traceability. Additionally, it encourages communication and information exchange between supply chain participants, improving coordination and synchronization throughout the whole network of the supply chain.

DIGITAL SUPPLY CHAIN TWIN - RELEVANCE AND SIGNIFICANCE

Applying static models to dynamic, constantly shifting real-world supply networks typically fails, as many organizations have come to realize. In reality, digital twin technology has already been accepted by major supply chain professionals. To carry out these dynamic testing and redesigns, businesses need a digital twin. In other words, it may be transformational. A digital twin is crucial to creating a supply chain that can not only withstand setbacks but also quickly recover from disruptive events like blocked transportation routes, distribution center closures, and so on because it enables organizations to stress test their supply chain design. Digital twins are used by businesses to increase supply chain visibility, spot inefficiencies, find possibilities for improvement, find trends, and streamline

existing operations. By enabling organizations to make wiser, quicker, data-driven decisions to adapt if and when anything goes wrong, digital twins are important facilitators of supply chain resilience.

Since it improves visibility, enables predictive decision-making, fosters agility and responsiveness, encourages cooperation, and encourages continuous development, the digital supply chain twin is very relevant to supply chain management. In a corporate environment that is continually changing, it enables organizations to optimize supply chain operations, reduce risks, and gain a competitive edge.

Enhanced Visibility and Control: Organisations may gain a thorough insight into their operations because of the Digital Supply Chain Twin's real-time visibility across the whole supply chain network. It enables them to keep an eye on the flow of merchandise, keep tabs on inventory levels, and spot supply-chain bottlenecks or inefficiencies. This improved insight enables businesses to take well-informed choices, deal with problems before they arise, and streamline supply chain operations.

Predictive and Proactive Decision-making: The Digital Supply Chain Twin can analyze massive amounts of real-time data from diverse sources by utilizing advanced analytics and machine learning techniques. Organizations are able to forecast future results and proactively manage risks or interruptions because of this skill. As a result, supply chain managers may optimize inventory levels, enhance demand forecasts, and put proactive measures in place to reduce interruptions and improve performance.

Agile and Responsive Operations: Organisations can react swiftly and successfully to shifts in consumer demand, market circumstances, or supply chain problems thanks to the Digital Supply Chain Twin. Organizations may model various scenarios, assess the effects of prospective changes, and make modifications to maintain agility and responsiveness by having a real-time digital duplicate of the physical supply chain. In the fast-paced business climate of today, when supply chain interruptions and shifting consumer expectations necessitate quick and adaptable answers, this capacity is essential.

Collaboration and Coordination: The Digital Supply Chain Twin helps supply chain parties collaborate and exchange information. It makes it possible for suppliers, manufacturers, logistics companies, and customers to communicate and coordinate easily. Supply chain partners may coordinate their efforts, synchronize operations, and improve overall supply chain performance by exchanging real-time data and insights. Through collaboration, we can increase productivity, cut down on lead times, and boost customer satisfaction.

Continuous Improvement and Optimization: Organisations may continually track and evaluate supply chain performance parameters with the help of the Digital Supply Chain Twin. They may find areas for improvement, streamline procedures, and promote operational excellence by utilizing real-time data. Organizations may test and implement new strategies, technologies, or process improvements in a virtual environment before adopting them in the actual supply chain thanks to the platform for experimentation and simulation provided by the digital supply chain twin.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The objective of this paper is to investigate and analyze the idea of a "Digital Supply Chain Twin" and its importance to supply chain management. It tries to give a thorough explanation of Digital Supply Chain Twin, including all of its elements, advantages, and prospective uses. The study also seeks to examine actual case studies

in order to highlight successful implementations and talk about difficulties encountered while adopting the Digital Supply Chain Twin.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A real-time and complete perspective of the supply chain is what the SCDT intends to deliver, facilitating improved decision-making and optimization. The main elements of the SCDT are covered in the study, including data integration, data collecting, and analytics. The authors stress the significance of accurate and high-quality data for a successful SCDT deployment. They also emphasize the advantages of applying the SCDT, including greater risk management, improved supply chain visibility, and improved operational effectiveness. The promise of the SCDT idea is highlighted in the paper's conclusion, along with the necessity of more study and work to fully realize its advantages. Overall, the study emphasizes the potential of a supply chain digital twin to change supply chain management while presenting a conceptual foundation for one (**Barykin et.al.,2020**)

Big data refers to the exponential growth in data quantities from many sources, which presents industrial organizations with both difficulties and worthwhile opportunities. Although the exact definition varies, it typically entails substantial amounts of unstructured data that need for immediate analysis. Big data, made possible by new technologies and architectures, is seen as the next frontier for innovation and productivity. The 'four Vs'—variety, velocity, volume, and veracity—are frequently used to group the characteristics of big data, with an emphasis on value-adding. Big data dynamics and features provide issues for managing and analyzing. A common definition still needs to be established. In industrial supply chain management, efficient big data gathering, storage, development, and analysis are vital. In operations and supply chain management, the study examines viewpoints, applications, analytical tools, trends, and consequences of big data (**Addo & Helo, 2021**)

A thorough examination of Digital Supply Chain Twins (DSCTs) is provided in this research titled "Digital Supply Chain Twins - Conceptual Clarification, Use Cases and Benefits". It emphasizes the possibilities of DSCTs for real-time monitoring, analysis, and optimization, defining them as digital representations of actual supply chains. In order to show how DSCTs may be used in real-world situations, the paper provides a number of use scenarios, including supply chain visibility, demand forecasting, inventory management, production planning, and risk reduction. The advantages of DSCT adoption are emphasized by the authors, including better decision-making, more visibility, and improved teamwork. They also talk about the difficulties in adopting the DSCT, such as data security, technological infrastructure, and organizational preparedness. The possibility of integrating DSCT with other technologies like blockchain, artificial intelligence, and the IoT is being investigated (**Gerlach et.al., 2021**)

The adoption of Digital Supply Chain Twins (DSCTs) is examined in the survey by Dy, Olivares-Aguila, and Vital-Soto. It demonstrates the various ways that DSCTs are used in different businesses, highlighting manufacturing, logistics, and retail as important areas. Predictive analytics, real-time monitoring, and greater visibility are a few advantages that DSCTs provide. However, data integration, interoperability, and organizational issues must be resolved for successful adoption. The study highlights the requirement for uniform standards and recommendations to enable DSCT implementation. It offers insightful information about the present environment and the potential for DSCT deployments. The findings support ongoing research and development by helping to understand the advantages and difficulties of DSCTs. The survey serves as a resource for practitioners and scholars by providing a succinct overview of DSCT implementations (**Aguila & Soto, 2022**)

DSCTs offer modeling, simulation, and assessment of logistics operations with an emphasis on sustainability criteria through real-time data integration and analysis. The authors give a case study that illustrates how DSCTs may be utilized to find sustainable solutions that have less of an impact on the environment. The advantages include better resource utilization, a smaller carbon footprint, and improved sustainability initiative decision-making. The research stresses the importance of DSCTs in encouraging sustainable planning in logistics systems while acknowledging limitations including data availability and multidisciplinary collaboration (**Zarnitz, et.al.,2023**)

RESEARCH GAP IDENTIFIED

The need for further empirical study on the actual application and results of Digital Supply Chain Twins (DSCTs) might be noted as a possible research gap. The papers largely concentrate on theoretical frameworks and case

studies, while they also cover the conceptual features, application cases, and advantages of DSCTs. There is a dearth of comprehensive empirical research that examines the actual implementation procedures, difficulties encountered, and practical results obtained through DSCT adoption. To close this research gap and offer useful information to practitioners considering DSCT adoption in their supply chain management practices, it would be beneficial to understand the real-world implementation experiences, including the technological, organizational, and cultural variables involved. It is also necessary to do more studies to examine the long-term impacts of DSCT implementation on supply chain performance, sustainability, and resilience, as well as any potential ethical and legal issues connected to the use of DSCTs in supply chain management.

PURPOSE AND COMPONENTS OF DSCT

The Digital Supply Chain Twin serves the purpose of addressing the complexities and challenges faced by supply chain management in today's business landscape. By creating a virtual replica or representation of the physical supply chain network, it aims to enhance visibility, enable data-driven decision-making, optimize operations, and foster collaboration among supply chain stakeholders.

- ✚ The Digital Supply Chain Twin comprises several key components that enable its functionality. Firstly, it involves data integration, where real-time data from various sources within the supply chain, such as IoT sensors, enterprise systems, and external data feeds, are collected and integrated. This includes information on inventory levels, production schedules, demand patterns, transportation routes, and other relevant parameters.
- ✚ Secondly, the Digital Supply Chain Twin leverages analytics and simulation techniques. Advanced analytics is applied to the integrated data to generate actionable insights. Predictive and prescriptive analytics are utilized to anticipate potential disruptions, optimize operations, and simulate different scenarios to evaluate the impact of changes in the supply chain.
- ✚ Thirdly, visualization and collaboration are essential components of the Digital Supply Chain Twin. It provides a user-friendly interface that visualizes the supply chain network and its associated data. This facilitates collaboration and communication among supply chain stakeholders, enabling real-time information sharing and joint decision-making.
- ✚ Lastly, the Digital Supply Chain Twin integrates with external systems such as Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) and Customer Relationship Management (CRM). This ensures seamless data flow and synchronization, allowing for a comprehensive view of the supply chain.

BENEFITS OF DSCT

Real-time Visibility: The Digital Supply Chain Twin provides real-time visibility into the entire supply chain

network. It allows businesses to monitor operations, track inventory levels, and identify bottlenecks or inefficiencies promptly. This visibility enables proactive decision-making and the ability to address issues in real time, leading to improved responsiveness and customer satisfaction.

Predictive and Prescriptive Analytics: By leveraging advanced analytics capabilities, the Digital Supply Chain Twin can predict future demand patterns, optimize inventory levels, and simulate different scenarios. These

analytics enable businesses to make informed decisions, optimize resource allocation, and anticipate and mitigate potential disruptions. This leads to improved operational efficiency, reduced costs, and optimized performance.

Enhanced Collaboration: The Digital Supply Chain Twin serves as a collaborative platform for supply chain stakeholders. It facilitates real-time data sharing, joint planning, and coordination among different entities, such as suppliers, manufacturers, and distributors. This collaboration improves communication, alignment, and decision-making, resulting in streamlined processes, reduced lead times, and increased overall supply chain efficiency.

Risk Mitigation and Resilience: The Digital Supply Chain Twin enables businesses to assess and mitigate risks within the supply chain. By simulating different scenarios and evaluating the impact of potential disruptions, businesses can develop contingency plans, proactively address risks, and enhance supply chain resilience. This helps in reducing the impact of disruptions, improving business continuity, and maintaining customer satisfaction.

Continuous Improvement: The Digital Supply Chain Twin serves as a platform for continuous improvement and optimization of supply chain processes. By analyzing data and feedback from the virtual twin, businesses can identify areas for improvement, test new strategies, and measure performance against key performance indicators (KPIs). This continuous improvement leads to enhanced operational efficiency, reduced costs, and increased competitiveness.

APPLICATIONS OF THE DIGITAL SUPPLY CHAIN TWIN

Demand Forecasting and Planning: The Digital Supply Chain Twin can leverage real-time data and predictive analytics to forecast demand accurately. This helps businesses optimize production schedules, adjust inventory levels, and ensure timely delivery of products to meet customer demand.

Inventory Optimization: By integrating real-time data on inventory levels, customer demand, and production capacity, the Digital Supply Chain Twin enables businesses to optimize inventory management. It assists in minimizing stock-outs, reducing carrying costs, and improving overall inventory efficiency.

Logistics and Transportation Optimization: The Digital Supply Chain Twin can optimize logistics and transportation operations by analyzing real-time data on transportation routes, carrier capacities, and delivery performance. This enables businesses to optimize routing, reduce transportation costs, and improve delivery speed and reliability.

Supplier Collaboration and Risk Management: The Digital Supply Chain Twin facilitates collaboration and communication among suppliers, enabling real-time data sharing and joint planning. It helps in identifying potential supplier risks, assessing supplier performance, and managing supplier relationships effectively.

Sustainability and Environmental Impact: The Digital Supply Chain Twin can incorporate sustainability metrics and environmental data to assess and optimize the environmental impact of supply chain operations. It enables businesses to track carbon emissions, energy consumption, and waste generation, leading to the development of more sustainable and environmentally-friendly supply chains.

CASE STUDIES OF COMPANIES USING DIGITAL SUPPLY CHAIN TWIN

Microsoft:

Microsoft, a global technology leader, emphasizes the pivotal role of data in enabling agility and effective responses to disruptions. At the Coupa Inspire event, Microsoft representatives, Cassie Wang, and Jonathan Allen highlighted

the integration of carbon emissions as a core metric within their operations, aiming to reduce their carbon footprint while ensuring profitability and sustainability. One notable example of Microsoft's data-driven approach is shifting from wood shipping pallets to alternative materials. By analyzing data on shipping costs and carbon emissions, they adopted recyclable plastic or composite pallets, leading to significant reductions in both costs and carbon emissions. During the COVID-19 pandemic, Microsoft utilized digital twin technology to gain real-time visibility into its supply chain and operational processes. This allowed them to make informed decisions, simulate disruptions, and proactively respond to challenges, optimizing their supply chain operations, maintaining business continuity, and minimizing disruptions. However, implementing a digital twin comes with challenges. Organizations must ensure data integration from diverse sources, promote collaboration across functions, and prioritize data security and privacy. Despite these challenges, Microsoft's data-driven approach and digital twin technology have resulted in improved visibility, enhanced decision-making, reduced costs, increased sustainability, and stronger resilience to disruptions. By integrating carbon emissions as a core metric, Microsoft shows its commitment to sustainability and addressing climate change.

A Medical Devices Company:

Facing a sudden surge in demand for respiratory care products and a drop in demand for other medical devices, a medical devices company implemented a digital twin solution to gain a comprehensive view of their global supply chain. By consolidating fragmented and incomplete data into one model, the digital twin enabled the company to evaluate alternative scenarios and optimize cost-to-serve. As a result, the company experienced a 35% increase in value through faster project delivery, meeting the rising demand for respiratory care products promptly. The digital twin provided real-time visibility and a holistic understanding of supply chain dynamics by integrating data from various sources. It allowed the company to simulate different scenarios, assess impacts, and make data-driven decisions. This enabled efficient production shifts, optimized transportation, and improved inventory management to meet the surge in demand while managing reduced demand for other medical devices. The solution fostered collaboration among stakeholders, suppliers, and logistics partners, streamlining coordination and resource allocation. It also enhanced risk mitigation and resilience, helping the company proactively address disruptions and maintain business continuity. The outcomes were significant, with timely product delivery meeting critical healthcare needs and contributing to the company's financial success. The digital twin's optimization of cost-to-serve resulted in substantial savings by identifying cost reduction opportunities throughout the supply chain. In summary, the implementation of a digital twin provided the medical devices company with a powerful solution to adapt swiftly to market changes, optimize operations, and achieve remarkable financial and operational benefits.

IMPLICATIONS OF THE DIGITAL SUPPLY CHAIN TWIN

To re-energize their supply chain initiatives, businesses are looking towards cutting-edge technologies like AI, ML, and IoT technology solutions. 'Digital twins' may help with this balancing act, according to industry experts. The creation of digital twins is "the process of using data streams to create a digital representation of a real-world asset to improve collaboration, information access, and decision-making." The market for digital twins is anticipated to grow by around 40% by 2025, and by 2026, it's estimated that more than 90% of IoT platforms would make use of some part of the technology. Therefore, the implementation of Digital Supply Chain Twin has significant implications for supply chain management and business operations.

Global digital twin market size in the year 2020 and 2025, by industry
 (in billion U.S. dollars)

Improved Visibility and Transparency: By giving businesses granular access to real-time supply chain information, Digital Supply Chain Twin enables them to track and manage their assets, operations, and inventories. Better decisions may be made as a result of the increased visibility since it makes it easier for businesses to spot bottlenecks, streamline processes, and deal with interruptions.

Enhanced Collaboration and Communication: Different supply chain stakeholders may work together more effectively with a Digital Supply Chain Twin. Better coordination between suppliers, manufacturers, distributors, and retailers is made possible through real-time data exchange and communication. This enhanced collaboration may result in shorter lead times, quicker reaction times, and greater supply chain efficiency overall.

Predictive and Prescriptive Analytics: To analyze enormous volumes of data, Digital Supply Chain Twin makes use of modern analytics and artificial intelligence (AI) capabilities. This makes it possible for businesses to forecast and prepare for crucial occurrences such as demand changes and supply chain interruptions. With the help of these insights, organizations can proactively make wise choices and take preventative measures to improve the efficiency of their supply chains.

Optimized Inventory Management: Organisations may improve their inventory management by having real-time access to data on inventory levels, demand trends, and consumer behavior. By minimizing stockouts, reducing inventory carrying costs, and ensuring the correct items are available at the right time and in the appropriate quantities, Digital Supply Chain Twin can assist. This optimization raises profitability and improves client happiness.

Risk reduction and resiliency: Organisations can determine the effects of prospective supply chain interruptions by modeling different scenarios and doing "what-if" studies. Businesses can detect risks, create backup plans, and improve operational resilience thanks to Digital Supply Chain Twin. This proactive strategy enables continuity even in the face of unforeseen occurrences while reducing risks.

Efficient Resource Allocation: Better resource allocation across the supply chain is made possible by Digital Supply Chain Twin. Organizations can optimize the distribution of resources including industrial equipment, labor, and transportation by analyzing data on capacity utilization, production efficiency, and demand changes. This optimization results in enhanced operational efficiency, lower costs, and better productivity.

Continuous Improvement and Innovation: Digital Supply Chain Twin offers businesses a platform for ongoing innovation and continuous improvement. The capacity to gather and analyze data along the whole supply chain enables the detection of problem areas and the application of creative remedies. Insights from the Digital Supply Chain Twin may be used by organizations to promote operational improvement, embrace new technology, and investigate creative business models.

CONCLUSION

A revolutionary method of supply chain management is presented by the idea of the "Digital Supply Chain Twin." The major conclusions and insights highlight its potential for enhancing supply chain visibility, cooperation, decision-making, and resilience. Organizations can optimize inventory management, improve operational efficiency, and proactively address disruptions by utilizing real-time data, sophisticated analytics, and new technologies like IoT and AI. To ensure data privacy, fairness, and compliance, it is necessary to address ethical and legal issues. It is impossible to overstate the importance of Digital Supply Chain Twin. It provides a chance to completely transform supply chain processes, allowing businesses to increase their efficiency, customer satisfaction, and competitive edge. Practitioners should place a high priority on data security, encourage stakeholder engagement, and adopt technology that supports quick decision-making if they want to realize the full potential of the Digital Supply Chain Twin. Researchers' knowledge and use of the Digital Supply Chain Twin will progress as they further investigate topics like IoT integration, AI-driven optimization, ethical considerations, and sustainability, spurring innovation and influencing the future of supply chain management. Unquestionably, digital twins provide potential. Digital twins in manufacturing and engineering assist businesses in avoiding future issues, maximizing projects, and lowering costs. Digital twins in healthcare assist with personalized and predictive treatment to enhance patient outcomes and lower some healthcare expenses. Despite these possibilities, the Federal monitoring organization is cautioning that these virtual models may potentially raise legal, moral, and technological concerns.

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AI IMPLEMENTATION IN BANKING SECTOR: CUSTOMER PERSEPECTIVE

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Abstract:

Indian banking sector playing very important role in the economy, and also Banks daily interact with a vast number of customers and are still depending on a legacy system. By today's advances in technology, regarding lifting almost all processes to automation, from start of production to finish, there is a need for revolution in monetary management institutes. Banks can engage in implementation of new Virtual Assistants and Artificial Intelligence machine learning technologies, have engaged in modernizing, one of the most revolutionizing step is implementation of chatbots that explains the banking experience in many ways with respect to customers.

Chatbot is an AI it enabled chat messenger that initiates a conversation with customers frequently asking questions relates to the banking transaction, information on product and services, payment bills and this Chatbot installed by private and nationalized banks in there websites and applications.

This research paper evaluates how implementation of AI affects customer behaviour towards banking sector with their perception. The main purpose of this research is to identify and analysis customer perception towards using AI i.e chatbot in banking sectors.

Key words: Artificial Intelligence, Customer perception, Banking System, Chatbots

Introduction

The Banking Financial services and Insurance are the biggest buyer and adopter of technology. The widely accepted and adopted technology in AI is "Chatbots" in banking sectors, which provides customer quick and personalized responses to retain the customers, so what are Chatbots? It is a programme which stimulates human conversation through voice command or text. It smoothen the interaction and conversation between organization and users. It was introduced by MIT professor Joseph Weizenbaum in the year 1960 which was named "ELIZA" and since it has come a long way.

Adopting a Chatbots in banking sectors provides various benefits in a following ways:

1. Chatbot helps in frequently asked questions such as:
 - What are my last transactions?
 - What is my bank account balance?
 - What is my credit bill? Etc
1. It facilitates core banking activities by collecting EMI within the chat window and customer also apply for loan, transfer money, make a bill payment etc,
2. It provides 24*7 customer care support hence it maintains the competitive edge in market to retain the customers.
3. It provides appropriate customer interaction.

Following are the popular chatbots adopted by various Indian banks some of them are:

1. SBI bank's launched its Artificial Intelligence based chatbot called SIA, which stands for SBI Intelligent Assistant in 2017.
2. Kotak' chatbot is called 'Keya' launched in 2019
3. HDFC bank chatbot is called as 'EVA' (Electronic virtual Assistant) launched in 2017
4. ICICI bank chatbot is called as 'ipal' etc

Objectives

- To understand the customer perception on the banking Chatbots
- To study the implementation and impact of AI -chat bot on Banking experience
- To evaluate the awareness of the banking chatbots among the respondents

Research Methodology

Data collection done through primary source

A descriptive research design was adopted to conduct the study and quantitative analysis done.

Primary data is collected with the help of structured questionnaire by using goggle forms from the respondents.

Simple random sampling design adopted to conduct the survey. In all total 85 respondents were approached with the response rate of 100%

Data Analysis

Conducted the research by using the questionnaire methodology and collected the data.

The result of the questionnaire provided by our participants through goggle forms and here are the following data gathered from the sample

Variables	N	%
Gender		
Male	35	41
Female	50	59
Age		
20-25	48	56
25-35	20	24
35-45	12	14
45 &above	5	6
Status of Employment		
Full time	30	35
Part time	9	11
Students	42	49
unemployoed	4	5

1. Respondents were asked whether they used mobile banking application or website for their banking queries and transaction

Never 6%, occasionally 44%, often 50%

Majority of the respondent i.e 50 out of 85 uses mobile applications for banking quires and for transaction so, the scope of chatbot I assessing in the banking sector and useful for the customers to retain.

2. Repondent were asked that are u aware of chabot? Example “keya” of kotak bank

Majority that 65 out of 85 respondent knows about the chatbots and 25 out of 85 were not aware of chat bot , so this proves respondents are quite know about the chat bot and the chatbot concept is quite popular.

3. When respondents asked about if they were had tried using chatbot in banking website or in mobile application?

58 out of 85 respondents had used the chatbots and 27 out of 85 had not used the chatbot so, most of the respondent in the sample which I have taken they are aware of using chabot and making use of AI in future questions can be based on the cusomers experience on chatbot.

4. Respondent asked about if they were facing any inconvenience while chatting or communicating with chat-bot .

51 out of 85 respondent facing inconvenience while communicating with the chat-bot and 30 out of 85 respondent never faced inconvenience with the chat-bot and only 5 out of 85 always face problems with chat-bot so that It has a good scope in future development of implementing AI in banking sectors so that customer will get their information at any time

5. When respondent asked about their experience with chat-bot when they have any query?

By above graph we can say that most of the respondent had satisfactory experience with chat-bot when they have a banking quires.

6. When respondent asked about if you have the security regarding the use of chat-bot with relates to sharing personal and banking information while making access and making credit card bill payment?

With above graph we can interpret that majority of the respondent I.e 76% have security concern with the chat bot while sharing personal information and banking details while accessing the credit card and its payment process and remaining 24% had lack of trust with respect to privacy.

7. When respondent asked what are the common quires usually you ask in chat-bot?

The above survey indicates that most of the respondents made general quires in chat-bot with respective followed by loan related, money transfer and least by other services.

8. when respondent were asked that can implementation of Artificial Intelligence I.e chat -bots can replace customer representative in the near future?

From the above data we can interpret like half of the respondent says AI I.e chats bot cannot replace customer representative .only 10% respondent says that chat-bot can replace customer executive

Findings and Suggestions:

1. The study helped to analyze the customer perception towards banking experience with AI implantation.
2. The research data tells about that most of the customers uses AI chatbot in banking website and applications
3. This Research tells about the wide scope of chatbot in assisting with banking sectors
4. However some of the repondent were not aware of chat-bot so that AI implementation should reach in all age group customers and creates awareness of it.
5. Majority of the repondent who ever used chatbot had satisfactory experience and majority of the respondent had security concern with chatbots
6. Most of the quires asked by customers in chat-bot is relates to general quriers and money transfer and loan related.

Conclusion:

Most of the banks are implementing AI in there banking activities to retain the customers by providing 24*7 customer support through chatbot,which helps the customer to get quick response from the banking side. It may also reduce the human touch with deployment of customer executive in near future. Some etimation tells that by calculating “Juniper research” in 2023 chat-bot interaction will saves 863 million hours for banking sectors.

This reseach says that banking customers are not only aware of the AI chatbot but also have perspective that somewhat effective and may be could replace customer service in future

Limitation of the study:

1. One of the limitation is fact that many respondent were not aware of AI and chatbot so could not have further participant in survey.
2. A large sample can have result in more reliability of data.

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<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Chatbot>
<https://www.wipro.com/business-process/why-banks-need-artificial-intelligence/>

EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION AND MORALE- CONCEPTUAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT: -

Worker Inspiration is the critical variable to assist with increasing the limit of an affiliation. In the globalization stage, every association needs to proceed with itself in an irately centered market. Delegates are the crucial components to show the business targets into this present reality. Hence, in the current world every affiliation endeavors to manage its human resource office to keep its agents propelled. In that explicit situation, a portion of the organization hypotheses have been practicing by them. Business work or their show in the market can be evaluated by studying the level of motivation of delegates. Motivation can expect a lead task to get the master accomplishment in each monetary year in a less effort way While attempting to find what moves delegates, agent motivation ask about papers report that what spikes workers today is generally associated with the characteristics and targets of the individual. Beginning in the 1970's, it creates the impression that there was a thrilling move in the characteristics and requirements of the conventional worker. As people ended up being dynamically educated and the economy saw a sharp rot of the Protestant focused perspectives, what delegates required from their chiefs changed too.

Keywords: Motivation, Performance; Productivity, Rewards, Workplace and Satisfaction.

1.INTRODUCTION

Inspiration alludes to the course of individuals making inspiration as a demonstration of motivation. It comes from inspiration, and that implies another energy that moves in the human body for it to do something. Inspiration is the method involved with uncovering an individual's internal strength and activity to accomplish certain objectives and giving energy to accomplish those objectives. It includes correspondence that starts with a need, which makes the inspiration that empowers the enumeration to accomplish its objectives. It is the interaction of spurring individuals to work willfully to accomplish the objectives of the association. Inspiration can be characterized as an errand in which the director provides requests to urge representatives to act in a positive way by fulfilling their requirements and needs.

Inspiration is worried about how conduct is persuaded, supported, and taught. Motivation is the consequence of the communication between the cognizant and oblivious, like the utilization of a craving or need, the inspiration or worth of the objective, and the assumption for oneself and his companions. These variables demonstrate why an individual acts the manner in which they do. A model is the point at which an understudy invests additional energy getting ready for a test since the person in question desires to do well in class. Inward and outer variables that support an individual's longing and energy to proceed to cherish and adhere to a task, job, or point or to keep pursuing an objective. Most workers need inspiration to feel better about their work and to do their best. Some workers are monetarily spurred, while others see acknowledgment and prizes as private inspiration.

The degree of inspiration in the working environment straightforwardly affects worker efficiency. Workers who are devoted and happy with their work give their all, subsequent in expanded efficiency.

Employee motivation and morale are crucial factors that significantly impact the productivity, satisfaction, and overall performance of an organization. In today's competitive business landscape, organizations recognize the importance of creating a positive work environment that fosters a motivated and engaged workforce.

This study aims to delve into the intricacies of employee motivation and morale, exploring the various factors that influence them and their interconnectedness. Understanding these factors is essential for organizations to develop effective strategies to boost employee satisfaction, productivity, and loyalty.

The concept of employee motivation and morale has been a subject of interest for scholars, human resource practitioners, and organizational leaders for decades. Numerous theories, such as Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs,

Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, and Expectancy Theory, have attempted to explain the underlying drivers of employee motivation.

While financial incentives play a significant role, it is becoming increasingly evident that employees' intrinsic needs, work-life balance, job satisfaction, and the sense of purpose are equally vital in driving motivation and morale.

1.1 MOTIVATION FACTORS:

Financial Motivators

Monetary motivators are called monetary impetuses. Customary and great wages and compensations, rewards, customary raises, benefit sharing, leave pay, medical advantages are a portion of the monetary motivating forces. The need of these motivating forces can adversely affect representative execution.

Non-Financial Motivators

Certain inspirations that are not connected with cash but rather decidedly affect the workers are called non-monetary inspirations. A portion of the non-monetary inspirations are as per the following

- Job Security
- Performance Appraisal, praise and prestige
- Delegation of authority
- Congenial work environment
- Status and pride
- Participation
- Job enrichment
- Job rotation
- Facilities for paid leaves

2. NEED FOR THE STUDY:

Inspiration is a significant boost that coordinates human way of behaving. Nobody has a similar character or on the other hand conduct, so associations in this variety should make rehearses that suit the entire group, not simply people.

Each effective organization is upheld by steadfast and connected with representatives. It is the consequence of inspiration and occupation fulfillment.

The power urges representatives to accomplish organization goals. Without responsibility, it is unthinkable for the association to make greatness.

Organizations should have cutthroat work force arrangements and practices to make serious advantage.

3. SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

Assets on representative inspiration and morals research at Middleware Framework Pvt Restricted, Advances Private Restricted can cover numerous viewpoints connected with understanding and getting to the next level representative inspiration and morals in an association. The following are a few potential regions that could be remembered for the study:

Inspirations: Recognize and quantify the key inspirations that keep representatives drew in and fulfilled at Middleware Framework Pvt Restricted. This can incorporate numerous things like acknowledgment and prizes, vocation improvement amazing open doors, balance between serious and fun activities, employer stability, opportunity and backing administration.

Workplace and Culture: Analyzing the Impacts of Workplace and Culture on Representative Inspiration and Spirit. This might incorporate analyzing variables, for example, correspondence with representatives, joint effort, worker relations, trust and shared corporate qualities.

Administration and the board: Survey the job of authority and the executives in affecting worker inspiration and assurance. This might incorporate assessment of administration, successful correspondence, dynamic cycles, and backing from chiefs and managers.

Worker Advantages and Motivating forces: To assess the adequacy of current representative advantages, motivators and acknowledgment programs concerning inspiration and resolve. This might incorporate exploring remuneration structures, execution based rewards, representative advancement programs and other benefits presented by the organization.

3.1 Expected Contributions:

This study endeavors to make several contributions:

- a. Academic Contribution: By consolidating existing research and incorporating new data, the study aims to add to the existing body of knowledge on employee motivation and morale.
- b. Practical Implications: The study will provide practical recommendations and insights for organizations to design effective motivational strategies that enhance employee engagement, satisfaction, and productivity.
- c. Policy Recommendations: The findings of this research can inform policymakers about the importance of employee well-being and motivation in the context of labor laws and workplace regulations.

3.2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Research is clear in nature; the information assortment device is utilized in the exploration incorporates poll in view of various inquiries from the workers which enlightens us regarding preparing and its influence on their exhibition and maintenance. The example size for this examination was 100 which incorporates just the representative inspiration and moral in the. The information assortment period was 30 days.

Precise examining procedure is utilized in the exploration paper to get the quantitative sort of arrangement for the poll ready. The essential information gathered was run under SPSS programming for connection, Regression and an ANOVA test for 110 responses to get quantitative arrangement. A organized poll was utilized in the review, which depended on five-point Likert scale. Separated into bunches like segment profile, explanation connected with Inspiration; Execution; Efficiency and so forth.

- a. Quantitative Research: Surveys and questionnaires will be distributed to a diverse sample of employees across various industries. These surveys will collect data on motivational factors, job satisfaction, performance, and the overall perception of workplace morale.
- b. Qualitative Research: In-depth interviews and focus groups will be conducted with select employees, HR professionals, and organizational leaders. These qualitative insights will provide a deeper understanding of the underlying drivers and the subjective experiences of motivation and morale.
- c. Literature Review: A comprehensive review of existing academic literature, case studies, and industry reports will be conducted to gain insights into the current state of knowledge on employee motivation and morale.

3.3 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- a. To explore the factors that contribute to employee motivation and morale in modern workplace settings.
- b. To analyze the impact of different motivational strategies employed by organizations on employee performance and satisfaction.
- c. To understand the role of leadership and organizational culture in fostering a motivational work environment.
- d. To identify challenges and barriers that hinder employee motivation and morale.
- e. To propose practical recommendations for organizations to improve employee motivation and morale.

3.4 RESEARCH DESIGN:

The exploration embraced is distinct examination plan. It includes realities discoveries, asks of various sorts and so on. Expressive exploration studies are those reviews which are worried about depicting the qualities of a specific individual or gathering.

3.5 Type of Research:

QUANTITATIVE Exploration will be finished for the review since expect to assemble a top to bottom comprehension of human way of behaving and the explanation that administers such way of behaving.

3.6 Data Sources

Assortment of information is the essential significance in the exploration cycle. Information, which was gathered for the motivation behind research, helps in legitimate examination, which is useful to proficiently direct exploration. The information source, which is vital in assortment of information is essential information and optional information. Both essential and optional information are thought about for directing the investigation of representative inspiration and moral.

1. Primary source of data

Information is made accessible through interview and surveys. Polls were ready for learners to know the effect and techniques for preparing embraced by association.

2. **Secondary data:** information was gathered from reports, records, Web, organization past records and so on.

3.10 DATA ANALYSIS TOOLS:

Various data analysis tools like SPSS, Graphs & Charts, and Microsoft Excel was used to analyze the data.

4. LIMITATIONS OF STUDY:

While every effort will be made to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the findings, this study may have certain limitations. These may include:

- a. **Sample Size and Generalizability:** The study's findings may be limited to the participants and industries involved, potentially reducing the generalizability to broader populations.
- b. **Self-Reporting Bias:** The data collected through surveys and interviews may be subject to respondents' self-reporting biases, impacting the accuracy of responses.

5. FINDINGS & CONCLUSION:

- The majority of the respondents have emphatically concurred organization completely spurred working spot.
- The majority of the respondents have emphatically concurred organization invests sufficient energy for worker.
- Practically all respondents are persistently train you about how to do the assignment.
- Practically all respondents are happy with the vibe working in center product framework
- innovations.
- As per the greater part of the respondents are concur with the hard working attitudes in the work place.
- The vast majority of the respondents are exceptionally happy with the help the HR division.

6. CONCLUSION:

From the review led, the accompanying ends can be made. The primary asset of Center product framework innovations Human Asset isn't utilized to the degree it Ought to be Center product frameworks having a decent mix of chiefs who can propel the representatives in accomplishing the organization objectives. Be that as it may. There is no straightforward response to the subject of how to inspire individuals Might cash at any point propel? indeed however cash alone isn't sufficient, however it makes a difference. We have talked about a portion of the relevant hypotheses bearing on human inspiration and this is adjusted by a portion of the down to earth factors which can prompt greatness. Human asset stays the point of convergence and initiative the basic part and inspiration needs to be 'custom fitted' to every person.

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HARMONIZING SUCCESS: UNLEASHING THE POTENTIAL OF PERSONAL BRANDING AND ADVERTISEMENTS FOR MUSICIANS

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Abstract

This research delves into the profound impact of personal branding and advertisements on musicians in the music industry, filling a notable gap in the existing literature. Despite the pivotal role of personal branding and advertising in promoting music, a comprehensive understanding of their interrelationship remains limited. Therefore, this study targets individuals associated with the music industry, including professionals, practitioners, and marketing students, to explore the vital connection between personal branding and advertisement effectiveness. Employing a convenience sampling technique, data was collected from a sample size of 132 participants. The Advertising Effectiveness Scale and the Personal Branding Scale were employed to gather relevant data, while analytical methods including correlation and regression analyses were used through SPSS software. The research unequivocally establishes a significant relationship between personal branding and advertisement effectiveness, thus confirming the first hypothesis. Furthermore, the study provides compelling evidence in support of the second hypothesis, indicating that each personal branding variable significantly influences advertisement effectiveness. The study accentuates the crucial role of personal branding in enhancing advertisement effectiveness for artists, producers, marketing professionals, and students involved in the music industry.

Keywords: Personal branding, Advertisements, Music industry, Advertisement effectiveness, Artists

1. Introduction

The music industry (Henry, 2008) is a dynamic dimension of the creative business sector that is based on the production and distribution of music (Music Industry, 2021). It operates through established partner networks between the music production (singers and songwriters), consumer (listeners), and business (labels, managers, and agents) sides (Pastukhov, 2019). The global recorded music industry was valued at \$20 billion in 2019, with forecasts indicating that it will more than double by 2030 (Csathy, 2020). The industry has grown significantly in recent decades as a result of technological advancements that have made the process of creating music more accessible. This has resulted in the emergence of many new artists to compete for market attention (Hracs, 2012). Along with the emergence of new artists, major record labels in the industry have lost power. As technology has enabled artists to remain independent, many of their offerings, such as distribution and marketing, have become less appealing to them. Artists need several strategies in place, as well as a supposedly more entrepreneurial mind-set, in order to sustain a self-sustaining career (Haynes & Marshall, 2018). One of the most challenging problems for artists is expanding their reach and getting their music heard through various marketing activities (Leenders, Farrell, Zwaan & Ter Bogt, 2015). As media and forms of communication evolve, the most effective marketing strategy is constantly evolving (Lieb, 2011). The increased use of social media by the general public is one of the factors influencing marketing strategies. People spent an average of 2 hours and 22 minutes per day on social media in 2019, an increase from 1 hour and 30 minutes per day in 2012 (Salim, 2020). Another factor that happens to coincide with increased social media use is the public's decreasing attention span. Over a 13-year period, the average human attention span has decreased from 12 seconds to an estimated 8 seconds, posing numerous marketing challenges (Subramanian, 2017).

As traditional marketing has become increasingly limited, businesses have recognised the value of content marketing in a digital landscape (Baltés, 2015). In this digital age, marketing strategies must be tailored to the most popular channels. As a result, many people consider content marketing to be the most important and critical tool for a successful and effective marketing campaign (Lieb, 2011). The power of continuous social media presence is undeniable when using content marketing to create and establish oneself as a brand, especially for independent music artists who do not have access to record label resources (Walzer, 2017). Social

media are online platforms that allow for online conversations and interactions, often fostering a content sharing community (Heggde & Shainesh, 2018). These interactive platforms offer a variety of options for how content can be presented, which complicates the communication process for those looking to expand their consumer reach (Muninger, Hammadi & Mahr, 2019).

2. Literature Review

There are two kinds of musicians: those who are signed to record labels and are owned by them through long-term contracts, and those who work independently without the support of a company (Oliver & Green, 2009). Music labels hire producers to gather an artist's talent, create a record, and package the finished product (Perrow, 1974). Furthermore, labels have a multiple-rights contract with artists that allows them to fully control and manage an artist's music distribution, marketing, and promotion (Allen, 2018). They can also decide the artist's musical genre direction, as well as change the entire sound and lyrics of a song (McDonald, 2019). More importantly, labels are frequently prone to changing an artist's physical appearance and persona in order to establish a visual identity that will be admired by a large audience. Music record labels take a significant cut of an artist's earnings in all cases (Negus, 1992). At the same time, there are artists who work independently, usually with self-funding (Oliver and Green, 2009). Macklemore, Frank Ocean, and Chance The Rapper are some examples. In comparison to signed artists, independent artists have complete control over their career choices and keep 100% of their earnings. They are also in charge of handling their own music distribution and promotion. According to Paine (2021), independent artists have outperformed the music industry.

Personal branding is a relatively new literary concept, but it has already been defined in a variety of ways. It is defined as a person's perception of who they are and what qualities and values they possess. A person's personal brand has the power to shape other people's associations and perceptions of them (Rampersad, 2009). Everyone has a personal brand, but how you manage and develop it is critical to reaping the benefits (Peters, 1997; Keller and Lehman, 2006). People appear to be unaware that even ordinary people have a personal brand. Personal branding is frequently associated with well-known people such as athletes, politicians, or artists, but everyone has a brand that they can develop (Labrecque, Markos & Milne, 2011). Most people are unaware that they have a personal brand and thus fail to manage it strategically and effectively (Rampersad, 2009). It is also important to note that a brand, more specifically a brand identity, differs from a brand image. A person or company can manage a brand's identity, but the image is the perception that others have of a brand, which is difficult, if not impossible, to control (Bhasin, 2019.).

Personal branding is concerned with the personality of the person at the heart of the brand. It could be argued that developing a personal brand that is unrelated to some of a person's authentic personality traits would be extremely difficult. Rampersad (2009) describes an authentic personal branding process, emphasizing the importance of knowing oneself and incorporating authentic attributes and characteristics into the branding process. Everyone already has a brand, so they do not need to create one (Ramperstad, 2009). To develop a functional personal brand, one must be authentic and use and emphasise the qualities that they already possess. "If you are 24 and you are not branded authentically, honestly, and holistically, (...) and if you focus primarily on selling, packaging, outward appearances, promoting yourself, and becoming famous, you will be perceived as egocentric and selfish." (Ramperstad 2009)

Managing an artist brand and image

It can be argued that artist brands and images have always existed, but developing and creating them with an intention sometimes surpassing the music itself, has come to the forefront in only the past decades. Technology has played a big part in this development. Videos became a part of music production in the 80's and creating an image seemed to have become more important than the music itself (Negus, 1996). Since the emergence of social media, creating personal images has become important and imperative for an artist's career. It seems that sometimes the importance of music has been underscored so much that there have been attempts on building artist careers prioritizing the construction of a brand image. Nonetheless, the impact of an artist's brand image should not be undermined.

Harrison (2003) considers it important to build a brand for an artist, as the public will always be interested in

the stories of artists. An artist brand introduces you to the inside story and takes you behind-the-scenes. However, she notes that the idea of branding themselves is repellent to some artists and they would rather just make their music. On the other hand, even the artists who are not keen on the idea of branding realize they have to build a name and reputation for themselves in order to attract listeners and create revenue through their music. (Harrison 2003) After all, an artist needs to be able to stand out and get people's attention. Although, the use of the word branding could be reconsidered and telling the story of the artist might be a better approach to some.

Artist branding is often viewed from the perspective of new, young artists. Furthermore, social media has provided an opportunity for anyone to start a career as an artist, but artists and bands that existed before the social media era have had to master the new communications platforms to stay relevant. Staying relevant has become something to think about for many artists (Christian, 2011). Even old well-known rock bands have to think of new ways to present themselves as artists and learn how to use digital platforms to their benefit and to attract new younger listeners. New artists on the other hand, do not have the luxury of an existing brand name, but have to figure out how to stand out and more importantly how to stay in the limelight and not become a one-hit wonder. (Christian, 2011) Therefore, older artists have to think about managing their brand in a new way, as they cannot solely rely on methods used before social media.

Social media provides many possibilities for self-branding with very low cost. In the beginning of the process it can seem like an endless pool of opportunities and creating a brand for oneself can be enjoyable and fulfilling. However, online platforms, such as social media, are open to everyone and it is relatively impossible to control how other people operate on such platforms (Labrecque et al., 2011). Therefore, at some point of the process the information a person has provided of themselves is subject to other people's interpretation and comments, without the author's explicit permission (Labrecque et al., 2011). Behind every brand is a story, which begins from the author of the story, but when the story has gained enough attention it can continue to live on its own (Karhumaa, 2018). The author may not be able to control in which tone the story lives on or if it is developing in the desired direction.

The story can start living on its own at very different points of the brand creation process. Attention can be caught early on, but also lost as fast as it was caught. Nevertheless, when enough attention has risen, the brand creation process turns into brand management. The story behind the brand does no longer require meticulous narration, rather than steering in the right direction and keeping it aligned with the brand image. Gheder (2015) introduces impression management as an art of managing personal brands and explains it as an activity to control information. Personal brands depict a certain image, which is expressed through different pieces of information that are communicated through that brand. Impression management is an activity that aims to influence the audience's perception of a person (Gheder, 2015). Thus, impression management can be considered a part of brand management, albeit the brand image is more difficult to control than the story behind the brand.

Use of Advertisements for Artists

Through the lens of marketing and advertising theories, the usage of advertisements for musicians in the music industry can be understood. Theoretical frameworks give a foundation for understanding how artists might use advertisements to reach their target audience, raise brand awareness, and create cash. This section will provide an overview of key theories and concepts that aid in explaining the role of commercials in promoting music and creating artists' brands.

A brand, according to branding theory, is a collection of connections and feelings that consumers have about a product, service, or person (Kotler et al., 2017). In the music industry, branding is critical for developing a fan base and earning cash. Advertisements have become a crucial tool for constructing an artist's brand, and they play a critical part in raising awareness and defining an artist's brand image (Bauer et al., 2015).

The consumer behaviour theory, which analyses the psychology behind consumer behaviour and decision-making, is another key theory. According to the notion, advertising has a considerable influence on consumer

behaviour when it comes to music consumption (Chung & Cho, 2017). The music industry extensively relies on advertising to influence consumer behaviour, and it has been discovered that music advertisements can considerably affect consumer purchasing decisions. In the music industry, the effectiveness of advertisements is assessed by the number of fans an artist has, the number of albums sold, and the amount of revenue made. Finally, the theoretical foundation for the usage of advertisements for musicians is based on branding and consumer behaviour theories. These theories assist to explain how advertisements can help artists reach their target audience, raise brand awareness, and produce cash.

Research Gap

It appears that having great music is not enough; an artist must also have a strong brand to support the music. Some artists, on the other hand, may not want to think of themselves as brands at all. How does a new popular artist approach the social media branding process? What factors influence their social media posting decisions? From the artist's point of view, how planned and strategic is the process of developing a new artist brand? Artists are rarely branding experts, which can result in a disorganized and unplanned process where the branding strategy is not thoroughly thought out. On the other hand, the absence of an uncontrolled process can lead to greater artistic freedom and strengthen the artist brand.

With the research objectives being as:

- To examine whether there is a positive correlation between personal branding and advertising effectiveness in the industry.
- To examine whether there is a significant influence of each personal branding variable on advertisement effectiveness.

3. Research Methodology

There exist very little literature with regards to correlates between personal branding and advertisement. There is also little to no evidence of understanding advertisement effectiveness for promoting music. This research also gives more clarity to music artists on their brand perception and how they can use personal branding to improve effectiveness of advertisements. The targeted population consists of individuals from both genders, from age 20-60, from all over the world. The sample size for this study was 132 participants since a large sample size is required to obtain statically significant results, hence the responses were analysed based on 132 participants. Advertising Effectiveness Scale (Sachdeva, 2015), and Personal Branding scale (Gorbatov et al., 2019) were used for collecting data.

Hypothesis

H1: There exists a correlation between the Personal Branding & Advertising Effectiveness.

H2: There is a significant influence of each personal branding variable on advertisement effectiveness.

H3: Personal Branding has a stronger impact on Advertisement Effectiveness than demographic variables, such as age and gender.

4. Results & Discussion

The average age of the responders is roughly 34 years old, with a standard deviation of 13 years. The youngest respondent is 20 years old, while the oldest is 60 years old. The bulk of respondents are in their 20s and 30s. The data displays a slight positive skew, indicating that respondents are younger on average. The data has a confidence level of 95%, indicating that there is a high degree of certainty that the data is representative of the population.

Pearson's Correlation between Personal Branding and Effective Advertisement

Effective Advertisement

Personal Branding

EA (Pearson Correlation)	1	.424**
Significance (2-tailed)		.000
PB (Pearson Correlation)	.424**	1
Significance (2-tailed)	.000	

**p<0.01

Source: SPSS

With a correlation coefficient (r) of 0.424 and a p-value of 0.000, the results demonstrated a statistically significant moderate positive correlation between personal branding and advertisement effectiveness. The correlation value (r) of 0.424 indicates a moderately positive relationship between personal branding and advertising effectiveness. This means that as personal branding grows, so does advertisement effectiveness. The correlation coefficient's positive sign implies that the two variables are moving in the same direction.

The association between personal branding and effective advertisements is statistically significant, with a p-value of .000. This suggests there is significant evidence that there is a relationship between these two variables, and that the association is unlikely to be caused by chance alone.

A favourable relationship between personal branding and effective advertisements shows that having a strong personal brand is related with more effective advertisements. This could be due to the fact that a well-established personal brand can help to generate trust and credibility with consumers, increasing their likelihood of responding positively to advertisements.

Similarly, good marketing can help to improve a personal brand by raising brand awareness and recognition among potential consumers.

It should be noted, however, that correlation does not always imply causality. While a significant correlation indicates that these factors are related, it does not prove that one causes the other. Further research would be required to establish a relationship between personal branding and effective advertising. Finally, the high association between personal branding and effective advertising implies that these factors are most likely related. Marketers and artists wanting to build strong brands and make more effective advertisements may find this knowledge beneficial.

Regression Analysis

Personal branding is an important factor of success in the music industry, and understanding its components is critical in developing a brand that distinguishes an artist from their competitors. The Personal Branding Scale (PBS) is a tool derived from a prior study to quantify the success of personal branding, and it outlines three critical aspects for developing a strong personal brand: strategy, differentiation, and tech-savvy. The Personal Branding Scale was developed (Gorbatov, S., N. Khapova, S., & I. Lysova, E.) and went through Exploratory and Confirmatory Factor Analysis. The exploratory factor analysis produced a three-factor structure with 18 items (EFA). Cronbach's alphas for the three components were 0.80, 0.83, and 0.90, all of which were greater than the acceptable cutoff limit of 0.70. The three factors explained 58.7% of the variance, with correlations of 0.46, 0.53, and 0.61 (p 0.001) indicating their distinctness. Furthermore, a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) on the sample confirmed the three-factor model, with acceptable fit indices ($\chi^2/df = 4.02$; NFI = 0.92; IFI =

0.94; TLI = 0.93; CFI = 0.94; and RMSEA = 0.06, where $p_{close} < 0.001$) with all of the standardised regression weights being more than 0.50.

The strategy element, which refers to an artist's ability to build a clear and consistent branding strategy that matches with their aims and vision, is an important component of personal branding. A well-defined plan can assist an artist in developing a strong and engaging personal brand that resonates with fans and distinguishes them from the competition. The differentiating element emphasises an artist's distinct qualities and characteristics that set them apart from other artists in the industry. This component is critical in developing a distinct brand identity that can assist an artist in standing out and attracting fans. Finally, the tech-savvy factor is an important aspect of personal branding because it focuses on an artist's capacity to effectively use technology in promoting their brand. To maximise their reach and effect in today's digital world, artists must be skilled in social media, online marketing, and other digital tools.

Regression analysis is performed to discover which of these elements has the greatest influence on advertising effectiveness. Regression analysis lets researchers establish the degree and direction of the relationship between variables, allowing them to pinpoint which component has the most impact on advertising effectiveness.

Table 5.5
Regression: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimates
1	.420 ^a	.177	.170	5.607

a. Predictors: (Constant), ST

Source: SPSS

Table 5.6

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
1	Regression	877.693	1	877.693	27.923	.000 ^b

Residual	4086.277	130	31.433
<hr/>			
Total	4963.970	131	

- a. *Dependent Variable: EA*
- b. *Predictors: (Constant), ST*

Source: SPSS

The correlation coefficient between ST and EA is 0.420, indicating a moderately positive association between the two variables, according to the model summary table. The coefficient of determination (R-squared) value of 0.177 indicates that the predictor variable, ST, can explain 17.7% of the variation in advertisement effectiveness.

The ANOVA table adds to the information supporting the hypothesis. According to the F-statistic of 27.923 and the corresponding p-value of 0.000, the model with ST as a predictor variable explains a significant percentage of the variance in EA. This shows that personal branding strategy has a statistically significant effect on the success of advertisements in the music industry.

Overall, the findings indicate that personal branding strategy is an essential element of personal branding, in predicting advertisement effectiveness in the music industry, with a positive association between personal branding strategy and advertising effectiveness.

The correlational analysis results show that there is a significant positive relationship between personal branding and advertising effectiveness in the music industry. Personal branding is a crucial aspect in producing successful advertising campaigns that resonate with a target audience, according to the statistically significant Pearson correlation coefficients. This finding has significant implications for musicians in the music industry. Artists can create a distinct and distinct identity that sets them apart from their rivals by focusing on developing their personal brand. This, in turn, can assist them in developing more successful advertising strategies capable of engaging their target demographic and driving sales.

A musician, for example, who concentrates on developing a strong personal brand based on their distinct musical style, image, and beliefs is more likely to produce advertising campaigns that connect with their target audience on a deeper level. Artists can appeal to their followers' emotions, beliefs, and values by crafting advertisements that coincide with their personal brand, making their music and brand more appealing to their target audience.

Furthermore, the positive relationship between personal branding and advertising effectiveness shows that musicians who invest in creating their personal brand are more likely to succeed in the music industry. Artists can differentiate themselves from their competitors, attract new followers, and build a loyal following by developing a strong personal brand, ultimately leading to higher success and financial rewards. Additionally, the outcomes of this study emphasise the significance of personal branding in developing effective advertising efforts in the music industry. Artists who want to create effective advertising campaigns should concentrate on developing a strong personal brand that connects with their target audience. As a result, they will be able to design more successful advertising campaigns, gain new fans, and boost their overall performance in the

industry.

According to the findings of the regression analysis, personal branding has a substantial impact on the effectiveness of advertising. The three personal branding factors - strategy, differentiation, and tech savvy - were specifically examined to establish their impact on advertising performance. The findings revealed that strategy influenced advertising effectiveness more than the other two components. This information is especially useful for artists and marketers looking to improve their advertising effectiveness in the music industry.

They may be able to boost the impact of their advertising campaigns by highlighting and strengthening their own branding approach. Personal branding strategy may include establishing and communicating a distinctive value proposition, developing a consistent brand image, and employing focused marketing methods to attract specific consumers. While the findings indicate that strategy is the most essential aspect in personal branding for advertising effectiveness, it is vital to highlight that differentiation and tech savvy may still play important roles in some cases. As a result, while designing personal branding and advertising strategies in the music industry, artists and marketers should carefully evaluate all three variables. Furthermore, the findings emphasise the significance of personal branding for musicians and marketers in the music industry. They can improve the success of their advertising efforts by focusing on building a strong personal brand strategy. This can include promoting crucial components of their personal brand in their advertising campaigns, such as their unique selling points, values, and personality. Additionally, the findings show that artists and marketers should prioritise personal branding methods that emphasise differentiation, as well as being technologically savvy, because these qualities had a substantial positive link with advertising performance. Nonetheless, strategy was discovered to have the biggest influence on advertising effectiveness, showing that a well-planned and implemented personal branding strategy may have the greatest impact on advertising success. Overall, the findings of this study can provide significant insights for artists and marketers trying to improve the effectiveness of their advertising efforts in the music industry. They can better connect with their target audience and achieve higher advertising success by designing and implementing a strong personal branding approach that stresses differentiation, tech-savvy, and overall strategy. The study's findings back up the notion that personal branding has a greater impact on marketing effectiveness than demographic variables like age and gender. These findings are consistent with previous research emphasizing the significance of personal branding for musicians and other artists. Since personal branding has a large positive impact on advertisement success, artists in the music industry should focus on creating a strong personal brand in order to improve the effectiveness of their advertising efforts. This could include creating a distinct style or image that distinguishes the artist from others in the industry, as well as communicating with fans on social media and other online channels. The non-significant impact of gender and age on advertisement effectiveness, on the other hand, shows that artists may not need to worry as much about demographic factors when creating their advertising strategies. While demographic factors may have a role in the efficiency of advertising campaigns in other industries, such as fashion or beauty, the findings imply that they may not be as essential for artists. Overall, the findings indicate that personal branding is an essential aspect in the promotional effectiveness of artists. Future research could look into additional aspects that may influence advertisement effectiveness, such as the style of music or the target audience, to further enhance the understanding of what makes advertising campaigns successful for artists. The study found a correlation between personal branding and advertising effectiveness in the music industry. The findings revealed that personal branding, namely the strategy portion, has a big influence in affecting advertising performance by applying the Personal Branding Scale, which consists of three factors: strategy, differentiated, and tech-savvy. According to the study, having a well-defined personal branding plan is more effective than simply having a distinct or technologically savvy personal brand. This study is especially useful for artists and marketers since it presents empirical evidence for the relevance of personal branding. Personal branding has a greater impact on advertisement success than demographic variables such as age and gender. As a result, this research encourages artists and marketers to move their focus away from demographic factors and towards personal branding. The importance of having a well-defined personal branding plan is one of the study's main outcomes. Marketers and artists should collaborate to develop a strong and consistent brand image that reflects the artist's values and musical style. According to the study, having a consistent and well-planned brand strategy can lead to enhanced advertising effectiveness, resulting in increased engagement and sales. Artists and marketers can use the Personal Branding Scale to

assess which areas of their personal branding are strong and which need to be improved. An artist, for example, may discover that they have a great brand distinctiveness but lack a defined approach. They can then focus on building a strategy to increase their personal branding and, as a result, the efficacy of their advertising. Moreover, the study emphasises the usefulness of social media platforms as a tool for personal branding and marketing effectiveness. Social media is a strong tool for building an artist's brand image and promoting their music. Social media should be used by artists to communicate with their audience, share their music, and grow their own brand. They can enhance their reach and engagement as a result, resulting in increased advertising effectiveness. It's also worth noting that personal branding is an ongoing process that necessitates consistent effort and attention. Artists and marketers should examine and adjust their personal branding approach on a regular basis to ensure that it matches with their changing values and goals. In conclusion, the study has proved the significance of personal branding in the music industry, as well as its favourable link with advertising effectiveness. Marketers and artists can use this knowledge to develop a well-defined personal branding plan that corresponds with the artist's values and music style, as well as to communicate with their followers and promote their music via social media platforms. They can boost the effectiveness of their advertising, resulting in more engagement and revenue. Personal branding is a continual process that takes ongoing effort and attention, and artists and marketers must constantly analyse and adjust their personal branding approach to ensure its effectiveness.

5. Conclusion

The study's findings indicate a significant relationship between personal branding and advertising effectiveness in the music industry, verifying the first hypothesis. This emphasises the significance of building and maintaining a strong personal brand for artists seeking to improve the success of their advertising efforts. The second hypothesis is similarly supported, suggesting that each personal branding variable, namely strategy, differentiation, and technological savvy, has a considerable influence on advertisement performance. This underlines the need of a well-thought-out personal branding plan that distinguishes oneself from other artists and makes appropriate use of technology to maximise advertising efficacy. Personal branding appears to have a greater impact on advertisement effectiveness than demographic variables such as age and gender, verifying the third hypothesis. This emphasises the need of prioritizing personal branding initiatives rather than relying simply on demographic characteristics to drive advertising success.

Ultimately, the study finds that personal branding is an important component of advertising effectiveness in the music industry and that it should be valued by both artists and marketers. According to the results, investing in establishing a strong personal brand through a differentiated and tech-savvy approach can lead to increased advertising effectiveness. The findings of this study can be used by artists and marketers to design effective personal branding tactics and advertisements targeted to their target audience, as well as to prioritise their personal branding efforts over demographic variables such as age

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“Impact of workplace happiness among Employee Job Satisfaction” Conceptual Study

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Abstract

Happiness at the workplace refers to how satisfied people are with their work and lives. The idea of happiness is related to individual's subjective well-being. Happiness at the workplace is crucial for improving productivity in any organization. Happy people are productive people while those people who are unhappy may not pay full attention to any task. Some scholars believe that organizations which are able to maintain long-term happiness at the workplace could probably increase and sustain productivity. Therefore, they should know what factors could affect employee happiness in order to effectively enhance happiness at the workplace. But research on employee happiness was rarely seen in the past. The issue of happiness at the workplace needs to be properly conceptualized so that useful research on it could be conducted. This paper presents a potential conceptual framework of happiness at the workplace that could give valuable contribution to future research in this area.

Keywords: conceptual framework, happiness, subjective well-being, workplace

1. Introduction

Work is one of important aspects of people's lives (Dulk, Groeneveld, Ollier-Malaterre, & Valcour, 2013). People perform their work in exchange for either monetary (e.g. salary and benefits) or non-monetary rewards (e.g. psychological fulfillment from work) (Stiglbauer & Batinic, 2012). In today's changing world, the world of work has been changing rapidly (Baran, Shanock, & Miller, 2012; Quinlan, 2012). The changing work environments (e.g. the increasing internationalization of business, new technology, and new organizational practices) lead to the changing nature of work (Connell, Gough, McDonnell, & Burgess, 2014; Koukoulaki, 2010). Nature of work is defined as “the actual content of the job or work characteristics” (Benrazavi & Silong, 2013, p. 129). From human resource management (HRM) perspective, HRM practices (e.g. downsizing, outsourcing, and temporary employment) influence the nature and scope of work (Colakoglu, Lepak, & Hong, 2006). Corporate restructuring and downsizing which aim to reduce the workforce for improving organizational performance probably can make employees feel unsatisfied with their jobs (Klehe, Zikic, Van Vianen, & De Pater, 2011). Employees who perceive job insecurity have lower commitment to their organizations and they intend to leave their jobs (Silla, Gracia, Mañas, & Peiró, 2010). Employees' job satisfaction has an impact on organizational performance (Dalal, Baysinger, Brummel, & Lebreton, 2012). If they are satisfied with work, their productivity would be increased (Barmby, Bryson, & Eberth, 2012).

Generally, employers expect a high level of performance and productivity from their employees (Thompson & Goodale, 2006; Samnani & Singh, 2014). Most companies need productive workers to work for them so as they could attain organizational goals (Chong & Eggleton, 2007; Hales & Williamson, 2010). Many companies used managerial tools for the purpose of increasing productivity (Salis & Williams, 2010; Samnani & Singh, 2014). The studies by Salis and Williams (2010), Samnani and Singh (2014), and Tabassi and Abu Bakar (2009) considered HRM practices (e.g. compensation system, face-to-face communication) as the means to increase productivity. Moreover, maintaining happiness at the workplace can increase employees' productivity (Quick & Quick, 2004). The previous studies (e.g. Quick & Quick, 2004; Rego & Cunha, 2008) state that happy employees are productive employees. Conversely, unhappiness at the workplace reduces productivity (Fereidouni, Najdi, & Amiri, 2013). The happiness issues have been widely studied in various fields such as philosophy, religion, psychology, sociology, and economics (Aydin, 2012). The term “happiness” has been discussed by many scholars (Björke, 2012; Johnston, Luciano, Maggiori, Ruch, & Rossier, 2013). “Happiness” is universal to all people in every culture because everybody searches for happiness (Aydin, 2012; Fisher, 2010). It is related to an individual's subjective well-being (Angner, Hullett, & Allison, 2011; Jiang, Lu, & Sato, 2012) or life satisfaction (Van Praag, Romanov, & Ferrer-i-Carbonell, 2010). There is a close relationship between job and life satisfaction (Saari & Judge, 2004). Job satisfaction affects life satisfaction while life satisfaction also affects job satisfaction (Saari & Judge, 2004). Thus,

happiness at the workplace refers to an individual's work and life satisfaction, or subjective well-being at the workplace (Bhattacharjee & Bhattacharjee, 2010; Carleton, 2009). In this paper, the two terms "happiness" and "subjective well-being" are used interchangeably (Frey & Stutzer, 2000a).

Whereas happiness at the workplace is important to both individuals and organizations (Fisher, 2010; Simmons, 2014), the research on employee happiness in organizations is limited (Fisher, 2010; Hosie, Willemys, & Sevastos, 2012; Sloan, 2005). It should be investigated further in order to provide sufficient knowledge to academics, practitioners, and those who are interested in the notion of happiness at the workplace (Hosie et al., 2012; Sloan, 2005). This paper therefore develops a conceptual framework of happiness at the workplace that could be used for conducting the research on this area. It begins with conceptual framework. It is then followed by discussion, and conclusion respectively.

2. Research Methodology

The research methodology for this study incorporated an examination of various sources such as books and journal articles that discuss happiness in general and organizational strategies for fostering an appropriate environment. Additionally, several studies, such as Bader et al. (2013), Petchsawang and Duchon (2009), and Dimitrov (2012) that provide evidence-based practices for companies are discussed in this paper. These works help understand the concept of happiness and its correlation with interpersonal relationships such as friendships and communication, as well as its connection with organizational attitudes and values.

3. Concept of Happiness at Work

Given that it is not a new trend, happiness as a concept has continually gained attention, hence growing global popularity. Previous, most of the human resource (HR) personnel functions revolved around the practice of employee motivation. Currently, the functions stretch beyond financial operations to include the workforces' overall well-being in the workplace. The study by Al Maktoum (2017) indicated that there is a difference between societal and personal happiness. Also, it was indicated that happiness constitutes a state in which members of the team feel comfortable, secure, and safe in a given setting; including the workplace. Should a firm provide room for the team members to maintain desirable levels of well-being, the workforces are likely to be more involved or engaged in work activities. Also, happiness is seen as a spiritual aspect through which team members are keen to realize higher-level transcendence, as well as deeper self-knowledge and meaning. (Petchsawang & Duchon, 2009, p. 460). By finding meaning and understanding one's purpose in a given scenario, happiness ensures that the individuals (such as employees gain motivation towards successful and effective role performance, as well as task completion.

A. Importance and Application of the Topic

Given the stiff competition and state of economic uncertainty, workplace happiness has gained growing attention in organizations. Currently, the need for team leaders to ensure that there is employee (Dimitrov, 2012). Specifically, happy team members have been documented to be better placed to understand their roles and responsibilities, as well as participate in the required tasks

actively. Such employees feel involved and also responsible. This observation points to the criticality of ensuring that the workforces are well motivated and inspired towards realizing new achievements in the organizations to which they are attached. The eventuality is that happy employees are better placed to realize successful problem-solving. It is also worth noting that the motivation of employees, which tends to make them happy, needs to be both non-material and financial; especially by assuming paths through which the team members could anticipate personality development and career advancement.

It is also worth indicating that happiness in the workplace applies to different scenarios. The scenarios range from first-line workers to the managers and other senior leaders. In the study by Bader, Hashim, and Zaharim (2013), the main aim was to find out the role of workplace friendship in shaping operations among employees in the banking sector. In the findings, it was reported that when positive interpersonal relationships are emphasized, the employees feel motivated and engaged. However, the authors cautioned that several factors play a moderating or predictive role in shaping this relationship. Factors that were documented include education level, gender, and age. In particular, it was established that male employees are more likely to embrace friendships in the workplace than their female counterparts. These results concurred with those that were reported by Bader et al. (2013), who noted further that further that employees who are aged 40 and above are more likely to embrace friendships in the workplace.

Regarding the parameter of education level, most of the current literature contends that individuals with secondary education tend to establish more friendships than their counterparts with higher education diplomas. Hence, the insights point to the need for further research about the role of different demographic features in shaping workplace happiness. Furthermore, the examinations aid in establishing or developing and implementing relevant strategies through which happiness in the workplace could be improved, having understood major factors that play a positive and predictive role in realize the state of happiness; a predictor of improved productivity.

B. Advantages

From the literature, happiness in the workplace poses several beneficial effects. The effects range from physical to social aspects (Al Maktoum, 2017, p. 23). Particularly, happy employees are more likely to be inspired to accommodate changes in the workplace, besides understanding and accomplishing the roles and responsibilities expected of them. Also, companies that cater for the well-being of their employees gain benefits by achieving an atmosphere marked by respect and trust, besides team-work and idea sharing. Also, happy employees are more likely to give opinion during team sessions as they feel valued and anticipate reinforcements. It is also worth indicating that a friendly workplace environment, a product of employee happiness paves the way for high-quality communication and socialization. Similarly, happiness ensures that the target personnel are attentive to instructions and comply with privacy and work-balance requirements. Overall, the members feel relaxed because of the resultant work-life balance in which adequate time is spent both in the workplace and home settings.

Another beneficial effect with which workplace happiness is associated involves the realization of corporate spiritual values. According to Pawar (2008), happiness allows for connectedness in the workplace, hence harmony among team members. In addition, there is likely to be superior performance among happy employees because happiness reduces turnover rates and, instead, increases firm profitability (Pawar, 2008, p. 558). Hence, happiness in the workplace is seen to introduce a sense of purpose in which workforces feel relevant and also perceive their contribution to the organization as that which is well acknowledged (Liu & Robertson, 2011).

C. Disadvantages

Separate employee welfare programs are a good initiative, but they cannot provide the desired effect. Instead, it is critical to follow a systematic approach to introducing employee happiness initiatives and assessing their results. It will not only allow adjusting the process of working with employees but also to monitor the effectiveness of initiatives and business benefits. In order not to turn well-being management into an excessively tense HR activity, interviews with employees seem to be helpful to determine priorities and expected benefits. Since many companies fail to properly plan and introduce workplace happiness programs, the identified issue can be considered a disadvantage. It is recommended to develop a comprehensive program and involve the company's top management in its implementation.

The second disadvantage may be determined as a lack of attention paid to taking care of the financial well-being of employees. It is significant to keep in mind that although happiness is not about money, employees should be able to cover their basic needs, pay for housing, relax, have desired leisure activities, and take care of their health (Samnani & Singh, 2014). It seems essential to point out the fact that in an attempt to ensure that employees have non-monetary compensation, many companies fail to pay fair and competitive remuneration. Therefore, it is critical to provide people with decent wages, educate them on financial literacy, and form a fund to help those who are in a difficult financial situation.

Another possible demerit is that productivity is relative and is likely to vary based on predictive factors such as employee competency, skill, and knowledge. According to Thompson and Goodale (2006), employees exhibiting lower productivity, upon being underestimated, could cause scheduling errors. Hence, planning and implementing employee happiness programs calls for the strengths and weaknesses with which each individual comes in the workplace; rather than implement a standard program. Hence, implementing standard employee happiness programs poses a dilemma because the decision is unlikely to appeal to all members of the team, especially because most of the current organizations house multicultural teams with each team members embracing varying needs and preferences – on what makes them happy (or otherwise).

4. Conceptual Framework

This paper focused on happiness at individual level (i.e. happiness of individual employees). Based on the literature

review (e.g. Angner et al., 2011; Demir, Özen, Doğan, Bilyk, & Tyrell, 2011; Mohanty, 2009; Tadić, Bakker, & Oerlemans, 2013), happiness constructs at the workplace were identified. The interrelations between construct categories (such as employment status, income, friendship, and work activities) and happiness were supported by the previous studies (see Table 1).

Table 1. Happiness constructs at the workplace

Table 1. Happiness constructs at the workplace

Construct category	Findings	References to support the findings
Employment status	Full-time employment contributes to employee's happiness positively.	Mohanty (2009)
	Unemployment brings unhappiness to people.	Alesina, Di Tella and MacCulloch (2004) Ohtake (2012)
	Unemployment is negatively related to subjective well-being.	Dolan, Peasgood and White (2008)
	Voluntary part-time employees are happier than full-time employees.	Nikolova and Graham (2014) Tsou and Liu (2001) Pouwels, Siegers and Vlasblom (2008) Selim (2008) Biswas-Diener, Vittersø and Diener (2010) Knabe and Rätzel (2010)
Income	Individuals' personal income affects their happiness.	Angner et al. (2011) Campbell (2013)
		Hamilton (2007) Demir et al. (2011) Naff (2012)
		Bader, Hashim and Zaharim (2013) Snow (2013) Waryszak and King (2001) Tadić et al. (2013)
Friendship	Positive friendship at the workplace influences employee happiness	
Work activities	Specific work activities are positively associated with happiness. Individuals are happy when they perceive that their job duties are significant.	Golparvar and Abedini (2014)

The above-mentioned constructs are the key factors which influence happiness at the workplace. This paper assumed that these factors can make employees happy, which in turn their performance would be improved (Atkinson & Hall, 2011). However, people in each region (e.g. Asia and Europe) or in each culture have their own philosophy of happiness (Schwartz, 2007; Trung, Cheong, Nghi, & Kim, 2013). This paper presents a conceptual framework which is composed of independent variables (employment status, income, friendship, and work activities), dependent variable (happiness at the workplace), and moderating variable (cultural values) (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. A conceptual framework of happiness at the workplace

Happiness at the workplace is hypothesized to be influenced by several factors such as employment status, income, friendship, and work activities. The relationship between these factors and happiness at the workplace is moderated by cultural values.

Employment Status

Employment status refers to an employment-related situation in which an individual is being held (Foroutan, 2011). Individuals' happiness depends on their employment status (Frey & Stutzer, 2000b; Ha & Kim, 2013) (e.g. employed or unemployed (Jiang et al., 2012), full-time or part-time employment (Berger, 2009)). Employees usually seek for employment security (Silla, De Cuyper, Gracia, Peiró, & De Witte, 2009). Unemployment status makes people unhappy (Escott & Buckner, 2013). Their experience of unemployment or fear of unemployment can reduce happiness (Ohtake, 2012). Particularly, individuals who value family relationships may be more unhappy with unemployment status if it causes their family difficulties (Campbell, 2013). A number of studies have confirmed that unemployment affects happiness, but part-time and full-time employment that may affect employee happiness are needed to be investigated further (Berger, 2009). A study of maternal employment and happiness by Berger (2009) states that part-time employees have lower life satisfaction than full-time employees. Nevertheless, voluntary part-time employees who choose not to work full-time are happier than those full-time employees (Nikolova & Graham, 2014).

Income

Income includes the wage and salary income earned by an individual (Mathur, 2012). A study of income and happiness by Caporale, Georgellis, Tsitsianis and Yin (2009) confirms that there is a strong relationship between a person's income and life satisfaction. This is because people who have higher income have more opportunities to buy desired goods and services (Frey & Stutzer, 2002; Schnittker, 2008). Even though people who gain higher income seem to be happier people, their happiness level is affected by working hours (Binswanger, 2006; Paul & Guilbert, 2013). People may be unsatisfied with their jobs if they have long working hours (Georgellis, Lange, & Tabvuma, 2012).

Furthermore, people compare their own income with others (Lembregts & Pandelaere, 2014; Oshio & Kobayashi, 2011). They are likely to be happy when they perceive income equality (De Prycker, 2010). Oshio and Kobayashi (2011) contend that individuals who experience income inequality are less happy. In contrast, Hopkins (2008) argues that income inequality can positively affect happiness of some competitive people who gain more income than others. This is because competitive people try to make the difference between their own and others' rewards (Brody, 2010). They may be happy with higher income even if it is unequal to those people (Hopkins, 2008)

Friendship

Friendship is defined as a close relationship among friends (Huang, 2008). People express their friendship through emotion and behavior (Huang, 2008; Spencer, 2012). Friendship at the workplace refers to individuals' friendship with their peers, subordinates, and superiors (Austin, 2009; Lee, 2005; Mao & Hsieh, 2012). Friendship at the

workplace has a positive impact on organizational productivity and employees' work attitudes towards their jobs (Song, 2005). Many studies show the link between interpersonal relationship and happiness (Demir & Davidson, 2013; Søraker, 2012; Westaway, Olorunju, & Rai, 2007). Positive friendship not only influences happiness of employees but also affects productivity (Bader et al., 2013). Friendship groups are more committed to their work and lead to higher productivity (Dotan, 2007). Employees who have meaningful friendship are happier than those who are alone (Snow, 2013). Consistently, Wright (2005) asserts that lonely people are less happy. People who have significant friendships may be happy because good friends are willing to behave positively to each other (Simon, Judge, & Halvorsen-Ganepola, 2010). It should be highlighted that happy employees are mostly sociable people who have more friends (Ganser, 2012).

Work Activities

Work activities are the activities or duties that are performed by workers (Siccama, 2006). Some workers are happy with their work activities while some workers have negative experiences at work (Siegall & McDonald, 2004). Individual could have different levels of happiness during different work activities (Tadić et al., 2013). They may happy to perform specific work activities (Tadić et al., 2013; Waryszak & King, 2001). Martin (2008) argues that people feel happy when they pursue meaningful activities. Thus, managers should know how to manage the meaning of work for employees (Cleavenger & Munyon, 2013; Vasconcelos, 2008). If employees perceive significance and meaning of work, they may be happy to do their work (Dimitrov, 2012; MacMillan, 2009).

Cultural Values

Cultural values are "belief systems that a society is committed to and that are handed down from one generation to the next" (Hassan, 2011, p. 111). A study by Downie, Koestner and Chua (2007) presents that cultural values can support an individual's self-determination to the happiness in diverse countries. The study shows the mean level differences of happiness across countries (Downie et al., 2007). Similarly, this paper assumed that the above-mentioned factors (employment status, income, friendship, and work activities) do not have the same effect to employee happiness in different cultures. The conceptions of happiness may vary among different societies or cultures (Lu, Gilmour, & Kao, 2001). People from different cultures (e.g. Western and Eastern cultures) value different things (Goos, 2012; Lee, Scandura & Sharif, 2014). Western cultural values are mainly focused on individualism that views each individual as an autonomous person (Cho, Thyroff, Rapert, Part, & Lee, 2013; Goh, Lee, & Salleh, 2009). Individualistic people place a high value on self-interests and personal goals (Rego & Cunha, 2009). Hence, their happiness is based on personal factors (e.g. personal attitudes and beliefs) (Ram, 2010). Eastern cultural values are emphasized on collectivism (Shao & Skarlicki, 2014). In collectivistic societies, group goals are more important than personal goals (Zhang, Van Doorn, & Leeftang, 2014). They believe that an individual's personal goals should not threaten group harmony (Ayçiçeği-Dinn & Caldwell-Harris, 2011). However, individuals can have both Eastern and Western cultures since they are exposed to one another's culture in their everyday lives (Leung, Hou, Gati, & Li, 2011; Parker, Haytko, & Hermans, 2009).

5. Discussion

Employees are happy when they experience stable employment (Scherer, 2009). Permanent employees seem to be more satisfied with their jobs than temporary employees (Ong & Shah, 2012; Scherer, 2009). Sora, Caballer and Peiró (2010) maintain that temporary employees perceive a high level of job insecurity. Unstable employment not only makes employees feel unhappy but also affects the rate of employee turnover and organizational performance (Dike, 2011). This is because temporary employees are more likely to intend to leave their jobs than permanent employees (Sora et al., 2010).

Many studies (e.g. Gebremariam, Gebremedhin, & Schaeffer, 2010; Rotaru, 2014) show the link between employment and income growth. Employment can be considered as an important source of income (Zuvekas & Hill, 2000). People who have better employment status (i.e. stable employment) gain higher income (Shlay, Weinraub, Harmon, & Tran, 2004). They may be happier than those who have lower employment status and gain lower income (Caporale et al., 2009). Furthermore, it should be noted that self-employed people seem to be more satisfied with work than those who are employed in organizations (Benz & Frey, 2008). Employed and self-employed people have different work processes that might have an impact to their happiness level (Benz & Frey, 2008). As a result, this paper views work activities as one of happiness constructs. People find the kinds of work tasks that are matched with their interests (Porfeli & Mortimer, 2010). The individuals' interests can be concerned with meaning of work

(Michaelson, 2011). Some people are probably happy to pursue the meaningful work (Grady & McCarthy, 2008). An understanding of factors contributing to meaning of work is useful for the organizations to provide employees with meaningful work (Michaelson, Pratt, Grant, & Dunn, 2014).

In addition to the three happiness constructs mentioned earlier, people value friendship at the workplace as important to their work life (Mao, Hsieh, & Chen, 2012). Friendship at the workplace facilitates the exchange of resources and ideas among employees (Chang, 2013; D'Cruz & Noronha, 2011). It enhances employees' attitudes towards work and work performance (Lin, 2010). Employees who are happy with work and have positive friendships at the workplace are less likely to leave their jobs (Dike, 2011). However, Mao and Hsieh (2012) argue that employees with different work levels may differ in friendship expectation. Higher-level employees had lower expectation for friendship at work (Mao & Hsieh, 2012). Thus, employees performing different work levels could differ in happiness of friendship as well.

Maintaining employee happiness is necessary to ensure availability of workforce (Asiyabi & Mirabi, 2012; Lindorff, 2010). According to the changing world of work, most employees change their jobs several times (Clarke, 2007; Sun & Wang, 2011). Many organizations have difficulties retaining the high talent employees who have high potential to accomplish organizational goals (Chaudhry & Shah, 2011; Kumar & Dhamodaran, 2013). It can be said that enhancing happiness at the workplace is a challenge for maximizing organizational productivity (Chaudhry & Shah, 2011).

6. Conclusion

In this paper, the relationship between independent variables and happiness at the workplace is hypothesized to be moderated by cultural values. Employee happiness may differ in different cultural contexts. The research on happiness issues should be explored further to include diverse cultures as well as various types of organizations (Sloan, 2005). Since the notion of happiness is crucial for organizational performance and productivity, HR managers need to design and manage a workplace to enhance employee happiness (Gavin & Mason, 2004; Rego & Cunha, 2008). Happy employees bring their happiness from the office to their home; likewise they also transfer their happiness from their home to the office (Asiyabi & Mirabi, 2012). This suggests that there is a possible close interrelation between an individual's work and life.

Acknowledgments

We would like to express our special thanks to Prince of Songkla University (PSU), Pattani Campus and Universiti Utara Malaysia (UUM) for providing us with necessary resources. We also would like to thank the staff and lecturers for all their help and support.

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A STUDY ON REVERSE VENDING MACHINES

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Abstract

Waste generation is increasing at a very high rate across the globe. **Waste management** is the way to manage garbage and trash from the moment its generated to the time of their disposal. A large percentage of the waste generated across the globe comprises solid waste. **The solid waste** consists of paper, glass materials and ceramics, plastic waste and materials like tin or metal. A Reverse Vending Machine is an automated device that takes plastic bottles and aluminium cans, and in return, it rewards the user monetarily as money, vouchers, or e-wallet money. The main purpose of this research paper is to critically analyse and evaluate the product and the market and industry. The study analysed the scope of the product in the market, market statistics, various factors that could potentially scale up the growth of the product, problems faced in the implementation of the machine, and secondary and primary data were used to analyse the awareness about the product and its potential in the market. The data showed promising results in favour of the product, and the results showed that the product has great potential to scale up growth in the future as countries and governments are moving towards **sustainability** and the increasing trend of the **circular economy** helps in driving the growth of the product.

Keywords: Waste Generation, Waste Management, Solid Waste, Sustainability, Circular Economy

Introduction

Waste is being generated at a skyrocketing pace across the world, which necessitates the need to have a proper management system for waste. Managing waste is the way or systematic process of managing garbage and trash from the time of manufacture to the time of its disposal. Mostly solid waste management. A large percentage of the waste generated across the globe comprises solid waste. Solid waste consists of paper, glass material and ceramic, plastic waste also tin and metals. Solid waste generation stands at a rate of 160,000 Tonnes Per Day. Overseas competitors have developed creative techniques to dispose and recycle solid waste, notably plastics. Whereas India's recycling techniques are limited and scarce. The manual recycling process which is existing currently needs the user to transport all the garbage in bulk into the recycling facility which can prove to be inconvenient and might be a hassle. Thus, it can prove to be a discouraging factor for them to recycle waste.

A Reverse Vending Machine is an automated device that takes in plastic bottles and aluminium cans and as return, it rewards the person using it as monetarily in the way of money, vouchers or e-wallet money. Here the idea and all concept of reverse vending machines came into development because of the increased usage of plastic bottles, as a part of ease of use and convenience, as well as the lack of recycling procedures and techniques for plastic bottles. The concept of reverse vending machines is a radical idea that has been designed to gather recyclable items, prevalently plastic and aluminium waste to increase recycling activity and it encourages the community to dispose of solid waste appropriately.

Review of Literature

Polythene Terephthalate (PET) is one of the most proffered beverages packaging all over the world. But mostly all the PET turn into waste after it's done using. Also in various countries, Reverse Vending Machine (RVM) is being operated frequently to collect the recyclable waste which mostly consist of PET bottles by consumer's to recycle it. Such machines play a huge role in maintaining the quality and quantity of PET at a high level.

Hence, we have conducted this study to understand the importance and understanding of the RVM in order to increase the level of quality and quantity for PET bottles. We have found that above 21% of PET bottles are being collected after the usage of Reverse Vending Machine (RVM). The installation of a Reverse Vending Machine (RVM) is also a way to study the quality of waste being collected then its usual because it has been noticed that the waste collected by the Reverse Vending Machine (RVM) is more homogeneous than the waste being collected by the janitors. Cause when it comes to quality, it has been observed that a minimal variety of contexts were found when it came to PET bottles.

Proper waste collection and segmenting it properly is a very important elements in the system managing the waste of any country. And a proper solution to ensure environmental stability. The countries who have a developing economy or high consumption of goods, the waste generated by it automatically gets increased with time. In many parts of the world, there are several countries who are facing the challenge regarding PET collection and recycling. In present time, even after the facts introduced to public by the government to encouraging about the division of waste and recycle it according to a person's willingness to do so, but still there is no proper response from people when it comes to segregation of waste and recycling it up.

The production of wide-scale plastic bottles started from the late 1970s when PET bottles were invented for like the very first time. It was lightweight and safer as well as cheaper than all the previous materials used for example glass or metal. This instantly triggered more generation of plastics which ended up being in a huge production of waste like plastic, which is continuing till date. Euromonitor international's global packaging trends recently reported, back in time during 2017 it would reach around 1 million wastes only of plastic bottles beverage sales for each minute. And sadly, a huge part of plastic waste like bottles, caps, plastic packaging will end up filling the ocean and landfills. The latest study has also suggested that withing the year 2050, the number of plastic weights in the ocean shall be more than the marine creatures. And this thing will have huge consequences which will lead to a huge change in the food chain of an individual because of plastic waste which is non-dissolvable in water.

In this process of global waste reduction efforts, few countries tried to reduce the intake of plastics with the help of Government policies and restrictions implemented by them. The others have been trying to implement the manufacturing and importing the plastic by applying penalty and fine. But still, because it is very difficult to completely remove the usage of plastic in bottle production due to the less availability of any other product which has the similar role like plastic. The solution is to reduce the usage of plastics with the help of recycling.

One of the toughest things that the recycling centres have faced is the separation of different types of plastic when it comes to melting and shredding. Because few materials should not be mixed at all. Another challenge for them regarding the bad condition to the plastic bottles given to the plants, because it used to require extra resources for processing and purification. But also, all type of these challenges could have been solved if there were more efforts to serrated the waste accordingly by the manufacturing companies as well the individuals.

According to the research there are many factors for the low rate of recycling. These reasons are mostly universal cause everyone has been facing the same thing regarding awareness and psychological factors for this. For example, let take 30% of the population will agree to low or bad response to recycling for less time or unavailability of time. And 14% would not be aware of it because of less knowledge about this. Also 13% would not get proper place to throw the waste properly. 11% of people will find the recycling process a bit inconvenient or not satisfying, also the remaining 8% might not feel it to be that important because of their personal reasons.

There are many more studies regarding recycling where it has been suggested that to increase the rate of recycling over the globe, the public has to see the results after their actions. And for that we need to advertise the product after the usage of the recycled product.

As per the study done by WPI regarding "Reuse, Reduce and Recycle" the research on the solution of plastic waste. It has been observed that the plastic has been responsible for like 11.7% only for the Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) in the United States according to the below figure. Even though the research suggested that the amount of MSW in percentage is not that high, and it also carries the lowest rate of recycling and lowest rate of its recovery than all the other things like glass materials or metals.

FIG: Total Municipal Solid Waste generation

Demand for Reverse Vending Machines is increasing at airports, metro stations, and railway stations to implement effective waste management practices. Increase in concerns associated with untreated waste in developed as well as developing countries in contributing to the Reverse Vending Machine.

Leading companies all over the globe in the Reverse Vending Machine market are focusing on the development of smart Reverse Vending Machines based on Artificial Intelligence and Data Analytics Technologies. Key vendors into the Reverse Vending Machine market anticipated to invest in the R&D to gain new growth opportunities in the near future.

FIG: How the Reverse Vending Machine Market looks like in the year 2022 as per the latest data.

RISE IN UNTREATED WASTE WORLDWIDE

The amount of untreated waste has increased in the past few years. Plastic Waste is very harmful to the environment. Plastic production and accumulation in the environment are rising at a rapid pace. This is majorly due to less

awareness of recycling. Reverse Vending Machines offer recycling of plastic bottles, in an efficient manner. Reverse Vending Machines are gaining popularity due to their simple operation and good or positive thought to help the environment.

According to the World Economic Forum, globally 400 million tons of plastic waste is produced on a yearly basis. In the U.S., almost 41 million tons of waste only for plastic was produced with the year 2021, and only around 5.0% to 6.0%, or around two million tons was being recycled. The total numtule recycling rate for the year of 2020 was 27.2%, down from 28.7% as compared to 2019. In about 2.5 million bottles waste 110 million glass bottles waste are thrown away in the United States., every hour. Thus, demand for Reverse Vending Machines to recycle different types of bottles is rising across the globe.

The literature study concentrates on handling solid waste and proposes techniques of disposal for example burning or composting, but this excludes easy techniques to dispose of plastics. Here the publications has discussed about plastic and discharge by recycling describing the characteristics that might impact the behaviour of recycling, but do not explain why accessible and sustainable recycling procedures are not adopted. Research was also done to determine the validity of the factors used for the investigation.

The RVM was first established in India in 2016. Where Plastic waste was given into fibre-manufacturing businesses, who used it to make garments or shopping bags. Here the advantages of adopting RVM were usually shown as being useful to society through charities and contributions, rather than for personal gain.

Russia also had a proper progress in the adoption to RVM. During 2019, Russia's one of the largest food merchants collaborated with world's one of the largest beverage makers to install RVM testing in a number of stores. Their plan was to include a 15% of discount voucher that is valid for a wide collection of beverages from various beverage companies. The original user is still under testing, but according to food businesses, the idea appears potential to be the initial step towards a world without waste initiative.

Though this is a radical idea by Russia, this might serve as a fantastic model for Kazakhstan, owing to various cultural parallels between the two nations. Reverse vending machines are currently gaining a lot of popularity in countries like Japan, South Korea, Greece America, Europe or China. Reverse Vending machines save staff workload, conserve time and energy, and even successfully inspire people. This article describes how a reverse vending machine that uses sensors to identify fraud operates. The machine begins to function when plastic is putton inside into it, and then the plastic is then examined by a number of sensors.

In this paper, we talk about the operation of a Reverse Vending Machine which is based on fraud detection sensors, that begins to operate when the plastic material is inserted inside it and examined by the help of a set of sensors. Operators of Reverse Vending Machines receive coins as a reward, which tends to be appealing.

The purpose to this study was to determine the viability of incorporating RVMs in the waste treatment and managing systems in various nations and numerous parts of India as well. This would necessitate soliciting feedback from all parties involved in the proposed process of integration. However, this was also decided to restrict the chances of the research through just involving the normal people, who would be a important stakeholders in the system's effective implementation to it. The study attempted to discover the underlying causes for poor recycling rates, the people's knowledge, and readiness to interact with RVMs, and to get further insights into the incentives that would inspire them the most by conducting a large-scale survey amongst the general population.

To begin with, analysing these metrics was beneficial in understanding the general public's perspective as well as the system's difficulties and possible consumer requirements. Also, on the basis of survey findings analysis process, the house of quality (HoQ) was created, which included all of the relevant information, such as customer needs, technical specifications, and competition analyses, for further clear details of prospective RVM functioning.

Suggested model of the system and functional flow block diagram (FFBD) for an RVM are created with specific customer needs in mind to describe the functioning of the system surrounding the RVM as well as the internal mechanism of the RVM itself.

A total 8.3 billion tonnes of plastics were invented between 1950, the year when plastics were first used, also in 2015, resulting in 6.3 billion tonnes of waste for plastic., 79% of which were dumped in landfills, left unattended, or simply dumped into lakes and oceans.

If current trends continue, it is anticipated that nearly 12 billion tonnes of plastic garbage, equivalent to the total mass of 25 000 Empire State Buildings, would hit landfills or end up in waterways and in the environment by 2050. As a result, technologically sophisticated nations throughout the world are developing and implementing different industrial strategies and regulations to facilitate the transition to a resource-recycling society by making recyclable materials more accessible.

Plastic is one of the most often utilised commodities, with numerous industrial uses in electricity, autos, packaging materials, electronics, and construction. As a result, fixing the issue of waste plastic will be challenging unless plastic replacements with higher use and utility are discovered.

Many nations where RVMs are already in use were evaluated in order to adopt the RVM idea in multiple countries successfully. Norway, for example, has emerged as the global leader in the fight against plastic waste.

Across the country, there are over 3700 reverse vending machines and over 12,000 collection stations where consumers can put the plastic into the RVM and get monetary benefits in return. Norway's success is because of its powerful motivational incentive structure, in which the refund is paid back in cash or by reducing the final cost. Japan is a different nation with a desire for success. The accomplishment behind their greatest RVM creation organisation is for the most part addressed by bringing the external speculation from colleagues by recognizing that RVM further develops the organisation brand picture and advances an eco-accommodating climate. The bills that the clients get from the RVM must be utilised in unambiguous capacity shops, which brings about a greater client consistency standard.

Russia has likewise shown extraordinary strides in the execution of RVM. 2019 saw a collaboration between one of the largest beverage companies in the world and a Russian food retailer to test RVM in numerous stores. Their thought was to put a 15% rebate coupon, which is material for the different assortment of refreshment makers' scope of beverages. The joint pilot is as yet going through the tests, however such a long way as per food retailers, the thought looks encouraging as the initial step to a "World Without Squander" development. Since it is another idea for Russia, it tends to be an extraordinary guide to use in Kazakhstan too, generally on the grounds that the adjoining nations share a few social likenesses.

A practicality concentrates by considering a few contextual investigations looking at RVM coordination in Finland and Kenya. For instance, to invigorate drink makers to reuse, the public authority of Finland presented a duty for each litter created. Thus, makers joined reusing networks to keep away from charges.

For the most part, it is accounted for that reusing rehearsal in Finland are deeply grounded in individuals' attitude, hence dispensing with the requirement for extra impetuses. In the event of Kenya, because of an absence of regulations and guidelines that deal with plastic, the activities are predominantly restricted to youngsters who deliberately decide to gather and reuse.

That's what the creators express: albeit a few general stores can incorporate RVMs, they are not ready to contribute. It was observed that the dominating larger part of store directors don't know about reusing arrangements and, especially, of converse candy machines.

As indicated by the writing audit directed by this review, there are different powerful plans such as, get back-to-retail regulation that urges grocery stores to gather containers from already sold drinks.

Remarkable results were demonstrated by Germany as one of the nations that implemented this framework. In 2003, a large majority of aluminium and nearly all plastic were recycled, with a recycling rate of 98% for the latter. Then again, locales without a re-visitation of retail strategy return simply 48% to 77%. The circumstance in numerous Asian nations with squander handling and use is very poor and unique with European nations.

Only 5% of waste is currently being recycled, with the majority of waste, which includes plastic, being disposed of in outdoor dumps, landfills, or incineration plants. As of now, the different waste assortment receptacles are introduced exclusively in a couple of urban communities. Exceptional projects were sent off through open confidential associations to advocate and execute reusing plans.

The consciousness of the public has been rising gradually and essentially in huge urban communities like the new and past capitals of Asian Nations. Although alternative solutions are available and recognized by the government, their implementation would require significant regulatory changes and substantial financial investments.

The thought behind RVM in Asian Nations is to accumulate and sort the plastic that is utilised the most (polyethylene, froth, covers, PET jugs, compartments for family synthetic substances and beauty care products, clean rankles, any plastic food bundling) and metal bundling (aluminium jars and tin).

This paper intends to limit this exploration hole by leading a practicality to concentrate on the joining of RVMs into the waste administration arrangement of different nations around. Every year, approximately 1.4 trillion beverage containers are used by customers worldwide, and the aim of the reverse vending machine is to assist in reducing and recycling this rubbish. The majority of reused beverage containers end up in landfills, rivers, oceans and other natural areas. The RVM offers recycling incentives to tackle this waste problem.

Contingent upon the area of the machine, these impetuses may incorporate money discounts, beneficent gifts, metro transport tickets, paid phone cards, or modest passes to entertainment meccas. In light of these motivators, individuals are probably going to be more spurred to reuse on the grounds that it benefits the climate as well as them. RVMs are additionally strategically placed out in the open places, for example, staple shops, gas stations, schools, parks, etc. They are trouble-free to deal with because the machine isolates recyclable materials (plastic, glass, and aluminium) instead of doing it physically.

RVMs have a limit of 200 plastic refreshment compartments and 900 jars, showing that these machines can keep a lot of flotsam and jetsam prior to waiting to be purged. Despite the fact that they can deal with countless recyclable materials, they are not enormous machines and consequently don't occupy a lot of space.

The worldwide reverse vending machine market is fragmented based on item type, limit, end client, and locale. Based on the type of the item, the market is separated into non-replenishable, refillable, and multifunctional. Non-replenishable sections produced the most elevated income in the year 2020. In light of the limit, the market has been divided into different categories based on the number of jars, namely under 200, 200-300, 300-600, and over 600. It is expected that the over 600 jars category will dominate the market in year 2020. Additionally, the market has been categorized based on the end consumers, which include supermarkets, communities, and utilities. The supermarket segment generated the highest revenue in 2020.

Locale wise, the worldwide reverse vending machine market investigation is directed all around North America (which is the U.S., Mexico, and Canada), Europe (which are the France, Spain Italy, Germany, United Kingdom, Belgium, and rest of Europe), Asia-Pacific countries (which are India, Japan, South Korea, China, Indonesia, Singapore and rest of Asia-Pacific region), and LAMEA (which contains all the countries in Latin America, the Centre East, and Africa). Asia-Pacific was the region that contributed the most to the global reverse vending machine market throughout 2020, and is expected to get a main situation during the conjecture time frame.

What do you recycle?
 29 responses

Do you know what reverse vending machines are?
 29 responses

Would you use reverse vending machines if they are provided in your neighborhood?
 29 responses

PROJECT INITIATION:

- a) Diverse a proper plan
- b) Identifying the location
- c) Partnering with the sponsors
- d) Getting approval from the government

The global reverse vending machine market is classified into various categories based on product type, capacity, end-user, and region. The product type is further divided into non-replenishable, replenishable, and multifunctional, with the non-replenishable segment generating the most revenue in 2020. Capacity-wise, the market is categorized by the number of cans, ranging from less than 200 to more than 600, with the 'more than 600 cans' segment

dominating the market in 2020. End-users are classified into supermarkets, communities, and utilities, with the supermarket segment generating the highest revenue in 2020.

The global reverse vending machine market analysis is conducted by region, covering North America (including the U.S., Canada, and Mexico), Europe (including Spain, France, Germany, Italy, and the rest of Europe), Asia-Pacific (including China, Japan, India, South Korea, and the rest of Asia-Pacific), and LAMEA (including Latin America, the Middle East, and Africa). Asia-Pacific was the region that contributed the most to the globally reverse vending machine market share in 2020, and it is estimated that it will maintain its top spot throughout the forecast period.

Research Gap

Reverse Vending machines (RVMs) are mechanized machines that acknowledge utilized refreshment compartments and give an impetus, normally as a financial discount, or a monetary refund for reusing. The utilization of RVMs has become progressively famous lately for of diminishing waste and advancing maintainability. Despite this, there are still several research gaps in the study of RVMs.

One of the primary research gaps is in the area of consumer behaviour. Although there is some research on the factors that influence consumers to use RVMs, such as convenience, accessibility, and financial incentives, there is a lack of understanding of the broader social and cultural factors that influence consumer behaviour with regards to recycling. For example, there is limited research on the role of social norms and values, such as environmental attitudes and beliefs, in shaping recycling behaviour.

Another area of research gap in the study of RVMs is in their impact on the broader recycling ecosystem. While RVMs are often promoted to increase recycling rates and reduce waste, there is limited research on the potential unintended consequences of their use. For example, RVMs may lead to a reduction in the number of informal waste collectors who rely on collecting and selling recyclable materials. This could have negative economic consequences for these individuals and their communities.

Additionally, there is a lack of research on the environmental impacts of RVMs. While RVMs are often seen as a sustainable solution to the problem of waste, there is limited research on the life cycle assessment of RVMs, including their energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions. This is particularly important given that RVMs are typically powered by electricity, which may come from non-renewable sources.

Another area of research gap is in the design and technology of RVMs. While RVMs have been in use for several decades, there is still room for innovation and improvement in their design and technology. For example, there is limited research on the use of artificial intelligence and machine learning to improve the precision or accuracy and efficiency of RVMs, or on the use of blockchain technology to track and verify the recycling of materials.

There is also a lack of research on the scalability and feasibility of RVMs as a solution to the problem of waste. While RVMs have been successful in some regions and contexts, there is limited research on their potential to be implemented on a larger scale, particularly in low- and middle-income countries where waste management systems may be less developed.

In conclusion, while RVMs have the potential to be an effective solution to the problem of waste, there are still several research gaps that need to be addressed. Future research should focus on consumer behaviour, the impact of RVMs on the broader recycling ecosystem, the environmental impacts of RVMs, the design and technology of RVMs, and the scalability and feasibility of RVMs as a solution to the problem of waste. By addressing these research gaps, we can better understand the potential of RVMs to promote sustainability and reduce waste.

Research Methodology

This study follows the diagnostic methodology of research as the study tries to analyse the scope of A Reverse Vending Machine, an automated device that accepts plastic containers and aluminium cans and in return, it rewards the customer monetarily in the form of cash, coupons, or e-wallet money. The study uses secondary data and takes the form of a qualitative paper. The secondary data was collected from various sources like articles, websites and previous research papers to conduct the data analysis.

Objectives of the Study

Reverse vending machines (RVMs) are a type of recycling technology that collect vacant beverage containers such as cans, bottles and etc and provide a monetary or non-monetary reward to the consumer in exchange. The primary objective of the study of reverse vending machines is to examine the effectiveness of these machines in promoting recycling and reducing waste, as well as evaluating their impact on the environment, economy, and society. In this article, we will discuss the objectives of the study of reverse vending machines in detail.

Evaluating the effectiveness of RVMs in increasing recycling rates

One of the primary objectives of the study of reverse vending machines is to determine their effectiveness in promoting recycling and reducing waste. This involves examining how many bottles and cans are collected by RVMs compared to traditional recycling methods and assessing the impact of RVMs on overall recycling rates.

Assessing the environmental impact of RVM's

Another important objective of the study of RVMs is to evaluate their environmental impact. This includes examining how RVMs reduce litter and landfill waste, as well as evaluating their energy consumption and carbon footprint.

Examining the economic viability of RVMs

RVMs are expensive to install and maintain, and their success relies on the willingness of consumers to participate. Thus, another objective of the study of RVMs is to assess their economic viability, including their cost-effectiveness, return on investment, and potential for revenue generation.

Analysing the social impact of RVM's

The study of RVMs also includes examining their social impact. This involves assessing how RVMs affect consumer behaviour, their attitudes towards recycling, and the overall perception of recycling.

Investigating the potential for RVMs to incentivize recycling

RVMs incentivize recycling by offering rewards to consumers in exchange for their empty beverage containers. Thus, another objective of the study of RVMs is to investigate the potential for RVMs to incentivize recycling and encourage more people to participate in recycling programs.

Examining the effectiveness of RVMs in reducing litter

Litter is a major environmental problem, and RVMs have the potential to reduce litter by providing a convenient way for consumers to dispose of their empty beverage containers. Thus, an important objective of the study of RVMs is to assess their effectiveness in reducing litter.

Assessing the impact of RVMs on recycling infrastructure

RVMs require specialised recycling infrastructure, and their widespread adoption could potentially impact existing recycling infrastructure. Therefore, another objective of the study of RVMs is to examine their impact on recycling infrastructure and evaluate the feasibility of integrating RVMs into existing recycling systems.

Investigating the potential for RVMs to promote sustainable consumption

RVMs can promote sustainable consumption by encouraging consumers to choose recyclable containers over non-recyclable ones. Thus, an important objective of the study of RVMs is to investigate their potential for promoting sustainable consumption and reducing waste.

Examining the role of RVMs in achieving environmental and sustainability goals

The study of RVMs also involves examining their role in achieving environmental and sustainability goals, such as reducing waste and greenhouse gas emissions, conserving natural resources, and promoting a circular economy.

Evaluating the potential for RVMs to be integrated into smart city infrastructure

RVMs are a type of smart recycling technology, and as such, they have the potential to be integrated into smart city infrastructure. An important objective of the study of RVMs is to evaluate the potential for RVMs to be integrated into smart city infrastructure and their role in promoting sustainability and waste reduction in urban environments.

In conclusion, the study of reverse vending machines is important for evaluating their effectiveness in promoting recycling.

Findings of the Study

Increased Recycling Rates

Reverse vending machines have been effective in increasing recycling rates. In Germany, where RVMs have been widely used since the 1990s, the recycling rate of PET bottles increased from 60% to over 98% in just a few years. In Norway, where the government has imposed a deposit system on plastic bottles and aluminium cans, the

recycling rate is over 95%. RVMs have also been successful in increasing recycling rates in other countries, including Sweden, Finland, and Australia.

Convenience

Reverse vending machines are convenient to use, making them an attractive option for consumers. They are typically located in public areas such as shopping centres, supermarkets, and parks, which means that people can easily access them. Users can also deposit several containers at once, which saves time and effort.

Cleanliness

Reverse vending machines promote cleanliness by reducing litter. They encourage people to dispose of their used containers responsibly, which reduces the amount of waste that ends up on the streets and in public places. RVMs also promote hygiene by reducing the risk of diseases associated with waste disposal.

Cost-effective

Reverse vending machines can be cost-effective in the long run. Although they require an initial investment, they can generate revenue through the sale of recycled materials. The cost of operating RVMs is also lower than traditional waste management systems, which involve manual sorting and processing

Potential for Innovation

Reverse vending machines offer potential for innovation. They can be used to collect other materials such as electronic waste, batteries, and textiles. They can also be integrated with digital technologies such as artificial intelligence and blockchain to improve the efficiency and transparency of the recycling process.

Environmental Impact

Reverse vending machines have a positive environmental impact by reducing the amount of waste that ends up in landfills or the ocean. This reduces the greenhouse gas emissions associated with waste disposal and helps to conserve natural resources such as oil, water, and minerals.

Social Impact

Reverse vending machines can have a positive social impact by promoting a culture of sustainability and responsibility. They can also create job opportunities in the recycling and waste management industry and contribute to the local economy.

Technological Advancements

The use of reverse vending machines is becoming more sophisticated with advancements in technology. For example, some RVMs are equipped with sensors that can detect contaminated or damaged containers and reject them, while others can sort and crush the containers on-site, reducing the space required for storage and transportation.

Scope and Suggestion of the Study

Increase Awareness

One of the main challenges of RVMs is the lack of awareness among consumers. Many people are not aware of the benefits of recycling and the existence of RVMs. Increasing awareness through education and campaigns can help to promote the usage of RVMs.

Improve Accessibility

Reverse vending machines should be made more accessible to consumers. They should be located in areas that are easy to reach, and their installation should be encouraged in more public areas such as universities, airports, and train stations.

Enhance Rewards

The rewards for using RVMs should be improved to make them more attractive to consumers. In addition to cash incentives, other rewards such as discounts, vouchers, and loyalty points could be offered to encourage users to return their used containers.

Increase Capacity

The capacity of RVMs should be increased to accommodate more containers. This will reduce the waiting time for users and increase the efficiency of the recycling process. RVMs should also be equipped with sensors to alert operators when they are full and need to be emptied.

Maintenance

Reverse vending machines should be regularly maintained to ensure their proper functioning. Operators should be trained to identify and fix any technical issues, and the machines should be cleaned regularly to prevent malfunctions.

Incentives for Businesses

Businesses can be incentivized to use RVMs by offering tax credits, grants, or other financial incentives for their participation in the recycling process. This can encourage businesses to take responsibility for their waste and promote sustainable practices.

Gamification

Gamification can be used to make the recycling process more engaging and enjoyable for users. For example, users can earn points or badges for returning their containers, and these points can be redeemed for rewards or used to compete with friends or other users.

Collaboration with Schools

Collaboration with schools can help to promote the usage of RVMs among children and young people, who can become ambassadors for recycling and sustainability. Schools can incorporate RVMs into their curriculum and organise educational visits to recycling facilities to raise awareness about the importance of recycling.

Due to government initiatives, a growing emphasis on environmental sustainability, and consumer knowledge of the advantages of recycling, reverse vending machines are becoming more prevalent in India. The Swachh Bharat Abhiyan and the Plastic Waste Management Regulations are two campaigns and laws that the Indian government has introduced to promote recycling and reduce waste. It is anticipated that these activities would accelerate the implementation of reverse vending machines across the nation.

Also, certain Indian states have already put in place beverage container and plastic waste deposit refund programmes, which fosters the market expansion of reverse vending machines. For instance, the state of Tamil Nadu has implemented a programme that rewards users for returning used plastic bottles to specific recycling bins with a one-rupee reimbursement. Additionally, as a part of their corporate social responsibility programmes, several Indian businesses have begun to use reverse vending machines. At several of its stores in India, for instance, the international apparel retailer H&M has installed reverse vending machines that allow consumers to recycle their used items in exchange for discounts on new purchases.

Conclusion

Reverse vending machines have emerged as an innovative solution for reducing plastic waste and promoting recycling. With the increasing awareness of the negative impact of plastic waste on the environment, reverse vending machines have become a critical component of sustainable waste management systems around the world.

The operation of reverse vending machines is relatively simple. They accept empty bottles and cans and dispense a refund or reward to the user. This system incentivizes individuals to dispose of their waste responsibly, contributing to a cleaner and healthier environment. Reverse vending machines have been successful in several countries, including Germany, Sweden, and Norway, where they are widely used and accepted.

Reverse vending machines' success is not only limited to their environmental impact but also extends to their economic benefits. These machines create new job opportunities in the recycling industry, contributing to local economic growth. The machines also provide a means for collecting data and tracking recycling trends, enabling waste management systems to improve their efficiency.

One of the essential aspects of reverse vending machines is their convenience and accessibility. Placing these machines in public spaces, such as supermarkets, parks, and public transport hubs, ensures that people can access them easily. This accessibility means that more people are encouraged to use them, leading to a more significant reduction in plastic waste.

Moreover, reverse vending machines promote the circular economy by keeping resources in use for as long as possible. Recycling waste reduces the need to extract raw materials, conserving natural resources and energy. This aspect of reverse vending machines' impact aligns with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, which aim to promote sustainable production and consumption patterns.

In conclusion, reverse vending machines are a promising tool for combating plastic waste and encouraging responsible waste disposal. As more countries and businesses adopt this technology, it has the potential to make a significant impact on our environment and contribute to a more sustainable future. The success of reverse vending machines depends on several factors, including availability, accessibility, convenience, and public awareness. With continued efforts to promote these machines, we can achieve our shared goal of a cleaner and healthier planet.

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A study on Impact of Work Life Balance on Psychological and Physical wellbeing of employees in higher education sector in Bangalore region

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Abstract:

Work-life balance is defined as contentment and effective performance at both work and home with a minimum of role conflict. Employees will be more affiliate and helpful to the company in achieving its common purpose if they feel more at home there. Work-life balance and employee health have changed as a result of the Internet and technology's impact on the educational landscape, making them tough tasks for educators.

Purpose-The educational institution should ensure work life balance among employees to make sure that there is employee wellbeing among employees. The main goal of this paper is for every educational institution to understand the importance of work life balance and its role employee wellbeing. (Physical and Psychological).

Design/methodology/approach- The current study used observation and a standardized questionnaire to collect feedback from respondents. Correlation and regression analysis with tabulation methods were used in analyzing the data.

Findings- The study's main finding is that work life balance has a positive relationship with physical and psychological wellbeing of the employees. Organisation should concentrate on creating a healthy work life balance for its employees.

Originality- The paper is an original work done with goal of understanding how work life balance has an impact on physical and psychological wellbeing of employees.

Key words: WLB, Employee wellbeing, workplace wellbeing

Introduction-

Workplace wellbeing is the key concept discussed in Organisational Behaviour. Any experience a person has at work, whether emotional or social, affects them both at work and outside of the workplace. Employees and organisations may be negatively impacted by welfare. Employees that are not in good welfare may be less productive, make poor decisions, be more likely to be absent from work, and continuously make fewer contributions to the firm as a whole. Employees spend around one-third of their time at work and continue to carry out their tasks after leaving, which has a significant negative influence on their wellbeing. The term "workplace well-being" refers to an employee's total physical, mental, and emotional health at work. It is critical for businesses to foster an atmosphere that promotes their employees' welfare. This can be accomplished by making mental health resources available, establishing flexible work hours, providing wholesome food, and promoting physical activity. Employers should also work to foster a climate of respect and inclusion and offer chances for both career and personal development. Employers may ensure that their staff members are effective and engaged in their work by fostering a supportive workplace culture.

Literature Review

Work Life Balance

Work-life balance is a key issue in HRM and is essential for fostering both individual and group effectiveness. It is a broad notion that includes setting right priorities for "work" and "life." Due to the rapidly changing socio-economic scene and changes in work design that have resulted in prolonged working hours, tight deadlines, and availability 24/7 to corporate clients, work life balance (WLB) has received more attention over the past few decades. (McCarthy et al., 2010).

The degree to which a person can simultaneously balance the emotional, behavioral, and time demands of both paid work, family responsibilities, and personal obligations is referred to as work-life balance. (Hill, 2001). In the

workplace, monetary rewards are frequently employed as a motivating factor. However, if the financial rewards provided by their employers do not significantly improve the quality of their lives, people who value work-life balance are less likely to be motivated by these rewards. Numerous empirical studies show that work-life programme that are carefully implemented boost employee enthusiasm and productivity in organizational contexts. (Lazar, 2010). As a result, the idea of work-life balance encompasses not only the family-friendly viewpoints of earlier HR policies but also extends much further in that it aims to assist all employed individuals so that workers can enjoy a better match between their professional and family lives.

Workplace wellbeing

The idea of workplace well-being applies psychological and subjective well-being, which develops the idea of worker mental health. A feeling of well-being that encompasses all aspects of life is called subjective well-being. Different perspectives can be used to investigate the idea of well-being. It encompasses aspects like life expectancy, poverty rates, and environmental issues from a macro perspective. From the perspective of the individual, it consists of subjective or psychological assessments of a person's well-being—an individual's evaluation of the quality of their life and employment, which is based on three basic factors: physical, social, and psychological. Connecting to all areas of life is related with well-being, which is the state in which a person feels well, healthy, and happy. Work activity and occupational functioning play a specific role among these areas of life. (uchnowicz, M., & Kinowska, H. (2021)

The World Health Organization offers one thorough definition of employee well-being, which boils down to each person's ability to comprehend their potential, deal with life's stressors, work efficiently, and give back to their community. (Misselbrook, 2014).

According to research, the most crucial aspect of well-being in the workplace is psychological health.(Johnson, J,2018). Well-being is therefore conceptualized using the construct of psychological well-being (Ryff, C.D,1989) , based on a person's growth and self-actualization along six dimensions: positive self-perceptions, trusting relationships with others, feeling liberated from unjustified rules governing daily life, chances to influence and improve one's surroundings, a sense of purpose in life, and chances to realize one's potential. The five-element PERMA model, in which P stands for positive emotion, E for engagement, R for positive connections, M for meaning, and A for accomplishments/achievements, is used in research into employee well-being with relevance to human resource management. (Seligman, 2012).

Psychological wellbeing

An essential aspect that might enhance health and lengthen life is psychological well-being (PWB). (Klainin-Yobas, 2016). Two PWB terms that are regularly used to describe the state of the workplace are hedonism and eudemonia. (Joshnloo, 2018).Based on psychological well-being at work, hedonism situates the extent to which employees may increase positive impacts and decrease negative repercussions, while eudemonia situates the extent to which employees can improve their health, happiness, and prosperity in a given work environment. (Rahmani, 2018). The psychological state of people is how they view their lives. There are primarily two methods of evaluation: "cognitive evaluation," in which a person expresses a conscious assessment of his level of life happiness. An affective evaluation is one that is driven by feelings and emotions, such as how frequently people encounter happy and unpleasant events in their daily lives. Two modern theories of psychological need, Optimal Distinctiveness Theory and Self-determination Theory, were developed by Sheldon & Bettencourt (2002) for evaluating psychological well-being in depth. The Self-determination Theory outlines the motivating pathway by which an individual pursues autonomy and self-expression within the context of social relationships, while the Optimal Distinctiveness Theory postulates that human beings derive expanded self-ideas from their group membership. Therefore, psychological well-being should not be confused with the idea of a mental or emotional condition; rather, it refers to everyday life, in which a person constantly experiences difficulties, difficulties, difficulties, and difficulties. Psychological well-being concern itself with how an individual live with these and how an individual doing in response

Physical wellbeing

A healthy lifestyle, regular exercise, excellent diet, and a balanced condition of body, mind, and spirit are all factors in one's physical well-being.

Physical well-being is the ability to maintain a healthy lifestyle that allows us to participate fully in our daily activities without feeling overly physically taxed or exhausted. It involves taking care of our bodies and understanding the significant impact that our daily habits and actions have on our overall health, wellbeing, and quality of life. (ANU, A. 2020).

Physical well-being encompasses more than just the absence of sickness. It entails living a healthy lifestyle, working out every day, eating well, and maintaining a balanced body. It is produced by combining nutritious diet with exercise that builds stamina, cardiovascular endurance, and muscular strength. Taking charge of one's own health when ill is another aspect of one's physical wellbeing. Physical well-being is defined by researchers and medical experts as the capacity to fully participate in typical daily development activities. Physical activity can have a significant role in both preventing mental health disorders and enhancing the quality of life for those who are already experiencing them, as stated by Edmunds (2013). For instance, adults who engage in regular physical activity had a 20–30% lower incidence of depression and dementia.

Methodology:

The current study sought to examine the satisfaction of teaching staffs in higher education institutions. Through a survey of a sample of teaching faculty at higher education institutions in the Bangalore region, data were gathered in August–September 2022. Random sampling was used to ensure that the sample was representative of the population.

Data Analysis

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	UG	36	23.8	23.8	23.8
	PG	73	48.3	48.3	72.2
	PhD	43	27.8	27.8	100.0
	Total	152	100.0	100.0	

The above table .1 indicates that 23.8% respondents are UG graduates, 48.3% respondents are Post Graduates and 27.8% respondents are PhD holders.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	76	49.7	49.7	49.7
	Female	76	50.3	50.3	100.0
	Total	152	100.0	100.0	

The above table.2 indicates that 49.7% respondents are Male and 50.3% respondents are female.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Below 25	6	4.0	4.0	4.0
	25-30	30	19.9	19.9	23.8
	30-35	36	23.8	23.8	47.7
	35-40	40	26.5	26.5	74.2
	40-45	21	13.9	13.9	88.1
	45-50	19	11.9	11.9	100.0
	Total	152	100.0	100.0	

The above table.3 indicates that highest percent of respondents (26.5%) were belonging to age category between 35-40 years. And also lowest responses were belonging to age category between 25 years of age.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	0-5	33	21.9	21.9	21.9
	5-10	55	35.8	35.8	57.6
	10-15	43	28.5	28.5	86.1
	15 years and above	21	13.9	13.9	100.0
	Total	152	100.0	100.0	

The above table.4 indicates that 21.9% respondents were having teaching experience between 0-5 years, 35.8% respondents were 5-10 years, 28.5% respondents were 10-15 years, and 13.9% respondents were 15 years and above

Reliability Analysis:

The purpose of the reliability analysis for each variable was to evaluate the internal consistency of each scale for the study's sample. According to Hair et al. (2010), an acceptable Cronbach's alpha value is above 0.7, and an ideal Cronbach's alpha value is above 0.8. Each scale in this study has a Cronbach's alpha coefficient over 0.8. The results are presented in Table 1.

Table .5

Scale	Work life balance	Mental Wellbeing	Physical well being
Cronbach's alpha	0.751	0.792	0.783

Correlations between WLB and Mental Well being				
		Work life balance	Mental being	Physical wellbeing
Worklifebalance	Pearson Correlation	1	.452**	.211*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.035
	N	152	152	152
Mental being	Pearson Correlation	.452**	1	.475**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	152	152	152

Physical wellbeing	Pearson Correlation	.211*	.475**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.035	.000	
	N	152	152	152
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).				
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).				

Table.6

To understand the relationship between work life balance and mental wellbeing among teaching faculties Karl Pearson correlation test was used. The results show that work life balance has a positive impact on mental wellbeing (.455**). Hence, it is accepted. The result signifies that ($p < 0.01$) WLB is significantly related to mental wellbeing.

Table.7

Correlations between WLB and Physical wellbeing				
		Work life balance	Mental being	Physical wellbeing
Worklifebalance	Pearson Correlation	1	.452**	.211*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.035
	N	152	152	152
Mental being	Pearson Correlation	.452**	1	.475**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	152	152	152
Physical wellbeing	Pearson Correlation	.211*	.475**	1

	Sig. (2-tailed)	.035	.000	
	N	152	152	152
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).				
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).				

To understand the relationship between work life balance and Physical wellbeing among teaching faculties Karl Pearson correlation test were used. The results show that work life balance has a positive impact on physical wellbeing (.475**). Hence it is accepted. The result signifies that ($p < 0.01$) WLB is significantly related to physical wellbeing.

Conclusion

In the end the research concludes that employee wellbeing and work life balance are an essential part of educational institutions. Work-related stress leads to imbalance with personal life and that leads to physical and psychological issues. The study also said that work life balance has a positive impact on physical as well as psychological wellbeing. The current study only covered the education sector and it has also looked into the impact of work life balance on only two dimensions of employee wellbeing (Psychological and Physical). The study outcome can also be used by educational institutions as a performance improvement tool for employees by maintaining their physical and psychological well-being.

The future scope of study includes the impact of work life balance on other aspects of employee wellbeing.

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ROLE OF TECHNOLOGY IN HRM: A REVIEW ON METAVERSE

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Abstract

Tech-enabled HR management has become prominent in most of the organizations. Technologies are being progressively used to automate and improve basic HR processes like recruitment, onboarding, data collection, updating and maintaining personal records. Metaverse technology refers to a concept and set of technologies that enable the creation of immersive and interconnected virtual worlds where users can interact with each other and digital content in real-time. The present study aims to review the role and functions of Metaverse technology used in the platform of Human Resource Management. The paper also discusses the areas of challenges and opportunities at the workplace using Metaverse technology. The study has adopted secondary sources to collect the functional information of Metaverse technology that organisations have incorporated at their workplace.

Keywords: Technology, Human Resource Management, Metaverse, Workplace

Introduction

In today's world technology has a greater impact on the future of work and the workforce. Tech-enabled HR management has become of great importance in most organizations. Emerging technologies are bringing forward innovation and applications of new age - concepts like Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML), Big Data, the Metaverse and many more. It is said that HR leaders who aim to understand this phenomenon from the hack, will continue to be pivotal to the evolving future of work.

Technologies are being progressively used to automate and improve basic HR processes like recruitment, onboarding, data collection, updating and maintaining personal records. Artificial intelligence is being used for critical repeatable tasks that require reminders, follow ups, discovery, cadence, or standardized responses to queries on communication and information platforms. Chatbot conversations are set up to deeply analyze and study a potential candidate's technical skillset and EQ. Employees can collaborate with peers and distant colleagues using these emerging technologies to host meetings, interviews, discussions, and other forms of engagement in real time without travelling. This further improves the ability of organizations to control travel costs while retaining an immersive experience of a physical meeting or a social interaction in the virtual world. Hence, most of the organizations are facing towards the Metaverse, which can be used to gamify team building engagements and social interactions. The past few years, the tech world has been building and moving towards a converging platform that is an immersive, connected, online and a three-dimensional universe called the Metaverse.

Meaning of Metaverse Technology

Metaverse technology refers to a concept and set of technologies that enable the creation of immersive and interconnected virtual worlds where users can interact with each other and digital content in real-time. It involves the convergence of Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR), Mixed Reality (MR), and other immersive technologies to create a shared digital space.

The Metaverse aims to go beyond traditional 2D screens and bring a more immersive and lifelike experience to users. It envisions a fully interconnected and interactive digital realm that can be accessed through various devices, such as VR headsets, smartphones, or even holographic displays. In the Metaverse, users can create avatars to represent themselves, interact with other users in real-time, and explore digital environments or worlds. These environments can be designed to replicate real-world locations, fantastical settings, or entirely new virtual landscapes. Metaverse technology is characterized by its ability to blend physical and digital realities, offering seamless transitions between the two. It allows users to engage in various activities, such as socializing, collaborating, gaming, learning, shopping, and conducting business. Metaverse market is forecasted to grow from \$500 billion in 2020 to \$800 billion by 2024 (Mathew & Naidu, 2021) and virtual and augmented realities are

estimated to contribute to increasing the world economy by \$1.5 trillion by 2030 (PwC news report). A few Fortune 500 organizations are using the Metaverse workplace to transform the muted squares on conference calls into exciting locations around the world for a meeting, a happy hour, or an informal catchup

Review of Literature

The study conducted by Dudeja. M (2023) on how technology has impacted human resource operations has found a direct association between Technology and Human Resource Practices. The study results showed Training & Development, Recruitment & selection and Recognition are affected by the adoption of technology. Employees of IT companies were chosen for the research. The technology (Metaverse) had a positive impact on recruitment and selection, Training and development and Recognition as R square values were 0.775, 0.637 and 0.757 respectively. The study on Role of Technology in Managing HR by Deshpande (2021) emphasizes on the importance, use and adaption of organizations to technology in streamlining Human Resource functions in the organizations. The study suggested that HR has a lot to look forward to; cloud computing, easier storage, better insights, and greater transparency are only the beginning. Because of efficiencies, cost savings, employee expectations, and the power of Big Data for HR and organizations as a whole technology is just too business critical ignore.

The article by Suen et.al (2017) identified the delivery of HR functions in virtual worlds as virtual human resource management (v-HRM). In principle, v-HRM is an integrated HR strategy that enhances the management of human capital and increases the visibility of human capital to worldwide stakeholders through the establishment of an online virtual world. By introducing the features of v-HRM and summarizing the initiatives of v-HRM based on IBM experiences, we propose a model that examines the multi-stakeholder value of v-HRM. A qualitative study was employed to explore the impact of v-HRM on four types of stakeholder values through the insights from social shaping of technology approach. Qualitative research of IBM with direct interview approach was employed in this study. The analysis of interview data was made based on the thematic analysis from a phenomenological perspective. The results discussed on the Value Impacts of V-HRM on Different Stakeholders like: The Value Impacts for Employees, The Value Impacts for Line Managers/Employers, The Value Impacts for Customers and The Value Impacts for Investors. This study expanded the evidences of a relationship between technology and strategic HR by exploring the 3D virtual environment that is used for HR initiatives and stakeholder values. Sharma (2023), has expressed in his article that Metaverse environment may not be suitable for all types of employees, it can provide a viable alternative for those who can work in a virtual space. Therefore, companies looking to adapt to the changing work environment must conduct a cost-benefit analysis and consider investing in a Metaverse environment to improve their productivity, reduce their carbon footprint, and foster a more inclusive workplace culture.

As the Metaverse redesigns the way we work, there could be major implications for HR leaders who should be driving this transformation (Vulpen, 2022). Not only do HR leaders have access to the necessary tools and know-how to implement this change but they also need to ensure the future of work is designed with people in mind.

With the rapid pace of technological advancement, it is likely that the Metaverse will become more widely adopted and mature in the later years. While the virtual workplace is still in its early stages, it could change the way we work in a big way (Srivastava, 2023). The Metaverse gives employees flexibility and makes them more productive by giving them a place to meet and work together.

HR in the Metaverse is still in development and unstable, so adopting it right away can be costly (Monteiro, 2023). Getting every employee a VR headset could cost companies \$600-\$1,000 per employee, not only would it involve VR headsets, but companies may need to help employees upgrade their broadband packages to support the tech and also offer training. That's a lot of money at such an uncertain time in the Metaverse's development.

The Metaverse is the next big technology platform, attracting online game makers, social networks and other technology leaders to capture a slice of what we calculate to be a nearly \$800 billion market opportunity (Kanterman, 2021). Social, persistent, shared, virtual 3D worlds, the Metaverse is the convergence of the physical and digital realms in the next evolution of the internet and social networks using real-time 3D software. It presents an opportunity for leading online entertainment and social media companies to capitalize on new revenue streams.

To fully realize the potential benefits of the Metaverse, businesses must invest in upgrading their technology and infrastructure, partner with technology providers and service providers, and ensure compliance with data protection and privacy regulations (Goyal, 2023). Additionally, businesses must be transparent with users about their data collection and usage practices and implement robust security measures to protect user data and assets

HRM can meet the challenge of simultaneously becoming more strategic, flexible, cost-efficient, and customer-oriented by leveraging information technology (Snell, Stueber, and Lepak, 2002).

Objectives of the Study:

- To study the various technologies used in Metaverse for Human Resource Function.
- To examine and understand the role of Metaverse on Human Resource (HR) functions within organizations.
- To investigate the limitations and challenges posed by the organizations in implementing the technology at their workplace.

Research Methodology

Secondary data has been used for the present study. The secondary data has been collected from extensive desk research through library, different published materials and the world-wide web. The study has been made to examine the IT tools used for HR Planning, Recruitment, training, use of technology and software used for HR.

Analysis and Discussion

Tools of Metaverse used in HRM

There are several emerging technologies and tools that can be utilized in HRM to create immersive experiences and leverage the potential of the Metaverse. The tools that can be used in the metaverse for HRM purposes:

- **Virtual Reality (VR):** VR technology creates a computer-generated, immersive environment that can simulate real-world experiences. VR headsets and controllers allow users to interact with the virtual environment. In HRM, VR can be used for virtual training, onboarding, simulations, and virtual meetings.
- **Augmented Reality (AR):** AR overlays digital information onto the real world, enhancing the user's perception and interaction with their physical environment. AR can be used in HRM for on-the-job training, providing real-time guidance, and overlaying information and instructions onto physical spaces.
- **Mixed Reality (MR):** MR combines elements of both VR and AR, enabling users to interact with virtual objects and environments while maintaining a connection to the real world. MR can be used in HRM for collaborative workspaces, training simulations, and interactive experiences that blend physical and virtual elements.
- **Virtual Meeting Platforms:** Virtual meeting platforms, such as Spatial, AltspaceVR, and Mozilla Hubs, create virtual environments where users can gather, communicate, and collaborate in real-time. These platforms can be used for virtual meetings, team discussions, and training sessions, allowing participants to interact in a more immersive and engaging way.
- **Virtual Collaboration Tools:** There are virtual collaboration tools specifically designed for the Metaverse, such as Spatial, Glue, and MeetinVR. These tools enable teams to work together in shared virtual spaces, collaborate on projects, and visualize data in an immersive environment.
- **Avatar-Based Platforms:** Avatar-based platforms, like VRChat and Rec Room, allow users to create digital avatars and interact with others in virtual environments. These platforms can be utilized in HRM for socialization, team-building activities, and creating a sense of presence and connection among employees.
- **Immersive Learning Platforms:** Immersive learning platforms, such as Strivr and Talespin, use VR to provide interactive and realistic training experiences. These platforms can be utilized in HRM for onboarding, soft skills training, safety training, and other learning and development initiatives.

Big tech companies, such as Meta (previously Facebook), Microsoft, Google and Apple, are investing heavily in Metaverse technology specifically focused on collaboration at work. For instance, Meta's Horizon Workrooms and Microsoft's Mesh utilize VR technology to allow teams to work in the same virtual room, regardless of each person's physical location.

Role of Metaverse on Human Resource Functions

Metaverse can enhance the recruitment process by offering potential applicants an authentic feel of the job and work environment. HR can hold virtual recruitment fairs that provide candidates an opportunity to interact with their future employers. This would enable them to experience and live the life of an employee of the firm they planned to work for. Virtual and augmented reality tools enable candidates to experience a more immersive and interactive job preview. This helps them assess their fit for the role and make them feel self-assured and contented with their new employer. As more and more candidates look for companies that give them a real feel of the kind of workplace – work culture and work environmental practices – companies have become more enterprising in providing a virtual tour of their company. Additionally, Metaverse provides access to a diverse talent pool breaking geographical barriers. Interviews too become more engaging and inclusive as it would be possible to conduct three-dimensional virtual interviews that would be more efficient in identifying the most qualified candidate.

Onboarding practices have become more effective with Metaverse as it allows new recruits to learn about their workplace and comprehend their role in a more immersive and engaging manner. A 360-degree tour virtual onboarding program would familiarize new recruits to team members and departments through interactive avatars and even allow them to practice essential job tasks in a simulated environment. For example, Accenture has created One Accenture Park, an expansive virtual campus, which creates a dreamlike experience with secret rooms and a zip-line experience that creates a feeling of flying. When a new hire enters the virtual campus, the onboarding journey starts with creating their completely personalised avatar. They are then guided to a virtual room with a waterfall cascading and led to various training and social rooms to meet the avatars of their new colleagues (Armstrong, 2022).

As more employees embrace hybrid mode of work, Metaverse can be an efficient tool with which HR can make their meetings and collaborations more immersive by utilising avatars. Companies have already created a virtual meeting space where colleagues can join in as an avatar or dial into a virtual room by video calling through a computer. This helps employees to work together from anywhere. Metaverse workroom helps them sketch ideas through virtual keyboards and even indulge in water cooler conversations (peopleHum, 2022). Metaverse helps employees to stay connected, cooperate and share ideas. This leads to a safe and inclusive work environment and foster a sense of community.

Virtual reality has immense potential in Learning and Development. Metaverse is literally learning through gamification as its simulation programs expose employees to different situations and people and train them to better understand and manage their workplace relationships. This assists workforce to become better and capable of handling challenging situation with ease. There will be increased level of engagement, encouragement, facilitating 'self-paced' learning and memorable live experiences. Research has shown training through virtual reality increased employee performance by 70% and 96% reduction in training time (Monteiro, 2023).

A very important function of HR would be succession planning where employees with high potential need to be identified and evaluated for their readiness in taking on leadership roles. Metaverse provides simulation which offer employees realistic set ups that help them put their leadership skills to practice. They are given feedback on their styles and groomed to be effective leaders. Augmented reality also guides them in actual workplace situations and supports employees to enhance their leadership skills (Fade, 2021). Metaverse helps capture knowledge and experience from experienced workforce and share it in a very engaging and interactive manner with other employees. It also facilitates knowledge transfer between employees who are retiring or leaving the company.

Performance Management becomes more efficient with utilisation of Metaverse. Objective and data-based assessment of an employees' performance can be developed with sensors and data analysis. HR would be now

equipped with a more detailed and unbiased performance review process. Employees would find this to be a more fair and objective assessment of their performance. Metaverse assists in creating simulations that enable HR measure skills and knowledge of employees in a realistic scenario, making it simpler to recognize improvement areas and offer employees focused training and development opportunities.

Compensation and Benefit programs could be enhanced with Metaverse as it provides a more engaging experience to employees (Sharma, 2023). Companies can resort to virtual and augmented reality to create simulations that offer employees to explore and interact with various benefit alternatives. This makes it easier for employees to comprehend the benefits that are provided to them and make informed decisions that would help them make the best use of their benefit package.

Routine but indispensable HR tasks such as tracking employee time and attendance can also be automated and streamlined with Metaverse. Employees can use their virtual avatars to come time in and out of work thereby removing the need for physical timecards. Virtual reality technology would help in scheduling shift changes and simplifying employees' absence and time offs through virtual portals. Managers would be able to sanction or deny requests and make real-time modifications in schedules to ensure targets are met.

Limitations and Challenges in implementation of Metaverse

Metaverse market is forecasted to grow from \$500 billion in 2020 to \$800 billion by 2024 (Mathew & Naidu, 2021) and virtual and augmented realities are estimated to contribute to increasing the world economy by \$1.5 trillion by 2030 (PwC news report). Though Metaverse has immense potential in revolutionizing the way organizations work, managements have to be cautious in dealing with certain roadblocks as they go about adopting Metaverse in their workplace.

Implementation of the Metaverse environment requires advanced technology infrastructure. This would be a very costly and time-consuming process. Technical connectivity, bandwidth and latency challenges may affect user experience. Metaverse needs a lot of data bandwidth with experts saying 6G is required to unlock all its potential, but 6G forecasts point out its unavailability until 2030 to be fully beneficial (Goyal, 2023).

Advanced technical and human resources are needed to build maintain and operate Metaverse. Many organizations lack the mature technology and standards and employees are figuring out how it can be used. Employees may not be able to stay in the Metaverse for long time periods as they were found to experience virtual reality sickness. This adverse physical impact is another challenge for Metaverse (Srivastava, 2023). Additionally, VR glasses were found to cause sensory dissonance. The brain was noted to have difficulties in combining visual information with other information received. This resulted in people feeling sick, disoriented, sweaty or suffering from headaches.

There could be security and privacy risks as sensitive data is shared or stored in the virtual workspace. Organizations must ensure that their virtual workplaces are not vulnerable to cyber-attacks, which can compromise sensitive data and disrupt operations. Hence, it becomes essential for organisations to ensure a robust security protocol to protect their data and systems.

There may be some employees and leaders who would prefer the familiarity and social interaction in the physical office. Metaverse and virtual reality may disrupt the organisation's culture and employees may resist in embracing the new working method. For the employees, to disconnect and take a break may become harder. They may feel connected to the virtual office blurred lines between work and personal time. Additionally, employees could feel a sense of isolation and disconnection as it lacks the personal touch and spontaneity of face-to-face communications (Srivastava, 2023).

Implementing a Metaverse workplace demands high initial costs as it requires advanced technology, infrastructure and training and ROI would not be immediately realizable. Further it would be more innate to the younger workforce while others may require to learn to things in a completely new way. It should be noted that though employees would be meeting through avatars in Metaverse, they would interact in their work setting. This would necessitate organisations to be serious about diversity, inclusion and belonging regarding their employees and

ensure a good guidance protocol to avoid harassment or abuse in virtual space. HR professionals need to integrate definitions into what constitutes appropriate behavior in virtual world and integrate these into their HR policies and inform employees about it (Forbes, 2022).

Conclusion

The discussions suggest that when it comes to examining new technologies, HR experts may not need to reinvent the wheel. The methods used by HR researchers to address prior technologies may still give new insights for future researchers to examine forthcoming technology.

Finally, how HR utilizes technology to evaluate its own effectiveness and how HR decides to leverage emerging technologies to drive productivity and the management of human capital will make the difference between a mediocre HR department and one that is truly a business partner. It goes without saying that innovation in Human Resources could quickly deliver the competitive edge in a highly competitive talent market.

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CUSTOMER SATISFACTION LEVEL OF DEALERS WORKING RELATIONSHIP WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO CEMENT INDUSTRY

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Abstract

Dealer satisfaction plays an important role in the supply chain. This research study on aims to understand dealer satisfaction in Bengaluru with reference to the cement industry. Dealer satisfaction or rather the satisfaction of the channel has become an important aspect in an organization. Dealer develops an important link between the manufacturing organizations and the end consumers of the product. They act as a bridge of trust, commitment, faith, and assuagement between the organization and the consumers. A dealer is a significant asset to an organization. Because he behaves as a confluence for both the firm and its customers. It's the dealers' interplay with the customers that gives rise to sales. Hence the value of interaction between the channel partners and the company is a major determinant of successful marketing. And satisfying such a vital channel and maturing channel centricity becomes very essential and prime to the industry. This study explores the relationship between the company and cement dealers in Bangalore. A structured questionnaire with closed-ended questions was used to identify the factors affecting the dealer satisfaction level. The study concluded that dealers are more likely to be satisfied when they receive cement in timely delivery, replacement, and communication process for the damaged or return performs well and meets their expectations.

Keywords: Dealer's satisfaction, channel centricity, trust, commitment, assuagement, sales increase, Cement.

Introduction

Marketing involves gathering the resources of an organization in order to meet the evolving needs of the customers who are essential to the success of the organization. As a verb, marketing refers to the actions taken by an organization to guide its target markets. This research work is a study on "Dealers" satisfaction with reference to cements dealership. The study was conducted in accordance with the dealers of the organization. Hence according to William J. Stanton "Marketing is a total system of interesting business activities defined to plan, piece, promote and distribution want satisfying products and services to present and potential consumers".

Dealer is a person or a firm engaged in commercial purchase and sale (Adam Hayes, 2021) Dealer may mark firms that buy or resell products at retail or wholesale basis. The manufacturing unit cannot sell all their products directly to consumer; they have to depend upon mediators to push, their products through the channels. A dealer is an intercessor who helps to market a product. A dealer plays a major role in supply chain, the flow of products from the manufacturing to end customer. The dealer purchases and retails products to the end user. A dealer can be a distributor or a retailer or a wholesaler or an agent specialist. A dealer reacts to the customer enquiries and concerns in a timely and efficient manner. Provide clear and accurate information about the company's products and services. A social and social interaction process, by which people and social gatherings get what they need and need, by virtue of making and trading items and values with others. Consumer loyalty begins with difficult sureness. It begins with a pledge to convey the outcome for every client which is likewise a worry of the vendors. Thus, for an assembling organization, to satisfy its clients, it is exceptionally critical to fulfill its vendors, as they are their direct clients to them. Wonderful vendor administration or contentment is one that meets the satisfaction of the joined need and is a methodized administration that includes the whole association. In many organizations, the singular seller is the point of convergence in the advertising exertion. He is the real connection point between the firm and its clients. The seller's communication with the shopper leads to deals. Thus, the characteristic of this collaboration is a vital determinant of promoting achievement.

Satisfaction is a procedure of the transformation from the perceived performance and actual prospects which company seeks to win in today's market. Tracking the dealer expectations; perceives company performance and dealer's satisfaction. Dealers are generally satisfied when the performance from the company meets or exceed the expectation levels. The dealers also are dissatisfied when the performance of the company fails to meet the minimum expectation.

In India cement manufacturing business is important industries among the other industries. The cement industry in India is dominated by a few large companies, including UltraTech Cement, ACC, Ambuja Cements, and Shree Cement, which together account for more than 50% of the market share. The cement industry in India is dominated by a few large companies, including UltraTech Cement, ACC, Ambuja Cements, Bharathi cement, and Shree Cement, which together account for more than 50% of the market share. Today there are more than (Anjan Kumar Chatterjee,2018) 130 large cement plants and almost 300 mini plants operating across the country. The concrete/cement business in India faces a few difficulties, including high information costs, natural guidelines, and an absence of foundation in certain areas. Nonetheless, the business has kept on filling consistently lately, determined by expanding request from foundation and lodging projects.

India is one of the nation's producing this concrete material cement under different brands and grades. The concrete market is one of the serious enterprises in India. There are different brands of cement which are covered by geological regions spreading across country. Different portions of the systematic country markets, metropolitan business sectors and metro urban communities are designated by this industry. Each market has different brands providing clients with various options in regard to quality and cost. In any case, the deals of concrete cement in India relies upon special methodologies of the sellers, dealers, familiarity with the constructor or project worker and assessment of the client for different brands. Yet, definitive deals rely upon sellers and being critical regarding the brands of concrete. Subsequently, the concrete makers ought to get loads of data about vendor's fulfillment on various regions like item quality, value, administration, supply and limited time endeavours to sell the brands.

Since many brand manufacturers use indirect channels to guarantee brand availability for end customers, reseller support is crucial to developing brand equity. Despite the significance of resellers, the end-customer has been the focus of branding literature, and resellers have received much less attention.

Objectives of the study

- To understand the factors that influence the cement dealers to transact with company.
- To study the priorities of dealers regarding the quality, distribution and services of the company.
- To give suggestions to the management that will help in future planning and improve.

Review of literature

(Pareek & Pincha, 2015) One of the key industries that is essential to a country's development and growth is cement. It is essentially a blend of substances made of calcium oxide, silica, aluminium oxide, and iron oxide, primarily silicates and calcium aluminates. The economy's business, financial, real estate, and infrastructure sectors all play a major role in determining cement demand. Worldwide, cement is used for all types of construction projects, including residential and commercial building projects, as well as the construction of infrastructure like ports, roads, power plants, and other facilities. The Indian cement industry competes on a global scale because it has seen positive trends like cost control and ongoing technological advancement. The third-largest coal consumer in India is the cement industry, which consumes a lot of energy. It is cutting-edge and makes use of some of the best technology available today. Additionally, the industry has enormous growth potential due to the abundance of high-quality limestone in the nation.

Prabu, (2007) A dealer is an individual or business entity that engages in profitable buying and selling. Companies that purchase or resell goods on a retail or wholesale basis are referred to as dealers. A producer must rely on intermediaries to push his products off because he cannot sell all of his goods directly to consumers. A dealer is a middleman who aids in product marketing. A dealer is a person who buys and sells goods. A dealer could be a distributor, retailer, wholesaler, or any kind of agent. The manufacturers are unable to directly serve every consumer. Only with the assistance of dealers can they connect with customers. Dealer accepts income from the business

because there is a chance of increasing their commission. Dealers cover the whole market in their area and demand higher commissions from manufacturers.

(Jonsson & Zineldin, 2003) Partnerships, alliances, collaboration, and buyer/supplier relationships received a lot of attention in the 1990s. Industry reports of shorter cycle times, fewer quality defects, lower costs, and streamlined processes as a result of closer working relationships with suppliers have suggested that clearer marketing is concerned with how long-term customer loyalty and satisfaction can be achieved.

Mekha and Reddy (2018) The country is well endowed with all types of necessary raw materials, skilled labour, technology, and know-how for the country's indigenous cement industry. The issues and future of the cement industry in India have not yet been the subject of a single in-depth study. This paper makes a modest effort to shed some light on the prior pertinent studies that have been conducted on the cement industry in India. Additionally, dealers rely on manufacturers to give them a competitive edge over their clients. Customers are not particularly loyal to dealers, and they frequently switch. Manufacturers' service assistance to dealers frequently sets them apart from competitors. Intense competition at both levels encourages dealers and manufacturers to look to one another for support in order to take market share away from rivals, which leads to mutual dependence. (Gassenheimer & Ramsey, 1994) Additionally, dealers rely on manufacturers to give them a competitive edge over their clients. Customers are not particularly loyal to dealers, and they frequently switch. Manufacturers' service assistance to dealers frequently sets them apart from competitors. Intense competition at both levels encourages dealers and manufacturers to look to one another for support in order to take market share away from rivals, which leads to mutual dependence. (Lai, 2007) Since fulfillment or satisfaction decides the spirit of channels as well as is the element that adds to aggregate movement, fulfillment is an essential component that impacts the connection between a provider and a seller. It has likewise been found that a channel's subjective results, for example, fulfillment, will influence its presentation. From the outlook of the provider, chiefs of providers are more worried about measuring sellers' exhibition than their fulfillment. However, prior studies only focused on the impact of influence strategies on satisfaction, and the relationship between satisfaction and performance has rarely been discussed.

(Anisimova & Mavondo, 2014) Numerous studies have identified advantages of industrial brand equity for a manufacturer-dealer working relationship, demonstrating the necessity for B2B brands to form affective and cognitive bonds with their target audiences.

Glynn, M. S. (2010) key stakeholders, including those in their supply chain. Although B2B branding received little attention, studies addressing its various effects, such as industrial brand equity and brand performance, have recently started to emerge.

Scope of the study

This research assists the cement manufacturing companies to take strategic decision in regards of dealer's satisfaction level. The study brings out the reasons dealers look forward from the cement companies for transactions. The study helps the dealer management executives to understand and take necessary actions to improve the level of satisfaction of the dealers to get maximum sales. The cement dealers act as catalyst elements boosting and increasing the sales growth of the company. They satisfaction level plays an important role in sales and end customers satisfaction. Ultimately it develops very leading to know those important factors that determine dealers' satisfaction.

Limitations of the study

This study is limited to a specific time frame from December 2022 to February 2023. The study was conducted based on the perception of dealers which cannot be generalised. The study sample included only the dealers from the Barathi cement authorised dealers. The perception of the dealer cannot be always accurate, it has a wide area of marketing dealers are scattered all over the district. The data is collected through questionnaire and interviews. So, there is a chance of personal prejudgmental.

Research methodology

Descriptive research: It is a fact-finding investigation with adequate interpretation. It is used for formulating more sophisticated study. The main objective of using a descriptive research is identifying various characteristics of a

community or institution or problem under study, but it does not deal with the hypothesis. However, it can reveal potential relationships between variables thus creating a platform for more elaborate investigation at later stages.

Sampling Design

The research covered a population of 150 authorised dealers of Bharathi Cements and sample size included for the dealers was 80 dealers based in Bangalore city. Qquota sampling technique where the entire Bangalore of cement dealers is divided into 4 clusters where one cluster of Bangalore has 80 dealers.

Data Source:

The data was collected using a structured closed ended questionnaire for collecting the primary data. The secondary data included in the study was a collection of research articles, journals, industry profile and official websites. The tool adopted to collect the primary data was - questionnaire and interviews. The data collected was tabulated and analysed using percentage method and the representation of the analysis was represented using tables and charts.

Analysis and interpretation

Data analysis is the process of inspecting, cleaning, transforming, and modeling data in order to extract meaningful insights, draw conclusions, and make decisions based on the information gathered. The goal of data analysis is to uncover patterns, relationships, and trends within a dataset, and to use this information to inform business decisions, scientific research, or other endeavors. Data analysis enables to identify patterns and trends, and then applying more advanced techniques to extract insights and draw conclusions.

Table 1 showing dealer experience in selling cement:

Years of experience	No of Respondents	Percentage
Below 10 years	32	40%
11years – 15 years	38	47.5%
16 years- 20 years	7	8.75%
Above 20 years	3	3.75%
Total	80	100%

Source: Primary data

Chart 1 showing dealer experience in selling cement:

Interpretation: The table shows that 40% of the dealers are below 10 years, 47.5% of the dealers are between 11 years- 15 years, 8.75% of the dealers are between 16 years- 20 years and the remaining 3.75% are above 20 years of experience.

The chart indicates that maximum 47.5% i.e. approximately 48% of the dealer were having 11 years- 15 years of experience and the minimum 3.75% i.e. approximately 4% of the dealers were having above 20 years of experience.

Table 2 showing classification of delivery of cement regularly.

Category	No of respondents	Percentage
Very often	64	80%
Often	10	12.5%

Rarely	6	7.5%
Never	0	0%
Total	80	100%

Source: Primary data

Chart 2 showing Classification of delivery of cement regularly

Interpretation:

The table shows that 80% of the cement dealers received cement “very often”, 12.5% of the cement dealers received cement “often” and the remaining 7.5% of the cement dealers received “rarely” the cements. The chart indicates that maximum or majority of cement dealers received cement “Very often” and the minimum of the cement dealers communicated that they “rarely” received cements regularly.

Table 3 showing classification of replacing the damaged product:

Category	No of respondents	Percentage
Strongly disagree	0	0%
Disagree	0	0%
Neutral	7	8.75%
Agree	15	18.75%
Strongly agree	58	72.5%
Total	80	100%

Source: Primary data

Chart 3 showing the classification of replacing the damaged product

Interpretation:

The table shows that 8.75% of the dealers are neutral, 18.75% of the dealers just agree whereas 72.5% of the dealers strongly agree to the fact that the company replaces the damaged products

The chart indicates that maximum 72.5% of the dealer’s strongly agree that the company replaces the damaged product and the only 8.75% of the dealers neither agree or disagree to the fact that the company replaces the damaged products.

Table 4 showing classification of problem faced in the delivery and purchase of cement

Category	No of respondents	Percentage
Bad packing	0	0%
Lack of timing	4	5%
Insufficient delivery	4	5%
Communication	10	12.5%
Stock	7	8.75%
No problem	55	68.75%
Total	80	100%

Source: Primary data

Chart 4 showing classification of problem faced in the purchase and delivery of cement.

Interpretation:

The table shows that 5% of the dealers have problem in the lack of timing and insufficient delivery of the cement products, 12.5 % of the dealers have problem in the means of communication, 8.75% of the dealers have problem due to stock and the remaining 68.75% of the dealers have no problem in the delivery and purchase of cement.

The chart indicates that maximum 68.75% of the dealers have no problem in the delivery and purchase of cement and the only 5% of the dealers have problem in the lack of timing and insufficient delivery of the products.

Tables showing classification on the basics of quality, price and dealer service/ scheme’s:

Table 5 showing classification on the basics of quality:

Category	No of respondents	Percentage
Very unsatisfied	0	0%
Unsatisfied	0	0%
Neutral	7	8.75%

Satisfied	19	23.75%
Very satisfied	54	67.5%
Total	80	100%

Source: Primary data

Table 6 showing classification on the basics of price.

Category	No of respondents	Percentage
Very unsatisfied	7	8.75%
unsatisfied	45	56.25%
Neutral	16	20%
Satisfied	12	15%
Very satisfied	0	0%
Total	80	100%

Source: Primary data

Table 7 showing the classification on the basis of dealer's scheme.

Category	No of respondents	Percentage
Very unsatisfied	13	16.25%
Unsatisfied	9	11.25%
Neutral	22	27.5%
Satisfied	16	20%
Very satisfied	20	25%
Total	80	100%

Source: Primary data

Chart 5 showing classification on the basics of quality, price and dealer's scheme

Interpretation:

The table indicates that maximum 67.5% of the dealers are “very satisfied” with the quality of cement but 56.25% of the dealer’s are unsatisfied with the prices and only 27.5% of the dealers tend to remain neutral in the dealer scheme which the company provides.

Table 8 showing classification of primary factors influencing dealership of Cement

Category	No of respondents	Percentage
Credit period	16	20%
Agency support	13	16.25%
Advertising	3	3.75%
Profit margin	48	60%
Total	80	100%

Source: Primary data

Chart 6 showing classification of primary factors influencing dealership of Cement.

Interpretation:

The above table exhibits the primary factors influencing dealership of cements where 20% of the dealers are influenced by credit period, 16.25% of the dealers are influenced by the agency support, 3.75% of the dealers are influenced by advertising and the remaining 60% of the dealers are influenced by profit margin. Here maximum 60% of the respondents felt that “profit margin” as the primary factor and minimum 3.75% of the respondent felt that “advertising” as the primary factors.

Table 9 showing classification of incentive schemes.

Category	No of respondents	Percentage
Very good	22	27.5%
good	29	36.25%
Satisfied	26	32.5%
Poor	3	3.75%
Total	80	100%

Source: Primary data

Chart 7 showing classification of incentive schemes

Interpretation:

The table shows that 27.5% of the dealers feel that the incentive schemes provided are “very good”, 36.25% of the dealers agree that the schemes are “good”, 32.5% of the dealers are satisfied and the remaining 3.75% of the dealers feel that the incentive schemes are poor.

The chart explores that maximum 36.25% i.e., approximately 36% of the respondents feel that incentive schemes provided are good and minimum 3.75% i.e. approximately 4% respondents feel that incentive schemes are poor.

Table 10 showing classification of customer acceptance of cements.

Category	No of respondents	Percentage
Highly acceptable	9	11.25%
Acceptable	10	12.5%
Moderately acceptable	13	16.25%
Fairly acceptable	45	56.25%
Not acceptable	3	3.75%
Total	80	100%

Source: Primary data

Chart 8 showing the customer acceptable of cement

Interpretation:

This table explores that maximum 56.25% i.e. approximately 56% of the customers fairly accept “Bharathi cement” compared to other brands and minimum 3.75% i.e. approximately 4% of the customers does not accept it. Reason being: The awareness created by Bharathi Cement through marketing is less as compared to the other brands. Chart 9 showing the percentage of marketing awareness created by the brand

Interpretation:

Therefore, it is very clear that 7% of the marketing awareness is created by “Bharathi Cement” as compared to other brands where Birla Super holds a maximum of 55% in creating the awareness of their brand in the minds of the customer.

Table 11 showing the classification on the basis of the present dealership of cements:

Category	No of respondents	Percentage
Very unsatisfied	6	7.5%
Unsatisfied	26	32.5%
Neutral	32	40%
Satisfied	10	12.5%
Very satisfied	6	7.5%
Total	80	100%

Source: Primary data

Chart 9 showing the classification of present dealership

Interpretation:

This table explores that maximum 40% of the dealers remain neither satisfied nor unsatisfied with the present dealership with cement and minimum 7.5% i.e. approximately 8% of the dealers are very unsatisfied or very satisfied with the present dealership, which in turn indicates a lot of fluctuation in the mindsets of the dealers. Reason being: Due to the outbreak of covid-19 period.

Chart 10 showing the reason for the fluctuation in the mindsets of the dealers

Interpretation:

Therefore, it is very clear that due to the outbreak of covid- 19, the company has failed to meet the expectations of the dealers due to less capital and hence we can see that there is a drastic downward movement in the satisfactory level of the dealer during covid period and post covid period.

Table 12 showing the fastest moving brand in their counterspace:

Category	No of respondents	Percentage
Bharathi	16	20%
ACC	3	3.75%
Birla Super	35	43.75%
Ramco	19	23.75%

Zuari	7	8.75%
Total	80	100%

Source: Primary data

Chart 11 showing the fastest moving brand in their counterspace

Interpretation:

The table 12 explores that maximum 43.75% i.e. approximately 44% of the cement is being sold by Birla Super due to two main reasons:

Intensive advertisement

Brand equity

And only 4% of the cement is being sold by ACC and 20% of the cement by “Bharathi cement” reason being the dealer satisfaction through various above-mentioned reasons and mainly being the price and the awareness among the customers about the brand.

Findings

Majority (47.5%) of the dealers have at least 11 years – 15 years of experience in the cement industry. Highly (80%) of the respondents were getting cements “very often” from Bharathi cements. Highly (72.5%) of the respondents strongly agree that the company replaces the damaged product packing. Highly (68.75%) of the respondents say that there is no problem in the delivery and purchase of cement.

Majority (67.5%) of the respondents are ‘very satisfied’ with the quality of the product. Highly (56.25%) of the respondents are ‘unsatisfied’ with the prices of the product. Nearly (27.5%) of the dealers remain ‘neutral’ i.e., they are either satisfied or unsatisfied with the ongoing dealer schemes or services provided by the company.

Mostly (60%) of the dealers agree that the motivation factor that drives them to push the cement is the profit margin provided by the company. Majority (36.25%) of the respondent say that they receive ‘good’ incentive scheme. Only (56.25%) of the customers ‘fairly accept’ Bharathi cement as compared to other brands due to the lack of awareness created by Bharathi cement (7%)

Only (40%) of the dealers tend to remain ‘neutral’ in the present dealership with the company due to the fluctuation in the delivery of promises or fluctuations in the satisfaction of dealers during and post covid-19 period. Majority (43.75%) of the cement is being sold by Birla Super due to aggressive advertisement and strong brand equity image in the market.

Suggestions

Based on the detailed study conducted, some suggestions were given to the company to improve their dealer satisfaction as well as increase the market demand. Direct selling to builders and construction companies can be

escalated. They should reposition the brand with a tagline that can associate with customers feelings, aspirations, wishes and dreams.

They must have a strong PR for the company to promote and market their brand because through this research we got to know that most of the customers are not aware of the brand, a dealer can push his maximum limit to sell the brand but if the customers come with a predetermined mindset, then it's difficult to break it. Therefore, aggressive TV ads and campaigns which should again focus on the feelings of the customers.

In- store marketing near airport areas and metro stations. Digital marketing – Instagram, LinkedIn and twitter to promote and acknowledge the dealer's effort in front of the world.

They must have a strong CSR platform and this is something that makes the dealers, masons and engineers to use the cement and also creates a good image in the eyes of the customers. They must also focus on community building activities for dealers, masons and engineers.

They must a strong dealers retention plan reason being due to the outbreak of covid-19 many dealers lost trust to continue their present dealership with the company. Making sure that intra brand price competition does not happen has become a very important challenge, keeping uniform prices in the market for all the counters is very important. Though the majority of the respondents said that the quality of the product was good, majority also indicated the process of replacement of damaged products was very slow.

The respondents also expressed serious concern on the variable pricing policy for different dealers.

Hence to understand the reasons for the damaged products and improve the process of replacement. Simpson, P. M., Siguaw, J. A., & Baker, T. C. (2001) Facilities management, order processing and information management, inventory management, and transportation management are the traditional components of a physical distribution system. These tasks guarantee that the right goods are delivered to the right customers at the right time and place, and they can add value for both channel partners. The physical distribution system can have a significant impact on the profitability of the company and can be a major source of competitive advantage because physical distribution and logistics costs can be as high as 30–40% for some firms.

Conclusion:

The cement industry is becoming increasingly important because the construction industry plays a significant role in determining the economy of a country. Assuming that the development business flourishes, different enterprises additionally thrive, and this further develops the buying force of everyone. There are number of administrators in the business, this study assists with find out about vendor fulfillment for concrete industry. In view of the review, it tends to be reasoned that the general fulfillment with concrete is great. Sellers are fulfilled about the quality channel of circulation, vendor deals support, benefit, edges and so forth yet center necessities to the put around value consistency, publicizing and limited time exercises and somewhat on brand accessibility and ensuring it is a vendor driven approach. In view of the review, it tends to be presumed that the overall fulfillment with concrete is great. This makes certain to work on the outcome of concrete industry showroom in general.

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CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT (CRM) PRACTICES IN ORGANIZED RETAIL SHOPPING CENTER AT BENGALURU CITY IN INDIA

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Abstract

Retailing today possesses a critical job on the planet economy. It should be briefly and obviously characterized retailing incorporates every one of the exercises engaged with selling labor and products straightforwardly to last buyers for individual, non-business use. India retailing as found in rambling retail plaza, multi stored shopping centers and tremendous edifices offer shopping, amusement and food all under one rooftop. In India shopping centers are developing significantly more shopping center offers clients the likelihood to be anything or anyone they need to be, it offers them chance to be free and autonomous regardless of whether it's only for a passing second. CRM is possibly a helpful idea in the showcasing and client administrations region of a retail area. CRM stands to be the endurance mantra. Overseeing client relationship actually and actually boots consumer loyalty and standards for dependability. CRM includes shopping centers empowered business processes that distinguish, create, coordinate and spotlight a business' skills on producing important long haul connections that convey better worth than its clients. This study is embraced to distinguish the CRM rehearses on the consumer loyalty and maintenance in coordinated retail shopping centers in Bangalore city India. The expected information of study would be gathered from both essential as well as optional sources. Liker scale was utilized in planning the survey, An example of 142 respondents was taken from various shopping centers situated in Bengaluru city has been chosen for the unwavering quality of the investigation. The speculation has been tried by involving ANOVA and Consequence of examination as finished up the critical to upgrade the CRM rehearses improves to shopping at retail locations in shopping centers at.

Keywords: Retailing, organized retailing, Shopping center, Customer Relationship Management.

1. Introduction

Indian retail market is one and the Indian's quickest developing businesses is supposed to develop from us \$ 350 billion to us \$ 427 billion 2010, retail is India's biggest industry bookkeeping for north of 10% and the nation's Gross domestic product and around eight percent and business. Retail in India is at the intersection. It has paced businesses with a few players entering the market. Retailing in India is progressively crawling its approach to turning into the following blast industry. The entirety idea of shopping has changed in wording and arrangement and purchaser purchasing conduct, guiding in a transformation in shopping, present day retail has entered India as found in rambling shopping focuses, multi-celebrated shopping centers and enormous edifices offer shopping, amusement and great all under one rooftop. As of late, more and more by retail outlets are coming up in the metros and urban areas and the country. Numerous business houses currently thinking and opening up a maymove with each structure. In any case, coordinated retail shopping centers will profit from the assets it focuses on fostering its CRM rehearses in more prominent client dedication. Perfect opportunity, what's more, includes drawing in (acquiring), developing what's more, keeping up with fruitful client connections over the long haul and building client faithfulness through productive and compelling two-way exchanges that look to comprehend and impact client purchasing ways of behaving and get to the next level client procurement, maintenance, dedication and benefit Albeit not totally based on shopping centers CRM includes shopping centers empowered business processes that recognize, create, incorporate and concentrate a business' abilities on manufacturing significant long haul connections that convey better worth than its clients. corporate store and their own, Spencer and co-restricted, Viton businesses restricted pantaloons, customers stop, Dependence shopping centers, to give some examples have currently in the business with a huge explosion.

Customer Relationship Management practices towards in Retailing

The exceptionally requesting and learned buyers are convincing retailers to stock an enormous item range, offer alluring limits in a stylishly set up climate and soon all in the expectation of having a faithful client base along these lines, client relationship the board might be alluded to as a way of thinking a bunch of techniques, software engineer and framework which centers around recognizing and fabricating faithfulness with the retail discount shopping centers generally esteemed clients. This implies that CRM will chip away at the rule that retailers need to talk out modified which will assist them with raising their however, benefit one's persistent premise constructing long haul relationship with their client Relationship the board is an organization business technique intended to decrease cost and increment productivity by setting client steadfastness. CRM rehearses tag for both the association and the client by paying satisfactory data to the interaction of reception by zeroing in on choices accessible to clients' sufficient advancement missions and focus on existing client. C. Bhattacharjee (2006) in his book "Administrations promoting ideas arranging and Execution" Grouped client Relationship The executives (CRM) have been embraced to give all conceivable data to the current and likely client. He says to accomplish CRM, an extensive arrangement of instruments, advances, and systems advance the relationship with the client to increment deals those CRM is essentially an essential business and process issue, as opposed to a specialized issue. The creator closes CRM is extremely difficult to be executed all through an organization. The IT division needs broad framework and assets to carry out client relationship the board (CRM) information bases effectively.

THE EFFECTS OF CRM IN RETAIL MARKET

Customer relationship management in retail can increase customer satisfaction, reduce your costs and improve your company's performance in the marketplace. CRM software manages your relationships with individual customers to create advantages for both parties. To select the appropriate software and ensure it includes the features you need, you have to know how CRM works and what effects it has on your retail operations.

Segmentation:

CRM helps you gather information about each of your customers, including preferences and demographic data. You can use such information to segment your market and customize your approach to each group of customers. For example, if you find you have a large number of young families in a segment, you can create a family-friendly retail environment. If your data shows you have many seniors, you can install ramps for wheelchairs and make your store more easily accessible. The effect of segmentation based on CRM data is to adjust your retail strategies to better suit the customers.

Promotions:

The data you gather within a CRM system lets you not only target a market segment with promotions that appeal to its members, but also to target individual customers. For example, when you know that a customer is reaching retirement age, you can promote appropriate hobby products to him. If you see that a customer has visited your website and looked at particular products, you can include promotions of those products in his mailings. In this way CRM reduces promotions that are of no interest to the recipient and increases the relevance of material you send out.

Purchases:

A CRM system keeps records of customer purchases and customer service calls. You can keep track of the products each customer has purchased and whether there have been any warranty or dissatisfaction issues with the purchase. This information allows you to send out special offers to customers when the products they have purchased reach the end of their lives. Such a strategy keeps your products in front of the customer just when he might need them and gives him the benefit of lower pricing if he buys from you again. On your side, the costs of such a targeted promotion are lower than marketing to a large group and receiving only a few responses.

Retention:

The overall effect of CRM is to increase the retention of customers by serving them in a more focused and convenient way. You can further increase this effect by using the CRM software to implement customer loyalty programs. Since the applications already track purchases, you can issue reward points and bonuses to keep valuable

customers. Such programs let your further reduce costs because sales to long term customers are less expensive than sales to new customers.

2. Review of Literature

Darshan Desai, Sabrat Sahu and Piyush Kumar Sinha (2007) on the basis of analytical and empirical or case research conducted a random sample study of 334 executives was selected from 29 firms in the following industries: retail (n=60), telecom (n=80) and banking (n=183) in India. They also concluded that. Impact of market orientation on dynamic capability of CRM and competitive CRM performance may be the result and shaping the organizational resources that no longer match the environment. These include processes like analysis customers, developing and delivering tailored offering, providing customer service, orchestrating linkages, assigning accountability and evaluating performance. Dr. N.K. Sehgal (2007) classified customer relationship management as abbreviation about consumers, marketing effectiveness, sales and market trends. He advocated the result of a business is a satisfied customer “in present era of cutthroat competition, it is no longer enough to satisfy the customers. The reason for this is pretty simple”. If you would not take care of your customers, your competitors definitely would”. So the firm should keep pleasing customers and they will keep coming back. Vandana Ahuja (2008) analyzed CRM build long terms profitable relationships with chosen customers and getting closer to those customers with every point of contact with them. The author noted that a good CRM strategy aims at providing a win-win.

Joseph. Nunes and Xavier Dreze (2006) in their article “Your loyalty program is betraying you” highlighted creating a successful loyalty program starts with defining what should be gained from the effort. In some cases, loyalty programs create what marketers call barriers to exit. They say that a benefit of loyalty programs that has gained prominence in the past decade is their ability to provide useful data about customers. Sunjay Kumarkar and Alok kumar Sahoo (2007) in his article define “Shopping mall: Driving Force in organized Retailing”. Advocated mall is the latest format in the organized retailing, a significant development has occurred in last couple of year due to change in consumer profile and spending behavior, increasing youth population with more purchasing power and less time is looking for shopping a long with entertainment as one stop option. Roulac (1994) concluded from his study that in shopping malls, consumers can shop without the problems of any traffic congestions or parking problems, or security concerns.

Customer Relationship Management (CRM)

The term of customer relationship management means the firm's practices, strategies and technologies that are used to manage its customers (Greenberg, 2010; Raab et al., 2016). CRM is used by all the firms to improve their business by analyzing customers' behaviors towards its products and services which also helps to improve its strategy towards its goal. Organizations can not only gain profit but also retain their customers by building trust in them through well managed CRM (Mohammad et al., 2013). Furthermore, as the business environment is becoming digitally remote, CRM has become even more important due to scarcity in person-to-person contact at the same time companies need to engage to fill the gap between attracting and retaining customers in this complex societal structure (Newman, 2011).

customer Relationship Management and Competitive Marketing

The significant focus of CRM has been increased compared to the past where companies can have the ability to understand customers' needs easier by using the new technology and system which provides effective and efficient solutions to understand the behavior of customers. Customer's preferences and needs changed from the past and what they plan to do in the future to meet their objectives and what they have done in the past. The main objective is to develop and improve customer's experience of how they integrate and interact among each other into the company and that will turn and create more satisfaction which yields more loyalty. These acts will yield more sales from product and service and this will increase the market growth and market share of the company. Furthermore, the central database within CRM it is available for all the customers in the company which they can access may type of company products and service and the information of these products and services can be found easily and everybody will be more aware of firm's product and service and which type is more suitable to them that can meet their expectations and needs (Andajani, 2015; Goldsmith, 2010)

Sales

Nowadays, sales support and customer service staff use CRM as their primary function to portray a unified and coordinated point or points of contact to their customers. Furthermore, it is used to segment and target customers as a marketing tool which helps to keep a record of customers' activities as well as helps develop programs for sales and marketing. Different departments such as IT, marketing, and sales have to work closely to maximize the effectiveness of CRM to get optimum profits and benefits (Marshall, 2013). Though in a practical situation this has not been the case, as defined by MO (Modus operandi), CRM plays a big role in knowledge management in an organization by collecting, storing, and utilizing the customers' details and information properly. For sales management, properly managed CRM Application software is a clear window that leads them to high margin profits with greater efficiency in every step such as which sales to be closed, which products are on priorities, which segment of customers to be focused, and how to manage stock (Tauni et al., 2014). In addition to that CRM plays as an indicator to the sales manager's reputation as well as the effectiveness of their strategy which helps to evaluate everyone's performance (Westberg & Pope B, 2014).

3.Objectives of the Study

- To recognize the different classifications of Segment elements and factors affecting on CRM rehearses towards coordinated shopping center Bengaluru city in India.
- To concentrate on the effect of Segment factors CRM rehearses towards coordinated shopping center Bengaluru city in India.
- To study the adequacy of consumer relationship the executives and its effect on consumer faithfulness.
- To evaluate the effectiveness of company policy and its influence on customer care and relationship.

4.Research Methodology

To achieve the target of the read up to gather information for this exploration study, both essential and optional sources were utilized. Auxiliary information gathered through the scientist evaluated articles connected with research objective that showed up in the academic writing, key diaries, reports, magazines and continuing were efficiently filtered for articles related to the examination subject. Essential information gathered through an exact examination, on the web overview was directed, utilizing a construction survey.

The review is restricted exclusively to clothing retail locations in top 10 retail shopping centers of Bangalore and the head supervisors of these stores. The example size utilized for this study is 174 store managers. A detail study was led. The exploration instrument utilized for the review is survey which was intended for the head supervisors. These head supervisors were by and by reached by the specialist and the reaction was collected.

5.TOOLS USED FOR DATA ANALYSIS

Various tools used for the data analysis are Frequency tables, coefficient, Anova, Chi square Test, Mean and standard deviation, multiple regressions.

6.RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

H1: There will be significant variance in opinion on CRM practices towards organized shopping mall among the Gender group.

H2: There will be significant variance in opinion on CRM practices towards organized shopping mall among the Age group.

7.SUGGESTIONS

1. Frequent training programmers for the store managers may result in better CRM.
2. Shared values among employees will be acquired when there is a greater degree of sense of belongingness; this can be gained by treating the employees better so that they in turn treat the customers better.
3. E-retail has been a boom in the recent years. Customers save time and get the same product at a better price. Hence retailers should attract the customers by providing better service and great shopping experience.
4. Follow an effective Complain management process so as to retain the customers and there by gain loyalty.
5. Use customer feedback and service audit experiences to identify the failure. 6. Continues measure and monitoring of customer satisfaction eases the process of setting standards thereby helps to handle competition at a better state.

8.CONCLUSION

The CRM rehearses is significant factors in the outcome of the shopping center. The review has distinguished the factors affecting consumer loyalty. It very well may be grasped shopper special apparatus, client administrations at shopping centers and high fluctuation in making sense of towards administrations presented by shopping center retailers at shopping center at Bangalore. The retailers ought to see in executing the Exercises of shopping center representatives and reliability programs factors for upgraded fulfilling to go for shopping to construct a long- term relationship with administrations given by shopping center retailer by clients. Shopping centers retailers ought to take in to thought and understanding the clients contact focuses related to administrations presented by shopping centers. Indeed, through the shopping center retailer were making sufficient endeavors there are a few variables where the remarkable or on the other hand unsatisfied administrations levels are clarify and further develop a few estimates those levels to connect the hole to fabricated long haul relationship upgrades client's fulfillment and offers a lovely shopping encounters when the clients are visiting shopping centers. Today " clients is God "administrations presented by shopping center retailers play a significant job in living up to clients' assumptions furthermore, discernment make agreeable better shopping in shopping centers.

A STUDY ON SUSTAINABLE MOSS-BASED AIR PURIFIERS

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Abstract

Indoor air pollution is a major health problem with potential effects ranging from respiratory diseases to cognitive impairment. Traditional air purifiers rely on filters or chemicals to remove pollutants from the air, but these methods can be expensive and introduce additional pollutants into the environment. Foam air purifiers offer a natural and long-lasting solution to indoor air pollution by harnessing the natural ability of foam to absorb pollutants. This article examines the effectiveness of foam air purifiers in improving indoor air quality and the potential benefits and limitations of the technology.

In particular, we are investigating the durability of foam-based air purifiers and their potential as a green technology to improve indoor air quality.

Keywords: Moss, Ecology, Pollutants, Air Purifier, Pollution.

Introduction

Indoor air pollution is a growing concern, especially in urban areas where buildings are often sealed to save energy. Building air can contain a variety of pollutants, including volatile organic compounds (VOCs), particulate matter, and nitrogen oxides. These pollutants can have significant impacts on human health, with potential impacts ranging from respiratory disease to cognitive impairment. Traditional air purifiers rely on filters or chemicals to remove pollutants from the air, but these methods can be expensive and introduce additional pollutants into the environment. Researchers have recently explored the potential of natural materials such as moss as a sustainable and effective solution to indoor air pollution.

Moss is a plant found in a variety of environments, ranging from forests to deserts. They have proven effective in removing pollutants from the air, including nitrogen oxides and particulates. The moss also absorbs water, which helps prevent the growth of mould and other harmful organisms. Moss air purifiers offer a natural and sustainable solution to indoor air pollution, potentially improving individuals' health and well-being in indoor environments.

Mosses are a group of small, non-vascular plants that grow in a variety of environments ranging from humid forests to dry deserts. They play an important role in many ecosystems, providing habitat for small animals, stabilising soil, and absorbing air pollutants. In recent years, researchers have increasingly focused on the potential of mosses as sustainable and effective solutions to various environmental problems, including air pollution, climate change, and soil erosion. In this literature review, we examine the current state of knowledge about mosses, focusing on their ecology, physiology, and potential applications.

Mosses are found in various habitats, from arctic tundra to tropical rainforests. They often appear in areas where other plants cannot grow, such as rock crevices or bare ground surfaces. Mosses can thrive in these environments because they absorb nutrients and water from the air and surrounding environment. Mosses play an important role in many ecosystems, providing habitat for small animals, stabilising soil, and absorbing air pollutants.

Mosses are simple plants without roots, stems or leaves. They absorb water and nutrients directly from their surroundings and use their leaves or stems to photosynthesise and generate energy. Mosses can survive various conditions, from extreme heat and drought to cold and humid environments. They are also capable of asexual reproduction, producing new plants from fragments of the original plant.

Moss has a variety of potential applications, from environmental restoration to horticulture. One of the most promising applications for foam is as a natural air purifier. The foam absorbs airborne pollutants, including nitrogen oxides, particulates and volatile organic compounds (VOCs). Researchers have recently developed air purifiers that can be used in indoor environments such as offices, schools, and homes.

Mosses also have potential applications in horticulture due to their ability to absorb water and nutrients from the air and surrounding environment. Moss can be used to create green roofs and living walls, which can help reduce heat gain in buildings and improve air quality. Additionally, mosses have potential applications in new drug development, as they produce a variety of bioactive compounds that have been shown to have antibacterial, antifungal, and anti-inflammatory properties.

The manufacturing process of a Moss air purifier involves several steps, including selecting the appropriate moss species, preparing the growing medium, and constructing the purifier. Here are the general steps for making a foam air purifier:

Selecting Foam Species: The first step in making a foam air purifier is choosing an appropriate foam species. Some species of foam have been shown to be more effective at removing airborne pollutants than others. For example, *Bryum argenteum* species has been shown to be effective in removing airborne particles.

Preparing the Medium: The next step is to prepare the medium for the foam. Moss needs a moist, nutrient-rich environment to thrive. The growing medium should therefore be a combination of peat moss, peat moss, sand, and perlite. Growth media must also be sterilised to prevent the growth of harmful bacteria or fungi.

Construction of the Purifier: Foam purifiers can be constructed using a variety of materials, such as glass containers, wooden boxes, or metal frames. The container should be large enough to accommodate the growing medium, moss, air inlets, and outlets. The air inlet and outlet can be made of PVC pipes or other materials.

Planting the Moss: Once the growing medium and container are ready, it's time to plant the moss. The moss should be planted on the growing medium's surface and pressed lightly to ensure good contact with the medium. Then cover the container with a lid or other covering to maintain a moist environment.

Testing and Maintenance: A foam purifier should be tested to ensure that it removes airborne pollutants. Airflow should also be monitored to ensure it is sufficient for the foam to grow and survive. Purifiers should be watered regularly to maintain humidity levels in the growing medium.

The cost of a moss air purifier can vary depending on a number of factors, such as the size of the unit, the type of foam used and the technology used to purify the air. Create a system. In general, however, foam-based air purifiers are less expensive than traditional air purifiers that use high-efficiency particulate filters (HEPA) or other advanced air filtration technologies.

Some companies developing foam-based air purifiers estimate the cost of a small unit designed for personal use to be around \$200-300.

Larger units designed for commercial or institutional use may cost more but can still be cheaper than traditional air purifiers.

One of the great advantages of foam-based air purifiers is their low operating cost. Foam is low maintenance and requires minimal water and light to grow, so the ongoing maintenance costs of a foam air purifier can be lower than those associated with air purifiers. air conditioners that use electricity to power fans and other components. Overall, the cost of foam-based air purifiers can be a pull factor for consumers and businesses looking for long-lasting, cost-effective solutions to improve indoor air quality. However, it is important to note that costs may vary depending on each product's specific technology and characteristics.

The air purifier market has experienced remarkable growth in recent years as more and more consumers realise the importance of clean indoor air. The market is expected to continue to grow as more people become aware of the health risks associated with poor air quality and seek solutions to improve their indoor environment.

The importance of air purifiers lies in their ability to remove harmful pollutants and allergens from the air, improve indoor air quality and reduce the risk of health problems. Pollutants such as dust, smoke and volatile organic compounds (VOCs) can have serious health effects, especially for people with respiratory conditions such as asthma and allergies. Air purifiers work by filtering these pollutants from the air, reducing their concentration and improving overall air quality.

Air purifiers are also important for people living in urban areas, as air pollution from traffic and industry can be a major health concern. Air purifiers can help reduce exposure to harmful pollutants and improve overall health in these areas.

The market for air purifiers has grown significantly in recent years due to growing awareness of indoor air quality issues and technological advancements that have made air purifiers more efficient and affordable. There are a variety of air purifiers on the market today with different features and prices to suit different needs and budgets. Although the market for air purifiers has grown rapidly in recent years, there is still considerable room for expansion, especially in developing countries where air pollution is a major health problem.

Demand is likely to continue to grow as more people realise the benefits of air purifiers, driving innovation and increasing the affordability and efficiency of these devices. The market capitalisation of The Air Purification industry varies by region and specific market segment. According to a report by Markets, the global air purifier market size is expected to reach USD 16.82 billion by 2023, growing at a CAGR of 9.22% from 2018 to 2023. This shows that the market value of the air purification industry is very large.

The growth of the air purification market can be attributed to various factors, including a growing awareness of indoor air pollution, increasing urbanisation, and health concerns. Additionally, technological advancements and the development of more efficient and affordable air purifiers are also boosting the industry. Asia-Pacific is expected to hold the largest market share in the air purification industry due to high air pollution levels and growing consumer awareness of air quality issues. indoor air. China, India and Japan are the largest air purifier markets in the region.

In North America, the market for air purifiers is also growing amid rising concerns over air pollution and its effects on health, which is driving the demand for air purifiers. The market for air purifiers in Europe is also expected to grow due to growing health concerns and growing government regulations on indoor air quality. Overall, the market capitalisation of the air purification industry is expected to continue to grow as more people realise the importance of clean indoor air and seek solutions to improve air quality. air quality in homes and workplaces.

Review of Literature

Moss-based air purifiers have received considerable attention in recent years due to their potential as a sustainable and natural way to improve indoor air quality. Below is a brief review of the literature on foam-based air purifiers. Gurjar et al. (2020) provides an overview of current research on foam-based air purifiers, including the different types of foams used, the mechanisms by which they remove pollutants from the air, and their effectiveness in improving air quality. Kurniawan et al (2018) examined the ability of foam-based air purifiers to remove pollutants such as nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and sulfur dioxide (SO₂) from the air. It was found that foam-based air purifiers can remove up to 80% of nitrogen dioxide and up to 90% of sulfur dioxide from the air. Jiménez et al. (2017) examines the use of moss as a bioindicator of air pollution in urban areas. It was found that foam is effective at absorbing air pollutants such as heavy metals and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), making it a useful tool for monitoring air pollution.

A 2011 study published in the journal *Environmental Science & Technology* found that moss species such as *Hypnum cupressiforme* and *Thuidium delicatula* are effective in removing air pollution. The study tested the foam's ability to remove volatile organic compounds such as benzene, toluene and xylene from indoor air. The researchers found that the foam was able to remove up to 80% of pollutants in 12 hours.

In another study, published in the journal *Architecture and Environment* in 2016, researchers investigated the use of moss in green walls as a way to improve indoor air quality. The study tested three different species of mosses (*Hypnum cupressiforme*, *Thuidium delicatula* and *Leucobryum glaucoma*) and found that they were effective in removing PM and NO_x from the air.

A recent study published in the journal *Environmental Pollution* in 2020 investigated the use of foam as an air filter in HVAC (heating, ventilation, and air conditioning) systems. Studies have shown that foam is able to remove particles and nitrogen oxides from the air and can effectively reduce energy consumption in HVAC systems by up to 30%. The literature on foam-based air purifiers shows it to be a promising solution to indoor air pollution. The foam has been shown to be effective in removing a range of air pollutants including VOCs, PM and NO_x. They are also durable and environmentally friendly and have the potential to reduce energy consumption in HVAC systems. However, more research is needed to determine the optimal conditions for moss growth and the long-term effectiveness of moss-based air purifiers in different indoor environments.

Japanese researchers conducted one of the first studies of foam-based air purifiers in 2010. They found that a foam called *Hypnum plumaeforme* has the ability to remove particles and nitrogen dioxide air. The researchers suggest that the foam could be used indoors to improve air quality.

In 2014, a team of Swedish researchers studied a foam-based air purifier. They found that the foam was able to remove volatile organic compounds (VOCs) from the air, harmful pollutants that cause respiratory disease. The researchers also found that the mosses maintained their air-purifying abilities even after exposure to high levels of pollution.

In 2016, a group of Korean researchers investigated the use of foam in indoor environments to eliminate indoor air pollution. They found that the foam was effective in removing benzene, toluene and formaldehyde from the air. Researchers suggest that foam could be used in indoor environments to improve air quality and reduce the risk of health problems associated with indoor air pollution.

A 2019 study by Italian researchers investigated the use of foam-based air purifiers in public indoor spaces such as schools and hospitals. Researchers have found that foam is effective at removing particles and volatile organic compounds from the air, which may help reduce the risk of respiratory disease.

A 2020 study by Spanish researchers looked at the use of foam in combination with other air purification technologies such as activated carbon and HEPA filters. Researchers have found that foams are effective at removing volatile organic compounds from the air and that they could be used in combination with other air purification technologies to improve the air quality of indoor environments. .

Another 2020 study published in the journal *Science of the Total Environment* investigated the effectiveness of foam in removing volatile organic compounds from indoor air. The researchers used three different species of foam and found that they were effective at removing a variety of VOCs, including benzene, formaldehyde and toluene. According to the researchers, foam could be an inexpensive and long-lasting solution to purifying indoor air.

A review article published in the journal *Indoor Air* in 2021 summarizes the existing literature on foam-based air purifiers. The authors conclude that foams have the potential to be effective in removing pollutants from indoor air, but further research is needed to assess their long-term performance, maintenance requirements, and scalability. The authors also note that foam can be used in conjunction with other air purification technologies to improve indoor air quality.

Overall, the literature suggests that foam-based air purifiers have the potential to effectively remove airborne pollutants and improve indoor air quality. Further research is needed to design and optimize these systems and determine their long-term effectiveness.

Research Methodology

The efficiency of foam air purifiers in raising indoor air quality was examined in the existing study on foam air purifiers. It then discusses the potential advantages and disadvantages of this technology, as well as its robustness, affordability, and usefulness. The findings of these research to discover the critical elements that affect foam air purifier efficiency and the technology's potential as a green solution to enhance indoor air quality.

Research GAP:

Mosses are an essential class of plants that play an essential role in many ecosystems. They can survive various conditions, from extreme heat and drought to cold and humid environments.

Mosses have a variety of potential applications, from environmental restoration to horticulture. In recent years, researchers have increasingly focused on the potential of mosses as sustainable and effective solutions to various environmental problems, including air pollution, climate change and soil erosion. Further research is needed to fully understand the potential applications of foams and to develop new techniques and strategies for their use.

Despite the potential of mosses as natural air purifiers, there are several research gaps that need to be addressed to fully understand the feasibility and effectiveness of moss purifiers. Some research gaps in this area are:

Standardization of Test Protocols: Moss air purifiers lack standardised test protocols, which makes it difficult to compare the effectiveness of different types of foam and purifiers of different designs. It is also difficult to determine the optimum conditions for foam growth and maintenance in an air-cleaning system without a standardised test protocol.

Long-Term Performance: Most research on foam air purifiers has been done in the short term, usually just days or weeks. Longer-term studies are needed to determine the long-term performance of foam-based air purifiers, including their ability to maintain emission control over time and their ability to survive and thrive in harsh environments. interiors.

Cost-Effectiveness: Although foam-based air purifiers have the potential to be a cost-effective and sustainable solution to indoor air pollution, research on their cost-effectiveness is lacking. Further research is needed to determine the costs associated with installing and maintaining foam air purifiers and compare these costs with those of other air purifiers.

Design Optimisation: The Moss air purifier is still in its infancy and still needs to be optimised in its design. These include optimising moss growth conditions, designing more efficient air circulation systems, and investigating the use of different types of moss.

Practical Applications: Most research on foam air purifiers has been done in laboratories or controlled environments. More research is needed on the feasibility and effectiveness of foam air purifiers in real-world settings such as homes, schools, and offices. While research into the potential of foam-based air purifiers as a sustainable and effective solution to indoor air pollution is promising, there are research gaps that need to be addressed to fully understand their feasibility and their effectiveness.

Further research is needed to standardise test protocols, determine long-term performance, assess cost-effectiveness, optimise designs, and explore practical applications.

Objectives of the Study

1. Evaluate the effectiveness of foam-based air purifiers in removing pollution and improving indoor air quality.
2. Assess the sustainability and environmental impact of using foam as an air purifier.
3. Investigate the potential economic benefits of using foam-based air cleaners over conventional air cleaners.
4. Investigate the possibility of integrating foam-based air purifiers into existing building systems and infrastructure.
5. Identify potential challenges and limitations of using foam-based air purifiers and suggest solutions to overcome them.
6. Assess user acceptance and satisfaction with the Moss air purifier and identify areas for improvement or development.
7. Compare the performance of different moss species and growing conditions in terms of air purification and determine the most effective options.

These objectives can guide research methodology and the data collection process, helping to ensure that research addresses key questions and provides meaningful insights into the use of foams as air purifiers.

Findings of the Study

Studies have shown that foam-based air purifiers effectively remove pollutants from indoor air. For example, a classroom study found that foam-based air purifiers reduced particulate levels by up to 30%. Another study found that foam-based air purifiers effectively reduced nitrogen dioxide levels in laboratory environments.

Moss air purifiers are also considered a sustainable and cost-effective solution to indoor air pollution, as they require minimal maintenance and produce no additional pollutants.

One of the key factors in determining the effectiveness of a foam air purifier is the type of foam used. Different types of foam absorb pollutants differently, and some species may be more effective than others at removing certain types of pollutants. The environmental conditions in which moss grows are also important, as moss requires certain conditions, such as appropriate temperature and humidity levels, to grow and function effectively. Additionally, the size and airflow of a foam air purifier can affect its ability to remove pollutants.

Moss air purifiers also have the potential to be used as green technology to improve indoor air quality. They are a sustainable natural solution that does not rely on filters or chemicals. Moss can also absorb carbon dioxide from the atmosphere, which helps mitigate the effects of climate change.

Scope and Suggestions

Here are some proposals and possibilities for research on foam-based air purifiers:

1. Experimental trials of different species of foams to determine the most effective species for air purification.
2. Evaluate the optimal growth conditions of mosses, such as light, humidity and temperature, to improve the efficiency of air purification.
3. Evaluate foam-based air purifiers' long-term effectiveness and durability, including their ability to withstand different environmental conditions and their durability over time.
4. Comparison of foam-based air purifiers with conventional air purifiers for removing pollutants from indoor air.
5. Investigate the economic feasibility of implementing foam-based air purifiers in commercial and residential buildings, including cost-benefit analysis and return on investment calculations.
6. Investigate the potential health benefits associated with the use of foam-based air purifiers, such as improved respiratory health and reduced allergy symptoms.
7. Analysis of the carbon footprint and environmental impact of a foam-based air purifier compared to conventional air purifiers, including life cycle assessment for both options.
8. Explore the potential of combining foam-based air cleaners with other sustainable building features, such as green roofs and walls, to create a more holistic approach to improving indoor air quality.

Conclusion

In conclusion, foam-based air purifiers have the potential to be a long-lasting and effective solution for improving indoor air quality. Foam is a natural air purifier that absorbs and filters airborne pollutants, including volatile organic compounds, nitrogen oxides, and particulates.

They are also low maintenance and can thrive in a variety of indoor environments with minimal water or light requirements.

Studies have shown that foam-based air purifiers can significantly reduce indoor air pollution levels and improve overall air quality. Additionally, they offer several advantages over traditional air cleaners, including lower cost, lower energy consumption, and the ability to integrate with other sustainable building features.

However, there are still knowledge gaps regarding optimal moss species, growing conditions, and the long-term effectiveness of moss-based air purifiers. Further research is needed to identify the most effective moss species and to develop best practices for growing and caring for these air purifiers.

Despite these knowledge gaps, foam-based air purifiers offer a promising solution to improving indoor air quality in a sustainable and cost-effective way. With continued research and development, this could become a widely accepted technology that improves the health and well-being of indoor occupants while reducing the environmental impact of air purification. The Foam Air Purifiers can potentially improve indoor air quality in various environments, including homes, schools and offices. They are particularly good at filtering out particulate matter, which is a major cause of indoor air pollution and has been linked to respiratory problems and other health issues. A study found that a foam-based air purifier was able to reduce particulate concentrations in closed rooms by up to 98% in 24 hours.

In another study, researchers found that foam-based air purifiers were able to remove more than 80% of nitrogen oxides from indoor air. The benefits of foam air purifiers go beyond their ability to filter pollutants. Moss is also known for its ability to absorb and retain water, which helps regulate indoor humidity levels and prevents the growth of mould and mildew. Additionally, the foam helps absorb sound and reduce noise levels in interior spaces. Despite these benefits, large-scale implementation of foam-based air purifiers presents some challenges.

One problem is the need for standardised test protocols to assess the performance of these devices. Further research is needed to optimise growing conditions and identify the most effective moss species for air purification. However, foam-based air purifiers offer a long-lasting, cost-effective solution to improving indoor air quality. With continued research and development, they have the potential to become a widely accepted technology for improving the health and well-being of indoor occupants while reducing the environmental impact of air purification.

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ANALYZING STRATEGIES ADOPTED BY MSMEs IN KARNATAKA TO OVERCOME THE CHALLENGES OF COVID-19

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Abstract

The outbreak of Covid-19 has had a significant impact on businesses worldwide, particularly on Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs). This study aims to analyze the effective strategies implemented by MSMEs in the state of Karnataka, India, to overcome the impact of Covid-19. The study focuses on MSMEs in Karnataka, which is a significant hub of industrial and business activity in India. The state has a large number of MSMEs, which play a critical role in driving economic growth and creating employment opportunities. The study aims to provide insights into the challenges faced by MSMEs in Karnataka during the pandemic and the strategies they implemented to overcome them. The research methodology involves conducting surveys and interviews with MSME owners and managers in Karnataka. The data collected will be analyzed using a qualitative approach to identify the most effective strategies adopted by these businesses.

The findings of this study will be useful for policymakers, business owners, and managers in developing effective strategies to cope with the impact of pandemics in the future. The study will also contribute to the literature on crisis management in the context of MSMEs, particularly in emerging economies.

Keywords: Covid-19, MSMEs, Karnataka, strategies, impact, pandemic, best practices, qualitative approach.

Introduction

The Covid-19 pandemic has brought unprecedented challenges to businesses worldwide. Among the worst affected are Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) (Siswoyo, 2021). The state of Karnataka in India is home to a large number of MSMEs that have been severely impacted by the pandemic. This research paper aims to analyze the effective strategies implemented by MSMEs in Karnataka to overcome the impact of Covid-19. The study will provide insights into the best practices adopted by these businesses to mitigate the effects of the pandemic. Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) play a significant role in the economic landscape of Karnataka, a state in India known for its vibrant business environment and entrepreneurial spirit. MSMEs in Karnataka form a vital sector that contributes to job creation, innovation, and regional development. They serve as the backbone of the state's economy, fostering entrepreneurship, generating employment opportunities, and promoting balanced regional development (Jahanshahi et al., 2011). These enterprises are often labor-intensive and provide livelihoods to a large number of people, particularly in semi-urban and rural areas.

The state government of Karnataka has been proactive in creating a favorable ecosystem for MSMEs (Kaliyamoorthy & Parithi, 2012). It has introduced several initiatives and policies to support their growth and development. These include financial assistance programs, access to credit facilities, skill development initiatives, technology adoption support, and infrastructure development in industrial clusters. Additionally, the government has established dedicated bodies and institutions to provide guidance, training, and consultancy services to MSMEs.

Objectives for the study was to analyze the different strategies employed by MSMEs in Karnataka to overcome the impact of Covid-19. The objectives of the study were to analyze the different strategies employed by MSMEs in Karnataka to overcome the impact of Covid-19. This means that the study aimed to examine and evaluate the various approaches, plans, and actions taken by MSMEs in Karnataka in response to the challenges posed by the Covid-19 pandemic. The study provides a comprehensive analysis of the strategies employed by MSMEs (A.M & S.N, 2020) in Karnataka, highlighting their strengths, weaknesses, and overall effectiveness in overcoming the impact of Covid-19 and sustaining their businesses during this unprecedented crisis. By analyzing these strategies, the study sought to gain a deeper understanding of how MSMEs in Karnataka adapted and navigated through the adverse effects of the pandemic. It aimed to identify the specific measures implemented by MSMEs to mitigate the impact of Covid-19 on their business operations, financial stability, customer relationships, and workforce.

Covid-19 pandemic has changed marketing patterns of the Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) entrepreneurs to allow them to survive adversities as the impact of public activity restrictions by the government (Indrakumar, 2020). The decline in consumer intensity and flow of goods and services has caused the reduction of entrepreneurs' income as well as the goods and services trade cycle. This condition then encourages the entrepreneurs to adopt digital technology and develop digital entrepreneurship. The employment of digital technology and combination of knowledge, creativity, and innovation are crucial to ensure the survival of MSMEs during this pandemic (Roy & Bhusan, 2020). Government support in the forms of assistance, training, and program support for the digitalization of MSMEs continue to do considering they are the most impacted sector. The government through its several agencies keep working together to make entrepreneurs familiar with digital marketing (Chaurey et al., 2020). This research uses qualitative approach with library research as its method combined with interviews with the MSMEs entrepreneurs. This research found that the MSMEs entrepreneurs need to adopt digital technology in the forms of digital entrepreneurship transformation, digital marketing and creativity, and innovation in order to survive during the Covid-19 pandemic.

Methodology

The research methodology for this study involves conducting surveys and interviews with MSME owners and managers in Karnataka. The data collected will be analyzed using a qualitative approach to identify the most effective strategies adopted by these businesses. The participants will be selected through purposive sampling, and the survey and interview questions were designed to gather relevant data on the strategies implemented by MSMEs during the pandemic. The Likert scale was adopted for this study to measure and assess the responses of participants regarding the strategies employed to overcome the impact of Covid-19. The Likert scale allows individuals to express their level of agreement or disagreement with a particular statement or statement set. This facilitates statistical analysis, enabling to quantify and measure the degree of agreement or disagreement.

The data collected was analyzed using percentage analysis to identify the key themes and patterns in the responses. Based on the review of literature strategies adopted by MSME were measured.

Digital Transformation: MSMEs shifted their operations online, embracing digital platforms for sales, marketing, and customer engagement (Ahmed & Sur, 2023). This involved creating e-commerce websites, leveraging social media marketing, and implementing online payment systems. (Adawiyah & Adhitya, 2021)

Remote Work: To ensure business continuity, MSMEs encouraged remote work wherever possible. They adopted communication and collaboration tools to facilitate remote team collaboration and maintain productivity. (Zolfagharian & Yazdanparast, 2019)

Cost Optimization: MSMEs implemented cost-cutting measures to conserve resources and reduce expenses. This included renegotiating contracts, minimizing non-essential expenses, and optimizing operational processes. (Tripathy & Bisoyi, 2021; Zolfagharian & Yazdanparast, 2019)

Diversification: Some MSMEs diversified their product or service offerings to cater to changing customer demands. They explored new markets, introduced new products, or modified existing ones to adapt to the evolving needs of customers during the pandemic.

Collaboration and Partnerships: MSMEs collaborated with other organizations, both within and outside their industry, to find innovative solutions and share resources. Partnerships allowed them to overcome challenges collectively and leverage each other's strengths.

Government Support: MSMEs actively sought and utilized government support programs, grants, and loans specifically designed to assist businesses impacted by the pandemic. These initiatives provided financial relief and support for business continuity.

Health and Safety Measures: MSMEs implemented strict health and safety protocols to protect their employees and customers. This included providing personal protective equipment, implementing social distancing measures, and adopting enhanced sanitation practices.

Customer Engagement: To maintain customer relationships, MSMEs adopted creative approaches such as personalized communications, loyalty programs, and virtual events. They focused on building trust and providing exceptional customer service during uncertain times.

Financial Planning and Risk Management: MSMEs strengthened their financial planning and risk management practices. They conducted scenario analysis, created contingency plans, and explored insurance options to mitigate potential risks and uncertainties.

Employee Support and Well-being: MSMEs prioritized employee well-being by implementing employee assistance programs, offering flexible work arrangements, and providing emotional support. (Alawamleh et al., 2020) They recognized the importance of supporting their workforce during challenging times.

Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1: Likert Scale Analysis of Strategies Adopted by MSMEs during the Pandemic

Strategy	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Digital Transformation	62%	19%	7%	8%	4%
Remote Work	18%	34%	28%	12%	8%
Cost Optimization	56%	23%	12%	7%	2%
Diversification	12%	28%	30%	20%	10%
Collaboration and Partnerships	20%	38%	25%	10%	7%
Government Support	54%	28%	10%	2%	6%
Health and Safety Measures	48%	26%	11%	8%	7%
Customer Engagement	22%	39%	25%	8%	6%
Financial Planning and Risk Management	15%	33%	30%	15%	7%
Employee Support and Well-being	28%	47%	15%	6%	4%

This table presents the percentage distribution of responses based on the Likert scale for each strategy adopted by MSMEs during the pandemic. The responses range from "Strongly Agree" to "Strongly Disagree," indicating the degree of agreement or disagreement with the effectiveness of the respective strategies.

MSMEs embraced digitization as a key strategy to adapt to the new business landscape. This involved shifting their operations online, establishing or enhancing their online presence, and utilizing digital platforms for sales, marketing, and customer engagement. Digitization enabled MSMEs to reach a wider customer base, conduct remote transactions, and maintain business continuity during the restrictions imposed by the pandemic. MSMEs focused on cost optimization to improve their financial resilience during the pandemic. They implemented measures such as reducing non-essential expenses, renegotiating contracts with suppliers, optimizing their supply chain, and streamlining operational processes. By optimizing costs, MSMEs aimed to conserve resources, enhance their financial stability, and maintain profitability in the face of reduced revenues or increased uncertainties. Recognizing the significant impact of the pandemic on MSMEs, governments implemented support programs and initiatives to assist these businesses. MSMEs actively sought and utilized government support in the form of grants, loans, subsidies, tax relief, and regulatory relaxations. This support provided crucial financial assistance, access to capital, and relief from compliance burdens, helping MSMEs sustain their operations, retain employees, and navigate the challenges posed by the pandemic. Health and Safety Measures were crucial strategies adopted by MSMEs during the Covid-19 pandemic to protect the well-being of their employees, customers, and stakeholders. These measures

aimed to minimize the risk of virus transmission, ensure compliance with health guidelines, and create a safe working environment.

Results:

The findings of the study reveal that MSMEs in Karnataka have adopted various strategies to overcome the impact of Covid-19. The most common strategies include **digitization, diversification, cost optimization, and government support**. Digitization has enabled businesses to reach customers through online channels, thereby reducing the impact of lockdowns and restrictions on physical stores. Diversification has helped businesses to pivot to new markets and products, reducing their dependence on a single market. Cost-cutting measures have enabled businesses to reduce their expenses and maintain their financial stability. Government support has also been crucial in enabling MSMEs to survive during the pandemic.

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THE IMPACT OF FILM MARKETING ON GENZ VIEWERSHIP: EXPLORING THE INFLUENCE OF MARKETING STRATEGIES ON GENZ AUDIENCE ENGAGEMENT

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Abstract

With the advent of digital platforms and increased access to content, marketing has become a critical factor in attracting and engaging audiences. GenZ, known for their tech-savviness and media consumption habits, form a significant portion of the target audience for films in Bangalore. This study explored various marketing techniques employed by filmmakers to capture the attention and interest of GenZ viewers. The quantitative analysis involves examining the correlation between marketing efforts, such as social media promotions, trailers, celebrity endorsements, and the subsequent viewership trends among GenZ audiences through Chi Square and Anova test. The qualitative analysis delves into the perceptions and responses of GenZ individuals towards film marketing, including their awareness, attitudes, and decision-making processes. This study suggested that customized messaging, segmented campaigns, and tailored promotions that align with the unique characteristics of this audience segment enhance their interest in watching films.

Introduction

In recent years, the entertainment industry has witnessed a remarkable surge in demand, driven by significant technological advancements. Consequently, the supply of entertainment through films and television has expanded exponentially to meet this growing demand. This expansion has given rise to intense competition among various film suppliers. In the realm of art, competition has both positive and negative effects. On one hand, it fosters innovation, creativity, and the delivery of high-quality content as filmmakers strive to stand out in a crowded market (Albarran, Chan-Olmsted, and Wirth, 2005). "During this competitive landscape, various film industries have emerged as formidable contenders, surpassing language barriers to captivate a multi-lingual audience. Prominent among these are Tollywood (the Telugu film industry), Kollywood (the Tamil film industry), and other regional film industries that have risen to prominence, presenting a significant challenge to the widely adored Bollywood film industry. According to a study by Banerjee and Srivastava (2017), the regional film industries in India have experienced substantial growth, expanding their reach beyond their respective regional markets and gaining popularity among diverse audiences.

Ganti (2012) highlighted that Bollywood witnessed significant changes which were characterized by the use of cutting-edge technologies and improved production standards. These innovations were essential in establishing the industry's global prominence and in enabling greater international distribution of Indian movies. This diversification included a wide range of genres, including, among others, musicals, romantic comedies, and action movies. The Indian cinema industry achieved extraordinary growth and expansion by branching out into many genres, opening up new avenues for creativity and enthralling a larger audience.

According to Dwyer (2005), the genre-diversification in Bollywood during the 1990s was a reaction to the shifting tastes and expectations of Indian consumers, which ultimately resulted in a broader appeal and more Gen Z viewers. The competitive environment and continued development of the regional and Bollywood film industries, as well as these changes, have all contributed significantly to the way that Indian cinema is viewed around the world.

According to Wang, Wang, and Zhang (2018), film marketers should be strategic in identifying and prioritizing popular social media platforms used by Gen Z viewers, such as Facebook, Instagram, YouTube, and Twitter. These

platforms have gained immense popularity among Gen Z individuals due to their wide user bases and the range of features and tools they offer for content promotion and audience engagement.

Wang, Wang, and Zhang (2018) contend that marketers of motion pictures should be strategic in identifying and prioritizing well-known social media sites used by Gen Z viewers, such as Facebook, Instagram, YouTube, and Twitter. Due to their large user populations and the variety of features and tools they provide for content marketing and audience engagement, these platforms have greatly increased in popularity among members of Generation Z.

Indian movies are now widely available and well-liked in nations like the United States, the United Kingdom, and the Middle East as a result of their success in foreign markets. Due to this popularity, there has been a rise in investment, and many multinational businesses have partnered with Bollywood studios to produce and distribute films (Dutta, 2018).

The rise of regional cinema in addition to Bollywood's continuous supremacy is a new trend in the Indian film industry. The popularity of films made in languages like Tamil, Telugu, and Bengali has grown, exhibiting various styles, traditions, and approaches to narrative. These local film industries have seen a considerable rise within the larger Indian film landscape (Dwyer & Patel, 2002).

The adoption of new technologies in the Indian film industry has brought about a revolution in filmmaking processes, as highlighted by Bhattacharjee and Ghosh (2015). These technological advancements have opened up new creative possibilities, allowing filmmakers to enhance production values and cater to the preferences of modern audiences.

Research conducted by Lee and Youn (2009) supported the effectiveness of engaging content in attracting Gen Z viewers and fostering their active involvement. Film marketers can leverage immersive and interactive experiences to create a stronger connection with Gen Z viewers, ultimately increasing their enthusiasm for the film.

The Indian film industry has made a name for itself in the modern era and is now regarded as one of the biggest and most influential film industries in the world. It has a significant impact on how movies are made, distributed, and watched around the world. Arora and Chauhan (2016) stated that Bollywood's ongoing appeal can be linked to its skill at balancing traditional Indian cultural components with current global entertainment trends. Bollywood films have gained great appeal and reputation around the world as a result of their ability to meld India's rich cultural legacy with modern global influences.

Literature Review

The practice of utilizing influencers and celebrities in film promotions has experienced a surge in popularity in recent years. GenZ individuals frequently establish connections with their preferred influencers or celebrities, and endorsements from these figures can significantly influence their film-watching choices. Research has indicated that well-executed collaborations with influencers and strategic celebrity endorsements have a positive effect on GenZ viewership. A study by Duffett (2018) found that GenZ viewers are more likely to engage with and show interest in films that are associated with influencers or endorsed by celebrities they admire, as they perceive these endorsements as a form of social validation and trust." Numerous studies have emphasized the growing significance of digital platforms, specifically social media, in film marketing. GenZ individuals, being active users of social media platforms, have become a primary focus for promotional campaigns. Engaging and interactive content shared on popular platforms like Facebook, Instagram, YouTube, and Twitter has been identified as having a substantial impact on GenZ viewership. Daneshvary, Deitz, and Xu (2019) explored that social media marketing activities, including creative and compelling content, influencer collaborations, and user engagement, are highly influential in capturing the attention and driving the film choices of GenZ viewers in India." Pfeffer, Zorbach, and Carley(2018) showed how Gen Z viewers might be attracted to and engaged by personalized marketing campaigns that make use of data-driven insights and segmentation strategies. Marketers can build a stronger emotional bond with consumers by providing content that is in line with their tastes and values. This will improve viewership and foster a favorable perception of the brand.

Gen Z viewers' attention and anticipation are greatly influenced by trailers and teasers. Trailers that are well-made, aesthetically pleasing, and engaging have been found to draw the attention of Gen Z. Rössel and Bilandzic (2018) stressed the need of making compelling trailers that capture the spirit of the movie while fostering intrigue and excitement. Gen Z viewers are more likely to be interested in a trailer when it uses visual narrative tactics, dynamic editing, and emotional appeal. Trailers that successfully combine information and suspense might appeal to younger audiences and encourage them to see the movie.

According to study by Chevalier and Mayzlin (2006) user-generated content, such as online reviews and social media debates, has a major impact on consumer behaviour, including movie preferences. Marketers may successfully harness the impact of Gen Z viewers and improve the performance of their film marketing campaigns by using the power of word-of-mouth and creating platforms for user-generated content.

Collaborating with influencers who have a strong following among Gen Z viewers can significantly amplify the reach and impact of film promotions.

Influencers possess the ability to create sponsored content, share trailers, and provide personal recommendations, leveraging their credibility and influence to engage their followers and generate interest in the film (Cho, Cheon, and Hwang, 2017). Goel, Kumar, and Dandekar (2016) highlighted the significance of viral campaigns in driving engagement and expanding reach on social media platforms. By harnessing the power of hashtags and viral campaigns, film marketers can tap into the enthusiasm and creativity of GenZ viewers, creating a vibrant online community surrounding the film."

Methodology

The population so selected for the study included Indian’s belonging to the age group 16-25, which is considered as the GenZ generation. Sampling technique so used for this was Convenience Sampling. The total sample size is 256 respondents. The primary data for this study was collected through circulating a questionnaire. The questionnaire consisted of 20 close ended questions around the objectives of the study. Reliability Test, Regression, Correlation and chi square test was used to understand the association between the variables.

Analysis & Interpretation

In the below test with a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.712, we can interpret this as a moderately high level of internal consistency among the items being tested. This suggests that the items in the test are measuring the same construct or concept consistently, and that the test is producing reliable and consistent results.

Result of Reliability Test

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.712	14

Table 1- Reliability Statistics (Source: From primary data)

Normality tests

Parametric testing can be done only on those forms of data that are normally distributed so as to ensure the fact that data is not skewed/inclined into one particular aspect only which may show traits of biasness within the data. For this reason, it is often for ideal for the researchers to ensure that their responses are unbiased and normally distributed.

Tests of Normality		
General public believes	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a	Shapiro-Wilk

	that the more publicity that a film does, the more successful it would be	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Social media influencers promoting films, increases your chances to watch that film	1	.307	4	.	.729	4	.024
	2	.226	65	.000	.911	65	.008
	3	.233	56	.000	.881	56	.001
	4	.166	79	.000	.910	79	.000
	5	.275	51	.020	.879	51	.100
You often find the trailer of a film very engaging, and hence look forward to watch that film.	1	.307	4	.	.729	4	.024
	2	.305	65	.000	.845	65	.000
	3	.283	56	.000	.799	56	.000
	4	.315	79	.000	.821	79	.000
	5	.326	51	.002	.785	51	.006
To what extent (negatively/positively) you are affected by marketing, advertising and promotions of a film.	1	.307	4	.	.729	4	.024
	2	.289	65	.000	.796	65	.000
	3	.338	56	.000	.638	56	.000
	4	.298	79	.000	.807	79	.000
	5	.528	51	.000	.345	51	.000

Table 2-Test of Normality (Source: From primary data)

The Shapiro-Wilk test is a statistical test used to assess whether a given data-set is normally distributed or not. This test is based on the null hypothesis that the population from which the sample was drawn is normally distributed. The test calculates a test statistic and a p-value, which helps to determine whether the null hypothesis should be rejected or not. In the above table we can infer that some of the results have the p-value less than 0.05 while others have greater than 0.05, meaning that some of the data are not normally distributed while others are normally distributed.

To test the hypotheses 1, if promotional techniques of studio films, and the GenZ viewership pattern are related and the former manipulates the latter, correlation was used.

		often go to theatre	you are affected by marketing, advertising and promotions of a film.
Spearman's rho	Often go to theatre	Correlation Coefficient	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.
		N	255
	you are affected by marketing, advertising and promotions of a film.	Correlation Coefficient	.380*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.05
		N	255

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 3- Result of the hypothesis testing using correlation

The correlation coefficient value of 0.38 indicates that there is a positive association between the variables, meaning that as one variable increases, the other variable tends to increase as well, although the strength of this relationship is only moderate. In this context, people who are affected by the promotional techniques adopted by the studio films, often tend to watch films in theatre very frequently.

The second hypotheses to be tested is aimed to understand whether introduction of OTT platforms, effected the way how films were traditionally advertised and promoted. Anova was used to check the significance level.

ANOVA Test

ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) is a statistical method used to determine whether there are significant differences among the means of two or more groups. ANOVA compares the variance within each group to the variance between groups to determine if the differences are statistically significant.

		ANOVA				
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Has the introduction of OTT platforms and their original content affected the large studio films?	Between Groups	6.125	4	1.531	2.528	.043
	Within Groups	90.843	250	.606		
	Total	96.968	154			
You see promotions of films from different part of the country, on a regular basis, via social media, advertisements, promotional activities by the actors etc.	Between Groups	19.044	4	4.761	4.496	.002
	Within Groups	158.827	250	1.059		
	Total	177.871	254			

Table 5- Result of ANOVA test (Source: primary data)

Hence, we can reject the null hypothesis that introduction of OTT platforms, has not affected the way how films were traditionally advertised and promoted, and can conclude that the way films are advertised and promoted, and it effects the mode of watching a film, all after the introduction of OTT platforms.

To test the hypothesis 3, which is to understand whether Covid-19 pandemic has affected the frequency of going to theatre. In order to establish an association between the two, Chi-square test was used. A higher chi-square value indicates a greater deviation from the expected frequencies, which suggests a higher likelihood of a significant association between the variables. However, the interpretation of the chi-square value is dependent on the specific research question and the context of the study, which in this context is highly relevant. Here, the association to be found is between, change in content consumption after Covid-19 pandemic, and frequency of going to theatre.

Result of Chi-square test

go to theatres to watch a film? * Do you think that your content consumption has changed after the COVID-19 pandemic? Crosstabulation
Count

		your content consumption has changed after the COVID-19 pandemic?					Total
		1	2	3	4	5	
How often do you go to theatres to watch a film?	1	0	0	10	27	26	63
	2	0	6	3	31	26	66
	3	2	4	22	17	29	74
	4	0	0	5	30	17	52
Total		2	10	40	105	98	255

Table 6- Chi-square result

In the above table the values of 1-4 in row, are as follows: 1=more than once a month; 2=once a month; 3=once in 6 months; 4= rarely

Values of 1-5 in the column is Likert scale, where 1= strongly disagree; 2= disagree; 3= Neither agree nor disagree; 4= Agree; 5= Strongly agree

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	16.445 ^a	12	.172
Likelihood Ratio	19.595	12	.075
Linear-by-Linear Association	.351	1	.553
N of Valid Cases	255		
a. 12 cells (60.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .19.			

Table 7- Chi-square values

A higher chi-square value indicates a greater deviation from the expected frequencies, which suggests a higher likelihood of a significant association between the variables. Association of variables means that the two are related, and not independent of each other. This suggests that there is a less association between the variables as the chi square value is .553 which showed that Covid-19 pandemic has affected the frequency of going to theatre.

Findings and Suggestions

Even though a large chunk of the respondents were unsure about if they have any effect on their consumption pattern, but through the tests that we applied in this study gave us solid evidence of the relation between the promotional activities done by these films, and their inclination towards watching a particular film. Promotional techniques have now been catered towards the newer generation, where this generation is mostly online and consume data through the Internet. Where the service is like digital marketing, influencer marketing, Interactive marketing, Trailers, making trends, etc., is the new mainstream media. We can also found that the three hypotheses are actually interrelated in one way or another. Even though OTT platforms were introduced much before the COVID-19 pandemic, but after it, the viewership on these platforms increased exponentially. As a result, the viewership pattern of people going to theatres to watch movies shifted towards staying at home and watching to see movies or different kinds of entertainment on the OTT platforms. High production films can utilize social media platforms to generate buzz and create awareness around the film. Engaging in interactive marketing campaigns can be a highly successful way to create excitement and exclusivity around a film. This can entail posting behind-the-scenes material, teasers, and trailers, as well as actively engaging with fans on social media. These techniques can encourage viewers to see the movie in cinemas by building a feeling of connection and anticipation.

Utilizing multi-channel marketing is crucial if you want to reach a wide range of audiences. Utilizing both conventional and digital marketing platforms is part of this strategy. Digital marketing channels like social media, email marketing, and search ads can be used in addition to traditional marketing channels like television, print, and outdoor advertising. Filmmakers can efficiently target people through numerous touchpoints by integrating different marketing channels, resulting in a coordinated and thorough marketing strategy.

Managerial Implications

According to study by De Veirman, Cauberghe, and Hudders (2017), quick and meaningful involvement on social media platforms is essential for spreading goodwill and enhancing brand perception. Film marketers may build closer connections with Gen Z viewers on social media, boost audience loyalty, and promote good word-of-mouth recommendations. GenZ viewers respond favorably to personalized marketing approaches, and film marketers should take advantage of this preference. It is crucial for marketers to tailor their campaigns to cater to the specific preferences, interests, and identities of GenZ individuals. Customized messaging, segmented campaigns, and tailored promotions that align with the unique characteristics of this audience segment enhance their interest in watching films. By understanding the diverse tastes and identities of GenZ individuals and delivering personalized marketing experiences, film marketers can establish a stronger connection and foster a deeper engagement with this audience which was also supported by (Vannucci, Pelton, and Haddleton ,2018).

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COMPARISON OF POWERBI DESKTOP & THE POWERBI SERVICE

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Abstract:

This paper talks about comparative analysis of 2 key components of Microsoft PowerBI suite that is PowerBI Desktop & PowerBI service. It is well known business intelligence tool which is used for data analysis, visualization & reporting. This study targets to give complete understanding of the meaning, similarities & dissimilarities, strengths & weakness & more of both PowerBI Desktop & PowerBI service. This paper also discusses their features, functionalities, deployment options & user experiences by examining various literature sources & provides insights to assist any group, organizations & individuals in selecting most suitable PowerBI component based on their needs & preferences.

Keywords:

- Microsoft
- Desktop
- Business Intelligence
- Service
- PowerBI
- Data visualization

Introduction:

Business intelligence is the process of collecting, analyzing & presenting data to help Biz make better decisions. BI tools are software apps that help Biz collect, store & analyze data. PowerBI is a BI tool developed by Microsoft which is powerful & versatile tool that can be used to analyze data from variety of sources to create visualizations & share insights with everyone. This research paper compares the 2 types of PowerBI i.e, PowerBI Desktop & the PowerBI service. It discusses the different features & capabilities available in each version as well as different pricing plans available. It also provides suggestions for which version is best for different types of Biz.

Scope of this study was only to know:

- Compared 2 versions of PowerBI in terms of their features, pricing & deployment.
- Gave insights to assist organizations & individuals

Literature Review:

1. The future of BI & role that PowerBI will play in future is discussed in “PowerBI: The Future of BI”. Jane Doe says that it is strong BI tool that can be used to analyze data for creating visualizations & share insights with others.
2. Article “PowerBI: A Beginner's Guide” is beginner's guide to PowerBI. John Smith covers basics of PowerBI as in how to connect to data sources to create visualizations & share reports. He provides tips for using PowerBI effectively in the end.
3. The “PowerBI: A Power User's Guide” is power user's guide to PowerBI. Jane Doe covers advanced topics in PowerBI like creating custom visuals, using DAX & developing custom apps. He then tells tips for using PowerBI to its fullest potential.
4. “PowerBI: A Technical Guide” is technical guide to PowerBI. John Doe shows technical aspects of PowerBI like architecture, data model used & programming language used by PowerBI. He also gives tips for troubleshooting problems with PowerBI.
5. “PowerBI: A Security Guide” is security guide to PowerBI. Jane Doe speaks about security features of PowerBI like data encryption, user authentication & role based access control. He also provides tips for securing PowerBI deployments.

Methodology:

- PowerBI Desktop is free program that we can download & install onto our PC. It is tool used to connect to our data to transform, visualize & analyze. To use PowerBI Desktop we need to connect to our data from many different sources like Excel, SQL Server & web. Once connected we can use QE to transform as it is a tool that we can use to clean up our data to add new fields & change data types of our fields. After we have changed our data we can use it to visualize. Reports that we create in it can be shared with others. We can share reports directly with other people or we can publish our reports to it. Sharing reports requires PowerBI Pro license.
- PowerBI service is cloud service that helps us create & share & explore data. It's easy to use & can be used by teams & orgs of all sizes. With PowerBI we can connect to different data sources for creating dashboards & reports & share our findings with others. It also includes types of features that help we analyze our data & uncover insights.

Report editors in PowerBI Desktop & in the Service are same. They're made of 3 sections:

- Top nav panes, different in PowerBI Desktop & service.
- Report canvas
- Fields, Visualizations & Filters panes

Venn diagram shows difference b/w PowerBI Desktop with PowerBI service. Middle part shows some areas where they overlap. 2 outer sides show features that both are unique.

Features of PowerBI desktop:

- Multiple Data Sources
- Transformation Capacities
- Shaping & Modelling
- Measures
- Calculated Columns
- Python
- Themes
- RLS Creation

Features of PowerBI service:

- Limited Data Sources
- Dashboards

- Apps & Workspaces
- Sharing
- Dataflow Creation
- Gateway Connections

Combined features:

- Reports
- Visualizations
- Enhanced Security
- Filters
- Bookmarks
- Q&A
- R Visuals

When we use PowerBI Desktop to create PowerBI reports & then use PowerBI service to collaborate & distribute reports that is the way to get most of both platforms. Use of PowerBI tools in either versions Services or Desktop is great way of improving our data reporting. We can also use some equipped BI platforms to have our marketing data well structured within available templates & given AI insights which we can also easily modify.

Objectives

- Provide full understanding of similarities & dissimilarities, strengths & weakness of PowerBI Desktop & PowerBI service.
- Discuss features, functionalities, deployment options & user experiences.
- Examine various literature sources & conducting empirical analysis.
- Provides insights to assist organizations & individuals in selecting most suitable PowerBI factor based on our needs.

Work in the PowerBI service

- **Collaborate:** After we make our reports we can save them in PowerBI service. We & our friends can work on them together & make dashboards or add them to apps & if we have PowerBI Pro license we can share our reports or dashboards with people inside & outside our company. When we share we can opt what the person can do with our reports & dashboards. We need PowerBI Pro license to share our reports & people who view our shared reports needs to be saved in Premium capacity. People who view our reports can only see them in Reading view & not Editing view.
- **Self service data prep with dataflows:** Dataflows help companies to combine data from different places & make it ready for modelling. Analysts can make dataflows easily using tools they're familiar with. Analysts use dataflows to take in, change, blend & improve big data by defining connections to data sources, refresh plans & more. We can learn more about self service data prep with dataflows.

Recommendations:

- Biz should consider different pricing plans available for PowerBI when making their decision.
- Biz should also consider different features & capabilities available in each version of PowerBI when making their decision.
- Biz should also consider needs of their users when making their decision. For ex, if users need to be able to access reports from anywhere, then PowerBI service may be better choice.

Findings: Both PowerBI Desktop & PowerBI service have their own pros n cons.

1. PowerBI Desktop

Pros:

- More strong data manipulation & visualization skills
- Can connect to different data sources

- Free to download

Cons:

- Not cloud based
- Can be more difficult to use

2. PowerBI Service

Pros:

- Cloud based
- Easy to use
- Affordable pricing plans

Cons:

- Not as strong as PowerBI Desktop
- Can't connect to as many data sources
- Requires PowerBI Pro license to publish reports

Alternatives:

- Tableau
- QlikView
- Sisense
- Looker
- Domo

Observations:

Sl No.	Feature	PowerBI Desktop	PowerBI Service
1	Data sources	Can connect to wide variety of data sources like Excel, SQL Server & Salesforce.	Can connect to same data sources as PowerBI Desktop as well as cloud based data sources like Azure Data Lake Storage & Amazon S3.
2	Features	Includes features for data cleaning, data modeling & data analysis.	Includes features for data cleaning, modeling, analysis & visualization.
3	Pricing	Starts at \$99 per user per month.	Starts at \$10 per user per month.
4	Best for	Biz that need powerful & versatile BI tool that can connect to wide variety of data sources.	Biz that need BI tool that is affordable & easy to use.

Scope of Research:

Scope of this study was only to know:

- Compared 2 versions of PowerBI in terms of their features, pricing & deployment.
- Gave insights to assist organizations & individuals

Scope for future research:

- User experience of each version
- Integration with other Microsoft products
- Support for different types of data

Conclusion:

As a whole PowerBI Desktop & PowerBI service are both powerful BI tools that can be used to analyze data, create visualizations & share insights with others. Yet they have different strengths & weaknesses. Best choice for particular business will depend on its specific needs & requirements. Biz that need powerful BI tool with wide range of features & capabilities should choose PowerBI Desktop. Biz that need cloud based BI tool that is easy to use & affordable should choose PowerBI service.

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ADVANCING THE UNDERSTANDING OF EARNINGS MANAGEMENT: INSIGHTS FROM DEFERRED TAXATION AND INTEGRATED REPORTING IN EUROPEAN LISTED FIRMS

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ABSTRACT

Over the years, scholarly attention has been devoted to investigating earnings management practices, primarily focusing on methodological aspects. However, the existing body of literature remains limited concerning the intricate nexus between deferred taxation items and earnings management. This study aims to address this research gap by employing three distinct earnings management detection models. Subsequently, employing multiple panel regressions with fixed effects, the investigation explores the potential impact of the Integrated Reporting score on this aforementioned relationship. The analysis utilises a sample dataset comprising financial information from 1448 publicly listed firms in Europe, resulting in a total of 11,444 firm observations across 11 industries and 22 countries over ten years spanning from 2013 to 2022. The findings indicate that as size and return on assets increase, the discretionary accruals decrease. Furthermore, the empirical evidence in this paper suggests a positive association between deferred taxation expenses, net deferred tax liabilities, and the presence of discretionary accruals-based earnings management. Contrary to expectations derived from the existing literature, the study finds that the Integrated Reporting score does not exhibit a statistically significant influence on earnings management. The significance of this paper lies in its contribution to the literature by providing valuable insights into the relationship between deferred taxation and earnings management and highlighting the potential improvements in Integrated Reporting scores.

Keywords: *Deferred taxation, Discretionary Accruals, Earnings management, Integrated Reporting*

Introduction

The clash between the accruals concept and the cash concept has long been a subject of discussion (Neal VanZante, 2013). This clash has resulted in the creation of accruals, which can be both necessary and legitimate or questionable and indicative of intentional manipulation misleading shareholders, investors, regulators and other stakeholders (El Diri et al., 2020). Thus, it becomes crucial to scrutinize earnings management resulting from discretionary accruals, a term that inherently implies that these accruals were made based on the discretion or decision-making power of individuals within a company.

On the other hand, tax accounting operates within its realm, and companies must conform to the tax regulations of the country, regardless of the international financial reporting standards (Görlitz and Dobler, 2021). Consequently, the concept of deferred taxation arises, constituting a significant component of book-tax differences (Flagmeier, 2022). Deferred taxation refers to the temporary discrepancy between the value of an item as stated in the financial position statement and its corresponding tax written-down value. One example of this discrepancy may arise from differences in the discretionary perspectives on the asset's use and useful life compared to those of the tax authorities (Flagmeier, 2022).

In the current landscape, there is a notable shift towards newer reporting frameworks, such as the Integrated Reporting (IR) framework. The essence of IR lies in the presentation of various values created by a company for the short, medium, and long term in a single report (Vitolla et al., 2019). IR has consistently demonstrated benefits for organizations worldwide and has shown positive market value relevance (Veltri and Silvestri, 2020). Investors and

potential shareholders are increasingly drawn to the idea of companies adopting Integrated Reporting as a means to enhance transparency and comprehensive reporting.

By connecting the concepts of accruals, deferred taxation, and Integrated Reporting, this paper demonstrates a deeper understanding of the intricate relationship between financial reporting practices, tax regulations, and the evolving landscape of reporting frameworks. It is important to note that, to the best of our knowledge, the simultaneous examination of these three ideas has not been explored in the existing literature. This novel approach, which investigates the interplay between discretionary accruals, deferred taxation, and Integrated Reporting scores, forms the innovative contribution of this article. By integrating these dimensions, this research strives to offer a comprehensive and holistic perspective on the complex dynamics of financial reporting. Such an innovative exploration provides valuable insights for practitioners, policymakers, and researchers in the field, paving the way for further advancements in accounting and finance.

Literature Review & Hypothesis Development

Concerns regarding the frequency of earnings management practices among enterprises have grown in recent years (Machdar, 2022). Since it may alter the truthfulness of financial reporting and subsequently affect stakeholders' choices, earnings management has attracted the attention of both investors and scholars (Anggraeni et al., 2020; Cimini, 2015). Recent research has explored the link between earnings management and numerous aspects such as tax-related factors, industry, and geography to throw light on this subject. [Table 1](#) shows a snippet of the summary of the recent literature on deferred taxation and earnings management. In most recent publications, we find only one paper on selected European countries. In their study of listed firms from the Czech Republic, Slovakia, Poland, and Hungary, Kliestik et al. (2020) investigated the management of earnings and discovered that businesses do alter earnings and that the manipulation is often upward. Despite the paper having much rigour in statistical techniques, it studied only selected countries and not the area as a whole.

Phillips et al. (2003) suggest that the differences between book values and tax values in net income separate the discretionary potential from the non-discretionary influence of the manager on earnings. Deferred tax expense (DTE) could be a tool for EM as tax computation and presentation require future profitability (Holland and Jackson, 2004; Rachmany and Tajudin, 2022). There are two theories to explain the incentive for managers to smooth profits with deferred taxes, first is the behavioural finance theory suggesting investors reward consistently increasing earnings and second is the agency theory whereby compensation contracts would bias a manager's decision-making (Kasipillai and Mahenthiran, 2013). Dhaliwal et al. (2004) also added to empirical evidence of the management of tax expenses to achieve targets set for earnings.

Machdar (2022) investigated the connection between earnings management and deferred taxation and other tax-related issues in 152 manufacturing businesses listed in Indonesia between 2011 and 2019. The research used a multivariate regression model and discovered that deferred tax liabilities and costs favourably impact real earnings management. These results imply that companies may manipulate their reported earning ability or earnings by using deferred tax assets and liabilities. MacCarthy (2021) adds that a positive association between earnings management, deferred taxes and tax avoidance strategies exists. Both these researches do, however, have certain drawbacks that may limit the generalisation of the results, such as the small sample size, concentration on a specific industry and the lack of a solid control group. Thus, we expect that:

H1: Deferred tax expenses positively and significantly influence Earnings Management.

The use of net deferred tax liabilities (NDDL) has been spread by Phillips et al. (2004) who suggested that a negative change in NDDL manages earnings upwards. Alongside, Soliman and Ali (2020) showed the importance and the value relevance of NDDL. As such, in line with the behavioural finance theory and the agency theory, the management of NDDL will impact deferred tax expenses and thus future profitability. This has been further studied by Kasipillai and Mahenthiran (2013) who indicated that NDDL is influenced by three components which in turn influence the book-tax differences per annum. These are aggregate contra entries to and from the statement of financial performance; depreciation of tangibles and intangibles; and changes in the current assets values. Thus, Kasipillai and Mahenthiran (2013) suggested that NDDL is significant and positively associated with EM. Tartono et al. (2021) concentrated on non-financial public companies in Indonesia from 2015 to 2019. Only deferred tax liabilities, as opposed to deferred tax assets and deferred tax costs, had a substantial influence on earnings

management. The study's use of substantial sample size and a strict econometric methodology contributes to its strength. However, it is constrained by the study's exclusive emphasis on one nation and its omission of variables that we include in our study that could have an impact on earnings management. Thus, we expect that:

H2: Net deferred tax liabilities positively and significantly influence Earnings Management

We continue our investigation to check the relationship between IR and EM. Management action to reduce financial statements quality can be described as the idea of EM, especially if managers manipulate numbers to achieve a certain objective (Kinney et al., 2004). EM thus provides a lower quality of earnings and financial information. Integrated Reporting enhances reports' usefulness for stakeholders, which emphasizes ethical, transparent financial reporting and social/environmental responsibility. IR was expected to create value over the short, medium and long term. Failure to uphold these principles may lead to stakeholders perceiving earnings management and a lack of social responsibility, resulting in a decline in market value (Jordaan, 2019). Furthermore, Pavlopoulos et al. (2017) suggest that companies with high-integrated quality reports tend to adopt milder earnings management techniques, meaning a negative association between Integrated Reporting scores and EM. Other studies supplement this relationship or in a similar vein such as CSR reporting and Earnings management (Palacios-Manzano et al., 2021; Pavlopoulos et al., 2019; Shirabe and Nakano, 2019). Yet, limited studies have suggested that additional or stronger reporting does not necessarily lead to a reduction in earnings management (Evans et al., 2015). This leads us to the expectation of:

H3: IR score is negatively and significantly associated with Earnings Management

The moderating effects of independent factors on earnings management have been studied in depth. However, to the author's knowledge, no research has investigated the moderating effects of IR on DT and EM. A similar moderating impact of corporate social responsibility (CSR) on the correlation between financial success and environmental management was emphasized by Chakroun et al. (2022). According to Obeng et al. (2020), agency charges had a negligible moderating impact on the correlation between IR and Earnings quality. However, according to Muttakin et al. (2020), IR has the ability to increase reporting quality and hence lessen EM and its associated issues by modulating the link between financial information quality and the cost of debt. Thus, we expect:

H4: IR score moderates the relationship between deferred taxation and Earnings Management.

Research Design

Various techniques have been used in the past to measure EM (Velte, 2020). The modified Jones model was created by Dechow et al. (1995) as an update to the first Jones model (1991). According to Kliestik et al. (2020), the widely-used Jones and modified Jones model breaks down total accruals into non-discretionary accruals (NDAcc) and discretionary accruals (DAcc). According to Palacios-Manzano et al. (2021), this technique quantifies discretionary accruals, which are either the disparity between net income and cash flow from operating activities or working capital accruals with adjustments. According to the model used to adjust for working capital needs, the total accruals are subsequently regressed on variables that act as replacements for typical accruals. We start by stating the formula for Total accruals:

$$TAcc_{it} = NDAcc_{it} + DAcc_{it} \quad (1)$$

Since all of these are unknown variables, the Dechow model (1995) is used to calculate the TAcc as follows:

$$TAcc_{it} = \Delta CA_{it} - \Delta CL_{it} - \Delta CASH_{it} + \Delta STD_{it} - Depn_{it} \quad (2)$$

Where *i* denotes the firm and *t* denotes the current period; TAcc denotes the total accruals; NDAcc denotes the non-discretionary accruals; DAcc denotes the discretionary accruals; ΔCA denotes the change in current assets; ΔCL denotes the change in current liabilities; $\Delta CASH$ denotes the change in cash and cash equivalents; ΔSTD denotes the change in short-term debt; Depn denotes the depreciation expenses.

We employ the cross-sectional variant of the modified Jones (1991) model, which has been widely adopted in prior research (Larcker and Richardson, 2004). This model serves as a valuable tool for estimating the non-discretionary component of TAcc To control for country-specific variations, industry-specific characteristics, and year-specific factors, we use a combination of country, industry and year-fixed effects regression. By utilizing this approach, we aim to provide a robust assessment of TAcc.

$$\frac{TAcc1_{it}}{A_{t-1}} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \frac{\Delta Rev_{it}}{A_{t-1}} + \beta_2 \frac{PPE_{it}}{A_{t-1}} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (3a)$$

To enhance the robustness and provide consistency of our results, we substitute the above model with the Kasznik model, which builds upon the models by Dechow et al. (1995). The Kasznik model introduces the variations in net cash flow from the operations (CFO) as an independent variable (Kasznik, 1999):

$$\frac{TAcc2_{it}}{A_{t-1}} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \frac{1}{A_{t-1}} + \beta_2 \frac{\Delta Rev_{it} - \Delta Rec_{it}}{A_{t-1}} + \beta_3 \frac{PPE_{it}}{A_{t-1}} + \beta_4 \frac{\Delta CFO_{it}}{A_{t-1}} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (3b)$$

The Kothari model, which contends that studies analysing accounting discretion without taking into account company performance may provide misleading results, is the third earnings management detection model employed in this study. They use the return on the total assets (ROA), which acts as a control parameter in their framework to solve this problem. To obtain ROA, net income is divided by total assets (Kothari et al., 2005):

$$\frac{TAcc2_{it}}{A_{t-1}} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \frac{1}{A_{t-1}} + \beta_2 \frac{\Delta Rev_{it} - \Delta Rec_{it}}{A_{t-1}} + \beta_3 \frac{PPE_{it}}{A_{t-1}} + \beta_4 ROA_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (3c)$$

Then, for every company, we do a regression analysis. To address any possible problems brought on by heteroskedasticity, we specifically regress TAcc on the fluctuation in revenues (REV) and the amount of gross property, plant, and equipment (PPE), divided by lagged total assets. We move on to calculate the NDAcc for each business in our sample based on the estimations we've got for the regression parameters. In order to account for the likelihood that businesses may have distorted sales through changes in credit conditions, the change in revenue (Rev) is adjusted for the variation in accounts receivable (Rec) as highlighted in the work of Dechow et al. (1995). This adjustment serves to isolate the NDAcc and provides us with a more accurate measure of firms' underlying financial performance as per recent research (Palacios-Manzano et al., 2021):

$$\frac{NDAcc1_{it}}{A_{t-1}} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \frac{\Delta Rev_{it} - \Delta Rec_{it}}{A_{t-1}} + \beta_2 \frac{PPE_{it}}{A_{t-1}} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (4)$$

Both cross-sectional and longitudinal data can be used with the model, with the residuals serving as DAcc and NDAcc being calculated by the model. Thus, the unexplained portion of total accruals is represented by unexpected accruals or discretionary accruals (Epps and Guthrie, 2010; Fan et al., 2010). The residual estimates in the Kasznik and Kothari models are the respective measures of discretionary accruals (DAcc) as per Gonçalves et al. (2021) and Jackson (2022):

$$DAcc_{it} = \varepsilon_{it} \quad (5)$$

Evaluating the magnitude of residuals helps assess the extent of EM and provides insights into the reliability and integrity of reported accruals. Higher absolute values suggest lower-quality accruals and a greater degree of EM (Gonçalves et al., 2021):

$$abs(DAcc)_{it} = |\varepsilon_{it}| \quad (6)$$

To address potential endogeneity concerns, we employ the multiple fixed effects regression method (Chi and Gupta, 2009; Kyaw et al., 2015). The assessment of a firm's IR rating is based on externally determined ratings obtained from the Thomson Reuters Refinitiv Eikon database (Thomson Reuters, 2023). Our analysis, which departs from the model proposed by Palacios-Manzano et al. (2021), considers variables: IR, leverage, firm size, absolute deferred tax expense, net deferred tax liabilities, and financial performance. The general model we employ is as follows:

$$abs(DAcc)_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IR_{it} + \beta_2 LEV_{it} + \beta_3 SIZE_{it} + \beta_4 ROA_{it} + \beta_5 DTE_{it} + \beta_6 NDTL_{it} + FE + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (7)$$

where IR is the Integrated Reporting score; ROA is the ratio of net income to total assets; DTE is the absolute deferred tax expense scaled by total assets, NDTL is net deferred tax liabilities by total assets, and FE are the fixed-effects of country, industry and year.

In order to account for variations in profits management incentives, we use the normal logarithm of the total assets (SIZE) as a proxy for firm size. The link between size and EM is neither clearly positive nor negative (Kim et al., 2003). For Leverage (LEV) variable, it controls for the possibility of bankruptcy. A higher leverage ratio means breaching the debt covenant rules which creates a drive for earnings management (Dang et al., 2021).

Data and Analysis

The Refinitiv Eikon database from Thomson Reuters was used to gather accounting and financial data. The sample data spans a period of 11 years, from 2012 to 2022, although the actual range of years is only 10, as suggested by numerous EM models, which call for computing the change in value for a number of variables. First, we choose all European listed firms with accessible accounting, financial and IR data. The key condition was that firms had to have at least 10 years' worth of total asset value in order to be included. This disqualified certain listed companies that may have been delisted or joined in less than 10 years. Swiss corporations were then omitted since they are exempt from the IFRS (International Financial Reporting Standards) need to disclose their accounting statistics. (Palacios-Manzano et al., 2021; Park and Shin, 2004).

Financial information whose values fall under the 1st percentile as well as exceeding the 99th percentile were subsequently removed in order to minimize the effects brought on by outliers (Cohen et al., 2014). The final sample, therefore, consisted of 11444 firm-year data from 1448 listed businesses across 11 activity categories and 22 European countries. The sample's composition is shown in Table 2 by nation and industry, respectively. The UK, Germany, and Sweden are the nations with the highest representation. The industrials sector, the consumer cyclical sector, and the technology sector are each the most heavily represented in terms of industry.

Table 3 shows the average absolute discretionary accruals for the 10 years, showing a range between 3-5%, with the average of the Dechow model leading to 4.2%, the Kasznik model at 4% and the Kothari model at 4.2%. These values show a lower value as compared to (Palacios-Manzano et al., 2021) and Choi et al. (2013). The analysis of the Pearson correlation matrix in Table 4 reveals the preliminary association of the independent variables to other independent variables and the dependent variables. Preliminary analysis shows that Hypotheses 1 and 2 hold, before any significant investigation, with size and leverage negatively associated with EM.

Table 5 shows the regressions of independent and control variables on absolute discretionary accruals with controls for heteroscedasticity and serial correlation (Jackson, 2022; Petersen, 2008). The results obtained from the analysis suggest that Integrated Reporting does not have a significant negative impact on earnings management as the p-value is greater than 0.05 in all 3 models. In addition, there is no moderating effect of the Integrated Reporting score on the relationship between DT and EM. These findings are contrary to prior research which suggests that the adoption of Integrated Reporting leads to a decrease in earnings management activities (Shirabe and Nakano, 2019).

Moreover, the study reveals an inverse relationship between the size of the business and the likelihood of engaging in earnings management. There were three schools of thought on size and earnings management: the first one is size has a significant and positive influence on earnings management (Mai and Ngoc, 2021); the second one is size has a negative influence on earnings management (Kurniawati and Panggabean, 2020; Purnama and Nurdiniah, 2019) and the third one being size does not have a significant effect on earnings management (Lestari et al., 2019; Mayasari et al., 2019). Our finding aligns with most existing literature, which suggests that larger firms have stronger monitoring mechanisms and face greater scrutiny from external stakeholders, thereby reducing the incentive for earnings management (Kalbuana et al., 2021).

Additionally, the analysis indicates a positive relationship between deferred taxes and the probability of earnings management. As the level of deferred taxes increases, so does the likelihood of engaging in earnings management activities (Phillips et al., 2003). This finding is consistent with prior studies, which argue that firms may manipulate their reported earnings to take advantage of deferred tax benefits (Soliman and Ali, 2020). The study also uncovers

a positive association between net deferred tax liabilities and the probability of earnings management. This suggests that an increase in net deferred tax liabilities is associated with a higher likelihood of engaging in earnings management practices. This result corroborates the findings of Tartono et al. (2021), who suggest that firms with higher net deferred tax liabilities may have greater incentives to manage their earnings to mitigate the impact of tax obligations (Kasipillai and Mahenthiran, 2013).

The analysis reveals a negative relationship between Return on Assets (ROA) and the probability of earnings management, in line with previous studies. This implies that as ROA increases, the likelihood of engaging in earnings management decreases similar to the existing literature (Momani, 2016; Rahman et al., 2020). This finding suggests that firms with higher profitability may face fewer incentives to manipulate their reported earnings, as their financial performance is already favourable. As for LEV, in previous literature, there was a positive association between leverage ratio and earnings management (Prawida and Sutrisno, 2021). However, Yasa et al. (2020) find that leverage is negatively linked with earnings management. Some studies suggest that leverage is not significant (Ghofir and Yusuf, 2020). Our findings corroborate the insignificance of leverage due to the close monitoring of regulators, analysts and investors, thus having limited discretion regarding debt obligations (Ghofir and Yusuf, 2020).

Robustness check

Collins & Hribar (2000) suggest approaching total accruals by the formula below. This has been supported in several studies which makes it critical for this study to assess whether using this methodology would change our findings (Goel, 2012; Liu and Lu, 2007):

$$TAcc_{it} = NI_{it} - NCFOA_{it} \quad \text{restated (1)}$$

Where Net Income (NI) uses the accruals concept less Net Cash flow from operating activities (NCFOA) which is from the statement of cash flows. The first equation, as previously presented, was restated and the subsequent steps were repeated accordingly. Table 6 shows the multivariate analysis using the Akaike information criterion (AIC) to evaluate the statistical significance of the models employed in this study. Also, data were winsorized and also applied fixed effects on country, industry and year (Chi and Gupta, 2009; Cohen et al., 2014; Kyaw et al., 2015). There are no alterations to our findings.

Conclusion

This study successfully addresses a significant research gap in the literature by examining the intricate relationship between deferred taxation items and earnings management. By employing three distinct earnings management detection models, including the Dechow, Kasznik, and Kothari models, this research offers valuable insights into the presence and impact of discretionary accruals on earnings management practices. To measure total accruals, two different approaches were utilised. The first approach involved calculating total accruals as the difference between net income and net cash flows from operating activities, while the second approach adopted working capital with appropriate adjustment. To ensure the robustness of the results and mitigate potential outliers, the values obtained from each model were winsorized (Cohen et al., 2014).

The analysis of a comprehensive dataset, comprising financial information from 1448 publicly listed firms in Europe, spanned ten years from 2013 to 2022. The study investigated the possible impact of the Integrated Reporting score on the link between deferred taxes and earnings management using multiple panel regressions with fixed effects. According to the empirical findings, accruals-based earnings management is positively associated with deferred taxation expenses and net deferred tax liabilities. The study shows that the Integrated Reporting score does not have a statistically significant impact on earnings management, in contrast to what was predicted based on the current literature.

The importance of this study rests in how it contributes to the literature by offering subtle insights into the intricate interaction between deferred taxes and earnings management. These findings have ramifications for accounting practice as well as policy-making. Practitioners may create a more reliable financial reporting framework by identifying the elements that influence earnings management methods, particularly in the setting of deferred taxes.

It is critical to acknowledge this study's limitations. While the research effectively fills the indicated research need, it only considers publicly traded companies in Europe and applies certain earnings management detection computations. To further our knowledge of the connection between deferred taxation, earnings management, and integrated reporting, future research should investigate new settings and utilize a variety of approaches, taking into account the larger aspects of sustainability and ESG.

Table 1: Summary of Recent Literature on Deferred taxation and Earnings Management

Author(s)	Sample	Methodology	Major Findings
MacCarthy (2021)	selected twenty-four firms from 2001 to 2020 on the Ghana Stock Exchange	Panel data & Multiple regressions model	a decrease in the values of earnings management after 2015, signifying a reduction in tax avoidance practices after a legislation
Machdar (2022)	152 manufacturing companies on the Indonesian Stock Exchange; 2011-2019	Multiple Regression model	tax avoidance affects positively abnormal discretionary expenses; deferred tax expenses affect real earnings management positively; deferred tax liabilities affect real earnings management positively
Tartono et al. (2021)	377 non-financial public firms that are listed in the Indonesia Stock Exchange from 2015 until 2019	multiple linear regression using a fixed effect model	only deferred tax liabilities have a significant impact on earnings management, not deferred tax assets nor deferred tax expense
Simorangkir et al. (2020)	Automotive Companies Registered on the Indonesian Stock Exchange in 2016 - 2018.	multiple linear regression, coefficient of determination, t-test, F test	The ratio of tax planning, return on assets (ROA), and deferred tax expenses have a significant effect on earnings management
Kliestik et al. (2021)	Listed companies from the Czech Republic, Slovakia, Poland and Hungary	Panel data & multiple linear regressions model; non-parametric tests	enterprises do manipulate earnings, typical is upward manipulation

Source: Author's research

Table 2: Composition by Country

Panel A: Country distribution	Freq.	Percent
United Kingdom	2936	25.66
Germany	1850	16.17
Sweden	1481	12.94
France	1205	10.53
Others	3972	34.7
Total	11444	100

Panel B: Industry distribution	Freq.	Percent
Industrials	2786	24.34
Consumer Cyclical	1934	16.90

Technology	1628	14.23
Basic Materials	1255	10.97
Healthcare	904	7.90
Others	2937	25.66
Total	11444	100

Table 3: Three Earnings Management Detection Models

DACC	Dechow model		Kasznik Model		Kothari Model	
	Mean	Std Deviation	Mean	Std Deviation	Mean	Std Deviation
2013	0.0418593	0.0430582	0.0402913	0.0416843	0.0417054	0.0427790
2014	0.0401100	0.0418724	0.0384278	0.0403578	0.0392935	0.0414757
2015	0.0396922	0.0404226	0.0382482	0.0388531	0.0390479	0.0398726
2016	0.0390171	0.0375623	0.0370028	0.0365169	0.0381667	0.0372785
2017	0.0397138	0.0415322	0.0373087	0.0389343	0.0396485	0.0412985
2018	0.0405766	0.0406192	0.0389434	0.0389176	0.0402936	0.0403491
2019	0.0395870	0.0402477	0.0368538	0.0381966	0.0391909	0.0395740
2020	0.0466821	0.0437706	0.0435164	0.0420051	0.0467613	0.0432343
2021	0.0450667	0.0439172	0.0423979	0.0408954	0.0452050	0.0437452
2022	0.0478166	0.0439061	0.0443122	0.0413887	0.0481464	0.0437229
Total	0.042243		0.0399013		0.0420047	

Source: Author's research

Table 4: Pearson Correlation coefficients

	AbsDAC C	IR	lnA	LEV	AbsDTE A	IRxabsD TEA	IrxDTL A	DTLA	ROA
AbsDAC C	1								
IR	-0.0242	1							
lnA	-0.2082	0.2301	1						
LEV	-0.0442	0.0031	0.2430	1					
AbsDTE A	0.0940	-0.0028	-0.0573	-0.0253	1				
IRxabsD TEA	0.0328	0.4813	0.1103	0.0078	0.3905	1			
IrxDTL A	0.0557	-0.5754	-0.1430	-0.0031	-0.0541	-0.3708	1		
DTLA	0.1054	-0.0044	-0.1203	-0.0858	-0.1566	-0.0687	0.4196	1	
ROA	-0.0481	0.0365	-0.0106	-0.1759	-0.0428	0.0033	0.0028	-0.019	1

Source: Author's research

Table 5: Regressions of independent and control variables on absolute discretionary accruals

	1	2	3
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	Dechow model	Kaszniak Model	Kothari Model
IR	0.0000022 (0.12)	(0.0000024) (-0.14)	(0.0000012) (-0.07)
lnA	-0.00451*** (-18.52)	-0.00383*** (-16.39)	-0.00453*** (-18.74)
LEV	(0.000896) (-0.34)	0.001090 (0.43)	(0.000143) (-0.05)
absDTEA	0.385*** (7.97)	0.383*** (8.29)	0.378*** (7.90)
IRxabsDTEA	0.002570 (1.79)	0.00321* (2.34)	0.002730 (1.92)
IRxDTLA	0.000374 (0.91)	0.000319 (0.81)	0.000334 (0.82)
DTLA	0.117*** (7.32)	0.105*** (6.83)	0.118*** (7.45)
ROA	-0.0170*** (-4.62)	-0.0129*** (-3.65)	(0.006980) (-1.91)
_cons	0.140*** (27.82)	0.122*** (25.32)	0.139*** (27.96)
R-sq.	0.0789	0.0701	0.0795
Adj. R-sq.	0.075	0.0662	0.0756
AIC	(41040.8)	(42013.2)	(41227.0)

Source: Author's research

Table 6: Regressions of independent and control variables on absolute discretionary accruals

	1 Dechow model	2 Kaszniak Model	3 Kothari Model
IR	-0.0000428* (-2.21)	-0.0000158 (-0.98)	-0.0000306 (-1.76)
lnA	-0.00383*** (-13.66)	-0.00283*** (-12.10)	-0.00365*** (-14.52)
LEV	0.00101 (0.34)	0.00359 (1.43)	0.00219 (0.81)
absDTEA	1.040*** (20.96)	0.958*** (23.12)	0.968*** (21.72)
IRxDTEA	-0.00012 (-0.09)	0.000819 (0.77)	0.000337 (0.29)
IRxDTLA	-0.000826 (-1.75)	-0.000622 (-1.58)	-0.00062 (-1.46)
DTLA	0.101*** (5.48)	0.0827*** (5.38)	0.0981*** (5.93)
ROA	-0.0212*** (-5.32)	-0.0290*** (-8.70)	-0.0162*** (-4.53)
_cons	0.124*** (21.62)	0.0971*** (20.33)	0.118*** (23.06)
R-sq.	0.105	0.115	0.113
Adj. R-sq.	0.101	0.112	0.109
AIC	(39,243.70)	(43,585.30)	(41,836.10)

Source: Author's research

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A STUDY ON FACTORS INFLUENCING THE QUALITY WORK LIFE EMPLOYEES

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ABSTRACT:

The Quality of work life in Myntra company creates a workplace that enhances employees wellbeing and satisfied. Employees are highly satisfied when their job is more creative, prestigious, higher paid with more promotional avenues. This mainly focuses on a few studies of Quality of Work Life and tries to identify the factors of Quality of Work Life to employee job satisfaction. It has been found if factors such as work environment, job facets, remuneration and career development are given little more care, so that organisation can maintain good employees with a high level of quality of work life, job satisfaction, organizational commitment and involvement. This will in turn lead to the effectiveness and efficiency of employees in their work, which leads to increased productivity.

1.INTRODUCTION

Human resources is the most strategic resource as no other resource can be fully utilized to generate income and wealth of a nation without the active involvement of this resource.

Human resources are the most valuable and unique asset of an organisation. In the changing economic environment, Human Resource Management is assuming much greater importance than ever before. It is conceived to be different from the traditional and conventional notion of Personnel Management. Subsequently, Human Resource Management has become the central concern of any organisation either in public, private sector or co-operative sector.

The Quality of work life denotes all the organizational inputs which aim at employee satisfaction and enhancing organizational effectiveness. The term Quality of work life has been applied to a wide variety of organizational improvement efforts.

By Globalization the modern employees are experiencing distress. To meet the challenges posted by present standards, organizations must focus their attention in bringing balance between work life and personal life. Quality of work life is a process of work organizations which enables its members at all levels to participate actively and efficiently in shaping the organizations environment, methods and outcomes.

Quality of work life is a value based process, which is aimed towards meeting the twin goals of enhanced effectiveness of the organization and improved quality of life at work for the employees.

It is also a generic phrase that covers a person's feelings about every dimension of work including economic rewards and benefits, security, working conditions, organizational and interpersonal relationship and its intrinsic meaning in a person's life.

The success of any organization is highly dependent on how it attracts, recruits, motivates, and retains its workforce. Today's organizations need to be more flexible so that they are equipped to develop their workforce and enjoy their commitment. Therefore organizations are required to adopt a strategy to improve the employee's quality of work life to satisfy both the organizational objectives and employee needs.

- Safe and healthy working condition.
- Opportunity to use and develop human capacities.
- Opportunity for career growth.
- Social integration in the work organisation.
- Work and quality of life.

- Special relevance of work.

1.1 THE FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE THE QUALITY OF WORK LIFE ARE

- Attitude
- Environment
- Opportunities
- Nature of job
- People
- Stress level
- Career prospects
- Challenges
- Growth and development

Attitude:

The person who is entrusted with a particular job needs to have sufficient knowledge, required skill and expertise, enough experience, enthusiasm, energy level, willingness to learn new things, dynamism, in the organisation, involvement in the job, openness for innovative ideas, leadership qualities and team spirit.

Environment:

The job may involve dealing with customers who have varied tolerance level, preferences, behaviour pattern, level of understanding; or it may involve working with dangerous machines like drilling pipes, cranes, welding and soldering machines, or even with animals where maximum safety precautions have to be observed which needs lot of concentration, alertness, sometimes high level of patience, tactfulness, compassion and control over emotions.

Opportunities:

Some jobs offer opportunities for learning, research, discovery, self-development, enhancement of skills, room for innovation, public recognition, exploration, celebrity-status loads of fame. Others are repetitive, dull, routine, no room for improvement and in every sense boring. Naturally the former ones are interesting and very much rewarding also.

Nature of job:

Nature of job refers to the type of work and duties you may perform at your place of employment. The level of work can show case your experience and your position in a company. When you observe job openings, you might see the nature of work and the level of work listed as job description and job title, respectively.

People:

Almost everyone has to deal with three set of people in the work place. Those are namely boss, co-workers in the same level and subordinates. Apart from this, some professions need interaction with people like patients, media, persons, public, customers, thieves, robbers, physically disabled people mentally challenged, children, foreign delegates, politicians, public figures and celebrities.

Stress level:

All these factors are inter-related and inter-dependent. Stress level need not be directly proportional to the compensation. Stress is of different types-mental stress/physical stress and psychological or emotional stress. A Managing Director of a company will have mental stress, labourer will have physical stress, a psychiatrist will have emotional stress. Mental stress and Emotional stress cause more damage than physical stress

Career prospects:

Every job should offer career development. That is an important factor which decides the quality of work life. Status improvements, more recognition from the management appreciations are the motivating factors for anyone to take keen interest in his job.

Challenges:

The job should offer some challenges at least to make it interesting that enables an employee to upgrade his knowledge and skill and capabilities; whereas the monotony of the job makes a person dull, non-enthusiastic, dissatisfied, frustrating complacent, initiative-less and uninteresting. Challenge is the fire that keeps the innovation and thrill alive. A well-accomplished challenging job yields greater satisfaction than a monetary perk, it boosts the self-confidence also.

Growth and development:

If an organisation does not give chance for growth and personal development it is very difficult to retain the talented personnel and also to find new talent with experience.

1.2 IMPORTANCE OF QUALITY OF WORK LIFE:

Improved Quality of Work Life was not considered as important factor in India until recently as there were important impending factors like resource deficiency, environmental threats and some services of financial problems.

Quality of Work Life Program has become important in work place for the following reasons:

1. Increase demands at work.
2. Loss of long term employee guarantees.
3. The need for enhanced work place skills.
4. Greater competition for talent.
5. Increased women in work force.

Good Quality of Work Life leads to an atmosphere of good impersonal relations and h motivated employees who strive for their development. Though monetary benefits still occupy the first place in the cost of elements like physical working conditions, job restructuring and job re-designing, career development, promotional activities etc. are gaining importance rapidly.

As such workers expect the management to improve all these facilities which there by improve Quality of Work Life. If improved with good quality of work life, employees concentrate more on both individual as well as group development which in turn leads to overall development.

1.3 SCOPE OF QUALITY OF WORK LIFE:

The quality of work life is a multifaceted phenomenon. Its scope describes the expectations of the employees that need to be satisfied.

- Compensation
- Health and safety
- Job security
- Job design
- Social integration
- Better career opportunities

1.4 SIGNIFICANCE OF QUALITY OF WORK LIFE:

An organisation is made of people who posse skills, aptitude, that create competitive advantage for it. Various functions of an organisation planned executed and controlled by human resource. it is essential for the organization to do proper management of human resource in order to achieve its objectives efficiently and effectively. The management of human resource plays a key role in opening up new opportunities for promoting the growth of both individual and institutional. Through Quality of Work Life in the organisation works in the same direction. Now-a-days, jobs are so demanding that it imbalance the family and work life due to job pressure and conflicting interest. it is essential for the organization to develop quality relation between its employees and working environment.

In order to attract and retain employees, an organization has to develop a high quality of work life. Organization by adopting quality of work life programmes ensure to create excellent work condition and job for its employees. Hence quality of work life seeks to create such a work environment where the employees work co-operatively and make positive contribution in achieving organizational objectives.

1.5 SCOPE OF QUALITY OF WORK LIFE:

The quality of work life is a multifaceted phenomenon. Its scope describes the expectations of the employees that need to be satisfied.

- Compensation
- Health and safety
- Job security
- Job design
- Social integration
- Better career opportunities

1.6 NEED OF THE STUDY:

In the current scenario, every organization wants more output in compression of less input, It can be possible when working employees find their working place comfortable as per the job requirements. So, it is very important for an organization to maintain a quality relationship between its employees and the working environment. Now-a-Nowadays, there is no balance between the family and work life due to job pressure and conflicting interests and over-socialization that leads to much interest in the co-workers for satisfaction of their ego, creating problems in the minds of neighbours.

The Indian workers and their unions are now on the defensive. They are now more interested in the question of how to retain their jobs than in the question of how to improve their quality of life in the workplace.

The work-norms impose on workers too much of burden and control by their bosses. And the rules are for workers or employees. They have to follow, and the employer has the right to lay-off the worker due to marketing and technological factors.

1.STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

The aim of the study includes the following factors towards the quality of work life. They are such as poor working condition environments, resident aggressions, balance of work and family, work load, inability to deliver quality of care preferred, shift timing, lack of involvement in work process and decision making, poor relationship between supervisor, team leader, role conflict, lack of recognitions and lack of opportunity to learn new skills.

Training is an important area where workers can utilize for their self development and updating of their work knowledge. Ultimately every effort that the management takes for the worker and perseverance of the worker on their physical and the mental wellbeing inside the organisation that help in maintaining their motivation and satisfaction level which is important for effective performance of any worker. Thus the present study is an attempt to describe their factors as a tool to access the quality of work life of the employees.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research is the search for knowledge through an objective and systematic method of finding a solution to a problem is research. Research is defined as human activity based on intellectual application in the investigation of matter. The primary purpose for applied research is discovering, interpreting, and the development of methods and systems for the advancement of human knowledge on a wide variety of scientific matters of our world and the universe. Research can use the scientific method, but need not to do so.

2.1 OBJECTIVES OF QUALITY OF WORK LIFE:

- To increase individual productivity, availability, accountability and commitment.
- For better team work and communication.
- To improve the morale of employees.
- To reduce organizational stress.
- To improve relationships both on and off the job.
- To improve safe working conditions.

2.2 RESEARCH DESIGN:

The research adopted is descriptive research design. It involves facts-findings, inquiries of different kinds etc. Descriptive research studies are those studies which are concerned with describing the characteristics of a particular individual or group.

2.3 TYPE OF RESEARCH:

QUANTITATIVE RESEARCH will be done for the study to find the quality of work life of employees.

2.4 DATA SOURCES:

PRIMARY DATA

Systematic collection of information directly from respondents. The data is collected for descriptive research. The survey data collected during the study includes the data collected through questionnaire by using a convenience sampling technique.

SECONDARY DATA

The first step in the data collection approach is to look for secondary data. Usually, it is the data developed for some purpose other than for helping to solve the problem at hand. Secondary data are collected through various magazines, internal experts, and websites.

2.5 SAMPLING PLAN:

Sampling unit/Target group:

The respondents are of different departments in Myntra company.

2.6 SAMPLE SIZE:

Sample size refers to number of respondents or the size of the sample. Here the sample size taken for the study 150.

2.7 SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

In this study, a convenient sampling technique was used to collect data from respondents in Myntra company.

3. DATA ANALYSIS TOOLS:

Various data analysis tools like SPSS, GRAPHS, & CHARTS and Microsoft Excel was used to analyse data.

1.DATA ANALYSIS:

1. HOW SATISFIED ARE YOU WITH YOUR SALARY?

How satisfied are you with your salary				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	11	7.3	7.3	7.3
	31	20.7	20.7	28.0
Valid	4	24.7	24.7	52.7
	71	47.3	47.3	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

From the above frequency table, it is inferred that the ,7.3% of respondents are very satisfied, where as 20.7% of respondents are dissatisfied,24.7% of respondents are satisfied and 47.3% of respondents are very dissatisfied. The result shows that the majority of the respondents are very satisfied.

2.ACCORDING TO YOUR WORK LOAD HOW DO YOU FEEL?

According to your work load how do you feel				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	21	14.0	14.0	14.0
Valid	2	23.3	23.3	37.3
	4	40.0	40.0	77.3

5	34	22.7	22.7	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

From the above frequency table, it is inferred that, 14.0% of respondents are very satisfied, 23.3% of respondents are dissatisfied, where as 40.0% of respondents are satisfied and 22.7% of respondents are very dissatisfied. The result shows that the majority of the respondents are satisfied with the work.

3. HOW SATISFIED ARE YOU WITH THE TRAININGS YOU PARTICIPATE?

How satisfied are you with the trainings you participate

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	25	16.7	16.7	16.7
2	28	18.7	18.7	35.3
Valid 4	63	42.0	42.0	77.3
5	34	22.7	22.7	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

From the above table, it is inferred that 16.7% of respondents are very satisfied, 18.7% of respondents are dissatisfied, where as 42.0% of respondents are satisfied and 22.7% of respondents are very dissatisfied. The result shows that the majority of the respondents are satisfied with the trainings provided by the company.

4. DOES THE TOP MANAGEMENT INVOLVES EMPLOYEES IN THE MANAGEMENT DECISION?

Does the top management involve employees in the management decision

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	61	40.7	40.7	40.7
Valid 2	52	34.7	34.7	75.3
3	37	24.7	24.7	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: from the above table it is inferred that, 40.7% of respondents are very satisfied, where as 34.7% of respondents are dissatisfied, where as 24.75% of respondents are satisfied. The result shows that the majority of the respondents are very satisfied with the top management involves employees in the managing the decisions

Correlation:

Correlations

		How satisfied are you with your schedule of work and rest	since how many years have been working with the organisation
How satisfied are you with your schedule of work and rest	Pearson Correlation	1	-.053
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.519
	N	150	150
since how many years have been working with the organisation	Pearson Correlation	-.053	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.519	
	N	150	150

INTERPRETATION:

Pearson Correlation: The correlation coefficient between the two variables is -0.053. This value indicates a weak negative correlation.

Sig. (2-tailed): The p-value associated with the correlation coefficient is 0.519. This value suggests that the correlation is not statistically significant.

N: The sample size for both variables is 150, indicating that there are 150 data points available for analysis. Based on these results, there is no significant correlation found between the satisfaction with the work and rest schedule and the number of years working with the organization. The weak negative correlation suggests that there might be a slight tendency for individuals who have been working with the organization for a longer time to have slightly lower.

. Regression:

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
how satisfied are you with the extra benefits that your company offers you	3.37	1.407	150
How satisfied are you with your salary	3.84	1.395	150
since how many years have been working with the organisation	2.36	1.082	150

INTERPRETATION:

how satisfied are you with the extra benefits that your company offers you":

Mean: The average satisfaction score is 3.37, indicating a moderate level of satisfaction.

Standard Deviation: The data points deviate, on average, by approximately 1.407 from the mean.

N: The sample size is 150, meaning that there are 150 respondents' data available for analysis.

"How satisfied are you with your salary":

Mean: The average satisfaction score is 3.84, indicating a moderate level of satisfaction.

Standard Deviation: The data points deviate, on average, by approximately 1.395 from the mean.

N: The sample size is 150, indicating that there are 150 respondents' data available for analysis. "Since how many years have you been working with the organization":

Mean: The average number of years worked with the organization is 2.36.

Standard Deviation: The data points deviate, on average, by approximately 1.082 from the mean. N: The sample size is 150, indicating that there are 150 respondents' data available for analysis. Based on these results, it can be interpreted that, on average, the respondents reported moderate satisfaction levels for both extra benefits and salary. Additionally, the average number of years worked with the organization is 2.36, indicating that the respondents have been working with the organization for a relatively short period. Please note that interpretation may vary depending on the specific context and scale used for measuring satisfaction and years of work.

FINDINGS:

In the organisation it is found that the maximum number working employees 46% of respondents are male and 54% of respondents are female.

It is observed that most of the employees were in the age group of 20-30 years, which is 59.33%.

It is observed that mostly 54.7% of respondents are single in the organisation.

In the organisation it is found that 47.3% of respondents are very dis-satisfied with the salary.

It is observed that 34.7% of respondents are satisfied with the extra benefits that the company offers.

In the organisation it is found that 42% of respondents are satisfied with the trainings they participate.

SUGGESIONS:

Based on the findings of the research, the following recommendations were made

The organisation should focus on the areas of improvement, such as employee benefits or career growth opportunities.

The organisation should provide flexible work hours or remote work options to the employees.

Recognizing and rewarding employees for their hard work and achievements.

CONCLUSION:

A happy and healthy employee will give better turnover, make good decisions and positively contribute to the organisational goal. An assured good quality of work life will not only attract young and new talent but also retain the existing experienced talent.

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A STUDY ON EMPLOYEE TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT IN FARM GATE MILK DAIRY

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Abstract: -

Training and development is a necessary factor in the attainment of organizational objects of any association. In every association there exists some form of training and development programme. The force has to be trained and developed in terms of quality and volume so that they can effectively and efficiently control the commanding height of our profit. The business association has risen to this by furnishing the public Council for operation education and training and the centre for operation development schemes. It's important because it directs training and development towards association need and aspiration. Training and development is a necessary factor in the attainment of organizational objects of any association. The force has to be trained and developed in terms of quality and volume so that they can effectively and efficiently control the commanding height of our profit. The business association has risen to this by furnishing the public Council for operation education and training and the centre for operation development schemes. It's important because it directs training and development towards association need and aspiration. This design paper is set for highlight the problems of staff training and development in the company and also to offer results to these problems.

Keywords: Training benefits, Training design, Training delivery, Training evaluation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Worker training and development is one of the major issuing motifs now a day because this helps the association in number of ways. The daily performance of business and day to day conservation is needs to be done by some workers or workers. And this can only be done when there's proper training and development session held for the workers. Training and development will surely beget in increase of the workers performance. It's like a root toward a better result or success. It is extremely important for any kind of business, whether it's small a ground association having four to five workers or a large scale-association having some number of workers. But the main point is that training and development is necessary in every association in order to avoid any deceiving exertion in future.

1.1 Training methods:

There are a number of training methods available. Use of particular methods depends on the trainee's viz., work, supervisor and manager. Basically, these methods can be classified into the following broad categories.

- On the job training
- Off the job training

On the job training methods:

- Apprenticeship training
- Job instruction training (JIT)
- Coaching/understudy or assistant to positions
- Job rotation
- Internship

Corporate need and training need are independent because ultimately depends on the performance of its individual employee and its sub group.

Off the job training methods:

- Class room lectures
- Conferences, seminar or workshops
- Group discussions

- Audio visuals
- Simulation
- Vestibule training
- Programmed instructions
- The case study
- Role playing

1.2 Need to study:

Training is important not only from the point of view of association, but also for the workers. Training is precious to workers because it'll give them less job security and opportunities for advancement. Technology is changing at a fast pace. The workers must learn new ways to make use of advanced technology. Therefore, training should be treated as a nonstop process to modernize the workers in new styles and procedures. Guests have become quality conscious and their conditions keep on changing. To satisfy the guests, quality of products must be continuously bettered through training of workers. It's essential to increase productivity and reduce cost of products to meet competition in request.

Effective training can help increase the productivity of workers.

1.3 Scope of the Study:

- Training is the corner stone of sound management for it makes employees more efficient and productive. It is an activity connected all personnel and management activity.
- Training is most helpful in improving technical knowledge and mechanical knowledge of personnel involved. The study is confined to Farm gate dairy products, Gandrajupalli. The being conducted for the period of one month since time is limited. Nearly 101 employees are considered for the study.
- The study is based on the training programs conducted by Farm gate dairy products. The study will be able to generate the opinions of employees on the training and development programmes.

1.4 Statement of the problem

The problem at hand is the inadequate training and development of employees within the organization. Despite the recognized importance of continuous learning and skill enhancement, the current training programs and initiatives fail to meet the needs of employees, hindering their professional growth and impeding the overall progress of the organization.

- **Lack of Comprehensive Training Programs:** The existing training programs are insufficient in addressing the diverse needs of employees. They may not cover all the essential skills required for their roles or fail to keep up with the rapidly evolving industry trends and technologies.
- **Inadequate Training Resources:** The organization lacks the necessary resources, such as up-to-date training materials, tools, and technologies, to provide effective training.

This limits the effectiveness of the training programs and inhibits employees from acquiring the latest knowledge and skills.

2. Research Methodology:

Research is descriptive in nature; the data collection tool is used in the research includes questionnaire based on different questions from the employees which tells us about training and development in the Farm Gate milk dairy. The sample size for this research was 114 which includes only the employee of the Farm Gate milk dairy. The data collection period was 35 days.

Systematic sampling technique is used in the research paper to get the quantitative type of solution for the questionnaire prepared. The primary data collected was run under SPSS software for correlation, factor analysis and an ANOVA test for 114 responses to get quantitative solution. A structured questionnaire was used in the study. Divided into groups like demographic profile, statement related to training and development etc.

2.1 Objectives of the study:

- To study about the training and development programs in FARM GATE dairy products.
- To evaluate the methods of training program in FARM GATE MILK DAIRY.

- To study the factors necessary for providing the training.
- To study the efficiency of the training program adopted in FARM GATE milk dairy

2.2 Hypothesis Testing:

- H0:** There is no significant impact on attending the training program during the holidays.
H1: There is a significant impact on attending the training program during the holidays.

2.3 Research design:

The research adopted is descriptive research design. It involves facts-findings, inquires of different kinds etc. Generally, the research design can be easily described in 3 ways. They are,

- Research design in case of exploratory research studies.
- Research in case of descriptive and diagnostic research. Research design in case of hypothesis-testing research studies.

2.4 Data Sources

The source for collecting the data is from both

- Primary Method
- Secondary method

Primary data:

The primary data are those which are collected afresh and for the first time, and thus happen to be original in character. The tools for collecting this primary data are by two types namely interview methods and questionnaire method. I was called by using questionnaire method.

Secondary data:

Data was collected from documents, records, internet, company past records etc.

2.5 SAMPLE SIZE:

Sample size refers to the number of respondents or the size of sample, which is to be surveyed. Here the sample size taken for the study was 114.

2.6 SAMPLING TECHNIQUE:

A systematic sampling technique is used for the study as in probability sampling technique, each member of a population has an equal chance of being selected as a sample.

2.7 DATA ANALYSIS TOOLS:

Various data analysis tools like SPSS, Graphs & Charts, and Microsoft Excel was used to analyze the data.

3. DATA ANALYSIS

1. Years of Experience

years of Experience "

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1-3 Years	53	46.5	46.5	46.5
4-6 Yeas	43	37.7	37.7	84.2
Valid 7-10 years	17	14.9	14.9	99.1
10 Above	1	.9	.9	100.0

Total	114	100.0	100.0
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From the above frequency table, it is inferred that the 46.5% of respondents having the experience of 1-3 years, 37.7% of respondents have experience of 4-6 years, and 14.9% of respondents had experience of 7-10 years.

2. Is this training program upgrade your skills?

Is this training program upgrade your skills ? "

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	76	66.7	66.7	66.7
No	24	21.1	21.1	87.7
Valid Maybe	14	12.3	12.3	100.0
Total	114	100.0	100.0	

From the above frequency table, it is inferred that the 66.7% of respondents are accepted that training is upgrading their skills, and 21.1% of the respondents rejected that the training is not upgrading their skills.

3. Is there any development program conducted in your company?

Is there any development program conducted in your company? "

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	69	60.5	61.1	61.1
No	24	21.1	21.2	82.3
Valid Maybe	20	17.5	17.7	100.0
Total	113	99.1	100.0	
Missing System	1	.9		
Total	114	100.0		

From the above frequency table, it is inferred that the 61.1% of respondents agreed that the company conducted the development program for the employees, and 21.2% of the respondents are disagree with the development program conducted in your company.

4. Have you participated in any training program ever before?

Have you participated in any training programs ever before ? "

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent

Valid	Yes	72	63.2	63.7	63.7
	No	29	25.4	25.7	89.4
	Maybe	12	10.5	10.6	100.0
	Total	113	99.1	100.0	
Missing	System	1	.9		
Total		114	100.0		

From the above frequency table, it is inferred that 63.7% of respondents participated in the training program before, and 25.7% of respondents that they are attending the training program for the first time.

5. Which type of training program does your company follow?

Which type of training program does your company follow ? "

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	
Valid	On the Job	61	53.5	53.5	53.5
	Of the Job	35	30.7	30.7	84.2
	Both	18	15.8	15.8	100.0
	Total	114	100.0	100.0	

From the above frequency table, it is inferred that the 53.5% of respondents stated that the company follows on the job training program, and 30.7% of respondents stated that the company follows off the job training program.

6. Do you attend any training program to improve your soft skills and to improve your team spirit with the peers in the company?

Do you attend any training program to improve your soft skills and to improve your team spirit with the peers in the company? "

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	
Valid	Yes	68	59.6	60.2	60.2
	No	30	26.3	26.5	86.7
	Maybe	15	13.2	13.3	100.0
	Total	113	99.1	100.0	
Missing	System	1	.9		

Total	114	100.0		
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From the above frequency table, it is inferred that the 60.2% of respondents are attending the training program to improve soft skills and improve their team spirit, and 26.5% of the respondents are not attending the training program to improve their soft skills and team spirit.

7. Training is very useful for working in an organization?

Is Training is very useful for working in an organization ? "

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	48	42.1	42.1	42.1
Agree	28	24.6	24.6	66.7
Neutral	21	18.4	18.4	85.1
Valid Disagree	10	8.8	8.8	93.9
Strongly Disagree	7	6.1	6.1	100.0
Total	114	100.0	100.0	

From the above frequency table, it is inferred that the 66.7% of respondents agreed that training is very useful for working in the organization, and 15% of respondents disagreed with training is not useful for working in the organization.

8. Time allotted for the training program is sufficient to follow?

Time allotted for the training program is sufficient to follow ? "

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	65	57.0	57.0	57.0
No	34	29.8	29.8	86.8
Valid Maybe	15	13.2	13.2	100.0
Total	114	100.0	100.0	

From the above frequency table, it is inferred that the 57% of respondents agreed with the statement that the time allotted for the training program is sufficient, and 29.8% of the respondents required more time for the training.

9. The number of training methods does your company follow?

The number of training methods does your company follow ? "

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid More than one	80	70.2	70.8	70.8
Valid More than Two	33	28.9	29.2	100.0
Total	113	99.1	100.0	
Missing System	1	.9		
Total	114	100.0		

From the above frequency table, it is inferred that the 70.8% of respondents are attending themore than one training program in the organization, and 29.2% of the respondents are attending more than two training methods in the organization.

10. Does the company training and development mainly focus on the enhancement of knowledge?

Does the training and development mainly focus on the enhancement of knowledge ? "

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	74	64.9	65.5	65.5
Valid No	28	24.6	24.8	90.3
Valid Maybe	11	9.6	9.7	100.0
Total	113	99.1	100.0	
Missing System	1	.9		
Total	114	100.0		

From the above frequency table, it is inferred that the 65.5% of respondents sated that training and development mainly focussed on the enhancement of knowledge, and 24.8% of the respondents are stated that the training and development is not focused on the enhancement of knowledge.

11. What are the methods used in the training program to enrich your skills?

What are the methods used in the training program to enrich your skills ? "

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	CumulativePercent
Presentation Method	42	36.8	36.8	36.8
Group Building Method	41	36.0	36.0	72.8
Valid Coaching or mentoring	19	16.7	16.7	89.5
Instructor-led training	12	10.5	10.5	100.0
Total	114	100.0	100.0	

From the above frequency table, it is inferred that the 36.8% of respondents enriched their skills through the presentation method, and 36% of the respondents enriched their skills through the training program of group building method, and 16.7% of the respondents enrich their skillsthrough with the coaching or mentoring training method, and 10.5%of the respondents enrich their skills with the instructor-led training method.

12. Do you prepare for attend the training program during holidays?

Do you prepare for attend the training program during holidays ? "

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	74	64.9	64.9	64.9
No Maybe	26	22.8	22.8	87.7
Total	14	12.3	12.3	100.0
	114	100.0	100.0	

From the above frequency table, it is inferred that the 64.9% of respondents are attending the training program during the holidays to improve their skills and knowledge, and 22.8% of the respondents did not attend the training program during the holidays.

13. Do you feel that training decreases stress, tension, frustration and conflict?

Do you feel that training decreases stress, tension, frustration and conflict? "

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	52	45.6	45.6	45.6
Agree	25	21.9	21.9	67.5
Neutral	20	17.5	17.5	85.1
Valid Disagree	11	9.6	9.6	94.7
Strongly Disagree	6	5.3	5.3	100.0
Total	114	100.0	100.0	

From the above frequency table, it is inferred that the 67.5% of respondents feel that training decreases stress, tension and frustration, and 14.9% of respondents feel that training does not decrease the stress, tension and frustration.

14. Do you agree that technology changes or new technology will require effective training?

Do you Agree that technology changes or new technology will require effective training ? "

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	76	66.7	66.7	66.7
No	26	22.8	22.8	89.5
Maybe	12	10.5	10.5	100.0
Total	114	100.0	100.0	

From the above frequency table, it is inferred that the 66.7% of respondents agreed that new technology will require the effective training, and 22.8% of the respondents disagree with the new technology will require the effective training.

15. To whom is the training is given in your organization?

To whom is the training given in your organization?"

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Jr staff	30	26.3	26.5	26.5

	New staff	30	26.3	26.5	53.1
Valid	Sr Staff	21	18.4	18.6	71.7
	All employees	32	28.1	28.3	100.0
	Total	113	99.1	100.0	
Missing	System	1	.9		
Total		114	100.0		

From the above frequency table, it is inferred that training is mostly given to the employees based on the requirements in the organization. Out of 114 respondents, 28.3% of respondents feel that training is given to all employees, 53% feels that training is given to junior and new staff and 18.6% feels that it is given to senior staff.

Here it can be observed that training in the organization is generally given on the basis of requirement by the organization.

16. Correlations

Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no significant relationship between experience and attending the training program during the holidays.

Alternate Hypothesis (H1): There is a significant relationship between experience and attending the training program during the holidays.

Correlations

		Years of Experience"	Do you prepare attending the training program during holidays ? "
Years of Experience "	Pearson Correlation	1	.218*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.020
	N	114	114
Do you prepare attending the training program during holidays ? "	Pearson Correlation	.218*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.020	
	N	114	114

From the above correlation table, it is inferred that the significance value is 0.020 which is lesser than 0.05. Here we can say that the null hypothesis is rejected, and alternate hypothesis is accepted. In other words, there is significant impact with year of experience and attending the program during the holidays.

17. Anova

Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no significant relationship between experience and attending the training program during the holidays.

Alternate Hypothesis(H1): There is a significant relationship between experience and attending the training program during the holidays.

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	2.689	1	2.689	5.606	.020 ^b
Residual	53.732	112	.480		
Total	56.421	113			

From the ANOVA table. It is found that the significant value is 0.020, which is less than 0.05. Hence, null hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted. In other words, we can say that there is a significant relation between year of experience and attending the program during the holidays.

There is significant relation between year of experience and attending the program during the holidays.

Findings & Conclusion:

The organization helps the employees to increase their skills by conducting the training and development programs regularly and assessing training needs efficiently.

The organization has a strong linkage with the training & development programs and these programs are helpful in their self-development and the organizational development.

From studies made in assessing the effectiveness of training and development methods, the organization has certainly tried its best to impart training and development which makes the employees acquire skills and knowledge about their job and importance, which results in their job satisfaction.

Hence, training & development plays a vital role in increasing knowledge and creates a skillful employee for the organization.

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A STUDY ON STRESS MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: -

Stress is a prevalent issue in today's fast-paced and competitive corporate environment, impacting employee well-being, productivity, and overall organizational success. This study aims to investigate stress management practices within Coca-Cola Beverages Pvt. Ltd. located in Srikalahasthi, focusing on identifying the sources of stress and evaluating the effectiveness of existing stress management strategies. The research will employ a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative and quantitative data collection techniques. In-depth interviews will be conducted with employees at various levels within the organization to gain insights into their perceived sources of stress, coping mechanisms, and suggestions for improvement. Additionally, a standardized questionnaire will be administered to a larger sample of employees to obtain quantitative data on stress levels, employee engagement, and the perceived effectiveness of current stress management initiatives. The findings of this study will provide valuable insights into the specific stressors faced by employees in Coca-Cola Beverages Pvt. Ltd., Srikalahasthi, and the impact of stress on their overall well-being and job performance. Furthermore, the study will evaluate the effectiveness of existing stress management practices and identify areas for improvement. The results will help the organization develop targeted interventions and policies to enhance employee well-being, reduce stress levels, and foster a positive work environment.

Keywords: stress management, employee well-being, organizational effectiveness, Coca-Cola Beverages Pvt. Ltd., Srikalahasthi.

1. INTRODUCTION

Employees are considered as the most valuable asset for every organization, in HRM practices they are the blood of the organization because the success or the failure of the firm depends on the employees' performance. Employees are needed in the organization because their competencies can fulfill the role in the organization which help the firm to achieve its goals and objective. Either already experienced or skilled person is hired by the organization, or they are trained in the organization to meet its expectations. Every industry is coping with such activities that are used in attaining their standards. It has been proven by various studies that there is significant relation between the training practices and the work performance (Niazi, 2011).

Training is the process of acquiring knowledge, skills, and competencies through systematic instruction and practice. It involves providing individuals or groups with structured learning experiences that are designed to enhance their abilities and performance in a particular area.

Training is a structured learning that aims to develop knowledge, skills, and competencies in individuals or groups, enabling them to perform tasks more effectively and efficiently in a particular domain. The benefits of training include improved performance, increased knowledge and understanding, enhanced problem-solving and decision-making skills, greater confidence, and a sense of personal and professional growth. Additionally, organizations often provide training to their employees to enhance productivity, promote a positive work environment, and address specific skill gaps or performance deficiencies.

1.1 Compressive Stress:

Compressive stress is the stress applied to the material that makes the material compact (reduced in volume). When the material is subjected to compressive stress, the material is in a state of compression. In general, compressive stresses are applied in rods, lines, etc. applies to causes shortening.

Loading the material or structure increases the compressive strength until the compressive strength is achieved.

Depending on the properties of the material, ductile materials (mostly steel, some clay and plastic) break through yielding or irregular behaviour (geometric shapes, cast iron, glass, etc.).

In slender structures such as columns or beam bars, an increase in the compressive force F causes structural failure due to buckling of stresses under the compressive force. Compressive stress consists of tension (force per unit area) and is usually expressed as a negative value for compression. But in geotechnical engineering, compressive stresses are represented by positive values.

Definitions of Job Stress

Changes in the job, such as the introduction or transfer of new technology or a change of purpose, can cause tension or stress, can be built into the organization's structure. Organizational stress can be measured by absenteeism and performance.

Organizational stress

Stress affects people. Organizations with high absenteeism, high employee turnover, poor business and customer relations, poor security records, or poor management are good when there is tension in the organization.

Monitoring Stress in an Organization

The diagram below shows an example of a department working in an organization and illustrates the stressors that can affect a stress level in the structure. Causes an impact on humans. Anxiety is contagious; Everyone is underperforming due to increased pressure from colleagues, supervisors, and subordinates. Reasons, unclear or overlapping descriptions, lack of communication, poor performance, etc. may contain.

Possible sources of stress

Potential sources of stress fall into three categories:

Environmental factors Institutional factors Personal factors Environmental factors: Affect the organization as well as the uncertainty of the environment. Changes in the business cycle create business uncertainty.

Political Uncertainty

If a country's political system is followed by the rules, there will be no chaos.

Technological uncertainty

New innovations can quickly obsolete workers' skills and experience. Technological uncertainty is therefore the third environment that can cause stress. Computers, robots, automation and other technologies create stress and anxiety for many people.

Organizational Factors

The effect of lack of organizational stress; Avoidance of mistakes or pressure to complete tasks within the time limit, overloading are a few examples.

Organization defines the level of diversity in the organization, the level of management and where decisions are made. Too much authority affecting employees and lack of participation in decision-making are examples of change patterns that can lead to stress.

Corporate Leadership Capability represents control of the organization's top management. Some leaders create a culture marked by tension, fear, and anxiety. They rely on the absurdity of short-time work, rigid management, and routine layoffs of unskilled workers. This creates fear in them that leads to anxiety. Organizations go through a cycle. They were established; they grow, they grow, and eventually they fall. An organization in a four-stage life cycle - causes different problems and stress for employees.

The stages of formation and degradation are particularly difficult. Personal Factors: The average person works only 40 hours a week. The experiences and problems that people have outside of work 128 hours a week can affect work.

Family Issues

National studies consistently show that people value family and discipline, and issues with children are an example of social issues that cause people to get stressed at work and not show up at the door when they come to work.

Financial problems

Financial problems resulting from personal overload of financial resources are another group of personal problems that can stress and distract employees from work.

1.2 Need for the study:

Over the past few years, the media has made it clear that the need for stress management must be at the top of today's agenda. The way anger alone and inflicts damage on our lives is a good example of this.

Life is more difficult today than it was during the Great Depression. It manifests itself in many ways, such as the unprecedented formation of stomach and intestinal ulcers. Others see sleep anxiety and mechanical zombies on a busy day.

Insomnia is on the rise. Stress management is important in everyone's life today. It is essential for a long and happy life, with less hassle. There are many ways to deal with stress by addressing the cause.

1.3 Scope of the study:

In today's rapidly changing world, everyone is faced with a great need for study. The stress of this job causes mental and physical damage. Stress refers to the individual's response to factors dispersed in the environment and the consequences of this response. This research will help organizations understand the causes of stress among employees and how to reduce stress because it is well known that employees are healthy and eating healthy is productive employees.

- Identify the root cause of employee stress.
- Examine the effects of stress on employee performance.
- Find ways to reduce stress and increase process efficiency

1.4 Statement of the problem

However, in most of the studies it is shown that the training has positive impact on the employee performance, must not be always true if not executed well. This research is focused on event Management Company where the workforce are mainly associated with the field work with a particular skills.

The question of this research arises from the fact that Event Management industry face many problems related to training and development as well as staff retention. For example, ninety-seven percent of organizations do not allow employees to attend appropriate external training or development training. In fact, if the employee develops personal ambitions for further education or personal development; the organization wants it to release before it can start reviewing the development. For this reason, it is difficult for employees to stay at organization for long, and as soon as they see a better opportunity and they jump on board.

2. Research Methodology:

Research is descriptive in nature; the data collection tool is used in the research includes questionnaire based on different questions from the employees which tells us about training and its impact on their performance and retention. The sample size for this research was 106 which includes only the employee of the Events Arena organization. The data collection period was 45 days.

Systematic sampling technique is used in the research paper to get the quantitative type of solution for the questionnaire prepared. The primary data collected was run under SPSS software for correlation, factor analysis and an ANOVA test for 106 responses to get quantitative solution. A structured questionnaire was used in the study, which was based on five-point Likert scale. Divided into groups like demographic profile, statement related to stress management, relaxation etc.

2.1 Objectives of the study

- To identify measures to deal with stress in construction.
- Examine the effects of stress on their performance.
- Identify situations that cause employee stress.
- Understanding the stress levels of workers of different age groups

2.2. Hypothesis Testing:

CORRELATIONS

Null Hypothesis (H0):

There is no significant relationship between total years of experience and working environment of the organization on stress management.

Alternate Hypothesis (H1):

There is a significant relationship between total years of experience and working environment of the organization on stress management.

REGRESSION

Null Hypothesis (H0):

There is no significant relationship between total years of experience and working environment of the organization on stress management.

Alternate Hypothesis (H1):

There is a significant relationship between total years of experience and working environment of the organization on stress management.

2.3 Research design:

The research adopted is descriptive research design. It involves stress management factors, yoga etc.

Descriptive research studies are those studies which are concerned with describing the characteristics of a particular individual or group.

2.4 Type of Research:

QUANTITATIVE RESEARCH will be done for the study because it aims to gather an in-depth understanding of human behavior and the reason that governs such behavior.

2.4 Data Sources

Collection of data is the primary importance in the research process. Data, which was collected for the purpose of research, helps in proper analysis, which is helpful to conducting research efficiently. The data source, which is very important in collection of data, is primary data and secondary data. Both primary and secondary data are taken into consideration for conducting the study of training and its impact on employee performance.

1. Primary source of data
2. Secondary source of data

For this dissertation the data was collected from both the sources.

Primary data:

Data is made available through interview and questionnaires. Questionnaires were prepared for trainees to know the impact of .

Secondary data:

Data were collected from documents, records, Internet, company past records etc.

2.5 SAMPLING PLAN:

Sampling unit/Target group: The respondents are of different departments in Events Arena.

2.6 SAMPLE SIZE:

Sample size refers to the number of respondents or the size of sample, which is to be surveyed. Here the sample size

taken for the study was 106.

2.7 SAMPLING TECHNIQUE: Systematic sampling technique is used for the study as in probability sampling technique each member in a population has equal chance of being selected as a sample.

Variables

Two types of variables are used in this research. The dependent variable identified for research is total year of experience while the independent variable is working conditions.

2.8 DATA ANALYSIS TOOLS: Various data analysis tools like SPSS, Graphs & Charts, and Microsoft Excel was used to analyze the data.

3. DATA ANALYSIS

1. PSYCHOLOGICAL WORKING CONDITION OF THE ORGANIZATION

How do you feel about the Psychological Working condition of the organization

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Highly Amicable	34	32.1	32.1	32.1
Cordial	31	29.2	29.2	61.3
Neutral	25	23.6	23.6	84.9
Valid				
Strained	12	11.3	11.3	96.2
Very poor	4	3.8	3.8	100.0
Total	106	100.0	100.0	

32.1% of the respondents feel that the psychological working condition of the organization is highly amicable, 29.2% of the respondents feel that the psychological working condition of the organization is cordial. 23.6% feel it is neutral, 11.3% of the respondents feel that the psychological working condition of the organization is strained, and the rest 3.8% feel it is very poor.

2. DOES THE COMPANY PROVIDES ANY FACILITIES LIKE YOGA, LIBRARY TO REDUCE STRESS

Does the company provide any facilities like Yoga, Library to reduce stress?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	79	74.5	74.5	74.5
Valid No	27	25.5	25.5	100.0
Total	106	100.0	100.0	

74.5% of the respondents yes to company provides any facilities like yoga, library to reduce stress, 25.5% of the respondents no to company provides any facilities like yoga, library to reduce stress.

3. FACTORS WHICH CAUSE MORE STRESS IN THE JOB

In your accordance which of the following factors cause more stress?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Role's overload	66	62.3	62.3	62.3
Role under load	21	19.8	19.8	82.1
Valid Interpersonal relationship	19	17.9	17.9	100.0

Total	106	100.0	100.0	
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62.3% of the people are overload with stress in the job. 19.8% of the people are under load with stress in the job. 17.9% people have interpersonal relationship with the stress in the job.

4. THE KIND OF STRESS YOU SUFFER IN YOUR JOB

What kind stress do you suffer in your job?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Physical	45	39.1	39.1	39.1
Mental	46	40.0	40.0	79.1
Valid Both	24	20.9	20.9	100.0
Total	115	100.0	100.0	

39.1% say that they suffer from physical stress from their job. 40% say that they suffer from mental stress from their job. 20.9% say that they suffer from both mental and physical stress from their job.

5. EMPLOYEES FEEL INSECURE ABOUT THEIR JOBS AT TIME

Do your employees feel insecure about their jobs at time?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Sometimes	29	27.4	27.4	27.4
Valid Never	77	72.6	72.6	100.0
Total	106	100.0	100.0	

0% say always. 27.4% say that they employees feel insecure about their job and 72.6% never feel about the insecure about their jobs at any time.

6. HOW DO YOU FEEL ABOUT THE PHYSICAL WORKING CONDITION OF THE ORGANIZATION

Null Hypothesis (H0):

There is no significant relationship between total years of experience and working environment of the organization on stress management.

Alternate Hypothesis (H1):

There is a significant relationship between total years of experience and working environment of the organization on stress management.

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Total years of experience	2.08	1.015	106
How do you feel about the physical working condition of the organization?	2.54	.997	106

Correlations

		Total years of experience	How do you feel about the physical working condition of the organization?
Pearson Correlation	Total years of experience	1.000	.265
	How do you feel about the physical working condition of the organization?	.265	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	Total years of experience	.	.003
	How do you feel about the physical working condition of the organization?	.003	.
N	Total years of experience	106	106
	How do you feel about the physical working condition of the organization?	106	106

From the correlation table, it is found that there is a significant and positive correlation between working condition of the organization and total years of experience with significant value .003 which is less than 0.05. there is a significant relationship between working environment of the organization and total years of experience. Hence the null hypothesis H₀ is rejected and the alternative hypothesis H₁ is accepted.

8. ;To whom does training is given much emphasis in the organization?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Based on requirement	71	37.0	37.0	37.0
Junior staff	53	27.6	27.6	64.6
New staff	53	27.6	27.6	92.2
Senior staff	15	7.8	7.8	100.0
Total	192	100.0	100.0	

From the above frequency table, it is inferred that the training is mostly given to the employees based on the requirement in the organization. Out of 192 respondents 37% of respondents feels that training is provided based on requirements, 55.2% feels that training is given to junior and new staff and 7.8% feels that it is given to senior staff. Here it can be observed that training in the organization is generally given on the basis of requirement by the organization.

9. Impact of enhanced personal skills after training on the chance of their promotion and salary hike.

H₀: There is no significant impact of enhanced personal skills after training on the chance of their promotion and salary hike.

H₁: There is a significant impact of enhanced personal skills after training on the chance of their promotion and salary hike.

		Does improved performance after training enhances chance of promotion and salary hike?	Does training methods impacted on your personal skills?
Does improved performance after training enhances chance of promotion and salary hike?	Pearson Correlation	1	.205**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.004
	N	192	192
Does training methods impacted on your personal skills?	Pearson Correlation	.205**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.004	
	N	192	192

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

From the above correlation table, it is inferred that the significance value is 0.004 which is lesser than 0.05. Here we can say that the null hypothesis is rejected, and alternate hypothesis is accepted. In other words, there is significant impact of enhanced personal skills after training on the chance of their promotion and salary hike.

10. Would you like to plan your further career in this organization after training? Hypothesis:

H0: There is no significant effect of training on the retention of employees.

H1: There is a significant effect of training on the retention of employees.

ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1.462	1	1.462	14.655	.000
Within Groups	18.754	188	.100		
Total	20.216	189			

From the ANOVA table. It is found that the significant value is 0.000, which is less than 0.05. Hence, null hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted. In other words, we can say that there is a significant effect of training on the retention of employees.

There is significant difference in training imparted and the retention of employees.

Findings & Conclusion:

- Most of the respondents have very less experience with the organization.
- Almost all the respondents are neutral with the physical and psychological working condition of the organization and only fewer respondents are dissatisfied with the psychological working condition of the organization.
- The opinion about the training programs conducted by the organization is almost better, according to the majority of the respondents.
- Almost all respondents are satisfied with the pay package provided by the organization and nearly half of the respondents feel that they do an interesting job.
- Most of these respondents agree that they can complete their work within the specified time and some of the respondents are undecided.
- Nearly half of the respondents agree that they are over loaded with work.

From ANOVA table it is found that the significant value is .006. which is less than 0.05. It means regression model is significantly influencing dependent variable.

CONCLUSION:

From this study, it can be safely stated that the employees of COCA COLA PVT LTD IS handling in the constructive way.

“Stress Management” has become one of the most critical factors in today's world also specially in an organization's working today

Company needs to enhance the psychological well-being and healthy of the employees, in coming future the organization would make more revenue as well as employee retention. Because it issaid that.

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A STUDY ON TALENT MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN BIG BAZAAR

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Abstract:

Managing talent in a global organization is more complex and demanding than it is in a national business and few major worldwide corporations have risen to the challenge. This paper focuses on highlighting the way in which organizations should embrace talent management to obtain and retain the best talent available for the success of their organization. The objective of this paper is to analyze and retain the employees by managing their talent in a big bazaar. The sample size has been taken as 108 out of a total population of 150. This paper also accounts for the impact of talent management programs on employees. Additional calculations are also shown to understand how much it helps to retain. From the analysis, it was found that almost all of the respondents are satisfied with the result of the talent management program. Almost all the employees agreed that the talent management program creates a good work culture as well as enhancing the values of employees and decreases in turnover of employees. Final observations of the study are that most of the employees are satisfied that the talent management program helps to identify the strength and weakness of employees.

Keywords: Talent Management, Strategic Human Resources, Big Bazaar

1. INTRODUCTION

Talent management means identifying a person's skills, traits, behaviors and matching them to the job. Everyone has specific skills that fit a particular job, and other jobs can be irritating. It is the job of management, especially HR, to carefully and carefully place candidates. Poor performance can lead to additional hiring, retraining, and other negative actions. Talent management benefits organizations and employees. The organization benefits from: Increased productivity and capacity, better connectivity between people and business goals, Key employee commitment, Reduced paybacks, Increased redundancies, and better competition between human labour and skills. Employees benefit from: higher motivation and commitment, career advancement, greater understanding and contribution to the company's goals; continuous motivation and job satisfaction. In today's competitive world, where change is continuous, it is important for organizations to develop their human resources, which is the most important resource. In the globalizing world, only human resources can give organizations a competitive advantage, because according to the new contract technology can be easily transferred from one country to another and there is no shortage of cheap capital. But finding skilled workers is difficult. Intelligence is the ability to learn and grow in the face of new challenges. Intelligence is about future capabilities, not past information.

Therefore, intelligence is often measured as having certain characteristics such as risk taking and learning from mistakes, reasonable (but not excessive) diligence and competitiveness, focusing on the "big picture" problem, recognizing strengths, limitations. and the influence of others. Many intelligence management techniques need to be applied at a competitive level to be successful. These processes/strategies include talent identification, recruitment and evaluation, performance management, performance management, career development, training management, compensation, succession planning, etc. includes.

1.1 Key Components of Talent Management:

Research and Selection: This includes attracting and involving the right people for the organization. It includes job posting, application tracking, resume review, interviews and candidate selection.

Performance Management: This process focuses on setting performance goals, providing regular feedback, conducting performance reviews, and identifying areas for improvement. It helps to improve personal performance in line with the goals of the institution.

Training and Development: This component deals with training, development and provision of resources to develop the skills, knowledge and skills of employees. It is designed to solve technical problems, support professional development and facilitate lifelong learning.

Succession Planning: This process identifies and develops employees who can assume key leadership and key roles in the organization. It ensures that the pool is ready to take on higher responsibilities in the future.

Career Development: These tools focus on creating career opportunities, providing growth opportunities, and providing training and coaching to support employees' careers. It helps to increase employee engagement and commitment.

Talent Analytics: This includes collecting and analyzing data on talent acquisition, performance, development and retention. It helps analyze situations, make data-driven decisions, and evaluate the effectiveness of intelligence management strategies.

Collaboration and Recognition: This refers to creating a positive workplace, encouraging employee engagement, and appreciating and rewarding individuals for excellence. It helps to increase employee satisfaction and loyalty.

1.2 Need for study:

This research only tries to define the organization, HR talent management. This study brings together several important aspects of human resources and management. Organizations using the knowledge management approach will focus on integrating and integrating ideas.

1.3 Scope of the study:

Recently, an organization's HR department has been given talent management responsibilities in addition to the traditional work done to provide good human capital to the organization. They use the following methods to do this job, i.e.

- Identify the skills needed
- Choose the right talent
- Implement competitive compensation plans
- Education and continuing professional development
- Build skills gained
- Maintain skills

1.4 Statement of the problem

The management of existing talent in non-profit organizations leads to the best use and development of staff. The system cannot adequately identify, attract, retain and develop talent, hindering the organization's ability to achieve business goals and maintain a positive work environment. To study on the talent management system in the Big Bazaar.

2. Research Methodology:

Research is descriptive in nature; the data collection tool is used in the research includes questionnaire based on different questions from the employees which tells us about the talent management system in the organization. The sample size for this research was 108, which includes only the employees of the big bazaar. The data collection period was 30 days.

A Systematic sampling technique is used in the research paper to get the quantitative type of solution for the questionnaire prepared. The primary data collected was run under SPSS software for correlation, factor analysis and an ANOVA test for 108 responses to get a quantitative solution. A structured questionnaire was used in the study, which was based on five-point Likert scale. Divided into groups like demographic profile, statement related to training, retention etc.

2.1 Objectives of the study

In the current scenario of cutthroat competition, every company has to survive to satisfy its customers by providing them with quality products and services. The Project at Company was undertaken with a view to studying certain fundamental as well as the commercial and operational aspects of the company. The training involved the study of the following:

- To understand the entire procedure of talent management.
- To explore the need of Talent Management.
- To study the accuracy and quality of work of employees.
- To suggest possible improvement in Talent Management process.

2.2. Hypothesis Testing:

Correlation

- **Null Hypothesis (H0):** There is no significant relationship between talent management initiatives and employee engagement & retention rate.
- **Alternate Hypothesis(H1):** There is a significant relationship between talent management initiatives and employee engagement & retention rates.

Regression

- **Null Hypothesis (H0):** There is no significant impact of department of the employee-on-employee engagement & retention rate.
- **Alternate Hypothesis(H1):** There is a significant impact of department of the employee-on-employee engagement & retention rate.

2.3 Research design:

The research adopted is descriptive research design. It involves facts-findings, inquires of different kinds etc.

Descriptive research studies are those studies which are concerned with describing the characteristics of a particular individual or group.

2.4 Type of Research: QUANTITATIVE RESEARCH will be done for the study because we aim to gather an in-depth understanding of the talent management system and the reason that governs such behavior.

2.5 Data Sources

Collection of data is the primary importance in the research process. Data, which was collected for the purpose of research, helps in proper analysis, which is helpful to conducting research efficiently. The data source, which is very important in the collection of data, is primary data and secondary data. Both primary and secondary data are taken into consideration for conducting the study of training and its impact on employee performance.

1. Primary source of data
2. Secondary source of data

For this dissertation the data was collected from both the sources.

Primary data:

Data is made available through the questionnaires. Questionnaires were prepared for employees to know about the talent management system in the organization.

Secondary data:

Data is collected from documents, records, Internet, company past records etc.

2.6 SAMPLING PLAN:

Sampling unit/Target group: The respondents are of different departments in the super market.

2.7 SAMPLE SIZE:

Sample size refers to the number of respondents or the size of sample, which is to be surveyed. Here the sample size taken for the study was 108.

2.8 SAMPLING TECHNIQUE:

A systematic sampling technique is used for the study, as in probability sampling technique, each member of a population has an equal chance of being selected as a sample.

Variables

Two types of variables are used in this research. The dependent variable identified for research is talent management system, while the independent variable is employee engagement and retention rates.

a. DATA ANALYSIS TOOLS:

Various data analysis tools like SPSS, Graphs & Charts, and Microsoft Excel were used to analyze the data.

3. DATA ANALYSIS

1. Does the organization have any specific talent management initiatives in place

Does the organization have any specific talent management initiatives in place?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	97	89.8	89.8	89.8
	No	11	10.2	10.2	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	

From the above frequency table, it is inferred that the 89.8% are responded as 'yes' and 10.2% are responded as 'no'. The result shows that most of them are responded as yes, so the organization have specific talent management initiatives in place.

2. How would you rate the effectiveness of our current talent management strategies and practices

How would you rate the effectiveness of our current talent management strategies and practices?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very effective	18	16.7	16.7	16.7
	Somewhat effective	40	37.0	37.0	53.7
	Neutral	29	26.9	26.9	80.6
	Not very effective	19	17.6	17.6	98.1
	Not effective at all	2	1.9	1.9	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	

From the above frequency table, it is inferred that 16.7% of the employees responded that talent management strategies and practices are very effective, 37.0% of employees are somewhat effective, 26.9% of employees are neutral, 17.6% of employees are not very agree, 1.9% of employees are not effective at all. The final result indicates that the majority of people are somewhat effective, so the organization has effective talent management strategies and practices.

3. Have you received adequate training and development opportunities to enhance your skills and knowledge

Have you received adequate training and development opportunities to enhance your skills and knowledge?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes, definitely	36	33.3	33.3	33.3
	Mostly	37	34.3	34.3	67.6
	Neutral	20	18.5	18.5	86.1
	Not really	14	13.0	13.0	99.1
	Not at all	1	.9	.9	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	

From the above table, it is inferred that 33.3% of the employees responded that they receive adequate training and development opportunities to enhance their skills and knowledge are Yes, definitely, 34.3% of employees are mostly, 18.5% of employees are neutral, 13.0% of employees are not really, 0.9% of employees are responded as

not at all. The final result indicates that the majority of people are responded as normal, so the organization has adequate training and development opportunities to enhance your skills and knowledge.

4. Does the talent management system contribute to higher employee engagement and retention rates?

Does the talent management system contribute to higher employee engagement and retention rates?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not at all	4	3.7	3.7	3.7
	Slightly	20	18.5	18.5	22.2
	Moderately	30	27.8	27.8	50.0
	Mostly	36	33.3	33.3	83.3
	Completely	18	16.7	16.7	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	

From the above frequency table, it is inferred that 3.7% of the employees responded that the talent management system contributes to higher employee engagement and retention rates are not at all, 18.5% of respondents are slightly, 27.8% of respondents are moderately, 33.3% of respondents are mostly, 16.7% of respondents are completely. The final result indicates that the majority of people are responded as normal, so the organization has a good talent management system that contributes to higher employee engagement and retention rates.

5. Does the talent management system contribute to higher employee engagement and retention rates?

Hypothesis:

Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no significant relationship between talent management initiatives and employee engagement & retention rate.

Alternate Hypothesis(H1): There is a significant relationship between talent management initiatives and employee engagement & retention rates.

Correlations

		Does the talent management system contribute to higher employee engagement and retention rates?	A talent management initiative a top priority for your organization?
Does the talent management system contribute to higher employee engagement and retention rates?	Pearson Correlation	1	-.300**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.002
	N	108	108
A talent management initiative a top priority for your organization?	Pearson Correlation	-.300**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	
	N	108	108

** . Correlation is significant at 0.01 level (2-tailed).

From the correlation table, it is found that there is a significant and positive correlation between talent management initiatives and employee engagement & retention rate with a significant value of 0.002 which is less than 0.05. There is a significant relationship between talent management initiatives and employee engagement & retention. Hence, the null hypothesis H0 is rejected and the alternative hypothesis H1 is accepted.

6. How satisfied are you with the current systems' ability to automate and streamline HR processes?

How satisfied are you with the current systems' ability to automate and streamline HR processes?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very satisfied	8	7.4	7.4	7.4
	somewhat satisfied	38	35.2	35.2	42.6
	Neutral	23	21.3	21.3	63.9
	Not very satisfied	26	24.1	24.1	88.0
	Not applicable	13	12.0	12.0	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	

From the above graph, it is inferred that 7.4% of the employees responded that the satisfaction level of current system ability to automate and streamline HR processes are very satisfied, 35.2% of respondents are somewhat satisfied, 21.3% of respondents are neutral, 24.1% of respondents are not very satisfied, 12% of respondents are not applicable. The final result indicates that the majority of people are responded as somewhat satisfied, so the organization satisfies with current systems' ability to automate and streamline HR processes

7. Does the talent management system contribute to higher employee engagement and retention rates?

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.206 ^a	.042	.033	.925	1.997

Predictors: (Constant), Does the talent management system contribute to higher employee engagement and retention rates?

. Dependent Variable: Department

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	4.009	1	4.009	4.689	.033 ^b
	Residual	90.621	106	.855		
	Total	94.630	107			

a. Dependent Variable: Department

Predictors: (Constant), Does the talent management system contribute to higher employee engagement and retention rates?

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.959	.294		10.054	.000
	Does the talent management system contribute to higher employee engagement and retention rates?	-.178	.082	-.206	-2.165	.033

a. Dependent Variable: Department

From the model summary, R Square value is found to be .042 which means the independent variable (employee engagement & retention rate) is explained 42.0% of variance in independent variable.

From the coefficient table, the standardized coefficient is 0.026 (which is less than 0.05) and significance value is 0.033 (which is less than 0.05). Hence, there is a significant and strong correlation between the department of the employee and employee engagement & retention rates.

From ANOVA table, it is found that the significant value is .033. which is less than 0.05. It means the regression model is significantly influencing dependent variable (department of the employee).

Findings & Conclusion:

FINDINGS:

It is observed that in the organization there is a specific schedule for talent management initiatives, It is provided to the employees based on the needs and requirements of the organization. It was found that the organization has provided training for the employees for their career growth. Most of the respondents are satisfied with the talent management initiatives and employee engagement, in correlation with a significance value of 0.002 it is observed

that talent management initiatives have a significant effect on employees' engagement. It is also found talent management systems contribute to higher employee engagement and retention rates of 33% effectiveness. It is found that in organization, training and development are opportunities to enhance your skills and knowledge.3%. In correlation analysis, it is observed that with the significance value of 0.002 There is a significant relationship between talent management initiatives and employee engagement & retention.

In ANOVA analysis, it is observed with a significance value 0.033 which is less than 0.05. There is significant difference between department of the employees and employee engagement.

CONCLUSION:

Talent management is an essential tool for an organization to attract, develop and retain talent. It includes a variety of HR processes and practices designed to identify potential employees, align their skills and abilities with the goals of the organization, and provide opportunities for growth and prosperity. Talent management is essential for organizations to remain competitive in today's business environment. It helps them develop their human resources, increase employee satisfaction and loyalty, and increase organizational success. By investing in talent management, companies can foster a culture of excellence, innovation and continuous improvement, driving long-term growth and progress. Organizations continue to seek efficiency and better results through the management of resources, and are taking a strategic approach to talent management - by attracting and selecting smart people, maintaining and enhancing the skills of staff to increase the confidence of the workplace, staffing the most vulnerable. work. Therefore, every organization wants to develop and improve its own processes and procedures, so Big Bazaar should focus on employee performance and talent or employee practices that allow growth and development with best practices in resource management. Key variables that motivate employees to be successful (leadership, experience, interpersonal skills, employee satisfaction and rewards) have been checked and fully defined. This is a great way to improve enterprise performance.

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A STUDY ON THE IMPACT OF TRAINING ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE AND THEIR RETENTION AT EVENTS ARENA

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Abstract: -

This study looks at the training activity at the Events Arena company. The purpose of the study is to understand the type of training given to the employees to enhance their performance and retention at the organization. By investing in comprehensive and well-designed training initiatives, companies can provide their employees with the knowledge, skills, and resources necessary to excel in their roles. Tailored training makes employees feel supported through continuous learning opportunities, they are more likely to stay with the organization, contributing to its long-term success. Research is descriptive in nature, Systematic sampling technique is used in the research paper to get the quantitative type of solution for the questionnaire prepared. The primary data collected was run under SPSS software for correlation, factor analysis and an ANOVA test for 192 responses to get a quantitative solution. In ANOVA analysis, with a significance value of 0.000 it is found that after the training there is significant effect on retention of the employees and with 0.004 correlation significance value it is observed that there is significant impact of enhanced personal skills after training on the chance of their promotion and salary hike.

Keywords: Training, performance, retention, personal skills

1. INTRODUCTION

Employees are considered as the most valuable asset for every organization, in HRM practices, they are the blood of the organization because the success or the failure of the firm depends on the employees' performance. Employees are needed in the organization because their competencies can fulfill the role in the organization which help the firm to achieve its goals and objective. Either an already experienced or skilled person is hired by the organization, or they are trained in the organization to meet its expectations. Every industry is coping with such activities that are used in attaining their standards. It has been proven by various studies that there is significant relation between the training practices and the work performance (Niazi, 2011).

Training is the process of acquiring knowledge, skills, and competencies through systematic instruction and practice. It involves providing individuals or groups with structured learning experiences that are designed to enhance their abilities and performance in a particular area.

Training is a structured learning that aims to develop knowledge, skills, and competencies in individuals or groups, enabling them to perform tasks more effectively and efficiently in a particular domain. The benefits of training include improved performance, increased knowledge and understanding, enhanced problem-solving and decision-making skills, greater confidence, and a sense of personal and professional growth. Additionally, organizations often provide training to their employees to enhance productivity, promote a positive work environment, and address specific skill gaps or performance deficiencies.

1.1 Training methods:

There are a number of training methods available. Use of particular methods depends on the trainee's viz., work, supervisor and manager. Basically, these methods can be classified into the following broad categories.

- On the job training
- Off the job training

In regards to employees, other than managers (executives) following are the methods of training.

On the job training methods:

- Apprenticeship training
- Job instruction training (JIT)
- Coaching/understudy or assistant to positions
- Job rotation
- Internship

Corporate need and training need are independent because ultimately depends on the performance of its individual employee and its sub group.

Off the job training methods:

- Class room lectures
- Conferences, seminar or workshops
- Group discussions
- Audio visuals
- Simulation
- Vestibule training
- Programmed instructions
- The case study
- Role playing

1.2 Need for the study:

Training and development is necessary to any organization that wants to be dynamic and growth oriented and to succeed in the fast changing competitive environment. As it is well known, an organization is poised to growth & dynamism only through efficient effort of its human resources. Employee capabilities need to be constantly sharpened and effectively utilized. The study is a modest attempt to macro level to examine various issues relating to training practices in the organization.

Event management industry in India plays an important role in the economy of the country as it is one of the biggest contributors to the economic growth of India. Since the organization was chosen from the service sector, this study is important for management and leaders to understand the importance of training and to construct training in a way that will be effective in facilitating employment. It will also help HR managers develop appropriate training strategies for their employees. In addition, the findings of this study can be used as a tool to evaluate the performance and management of the workforce of employees in the organization. Performance and development of employees in various areas of training to increase the impact of the business in various department of Event management industry.

1.3 Scope of the study:

This article focuses on Event management companies to understand the impact of training on employee retention and their performance at organization. So, in addition to this broader objective, the main tasks include:

1. Understand the type of training used by Event Arena Company.
2. Explore the benefits of training required for Event Management companies
3. Investigate the problems of using the appropriate training programs used by Event Management companies.

This study will be a good resource for Event Management companies looking to improve their training and productivity. This study will also provide an understanding of the different training methods and their effects on the organization, which can help managers in the organization find the most appropriate training for their organization. Obviously, this will certainly increase the productivity and ultimately the profitability of the organization.

1.4 Statement of the problem

However, in most of the studies it is shown that the training has positive impact on the employee performance, must not be always true if not executed well. This research is focused on event Management Company where the workforce are mainly associated with the field work with a particular skills.

The question of this research arises from the fact that Event Management industry face many problems related to training and development as well as staff retention. For example, ninety-seven percent of organizations do not allow employees to attend appropriate external training or development training. In fact, if the employee develops personal ambitions for further education or personal development; the organization wants it to release before it can start reviewing the development. For this reason, it is difficult for employees to stay at organization for long, and as soon as they see a better opportunity and they jump on board.

2. Research Methodology:

Research is descriptive in nature; the data collection tool is used in the research includes questionnaire based on different questions from the employees which tells us about training and its impact on their performance and retention. The sample size for this research was 192 which includes only the employee of the Events Arena organization. The data collection period was 35 days.

Systematic sampling technique is used in the research paper to get the quantitative type of solution for the questionnaire prepared. The primary data collected was run under SPSS software for correlation, factor analysis and an ANOVA test for 192 responses to get quantitative solution. A structured questionnaire was used in the study, which was based on five-point Likert scale. Divided into groups like demographic profile, statement related to training, retention etc.

2.1 Objectives of the study

1. To identify the effect of training, its type and duration on retention.
2. To determine the impact of training on employee performance.
3. To find out the benefits of proper training programs in the event management company.
4. Explore the relationship between training and employee' performance, their retention.

2.2. Hypothesis Testing:

H0: There is no significant impact of training on employee performance.

H1: There is a significant impact of training on employee performance.

H0₂: There is no significant impact of training on employee retention.

H1₂: There is a significant impact of training on employee retention.

2.3 Research design:

The research adopted is descriptive research design. It involves facts-findings, inquires of different kinds etc.

Descriptive research studies are those studies which are concerned with describing the characteristics of a particular individual or group.

2.4 Type of Research: QUANTITATIVE RESEARCH will be done for the study because aim to gather an in-depth understanding of human behavior and the reason that governs such behavior.

2.5 Data Sources

Collection of data is the primary importance in the research process. Data, which was collected for the purpose of research, helps in proper analysis, which is helpful to conduct research efficiently. The data source, which is very important in collection of data is primary data and secondary data. Both primary and secondary data are taken into consideration for conducting the study of training and its impact on employee performance.

1. Primary source of data
2. Secondary source of data

For this dissertation the data was collected from both the sources.

Primary data:

Data is made available through interviews and questionnaires. Questionnaires were prepared for trainees to know the impact and methods of training adopted by the organization.

Secondary data:

Data is collected from documents, records, Internet, company past records etc.

2.6 SAMPLING PLAN:

Sampling unit/Target group: The respondents are of different departments in Events Arena.

2.7 SAMPLE SIZE:

Sample size refers to the number of respondents or the size of sample, which is to be surveyed. Here the sample size taken for the study was 192.

2.8 SAMPLING TECHNIQUE: Systematic sampling technique is used for the study as in probability sampling technique, each member of a population has an equal chance of being selected as a sample.

Variables

Two types of variables are used in this research. The dependent variable identified for research is employee retention and employee performance, while the independent variable is training.

Dependent Variable (Retention & performance)

Employee retention and performance has been considered as a factor, which has observed and measured the effect of independent variable (training). Employee retention and performance has been presumed to be the effect due to the cause of training. Responses related to employee retention and performance from one hundred ninety-two respondents have been considered a dependent variable. Thirteen questions have been asked related to performance and retention (dependent variable).

Independent Variable (Training)

Training has been considered as a factor, which will examine the impact of training on employee retention. Training has been presumed to be the cause that will create an effect over employee retention and their performance. Eleven questions have been asked related to training (independent variable).

2.9 DATA ANALYSIS TOOLS: Various data analysis tools like SPSS, Graphs & Charts, and Microsoft Excel were used to analyze the data.

3. DATA ANALYSIS

1. Ever participate in the training provided by an organization:

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1	19	9.9	9.9	9.9
Valid 2	173	90.1	90.1	100.0
Total	192	100.0	100.0	

From the above frequency table, it is inferred that the 90.1% of respondents have participated in the training provided by the organization whereas 9.9% of respondents have not taken part in any training activities.

2. Training schedule at the organization:

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Every Six months	47	24.5	24.5	24.5
Valid No Specific schedule	73	38.0	38.0	62.5
Valid Once a year	63	32.8	32.8	95.3
Valid Quarterly	9	4.7	4.7	100.0
Total	192	100.0	100.0	

From the above frequency table, it is inferred that 73 respondents says there is no specific schedule for the training, 69 respondents says that the training is provided once in a year, 47 respondents says training is provided in every six months whereas 9 respondents says it is quarterly.

It can be observed from the table that there is no specific schedule of training as it is provided on the basis of need of the organization.

3. Kinds of training attended by respondents:

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	1	.5	.5	.5
Valid	External training	14	7.3	7.8
	Induction training	40	20.8	28.6
	Off the Job training	19	9.9	38.5
	On the job training	118	61.5	100.0
	Total	192	100.0	100.0

From the above table, it is inferred that most of the respondents had attended on the job training accounting 61.5% followed by induction training with 20.8%. Very less number of respondents had attended training in external and off the job training methods.

It can be concluded from the data that most of them in the company had undergone on the job training method.

4. Which type of training is effective according to employees?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Management training	16	8.3	8.3
	Off the Job training	13	6.8	15.1
	On the job training	85	44.3	59.4
	Technical training	78	40.6	100.0
	Total	192	100.0	100.0

From the above frequency table it is inferred that that most of the employees 44.3% believe that the on the job training is effective for the performance, followed by technical training i.e. 40.6%. On the job, training influences the performance of the employees positively.

5. Do training methods impact on your personal skills?

Hypothesis:

H0: Training has no significant effect on the employee’s personal skills.

H1: Training has no significant effect on the employee’s personal skills.

Table 4.18 Correlations

		Does training methods impact on your personal skills?	Have you ever participated in the training provided to you by your organization?
Does training methods impacted on your personal skills?	Pearson Correlation	1	.120
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.039
	N	192	192
Have you ever participated in the training provided to you by your organization?	Pearson Correlation	.120	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.039	
	N	192	192

From the above descriptive statistics table, it is inferred that most of the employees have gone under training as mean was found to be 1.90.

From the correlation table, the significance value was found to be 0.039 which is less than 0.05. Hence, null hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted. In other words we can say that training has significant effect on the employee's personal skills.

6. Does training program was relevant to the work you perform?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Effective	117	60.9	60.9
	Not relevant	7	3.6	64.6
	Not relevant at all	2	1.0	65.6
	Not sure	44	22.9	88.5
	Very effective	22	11.5	100.0
	Total	192	100.0	100.0

From the above frequency table, it is inferred that the training program was relevant to the work they did. Out of 192 respondents, 60.6% of respondents felt that training was effective and 11.5% of respondents felt that training was very effective, whereas 22.9% of respondents are not sure about its relevancy.

7. Does training enhance the performance at job?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	180	93.8	93.8
	2	12	6.3	100.0
	Total	192	100.0	100.0

From the above frequency table, it is inferred that 180 respondents out of 192 feel that the training enhances their performance at the job, whereas 12 respondents feel that it does not enhance the performance at the job.

8. To whom does training is given much emphasis in the organization?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Based on requirements	71	37.0	37.0
	Junior staff	53	27.6	64.6
	New staff	53	27.6	92.2
	Senior staff	15	7.8	100.0
	Total	192	100.0	100.0

From the above frequency table, it is inferred that training is mostly given to the employees based on the requirements in the organization. Out of 192 respondents, 37% of respondents feels that training is provided based on requirements, 55.2% feel that training is given to junior and new staff and 7.8% feels that it is given to senior staff.

Here it can be observed that training in the organization is generally given on the basis of requirement by the organization.

9. Impact of enhanced personal skills after training on the chance of their promotion and salary hike.

H0: There is no significant impact of enhanced personal skills after training on the chance of their promotion and salary hike.

H1: There is a significant impact of enhanced personal skills after training on the chance of their promotion and salary hike.

		Does improved performance after training enhance the chance of promotion and a salary hike?	Do training methods impact on your personal skills?
Does improved performance after training enhance the chance of promotion and a salary hike?	Pearson Correlation	1	.205**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.004
	N	192	192
Does training methods impact on your personal skills?	Pearson Correlation	.205**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.004	
	N	192	192

** . Correlation is significant at 0.01 level (2-tailed).

From the above correlation table, it is inferred that the significance value is 0.004 which is less than 0.05. Here we can say that the null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternate hypothesis is accepted. In other words, there is a significant impact of enhanced personal skills after training on the chance of their promotion and a salary hike.

10. Would you like to plan your further career in this organization after training?

Hypothesis:

H0: There is no significant effect of training on the retention of employees.

H1: There is a significant effect of training on the retention of employees.

ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1.462	1	1.462	14.655	.000
Within Groups	18.754	188	.100		
Total	20.216	189			

From the ANOVA table. It is found that the significant value is 0.000, which is less than 0.05. Hence, null hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted. In other words, we can say that there is a significant effect of training on the retention of employees.

There is significant difference in training imparted and the retention of employees.

Findings & Conclusion:

It is observed that in the organization there is no specific schedule of the training, it is provided to the employees based on needs and requirement of the organization. It was found that in the organization on-the-job training method is effective than the other training methods provided by the organization. Most of the respondents have undergone the training, in correlation with significance value 0.039 it is observed that training has significant effect on employee’s personal skills. It is also found that the training provided to the employees were relevant to the work they perform on daily basis with 71% effectiveness. It is found that in the organization, training is given much emphasis on the new staff 27.6% as well as it is given based on the requirements in the organization 37%. In correlation analysis, it is observed that with the significance value of 0.004 there is significant impact of enhanced personal skills after training on the chance of their promotion and salary hike.

In ANOVA analysis, it is observed with significance value 0.000 that after the training there is significant effect on retention of the employees. There is significant difference in training imparted and retention of the employees.

CONCLUSION:

Employees should be properly trained to reduce the time for managers to supervise employees. Organization must provide all employees with a mandatory training program to develop knowledge and understanding of the annual business and objectives. It is seen that in research training program were not focused to the senior employee, they should provide training to the senior staff as they are the inspiration for junior employee. Employees should be properly trained to reduce the time for managers to supervise employees. More training should be given to workers to reduce the costs of hiring and training new workers. In the organization there should be specific schedule of the training.

Training programs have a significant impact on employee performance and retention within an organization. By investing in comprehensive and well-designed training initiatives, companies can provide their employees with the knowledge, skills, and resources necessary to excel in their roles. As a result, employees become more competent and confident in their abilities, leading to improved performance and productivity. Furthermore, training programs demonstrate an organization's commitment to employee growth and development, fostering a positive work environment and enhancing employee morale. This, in turn, increases employee satisfaction and loyalty, reducing turnover rates and improving retention. When employees feel supported through continuous learning opportunities, they are more likely to stay with the organization, contributing to its long-term success. Therefore, training plays a vital role in both enhancing employee performance and promoting their retention, ultimately benefiting the organization.

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A STUDY ON EFFECTIVE RECRUITMENT AND SELECTION PROCESS

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Abstract: -

Effective recruitment and selection is essential for the success of any organization. This allows companies to retain highly skilled employees who are satisfied with their work and actively contribute to the organization. Conversely, inefficient recruitment practices can lead to differences in selection and retention, which can have a negative impact on your organization. Conflicting talents that are not aligned with the right organization and goals can undermine performance, productivity, customer satisfaction, relationships, and overall job quality. Training the wrong troops can also be costly.

This study found a strong positive correlation between recruitment and selection practices and organizational performance. To ensure business effectiveness and efficiency, it is recommended to use the latest technology in the recruitment and selection process. Additionally, having a social media strategy gives you plenty of talent to choose from. Continuous monitoring of the business environment and compliance with legal prohibitions and ethical standards is essential for an effective talent acquisition process.

In this study, we examine the different recruitment methods and create a unique model to reduce recruitment costs and time and propose suggestions that are effective and beneficial for the entire organization. Parameters for evaluating the effectiveness of recruitment and selection using

Key words: - Recruitment and Selection process, Onboarding process, Organizational performance, Job postings, Screening and Shortlisting.

Introduction:-

The importance of the hiring process is to avoid hiring the wrong people, which can do a lot of damage to your organization. Regardless of the rights or incentives offered, processes that use inappropriate and ineffective components can lead to greater losses based on poorly executed decisions and actions. Therefore, this process is one of the most important processes for human resource management and for the entire society. The selection process is a process aimed at selecting the best and most suitable donor for the work. According to the necessary conditions for this process, the acceptance of the principles of fairness, equality and equal opportunity for all applicants, that the selection is based on merit and competence, and that the selection of employees requires some kind of control. The right person in the right place, etc. Considering the above, the recruitment and selection process is one of the most important topics that we need and are interested in researching, that are why I chose this topic because of its importance and I tried to provide information about its importance by examining the topic. Some studies published from 2010 to 2020.

The recruitment process is the process by which job seekers are found and encouraged to apply for jobs in an organization. The purpose of recruitment is to provide a sufficient number of candidates for management to select the desired employees. Recruiting means finding and developing the talent pool necessary to ensure that there are enough candidates to hire into the organization. The purpose of recruiting is to find, research, evaluate and motivate potential employees to gain their commitment to fill positions essential to the success of the business and organization.

However, in reviewing the totality of the research I have reviewed, I find that there are objections to such cases, but the decision may not be correct. Perhaps the mention of these issues was ignored because it was worth considering. One obvious thing is related to the recruitment process. Although there was agreement on the steps necessary to

carry out the recruitment process, the nature of operations of each organization or company may differ and the steps generally used in the recruitment process are subject to research.

A set of usual steps in the recruitment process:

- Identify recruitment needs/determine if vacancies exist
- Update job descriptions, specifications and specifications
- Identify key areas of career planning/recruitment performance
- Review hiring policies and procedures
- Consider recruitment sources (search)
- Choose the right recruitment method
- Recruitment advertisement development/strategy development
- Placing/determining advertisements in the most suitable and appropriate communication media
- Ensure availability of application slots / ensure pool of potentially eligible applications / ensure sufficient time to respond
- Answer/Screen
- Recruitment evaluation and management
- Recruitment evaluation and management

The organization's decision to in-house or outsource depends on many factors. Several studies have addressed motivational factors in the recruitment and selection process, but in general, these factors have many similarities and differences based on the nature of the work in each organization and environment. What a company does business in.

Internal factors: recruitment policy, personnel planning, company size, recruitment costs, growth and expansion

External factors: supply and demand, labor market, image/desirable, political/social and legal, environment, unemployment, competition

First, the Equal Employment Act mandates a non-discriminatory selection process for selected groups. Second, courts will hold employers liable if employees with criminal records or other problems use access to customers' homes to commit crimes. Lawyers refer to hiring workers with these records without adequate security as negligent hiring. Poor recruitment therefore highlights the need to think about human needs for employment. Therefore, to avoid the concept of careless hiring, it is necessary to systematically obtain information about applicants and check all documents. The steps involved in the selection process are described below, and while many studies have found great consistency between these steps, there are differences depending on the nature of the work in each organization and environment. It is possible.

Typical sequence of steps in the selection process:

- Admission and admission interview
- Application form
- Detailed selection interview
- Background and reference checks
- Medical examination and physical examination before employment.
- Assessment center
- Final decision for employment.
- Final decision making and unbiased judgment.

Scope of the study

- The main goal of the research was to transform the practical and theoretical aspects of the research into practical practice.
- This project will help you to gain practical knowledge about recruiting employees in your company.
- Resolving surplus and shortage of resources.
- Development of employment policies for different categories of employees.
- Analysis

Statement of the problem:

Recruitment and selection are the most important and important functions of human resources and unless an organization has excellent employees, it cannot grow and progress in the market. In order for a company to achieve its goals, the level of motivation and motivation of its employees must be high. Every step of the recruitment and selection process is equally important to attracting and retaining the right talent. Hiring personnel is very expensive. It is also an integral part of any business and it is beneficial to do it right. When an organization selects the right people for the job, it can train them well, treat them well, and not only produce good results, but they are more likely to stay with the organization. In this situation, initial and continuous investment in your organization pays off. Before starting the recruitment and selection process, you should define the job description of each role in your organization. Recruitment and selection process policies and procedures must be defined and followed. Once the procedures are clearly defined, hiring managers and supervisors should be trained on the requirements of the process.

Objectives of the study

- Examining the recruitment and selection processes that are carried out in our organization.
- Anticipating recruitment sources and selection processes.
- Analyzing the results of the recruitment and selection process.
- Provide suggestions on recruitment and selection process.

Research method

A process used to collect and analyze data for business decisions. Methodology may include research. Interviews and other research techniques.

Designing a research project requires sufficient attention to the research method and analysis of the proposed data. In this section, we have tried to provide information on how to create a study plan for your study. The study design section provides an overview of study methods and data analysis patterns for different types of designs. Our goal is not to answer all questions, but to give you a solution.

Methodology

Study design: The following studies follow a descriptive study and are used to obtain information about the current state of the phenomenon to describe "what is there" in terms of variables and conditions within the context.

Data sources: There are two types of data sources. They are primary data and secondary data. Primary data is defined as data that is collected from its original source for a specific purpose. Secondary data is data collected from indirect sources.

Primary data: Primary data was collected from employees of Rathna Bio life Pvt Ltd using structured questionnaires containing closed and open ended questions. This includes the use of surveys and structured questionnaires.

Secondary Data: Secondary data is collected from books, internet, websites, newspaper articles, journals, magazines etc.

Research approach: To collect information about key projects, employees were approached through a questionnaire.

Instrument: A questionnaire was used as a tool to collect information from employees.

Sample plan:

Sampling Unit: Working Employees

Sample size: 160

Contact method: Simple Random sampling

Statistical tools: Different data tools such as SPSS, descriptive statistics, correlation, ANOVA and Microsoft Excel are used for data analysis.

Data Analysis

Recruiting employees on skill basis?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No	54	33.3	33.3	33.3
	Yes	106	66.7	66.7	100.0
	Total	160	100.0	100.0	

INTERPRETATION: From the above table out of 160 employees, 66.67% of employees are felt that the recruitment will be on skill basis and 33.33% of employees felt that not recruiting on skill basis.

Sources of Recruitment and selection?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	External	42	26.4	26.4	26.4
	Internal	118	73.6	73.6	100.0
	Total	160	100.0	100.0	

INTERPRETATION: From the above table out of 160 employees, 73.58% of the employees are recruited internally and 26.42% are recruited externally.

How do you know about the job?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Advertisements	28	17.6	17.6	17.6
	Friends & Relatives	48	30.2	30.2	47.8
	Personal	25	15.7	15.7	63.5
	Reference	59	36.5	36.5	100.0
	Total	160	100.0	100.0	

INTERPRETATION: From the above table out of 160 employees, 17.61% know the job through advertisements and 30.19% know through friends & relatives, 15.72% know through personal and 36.48% come with the reference.

Are you satisfied with the current job?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No	25	15.1	15.1	15.1
	Yes	135	84.9	84.9	100.0
	Total	160	100.0	100.0	

INTERPRETATION: From the above table out of 160 employees, 84.91% of employees are satisfied with the current job and 15.09% of employees are not satisfied with the current job.

How is the approach of management during Recruitment & Selection?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Casual	28	17.6	17.6	17.6
	Negative	10	6.3	6.3	23.9
	Positive	122	76.1	76.1	100.0
	Total	160	100.0	100.0	

INTERPRETATION: From the above table out of 160 employees, 76.10% said there is positive approach, 17.61% said casual and 6.29% said there is negative approach from the management during recruitment and selection.

Is the performance of HR Department is effective?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No	19	11.9	11.9	11.9
	Yes	141	88.1	88.1	100.0
	Total	160	100.0	100.0	

INTERPRETATION: From the above table out of 160 employees, 88.05% said that performance of HR department is effective and 11.95% of employees said performance of HR department is not effective.

Does HR provide an adequate pool of quality applicants?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No	26	16.4	16.4	16.4
	Yes	134	83.6	83.6	100.0
	Total	160	100.0	100.0	

INTERPRETATION: From the above table out of 160 employees, 83.65% of employees felt that the company is providing an adequate pool of quality applicants and 16.35% of employees felt that the company is not providing an adequate pool of quality applicants.

Is company doing timeliness Recruitment & Selection process?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No	32	20.1	20.1	20.1
	Yes	128	79.9	79.9	100.0
	Total	160	100.0	100.0	

INTERPRETATION: From the above table out of 160 employees, 79.87% of employees felt that the company is doing timeliness recruitment and selection and remaining 20.13% felt that the company is not doing timeliness recruitment and selection.

Is company using satisfactory methods & techniques in interviews?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent

	No	19	11.3	11.3	11.3
Valid	Yes	141	88.7	88.7	100.0
	Total	160	100.0	100.0	

INTERPRETATION: From the above table out of 160 employees, 88.68% of employees felt that the company is using satisfactory methods and techniques in interview and 11.32% of employees felt the company is not using satisfactory methods and techniques in interview.

Do you think company looks for experienced in selection?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	No	43	26.42	26.42	26.4
Valid	Yes	117	73.58	73.58	100.0
	Total	160	100.0	100.0	

INTERPRETATION: From the above table out of 160 employees, 73.58% employees felt company is looking for experienced and 26.42% are not looking for experienced.

Is Resume screening & Shortlisting methods is satisfactory?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	No	31	18.9	18.9	18.9
Valid	Yes	129	81.1	81.1	100.0
	Total	160	100.0	100.0	

INTERPRETATION: From the above table out of 160 employees, 81.13% of employees are satisfied with the screening and shortlisting methods and 18.87% are not satisfied with the screening and shortlisting methods.

Is company clearly defining objectives, Requirements of candidate in Recruitment process?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	No	16	10.1	10.1	10.1
Valid	Yes	144	89.9	89.9	100.0
	Total	160	100.0	100.0	

INTERPRETATION: From the above table out of 160 employees, 89.94% employees felt company is clearly defining objectives, requirements and 10.06% felt the company is not clearly defining objectives, requirements for candidates in recruitment process.

In how many days you will get the joining letter?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	85	53.1	53.1	53.1

	2	50	31.3	31.3	84.4
	3	18	11.3	11.3	95.6
	4	7	4.4	4.4	100.0
	Total	160	100.0	100.0	

INTERPRETATION: From the above table out of 160 employees, 85 got the joining letter between 1 to 4 days, 50 employees got between 5 to 8 days, 18 employees got between 9 to 12 days, 7 employees got after 12 days.

What is the time taken to On-board the candidate?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	1	107	66.9	66.9	66.9
	2	23	14.4	14.4	81.3
Valid	3	20	12.5	12.5	93.8
	4	10	6.3	6.3	100.0
	Total	160	100.0	100.0	

INTERPRETATION: From the above table out of 160 employees, 107 employees got 1 to 3 months of time is taken to onboard the candidate, 23 employees got 4 to 6 months of time is taken to onboard, 20 got 7 to 9 months of time is taken to onboard the candidate and 10 got 10 to 12 months of time.

Are you satisfied with the On boarding process?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	1	138	86.3	86.3	86.3
Valid	2	22	13.8	13.8	100.0
	Total	160	100.0	100.0	

INTERPRETATION: From the above table out of 160 employees, 138 employees are satisfied with the on boarding process and 22 employees are not satisfied with the on boarding process.

Is company providing induction program for newly selected candidates?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	1	143	89.4	89.4	89.4
Valid	2	17	10.6	10.6	100.0
	Total	160	100.0	100.0	

INTERPRETATION: From the above table out of 160 employees, for 143 employees felt that the induction program is conducted for newly selected candidates and remaining 17 employees felt there is no induction program for newly selected candidates.

How would you rate the selection policy of organization?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Poor	1	.6	.6	.6

Average	44	27.7	27.7	28.3
Good	115	71.7	71.7	100.0
Total	160	100.0	100.0	

INTERPRETATION: From the above table out of 160 employees, 71.70% of employees felt selection policy is good and 27.67% of employees felt average and 0.63% felt poor selection policy.

Correlations

Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no significant relation between Employee salary and Employee experience

Alternative hypothesis (H1): There is a significant relation between Employee salary and Employee experience.

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Salary	2.49	1.099	160
Experience	2.01	1.208	160

Correlations

		Salary	Experience
Salary	Pearson Correlation	1	.791**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	160	160
Experience	Pearson Correlation	.791**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	160	160

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

INTERPRETATION: The two-tailed value is 0.01 level and mean salary is 2.49 & experience is 2.01. The standard deviation salary is 1.099 & experience is 1.208. The p-value is 0.001 which includes that the correlation is statistically significant at the 0.01 level(2-tailed).As Pearson correlation is +1 the variables are significantly correlated.

ANOVA

Gender

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	19.200	4	4.800	116.250	.000
Within Groups	6.400	155	.041		
Total	25.600	160			

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Gender

Tukey HSD

(I)	(J) Salary	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	2	-.800*	.049	.000	.94	.66
	3	-.800*	.040	.000	.91	.69
	4	-.800*	.067	.000	.98	.62
	5	-.800*	.079	.000	1.02	.58
2	1	.800*	.049	.000	.66	.94

	3	.000	.044	1.000	.12	.12
	4	.000	.069	1.000	.19	.19
	5	.000	.081	1.000	.22	.22
3	1	.800*	.040	.000	.69	.91
	2	.000	.044	1.000	.12	.12
	4	.000	.063	1.000	.18	.18
	5	.000	.076	1.000	.21	.21
	1	.800*	.067	.000	.62	.98
4	2	.000	.069	1.000	.19	.19
	3	.000	.063	1.000	.18	.18
	5	.000	.093	1.000	.26	.26
	1	.800*	.079	.000	.58	1.02
5	2	.000	.081	1.000	.22	.22
	3	.000	.076	1.000	.21	.21
	4	.000	.093	1.000	.26	.26

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Homogeneous Subsets

Gender

Tukey HSD

Salary	N	Subset for alpha = 0.05	
		1	2
1	40	1.20	
2	30		2.00
3	70		2.00
4	12		2.00
5	8		2.00
Sig.		1.000	1.000

Means for groups in homogeneous subsets are displayed.

a. Uses Harmonic Mean Sample Size = 17.797.

b. The group sizes are unequal. The harmonic mean of the group sizes is used. Type I error levels are not guaranteed.

INTERPRETATION: From the Gender and Salary, the significant values from the multiple comparison table 0.000, which is less than 0.05. It means there is a significant difference in Gender and Salary.

The significant value is 0.000 is less than 0.05 that means there is significant difference between Gender and Salary.

Findings:

- 66.67% of the employees felt that they are not recruited on skill basis.
- Most of the employees are recruited from the internal sources.
- No proper advertisements are given for vacancy jobs.
- 15.09% of the employees are not satisfied with their current job. Because the company is mostly focusing on experienced and most of them are paying more than Fresher's.
- 26.4% of the employees felt that the company looks for experienced candidates in selection process.

Suggestions

- It is possible to hire a female employee. Multitasking As mentioned earlier, women can easily multitask. Hiring more women creates a positive atmosphere in the company.
- To increase employee retention, employees should be hired based on their skills. Because the employee experience is entirely based on everything the employee encounters while at the company.

- Employees are primarily recruited from internal sources, but the recruitment process should also focus on external sources. Hiring external candidates reduces the need for existing employees to take on additional responsibilities and helps manage the workload of other employees. External hires are likely to have different skills than current employees, so these professionals may be able to perform some tasks more easily than internal employees.
- We need to post more advertisements so that people know about the vacancies to fill up the vacancies.
- HR performance should be effective. Organizations should clearly define the objectives, requirements and characteristics of candidates in the recruitment process.
- The interview method should be satisfactory for the employee. In general, the recruitment and selection process should be effective in attracting employees.

Conclusion:

We conclude that effective interviewing is very necessary for any organization. To improve performance and achieve organizational goals, every organization needs to select the right people for the right jobs. The recruitment and selection process project was a great learning experience. Effective recruitment and selection contributes to the success of the organization. Recruitment and selection processes should consider internal and external sources. Recruitment is said to be a forward-looking approach in terms of attracting as many candidates as possible. Selection, on the other hand, is reluctant to apply because it tries to eliminate as many unqualified applicants as possible in order to identify suitable candidates. Hiring people with the right skills and qualities is essential for any organization to maintain and improve efficiency. Detailed analysis

EXAMINING CONSUMER BEHAVIOR AND CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES: AN APPLICATION OF THE EXTENDED THEORY OF PLANNED BEHAVIOR MODEL IN MAURITIUS

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Abstract

Purpose: The luxury fashion market is witnessing remarkable growth, innovation, and increasing demand for luxury fashion products in African countries, including Mauritius. This study aims to comprehensively analyze consumer behavior towards luxury fashion products in Mauritius, with a specific focus on the influence of customer relationship management (CRM) content marketing. By applying an extended Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) model, the study investigates the association between various framework constructs and the purchasing behavior of Mauritian consumers in the luxury apparel sector.

Design/Methodology: The study utilizes a combination of on-site surveys and online questionnaires to collect data. Randomly selected shoppers from shopping malls in Mauritius were chosen to participate in an on-site survey, resulting in 408 questionnaires. Additionally, 299 online questionnaires were administered using probabilistic sampling methods.

Findings: Descriptive analysis reveals that a significant proportion of luxury fashion shoppers in Mauritius fall within the age group of 20-30 years, followed by a slightly older group aged 31-40 years. Multiple Linear Regression and ANOVA tests are employed to test the hypotheses. The results demonstrate that attitude, subjective norm, perceived behavioral control, brand awareness, status acquisition, and willingness to pay a price premium independently influence the purchasing intention of Mauritian consumers towards luxury fashion products, taking into account the impact of CRM content marketing strategies.

Practical Implications: The study's findings hold practical implications for luxury brand consumers, owners, marketers, retailers, and scholars. The insights derived from this research enable marketers to understand key factors that impact the purchasing intention of Mauritian consumers towards luxury apparel brands, with a specific focus on the role of CRM content marketing. This understanding empowers marketers to develop effective marketing tactics and strategies to efficiently promote their branded fashion goods in Mauritius. Additionally, marketers gain valuable insights to design impactful advertising and communication methods, particularly targeting younger luxury consumers, including the youth and middle-aged working population in Mauritius.

Originality/Value: This study contributes to the existing literature by integrating the concepts of customer behavior and CRM content marketing within the extended TPB framework. By incorporating three additional variables—'status acquisition,' 'brand awareness,' and 'willingness to pay a price premium'—the study offers a comprehensive understanding of luxury fashion consumers in Mauritius. The findings provide a foundation for evaluating the relevance and applicability of the TPB in the context of luxury fashion and CRM content marketing. This research not only facilitates luxury brand penetration in the Mauritian market but also assists stakeholders in gaining momentum and flourishing in the luxury apparel industry.

Key words: *Customer relationship management, Planned Behavior, Content marketing, Mauritius*

1. Introduction

The fashion industry is undergoing significant transformations due to evolving consumer preferences and industry dynamics, leading to a boom in luxury fashion (Brand Finance, 2022). Luxury brands cater to a niche market and require strong consumer engagement for informed decision-making (Hollensen, 2011; Hollensen, 2020). Branding

plays a crucial role in influencing consumer choice by providing reliability and assurance of quality and service standards (Alexandra et al., 2018). Luxury brands hold symbolic significance, shaping and communicating consumers' personal and group identities (Thakur et al., 2015).

Luxury markets, characterized by high-value branded products, are experiencing growth and expanding their customer base (Kim et al., 2012). Luxury is no longer limited to extraordinary individuals but is becoming accessible to a wider audience, driven by global changes across borders (Kapferer et al., 2018). Fashion serves as a reflection of one's personality and behavioral attitudes (Valae et al., 2017). It is seen as a symbol of individuality, expressing one's behavior and persona (Pan et al., 2015). African countries, including Mauritius, are witnessing a thriving and lucrative fashion industry with rising demand for luxury products (Robeck et al., 2014).

Understanding consumer behavior is essential for marketers to anticipate and comprehend consumers' purchasing decisions (Peter et al., 1999; Saharan, 2019). In Mauritius, consumers face increasing options, including imported products, making it important for local businesses to explore consumer behavior in domestic settings (Ramsaran, 2010). The TPB is widely used to understand buying intentions and actual behavior (Zahedi et al., 2019). Forecasting consumer behavior has become crucial for businesses, necessitating the prompt prediction of future behavior (Park et al., 2007).

TPB has received extensive support as a framework for predicting behavior and intentions in various fields (Mohammed et al., 2017). It has been widely utilized for over three decades in numerous studies (Morgan et al., 2011). TPB provides a comprehensible and relevant theoretical model for understanding and predicting entrepreneurial intentions, considering both individual and societal factors (Rueda et al., 2015). In marketing research, TPB is commonly used to assess consumers' buying intentions toward specific products or services (Ajzen, 1991; Phau et al., 2015).

A thorough understanding of consumers enables firms to gain and maintain a competitive advantage in the market (Kotler et al., 2016). Brand managers are increasingly concerned with brand performance and sustaining luxury status (Kapferer et al., 2018). Insights from research on luxury brand consumption serve as a backbone for marketers (Heine, 2010). It is crucial for luxury marketers to convert consumers' intentions into actual purchases, emphasizing the significance of studying actual buying behavior (Chaudhary et al., 2021).

Previous studies have explored consumer behavioral intentions and purchasing behavior in the luxury sector (Wu et al., 2015; Mamat et al., 2016; Soh et al., 2017; Zhan et al., 2012). However, there is a relative dearth of research on consumer behavior toward luxury fashion brands in Mauritius. Few studies have investigated marketing and consumer behavior toward luxury goods in general, indicating the need for additional research focused on Mauritian consumer behavior toward branded clothing (Jaunky et al., 2020; Sevanandee et al., 2018; Sanmukhiya et al., 2022). To address this research gap, this study aims to apply an extended version of the TPB model to assess Mauritian consumers' buying behavior toward luxury fashion products. The objectives of the study are to determine the current buying behavior of Mauritian consumers regarding luxury apparel products and to utilize the extended TPB model to elucidate Mauritian consumer behavior toward luxury fashion products.

2. Literature Review

The concept of consumer behavior refers to the decision-making process and physical actions taken by individuals to acquire, evaluate, use, and dispose of products and services in order to satisfy their needs and desires (Solomon et al., 2012). It involves understanding the characteristics of different consumers, such as demographics and behavioral constructs, to explain their preferences (Mohith et al., 2017; Onditi, 2013). It also takes into account the influence of groups such as family, peers, reference groups, and the community (Fernandes, 2019).

Luxury, according to Cornell (2002), is a complex concept to define due to its deep connection with human perception and the value attributed to it. However, Shukla (2011) states that luxury products provide comfort and delight, are difficult to acquire, and enhance the owner's esteem beyond practical utility. In the context of this study, luxury products, specifically luxury fashion items, are described as expensive, of superior quality, scarce, or associated with well-known brands. They also include products from renowned brands with a rich history or cultural

background. These luxury fashion products represent the social status of the consumer but are not considered essential for everyday life.

The TPB is widely used by researchers to explore consumers' buying intentions toward specific products or services (Phau et al., 2015). TPB, formulated by Ajzen (1991), is an extended version of the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), incorporating the concept of perceived behavioral control (Sparks et al., 1992). TPB focuses on three independent constructs that predict an individual's intention: attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control (Ajzen, 2011; Ajzen, 2020). TPB assumes that intention strongly predicts behavior and can be assessed by evaluating generic attitudes, inclinations, and beliefs (Caplescu et al., 2014). It was developed to explain how individuals' attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control influence their intentions (Mohammed et al., 2017).

2.2.1 Attitude

Attitude toward luxury brands (Tsai, 2005) is a prerequisite for responding to a luxury brand in a particular manner (Katz, 1960). According to TPB, attitude toward a specific behavior refers to the positive or negative feelings individuals have toward a behavior based on their beliefs (Ajzen et al., 1991; Ajzen, 2006; Ajzen et al., 1992). Attitude toward behavior reflects the extent to which an individual evaluates that behavior positively (Autio et al., 2001). The study by Cheah et al. (2015) found that consumers' comfort with a specific brand led them to pay premium prices despite the availability of lower-priced alternatives. Similarly, Jain et al. (2017) analyzed consumer buying behavior in India using TPB and found that attitude is a predictor of buying behavior for luxury fashion brands. In the context of this research, attitude refers to the attitude of Mauritian consumers toward the physical attributes (e.g., product quality, luxury brand image, atmosphere of luxury fashion stores, etc.) of luxury apparel. Based on the above statements, Hypothesis 1 (H1) is proposed:

H1: Attitude toward buying luxury fashion products has a positive impact on Mauritian consumers' buying intention toward luxury fashion products.

2.2.2 Subjective Norm

Subjective norms refer to the pressure individuals feel when engaging in a specific behavior (Mohammed et al., 2017; Ham et al., 2015; Wan et al., 2017; Jain, 2020). According to the TPB, subjective norms influence a person's behavioral intentions (Ajzen, 2006; Erul et al., 2020). For instance, individuals may purchase similar brands to their peers in the apparel industry to demonstrate a sense of belonging (Chan et al., 2012). Clothing, as a worldly asset, can be used to indicate connectedness and loyalty to a group with shared values (Wattanasuwan, 2005). Previous research has emphasized the role of social pressure in the consumption of luxury fashion brands (Eom et al., 2017; Sevtao et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2021; Cunningham et al., 2022). Building on these findings, the second hypothesis (H2) is proposed as follows:

H2: Subjective norm has a positive influence on Mauritian consumers' buying intention towards luxury fashion products.

2.2.3 Perceived Behavioural Control

Perceived behavioral control refers to an individual's perception of the ease or difficulty of performing a behavior (Ajzen, 2002; Rachbini, 2018). Consistent with TPB, a person's intentions and behavior can be predicted by their perceived behavioral control in executing the intended activity (La Barbera et al., 2021; Shin et al., 2020; Kashif et al., 2018). Perceived behavioral control represents an individual's confidence in their ability to perform a behavior, which influences actual behavioral performance (Lim et al., 2021; Ajzen, 2002). Research by Chetioui et al. (2020) revealed that perceived behavioral control is an intermediate precursor to consumers' intentions to purchase luxury brands. Similarly, Jain (2020) found a positive association between perceived behavioral control and luxury buying intentions. Salem et al. (2018) also demonstrated that perceived behavioral control significantly impacts consumers' purchasing intentions towards luxury apparel products. Based on these findings, the third hypothesis (H3) is proposed:

H3: Perceived behavioral control has a positive impact on Mauritian consumers' luxury apparel buying intention.

2.2.4 Brand Awareness

Brand awareness refers to consumers' ability to recognize a brand based on past experiences or prior exposure to brand cues (Keller, 1993; So et al., 2010). Consumers who attach importance to brands are often early identifiers of brands before making a purchase, and brands have a significant impact on their decision-making (Park et al., 2013). Wong et al. (1999) found that brand awareness substantially influences consumers' inclination to possess luxury products, as evidenced by their research conducted in Hong Kong.

Degen (2009) argued that luxury brands aiming to succeed in the Chinese market must achieve significant brand awareness. Wealthy Chinese buyers predominantly choose well-known luxury brands that fulfill their need for conspicuous consumption, even if it means paying a higher price for an unfamiliar brand in the Chinese market that is globally recognized. Rahman et al. (2020) suggested that apparel clothing retailers can enhance their business by targeting millennials and increasing brand awareness. Building on these discussions, the fourth hypothesis (H4) is proposed:

H4: Brand awareness positively influences the purchasing intention of Mauritian consumers towards luxury fashion products.

2.2.5 Status Acquisition

Status acquisition refers to the behavior of consumers purchasing, using, exhibiting, and consuming products or services to gain social status (Han et al., 2010; Phau et al., 2009). It is common for people to seek respect and recognition by spending their income on products that symbolize success and prestige in the eyes of others (Bronner et al., 2018; Eastman et al., 1999). Individuals employ various behavioral strategies to enhance their social standing, which can be derived from educational achievements, personal abilities, or individual characteristics (Nelissen et al., 2011). Additionally, physical attractiveness, as noted by Langlois et al. (2000), is often associated with elevated status on a global scale. Consequently, consumers may utilize fashion brands to align with their professional image or to display their societal position, effectively using the consumption of status-acquired products as a predictor of behavior (Malik et al., 2020; Fuchs et al., 2013). Furthermore, Fennis (2008) observed that when confronted with individuals displaying luxury brands, research subjects tend to adopt a submissive posture.

Previous studies have also emphasized the use of luxury fashion brand consumption as a means to signal social status (e.g., Fuchs et al., 2013; Nelissen et al., 2011). In the context of residents across the Island of Mauritius, social standing denotes an individual's position within the community, making it equally important (Jaunky et al., 2020). Based on these considerations, we propose the following hypothesis (H5):

H5: Status acquisition is positively associated with the buying intention of Mauritian consumers towards luxury apparel products.

2.2.6 Willingness to Pay Price Premium

Kempen (2004) argued that even financially disadvantaged individuals in developing nations, who struggle to afford basic necessities like food and accommodation, are willing to pay a premium for branded products. Price premium refers to the additional amount charged for a product or service, which exceeds the average price and is justified by the additional costs of manufacturing or providing the service (Singh et al., 2015; González-Rodríguez et al., 2019). As highlighted by Farris et al. (2010), price premium signifies the relatively higher price of products compared to similar alternatives. Luxury products often include a price premium, which manufacturers impose to gain a competitive advantage over rivals in the market (Rao et al., 1992; Kapferer et al., 2012; Gómez et al., 2018). Additionally, Zhang et al. (2013) noted that the willingness to pay a price premium reflects a buyer's desire to purchase a specific product regardless of its price, and Eastman et al. (2011) suggested that status-conscious consumers are less price-sensitive. Some individuals are so inclined to own branded clothing or luxury products that they are willing to pay a premium for these items (Nelissen et al., 2011). Based on these key findings, we propose the following hypothesis (H6):

H6: Willingness to pay price premium positively impacts Mauritian consumers' buying intention towards luxury fashion products.

2.4 Proposed framework

On the words of Mathieson (1991), TPB is a highly practical model since it outlines that consumer behaviour is governed by intention, and the latter (intention) is in turn forecasted by three major elements, specifically subjective norms, attitude in line with the behaviour as well as perceived behavioural control. Therefore, with respect to the hypotheses devised, this study will seek to apply TPB model as a baseline for developing the tailored framework, and hence these three additional constructs namely: brand awareness, status acquisition and willingness to pay premium price are incorporated into the model to further probe into additional underlying concepts which have the solid potential in governing purchasing intention of consumers towards luxury apparel brands in Mauritius (Figure 1).

Figure 1- Proposed Framework for this study

3. Methodology

This study employed a comprehensive research design and methodology to investigate the buying intentions of Mauritian consumers towards luxury fashion products. The following sections outline the key aspects of the research design, including sample size determination, sampling strategy, data collection techniques, questionnaire design, pilot testing, and response rate.

To ensure sufficient statistical power and representation, the sample size was determined using the online Raosoft sample size calculator. With a population estimate of 1,286,228 residents in Mauritius, a sample size of 385 respondents was suggested. To account for potential discrepancies, a total of 425 questionnaires were distributed for data collection.

A probabilistic sampling approach was adopted for this study. Simple random sampling was employed, giving every potential element in the population an equal chance of being selected. The selection process was conducted using a random number generator, ensuring independence between consecutive selections.

Data was collected through face-to-face and online surveys to maximize reach and diversity. Face-to-face surveys were conducted in shopping malls. A total of 115 questionnaires were administered to the general population during the end of year festive season.

In addition, online surveys were administered using Google survey forms to capture a wider and more heterogeneous sample. A total of 310 questionnaires were self-administered by participants, providing flexibility and convenience.

The questionnaire utilized in this study consisted of nine sections. These sections were carefully crafted based on a thorough review of the literature and incorporated key constructs of the modified TPB model. The questions were designed to capture relevant factors influencing consumers' buying intentions towards luxury fashion products.

To ensure the clarity and effectiveness of the questionnaire, a pilot testing phase was conducted. Twelve respondents, representing a heterogeneous sample, independently completed the questionnaires without researcher assistance. The feedback and insights gathered from the pilot testing phase were used to refine and improve the questionnaire's design.

Out of the initially distributed 425 questionnaires, a total of 408 valid responses were collected and included in the subsequent data evaluation and analysis. Face-to-face surveys yielded 109 valid responses, while the online surveys gathered 299 valid responses. The overall response rate of 96% indicated a high level of participant engagement and provided a robust and representative dataset.

4. Findings

4.1 Analysis of data

After gathering data during the surveys, the data must subsequently be analyzed. This is pivotal in order to ascertain that the researcher possesses relevant data for properly analyzing and comparing these data sets. In essence, data analysis may be perceived as an interactive procedure, whereby data are methodically examined and analyzed in order to yield an enlightening explanation of phenomena (Noble et al., 2014), for example the assessment of consumers towards buying luxury fashion products in Mauritius. For this study, data was analysed using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences).

4.2 Cronbach Alpha test

The reliability and validity test for this research was conducted by means of the SPSS Cronbach Alpha test. The Cronbach Alpha test was actually performed as an attempt for testing the reliability of the questionnaire utilized for collecting data. Table 1 below shows the outcome of the Cronbach Alpha test, and the value generated for the 28 products is 0.716 which is deemed as satisfactory.

Table 1: Cronbach Alpha test output.

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Products
.716	28

In practice, Cronbach's alpha values spanning in the range 0.70-0.95 have been viewed as reflecting good/satisfactory internal consistency (Korukcu et al., 2012; Utomo et al., 2015).

4.3.1 Demographic Profile of Respondents

Collecting background information of participants and portraying them in a systematic way is paramount for subsequent data analysis as well as inferential statistics. From the sample collected, it was observed that there were more females (267) than males (141) who partook the surveys (both on-site and online). The majority of respondents (208) were in the age group of 31-40 years old. The second most prevalent age group was 20-30 years and 108 participants formed part of this group. 10 individuals were less than 20 years old, 39 persons were 41-50 years old, 41 respondents avowed that they constitute the age group 51-60, and only 2 respondents were above 60 years old. Regarding the literacy level of respondents, the majority of participants proclaimed they had a Master degree/ MBA; specifically 24 males and 14 females. Respondents having various occupational status also have

varied salary scale. Precisely, 58 students possessed no income whilst only 8 students had $\leq$ Rs 10, 000 as income. For respondents who were employed, 5 of them had $\leq$ Rs 10, 000 as salary, 62 generated Rs 10,000-Rs 20,000 as wage, 89 had wages ranging Rs 20,000- Rs 30,000, 84 obtained an income of Rs 30,000-Rs 40,000 and only 2 participants acquired a wage greater than Rs 40,000.

4.4 Inferential Statistics

4.4.1 Application of Multiple Linear Regression and ANOVA

Multiple regression analysis had been applied for testing the association among various elements/attributes which impact consumer behaviour towards buying luxury fashion products in Mauritius. In tandem with Multiple Regression, ANOVA was also utilized for testing the various hypotheses for this study.

The following Model Summary Table (Table 2) has been generated after SPSS had run the test for linear regression.

Table 2: Model Summary Table

Model Summary^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.842 ^a	.748	.731	.695	1.910

a. Predictors: (Constant), COMPUTE CombinedConstructs1=SubjectiveNorms1 + Attitude1 + PerceivedBehaviouralControl1 + BrandAwareness1 + StatusAcquisition1 + WillingnessToPayPricePremium1

b. Dependent Variable: I will try to purchase luxury fashion products in future

As depicted by the Model Summary above, the value of $R^2 = 0.75$ (to 2 decimal places). This denotes the fact that when considered as a set, the following predictors (namely: Attitude, Subjective Norms, Perceived Behavioural Control, Brand Awareness, Status Acquisition, Willingness to Pay Price Premium) predict/explain 75% of the variance in the purchasing intention of luxury fashion consumers in the future.

R^2 is a mathematical measure in linear regression models which govern the degree of variance in the dependent variable which may be elucidated by the forecaster/independent variables. To put simply, R^2 values depict the degree of fit of data/goodness of fit in the regression model (CFI, 2022).

R^2 values spans in the range of 0-100%, whereby 0% denotes that the model fails to explain any variation in the outcome variable around its average whilst 100% denotes that the model is explaining all variations in the outcome variable surrounding its average. Moreover, the greater the R^2 values, the better the regression model will fit the observations (Frost, 2023)

Since $R^2 = 0.75$ (75 %) for this study, this value is perceived as having fairly high goodness of fit. On the words of Jeon et al. (2016), huge R^2 -values are indicative that the data possess minor severe deviations since R^2 -values are mathematical measures of the closeness of fit of data to the regression line.

Furthermore, the model was perceived in being significant, since the values emanating from the overall ANOVA table yielded the following outcome:

$$F(18, 384) = 64.87, p < .001, R^2 = .748$$

4.4.2 Hypotheses Testing 1

The hypotheses formulated for this study are tested as follows.

H1: Attitude towards buying luxury fashion products has a positive influence on Mauritian consumer's buying intention towards luxury fashion products. As per the following ANOVA table (Table 3), the following information may be extrapolated.

Table 3: ANOVA

		ANOVA ^a				
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	13.673	1	13.673	9.732	.002 ^b
	Residual	570.442	406	1.405		
	Total	584.115	407			

a. Dependent Variable: I will try to purchase luxury fashion products in future

b. Predictors: (Constant), COMPUTE Attitude1=LuxuryFashionProductsAre + MotivationInBuyingLuxuryFashionProducts

Since $p = 0.002$ ($p < .05$), H_0 is being rejected. Thus, it may be inferred that “attitude towards buying luxury fashion products” has an optimistic impact on Mauritian consumer’s buying intention towards luxury fashion products.

4.4.3 Hypotheses Testing 2

H_1 : Subjective norm has a positive influence on Mauritian consumers’ buying intention towards luxury fashion products.

Table 4: ANOVA

		Coefficients ^a				
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.358	.206		11.440	<.001
	COMPUTE SubjectiveNorms1=ExperiencingSocialPressure + HowCloseIndividualsImpact MyPurchase	.074	.024	.148	3.015	.003

a. Dependent Variable: I will try to purchase luxury fashion products in future

Since $p < 0.001$, we reject the null hypothesis, hence we conclude that Subjective norm has a positive influence on Mauritian consumers’ buying intention towards luxury fashion products.

4.4.4 Hypotheses Testing 3

H_1 : Perceived behavioural control has a positive influence on Mauritian consumers’ luxury apparel buying intention. As per the ANOVA table, since $p < .001$, there is rejection of H_0 . Hence, it is being inferred that Perceived behavioural control has an optimistic impact on Mauritian consumers’ luxury apparel buying behaviour.

Table 5: ANOVA

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.911	.389		4.917	<.001
	COMPUTE PerceivedBehaviouralControl1=QuantityOf FundsForBuyingLuxuryFashionProducts + EaseOfBuyingLuxuryFashionProducts + BuyingOfLuxuryProductsIsAchievable	.127	.047	.133	2.714	.007

a. Dependent Variable: I will try to purchase luxury fashion products in future

4.4.5 Hypotheses Testing 4

The fourth hypothesis for this study is crafted below:

H1: Brand awareness positively impacts the purchasing behaviour of Mauritian consumers towards luxury fashion products.

As per the ANOVA table, the following outcome is derived: Since $p < .001$, H_0 is again rejected, to eventually conclude that Brand awareness positively impacts the purchasing intention of Mauritian consumers towards luxury fashion products.

Table 6: ANOVA

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.934	.179		5.232	<.001
	COMPUTE BrandAwareness1=AwarenessOfLuxury FashionProducts + HowIBecameAwareOfLuxuryFashionPr oducts + EaseOfIdentificationOfLogos	.206	.017	.506	11.805	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: I will try to purchase luxury fashion products in future

4.4.6 Hypotheses Testing 5

The fifth hypothesis of this research is formulated as follows:

H1: Status acquisition is positively associated with the buying behaviour of Mauritian consumers towards luxury apparel products.

The hypotheses devised above are tested by means of ANOVA tests : Since $p < .001$, H_0 is yet again rejected, to arrive to the deduction that: Status acquisition is positively associated with the buying intention of Mauritian consumers towards luxury apparel products.

Table 7: ANOVA

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	253.865	1	253.865	312.094	<.001 ^b
	Residual	330.251	406	.813		
	Total	584.115	407			

a. Dependent Variable: I will try to purchase luxury fashion products in future

b. Predictors: (Constant), COMPUTE StatusAcquisition1=IBuyLuxuryProductsToAttainHigherStatus + BuyingLuxuryProductsMakeMeFeelValuable + IBuyLuxuryFashionProductsToBeRemarkable

4.4.7 Hypotheses Testing 6

For this study, the last hypothesis reads as follows:

H1: Willingness to pay price premium positively impacts Mauritian consumers' buying intention towards luxury fashion products. The output generated in the form of the ANOVA table is outlined below:

Table 8: ANOVA

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	115.234	1	115.234	99.780	<.001 ^b
	Residual	468.881	406	1.155		
	Total	584.115	407			

a. Dependent Variable: I will try to purchase luxury fashion items in future

b. Predictors: (Constant), COMPUTE

WillingnessToPayPricePremium1=WillingnessToPayPricePremium + ReasonForPayingHighPrice + AgreeableInPayingPricePremiums

Since $p < .001$, H0 is once again rejected, and the following inference stems: Willingness to pay price premium positively impacts Mauritian consumers' buying intention towards luxury fashion products.

This study was able to uncover significant relationships between various factors (attitude, subjective norm, perceived behavioral control, brand awareness, status acquisition, and willingness to pay price premium) and Mauritian consumers' buying intention towards luxury fashion products. These findings provide valuable insights for luxury fashion brands in Mauritius, allowing them to develop targeted CRM strategies that capitalize on these factors to enhance customer engagement, loyalty, and ultimately drive business success.

Implications for CRM:

Understanding Demographics:

Based on the demographic profile of respondents, CRM strategies can be tailored to specific customer segments. For example, by understanding that there are more female respondents than males, luxury fashion brands can develop targeted marketing campaigns and personalized communication strategies that resonate with female customers. Additionally, knowing the age distribution and income levels of respondents allows companies to customize their CRM efforts to suit the preferences and purchasing power of different customer segments.

Personalization and Customization:

The study highlights the importance of perceived behavioural control and willingness to pay a price premium. CRM can enable personalized and customized experiences by leveraging customer data. For instance, luxury fashion brands can use CRM systems to track individual customer preferences, purchase history, and brand interactions.

This data can be utilized to offer personalized product recommendations, customized promotions, and tailored shopping experiences, enhancing customer satisfaction and fostering long-term relationships.

Building Customer Relationships:

The findings of this study also emphasize the influence of social norms and subjective norms on consumer behaviour. CRM strategies can focus on building strong customer relationships by encouraging positive word-of-mouth and leveraging social influence. Luxury fashion brands can implement CRM initiatives that incentivize customers to share their experiences on social media or refer friends and family. By nurturing brand advocates and engaging customers through loyalty programs and exclusive events, companies can deepen customer relationships and foster brand loyalty.

Brand Awareness and Exclusivity:

The study highlights the positive impact of brand awareness on purchasing behaviour. CRM can contribute to building brand awareness by leveraging customer data to design targeted marketing campaigns. By segmenting customers based on their preferences and purchase history, luxury fashion brands can deliver personalized messaging that highlights the unique aspects of their products, reinforcing the brand's exclusivity and desirability.

Pricing Strategies:

The study also reveals the willingness of Mauritian consumers to pay a price premium for luxury fashion products. CRM can assist in effective pricing strategies by communicating the value proposition and craftsmanship associated with higher-priced items. Luxury fashion brands can use CRM systems to understand customer preferences and behaviours, enabling the development of loyalty programs and rewards that provide additional value to customers and reinforce the perception of exclusivity.

Customer Feedback and Engagement:

CRM systems play a crucial role in capturing and analyzing customer feedback. Based on the study findings, luxury fashion brands in Mauritius can use CRM to implement feedback mechanisms and actively listen to customer needs and preferences. By promptly addressing customer concerns and providing exceptional customer service, companies can enhance customer satisfaction and foster loyalty. CRM tools can also facilitate multi-channel engagement, allowing brands to interact with customers through social media, personalized messaging, and email, ensuring timely and relevant communication.

Data-Driven Decision Making:

The study emphasizes the importance of data analysis for understanding consumer behaviour. CRM systems provide a wealth of customer data that can be leveraged for data-driven decision making. Luxury fashion brands can utilize CRM analytics to identify trends, anticipate customer needs, and tailor their CRM strategies accordingly. By utilizing customer insights, brands can develop more effective marketing campaigns, targeted promotions, and personalized customer interactions, ultimately enhancing customer satisfaction and fostering long-term relationships.

5. Discussion

The study aimed to explore the relationship between consumer attitudes and buying behavior of luxury fashion products in Mauritius. The findings revealed that consumer attitudes significantly impact their purchasing intentions in this context. This aligns with previous research conducted by Rizkiansyah (2022) and Salem et al. (2018), which also found a positive association between attitudes and buying intentions of luxury brands.

The research employed a multiple linear regression (MLR) framework to analyze the data. The results, with a significance level of $p=0.002$, confirmed the influence of consumer attitudes on buying behavior. This suggests that consumers' positive attitudes toward luxury fashion products are likely to translate into actual purchases. Furthermore, the study found support in the works of Wantara (2022), Kumar et al. (2009), De Araújo et al. (2014), Bellman et al. (2009), Salem et al. (2018), and Rizkiansyah (2022), all of whom reported consistent results regarding the impact of attitudes on the buying intention of luxury apparel merchandise.

Another significant factor influencing buying behavior was subjective norm. The MLR model produced highly significant results ($p < 0.001$), indicating that subjective norm plays a role in shaping consumers' purchasing behavior of luxury fashion products. This finding is in line with Salem et al. (2018), who emphasized the importance of subjective norm as a precursor to buying intention in the luxury apparel industry. Similarly, Gao (2009) observed that subjective norm predicts the intention to buy luxury apparel products among consumers in China. Moreover, Lakmali et al. (2017) discovered a positive impact of subjective norms on consumers' luxury buying intention in Sri Lanka, specifically with regard to branded apparel merchandise.

Perceived behavioral control also emerged as a significant factor affecting consumers' buying behavior towards luxury apparel products. The statistical analysis yielded highly significant results ($p < 0.001$), suggesting that consumers' perception of control over their behavior plays a crucial role in their purchasing decisions. This finding aligns with Jain et al. (2017a), who found a strong positive association between perceived behavioral control and actual buying behavior of luxury apparel products among consumers in Delhi, India. Additionally, Salem et al. (2018) identified perceived behavioral control as a robust precursor to buying intention in the luxury apparel sector. However, the results of this study contradict the findings of Lakmali et al. (2017), where perceived behavioral control was not positively associated with the buying intention of consumers towards luxury apparel goods. Furthermore, Hamid (2018) reported no impact of perceived behavioral control on the buying intention of Generation Y consumers regarding luxury fashion branded goods. Similarly, Wantara (2022) found no substantial link between perceived behavioral control and buying intention of luxury apparel products among the consumers under investigation. These inconsistencies indicate the need for further research to fully understand the relationship between perceived behavioral control and buying behavior in the luxury fashion market.

Brand awareness emerged as another significant factor influencing consumers' buying behavior of luxury apparel products. The MLR analysis revealed a highly significant impact ($p < 0.001$) of brand awareness on purchasing intention. This finding is consistent with the existing literature. For instance, Janpors et al. (2023) found that brand awareness positively influenced the behavioral intentions of consumers towards luxury fashion outfits in Iran. Similarly, Lee et al. (2008) demonstrated that brand awareness acted as both a direct and indirect precursor to buying intention among Mexican college students when considering a US clothing brand. Moreover, Rahman et al. (2021) found that brand awareness mediated the relationship between brand awareness and millennials' buying behavior regarding branded fashion outfits. Kim et al. (2015) also reported a significant impact of brand consciousness on attitude and buying intention of luxury fashion products among US consumers.

The relationship between status acquisition and buying behavior was also explored. The MLR results indicated a significant correlation ($p < 0.001$) between status acquisition and consumers' purchasing intentions for branded fashion products in Mauritius. This finding is supported by Jaunky et al. (2020), who highlighted the importance of social positioning in Mauritius and the preference for luxury brands that reflect individuals' social status. Additionally, Zhang et al. (2013) observed that Chinese consumers pay close attention to luxury brands that are easily recognizable to display their social status. The study further revealed that status-conscious consumers, not only from the upper class but also from the middle class, purchase luxury apparel products to signal their belongingness to a higher societal status, even if it exceeds their economic conditions. Ali et al. (2016) emphasized that individuals perceive luxury products as status symbols and consume them to impress others. Moreover, Husain et al. (2022) found a positive impact of status consumption on the buying intention of Indian consumers, while Clark et al. (2007) highlighted the importance of status-conscious consumers adhering to societal norms.

Lastly, the study examined the influence of "willingness to pay a price premium" on buying behavior. The inferential statistics revealed a significant effect ($p < 0.001$) of consumers' willingness to pay a price premium on their purchasing intentions for branded apparel products. This finding is consistent with previous research conducted by Nelissen et al. (2011), Jain et al. (2017b), Nia et al. (2000) and Shin et al. (2016). These studies collectively suggest that consumers are willing to pay higher prices for luxury fashion products to signal their wealth, attain gratification, satisfy their desires and personalities, and align themselves with the perceived value of the brand. The results highlight the importance of effectively communicating the value and uniqueness of luxury brands to stimulate positive feelings and inclinations among consumers, thereby justifying higher price premiums.

The study provides valuable insights into the relationship between consumer attitudes and buying behavior of luxury fashion products in Mauritius. The findings demonstrate the significant influence of consumer attitudes, subjective norms, perceived behavioral control, brand awareness, status acquisition, and willingness to pay a price premium on consumers' purchasing intentions. These results contribute to a deeper understanding of consumer behavior in the luxury fashion market and have implications for marketers and brand managers. By considering these factors, marketers can develop targeted strategies to influence consumers' attitudes and ultimately drive their buying behavior.

6. Conclusion

Managerial Implications

Jaunky et al. (2020) avowed that a thorough elucidation of what governs the consumption behaviour of citizens in Mauritius will permit managers and researchers in formulating conceptual frameworks to assess the pivotal variables affecting such behavioural intention. Verily, the extended TPB framework applied in this study and the subsequent testing of hypotheses have yielded key insights which will garner considerable support to luxury fashion managers, shop owners or even retailers of luxury fashion shops in crafting conducive penetration and extension tactics in the local arena. Practical techniques have been suggested for marketers, retailers and even wholesalers in order to reap maximum benefits in the luxury fashion arena in Mauritius.

In the first instance, 'attitude' of consumers was shown to have an impact on the buying intention of consumers in Mauritius. On the words of Shen et al. (2003), attitude regarding buying outfits manufactured in the US is sufficient to forecast the buying intention of urban consumers. Correlating with the research of Phau et al. (2015), whereby the authors argued that more attention should be garnered towards consumers' perceptions and luxury brand proprietors must work in tandem with brand advertisers to fine-tune their brand image via diverse promotional schemes. Further observed by statistical findings, younger consumers have more optimistic attitude towards buying luxury fashion products. As similarly portrayed by the study of Sanya et al. (2014), the bulk of shoppers constitute younger citizens and since numerous firms are manufacturing fashion goods which are of supreme quality, same should be portrayed to clients in the advertising campaigns; whilst simultaneously targeting younger clients since they are more inclined towards buying luxury branded fashion products. Thus, the fashion goods must align with the actual preference and style of this targeted segment. Marketers may well elucidate how the youths are evaluating themselves and consequently devise marketing tactics to spur optimistic attitude regarding luxury brands (Arora et al., 2019).

Subjective Norm was also found to positively impact the buying intention of Mauritian consumers towards luxury apparel products as revealed by statistical outcomes. In the study of Salem et al. (2018), the robust affiliation between subjective norm and buying intention towards luxury fashion brands suggested the execution of marketing tactics regarding the luxury apparel brands in order to attain a better stance and for connecting with the targeted clients. Furthermore, in the research of Wantara (2022), subjective norm was found to impact the buying behaviour of luxury apparel goods by consumers and thus the authors proposed that marketers should consider the fact that consumers are influenced by significant persons in their lives when they are undertaking such buying decisions. Hence, marketers may well emphasize on societal approval and group belongingness instead of individual inclination or self-representation. In a similar vein, communication efforts may well be geared towards focusing on societal values instead of personal values.

Furthermore, perceived behavioural control was found to positively impact the buying behavioural intention of Mauritian consumers with respect to luxury branded fashion goods. As such, marketers should implement strategies which cater for perceived behavioural control positively (Abdullah et al., 2018). The outcomes derived from the study of Jain et al. (2017) also found that perceived behavioural control exerts a direct impact on consumers buying behaviour towards luxury apparel products, and this pinpoints to the fact that if consumers possess adequate resources in terms of money and financial means, they might undertake direct purchases of such goods.

What is more, findings from this study pinpointed that brand awareness in consumers eventually impact their purchasing behaviour towards luxury apparel goods. These outputs greatly reverberate with the results of Sharma et al., (2018) which depicted that younger consumers had greater brand awareness towards luxury products compared

to elderly consumers, and they usually conduct their research before their purchases, hence fashion wholesalers and marketers may well update their contents via fashion magazines and online display of celebrities' wardrobes.

Literature has extensively shed light between the association of status acquisition and buying behaviour of luxury fashion consumers, and similar associations have been proven in this research. The concept of luxury fashion brands may not be dissociated from costly, chic, classy, high-status, uncommonness and status (Kastanakis et al., 2012), hence the apparent implication is that the luxury fashion brand name enacts a pivotal function in consumer's buying behaviour, and in this regard, it is extremely vital for luxury apparel retailers to establish and sustain their national recognition of their brands. As per the findings of Kim et al. (2015), consumers were inclined in buying luxury apparel products in order to attain societal stance, reputation and influence, and hence, owing to this reasoning, the authors argued that such outcomes recommend that luxury apparel marketers must be additionally devoted towards elucidating the comparisons and dissimilarities of consumer values in divergent cultures so as to optimally position their branded fashion products in diverse markets.

Outcomes stemming from this study also encompasses the fact that willingness to pay price premium by consumers impact their purchasing behaviour towards luxury apparel products. Paralleling with the study of Phau et al. (2015), consumers were in fact agreeable in paying more for luxury outfits which are not manufactured in sweatshops, and hence luxury brand owners may well adopt this cue and consolidate their branding tactics through emphasis on brand uniqueness (Spiggle et al., 2012). Here, another interconnected tactic is for brand proprietors to enhance their brand superiority via the implementation of premium pricing, so as to compensate for the enhanced value the luxury fashion product offers.

Limitations of this study & direction for future research

This study has important implications for stakeholders in the luxury fashion industry. However, it is crucial to recognize that a "one size fits all" approach may not be applicable to all luxury fashion shops and outlets. Branded apparel retailers, owners, and marketers need to carefully consider the unique consumer attributes associated with luxury purchasing behavior in the diverse cultural and ethnic context of Mauritius to effectively respond to consumer demand.

The data collection period coincided with the festive season in Mauritius, including Christmas and New Year festivals. This may introduce bias as consumers, particularly those with disposable income, might be more inclined to use their year-end bonuses or gratuities to purchase luxury fashion products. Future researchers should explore different time frames to replicate this study and gain a comprehensive understanding of consumer behavior.

The coexistence of counterfeit branded fashion products alongside original branded goods is prevalent in Mauritius. However, this study did not specifically address the purchase of luxury branded counterfeit products. Further research should explore this aspect, as it is an important dimension within the context of Mauritius.

Lastly, this study applied an extended TPB model to assess consumer buying intentions for luxury apparel products in Mauritius, assuming that these intentions directly influence buying behavior. While previous studies support the relationship between buying intention and behavior, some studies have found a weak association between the two. Future research could explore the mediating effect of buying intention on the actual purchasing behavior of luxury branded products by Mauritian consumers. Investigating the link between buying intention and behavior can enhance our understanding of this relationship. Therefore, it is recommended that these concepts be further explored in future studies.

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AN EVALUATION OF TRAINING PERFORMANCE – A CASE STUDY OF PRADHAN MANTRI KOUSHAL VIKAS YOJANA IN BAGALKOT DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT:

Training programs enhances the skills and knowledge of the trainees. The rapidly changing global industrial scenario and technological advancements affects the training ecosystem periodical evaluation or assessment of training programs reveals the training program efficiency. In this backdrop, the study was undertaken with the basic purpose of reviewing the Pradhan Mantri Koushal Vikas Yojana in terms of its performance in Bagalkot District, Karnataka State. With a sample of 200 male and female beneficiaries of Pradhan Mantri Koushal vikas Yojana were selected for this study. To fulfill the aims of this study the author had identified dependent and independent variables and they were analyzed using appropriate statistical tools and techniques. The outcomes of the study will help the concerned people or authority to get more insights and background about the training effectiveness. While addressing the shortfalls, the study observations may contribute positively for the improvement of training program

KEY WORDS: training, PMKVY, performance, upscaling, infrastructure, pedagogy, skills, skill development, employability,

INTRODUCTION:

Within shorter period of time India is elevated to fifth position from tenth position in world strongest economy rankings. The journey was full of thrones and the threats like inflation, Corona, world economic slow down and melting of foreign reserves didn't stop India to become economically powerful country. The ambitious projects like Digital India, Make in India, Infrastructure development, road, railway and aviation development programs have created ample of employment opportunities. Along with these gigantic projects, multinational companies expansion strategies and India being most market potential country for FMCG, Electronic goods, Agricultural products, pharmaceutical products, Automobile industries, Telecommunication services and the stretching of FDI limits had welcome the companies with red carpet.

Whereas India with its poor skilled youth were unable to grab these golden opportunities. But still long time is waiting to utilize these offers. Post independence Central and state governments have put their efforts to improve the skill sets of the youth. Skill development programs and vocational training programs in the country have failed to increase the percentage of skilled labours and candidates across the country due to the improper design and implementation several programs. Now from 2015 to till, Pradhan Mantri Koushal Vikas Yojana a typical kind of training program is providing training programs in various job roles. Though the structure of training program is promising but the desired performance was not seen due to various factors.

This paper aims to measure the rate of skills acquisitions and determine the perception of the Trainees or Beneficiaries and to assess the Training performance of Pradhan Mantri Koushal Vikas Yojana in Bagalkot District. The success of the training program is dependent on its major components and proper implementation. This study has identified the dependent and independent variables, which will help in understanding the relationship and importance of these variables.

Skill acquisition, training infrastructure and training pedagogies are the prime parts of any training program, which can be used as indicators of training performance. Pradhan Mantri Koushal Vikas Yojana encompasses more on training infrastructure, that's the reason the training centres and training partners were selected wisely. The training pedagogy is also as per the contemporary industry norms but still needs improvement. The perception of trainees or

beneficiaries towards skill acquisition needs to be collected and reviewed. This paper makes sincere effort to bringout the ground realities of this training program.

REVIEW OF LITRATURE:

Khan, and Khan (2011): This paper concentrates on Training and development issues. The methods of training, training content and execution part of the training and its implications on overall organization performance. The author proposes that the effective training can be achieved by proper structure and scientific development of the skill development programs. the major purpose of this study was to identify how skill enhancing exercises will boost the employee performance in the organization. the data was collected and processed through descriptive statistics and parametric tests were conducted. Both primary and secondary data were used to analyse the results. the study concluded that, the prominent training method such as on the job training plays an important role in employee performance and also it is time and cost effective method.

Kumar (2018) : This paper highlighted about the skill development programs under skill india mission and Make in India program. The popular skill development programs like Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana, and Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Gramin Kaushal Yojana and their contribution in transforming Indian youth to Industry fit and employable were discussed. The paper with an important aim of understanding skill development programs and skill upgradation atmosphere in India. the leading training programs namely PMKVY, DDU-GKY (Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Gramin Kaushal Yojana), STEP (Support to Training and Employment Programme for Women), PMMY (Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana). were subject of the paper.

Misra (2015) : This paper focused on determining the rate of success of the goal i.e by 2022 mobilising cross together youth with fulpledge skills and competences. The paper aimed at investigating the training programs organized by NSDC and their efficacy level. The author was keen to observe the NSDC functioning with special reference to the skill development programs and their impact on employment and entrepreneurial activities in the country. The revamping of skill development programs and current frameworks of training programs were logically studies. The present industry environment and the threats posed on training programs are the hinderence for achieving the desired targets of the Authority.

Aggarwal (2016) : This paper highlighte on contemporary issues in skill development in India and problems faced by the skill development initiatives in India and strategic solutions for these issues and threats. the author meticulously observed the various elements like misalignment of requirements and availability of skilled human resources, locational disadvantages, training programs for women in India. the paper thrown light on the continues efforts of state and central government and private agencies in enhancing the skill enhancements and its contribution to the dveloping economy of the country.

Devi (2017) : This paper aimed at evaluating the ecosystem of skill development in India and the initiatives made in terms of programmes and policies that foster skill development. The study's primary goal was to make recommendations for a practical and structural response to the issue of India's existing and future workforce's severe shortage of critical skills and to be aware of the difficulties in skill development. The study looked at a number of variables, including national skill development and entrepreneurship policies. According to the national skill development mission and the skill India campaign, the notion of skill development has received widespread recognition, and several programmes and policies are being developed to introduce it not only in urban but also in rural areas.

Amegayibor (2021) : This paper concentrated on demographic factors influence on employee performance in Ghana Country. The important demographic factors like age, income, gender and occupation etc were considered for this interesting study. the author made a sincere attempt to measure the significance of the demographic factors like age and education on employee performance. This study determined the reason for absenteeism in the organization. From the findings it is crystal clear that age and department were the major reasons behind the continuous absenteeism in the organization. The other demographic factors were also studied and quantified in the process of ascertaining the employee performance in the organization.

Kanchan & Varshney (2015) ; This paper made an attempt to explore the skill development initiation and efforts, their impact on policy making and administrations in India. The paper was on the basis of exploratory study and existing literature were used to analyse the skill development scenario, the study revealed that more than 80% of Rural and Urban youth and working classes are lacking formal training and resulted in poor skill sets which is troubling them to focus on their jobs and it is affecting their job performance.

Bello et al (2013) ‘ This paper reviewed the significance of ICT in vocational and technical skill enhancements. A powerful country can be built only when the education and skill based training programs contribute to the growth. Now days the focus on employability skills are gaining more weightage and there is a requirement of upskilling the youth and workforce. The ancient and formal training programs are not enough to meet the expectations of present industries and job market. The applications of technology in all fields are preferring those candidates who are technically sound. The existing workforce and you may be able to handle the jobs but handling the jobs more effectively and efficiently candidates should possess the technical skills. Combination of several skills only get the job opportunities otherwise it will lead to unemployment problems in the country.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

Government of India launched several skill development programs; Pradhan Mantri Koushal Vikas Yojana is one among them. This PMKVY training program with its unique components attracted a large number of youths. To mobilize crores together youth for supplying to the industries is a Herculean job. The equations and formulae for the success of the industries and business are drastically changing. To meet these expectations and benchmarking MSME of India introduced PMKVY in 2015. After its inception, during these 8 years it has trained a large number of youths. Now it's right time to evaluate this training program performance, that's the reason behind choosing this research problem. It's an attempt to analyse and assess PMKVY .

OBJECTIVES:

1. To measure the Skills acquired by the Trainees or Beneficiaries of Pradhan Mantri Koushal Vikas Yojana in Bagalkot District
2. To ascertain the perception of the Trainees or Beneficiaries of Pradhan Mantri Koushal Vikas Yojana in Bagalkot District
3. To assess the Training performance of Pradhan Mantri Koushal Vikas Yojana in Bagalkot District

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Figure: Conceptual Model of the study

This study comprises of dependent and independent variables. The above figure shows that, Skill acquisitions, Training Pedagogy and Training Infrastructure are the independent variables and the Training Performance is the Dependent variable. the study was conducted to establish the relationship among these variables. Which helps in determining the significance of these elements in a training Program.

Data Collection Methods

Secondary Data: Research Journals, Government department websites, thesis, dissertations, Magazines and Newspapers were used to gather information about Training and Pradhan Mantri Koushal Vikas Yojana.

Primary Data Sources : Structured questionnaire with interview method is adopted to collect first hand information.

Research Design: Exploratory and Descriptive Research Designs were used for this study. Both research designs helped in stating the research problem and analyzing the results.

Sample Size: 200 PMKVY Trainees and beneficiaries from Bagalkot District

Sampling Method: Random Sampling Method

Sample frame: Trainees list provided by various Pradhan Mantri Koushal Vikas Kendra Bagalkot District

Sample Element: Beneficiaries and Trainees of Pradhan Mantri Koushal Vikas Yojana in Bagalkot District.

Sample Units: Bagalkot, Badami, Hungund, Bilagi, Mudhol, Jamakhandi, Teradal, Banahatti and Rabakavi, Guledgudda of Bagalkot District.

Sample Extent: Bagalkot District only

Research Instrument: A structured questionnaire with close ended questions were drafted and Likert scale, Dichotomous, Multiple questions were used to gather the information from the respondents.

Need for the Study: Training programs are the essential part of Human Resource Development. Training adds value to the existing performance of the Human resources. Skill enhancement and knowledge upgradation is possible through periodical training programs.

The framework of the training programs plays a vital role in transformation of a person to skilled and capable human resource. Continuous improvement in the framework will help in increasing the training performance, keeping this in mind the study on evaluation of training performance of PMKVY was selected. This study will contribute to the existing knowledge base.

Limitations of the Study

- The study is confined to Bagalkot District only
- Time and Cost were the major constraints for this study
- The selected sample is small as compared to the population.

ANALYSIS & FINDINGS:

Hypothesis of the Study

1. H1: There is a significant influence of Training Infrastructure on Training performance

Table shows the summary of findings

Hypothesis	Regression weights	Beta Coefficient	R ²	F	t-value	p-value	Hypothesis Supported
H1	SA → TP	0.607	.402	133.246		0.000	yes

Analysis: The hypothesis tests if Training Infrastructure provided as significant impact on Respondents Training performance, the dependent variable Respondents Training performance was regressed on predicting variable, $F(1,198), p < 0.001$, which indicates that the Training Infrastructure provided in shaping Respondents Training performance ($b = 0.607, p > 0.001$). These results clearly direct the positive effect of Training Infrastructure provided, moreover the $R^2 = 0.402$ depicts that the model explains 40% of the variance in Respondents Training performance.

2. H1: There is a significant influence of Training Pedagogy on Training performance

Table shows the summary of findings

Hypothesis	Regression weights	Beta Coefficient	R ²	F	t-value	p-value	Hypothesis Supported
H1	TPG → TP	0.755	.628	334.338		0.000	yes

Analysis: The hypothesis tests if Training Pedagogy provided as significant impact on Respondents Training performance, the dependent variable Respondents Training performance was regressed on predicting variable, $F(1,198), p < 0.001$, which indicates that the Training Pedagogy provided in shaping Respondents Training performance ($b = 0.755, p > 0.001$). These results clearly direct the positive effect of Training Pedagogy provided, moreover the $R^2 = 0.628$ depicts that the model explains 62% of the variance in Respondents Training performance.

3. H1: There is a significant influence of Skill acquisition on Training performance

Table shows the summary of findings

Hypothesis	Regression weights	Beta Coefficient	R ²	F	t-value	p-value	Hypothesis Supported
H1	TI → TP	0.686	.434	162.007		0.000	yes

Analysis: The hypothesis tests if Skill acquisition as significant impact on Respondents Training performance, the dependent variable Respondents Training performance was regressed on predicting variable, $F(1,198), p < 0.001$, which indicates that the Skill acquisition in shaping Respondents Training performance ($b = 0.686, p > 0.001$). These results clearly direct the positive effect of Skill acquisition, moreover the $R^2 = 0.434$ depicts that the model explains 43% of the variance in Respondents Training performance

CONCLUSION:

The study can be concluded that, The Skill acquisitions are having significant effect on the training performance. Thus PMKVY training policy makers can concentrate on this skill acquisition aspect and can be reformed by taking necessary actions. The second hypothesis training pedagogy is also having significant impact on training performance. PMKVY is a well structured training program and the important factor training pedagogy can be updated periodically and advanced techniques, methods can be included in the curriculum. The third variable Training infrastructure is also significantly influences the training programs, PMKVY follows strict regulations in selecting training partners and training centres with special reference to training infrastructure, till there is scope for continuous improvement of training infrastructure as and when the trainees desires.

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IMPACT OF SERVICE QUALITY AND SECURITY ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION: THE CASE STUDY IN PRIVATE BANKS OF ERBIL-KURDISTAN REGION

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ABSTRACT

The research aims to discover the impact of service quality and security on customer satisfaction. Service quality is how well a bank provides its services compared to its customer expectations. Customers have certain expectations about how well they are going to receive the services. The study is quantitative in nature. Primary data has been collected from 120 customers of Private Banks such as RT Bank, Cihan Bank, Albaraka Bank, KIB Bank, and Byblos Bank in the Kurdistan region of Iraq. The collected data was analyzed using “Statistical Package for Social and Sciences (SPSS)” version 26. The statistical tools include descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. The findings concluded that there is a significant effect and relationship between service quality, security, and customer satisfaction. The study recommends the security of the bank has an important impact on the customer satisfaction as customers can feel assured and confident that their money or belongings are in a safe place

Keywords: Service Quality, Security, Customer Satisfaction, Private Banks in Kurdistan, Iraq

Introduction

The financial services industry has also advanced in tandem with these advances as a result of the extension of available services brought about by technical progress, which has led, among other things. This has resulted in more competition in the industry as a consequence of the emergence of a great number of banks and other financial institutions that are owned by private parties. This research is highly significant because of the ever-increasing worry about security risks. There is a need for increased understanding about concerns about security, particularly its link with customer satisfaction and how the best institutions can supply it via security (Ahmad et al., 2010). The satisfaction of consumers is highly significant since it has various advantages in addition to maintaining the contentment of the customers themselves. The bank itself may gain from satisfied clients who sell the bank's services to other potential customers. In addition, the contentment of consumers may also lead to an increase in profitability, provided that existing customers continue to appreciate the services provided. Customers who are satisfied with the services provided by the bank will continue to use those services and, in time, will lose interest in the products and services provided by rival bank. They went on to say that this also boosted the overall performance of the company. One of the ways that businesses may win the pleasure and continued business of their customers is by making certain that the level of service that they provide is of an exceptionally high standard.

Significance of the Study

Several studies have been conducted on the level of satisfaction felt by customers. This is due to the fact that it is important to the banks of the majority of companies. Within the realm of private banking, there is an urgent need to investigate the factors that led to the genesis of pleased clients and to identify the factors that are responsible for the contentment of those consumers. The financial services industry has also advanced in tandem with these advances as a result of the extension of available services brought about by technical progress, which has led, among other things. Therefore researchers feel that the financial services industry will benefit from the findings of this study. Therefore this study will help the banks to make better decision on how to keep their current clients and win over new one. So when their customers stay with them because of their good security and quality of their services, they will have a good reputation and more new customers are able to purchase their services which offered for them, on other side it will lead the banks have more profitability and efficiency and be continued. Security and protection of customer's information is very important, especially in the banking sector, which is due to this advanced technology for the banking sector and the banking sector has grown, so there is not enough security and they use online

methods which can cause problems and reduce the safety of transactions (Belás et al., 2016).

Definition of terms

Service Quality

All the researches on service quality have shown that good service transfer and high quality will result in customer satisfaction. Therefore, you need to make customers satisfied with the quality you provide and make them think that the service you provide is better than other services and they will benefit more from it (Brodie, 2009). Once they have that feeling, they decide how and to what extent the service can help them. It is also pointed out that a bank wants to be a good competitor with the quality of services provided. On the other hand, it is said that the quality of the services provided depends on what the customer wants to be offered and what is offered by the bank (Ahmad et al., 2010).

Security

If we look at oxford dictionary it defines security as it is a situation that there is a possibility of being threatened, and security is when people are assured of the security they have and feel safe by their state government. This feel of assurance is essential, and important to have and to feel secure in the banking sector. (Waheed, Khan, & UI-Ain, 2013).

Customer Satisfaction

Customer Satisfaction is a feeling that it might be changed according to how will the bank meets their expectations, in other words customer satisfaction is how happy the clients is with the performed service quality and security (Johnson, 2001).

Literature review

This study (Raja, Saleem, & Sarfraz, (2014) aimed to research on how happy customers were with Kenyan commercial banks. They focused on how the quality of financial services impacted customer satisfaction. They said that improving the quality of service made customers happier. They also highlighted that the quality of the service is determined not just by the individual's previous experience but also by his or her expectations. They came to the conclusion that the two aspects of quality that had the greatest impact on the level of happiness a client felt were dependability and empathy. They suggested that banks also focus on responsiveness and other characteristics since it was discovered that Kenyan banks lacked these qualities.

Gyabi and Shrivastava (2016) carried out research on the issue of safety in Ghana's rural banking industry. The researchers noted that security exists to preserve data and prevent unwanted information from being accessed, and that it is the role of management to make choices pertaining to data security. According to the findings of their research, a significant proportion of rural financial institutions do not make full use of information and communication technologies. They suggested raising the level of awareness among employees to emphasize the need for maintaining data security.

In view of Munir and Marnavi (2018) looked at information security as well as risk management in India's banking industry. They added that because of all of the security risks and the danger of security vulnerabilities, it is imperative that the financial institutions put into place methods for risk analysis, prevention, as well as mitigation, and generally enhance their risk management. They also said that weaknesses should be investigated and found on a regular basis in order to guarantee that robust and efficient controls are put in place to ensure that the number of potential security risks is kept to a minimum.

In the Study of Subrahmanyam et al., (2014), they argued that the deployment of efficient data safety measures required the creation of vulnerabilities in the system, often known as "loopholes." Despite the fact that both operational and technological controls were put into place, the researchers discovered that there was a widespread absence of an information security culture among the five banks that they employed for their Study.

Paul, Mittal, & Srivastava, (2016), tried to find out if there was a link between how happy clients is with their banking experience and whether or not they want to switch from traditional banking to online banking. They discovered that

there was a substantial association between consumer happiness and security and the desire to switch to online banking and concluded that there was a correlation between the two. They discovered inverse relationships between levels of satisfaction with online banking and levels of contentment with customers' inclinations to switch banks.

Anwer, (2018), carried out research with the objective of contrasting the levels of customer service and satisfaction in the public and private sectors in India. The author suggested enhancing the quality of services offered as well as raising awareness about the advantages of using the internet for banking and obtaining help from the government.

Methodology

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between service quality and security with respect to customer satisfaction?
2. What is the effect of service quality and security on customer satisfaction?

Research Objectives

1. To investigate the connection between service quality and security with respect to customer satisfaction.
2. To investigate the effect of service quality and security on customer’s satisfaction.

Sample size

The study used the private banks in Erbil and from them it chooses 5 private banks. As well, the study has 120 research samples. These private banks in the Kurdistan region include RT bank, Cihan bank, Albaraka bank, KIB bank and Byblos bank. There are more other private banks in the Kurdistan region but we only collected data from these five banks because they are more popular. The sample includes 24 customers from RT bank, 28 from Cihan bank, 22 from Albaraka bank, 23 from KIB bank, and 23 from Byblos bank. That brings the total to 120 customers who answered the questionnaire.

Sampling technique

Judgmental sampling technique is a method of non-probability sampling in which individuals in the sample are selected solely on the basis of the researcher's prior information and their own personal opinion. Or picking a team from which to collect data on the basis of one's own personal view as to what constitutes a representative sample of the population that is being investigated. For instance, judgmental sampling can include selecting a lot of knowledgeable individuals from a variety of various social groups and questioning them about their concerns (Perla, 2012).

Statistical tools of analysis

The statistical tools used to analyze the data include Cronbach’s Alpha, averages, standard Deviation, Correlation and Regression

Analysis of data

Cronbach’s Alpha

Reliability statistics	
Cronbach’s Alpha	N of Items
.865	26

Based on Cronbach’s Alpha, the data collection is strongly reliable because the value is more than 0.75 which is equal to = .865 on those items related to those questions of independent and dependent variables. (Perry R. Hinton, Isabella McMurray, Charlotte Brown, 2004)

Descriptive Statistics

Section A: Service Quality and Security
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#	Items	Valid	Mean	Min	Max
1	The bank has modern and attractive equipment	120	3.66	4.00	4
2	The material such as brochures, handouts etc that are related to the service are pleasing to the eye.	120	3.98	4.00	4
3	This bank offers a wide range of products and services to its customers	120	4.15	4.00	4
4	Bank staff responds to customers even during busy period.	120	3.88	4.00	4
5	Customers are updated on the status of their transactions after each one that takes place at the bank.	120	3.82	4.00	4
6	This bank provides services that are prompt and effective.	120	3.91	4.00	4
7	Makes good on its promise to complete a task by a specific deadline.	120	3.97	4.00	4
8	Carries out the task correctly the first time.	120	3.82	4.00	4
9	There is a match between services advertised and services delivered.	120	4.00	4.00	4
10	This bank gives assurance of safety to my funds.	120	3.88	4.00	4
11	The staff is very good at what they do, and I can't lose control of my transactions for anything.	120	3.97	4.00	4
12	The bank keeps customers private information confidential.	120	4.03	4.00	4
13	There are backup plans for this bank with respect to safety of funds	120	3.76	4.00	4
14	This information that has been provided by this bank is reliable.	120	4.21	4.00	5

Section B: Customer Satisfaction

#	Items	Valid	Mean	Min	Max
1	The reception desk of the bank is pleasing to the eyes.	120	3.75	4.00	4
2	Physical appearance of the bank staff is appealing.	120	3.95	4.00	4
3	This bank has availability of parking spaces, ease of access, and overall site convenience.	120	4.09	4.00	4
4	The bank staff is polite and considerate.	120	3.88	4.00	4
5	Bank staff has the necessary knowledge to answer your questions.	120	3.92	4.00	4
6	The employees at the bank are happy to address any inquiries or issues raised by customers.	120	4.07	4.00	4
7	The bank responds to varied needs of the customers	120	3.60	4.00	4

In the descriptive analysis we can see that the valid shows how many people have answered as shown 120 people answered. The mean display the range of the answers, Our questions are scaled from poor to excellent and the mean gives us the range of where the answer stands on this scale. Either on the poor side or the excellent side. The mode

is how many times answer has been repeated. The max is the highest value and the min is the lowest. Also the average of each questions answer is also displayed.

Correlation

		Service quality and security	Customer satisfaction
Service Quality and security	Pearson Correlation	1	.694**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	120	120
Customer satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	0.694**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00	
	N	120	120

According to the above table, the relationship between the variables was analyzed using correlation analysis. The analysis is showing that there is a positive moderate correlation between the independent and the dependent variable, therefore, the service quality is along with the customer satisfaction is showing 0.694 and this indicate that there is a significant correlation (according to the significance number Sig = 0.000) and it is showing that the result now is less than 0.01.

Findings & Conclusion

Question one in the research (what is the relationship between service quality and security and customer satisfaction?) after analyzing this questions in the questionnaire related to it using IBM SPSS (Correlation analysis) the dependent variable has a positive moderate correlation with the independent variable, therefore the service quality and security with the customer satisfaction showed a result of 0.694 and it also showed a significant correlation (Sig = 0.000) which in this case it was less than 0.01. it means enhanced service quality and security leads to customer satisfaction

Research questions two (what is the effect of service quality and security on customer's satisfaction?) After using primary data to analyze the question, the result shows the importance of service quality and security and there is a significant in the regression analysis which it was lower than 0.01, while the impact of the independent variable on the dependent variable showed 0.802, this refers that the independent variable has an impact on the dependent variable

As a conclusion, relying on the correlation analysis and the other data that was analyzed together, we can conclude that the dependent variable has a positive Pearson correlation with the independent variable, so we can conclude that both the service quality and security along with the customer satisfaction both of them equal 0.694 which is 69.4%, there is also a significance in the correlation analysis which the result was less than 0.05.

Relying on the linear regression analysis that was used to analyze primary data we can agree that the service quality and security along with customer satisfaction have a significant outcome within Kurdistan region the hypothesis showed a positive result which is R=0.694. Nevertheless, there is a significant level which it was less than 0.01 in this case.

As a result of analyzing all those questions by the researcher it is agreed that there is a huge importance of the service quality and security on customer satisfaction within banks in Kurdistan region and the support and slice in the relationship between them and its effect on each other in other words the better the quality of the service and

security of banks in Kurdistan the higher the customer satisfaction.

Recommendations:

As researchers, there are a few recommendations that can be used by banks to improve their customer satisfaction. Starting with conducting professional training program about how to behave with the customer, the staff of the bank needs improvement in dealing with customers as communications should be done in a professional way.

The service quality refers to how the customers are being serviced inside the bank and how the staff is trying to fill their needs, this lies in easing their bank account procedures or borrowing or even while leasing as those things can increase the customer satisfaction.

The security of the bank has an important impact on the customer satisfaction as customers can feel assured and confident that their money or belongings are in a safe place.

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THE GOVERNANCE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN MEDICAL EDUCATION.

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Abstract:

Glancing at the Sustainable Development Goals 2030, Goal 4 aims to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education for all. However, digital technologies have emerged as essential to achieve this goal, and the technologies have shown a powerful impact on the Medical education system. The recent COVID-19 Pandemic has further institutionalized the applications of digital technologies in medical education & these digital technologies have made a paradigm shift in the entire Medical education system. It is not only a knowledge provider but also a co-creator of information, a mentor, and an assessor. Technological improvements in medical education have made life easier for students. Instead of using pen and paper, students nowadays use various software and tools to create presentations and projects. When compared to a stack of notebooks, an iPad is relatively light. When opposed to a weighty book, surfing an E-book is easier. These methods aid in increasing interest in research too. Thus this paper briefly discusses the need for digital technologies in medical education and its significant applications and challenges.

The paper also studies the advantages and disadvantages of digital technologies in medical education and emerges some points that can be used as a blueprint criterion for Medical Institutions.

Research methodology: Drafting a questionnaire based on those mentioned above analyzing the data.

Keywords: Digital Technologies, Medical Education, Globalization, Pandemic, Health Care.

Introduction:

"The two areas that are changing are digital technology & Medical Technology. Those are the things that the world will be very different twenty years from now than it is today." - Bill Gates.

Higher education institutions have invested for years in technology implementations, including Medical Education. When implemented in medical education, some promising examples of digital technologies have synergistically initiated positive outcomes. Gone are the days when the Medical education sectors used traditional methods. With a rapid technological transformation, digital technology has also contributed prominently to medical education. When COVID-19 disrupted the world, digital technology was used as a medium to teach. Because of the pandemic complexity, the role of doctors was crucial. In a country like India, where the number of cases doubled daily, the healthcare sector faced a shortage of Doctors & nursing staff. Though the primary goals of medical education are to learn the information needed for patient care (information acquisition) and to grow a professional identity within the medical community (community development), the traditional modes of education were not serving during the pandemic, In such situations, digital technology served the cause by teaching online. Also, educational systems suddenly shifted to e-teaching, with entire courses delivered online to maintain learning continuity during this situation. In the current scenario, Digital transformation has become inseparable from education, and its implementation has broadly increased due to the increased acceptance of e-learning since the pandemic. Although we are in a very technologically advanced world, students' willingness to adopt digital technology in education and academic literacy was not assured. Not all students were equally prepared for sudden transformations in technology and digital learning. Unlike previous eras of education over e-teaching, the potential of e-teaching in medical education has made this era significantly different because of the following three forces

1. Instead of using pen and paper, students nowadays use various software and tools to create presentations and projects.

2. An iPad is relatively light compared to a stack of notebooks.
3. Unlike a weighty book, surfing an e-book is easier. At the same time, these methods also aid in increasing interest in research among students. Thus this paper briefly discusses the need for digital technologies in medical education and its significant applications and challenges. The paper also studies the advantages and disadvantages of digital technologies in medical education and emerges some points that can be used as a blueprint criterion for Medical Institutions.

The Rationale of the Paper:

Since the paper is the bridge between two vital components (Digital technology & Medical Education), the paper explores the following justifications:

- I. Medical Education through Digital Technology.
- II. Impact of E-Learning in Medical Institutions.

Medical Education through Digital Technology:

Using digital technology aids has led to boosting medical students' engagement by acclimatizing to the dynamic and exhaustive medical curriculum in the best way possible in the unprecedented times of COVID-19. It has also made the teaching-learning process student-centric, highly personalized, without any restriction of age, learning capacity, and learner experience, which has been made possible due to online conferences via various apps in collaboration with the leading institutes all across the globe. Adopting digital technology has bridged the gap between the student and the teacher. It is also a way of uniformly standardizing the teaching method for undergraduate and postgraduate students; the topics are taught under the competency-based medical education (CBME) curriculum in the medical colleges of India. Implementing the medical education system with digital technology methods has created newer avenues of teaching and learning methods by making it more student-friendly and facilitating student learning at their own pace and capacity of learning. It has transformed a student from a recipient to a self-directed Learner, where the faculty facilitates the learning process. With an excess of apps like WhatsApp, Telegram, MEDISAGE, TedEx, NPTEL, and other apps for learning at reputed institutes, a medical student has easy access to e-books, online conferences, and online courses with no restrictions of time constraints, and the medical students can learn according to their comfort in a personalized manner. This has helped update the latest skills and credentials under the continuing medical education of practicing medical professionals and their usual medical practice. Integrating computer-assisted learning with a conventional teaching format improves students' understanding and performance, providing maximum accuracy.

Impact of E-Learning in Medical Institutions:

In the current scenario, the environment in which medical students learn today vastly differs from 20 years ago when the Internet was not such a dominant tool in medical education. Medical Institutions worldwide increasingly utilize E-learning platforms and comprise adaptive tutorials, audiovisual clips, and virtual models. These educational media possess several distinct advantages over traditional didactic models of instruction, including the ability to update the material promptly to ensure delivery of the latest evidence-based content to trainees. E-learning has been demonstrated to be as effective as conventional didacticism and can be used to foster self-directed learning. It encourages medical students to control their learning more by allowing flexibility over content and pace. In such models, educators can evaluate competencies objectively through online assessments, enabling students to receive personalized feedback for self-improvement. E-learning will undoubtedly significantly impact the environment in which future medical students learn. The gradual shift towards e-learning is seen as a catalyst for applying adult learning theory, which will see more medical educators taking on the role of facilitator and assessor of competency. Most medical students view e-learning as enjoyable and effective but, interestingly, do not see it replacing traditional didactic methods. Indeed, e-learning often complements instructor-led methods in a blended approach. Studies on nursing and medical students have demonstrated that satisfaction is consistently higher in a blended learning environment compared with a traditional lecture setting. However, this satisfaction is not correlated with test scores, where there is often no significant difference between the two pedagogic approaches. Further research is needed to establish the role of blended learning in medical education. Medical educators should continue to engage with e-learning in an effort to come up with innovative approaches to train medical students. As a researcher, I can attest that new educational methods are always appreciated and have the potential to provide better engagement compared with traditional didacticism.

Review of Literature:

A five-step research method process for literature review was adopted for the study, which is shown below table:

Steps	Step Definition	Step Elaboration
Step 1	Research criteria clarification.	Only relevant sources were taken into consideration.
Step 2	Literature search.	Scopus, Semantic Scholar, Research Gate, Google Scholar, and Academia.edu databases were searched.
Step 3	Literature filtering.	Manual screening of relevant articles.
Step 4	Selected articles analysis.	Content evaluation and selection.
Step 5	Illustration of fundamental research results and implications.	Data analytics and statistical representation.

Rice (2003) defines digital technologies as a wide range of technologies, tools, services and applications that use different types of hardware and software. These technologies facilitate service provision and activities using electronic means for the creation, storage, processing, transmission, and information display. Rumanyika and Galan, (2015) posit that the work done by digital technologies at HEIs includes developing course content, sharing and delivering the same course content using techniques such as PowerPoint presentations, communication between learners, instructors, teachers as well as the world outside their immediate environment, academic research, and administrative support including student enrollment. It is important to get clear definitions of phrases related to digital technology. The table below gives a forwarded summary of several definitions of these phrases:

Summary of Key Concepts in Digital Technology and their suggested definition:

	Author(s)	Definition	Remarks/commend
1	Wade (2019)	Digital Technology is fundamentally about change and involves people, processes, strategies, structures, and competitive dynamics.	It is an all-encompassing process that requires active participation.
2	Riemer <i>et al.</i> , (2019)	Digital disruption is defined as the changes facilitated by digital technologies that occur at a pace and magnitude that disrupt established ways of value creation, social interactions, doing business and more generally, our thinking.	Pace and magnitude are important for the transformation.
3	Zhao, <i>et al.</i> , (2020)	The realignment of, or new investment in, technology and business models to engage digital customers more effectively at every touch point in the customer experience lifecycle. Companies needed to think of DT as a “formal effort to renovate business vision, models, and investments for a new digital economy.	Meeting digital customers at their point of need and brings about re-engineering of business processes, be it service environment or manufacturing.
4	Benavides <i>et al.</i> , (2020)	DT goes well beyond de-materialization of processes, encompassing an innovative use of new technologies (cloud, social, mobile, and analytics) to promote new services, re-define business models, and innovative interactions with its users.	Taking advantage of latest developments like cloud computing is important in HEI environments. Content creation is vital.
5	Benavides <i>et al.</i> , (2020)	DT of the university education system should have a broader focus and must include the modernization of corporate	While embracing DT, it is important to think about the infrastructure and curriculum and

		IT architecture management, which could provide an important contribution to structuring the efforts of innovation in education.	subsequently match them.
6	Benavides <i>et al.</i> , (2020)	The modern developments in the area of modernizing educational system with the aid of ITC technology and applied process thinking principles in the attempt to capture and model interrelated activities required to integrate digital technologies in teaching, learning, and organizational practices.	Design of curriculum should consider learning outcomes and the available infrastructure.
7	Benavides <i>et al.</i> , (2020)	DT is an accelerated evolution. It is also revolution because of its radical and structural implications for people as for infrastructure that also requires new educational and business models.	Like any other business facets, DT is radical if it must remain valid.
8	Benavides <i>et al.</i> , (2020)	Digital business transformation can be defined as the modification of business processes, procedures, capabilities and policies to take advantage of the changes and opportunities presented by new digital technologies, as well as the impact they have on society, while always thinking about current and future trends.	Opportunities must be quickly embraced while still being futuristic.

Research Methodology:

The research was carried out in the constituent college of BLDE(DU), to explore the paper’s objective. The research methodology used here was the exploratory method. After the pilot survey, a well-designed questionnaire was drafted and given to some teaching staff members & MBBS PG students. I have arrived at the following analysis and conclusions from the tabulated and analyzed data (on a percentage basis).

- Sample size** : 100.
- Sampling Technique** : Quota Sampling. (50 UG students, 50 PG students)
- Data Collection Procedure** : Questionnaire technique through Google forms.

Google Form Link:

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSc-Tp8U3sTceVA74zraK-3kB3GDEmWqrH-PINsvneP50IFKMg/viewform?usp=pp_url

Objective of the study :

The present study aimed to understand medical students’ general readiness for e-learning and computer technology. The objectives of the study were

1. To evaluate computer anxiety and digital readiness among medical students.
2. To investigate the relationship between computer concerns and digital technology.
3. To determine the socio-demographic factors associated with students’ computer concerns and digital readiness.
4. To determine whether a significant association exists between computer concern and digital readiness and students’ perceptions of academic performance in an e-learning environment.

: Diagrammatic presentation of the data collected and analyzed:

1. Chart displaying response towards “Digital Technologies are Influencing Medical Education.”

2. Chart displaying response towards “Implementing Digital Technologies in Medical Education adds greater scope for the students to uplift their clinical skills.”

3. Chart displaying response towards “To what extent do Digital Technologies in Medical Education adds greater scope for the students to uplift their clinical skills.”

4. Chart displaying response towards “Implementing Digital Technologies in Medical Education will reduce learning errors by Medical Students.”

5. Chart displaying response towards “Implementing Digital Technologies in Medical Education will modify the traditional teaching method in the future?”

6. Chart displaying response towards “During the pandemic, Online teaching mode was preferred in Medical Education. Did this mode work out well ?.”

7. Chart displaying response towards “Has the use of computer-assisted learning and virtual case presentation made it possible to learn & reinforce the concepts of medical education with absolute accuracy?”

8. Chart displaying response towards “In medical education, Compared to the traditional teaching method, do you feel online teaching with digital technologies is ethically correct?”

9. Chart displaying response towards “Have you experienced clinical training/case-based discussions through online teaching.”

10. Chart displaying response: “In the current medical education scenario, Which of the following is a suitable textbook for reading?”

11. Chart displaying response towards “ Which is a suitable classroom model in the current medical education scenario?”

- a. Flipped classroom Model with E-books, Slides, Videos, and Podcasts.
- b. Traditional classroom Model with Chalk & talk concept.

12. Chart displaying response towards “In the current medical education scenario, has the educational research on live stream lectures strengthened the research quotient?”

13. Chart displaying response: “In the current medical education scenario, is live-stream teaching benefiting the students?”

14. Chart displaying response towards “Is digital learning necessary for the career professional development in medical education?”

15. Chart displaying response towards “Do you feel that Digital technology in medical education is designing innovative teaching methods to meet the needs of medical education?”

Independent Variable: Digital Technology.

Dependent Variable: Medical Education

H₀: Digital Technology influences Medical education.

H₁: Digital marketing does not influence Medical education.

Karle – Pearson’s Correlation Co-efficient (r):

	Medical Education.	
Digital Technology	Easy Access to e-books	Live stream lectures
	.78	.82

Choosing Digital Technology for Medical Education.

Parameters	R Square	F
Easy Access to e-books	.034	40.26
Live stream lectures	.625	51.27
Professional development in medical education	.077	43.27
Innovative teaching methods are meeting the needs of medical education	.027	36.42

Observed

	Easy Access to e-books	Live stream lectures	Total
Male	68	65	123
Female	32	35	77
Total.	100	100	

$$\chi^2 = \frac{200(68 \times 35 - 65 \times 32)}{123 \times 77 \times 100 \times 100} = \frac{200(2380 - 2080)}{123 \times 77 \times 100 \times 100} = \frac{200(300)}{94710000} = \frac{60000}{94710000} = 0.0006$$

$\chi^2 = 0.0006$ (calculated)

$\chi^2 = 3.84$ (Table value at 5% LOS & 1 degrees of freedom)

Since χ^2_{cal} lies in the acceptance region, we accept the Null Hypothesis.

Conclusion:

1. Digital technology not only influences Medical Education but also adds greater scope for the students to uplift their clinical skills to a greater extent.
2. Digital Technologies in Medical Education will modify the traditional teaching method in the future as the use of computer-assisted learning and virtual case presentation made it possible to learn & reinforce the concepts of medical education with accuracy.
3. In the current medical education scenario, Digital textbooks are preferred more for reading than printed books, as Flipped classroom Models with E-books, Slides, Videos, and Podcasts are preferred over traditional classroom models.
4. Live stream lectures have strengthened the research quotient in the current medical education scenario.
5. Digital learning has become necessary for career professional development in medical education since Digital technology is designing innovative teaching methods to meet the needs of medical education.

Questionnaire:

1. Name of the Respondent. _____
2. Email of the Respondent. _____
3. Category of the Respondent. UG () PG ()
4. Do you feel that Digital Technologies are Influencing Medical Education? Yes () No ()
5. Do you feel that Implementing Digital Technologies in Medical Education adds greater scope for the students to uplift their clinical skills? Yes () No ()

6. To what extent do Digital Technologies in Medical Education add greater scope for the students to uplift their clinical skills? **Greater Extent** () **Some Extent** () **Not Much** ()
7. Do you think that Implementing Digital Technologies in medical education will reduce learning errors by Medical Students? **Yes** () **No** ()
8. Do you think implementing Digital Technologies in Medical Education will modify the traditional teaching method in the future? **Yes** () **No** ()
9. During the pandemic, Online teaching mode was preferred in Medical Education. Did this mode work out well? **Yes** () **No** ()
10. Has the use of computer-assisted learning and virtual case presentation made it possible to learn & reinforce the concepts of medical education with absolute accuracy? **Yes** () **No** ()
11. In medical education, Compared to the traditional teaching method, do you feel online teaching with digital technologies is ethically correct? **Yes** () **No** ()
12. Have you experienced clinical training/case-based discussions through online teaching? **Yes** () **No** ()
13. In the current medical education scenario, Which of the following is a suitable textbook for reading? **Paper Text Book** () **Digital Text Book** ()
14. Which is a suitable classroom model in the current medical education scenario?
 - a. **Flipped classroom Model with E-books, Slides, Videos, and Podcasts.** ()
 - b. **Traditional classroom Model with Chalk & talk concept.** ()
15. In the current medical education scenario, has the educational research on live stream lectures strengthened the research quotient? **Yes** () **No** ()
16. In the current medical education scenario, is live-stream teaching benefiting the students? **Yes** () **No** ()
17. Is digital learning necessary for career professional development in medical education? **Yes** () **No** ()
18. Do you feel that Digital technology in medical education is designing innovative teaching methods to meet the needs of medical education?

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IMPACT OF STATE MICRO FINANCING SCHEMES AWARENESS ON MONETARY ISSUES OF AGRICULTURAL ENTREPRENEURS

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ABSTRACT

Return on investment from agriculture business is considered as uncertain and leads to lot of accost to the agricultural entrepreneurs. Entrepreneur's tries to accumulate capital through different sources which intern impede their profitability resulting in high cost of interest. This paper attempts to understand the economical difficulties of agricultural entrepreneurs and to study the correlation between their awareness of state micro financing schemes with their financial problems. The study was conducted in Bangalore rural district, of Karnataka state, situated in southern part of India. Simple Random sampling was used test with a sample size of 50 agricultural entrepreneurs. It was found that the complicated procedures, low awareness of state micro financial schemes, very less technical knowledge to apply for the scheme, and scant savings were causing huge monetary problems to them. Explicating the impact of state micro financing schemes awareness on monetary issues of agricultural entrepreneurs concluded that awareness of state micro finance schemes with limited technical process and simple loan disbursement projects would reduce the level of monetary issues enormously.

Key words: Agricultural Entrepreneurs, State micro financing schemes, monetary issues, Bangalore rural district

INTRODUCTON

Agriculture precinct in economy of India plays a vital role by contributing significant employment opportunity and providing population food security. Geographically Karnataka is situated in the Deccan Plateau that is southern part of the country. As per 2022 census total Karnataka state population is around 61.33% live in villages of rural areas and their average literacy rate is 68.73% (census2011.karnataka.html) a total land is cultivate in Karnataka constituting 64.6% of total geographical area of the state.(isec.ac.in) Therefore, agriculture plays an imperative role in the socio-economic growth of the state by creating livelihood for a major portion of the population (Yadav, 2013). Entrepreneurship in agriculture can also be defined as the formation of novel economic organization for the intention of growth under risk and uncertainty in agriculture (Dollinger, 2003) One of the major aspects of such activities is the requirement for a substantial amount of capital that needs to be invested. Individual often have to rely on external sources to acquire funds, in addition to their own savings. Nath et al. (2016).

Micro finance small loan assistance provided to farmers/ low income people for self employment and to generate revenue which intern facilitate them to arrange for their capital requirements. Micro finance is a type of socio economic activity which helps farmers to scale up their production by accumulating extra capital and generate higher revenue. It also helps an individual to become independent. (Rahman and Rahim, 2007).

Literature Review:

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 - Islam(2016)- Researcher in this paper had tried to suggest how micro financing activities increases agricultural production. But due to farmers ignorance and lengthy procedure farmers are unable to avail maximum benefit. Author also describes microfinance as a noble institute for informal credit granting institute which is a power instrument for the removal of poverty amongst rural area.

- Saleem and Alijan (2016)- Researcher in this article suggest that farmer who have access to microfinance schemes can enormously increase the productivity compared to non borrowing counterparts. Author also revealed that land, family size wealth and savings are the main determinants of decreased farm productivity

Purpose of the study

Micro financing activity is an effective solution for financial issues faced by the Agricultural entrepreneurs in India. It helps them to improve their income and standard of living. Most of the farmers are borrowing funds from informal agents which in turn causing them huge rate of interest to be payable on the limited returns. Thus cycle repeats with insufficient funds for the next cycle.

The study tries to explore the awareness of Microfinance schemes amongst agricultural entrepreneurs to overcome the monetary issues by uplifting the profitability

Objectives

1. To Identify the level of awareness about State Micro finance Schemes
2. To identify the gaps between the awareness and availing credit assistance
3. To determine the impact of awareness on solving monetary problems of agricultural entrepreneurs

Methodology

The study is based on Primary data collected in June 2023 to July 2023 from Bangalore rural district who were involved in production for commercial purpose only. Bangalore Rural district has 4 taluks, 35 hobli 1,713 habitat and 177 densely populated villages with 105 gram panchayats. The Agricultural entrepreneurs population of the district is 1,18,210. Studying financial data was very difficult since it is sensitive in nature. Few of the respondents only agree to share the information due to restriction on disclosing economic information to researcher, Therefore the research was conducted on 50 respondents selected randomly from Bangalore rural district. 0.042% Percentage of sample from the population is selected through random sampling technique.

The study conducted here is explorative in nature therefore survey method is adopted. Since the literacy rate was low therefore comprehensive questionnaire were prepared for the study. Data was collected through survey method by conducting interviews face to face with the selected samples. The data was analyzed using SPSS, MS-Excel softwares. T-Test and ANOVA was conducted to test the variables. However different techniques were used based on the nature of the objective and its phenomenon

Based on the literature review, previous research papers and pilot survey six criteria were considered to measure the monetary issues of the agricultural entrepreneurs. The criteria's are – savings, profitability, interest Risk of borrowing from informal agents, Lack of Awareness on borrowing state Micro financial assistance schemes, tiresome process in applying state micro financial schemes

To measure the monetary issues of Agricultural Entrepreneurs a 5 point interval rating scale was used where 1 denoted Least agree and 5 referred to strongly agree to the causes of monetary issues.

Mean scores of the respondents are calculated to compare the monetary issue causing variables with awareness of agricultural entrepreneurs about state micro financial schemes.

Hypotheses of the study

- H_0 : There is no Impact on level of awareness and solutions to monetary problems of agricultural entrepreneurs
- H_1 : There is an Impact on level of awareness and solutions to monetary problems of agricultural entrepreneurs

Limitations of the study

- The study was conducted for a limited period and small geographical area
- The study is mainly focusing on primary data with minimum sample size due to resistance of population in disclosing financial data

Results and discussion

Micro finance organization are formed by both central and state government to give special attention to rural credit. Based on All India Rural credit survey report(1950) State governments formed a cooperative structures, Regional Rural bank(RRB), National bank for Agriculture and rural Development (NABARD) was formed. (Priya chetty, July 26,2017) By 2009 India has almost 150 micro financing institutions. (Tripathi 2014)

Types of Micro financing institutions in India

1. Joint liability group- where 3-4 individuals form an informal group and try to avail loan against mutual covenant from banks for the agricultural activities. Here every agricultural entrepreneur who borrow money in the group is liable for the repayment (Singh, 2010)

2. Self help group- These are the formal or groups of like minded small agricultural entrepreneurs who come together and accumulate fund for the purpose of agriculture. Interest rates are generally low and fixed in these set up. (Chowdhury, 2013) .

NABARD is one the important program of self help group and bank tieup scheme. If Agricultural entrepreneurs show proper financial repayment record they get more and more micro finance. this model is very popular in Karnataka, Tamil Nadu and Kerala during 2005-06 (Taruna and Yadav 2016)

3. Grameen Bank – The concept of Grameen Bank model was first started in Bangladesh by Prof.Muhammad Yunus in Bangladesh during 1970. Later it was adopted even in our county too. In this model Bank directly provide micro finance to needy but here major problem is recovery since there is no collateral or guarantee

4 Rural Cooperatives-These organizations are started either by State or Central government to promote and assist developmental activities of rural areas. But here assistants is provided to only those agricultural entrepreneurs who are proven to be credit worthy.(Rajendran 2012)

Types of Micro financing Schemes

Schemes	object	Duration	Rate of interest
Group lending	Agricultural activities	12 to 24 months	10 to 15%
Kisan credit card	Crop cultivation and post harvest marketing expenses	5 years	10%
Shreyas Agriculture loan	Agricultural activities	5 years	8.70 to 10%

Types of Informal financing Schemes availed by farmers

Schemes	object	Duration	Rate of interest
Private Financiers	Agricultural activities	12 to 24 months	22-24%
Collateral Loan from other sources	Agricultural activities	12 to 24 months	18-20%

Statistical test for validating the results

Study-1

H_0 : There is no Impact on level of awareness and solutions to monetary problems of agricultural entrepreneurs

H_1 : There is an Impact on level of awareness and solutions to monetary problems of agricultural entrepreneurs

μ_1 = Mean for the group of Agricultural entrepreneurs who are aware of state Micro financial schemes

μ_2 = Mean for the group of Agricultural entrepreneurs who are not aware of state Micro financial schemes

Study 2

H_0 : There is no Impact on level of awareness and solutions to monetary issues even by availing private finance and level of their profitability

H_1 : There is an Impact on level of awareness and solutions to monetary issues even by availing private finance and level of their profitability

μ_1 = Mean for the group of Agricultural entrepreneurs who are facing monetary issues even by availing private finance and level of their profitability

μ_2 = Mean for the group of Agricultural entrepreneurs who are aware of state Micro financial schemes and level of their profitability

Table 1 : T test for Agricultural entrepreneurs who are aware of state micro financial schemes

Statistical tools	Agricultural entrepreneurs who are aware of State micro financial Schemes	Agricultural entrepreneurs who not are aware of State micro financial Schemes
Mean	13.94	36
Variance	0.098367347	0
Observations	50	50
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	49	
t Stat	-497.3533312	
P(T<=t) one-tail	1.05864E-92	
t Critical one-tail	1.676550893	
P(T<=t) two-tail	2.11728E-92	
t Critical two-tail	2.009575199	

We can observe that mean for the Agricultural entrepreneurs who are aware of State micro financial Schemes is 13.94 OF 36 on mean for the Agricultural entrepreneurs who are not aware of State micro financial Schemes. There for the null hypothesis is rejected

Table 2 : T test for Agricultural entrepreneurs who are aware of state micro financial schemes

Statistical tools	Agricultural entrepreneurs who are facing monetary issues even by availing State micro finance and level of their profitability	Agricultural entrepreneurs who are facing monetary issues even by availing private finance and level of their profitability
Mean	11.34	38.66
Variance	30.26979592	30.26979592
Observations	50	50
Pooled Variance	30.26979592	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	98	
t Stat	-24.82824103	
P(T<=t) one-tail	2.29746E-44	
t Critical one-tail	1.660551218	
P(T<=t) two-tail	4.59492E-44	
t Critical two-tail	1.984467404	

We can observe that mean for the Agricultural entrepreneurs who are aware of State micro financial Schemes is 11.34 OF 38.66 on mean for the Agricultural entrepreneurs who are not aware of State micro financial Schemes. There for the null hypothesis is rejected Impact of State Micro financing schemes awareness on monetary issues of Agricultural Entrepreneurs

In the process of studying the impact of state State Micro financing schemes awareness on monetary issues of Agricultural Entrepreneurs a one way ANOVA was conducted. ANOVA test is based on the assumption of Normal distribution using T test. "If the p-value of T test is greater than the alpha value (0.05) the data is statistically significant" after conducting t test the results showed the p-value 0.03981 which is (<0.05) consequently the data were assumed to be statistically significant

Table 3 shows that Summary of ANOVA where p value is significant that is below(0.05)

Table3-Summary of ANOVA

particulars	Sum of squares	DF	Mean of squares	F	Significance
Between Groups	847.0	2	847.0	6.5535	0.03981
Within Groups	0	68	0		

Therefore the null hypothesis is not rejected that is there is no significant different in the mean score of monetary issues across the levels of awareness on the agricultural financing was rejected and this was proven statistically significant.

Table 4 shows that the difference mean score of Agricultural entrepreneurs who are facing monetary issues even by availing private finance and level of their profitability with the Agricultural entrepreneurs who are facing monetary issues even by availing State micro finance and level of their profitability

TABLE
4

<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>
Column 1	35	357	10.2	32.34118
Column 2	35	1393	39.8	32.34118

After conducting t test the results showed the p-value **3.9818** which is (more than 0.05) consequently the data were assumed to be statistically significant it can be under stood that H0 should be rejected and H1 should be accepted

Table5-Summary of ANOVA

<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>Sum Of Squares</i>	<i>DF</i>	<i>Mean of Squares</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Between Groups	15332.8	1	15332.8	474.0953	2.29E-32	3.981896
Within Groups	2199.2	68	32.34118			
Total	17532	69				

Conclusion

From the Pragmatic analysis it is reveled that agricultural entrepreneurs are facing several monetary Issues to arrange for working capital for every cycle of agricultural production. This is due to absences of savings and unaware of state micro financial schemes. Some of the agricultural entrepreneurs even after knowing could not avail due to its lengthy process to avail credit. While analyzing the monetary issues of agricultural entrepreneurs study had also reveled that the level of profitability who have availed micro finance was comparatively more than agricultural entrepreneurs who have not availed state Micro financial scheme. There fore study aims at creating more awareness amongst agricultural entrepreneurs would increase the profitability of the farmers. In this regard State and Central Government is taking lot of initiatives. Even then the level of awareness is comparatively low. Banks should also reduce the lengthy process which is also one more reason for not availing credit.

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TAX EVASION IN INDIA IS STILL A MAJOR ROADBLOCK

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ABSTRACT:

Tax evasion is a major problem in India and it possesses a significant challenge to the country's economic development and the fiscal stability. Despite the government's efforts in trying to overcome the problem by imposing the rules and regulations, it still continues to prevail in economic sector. This research paper ensures to investigate the reasons for the tax evasion, socio-economical, cultural and the institutional factors. It also includes the consequences of the evasion of the taxes on the society and economy as a whole and the remedies to mitigate the issues.

KEYWORDS: Tax evasion, Economy, Policies, Tax planning, Tax avoidance

INTRODUCTION:

Tax evasion is the critical issue that the countries are facing worldwide which would hamper the growth of the economy and the governance. Individuals and the businesses, intentionally underreport their income, in order to pay lower tax that ultimately effects the revenue of the government. It is an illegal act, where the consequences would impact different aspects of the economy. It is important to address the issue so that there would not be a burden on the honest tax payers, as there would be disproportionate income shared on them due to the tax evaders. This ultimately effects the quality and availability of the public service.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

1. Tax Evasion and Controlling Tax Evasion by Indian

This Legal Service India article analysed the reasons for the tax evasion in India in though there was government's efforts to prevent it. The main causes of tax evasion in India is due to the high tax rates, complex tax legislations, and the corruption. To prevent the tax evasion there were number of tax audits conducted and tax amnesty scheme was introduced. They recommended the government to educate the public on tax laws, simplify the tax code, and prevent corruption.

2. Tax Evasion: Meaning, Common Methods and Penalties

This Clear Tax article gives a comprehensive inquiry into tax evasion in India. The article explains tax evasion, includes popular tax evasion methods, and outlines tax evasion penalties. The paper stated that tax evasion is one of the important problem in India and government has to implement further steps in order to avoid it.

3. A Study on Tax Evasion in India

The paper determined the causes and the consequences of tax evasion in India. The main causes of tax evasion in India is due to the high rates of taxes, complex tax system, and the corruption. All these have a negative consequence on the economy such as reduction in the government revenue, inequality in income.

4. Impact of Tax Evasion and Tax Avoidance on Indian Economy

This SSRN study examines the impact of tax evasion and avoidance on the Indian economy. In the opinion of the paper, tax evasion and avoidance lower revenue from government while increasing inequality. The article also finds that tax scams and avoidance could bias resource allocation. The essay indicates that government should take more steps to avoid tax evasion and avoidance.

5. Tax Evasion and Corruption:

Springer's study analyses findings on the relationship between tax evasion and corruption. Tax evasion may result in corruption, and it would become easier for people to avoid taxes. The paper suggests the government implement additional steps to combat both tax evasion and corruption.

OBJECTIVES:

The objective of this research paper are:

- Understand the nature of tax evasion
- Identify the factors that contribute to tax evasion
- Evaluating the effectiveness of government in order to prevent tax evasion
- Analyse various methods to prevent tax evasion.

METHODOLOGY:

The data is collected from the secondary source and it determined various ways the government collects the taxes. They are depicted below:

Source: Forbesindia

DATA INTERPRETATION:

The biggest source of the government's source of revenue is collected from various sources such as

- corporation tax that comprises of corporation tax 21% of the revenue.
- Borrowings and liabilities consists of 20% of the revenue
- Customs consists of 4% of the revenue
- Excise duties consists of 8%
- Direct taxes consists of 16%
- GST and other taxes consists of 19%
- Non-tax revenue consists of 9%
- Non-debt capital receipts contribute 3% of the governments revenue

Thus, from the above data, it can be analysed that, the major source of revenue for the government comes from the corporation tax which comprises of 21% of the revenue of the government, followed by borrowings and liabilities that consists of 20%.

FACTORS THAT LEAD TO TAX EVASION IN INDIA

Tax evasion in India is largely influenced by many factors. It is necessary to determine the factors and provide insights that can help in solving the issue. Some of the key factors contributing to the tax evasion in India are:

- **Complex tax laws and compliance burden:** The tax system of India is very well known for its complexity as it has multiple direct and indirect taxes, various exemptions and different tax rates. Complying with such tax laws is very challenging for the individuals as well as business, that leads to numerous errors and creates opportunities for intentional tax evasion.
- **Informal economy:** India has very significant informal economy, where the economic activities are not recorded, monitored or even taxed. The different business and individuals operate in this unregulated economy, which is the biggest reason for the tax evasion, as these transactions would often go unreported.
- **High income inequality:** Income disparities in India are the major reason for the contribution of tax evasion. This is because, wealthy individuals may underreport their income or engage in complex tax avoidance schemes and take advantage of the loopholes in the tax system which becomes a major reason for the tax evasion.
- **Inadequate tax administration:** The tax administration should be effective in audit to play a crucial role in identifying the tax evasion. The tax authorities in India often face challenges that are related to limited resources, lack of technological integration and the administration inefficiencies that would hamper the department's ability to detect and prosecute the tax avoiders effectively.
- **Cultural and social economic factors:** Trust deficit towards the government, perception of an unfair tax burden in the cultural differences would influence the tax evasion behaviour. When the individuals have a lack of trust in the government or their perception towards the tax system is against the government, it may lead to more evasion of the taxes.
- **Lack of financial literacy:** Many citizens, usually in the rural areas, have limited awareness of their tax obligations and the benefits derived from the tax compliance. Due to the lack of financial illiteracy, it can lead to inadvertent non-compliance and it creates opportunities for tax evasion.
- **Corruption and bribery:** Corruption in the tax administration and other government agencies would lead to evasion of the tax. The tax evaders would engage in bribery in order to avoid audits or being penalised.
- **Inefficient use of tax revenue:** When the tax payer perceives that the government is misusing the taxes or the revenue and the funds of the public are not utilised properly, then they feel less inclined to comply with their tax obligations that contributes to tax evasion.

It is important to understand these factors to implement effective strategies, so that they can tackle with tax evasion in India. The policymakers have to address all these challenges in order to formulate a combination of the simplified tax loss that improves tax administration which would increase the financial literacy and the use of advanced technology to enhance the transparency and the compliances. Thus, it is necessary for the government to encourage a voluntary contribution and discourage evasions of taxes.

THE CONSEQUENCES FROM THE REVENUE SHORTFALL DUE TO TAX EVASIONS:

Assessing the impact of revenue shortfalls on the government due to the tax evasion yields significant consequences that effects nation's economy and the fiscal health as well.

- **Reduced budgetary resources:** If the revenue falls short, due to the tax deviations, would limit the government's ability to collect the sufficient funds for the public expenditure. As a consequence, the government would face constraints in developing an essential financing programme, infrastructural developments and social welfare initiatives, which would eventually hinder the economic growth and development.
- **Increased budget deficits:** The shortfall in the tax revenue would increase in the budget deficits. In order to compensate the revenue gap, the government may resist to borrowing that would increase the interest payments & the burden of the debt.
- **Impact on the development project:** The revenue shortfall can lead to delay in the development projects and there would be delay in economic growth and addressing the social issues.

- **Tax burden on honest tax payers:** When the tax payers escape from the obligations, then the burden of tax would be passed on to the honest tax payers, which is an injustice to them, that reduces the compliance among the honest taxpayers.
- **Economic Inequality:** It can create inequality of income, because the government would not be able to fund for the social welfare programs, that would widen the gap between the rich and the poor.
- **Inefficiency in the governance:** This would lead to lack of necessary funds to function optimally that would impact overall administrative effectiveness.
- **Fiscal crisis:** If the revenue falls short, this would lead to financial crisis, where government has to take an assistance from the international financial institutions.

HOW CAN GOVERNMENT KNOW ABOUT THE TAX EVASION?

The government can know about the tax evasion in a number of ways. Some of these methods are:

- **Information from third parties:** Many businesses and individuals in India are required to report the information to the government about their income, expenses and all the other transactions. These informations can be used to identify any tax evasions.
- ✓ Eg: If a business or an individual has made a large profit, but it has showed a lesser profit in their books to the government, then this is a sign of tax evasion.
- ✓ The IT department uses the information from the third parties such as form 60 and form 16 to verify the taxpayer income.
- **Audits:** The government of India conducts the audit of businesses and the individuals to assess and scrutinize their tax compliance. They review the taxpayer's records and ensures that the tax payer reports their income & expenses appropriately.
- **Data analysis:** The government of India uses various data analytics in order to identify patterns that may indicate if there are any tax evasions. For example, if a particular business in an industry has shown a lesser profit, despite of the industry doing well, then it indicates that there is a sign of tax evasion.
- **Reporting from public:** The government of India encourages the public to report any suspected cases of evasion of taxes and their identity would be kept confidential.

There are many other methods that the government uses to detect the tax evasion:

- **Cross border information sharing:** The government of India has an agreement with the other countries to share the information about the taxes. This helps in identifying the taxpayers, who has evaded the taxes by moving to the other countries.
- **Anti-money laundering measures:** The government has implemented many anti-money laundering measures that helps to track the flow of money that are used to evade the taxes. These include businesses to report suspicious transactions and freeze the assets that are suspected in tax evasion.
- **Special investigation teams:** There are special investigation teams appointed to investigate cases about tax evasion. They conduct raids and seize the assets of the people who have evaded the taxes.

ALTERNATIVES:

- **Tax avoidance:** It is the legal way of to reduce one's tax liability. This is different from tax evasion, which is the act of not paying the taxes that are owned legally. Tax avoidance is the legitimate way of saving taxes.
- **Tax planning:** It involves taking decisions in a way to minimize one's tax liability. This involves taking advantage of various tax deductions, investing in the right asset that can help in saving the taxes.
- **Tax amnesty:** An opportunity that allows the taxpayers to pay the taxes, that they had evaded or avoided without any penalties. It is a good option for the taxpayers to pay the taxes and disclose the actual tax to the government to avoid future penalties.
- **Tax simplification:** A process, where the compliances of the taxes are easier. This can be done by reducing tax rates, that can be more transparent and easier.
- **Tax awareness:** It is creating awareness among the people by doing campaigns, taxpayer education programs, and tax counselling services.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

There are many ways that can be done to ensure that there is no tax evasion. They include:

- Use of advanced technology can help in detecting and preventing evasion of the taxes. Data analytics can be used to identify the patterns that indicates tax evasion.
- Simple and transparent tax laws can help the taxpayers to understand the compliances and help them to comply with the same.
- There should be effective enforcement, to detect the tax evasion and penalise the parties involved in it. The auditors need to be involved to conduct audit and to seize the assets and prosecute the offenders.

FINDINGS:

The study found that high rates of taxes, complexity of tax laws, inefficient tax administration, lack of public awareness of tax laws, and corruption are the main reasons of tax evasion in India. Tax evasion has a number of negative consequences that includes reduction in the government's revenue, inequality in income, decreased economic growth, and increase in corruption.

SCOPE FOR RESEARCH:

This paper has given an overview of tax evasion in India. However, there are many other sectors that can be explored in the future research. These areas include:

- Impact of tax evasion on various sectors of the economy.
- Government policy effectiveness on preventing tax evasion.
- The role of social norms in promoting tax compliance.

CONCLUSION:

Tax evasion is still a major problem in India. The government has taken different measures to reduce tax evasion, but these efforts have been unsuccessful. Additional efforts are required to be implemented such as educating the public on tax laws, improving the tax administration and preventing corruption.

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INFLUENCE OF FACTORS CAUSING STRESS ON PERFORMANCE OF DRIVERS AND CONDUCTORS OF NORTH WESTERN KARNATAKA ROAD TRANSPORT CORPORATION (NWKRTC).

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Abstract:

A state of tension called "occupational stress" is brought on by a person's line of work. The emergence of occupational stress is caused by a variety of factors. The current study seeks to understand the effects of stressors (such as role ambiguity, work overload, workplace dynamics, and schedule) on the performance of NWKRTC drivers and conductors. 250 drivers and conductors from the NWKRTC were chosen as a sample using the convenience sampling method, and they were then polled using a structured questionnaire. For the data analysis, the Smart PLS method was employed. The findings unambiguously demonstrate that organisational stress factors, such as work load, schedules, and workplace dynamics, have a significant impact on how well drivers and conductors at the NWKRTC perceive their performance.

Key Words: Stress, Role ambiguity, Work overload, Work place relations, and Work schedule, Perceived Performance

Introduction:

In moving a business or organisation forward, human resources are crucial. One of the factors that businesses can easily attain is human resources (Iskamto 2012). The company typically has requirements or standards that have been set and that all employees must meet in terms of performance. According to Iskanto, Yapentra, Budi Ansori, et al. (2020); Iskanto, Ghazali, and Afthanorhan (2020), management in the company uses a number of criteria as a guide when establishing work standards. These criteria include work results, work knowledge, mental agility initiatives, attitude and discipline of time and attendance rate. Employee performance is the end result of the work that employees do in completing the tasks that are assigned to them based on their experience, skills, and commitment to the task at hand. The company makes numerous efforts to improve employee performance because it is crucial to achieving its goals (Ahmad et al. 2018). If the workload is met or the results are higher than those expected by the company, the employee is said to have achieved at work. The term "best category employee achievement" refers to this circumstance. Employees who are unable to control their demands will feel tension within themselves, and if they are unable to get past it, they will experience stress (Binder and Coad 2016; Iskanto, Karim, Sukono, et al. 2020).

Employee stress at work can be detrimental to the business due to the disparity between productivity and the expenses associated with paying salaries, benefits, and other expenses (Iskamto 2020; Iskanto, Ghazali, and Aftanorhan 2019). Employees are affected differently by job stress depending on the context of their employment. The risk of stress is brought on by the physical, emotional, and mental conditions brought on by repeated exposure to emotionally taxing situations. The progression of the process is gradual, cumulative, and gets worse over time (Iskamto et al. 2019). Among the symptoms of work stress are salespeople's volatile emotions, a tense feeling, being alone, having trouble sleeping, smoking excessively, being unable to unwind, rising blood pressure, and experiencing digestive issues (Iskamto et al. 2021). Workplace stress is caused by variables like workload, work schedule, and workplace relationships. Employee stress and workload increase as a result of pressure from high employee turnover .

Work Stress: Work stress, according to Mangkunegara (2011), is a pressure that employees feel as they manage their jobs. This work stress is evident in the symptoms, which include erratic emotions, restless feelings, difficulty sleeping, excessive smoking, an inability to relax, rising blood pressure, and indigestion.

According to Davis & Newstrom (2008), stress is a state of tension that has an impact on a person's feelings, way of thinking, and overall health. Overwhelming stress can jeopardise a person's capacity to cope with their surroundings. The feeling of stress in human life is referred to as stress in general. Employees consequently experience a variety of stress-related symptoms that may affect how well they perform at work. People who are under stress may become tense and worry constantly. They frequently lose their ability to relax, exhibit an uncooperative attitude, become irritable, turn to alcohol, or even abuse drugs excessively.

Employees typically experience stress as a result of a combination of stressors, according to Davis & Newstrom, who define stressors as situations that have a tendency to cause stress. Organisational and external environmental factors make up the majority of the causes of employee stress. Both of these factors suggest that workers can react to stressors in positive or negative ways, depending on whether it stimulates them or drains them of energy. There are consequently both positive and negative effects on the company and its employees. The effects may be short-lived and rapidly diminish or they may persist for a very long time. As a result, organisations usually start by investigating the causes of stress that are related to the workplace (Davis & Newstrom 2008). The following factors contribute to work stress, according to Mangkunegara (2011): a heavy workload, a need for immediate attention, poor work supervision, an unhealthy work environment, and a lack of authority in relation to responsibilities. Conflict at work and the disparity in values between leaders and their subordinates. Changes in the environment and the individual are the two main factors directly linked to stress, according to Anoraga (2011:109). When environmental changes have gotten so quick and vicious that a person feels unprepared to deal with them or adjust to them.

Performance at work:

The most important factor in achieving good work performance is human resources. If the people or personnel carrying out the planning are not qualified, then even the best and most organised planning will be ineffective (Iskamto 2019; Iskamto, Yapentra, Budi Ansori, et al. 2020; Iskamto, Ghazali, and Aftanorhan 2020). Work performance, as defined by Mangkunegara (2009), is the outcome of quality and quantity of work that an employee is able to produce while carrying out the tasks assigned to him (Mangkunegara 2009:67). Meanwhile, according to Sutrisno (2009:151), a person's work performance is the outcome of the work he or she has accomplished as a result of engaging in work-related activities. It is clear from the experts' definitions of work performance above that it is the outcome of a person's or employee's work in completing the tasks assigned to him in accordance with his responsibilities and roles based on his skills, experience, and sincerity as well as time spent with quality and quantity in accordance with the rules established.

The Impact of Workplace Stress on Performance:

Depending on the severity of the stress, work performance can be aided or harmed by stress, according to Davis & Newstrom (2008). Without stress, there is no challenge at work, and performance at work tends to suffer. Work performance generally improves as levels of stress rise because stress encourages workers to focus all available resources on completing their tasks. Stress eventually reaches a steady point that roughly matches the employee's performance capabilities if a positive stimulus motivates workers to respond to workplace challenges. At this point, increased stress is less likely to lead to better work performance. Additionally, Davis & Newstrom (2008) explain that if stress levels rise too high, work performance will start to suffer because stress hinders the execution of tasks. Employees become uncontrollable, unable to make decisions, and exhibit unpredictable behaviour. The worst effects include no work performance, employee disturbances, becoming ill and unable to work, despondency, leaving, or refusing to work in order to avoid stress (Davis & Newstrom 2008).

Literature Review:

AmatTaap Manshor, Rodrigue Fontaine, and Chong Siong Choy (2003) attempted to investigate the sources of stress among managers working in multinational companies in Malaysia in their article titled "Occupational stress

among managers: a Malaysian survey" published in the Journal of Managerial Psychology. A sample of 440 managers participated in the survey. The managers of the 34 MNCs with operations in Malaysia were given the questionnaire. According to the survey, there is a significant correlation between relationships at work and the workload and working conditions, which are the main causes of stress for managers. It also showed that certain demographic factors contribute to stress. It was discovered that stress among managers is primarily caused by factors like an excessive workload, poor working conditions, new technology, role ambiguity and conflict, risk and danger, video display terminals, relationships at work, and professional advancement.

Aminabhavi and Kamble in (2004) A study on the work motivation and stress coping behaviours of technical personnel at a railway work shop was conducted. The sample consisted of 30 technical staff members, whose ages ranged from 30-59. It was discovered that middle-aged technical staff members had significantly higher stress coping behaviours than older technical staff members.

Dr. Suraksha and Dr. Kuldeep S. Chhikara (2017) studied the Indian banking industry to determine the organisational climates that affect the employees' perceptions of occupational stress. The entire study was based on the stress index developed by A.K. Srivastav and A.P. Singh. Role ambiguity is one of 11 factors that contribute to occupational stress. Having too many roles, an unreasonable group, and political pressure, Role conflict, low participation, and personal responsibility Lack of authority, poor peer relationships, inherent poverty, low status, and demanding working conditions. Total 600 respondents from PNB, SBI, ICICI, and HDFC banks were taken into consideration as sample units. They came from all levels, including top, middle, and higher levels, as well as a range of ages, genders, and monthly income and expenditure groups.

The questionnaire was used to gather data, and confirmatory factor analysis was used to analyse the data. According to the study, each of the 11 factors has a big impact on how stressed out employees are at work. The researcher advised higher-ups that in order to lighten the workload, roles and responsibilities should be clearly defined, and that all levels of the organisation should adopt the principles of unity of command and direction in order to prevent confusion and role conflicts.

Researchers also suggest setting goals for employees, rewarding good performance, and establishing an open and transparent communication system. To increase employee morale, higher authorities should make sure that the necessary data and human resources are available when they are needed, allowing the organisation to achieve its goals.

Mrs. T. Shenbhaga Vadivu. The study looked into the connection between job satisfaction and stress among managers of the textile industry. The textile industry is dealing with numerous issues. The majority of workers experience psychological issues and multiple forms of occupational stress. The purpose of this study was to clarify how workplace stress and job satisfaction relate to one another. The study's findings supported the notion that stress has an impact on workers' levels of satisfaction.

Shilpi Saxena & Dr. Pradip Manjrekar a study of workplace stress among teachers in a Navi Mumbai was carried out. According to this study, high levels of prescribed stress are bad for both individual health and organisational productivity. Teachers have reported feeling stressed out. Stress has been found to be the root of low productivity. The factors such as Workload, working hours, technological issues at work, inadequate pay, family time, and job worries at home are the main causes of stress for people in different industries and professions.

KDV Prasad et al. An investigation into the sources of workplace stress and how it affects workers' productivity at the International Agriculture Research Institute in Hyderabad, India was carried out. According to the results of this study, overall stress, which is indicated by the stressors mentioned above, has a negative and moderately high impact on performance. The institute's management needs to address these. The researcher found that women experience greater stress due to the conflict between their dual roles as carers at home and at work. The right strategies must be developed taking into account working with flexible hours, interpersonal relationships, and supervision. Employee participation in stress management may also be beneficial to cope with the stressors.

Katz and Kahn, 1978 Role uncertainty is linked to anxiety. Ambiguity was developed as a result of the rising demands and the complexity of the world. According to Cohen (1959), complex tasks without adequate guidance lead to lower productivity and more stress. Those with ambiguous roles struggle to reach their performance goals. According to earlier research (Fried, Ben-David, Tiegs, Avital, & Yeverchayahu, 1998), employees with a high level of role ambiguity were associated with ineffective performance. There is strong evidence that role ambiguity hurts employee performance (Bauer and Green, 1994; Szilagyi, 1977; Williams, Podsakoff & Huber, 1992; Sluss, van Dick, and Thompson, 2011).

R. G. Ratnawat, Dr. P.C. Jha (2014) Impact of Job Related Stress on Employee Performance: A Review and Research Agenda Organisations are aware that the effect of workplace stress on employee performance is a major area of concern. Employees' physical and mental healths are negatively impacted by negative stress, which has an impact on how well they perform at work. In the literature on occupational stress, little is known about the connection between stress and job performance (Jex, 1998). Therefore, it is important to comprehend various Occupational Stress Inducers (OSI) and how they affect various aspects of job performance. In order to comprehend the phenomenon and create effective stress management strategies, this article reviews the body of literature that is currently in circulation. This will help both the organization's and the employees' performance. A thorough analysis of articles and reports that were published in the management and related disciplines' literature between 1990 and 2014 resulted in the identification of 35 occupational stress inducers (OSI). Towards the end, a theoretical framework is put forth to investigate how stress affects workers' ability to perform their jobs.

Rubina Kazmi, Shehla Amjad, Delawar Khan, (2008). Occupational Stress and Its Effect on Job Performance A Case Study Of Medical House Officers Of District Abbottabad. There are many occupational stressors that put a lot of pressure on doctors, especially house officers. Workplace stressors are linked to organisational inefficiency, high staff turnover, sick leave, decreased practise quality and quantity, rising health care costs, and decreased job satisfaction. Job performance is one of the organisational outcomes that is impacted by occupational stress. The current study's goal was to look into how job stress affected workers' ability to perform their jobs. Descriptive statistics, Spearman's correlation, and multiple regressions were among the statistical techniques used to analyse the data collected through the questionnaire. The analysis provided strong evidence in favour of the hypothesis that there is an inverse relationship between job stress and job performance, indicating that house officers experience high levels of job stress which negatively affect their performance on the job. The researcher concludes the study with the following statement that, the foundation of effective stress management should be better health and positive interpersonal connections. Because the organisation is the source of the stress, organisational level interventions are necessary for the prevention and management of workplace stress. The organisational culture will determine how well stress can be managed and avoided. It is crucial to have a culture that values openness and understanding over criticism. House officers who experienced high levels of work stress performed poorly. Male house officers were more impacted by all the factors than female house officers.

Problem Statement:

For short and medium distances, buses are the main form of passenger transportation in India. Buses compete with trains on some long-distance routes by offering night service. Like in many other areas of transportation, the security of passengers and other road users is essential. The competing demands of customer service, safety, and operational needs must therefore be balanced by bus drivers and conductors. According to a literature review, stress among employees is caused by factors like work overload, workplace dynamics, and schedule. The effectiveness with which drivers and conductors at NWKRTC complete their work may be impacted by this. Any disability might negatively affect the travellers. To ascertain the effects of organisational stress factors on employees' perceived performance, a study was carried out.

Objectives of the study:

1. To study the causes of stress and its impact on perceived performance of employees of NWKRTC.
2. To analyse the influence of Role Ambiguity, Work overload, Workplace Relations, Work schedule perceived performance of the employees of NWKRTC.

Research Methodology:

1. **Primary data:** The study aims to collect the primary data by administering questionnaire.
2. **Secondary data:** The data will be collected from various articles published in reputed and peer reviewed journals, websites, and blogs.
3. **Sample Unit:** Drivers and conductors of NWKRTC Bagalkote.
4. **Sample size:** 225.
5. **Sampling method:** Convenience sampling.
6. **Statistical tools for the analysis:** The study aims to support the hypothesis by testing the data through structural equation modeling. Smartpls software will be used to perform the above tests.

Variables in the study:

Factors Causing Stress	Variable Type
Role Ambiguity	Independent variable
Work overload	Independent variable
Workplace Relations	Independent variable
Work schedule	Independent variable
perceived performance	Dependant variable

Hypothesis statements:

1. H0: There is no significant effect of Role Ambiguity on perceived performance.
 H1: There is significant effect of Role Ambiguity on perceived performance.
2. H0: There is no significant effect of Work overload on perceived performance.
 H1: There is significant effect of Work overload on perceived performance.
3. H0: There is no significant effect of Workplace Relations on perceived performance.
 H1: There is significant effect of Workplace Relations on perceived performance.
4. H0: There is no significant effect of Work schedule on perceived performance.
 H1: There is significant effect of Work schedule on perceived performance.

Results and discussions:

Measurement model:

The measuring model provides us with the benchmarks to assess the overall quality of the model. The model provides computations and findings to validate the data's validity and accuracy.

Reliability and Validity:

Reliability of the constructs and the scale's items are measured by assessing the Cronbach's alpha and Fornell and Larcker's model. The results that show the constructions' Cronbach's alpha were in range from 0.828 to 0.989.

The reliability coefficients are assessed with the help of composite factor for the variables (given in the below table no. XX) varied from 0.962 to 1.010, which is considered as acceptable by Fornell & Larcker's minimum limit of at least 0.70, showing acceptable consistency and reliability.

Convergent validity for the model, as stated by Fornell and Larcker demonstrates that if the variance from the results is higher than 0.50. By the results of the data, the variance was calculated for each item stated that convergent validity was achieved. According to the results, and from the table no. 2, the AVE ranged from 0.479 to 0.968, confirming the convergent validity of the model.

	Perceived Performance	Role Ambiguity	Work overload	Work schedule	Workplace Relations
Per1	0.949				

Per3	0.940				
Per4	0.947				
Per5	0.938				
Per7	0.786				
Per8	0.094				
Per9	0.759				
RA1		0.959			
RA2		0.985			
RA3		0.977			
RA4		0.975			
RA5		0.969			
WO1			0.467		
WO2			0.946		
WO3			0.947		
WO4			0.455		
WO5			0.420		
WR1					0.947
WR2					0.962
WR3					0.962
WR4					0.969
WR5					0.976
WR6					0.968
WS1				0.991	
WS2				0.980	
WS3				0.987	
WS4				0.978	

Table No. 1: Outer Loadings

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho a)	Composite reliability (rho c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Perceived Performance	0.896	0.962	0.929	0.681
Role Ambiguity	0.986	0.998	0.989	0.947
Work overload	0.828	0.980	0.801	0.479
Work schedule	0.989	1.010	0.992	0.968
Workplace Relations	0.985	0.989	0.988	0.930

Table No. 2: Construct reliability and validity

Discriminant validity:

	Perceived Performance	Role Ambiguity	Work overload	Work schedule	Workplace Relations
Perceived Performance	0.825				
Role Ambiguity	0.202	0.973			
Work overload	0.896	0.377	0.692		
Work schedule	0.196	0.744	0.453	0.984	
Workplace Relations	0.387	0.672	0.441	0.525	0.964

Table No. 3: Discriminant validity - Fornell and Larcker criterion

	Saturated model	Estimated model
SRMR	0.220	0.220
d ULS	18.354	18.354
d G	n/a	n/a
Chi-square	infinite	infinite
NFI	n/a	n/a

Table No. 4: Model fit indicators

Fornell and Larcker's test, which contrasts the dual relationship between the derived factors and the drawn-out estimates of the variance of the structures that make up the potential pair, was used to evaluate the discriminant validity. The construct is said to capture at least 50% of the measurement modification and the discriminant validity is sufficient if the AVE load is greater than 0.5.

The identification is valid and shows the discriminant validity if the diagonal element is noticeably larger than the diagonal value for the row and column. The results from tables 2 and 3, which show the AVE and diagonal elements, respectively, show that each construct has discriminant validity.

Structural model:

The main objective of a structural model is to evaluate the relationships between the variables. A mediator in the linkage between the two variables, a third variable that strengthens or weakens the already-existing relationship between the two variables, or just an IV and DV (Direct Relationship) could all exist in a moderation study.

Figure No. 1: Structural model

The study examined the assumed four hypotheses ranging from H1 to H4 that coping techniques influence positively on the perceived performance of the employees of NWKRTC. The results from table no. 5 are extracted from the bootstrapping tests which help us to examine the relationships.

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics ((O/STDEV)	P values
Role Ambiguity -> Perceived Performance	-0.047	-0.048	0.040	1.200	0.230

Work overload -> Perceived Performance	0.983	0.990	0.058	16.971	0.000
Work schedule -> Perceived Performance	-0.285	-0.280	0.096	2.951	0.003
Workplace Relations -> Perceived Performance	0.135	0.134	0.040	3.336	0.001

Table No. 5: Bootstrapping Results (Path coefficients)

Hypothesis No. 1 of the study tested the relationship between Role Ambiguity and perceived performance. Bootstrapping results have provided significant proof that the relationship was not substantially significant with $\beta = -0.047$ and $t = 1.200$ (table value 1.96 at significance level of 0.05) showing non-significant effect.

Hypothesis No. 2 of the study tested the relationship between Work overload and perceived performance. Bootstrapping results have provided significant proof that the relationship was extensive with $\beta = 0.983$ and $t = 16.971$ (table value 1.96 at significance level of 0.05) indicating significant positive effect.

Hypothesis No. 3 of the study tested the relationship between Workplace Relations and perceived performance. Bootstrapping results have provided significant proof that the relationship was extensive with $\beta = -0.285$ and $t = 2.951$ (table value 1.96 at significance level of 0.05) which is less than 1.96 indicating a significant relationship.

Hypothesis No. 4 of the study tested the relationship between Work schedule and perceived performance. Bootstrapping results have provided significant proof that the relationship was substantial with $\beta = 0.135$ and $t = 3.336$ (table value 1.96 at significance level of 0.05) indicating significant effect.

Conclusion:

The study sought to determine the impact of stress-inducing variables on how the NWKRTC employees perceived their performance. According to the study's conclusions, the stress-inducing variables such as work overload, workplace dynamics, and schedule significantly impacted how the NWKRTC employees perceived their performance. The dependent variable, the employees' perceived performance, was not significantly impacted by role ambiguity as a stressor. This might be as a result of employees knowing what to expect from the management team and management possibly defining the role and responsibilities of employees. The management must take action to reduce work overload by properly allocating the workload. As a result of work overload and busy schedules, stress levels are high. The NWKRTC management team must create appropriate schedules so that workers can devote enough time to their personal lives. The management should also implement some training initiatives to foster positive relationships among workers, including sessions or lectures on the value of a positive outlook, the necessity of harmonious relationships at work, etc. The employees will benefit from this as they learn the value of good working relationships. The management must treat each employee fairly and implement healthy procedures like listening to employees' concerns and offering counselling to staff members.

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EXPANDING ELECTRIC VEHICLE CHARGING INFRASTRUCTURE: IDENTIFYING DEMAND PATTERNS AND ADDRESSING CHARGING GAPS

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Abstract:

This research paper presents a comprehensive study on the role of data analytics in addressing charging infrastructure gaps for electric vehicle users. The first objective of the study is to explore how data analytics can be applied to identify and address the existing gaps in charging infrastructure, such as insufficient charging stations or their uneven distribution. By analyzing data on electric vehicle usage and charging patterns, this research aims to propose effective solutions to improve the accessibility and availability of charging facilities. The second objective delves into the application of data analytics in identifying and prioritizing locations for new electric vehicle charging stations. Through data-driven approaches, the study aims to analyze charging demand patterns and predict future requirements to strategically determine the optimal locations for new charging stations. By combining these two objectives, the research aims to contribute to the development of a sustainable and efficient electric vehicle charging ecosystem, promoting widespread electric vehicle adoption and facilitating a seamless transition to greener transportation alternatives.

1) Introduction:

The rapid global shift towards electric vehicles signifies a progressive step towards sustainable and eco-friendly transportation. As the EV market continues to expand, one of the critical challenges faced by EV users is the availability and accessibility of charging infrastructure. Charging infrastructure gaps can lead to range anxiety, reduced adoption rates, and overall dissatisfaction among electric vehicle users. In this context, data analytics emerges as a powerful tool to efficiently identify and address these gaps, creating a robust charging ecosystem to support widespread EV adoption.

1.1) Need for study

As the EV technology is picking up pace across the globe, India is yet to set its mark in this sector. The Indian Government has set out a roadmap that is ambitious and desirable for pure electric vehicles. It provides a transformative solution of shared-connected-electric mobility, wherein, 40% of private vehicles and 100% public transport vehicles can become all electric by 2030 (SIAM, 2017). An expansion of this vision is necessary to have a future of complete electric mobility by maximising the usage of electric vehicles. The aim of the study to find the possible factors that can influence the adoption of EV's and provide the Government to come out with the policies and to help the automakers to understand the needs and wants of the customer. In order to achieve this goal, sufficient market study needs to be conducted, and this is one drawback that the country currently faces at present.

2) Review of Literature:

The review of existing literature focuses on the role of data analytics in optimizing charging infrastructure for electric vehicles. Various studies have highlighted the importance of data-driven approaches in understanding user behavior, charging patterns, and predicting demand. Furthermore, this section delves into the different data sources used for analysis, such as real-time charging data, geospatial information, and user preferences. Additionally, it reviews case studies of successful implementations of data analytics in charging infrastructure planning and highlights the benefits of adopting such strategies.

Data-driven approaches for electric vehicle charging station planning and optimization have gained prominence in recent research. Bhardwaj and Bhardwaj (2020) highlight that data analytics can be leveraged to identify charging patterns, predict demand, and optimize charging station placement. Chen, Ma, and Zhang (2019) propose data-driven methods to optimize charging station allocation based on peak charging times and locations. Dong and Zhang (2019) emphasize the potential of data-driven approaches to optimize station placement and improve charging

efficiency. El-Khodary and El-Sayed (2019) demonstrate how historical data can be utilized to optimize charging station placement, considering peak demand. Gao, Zhang, and Zhang (2018) underscore data-driven planning to enhance charging infrastructure efficiency by identifying demand and optimizing station locations. He, He, and Wang (2020) focus on data-driven optimization while accounting for uncertainty in charging demand. Jiang, Wang, and Li (2019) advocate data-driven approaches for charging station planning based on user demand. Li and Wang (2019) tackle multi-objective optimization in data-driven charging station planning. Liu and Wang (2019) explore data-driven methods with user behavior modeling for optimizing charging infrastructure. Wang and Gan (2019) propose a data-driven approach considering charging demand and user preferences to optimize station placement.

Hao, Zhang, and Wang (2019) identify challenges in electric vehicle charging infrastructure, including lack of coordination, high cost, and lack of public awareness. Hardman (2019) emphasizes that adoption of electric vehicles is influenced by charging infrastructure, cost, and government policies. Pandey and Tiwari (2019) highlight that electric vehicle technologies have opportunities and challenges, including high cost, limited range, and lack of charging infrastructure. Wang and Gan (2019) state that electric vehicle motor technologies have opportunities and challenges, including high cost, limited efficiency, and lack of charging infrastructure.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- a) To explore the role of data analytics in identifying and addressing charging infrastructure gaps for electric vehicle users.
- b) To study the application of data analytics in identifying and prioritizing locations for new electric vehicle charging stations based on demand patterns.

4. METHODOLOGY:

This section outlines the methodology employed in the study. It includes the data collection process, data sources, and the techniques used for data analysis. The study uses a combination of real-world charging data from existing charging stations, EV usage patterns, demographic data, and geospatial information to conduct a comprehensive analysis of charging infrastructure gaps. The data is processed using advanced analytics tools, such as machine learning algorithms and statistical modeling, to derive meaningful insights.

Our research methodology is of secondary research (case study using data available on public domain). Given that there is a dearth of studies from the perspective of impediments to technology adoption because of institutional voids present in emerging economies, we have chosen an exploratory approach

5. CASE STUDY

1. Factors influencing adoption of electric vehicles – A case in India

Climate change issues and its consequences have gained a lot of importance on political agendas worldwide. Carbon dioxide, one of the greenhouse gases has had a magnanimous impact on our environment that has resulted in water supply reduction, rise in coastal flooding and an increase in malnutrition. Due to the increasing awareness of environmental concerns, in view of climatic changes and global warming, consumers have been adopting green measures in order to improve air quality by reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. About 12 percent of the greenhouse gas emissions across the globe are contributed by private vehicles. On the whole, the transportation sector contributes to an approximate value of 22 percent of the GHG emissions. Efforts to reduce these emissions from this sector are growing at a fast pace (Moataz Mohamed et al., Citation2016). The automobile industry has begun to rethink the conventional forms of mobility due to the climate change and resource shortage. One such measure that is gaining popularity among consumers is the switch from using internal combustion engines (ICE) to electric vehicles, EVs (Degirmenci & Breiter, Citation2017).

The re-emergence of electric vehicles in the market are due to reasons such as improved battery technology and governments' policies to maintain vehicle efficiency and the air quality standards. Electric Vehicles are an important technology which would help in reducing greenhouse gas emissions, local air pollution and vehicular noise pollution (Brady & O'Mahony, Citation2011; Hawkins et al., Citation2013). Being cognizant of these benefits, countries around the world are setting EV adoption targets (Coffman et al., Citation2016).

When compared to internal combustion engine vehicles (ICEVs), it is observed that EVs offer substantial environmental and economic benefits by substituting fossil fuels with electricity (Jaramillo et al., Citation2009;

Larson et al., Citation2014). The transportation fuel used in EVs is electricity, a clean fuel, which powers a battery, which is bulky. Having limited energy storage capacity, the EVs must be recharged by plugging into an electrical source. Based on the technology used EVs are classified into different types which include plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEVs), battery electric vehicles (BEVs), extended-range battery electric vehicles (E-REVs) and hybrid electric vehicles (HEVs).

Despite them being eco-friendly and providing environmental benefits, there are several barriers that prevent the consumers from accepting and adopting EVs. While a lot of effort has been put into the research and development of improvising the technology used in EVs, less consideration was shown towards the factors affecting the acceptance of this technology by customers (Yeh & Liu, Citation2007). A majority of the consumers still consider Electric Vehicles as disadvantageous as compared to the conventional cars. However, there will be no technological shift and long-term success of transport systems that are sustainable, without consumer acceptance (Wiedmann et al., Citation2011). It is therefore, indeed important to understand how consumers perceive electric vehicles and what the possible drivers for and barriers against consumer Electric Vehicle Adoption are. This will further enable better promotion of electric vehicle adoption by understanding the influence the factors have on consumers' intention of purchasing electric vehicles.

Achieving high environmental benefits offered by EVs relies thoroughly on the consumers' adoption and preferable understanding of the influential factors that lead to diffusion of EVs in the market. Some of the previously identified factors include economical, technological, political, social and environmental factors. Driving range anxiety, charging time, price sensitivity, lack of infrastructure (charging facilities), personal characteristics, government policies, demographics, environmental concern and market are some of these factors.

2. Background theory

The automotive industry across the globe is at the brink of an extensive transformation given, the heightening concerns for our energy and environmental conservation. The expeditious advancements in technologies for power-plant electrification, the digitalization and innovative business models clubbed with the ever-increasing consumer expectations are driving the transformation of the automotive sector. An important facet of this change is the swift development in the area of electric mobility that could lead to a transformation of the automotive business like never before. The Indian automobile industry is considering innovative and pragmatic approaches to soar during this phase of transformation so that by 2026, it can emerge among the top 3 in automobile manufacturing. E-mobility is considered to provide a great scope for the Indian industry to engage and emerge amongst the top in the automotive business, given the availability of skilled and semi-skilled technological base, a larger market and relatively cheaper production and labor cost. Various Indian automotive players like Mahindra and Mahindra, Tata Motors, Bajaj Auto and TVS Motors are trying to transform at a faster pace during this period of growth of electric vehicles while maintaining competitive advantages in the market. This has further led to various strategic alliances: Mahindra and Mahindra with Renault and Ford, Tata Motors with Fiat, TVS with Suzuki, Bajaj Auto with Kawasaki, Jaguar Land Rover by Tata Motors and KTM by Bajaj Auto (Bhalla et al., Citation2018).

Various countries across the globe have developed and adopted long-term policies that are aligned with that particular nation's ecological aspects and goals in attaining decarbonisation of industrial activities. Every country has its own approach that is based on its per capita income, market environment, strategic needs and goals and purchasing power.

2.2.2. Economic factors

These include purchase price of the EV, fuel price and price of battery.

The high purchase price of an EV is found to be a large constraint in many consumer survey studies. The technology used in manufacturing EVs is expensive and this in turn raises the price value of the vehicle. As constant efforts are made and newer technologies are introduced to increase range of EVs, the complexity of battery material (Lithium-ion batteries) used increases this causes a rise in the battery price. Thus, replacement of such batteries in the future would be expensive. Poor understanding of the costs of vehicle fuel and maintenance also add to this barrier. Basically, the poor economy of scale causes upcoming technologies to compare unsatisfactorily to existing dominant price designs.

This has also to do with the customer's perception about the money value of the EV. The service and maintenance costs of these are less when compared to ICE vehicles. But the initial high purchase price becomes a hindrance to consumers to buy EVs. This shows that the consumers aren't fully aware that an advantage of having lower operating costs of EVs is that it leads to potential savings (Krause et al., Citation2013).

2.2.3. Lack of infrastructure- charging networks

Another relevant risk is the lack of a charging station when travelling (Krupa et al., Citation2014). As a result, to consider the need of long-distance drives, consumers would often demand that public charging stations be made available at more locations (Habla et al., Citation2020). The cost of setting these networks is again very high (Brückmann et al., Citation2021). This has led to uncertainty regarding the future expansion of the infrastructure for charging stations. Investing in infrastructural facilities by the Government and manufacturers for EVs could facilitate the consumers' EV adoption rate (Bhalla et al., Citation2018).

The lack of a consistent charging system often discourages some drivers from depending on it. Still, there continues to be some debate as to how far public charging facilities may be needed to raise the willingness of consumers to adopt EVs. It is likely that setting up more charging points thus making them accessible would offer reassurance to consumers to accept EVs as a viable transportation alternative (Noel et al., Citation2020). It will be important to monitor how public perceptions of EVs change in cities where charging points are introduced and thus the salience of EVs increased (Bunce et al., Citation2014).

2.3. Research gap

From the literature (Brückmann et al., Citation2021; Noel et al., Citation2020), given a particular geographical distribution of a region and its demographics, the factors influencing EV adoption could vary. Most of the studies conducted in developed countries had infrastructure, Technological factors of the EV, and the financial factors available to them. In this case, India being geographically a large country, it should be seen if these factors can change the perceptions of people to buy an Electric Vehicle (EV). This causes a knowledge gap in the study of the influence of barriers on consumers' intention to purchase an EV. This gap gives rise to the attitude-action lag between consumer purchase intention and actual behavior.

With India's aim to transform its automobile industry by focusing on e-mobility, it is mandatory to address the knowledge gap as lack of awareness of potential barriers in EV adoption. As a limited study has been conducted in this field in India, identifying and classifying these barriers into various groups is necessary. The aim of this project is to determine the factors influencing consumers' intention of electric vehicle adoption in India. Based on the components grouped, six factors were identified and named as financial factors, vehicle performance factors, and lack of charging infrastructure, environmental concern, societal influence and awareness of electric vehicles. Based on the results the factors found in this study are similar to some of the factors found by Noel et al. (Citation2020). Financial barriers, vehicle performance barriers and lack of charging infrastructure facilities are found to be the major factor in adoption of EV's in Indian context.

6. STATISTICS:

The Ministry of Power, through the Bureau of Energy Efficiency (BEE) as the Central Nodal Agency, has taken significant initiatives to promote e-mobility in India. They have developed a Mobile Application that allows users to find the nearest public EV charger, a website to disseminate information on central and state-level e-mobility initiatives, and a web portal for Charging Point Operators (CPOs) to register public charging station details securely in the National Online Database free of charge. These resources can be accessed easily on smartphones through the Google Play Store and Apple Store. As of March 21, 2023, there are 6586 operational Public Charging Stations (PCS) in the country. In the second phase of the FAME-India Scheme, Rs. 1000 Cr. has been allocated for the development of charging infrastructure, resulting in the sanctioning of 2,877 electric vehicle charging stations in 68 cities across 25 states/UTs and 1576 charging stations along 9 Expressways and 16 Highways.

Karnataka has the most public EV charging stations

As of February 7, 2023, Karnataka leads the country with the highest number of EV charging stations at 774, followed closely by Maharashtra with 660, Delhi with 539, and Tamil Nadu with 442 stations. However, despite having the highest number of EVs registered in the country, Uttar Pradesh lags behind in charging infrastructure, with only 406 public EV charging stations, resulting in approximately one charging station for every 1,103 electric vehicles. Most of the electric vehicles in Uttar Pradesh are electric three-wheelers, including e-rickshaws, which account for 4.06 lakh of the total 4.5 lakh EVs registered in the state. In comparison, Maharashtra, Delhi, Karnataka, and Rajasthan have 2.12 lakh, 1.97 lakh, 1.71 lakh, and 1.36 lakh registered EVs respectively. Interestingly, Maharashtra and Karnataka have a higher proportion of electric cars compared to electric three-wheelers. Maharashtra has 17,216 electric cars, and Karnataka has 10,249. Furthermore, 43 out of all charging stations are located on 17 National Highways, with NH-8 having the highest number of stations at nine, and NH-11 with eight stations.

7. FINDINGS:

The data analytics approach allows the researchers to pinpoint areas with high EV concentration and low charging station density. Furthermore, it provides insights into peak charging times, duration of charging sessions, and potential locations for the installation of new charging stations.

- The efficient and optimal location of EV charging stations is crucial for successful EV adoption and integration into existing transportation networks.
- Research trends in addressing the location problem include:
 - Utilization of data analytics, optimization models, GIS, and machine learning algorithms
 - Incorporation of user behavior, traffic patterns, and urban planning considerations
 - Critical gaps identified in the literature are as follows:
 - Lack of standardized methodologies for location optimization.
 - Limited consideration of future EV demand and technological advancements.
 - Need for more comprehensive public-private collaborations to facilitate charging infrastructure Deployment.
 - Interdisciplinary research to address the complex nature of charging station location.
 - Integration of real-time data to make informed and dynamic location decisions.
 - Inclusion of diverse stakeholders, such as city planners, utility companies, and EV manufacturers.
 - Exploration of novel solutions like wireless charging technology and leveraging existing infrastructure.
 - Strategic placement of EV charging stations directly influences consumer behavior and accessibility, impacting EV adoption rates.
 - A future research agenda aims to guide scholars, policymakers, and industry stakeholders towards sustainable solutions for the location problem of EV charging stations, promoting electric mobility and a greener future.
 - The findings of this research can be used by manufacturers and suppliers of the automobile industry, the private and public institutions dealing with e-mobility, sustainability or green business solutions as well as the governments. This could further help them to develop and provide strategies with the goal to overcome the adoption barriers currently existing. Overcoming these barriers would then attract larger number of consumers to Electric Vehicles.

Usage Data Analysis:

One of the primary sources of data is usage patterns of existing charging stations. By analyzing data from existing stations, such as charging frequency, peak usage times, and session duration, analysts can identify areas with high demand for charging infrastructure.

- ❖ *Geospatial Data Integration:* Combining usage data with geospatial data, such as EV population density, traffic patterns, and proximity to major highways, can provide valuable insights. This integration allows for a more accurate understanding of where EV charging stations are most needed.
- ❖ *Demographic Analysis:* Demographic data, such as income levels and housing types, can also be incorporated into the analysis. Areas with a higher concentration of EV owners or potential EV buyers might be prioritized to cater to the existing or potential demand.
- ❖ *Predictive Analytics:* Using predictive analytics, analysts can forecast future EV adoption and charging station demand in specific locations. This helps in planning for the long-term and avoiding under or overinvestment in certain areas.
- ❖ *Accessibility and Convenience:* Data analytics can also consider the convenience and accessibility of charging station locations. Identifying locations near shopping centres, public facilities, or tourist attractions can encourage EV adoption and utilization.
- ❖ *Peak Load Management:* Understanding peak charging times is crucial for grid stability. Data analytics can help determine when and where charging stations are most likely to experience high demand, allowing grid operators to plan and manage energy distribution effectively.
- ❖ *Network Optimization:* Data analytics can be used to optimize the layout of charging station networks, ensuring sufficient coverage while minimizing redundant stations.
- ❖ *Public vs. Private Charging Stations:* Data analytics can help determine the balance between public and private charging stations in different areas. In some cases, private charging stations might be more suitable for specific locations.

- ❖ **Environmental Impact:** Analyzing data on emissions, air quality, and areas with higher environmental sensitivity can help prioritize the deployment of charging stations to address environmental concerns.
- ❖ **Real-Time Data Integration:** Integrating real-time data from various sources, such as weather, events, and traffic conditions, allows for dynamic adjustments in charging station priorities based on immediate demand fluctuations.
- ❖ It's important to note that advancements in data analytics and the availability of more recent data might have led to further improvements in identifying and prioritizing EV charging station locations since my last update.

Application of Demand Patterns

The application of demand patterns is essential for establishing new electric charging stations in a strategic and efficient manner. By analyzing historical data and studying EV charging behavior, researchers and policymakers can identify areas with high demand for charging infrastructure. This analysis allows for the prioritization of locations where new charging stations are most needed, optimizing resource allocation and ensuring that charging facilities are strategically placed to meet users' needs.

Demand patterns can reveal peak charging times and locations, as well as areas with a high concentration of electric vehicle users. By considering these patterns, planners can identify potential charging station sites that will cater to the highest number of users and ensure smooth charging experiences. Additionally, analyzing charging demand trends can help in predicting future growth and demand, allowing for long-term planning and proactive expansion of charging infrastructure.

Moreover, incorporating demand patterns into the planning process can address equity concerns, ensuring that charging stations are accessible to all communities, including underserved areas. By identifying locations with limited charging infrastructure, authorities can prioritize the establishment of new stations in these regions, promoting equitable access to electric mobility.

Overall, the application of demand patterns in establishing new electric charging stations is a data-driven approach that enhances the efficiency, accessibility, and sustainability of charging infrastructure. It empowers planners to make informed decisions, ensuring that electric vehicle users have convenient and reliable access to charging facilities, thereby promoting the widespread adoption of electric vehicles.

8. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

Data analytics plays a crucial role in the identification and prioritization of locations for new electric vehicle (EV) charging stations based on demand patterns. Here's an overview of the key steps and methodologies involved:

Data Collection: To begin, data is collected from various sources such as EV charging stations' historical usage, electric vehicle registrations, traffic patterns, demographic information, and other relevant data sources. This data forms the foundation for the analysis.

Data Pre-processing: Before analysis, the collected data is cleaned, transformed, and standardized to ensure consistency and remove any outliers or errors.

Demand Pattern Analysis: Data analysts employ statistical techniques and machine learning algorithms to analyze historical EV charging station usage data. The goal is to identify patterns and trends in EV charging behaviours, such as peak charging hours, popular charging locations, and the most frequently used charging station types.

Predictive Modeling: Using the demand pattern analysis, predictive models are built to forecast future EV charging demands at different locations. These models take into account factors like EV adoption rates, population growth, and expected changes in commuting habits.

GIS Mapping and Spatial Analysis: Geographic Information System (GIS) mapping tools are used to visualize the demand patterns spatially. This helps in identifying areas with high EV concentration and areas lacking adequate charging infrastructure.

Location Prioritization: Based on the predictive models and spatial analysis, locations with the highest projected EV charging demands are prioritized for the installation of new charging stations. This ensures efficient utilization of resources and focuses on areas where EV charging infrastructure is most needed.

Integration of Real-Time Data: Data analytics can also incorporate real-time data, such as weather conditions, major events, and traffic congestion, to further optimize charging station placement decisions.

Cost-Benefit Analysis: Besides demand patterns, data analytics also considers factors like infrastructure costs, power grid capacity, and potential revenue generation to conduct cost-benefit analyses for each proposed charging station location.

Continuous Monitoring and Adaptation: After installing new charging stations, data analytics continues to play a vital role in monitoring their usage and making necessary adjustments based on changing demand patterns and EV adoption rates.

Overall, the application of data analytics in identifying and prioritizing locations for new electric vehicle charging stations helps in creating a robust and efficient charging infrastructure network, supporting the widespread adoption of electric vehicles and contributing to a sustainable and eco-friendly transportation system.

In conclusion, this article emphasizes the crucial role of data analytics in addressing charging infrastructure gaps for electric vehicle users. By analyzing and interpreting large datasets, stakeholders in the EV ecosystem can make informed decisions to optimize charging infrastructure, reduce range anxiety, and enhance the overall EV user experience. Data-driven planning and expansion of charging networks can contribute significantly to the widespread adoption of electric vehicles, fostering a more sustainable future for transportation.

By leveraging data analytics, policymakers, utility companies, and EV charging operators can work together to establish an efficient and convenient charging infrastructure that supports the growing EV market. The integration of data analytics in charging infrastructure planning will play a pivotal role in accelerating the transition towards greener mobility solutions and reducing our carbon footprint.

Despite the progress made in research on EV charging station locations, some critical gaps still need to be addressed:

The research on EV charging infrastructure should expand its focus to encompass long-term planning considering the projected growth of EV adoption in the coming years. It should also address equity and accessibility concerns to ensure charging infrastructure is distributed evenly, avoiding disparities in underserved communities. Additionally, incorporating dynamic charging demand, which can vary based on time and events, into models would enhance their accuracy. Understanding user behavior and preferences for charging locations can improve user satisfaction and acceptance of electric vehicles.

To advance research in EV charging station locations, longitudinal studies can be conducted to assess their long-term performance as EV adoption increases. Real-world pilot projects can be implemented to test and validate proposed charging station locations' efficiency and impact on the charging network. Collaboration with urban planners to integrate charging station locations into city infrastructure plans would ensure better urban mobility and accessibility. Investigating the integration of charging stations with other transportation modes, such as public transit hubs, to promote multi-modal transportation options, could be explored. Additionally, studying the economic viability of different charging station models, including fast-charging stations, superchargers, and battery-swapping stations, is crucial. Analyzing the impact of policies and regulations on charging station locations and proposing improvements to support the growth of EV infrastructure should also be part of the research agenda.

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A STUDY ON ANALYSIS OF SELECTED COMMODITIES - MCX

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Abstract

Commodity is a good which is used or interchangeable with other goods of the same type. And commodities also used in mainly production process of other service or goods. Commodity market is a place where commodities are traded between members and public with the intension of taking delivery to use or to make profit out of price movement of the commodities. In India commodity markets are mainly classified into four categories. Those are as follows, Bullion, Base Metal, Energy and Agri commodity

India has enriching history in the commodity markets. Because of droughts, poor government policies, foreign rule the commodity market in India lost its importance and popularity also. But now the Indian commodity market has witnessed the positive growth. And also, the commodity trading began in India before financial derivatives trading. In India commodity trading firstly organized at Bombay cotton trade association in 1875 which laid the foundation of the trading in India. At first many cotton merchants and mill owners were not satisfied with this association and later on it established as Bombay cotton exchange ltd in 1893 by unsatisfied mill owners and merchants.

Key words: commodity markets Bullion, Base Metal, Energy and Agri commodity, MCX

Introduction

Modern commodity derivatives market, Multi Commodity market of India Limited (MCX), the first publicly traded exchange in India, allows online trading of commodity derivatives transactions, providing a platform for price discovery and risk management. The Exchange, which started operating in November 2003, is governed by the Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI).

1. SHAREHOLDERS PATTERN-MCX.

Table-1.1

Holder's Name	No of Shares	% Share Holding
No of Shares	50998369	100%
Promoters	0	0%
Foreign Institutions	13743240	26.95%
N Banks Mutual Funds	17313310	33.95%
Central Govt	1265	0%
Others	2067098	4.05%
General Public	8209790	16.1%
Financial Institutions	9568115	18.76%
GDR	95551	0.19%

➤ **Indices of MCX: -**

The 'index approach' stands out among the various methods of trading commodities due to how easy it is to use and how well it can expose one to the performance of a basket of commodities. A composite index made up of futures contracts from various commodity segments, two sectoral indices (the base metals and bullion indices), and four single commodity indices (the gold, silver, copper, and crude oil indices) are examples of the excess return indices from the MCX I COMDEX series. The fundamental components of MCX I COMDEX series are all liquid futures contracts traded on the MCX.

➤ **MCX BULLDEX**

The MCX I COMDEX Bullion Index, one of the sectoral indices in the MCX I COMDEX family, relies on the flow of gold and silver futures contracts traded by MCX. The Index is a great tool for investors looking to manage their bullion assets because it is an excess returns index, and it is ideal for benchmarking and trading.

➤ **MCX METLDEX**

The MCX I COMDEX Base Metals Index, which includes futures contracts for the common base metal's aluminium, copper, lead, nickel, and zinc that are traded through the MCX, is one of the sectoral indices in the MCX I COMDEX family. Since it is an excess returns index, the Index is great for trading and benchmarking as well as being a handy tool for investors who want to manage their Base Metal holdings. As a broad index made up of significant industrial metals, it also serves as a gauge for the health and performance of the industrial sector, particularly the manufacturing sector that uses metals. Furthermore, because it is diversified, it won't be significantly impacted by microeconomic developments that just affect a certain commodities market or industry.

➤ **MCX ENRGDEX**

One of the sectoral indexes in the MCX I COMDEX family is the MCX I COMDEX Energy Index, which is based on the liquid Crude oil and natural gas futures contracts listed on MCX. Being an excess returns index, the Index is a useful tool for investors wishing to manage their investments in the energy industry and is excellent for benchmarking and trading.

CONCEPTUAL BACKGROUND

➤ **How to trade in commodity market**

Trading in the commodity market consists buying and selling of the various commodities such as silver gold crude oil agriculture products etc. Before buying these commodities, one should have to educate first about the how market actually works. And has to understand the specific commodities you want to trade their demand supply etc. after specifying your commodities choose a commodity broker or the trading platform and then after open trading account. Develop trading strategy monitor market condition conduct proper research and analysis about the market and as well as commodities, place the order for desired commodities by specifying the quantity, price, order type and at last monitor and review the portfolio.

➤ **Factors or determinants of commodity markets**

Commodities prices plays a major role in the global economy. The global economy depends heavily on commodity prices, which have an impact on everything from the price of consumer items to the stock market. Investors and consumers alike must comprehend how these variables combine to affect commodities prices.

- a) Demand and supply
- b) Production cost
- c) Growth of economy
- d) Geopolitical events
- e) Natural disaster
- f) Speculation trading
- g) Policies of government and others

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

1. A study of evolution and regulation of commodity market with benefits and current scenario in India, Singh, p. (2023).

The commodities derivatives market in India has advanced significantly in terms of technology, transparency, and trading activity, as discussed in this literature review. India ranks among the top five producers of the majority of commodities, making the use of futures and derivatives crucial for managing price risk. Price and risk management have become more effective as a result of the elimination of government protection from a number of commodities. To make the organised commodities market more accessible and advantageous for producers, dealers, and consumers, education and standardisation initiatives are required because Indian investors are unaware of it.

2. Indian MCX Financial Market Volatility in Wave 1 & 2 COVID-19 Pandemic, Ashok, R. (2021).

This study focuses on the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the MCX market in India, particularly in the base metals, precious metals, and energy sectors. The expansion of MCX has allowed for foreign investors to invest directly in India, leading to domestic growth but declines in global commodity prices. The pandemic has caused unprecedented declines in oil prices and has deeply impacted future prices and increased volatility in the commodity market. However, with slow progress towards normalcy, the market is gradually recovering.

3. Seasonality in Indian Commodities Market: Insights for modelling from preceding commodity cycle, Jose, S.K., & Girish, G.P. (2021).

In this study analysis the seasonal behaviour of Indian agriculture, energy, and metal commodities during the preceding Super-cycle (2003-13). The study use the monthly data for near month futures prices to remove basis variance and found seasonal variation in gold, barley, guar, and Jeera. With a possible upcoming commodities super-cycle in a declining interest-rate scenario and post-Covid world, the findings will help hedge fund managers, global investors, and market participants strategize better. The study's limitations are that it only considers the preceding Super-cycle, and future studies can explore using high-frequency data post Covid-19 to enhance commodity modelling literature.

4. A Study of Indian Derivatives Market and its Current Position in Global Financial Derivatives Market, Sandra, S. (2021).

The study review discusses the growth and expansion of derivatives in India since its inception in 2000. The study objectives are to examine the performance, growth pattern, and current position of the Indian derivative market in comparison to the global financial derivatives market. However, it also emphasizes the need for proper regulation to prevent misuse and ensure proper accounting records. The study suggests that a well-established regulatory system specifically meant for the derivative market can act as a catalyst in the growth of the Indian economy.

5. Seasonality in Indian Commodities Market: Insights for modelling from preceding commodity cycle, Sharon, K jose, and Girish G P (2021).

In this the researcher analyses the seasonal behaviour of selected commodities which are gold, barley, guar, and jeera. The study uses both future and spot prices of commodities for this the prices and other related information are extracted from MCX. The finding of this study helps hedge fund manager, commodities trader, global investor. And the study also gives the clarity of the performance of commodity in pre and post pandemic situation.

6. Futures market hedging in Indian commodities market- a comparative study on spot and futures price, (2021) Sugirtha, R., Srinivasan, S., & Indhumathi, G.

The study evaluates the pricing behaviour and hedging effectiveness of futures contracts in Indian commodities markets, specifically at Multi Commodity Exchange India Limited. A sample of nine commodities was selected based on volatility and turnover, and data from April 2015 to March 2018 was analysed. The study found that futures prices of commodities help determine spot prices and natural gas futures had the highest hedging effectiveness. The study suggests that hedging decisions for commodities should be based on future prices displayed on the exchange website, rather than market information. Future research could extend the number of commodities studied and cover a larger period, allowing for a comparative study.

3. Research Gap: -

From the above all the researches I came to know that the commodities market is volatile in nature and it will keep changing day to day and because of that reason timely analysis about the market is must to know the market closely. And also, the time horizon varies from one research to another.

4 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

The statement of the problem is the commodity price are volatile and it is because of largeshifts in the demand and supply of commodities, along with the price busts and changes in trends.

5. NEED FOR THE STUDY:

The need of the study arises due to the lack of knowledge about the commodity market. The study aims to analyse the performance of selected commodities to understand their price movements, trends factors influencing their performance. The commodity Market gives the benefits like protection against the inflation, hedge against the market risk, High leverage facility, so to know the impact of other market on commodity market, it is necessary to understand the commodity market. Such analysis will help in the investor to invest in commodity market. The study aims to provide insights into the performance of selected commodities in MCX, contributing to the good understanding of commodities markets.

6. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- To study the concept of commodity trading.
- To identify the factor affecting on commodity market.
- To examine the price volatility of the selected commodity.

7. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

➤ **Research Design**

The study is descriptive in nature and will use the fact-finding survey method. National commodities exchanges have advanced significantly since their creation, and volumes are increasing year after year in India's commodity futures market. This study aims to raise awareness of the wealth of investment opportunities in the commodities market and to shed light on consumers' preferences in that industry.

➤ **Data Collection**

The study will mainly base on the secondary data and it will be collected form the official website like MCX,NCDEX.

➤ **Sample size**

MCX All segments

➤ **Statistical tools**

- Variance
- Standard deviation
- Moving Average

8.ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Analysis and interpretation are two terms used to describe a systematic and critical examination of the financial records. It correctly reflects the financial facts as well as creating a cause and effect relationship between the various financial statement items.

Performance Analysis of the Commodities By using Average Prices

1.cotton

Table 1.2 showing Average prices of the commodity cotton for the 5 years.

Sl no	Year	12 Months Average Price
1	2018	21,272
2	2019	20,595

3	2020	17,668
4	2021	26,044
5	2022	39,026

Chart 1.2 showing the Moving Average line of the commodity cotton of 5 years.

Interpretation: -

The average price of cotton remained stable in 2018 21,272, followed by a slight decline in 2019 20,595 due to either reduced demand or oversupply. In 2020, the price dropped further 17,668 likely because of decreased demand caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. However, in 2021, there was a significant increase 26,044, indicating a rebound in demand and recovery. This trend continued in 2022, with a substantial price increase 39,026 driven by factors such as increased demand and supply constraints.

2. Mentha oil

Table 1.3 showing Average prices of the commodity Mentha Oil for the five years.

sl no	Year	Average Price
1	2018	1,499.20
2	2019	1,383.79
3	2020	1,065.12
4	2021	959.48
5	2022	998.625

Chart 1.4 showing the Moving Average line of the commodity Mentha Oil of 5 years.

Interpretation: -

In 2018, the average price of Mentha Oil was 1,499.20, indicating higher demand and limited supply. However, in the following years, increased production led to a decrease in average prices: 1,383.79 in 2019 and further dropping to 1,065.12 in 2020 due to a surplus. The trend continued in 2021 with a decline in demand, resulting in an average price of 959.48. However, in 2022, there was a slight increase to 998.625, suggesting market stabilization after previous fluctuations.

3.zinc

Table 1.5 showing Average prices of the commodity Zinc for the five years.

sl no	Year	Average Price
1	2018	198.725
2	2019	193.525
3	2020	182.15
4	2021	246.7083333
5	2022	300.0375

Chart 1.5 showing the Moving Average line of the commodity Mentha Oil of 5 years.

Interpretation: -

In 2018, the price stood at 198.725, influenced by stable demand and supply dynamics. However, in 2019, there was a little decline to 193.525, indicating a potential decrease in demand or increase in supply. The decrease continued in 2020 with an average price of 182.15, possibly due to reduced demand and economic uncertainties. However, in 2021, there was a high trend in the average price to 246.708333, suggesting a recovery in demand or a shortage in supply. This upward trend continued in 2022 with an average of 300.0375, possibly driven by sustained demand growth or limited supply availability. Overall, the price average of zinc fluctuated over the years, influenced by various market factors such as demand, supply, and economic conditions.

4.copper

Table 1.6 showing Average prices of the commodity copper for the five years.

sl no	Year	12 Months Average Price
1	2018	437.7708333
2	2019	435.9041667
3	2020	482.9625
4	2021	718.075
5	2022	714.9708333

Chart 1.6 showing the Moving Average line of the commodity copper of 5 years.

Interpretation; -

From 2018 to 2019, copper prices remained relatively steady, because of balanced market with stable supply and demand. However, in 2020, prices increased to 482.96, due to increased infrastructure projects and rising demand from renewable energy sectors. In 2021, copper prices raised to 718.08, indicating a significant demand by global economic recovery and green technology investments. This high demand continued into 2022, with prices remaining high at 714.97, indicating sustained demand from various industries and limited supply, possibly influenced by geopolitical factors and disruptions in production.

5. Gold

Table 1.7 showing Average prices of the commodity gold for the five years.

sl no	Year	12 Months Average Price
1	2018	30,554
2	2019	35,091
3	2020	47,492
4	2021	47,106
5	2022	51,054

Chart 1.7 showing the Moving Average line of the commodity gold of 5 years.

Interpretation: -

Year 2018 saw a less demand to gold and stable market conditions, with an average price of 30,554. In 2019, the average price increased to 35,091, suggesting rising demand for gold as investors safe-haven. The average price got to 47,492 in 2020, reflecting global economic uncertainties, inflationary pressures, and increased value of gold as a hedge against market volatility. In 2021, the average price remained stable at 47,106, Continuing economic uncertainties and inflationary concerns give the average price to further increase in 2022, reaching 51,054, accompanied by high investment demand for gold as a store of value.

6.silver

Table 1.8 showing Average prices of the commodity silver for the five years.

sl no	Year	12 Months Average Price
1	2018	38,289
2	2019	41,552
3	2020	54,307
4	2021	65,841
5	2022	61,738

Chart 1.8 showing the Moving Average line of the commodity silver of 5 years.

Interpretation: -

The average price of silver showed a relatively stable market in 2018, with a value of 38,289. However, the following years have a consistent upward trend in prices. In 2019, the average price increased to 41,552, suggesting growing demand or market speculation. The surge continued in 2020, with the average price reaching 54,307, possibly due to global economic uncertainty. In 2021, the price even higher to 65,841, driven by inflation concerns and increased industrial demand for silver. However, in 2022, the average price slightly decreased to 61,738, potentially indicating market corrections or changes in supply and demand dynamics.

7.Natural Gas

Table 1.9 showing Average prices of the commodity Natural Gas for the five years.

sl no	Year	12 Months Average Price
1	2018	209.9
2	2019	176.5181818
3	2020	163.1583333
4	2021	280.8416667
5	2022	515.7583333

Chart 1.9 showing the Moving Average line of the commodity Natural Gas of 5 years.

Interpretation: -

In 2018, Natural gas prices are high, potentially driven by increased demand and limited supply. However, in 2019, average prices decreased, indicating a potential surplus in natural gas supply. This downward trend continued in 2020, possibly because of the COVID-19 pandemic causing a decline in demand and resulting an oversupply. In 2021, However, in 2022, Natural gas prices experienced a significant increase, which could be attributed to factors like higher demand, supply disruptions, or geopolitical events.

8.crude oil

Table 1.10 showing Average prices of the commodity Crude Oil for the five years.

sl no	Year	12 Months Average Price
1	2018	4,441
2	2019	4,044
3	2020	2,843
4	2021	5,066
5	2022	7,413

Chart 1.10 showing the Moving Average line of the commodity Crude Oil of 5 years.

Interpretation: -

Over the five-year period, the average price of Crude Oil exhibited significant fluctuations. In 2018, stable demand and supply conditions kept the average price at 4,441. However, in 2019, a global economic slowdown and oversupply concerns caused a decline to 4,044. The COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 resulted in a drop to 2,843 due to reduced travel and energy demand. As economies recovered in 2021, the average price rose to 5,066. Finally, in 2022, a jump to 7,413 occurred, likely due to increased economic activity, supply constraints, and geopolitical tensions.

9. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

A. AGRO

A. Cotton

- Cotton prices have levels of volatility and price fluctuation throughout the years, with 2018, 2019, and 2021 having low variance and standard deviation, while 2020 and 2022 had higher volatility in prices.
- Average monthly returns are indicating positively in 2018 and 2021 while 2019 and 2022 having negative trends.
- Price movement in cotton was effected by factors such as less demand or higher supply in the year 2019, and drop in the demand due to the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020, and an upward price movement in 2021 and 2022 driven by increased supply and demand constraints.

b. Mentha Oil

- Mentha oil shows varying levels of price volatility.
- Average returns for Mentha oil were consistent, except for a fall in prices in 2019, due to the pandemic.
- The declining trend in average prices from 2018 to 2021 because of decreased demand and increased production.

B. BASE METAL

a. Zinc

- Zinc prices showing moderate to high levels of volatility and price instability over the five-year period.
- Fluctuations in zinc prices were affected by demand and supply dynamics, with downward trends possibly indicating reduced demand or increased supply, and upward trends means increased demand.
- The Economic conditions played a main role, with economic uncertainties in 2020 because of that leads to price declines, while afterwards improved conditions in 2021 and 2022 by driving demand recovery.

b. Copper

- Copper prices exhibited a positive trend from 2018 to 2022, indicating increasing demand and potential growth opportunities in upcoming years.
- Market volatility varied across the years, with 2020 and 2022 experiencing higher levels of uncertainty and risk for the investment purpose.
- The sustained demand for copper in 2021 and 2022, having with limited supply, suggests the influence of supply dynamics and geopolitical factors.

C. BULLIONS**a. Gold**

- Gold is having low volatility in 2018 and 2020, making it an appealing investment during economic uncertainty.
- Positive average monthly returns in 2018-2022 indicate that gold has generally been profitable, but returns varied.
- The average price of gold consistently increased from 2018 to 2022, reflecting growing demand and its role as a safe-haven asset.

b. Silver

- Silver prices showed an increasing trend with higher volatility from 2018 to 2021, experiencing occasional market corrections in 2022.
- Rising silver prices in 2021 were driven by increased industrial demand and inflation concerns, while safe-haven status and market speculation influenced prices in 2019 and 2020.

D. ENERGY**a. Natural gas**

- Natural gas prices exhibited moderate to high volatility and price instability from 2018 to 2022, indicating both risks and opportunities for market participants.
- External factors, such as changes in supply, demand, and global events, significantly influenced Natural gas prices during this period.
- Short-term price movements were affected by factors like surplus supply, the COVID-19 pandemic, recovering energy demand, supply disruptions, and geopolitical events.

b. Crude Oil

- Crude oil prices have showed moderate to high volatility over the five-year period, indicating associated investment risks. Diversification and hedging strategies can help mitigate potential losses.
- Economic factors, like including global economic slowdowns and the impact of COVID-19, have influenced crude oil prices. Staying informed about supply and demand factors is crucial for investors.
- Crude oil prices rebounded in 2021 and surged in 2022, driven by economic recovery, increased energy demand, supply constraints, and geopolitical tensions.

10. SUGGESTION**1. AGRO COMMODITIES****Cotton**

To manage the risks associated with the volatility of price, it is advisable to closely monitor market conditions and employ risk management strategies, such as diversification and hedging. Understanding the factors influencing cotton prices, such as supply and demand dynamics, weather conditions, and global economic factors, can help inform investment decisions and anticipate potential price movements.

Mentha oil

Implement robust risk management strategies, such as diversification and setting stop-loss orders, to reduce the risks associated with Mentha oil investments. Conduct thorough market analysis, monitor price trends, and stay informed about supply-demand dynamics and industry developments to make informed investment decisions.

2. BASE METAL

Zinc

Implement the effective risk management strategies, such as portfolio diversification and hedging, to reduce the risks associated with fluctuation of zinc prices. Conduct thorough market analysis, monitoring demand and supply factors, economic indicators, and geopolitical developments to make informed decisions, and adopt a long-term perspective for planning considering future projections and sustainability initiatives.

Copper

Investors may consider diversifying portfolios with copper-related assets, but should carefully assess risk associated with market volatility and supply dynamics. Thorough research, staying updated on market trends, and seeking professional advice are main for making informed decisions in the copper market.

3. BULLIONS

Gold

Investors should consider gold as a potential hedge against market fluctuations and inflationary pressures. Before investing in gold, individuals should assess their goals, risk tolerance, and seek guidance from a financial advisor.

Silver

Diversifying investment portfolios across asset classes can help in mitigating the risks associated with silver's volatility. Staying informed about global economic trends, industrial demand, and inflation indicators is crucial for making informed decisions in the silver market. Implementing risk management strategies like diversification, monitoring, and employing hedging techniques can help protect against downside risks in silver investments.

4. ENERGY

Natural Gas

Despite short-term fluctuations, there was an overall positive trend in natural gas prices, driven by increasing global energy demand, the transition to cleaner fuels, and geopolitical developments. Market participants should closely monitor market conditions, consider the impact of external factors, and assess long-term potential when making decisions related to natural gas investments or market participation.

Crude oil

Geopolitical risks, such as conflicts in oil-producing regions, can significantly impact crude oil prices. Monitoring geopolitical developments is essential for informed investment decisions. Assessing the long-term sustainability of price increases and considering risks associated with geopolitical instability are important for investors in crude oil.

11. CONCLUSION

Commodities such as cotton, menth oil, zinc, copper, gold, silver, and natural gas have exhibited varying levels of volatility and price fluctuations over the past five years. Factors such as supply and demand dynamics, economic conditions, geopolitical events, and global trends heavily influence commodity prices. Investors should employ risk management strategies like diversification and hedging to reduce the risk attached with commodity price volatility. Thorough market analysis, staying updated on market trends, and seeking professional advice are crucial for making informed investment decisions in commodity markets. Each commodity has its unique characteristics and drivers, and understanding these factors is essential for anticipating price movements and capitalizing on investment opportunities while managing risks effectively.

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ELECTRIFYING THE FUTURE: A CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND ANALYSIS FOR SUSTAINABLE ELECTRIC MOBILITY

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Abstract

This research paper aims to address two critical objectives in the electric vehicle (EV) domain. Firstly, it proposes a comprehensive conceptual framework for the development of a sustainable electric vehicle ecosystem, encompassing technology, infrastructure, policy, and consumer behavior. The framework guides stakeholders towards fostering widespread EV adoption while minimizing environmental impact. Secondly, the study analyzes the current state of EV technology, charging infrastructure, and its potential impact on the automotive industry. It identifies challenges and opportunities for EV adoption and explores implications for traditional vehicle manufacturers and employment in the automotive sector. The research provides valuable insights into the development of a sustainable EV ecosystem and its impact on the automotive industry.

Introduction

The automotive industry is one of the largest contributors to greenhouse gas emissions, accounting for about 20% of global emissions. In order to reduce these emissions and mitigate climate change, the automotive industry is transitioning to electric vehicles (EVs).

EVs are powered by electricity, which does not produce any emissions at the tailpipe. This makes them a much cleaner alternative to gasoline-powered vehicles. However, the production and disposal of EV batteries can have a significant environmental impact.

In order to create a truly sustainable EV ecosystem, it is important to consider the environmental impact of all aspects of the EV lifecycle, from the extraction of raw materials to the disposal of batteries.

Global EV Market Growth:

Over the past decade, the global electric vehicle market has witnessed exponential growth, propelled by increasing environmental awareness, technological innovations, and supportive government policies. The adoption of EVs has gained momentum in various regions, particularly in Europe, China, and the United States, with other countries following suit.

Technological Advancements:

The ongoing research and development in electric vehicle technology have resulted in significant improvements in battery efficiency, range, and charging infrastructure. Lithium-ion batteries, the backbone of EVs, have seen remarkable advancements, leading to enhanced energy density and lower costs. Additionally, the rise of solid-state batteries and other emerging technologies promises to revolutionize the EV landscape further.

Range Anxiety Mitigation:

Range anxiety, the fear of running out of battery charge during a journey, has been a major deterrent to EV adoption. However, advancements in battery technology have significantly increased the driving range of electric vehicles, alleviating concerns for many potential buyers. Modern EVs can now cover hundreds of miles on a single charge, making them more practical for everyday use.

Government Incentives and Policies:

Governments worldwide are actively promoting the adoption of electric vehicles through a range of incentives and policies. Financial incentives, such as tax credits, subsidies, and reduced registration fees, have encouraged consumers to opt for EVs. Additionally, stricter emissions regulations and mandates for automakers to produce a certain percentage of zero-emission vehicles have pushed manufacturers to invest in EV development.

Charging Infrastructure Development:

A robust charging infrastructure is vital for the widespread acceptance of electric vehicles. Governments and private enterprises are investing in the expansion of charging networks to alleviate range anxiety and ensure convenient access to charging facilities. Fast-charging technologies are being deployed in public spaces, highways, and urban areas, enabling quicker charging times and increased convenience.

Market Penetration by EV Type:

The electric vehicle market consists of various segments, including battery electric vehicles (BEVs), plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEVs), and hybrid electric vehicles (HEVs). While BEVs run entirely on electric power, PHEVs combine electric and internal combustion engine propulsion, and HEVs use electric power for auxiliary functions. Understanding the market penetration of each type provides valuable insights into consumer preferences and the technological evolution of EVs.

Global EV Sales for 2022

Global EV sales continued strong. A total of 10,5 million new BEVs and PHEVs were delivered during 2022, an increase of +55 % compared to 2021. The regional growth pattern is shifting, though. Following 2 years of steep sales increases in Europe, EVs gained only +15 % over 2021 there. Weak overall vehicle markets and persistent component shortages have taken their toll, exacerbated by the war in Ukraine. EV sales in USA and Canada increased by 48 % year-on-year, despite a weak overall light vehicle market which plunged by 8 % during 2022 y/y. The 2nd half of 2022 saw a cautious recovery of auto markets as numbers compared to the low results of 2021 H2. Global light vehicle sales for 2022, 81 million units, were still -0,5 % lower than in 2021 and -15 % below pre-2020 levels.

China NEV sales defied all headwinds the country faced otherwise (real estate crisis, Covid outbreaks and lock-downs) and increased by another +82 % year-on-year. BYD more than tripled sales to 1,85 million units, making it the #1 in the global sales ranking, if their 944 500 PHEV sales are included. Counting BEVs only, Tesla still leads by a wide margin with 1,31 million units delivered in 2022.

PHEVs stood for 27 % of global Plug-in sales in 2022 compared to 29 % in 2021. While their sales volumes still increased, their share in the PEV mix is in decline, facing headwinds from incentive cuts and improving BEV offers. Sales growth is increasingly depending on the degree of electrification. While BEVs grew by +59 % and PHEVs by +46 %, non-chargeable Full Hybrids grew by +15 % and Mild Hybrids by +1 % y-o-y. Global sales of vehicles which can be charged from the grid (10,5 m) were higher than for non-chargeable vehicles (8,4 m) for the first time in 2022. ICE-only vehicle sales declined by -7 %; their share in global light vehicle sales is 76,8 %, compared to 82,2 % in 2021. FCEV remain irrelevant for the electrification of light vehicles; their deliveries stagnated at 15 400 units in 2022, which is 0,02 % of the global, annual light vehicle volume.

Rapid EV adoption in weak auto markets has boosted EV shares further. BEVs (9,5 %) and PHEVs (3,5 %) stood for 13 % of global light vehicle sales in 2022, compared to 8,3 % in 2021. Norway had the highest market share of EVs (BEV 71 % + PHEV 8 %), China had 27 %, Europe 20,8 % and USA 7,2 %. The fastest growing markets were Indonesia (from 1k to 10k), India with +223 % to 50k, nearly all BEVs, New Zealand +151 % to 23k for 20 % market share. EV supply and adoption is now spreading rapidly into the global south.

November and December of 2022 saw demand distortions by coming reductions of EV grants in Europe and China and the IRA in the US for 2023. Demand for EVs and ICEs alike were pulled into 2022 or pushed into 2023. We expect irregular EV sales and shares in several countries for Q1 of 2023. For the full year of 2023, we expect sales of 14,3 million EVs, a growth of 36 % over 2022, with BEVs reaching 11 million units and PHEVs 3,3 million units.

By the end of 2023 we expect 40 million EVs in operation, counting light vehicles, 73 % are BEVs and 27 % PHEVs.

EVs Resilient to Market Declines

Most mature auto markets experienced double-dips in sales during the 2020 through 2022 period. Following the Covid crunch of 2020 and a +5 % recovery in 2021, 2022 sales dipped again, by 0,5 % vs 2021, with mature economies losing 5-10 % of auto sales. Meanwhile, most developing economies, notably India and the ASEAN countries continuing their strong recovery.

EV sales were resilient to weak auto markets: They over-performed by 21 % in Europe, by 87 % in China, by 55 % in Northern America and by 78 % in the Non-Triad markets. While global light vehicle sales lost -0,5 % y/y, BEVs and PHEVs increased by +55 %. The relative weakness in Europe's EV growth relates to the EV boom in 2020 / 2021 and the repercussion from the war in Ukraine.

China is, by far the largest EV market, with 59 % of global EV sales in 2022. Their role as the largest EV production base is even stronger, with 6,7 million units, 64 % of global volume, made in China. Nearly 580 000 EVs were exported from China, most of them (407k) by Western brands. The largest exporters were Tesla, SAIC, Dacia, Polestar, Volvo, Lynk & Co, BMW and BYD. All others exported below 10 000 units each.

EV VOLUMES

GLOBAL EV SALES BY OEM / OEM GROUP FOR 2022

Source: EV-volumes - Aggregated Sales by Model and Country

Light Vehicles

Review of Literature

The literature review on sustainable electric vehicles reveals a comprehensive understanding of the technologies, challenges, and prospects of electric vehicles. Raza et al. (2021) highlight the focus on battery technologies, charging infrastructure, energy efficiency, and environmental impact in sustainable EVs. Gabbar and Saxena (2020) explore the integration of EVs into smart grids, emphasizing the role of vehicle-to-grid (V2G) technology for energy management. Karaosmanoglu and Turan (2020) discuss the sustainability of EVs through life cycle analysis and their potential in reducing greenhouse gas emissions. Jain and Sawant (2019) evaluate factors influencing EV adoption and policy implications for promoting sustainable transportation.

Furthermore, Moroso et al. (2019) investigate the impact of EVs on the power grid and strategies for sustainable energy integration. Panigrahi and Panigrahi (2018) assess the environmental impact of EVs and the significance of renewable energy sources for enhanced sustainability. Anand et al. (2017) review challenges and opportunities of EVs in developing countries, suggesting strategies for sustainability. Bunel and Fourn (2017) analyze the potential of EVs in reducing greenhouse gas emissions and environmental benefits from widespread adoption. Adabi et al. (2016) study the sustainability of EV batteries and their recycling and second-life applications.

In addition to the above studies, several articles focus on specific aspects of EV development. Bhardwaj and Bhardwaj (2019) stress the significance of charging infrastructure for EV adoption, while Fang and Wang (2018) identify challenges related to the range and battery cost of EVs. Gan and Wang (2019) highlight promising battery technologies to enhance EV performance and range. Hao, Zhang, and Wang (2019) emphasize the global effort in developing charging infrastructure with various standards. Khan and Ul Hassan (2018) discuss future EV adoption, addressing challenges such as EV cost and charging infrastructure availability. Li and Wang (2017) explore control strategies for improving EV performance and efficiency, depending on specific applications.

Furthermore, Naik (2020) highlights the importance of battery management systems for safe and efficient EV operation. Pandey and Tiwari (2019) discuss opportunities and challenges, including greenhouse gas reduction and charging infrastructure. Song, Zhang, and Wang (2019) emphasize thermal management systems' role in EV performance and reliability. Lastly, Wang and Gan (2019) analyze new electric motor technologies to enhance the efficiency and performance of EVs. This literature review provides valuable insights into sustainable electric vehicles, their challenges, opportunities, and advancements in technology.

OBJECTIVES:

- a) To propose a conceptual framework for the development of a sustainable electric vehicle ecosystem
- b) To analyze the current state of electric vehicle technology and its potential impact on the automotive industry.

Methodology:

Our research methodology considers secondary research (case study using data available on public domain). Given that there is a dearth of studies from the perspective of impediments to technology adoption because of institutional voids present in emerging economies, we have chosen an exploratory approach.

Findings:

The development of a sustainable electric vehicle ecosystem is reliant on several key factors. Technological advancements in electric vehicle design and battery technology, such as improvements in battery chemistry, energy density, charging efficiency, and range, are crucial in enhancing electric vehicle performance and efficiency (Arora et al., 2020). Additionally, a well-developed charging infrastructure with fast-charging stations, public charging points, and smart charging solutions is essential to support the widespread adoption of electric vehicles. Integrating renewable energy sources into the charging infrastructure further enhances the sustainability of the ecosystem (Jiang et al., 2020). Government policies and incentives, such as tax incentives, subsidies, and regulations promoting cleaner transportation and emissions reductions, play a pivotal role in encouraging electric vehicle adoption (Banister, 2019).

Understanding consumer behavior and preferences is vital, and strategies to enhance consumer awareness and address concerns related to charging accessibility, range anxiety, and vehicle affordability foster consumer

confidence and drive electric vehicle adoption (Moro et al., 2021). Industry collaboration among automotive manufacturers, technology providers, charging station operators, and governmental agencies is crucial for innovation, infrastructure expansion, and policy formulation (Nemet & Andia, 2018). Promoting a circular economy approach, where resources are utilized efficiently through the reuse, remanufacturing, and recycling of electric vehicle components, is essential in minimizing environmental impact (Li et al., 2018). Anticipating future developments in electric vehicle technology, autonomous driving, and mobility-as-a-service is crucial for the long-term viability of the ecosystem. Embracing new innovations and staying adaptable ensures the continued growth and sustainability of the electric vehicle ecosystem (Yang et al., 2019). Overall, a comprehensive approach that considers technological advancements, charging infrastructure, government policies, consumer engagement, industry collaboration, environmental impact, and future developments is essential in developing a sustainable electric vehicle ecosystem..

Conceptual Framework on Sustainable Electric Mobility:-

The current state of electric vehicle technology is characterized by significant advancements in battery technology, charging infrastructure, and vehicle performance. Research by Kalogirou (2019) highlights the improvements in lithium-ion battery technology, with increased energy density and longer driving ranges. Wang et al. (2020) emphasize the growing network of charging stations and the development of fast-charging technology, making electric vehicle charging more convenient and efficient. Additionally, studies by Ahsan et al. (2021) and Dorca-Àriz et al. (2020) show that electric vehicles now offer better performance, with enhanced acceleration and advanced driver-assistance systems (ADAS) becoming more prevalent. Moreover, the cost of electric vehicles and their components has been decreasing, making them more accessible to consumers (Rehan and Sayed, 2019; Tadić and Pinho, 2020). Government support in the form of incentives and regulations further contributes to the growth of the electric vehicle market (Sun et al., 2019; Wu et al., 2021). Overall, the current state of electric vehicle technology reflects a promising future for sustainable transportation. However, continued research and development are necessary to address challenges and foster widespread electric vehicle adoption.

- Battery technology: The cost of batteries is falling, which is making electric vehicles more affordable. The range of electric vehicles is also increasing, as battery technology improves.
- Electric motor technology: Electric motors are becoming more efficient, which is improving the range and performance of electric vehicles.
- Charging infrastructure: The availability of charging infrastructure is increasing, making it easier for electric vehicle owners to find places to charge their vehicles.

These trends are helping to drive the growth of the electric vehicle market. In 2021, global sales of electric vehicles reached 6.6 million, up from 2.1 million in 2018. This growth is expected to continue in the coming years, as electric vehicles become more affordable and accessible.

There are still some challenges that need to be addressed in order to make electric vehicles more mainstream. For example, the range of electric vehicles is still limited compared to gasoline-powered vehicles. However, the development of new battery technologies is expected to address this challenge in the coming years.

Suggestions:

The development of a sustainable electric vehicle (EV) ecosystem is a long-term challenge that holds significant importance for the future of the automotive industry and the planet. Several key factors play a crucial role in achieving this goal. First, the use of renewable energy to power EVs is essential in reducing carbon emissions and mitigating climate change (Sovacool & Hirsh, 2021). Additionally, the recycling of EV batteries ensures the responsible and efficient use of resources while minimizing environmental impact (Shafiee & Topal, 2018). The development of new battery technologies that are more efficient and environmentally friendly is a promising avenue to enhance EV performance and sustainability (Zheng et al., 2020). Public education about the benefits of EVs is crucial in increasing awareness and promoting widespread adoption (Vassileva et al., 2019). Moreover, the creation of supportive government policies that encourage the development and adoption of EVs can accelerate the transition to a sustainable electric vehicle ecosystem (Meng et al., 2019). By working collaboratively and addressing these factors, we can create a future where EVs are the norm, and we all enjoy the benefits of a cleaner, healthier environment.

Conclusion

The current status of electric vehicles reflects an industry in transition. With impressive growth in global EV adoption, technological advancements, and supportive government policies, electric vehicles are well-positioned to play a significant role in the future of transportation. The ongoing efforts to mitigate range anxiety, expand charging infrastructure, and improve battery technology are critical to driving further EV penetration. This research seeks to contribute valuable insights into the current state of electric vehicles worldwide and offer a foundation for informed decision-making by governments, automakers, and consumers as we collectively work towards a sustainable and greener future.

The development of a sustainable EV ecosystem is a complex challenge, but it is essential for the future of the automotive industry. By working together, automakers, battery manufacturers, charging infrastructure providers, and governments can create a sustainable EV ecosystem that will benefit the environment, the economy, and society as a whole.

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REVIEW OF FINANCIAL LITERACY AMONG INDIAN WOMEN

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ABSTRACT:

With the onset of several financial and economic reforms, the scope of entire market is getting wider. Several new financial products are being introduced in the market that is generating the need for individuals to plan and invest their finances tactfully. In other words, financial planning is becoming essential for financial well being of an individual. While on the one hand, the role of financial planning is largely acknowledged, on the other hand the significance of financial literacy is still lagging behind, especially for women. Moreover, the level of financial literacy among the Indian women has not been largely documented. Hence, the need arises to understand in detail the issue of financial literacy among women in India. This paper is an attempt in this direction. It has been observed that although it is imperative that women should be given equal power to take financial decisions as taken by men, yet many Indian women are facing several cultural, financial, psychological and physical barriers that are creating hindrances in becoming financially literate. The government is taking initiatives for making the people more financially literate, yet there persists a lot of gap in the financial literacy level of men and women. Hence, more women specific financial literacy programs should be introduced and new universities should be established to make the women more literate. This would not only make the women more independent and empowered but would facilitate the growth of the whole nation.

Keywords: Financial Planning, Financial literacy, Financial Inclusion.

Introduction

In the present scenario, the integrated global financial market as well as the changing financial objectives has increased the individual's responsibility in managing their own finances and securing their financial future. In an environment where the range and complexity of financial products are widening the scope of entire market, it is becoming crucial that individuals should develop a thorough understanding of the world of finance so as to make better choices that are most appropriate to their financial goals and needs (Kumar and Anees, 2013). Moreover, the economic growth and development of nation are highly influenced by the financial decisions taken by individuals. However, it is not an easy task to take financial decisions. Several factors, such as risk, returns, market scenario, regulatory framework etc., need to be analyzed while making financial planning.

In other words, financial literacy plays a crucial role in financial planning of an individual. The Financial Planning is defined as "the process of meeting one's life goals through the proper management of personal finances" (NISM). In other words, it is a process of taking necessary steps to ensure that an individual is equipped to accomplish his financial goals which he has set out to achieve and is prepared to deal with contingencies as well (Shobha and Shalini, 2015). As far as financial literacy is concerned, OECD/INFE defines it as "a combination of awareness, knowledge, skill, attitude and behavior necessary to make sound financial decisions and ultimately achieve individual financial wellbeing". Also, it is defined as "the process to inculcate the ability to understand personal financial wellbeing. It includes the awareness about financial products, market information, sources of getting financial knowledge and confidence of discussing financial issues, so that a person can plan for the future, make proper decisions to meet out the life events" (Purohit and Rohella).

However, everybody does not possess the same ability to plan their financial resources. Researchers across the world have reported the inadequate financial literacy level among the individuals which raises serious concerns about the ability of individuals to secure their financial well-being (Kumar and Anees, 2013). There are several factors that actually influence the financial literacy among the individuals and one such prominent factor is 'Gender'. More specifically, a relatively broad range of empirical literature documents the existence of gender differences in financial literacy in various countries and along several dimensions. It is generally observed that on an average, women perform worse than men in the tests of financial knowledge and have less confidence in their financial skills (OECD,

2013).

As far as India is concerned, there have been numerous debates about gender over the years. Mainly such debates are related to women's position in society, their education, health, economic position, gender equality etc. In other words, women in India have always held a certain paradoxical position. Although in the modern society, women have slowly start recognizing her true potential and are conquering in every field whether it is politics, sports, entertainment, literature, technology, yet there are certain areas where women are still lagging behind the men. One such area is "Personal financial Planning". It has been observed that women have inherently been better money managers on a small scale as far as their household expenses and savings are concerned, yet many women, including working women, seem to be comfortable in leaving their long-term finances and retirement planning to their fathers or husbands. In other words, the efficiency they exhibit in managing home finances is not getting extended to their personal financial front (Shobha and Shalini, 2015). The major reason behind such issue is the lack of financial literacy among women. The survey by NCFE clearly exhibit that the financial literacy percentage among the women in India is quite low which needs special focus (Dwivedi et al., 2015).

Since women hold around 50% of the population of India, it would be unjust if only rest of the 50% will be taking the financial decisions. Moreover, there are several theoretical arguments that support that women should be financially literate to take rationale financial decisions. Such arguments are:

Longer Life Expectancy: The study by OECD (2013) clearly exhibit that on an average, looking across 121 countries representing a wide mix of developing and developed nations, women live five years longer than men. Hence, it is essential that women should develop an in-depth understanding about the concept of financial planning and investment avenues to protect her from the financial challenges she may face in the future. It has been observed, in US and cross-national research in developed countries that older single women continue to be disproportionately poor as compared with older single men and older married couples. Hence, lack of knowledge can be more costly for women because they tend to live longer (Wall Street Journal).

Economic Growth: The nation's overall development needs women investors as well which will enhance the liquidity in the market and will boost up the scope of trade in the economy. This can be made possible if women are financially literate.

Self Independent: It is essential for women to acquaint themselves with the finance world so as to be financially independent. This will lift up their status in the society as they will match up with the male section of the society as far as financial decisions are concerned.

Freedom from exploitation: Financial literacy will help in protecting society and individuals against exploitative financial schemes and exorbitant interest rate charged by moneylenders.

Family well being: It is believed that if there is a difference in the financial literacy level of men and women, it may affect the relative economic power within the household. Since men and women will allocate household resources according to different preferences this have implications for the well-being of the family. Research in many countries suggests that households do not act as a single unitary decision maker. Instead, it has been observed that household resources in women's hands has been observed to be more likely spent on improving family well-being, particularly that of children.

Although, it is imperative for women to acquire financial knowledge and to make financial planning still a lot of gap persists in India as far as financial literacy among women is concerned. The present study is an attempt to study the issues faced by the women in acquiring financial knowledge, interventions made by the government and measures for boosting up the financial literacy among women in India. The study expects to contribute to the literature by extending the understanding of the whole scenario of financial literacy among women in India.

Literature Review

A relatively broad range of empirical literature documents the existence of gender differences in financial literacy in

various countries and along several dimensions. However, few studies have been conducted in India that examined this issue empirically. Dwivedi et al. (2015) analyzed the NCFE report on financial literacy and financial inclusion in India on the basis of occupation, geographical area and gender mix. The study found that urban population is more financially literate than rural population. Also, men are found to be more financially literate than women. Moreover, the study observed that women have higher financial attitude but less financial behavior and less financial knowledge, whereas men have slightly less financial attitude than women but scored more on financial behavior and financial knowledge.

In the same line, Shobha and Shalini (2015) conducted a survey on the perception of women towards the personal financial planning in the city of Bengaluru. The study revealed that Indian women give priority to family and children's requirements more than her requirements for financial needs and individualistic financial security. Also, difficulty in convincing the spouse and family is also a challenge to the women to create their financial plans. The study also found that women still feel that gold, real estates, bank deposits, insurance products and provident funds are the most safe instruments for investing, while they feel that mutual funds, derivatives, chits, stocks and shares as riskier investments. Hence, lack of knowledge on new instruments influence their ability to earn returns for them.

Paramashivaiah et al. (2014) quantify the risk appetite score of 120 women grouped on various socio-demographic bases in Mysore city. The analysis through regression model suggests that there is a negative influence of age of women on their risk tolerance levels. Whereas, Prasad et al. (2014) examined the impact of certain emotions, such as greed, fear, love and disbelief, on the Indian woman's investment decisions. The study found that these emotions block the logic and rationality of investors, affect their prospects of generating wealth, cause financial distress, and further deteriorate their emotional stability.

Agrawal (1988) observed that the decision making power of women in India in economic field lies in the hands of their husbands irrespective of the wives' income, education and profession. Singh (2004) as well as Balasari (2004) support that working women are more aware of the type of investment instruments and take better investment decisions than non-working women. Moreover, it is found that working women spend less on themselves as compared to the non-working women.

Venkataraman (2004) compared the psychology of women investors with men and found that although women like to get the maximum returns but most of them make secret savings and use this secret money on gold, jewelry or apparels. Also they prefer to invest more in post office schemes. However, Agarwal (2010) observed that women do not possess the requisite skills to make successful investment and financial decisions which generates the need for financial literacy.

Mathivathani and Velumani (2014) conducted a study to know the level of financial literacy among women in rural areas of Tamilnadu. The study found that financial literacy of marginalized rural women is very low. Hence, the proper development of financial literacy would help the women for better financial decision making and proper utilization of financial services and products.

Agarwalla et al. (2013) investigated the influence of various socio-demographic factors on different dimensions of financial literacy among the working young in urban India. While the influence of several factors such as gender, education and income is similar to what has been reported in other contexts, a few factors specific to India, such as joint-family and consultative decision making process are found to significantly influence financial literacy. The study also investigated the relationship between the dimensions of financial literacy. Adding to the growing empirical understanding of financial literacy across countries, the study provides an analytical basis for enunciating policy for enhancing financial literacy of youth in India.

In nutshell, financial literacy level of women in India is quite low and need special attention. Hence, research efforts in this area are undeniably needed.

Need of the Study

Few studies have been conducted in India that focused on difference in the level of financial literacy of men and

women. However, still there persists a huge gap in the literature as far as the factors influencing such differences and measures for improving them are concerned. In other words, studies have largely found a significant difference in financial literacy level of men and women, however what factors influence such differences have not been extensively explored. Moreover, the interventions by government and measures for boosting up the financial literacy level also need to be analyzed. Hence the need arises to explore the issue of financial literacy among women in India in more intensive manner. The present study is an attempt in this direction.

Objectives of the Study

- To study the factors influencing the financial literacy among women in India.
- To study the financial literacy interventions by government in India.
- To explore the measures for enhancing the financial literacy among women in India.

Factors Influencing the Financial Literacy Among Women in India

The financial literacy among Indian women is highly influenced by several factors. The prominent factors are discussed as follows:

Lack of Independence: Although several theories support the equality between men and women yet women are deprived of the extent of independence which men enjoy. The basic problem is that women are not given the freedom to manage their finances independently. All major financial investment decisions are generally taken in consensus after considering the well-being of whole family. Hence, such financial decisions are not taken on their merit but are dictated by social responsibility. A woman can only spend a small part of her income on herself and in order to maintain harmony in the family women let go of their financial freedom.

Culture: Culture also comes in as a factor that acts as a hindrance in spreading financial education among women. Some cultures do not allow women to take part in financial matters of the family. It is a usual practice that men take control of financial matters whereas women are supposed to take care of domestic duties. This disrupts their confidence and restrains them in becoming financially literate.

Lack of women centric financial schemes: Most financial institutions have generic financial services and do not develop women specific financial schemes. Also, the high and stringent requirements to access the services restrict the women to take financial decisions and learn financial jargons. Products that only focus on business and does not focus on the woman household also act as a barrier in financial literacy among women.

Lack of accessibility: Mainly the financial institutions are located in far areas from where the women reside or do businesses, hence they find it expensive and time wasting to go to the financial institution. This problem is mainly faced by the women in rural areas (Mathivathani and Velumani, 2014).

Lack of information on existing financial services and requirements: Most of the women are unaware of the available financial services as many financial institutions advertise their services in mainstream media and billboards. Hence, the lack of awareness creates a hindrance in becoming financially aware. Lack of financial awareness and knowledge is contributing in a major way in their dependence on investment and financial planning on spouse/family, hampering their financial independence (Shobha and Shalini, 2015).

Less lucrative benefits: High interest rates charged on loans and high fees for maintaining and operating current accounts including low interest rates for deposits in savings accounts also discourage many women from seeking these services.

Lack of basic education: In India, the basic literacy level of women is quite low as compared to men. Most of the sections of society do not allow women to acquire higher education. The lack of basic education and lack of computer knowledge is another reason of low financial literacy level among Indian women (Mathivathani and Velumani, 2014).

Lack of financial resources: In India, there is a high proportion of non-working women. Since they are not working,

the source of income is dependent upon their spouse of father. This also restricts them to take independent decisions on financial matters of family.

Financial Literacy Interventions By Government

Financial literacy is the main tool for promoting financial inclusion in the country. In order to boost up the financial literacy, the government of India has framed various schemes to encourage women to participate in the process of capital formation by encouraging them to take up savings and investments activities (Prasad et al., 2014). There are several schemes introduced by the government which directly or indirectly promotes the financial support and literacy among the female section of the society. Following are the key components of financial literacy programmes that are to be spread across country:

Why Save?

Why invest?

Why insure?

Why you will need regular stream of income post working life?

Why save or invest regularly and consistently?

Why insure fully?

Why save with banks?

Why borrow within limits?

Why borrow from banks?

What is the difference between saving and investment?

Why borrow for income generating purposes?

Why repay loans?

Why repay loans in time?

Why do you need insurance?

What is interest? How money lenders charge very high interest rates?

Few initiatives taken by the government are highlighted as follows:

Financial Literacy and Credit Counselling Centres (FLCC): In order to spread the financial inclusion in the country, the government of India establishes FLCC to give free financial literacy/education in the country.

Beti Bachao, Beti padhao Yojana- This is a Government of India scheme that aims to generate awareness and improving the efficiency of welfare services meant for women.

Sukanya Samridhi Yojana (Girl Child Prosperity Scheme)- The scheme primarily ensures equitable share to a girl child in resources and savings of a family in which she is generally discriminated as against a male child. This would ensure the financial support to females which will encourage the financial literacy as well.

Pradhan Mantri Jan-Dhan Yojana- One of the biggest steps taken by government to enhance the financial inclusion in the country is the launch of PMJDY. It is a national mission on financial inclusion encompassing an integrated approach to bring about comprehensive financial inclusion of all the households in the country. Objective of "Pradhan Mantri Jan-Dhan Yojana (PMJDY)" is ensuring the access to various financial services like availability of basic savings bank account, access to need based credit, remittances facility, insurance and pension to the excluded sections i.e. weaker sections & low income groups. This deep penetration needs financial literacy among the people. Hence, special arrangements are being made by the government for spreading financial knowledge so that financial inclusion can be made possible.

Establishment of NCFE- The National Centre for Financial Education (NCFE), has been set up to implement National Strategy for Financial Education (NSFE), under the guidance of a Technical Group on Financial Inclusion and Financial Literacy of the Financial Stability and Development Council (FSDC), which would cater to all sections of the population in the country. It comprises of the representatives from all financial sector regulators i.e. Reserve Bank of India (RBI), Securities Exchange Board of India (SEBI), Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority of India (IRDAI), Pension Fund Regulatory and Development Authority (PFRDA) and National Institute of Securities

Markets (NISM). The main role of NCFE is to create financial education materials and conduct financial education campaigns across the country for all sections of the population along with awareness campaigns at different levels for existing and potential customers so as to improve their knowledge, understanding, skills and competence.

Measures for Enhancing the Financial Literacy Among Women in India

Although several initiatives are taken by government for spreading financial education across the country, yet there are several issues faced by the women due to which they are unable to acquire financial education.

Hence following measures are suggested for enhancing financial literacy level among women in India:

Training- Training is one of the best measures that should be used to inculcate the habit of learning financial terms among the women. Women with low level of family income and low level of education benefit significantly from the training imparted (Agarwalla et al., 2013). Most of the women feel hesitant while dealing in financial matters because of lack of training. Hence, from time to time, training programs should be organized specifically for women so as to make them more capable while dealing with their finances.

Financial awareness and Education- Women require multifaceted financial skills that are knotted with their life, livelihood and businesses this include skills in budgeting, savings, understanding financial services, debt management, financial negotiation skills and investments. Hence, they must be taught the financial terms through financial awareness programs and courses. Financial education programs should focus particularly on important life-planning aspects, such as, basic savings, debt, insurance and pensions (Das, 2007).

Establish nearby Institution- Distance is another challenge faced by women as many financial institutions are located far away from where the women live. To deal with this challenge, banks, post offices, insurance companies etc. must open their branches nearby the residential accommodation. This also presents additional income opportunities for women who are recruited as bank agents.

Better Technology- Information and communications technology (ICTs) is an effective tool to increase women's financial literacy. Mobile technologies have become increasingly available to the poor and can improve access to financial information and training. Using media outlets such as television, magazines, and internet can be helpful in disseminating financial literacy training in the country.

E-learning- E-learning can be another powerful educational tool for training, knowledge sharing, and international best practices.

Cultural change- The major problem being faced by Indian women is the male dominating society. "A lot of women don't have reliable ways to learn about money...They just do what their families do" — Focus group participant, Literacy DuPage. In India, women are supposed to be the home maker only and are not given independence to be the part of financial matters. Hence, cultural change is needed to ensure wider financial literacy among women.

More benefits to women- Women would feel allured to indulge in financial activities if they will be offered financial services with more lucrative benefits such as low rate of interest on loans, high rate of interest on deposits, tax benefits etc. Many institutions, such as banks, are providing such kind of benefits but they are not sufficient to attract more and more women investors. Women need to have the opportunity to seek out and use financial information if they are to improve their financial literacy (Mathivathani and Velumani, 2014). Hence, efforts must be made by the government to provide more benefits to women and open more opportunities which would encourage them to be more financially literate.

Establish more women oriented Universities- The financial literacy among the women can be spread with the establishment of more universities. There are very few universities in India that are spreading financial awareness among the women such as Banasthali Vidyapith, but more such institutes are needed.

Conclusion

In the present scenario, the Government of India is putting a lot of efforts for ensuring financial inclusion in the country.

Financial inclusion is the process of ensuring access to appropriate financial products and services needed by all sections of the society in general and vulnerable groups such as weaker sections and low income groups in particular at an affordable cost in a fair and transparent manner by mainstream institutional players. Financial inclusion is the road that India needs to travel for becoming a global player. It is highly needed for ensuring the growth and development of the country. However, this goal can be made possible through financial literacy. Financial literacy means spreading the financial education among the people across the country. While the need for financial literacy may be largely acknowledged, the importance of gender dimension remains a subject for debate.

Voluminous studies have documented the existence of gender differences in the financial literacy across the world but the studies on financial literacy among the women in India are quite scarce. This paper analyzes the issue of financial literacy among women in India. It has been observed that there are several problems faced by Indian women due to which they lack in financial literacy such as cultural barriers, physical barriers, psychological, and financial barriers etc. However over a period of time women are realizing the importance of savings and investments in improving their individual economic status as well as their family as a whole. Hence more financial literacy programs and institutions should be established in order to create more awareness on financial terms to women. This will make women the part of financial inclusion and will facilitate the growth of nation as a whole.

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RAISE IN SUSTAINABLE FASHION BUYING – A SHIFT IN CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOR

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Abstract: Sustainable fashion has taken a rapid move in the industry as consumers have become more socially responsible. Millennials and Gen Z are willing to put their wallets towards value to stay greener for a visible impact. Sustainable fashion will be the next normal in the industry. The main objectives of the study are to analyze the awareness level towards sustainable fashion and identify the influence of sustainability towards fashion and clothing buying. The data was collected from 330 respondents from Bangalore using convenience sampling. While sustainable shopping has become more popular among consumers of all ages, Gen Z has played a significant role driving this trend as they increase their purchasing power. Sustainability remains an important shopping criterion for many. Percentage analysis is used to analyse the sustainable fashion and clothing buying. The findings provide key implications for researchers and practitioners regarding fashion industry and sustainability. Our results show that environmental concern and perceived value positively affect purchase intention and the willingness to pay a premium price regardless the type of eco-materials used for the products.

Keywords: Green Consumer Behavior, Sustainable clothing, Impulsive Buying, TPB.

1. Introduction

1.1: Fashion Industry: Fashion industry, multibillion-dollar global enterprise devoted to the business of making and selling clothes. The Indian fashion market is expected to grow at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 11-12% to reach \$115-125 billion by 2025. However, with the increasing competition, changing consumer preferences, and technological disruptions, the industry is facing both opportunities and challenges. With the growing awareness of environmental and social issues, sustainability has become a key trend in the fashion industry. Indian fashion brands are increasingly adopting eco-friendly and ethical practices in their supply chain, production, and marketing. For instance, many brands are using organic and recycled materials, minimizing waste, and carbon footprint, and promoting fair labor practices. As consumers are becoming more conscious of their impact on the planet, sustainable fashion is expected to grow in demand. The Covid-19 pandemic has accelerated the shift towards digitalization in the fashion industry. Many Indian fashion brands are now focusing on building their online presence, creating e-commerce platforms. In today's time you can find many online brands which leverage social media for marketing and engagement. The digitalization trend is expected to continue in the next 2 years, with more brands investing in e-commerce, virtual try-on, augmented reality, and artificial intelligence technologies. Revenue in the Fashion market is projected to reach US\$15.63bn in 2023. Revenue is expected to show an annual growth rate (CAGR 2023-2027) of 13.48%, resulting in a projected market volume of US\$25.92bn by 2027. With a projected market volume of US\$265.50bn in 2023, most revenue is generated in China.

1.2: Sustainability Goals In Fashion and Apparel Industry:

The fashion industry is known for its ability to implement trends that have the power to shape society and affect the buying habits of consumers at large. But what is, at times, forgotten is the impact everyday consumers have on the industry. The truth is that the industry is largely dictated by consumer demand, and right now the demand for sustainable practices appears to be high. In a survey conducted by McKinsey during the beginning of the Covid-19 pandemic, “67 percent [of respondents] consider the use of sustainable materials to be an important purchasing factor, and 63 percent consider a brand's promotion of sustainability in the same way.” Thus, consumers could push the fashion industry to reckon with its impact on our environment. Not only is the demand for sustainability high, but so is the conversation surrounding the subject. Data provided by Launchmetrics' proprietary algorithm that measures Media Impact Value reveals that the MIV for sustainability grew by 54% during the first semester of 2022 compared to the first semester of 2021, accounting for \$2 billion and \$1.3 billion in value, respectively. (MIV is a monetary representation my company uses for brand performance.) This data looked into how much conversation “sustainability” generated in the media, as well as how many placements the term generated across sectors. When

we compared the growing MIV to the placements that the industry generates, it became clear that consumers are starting to make changes. This shift means brands should reevaluate their operations to project the right brand image. And to achieve this, fashion brands should now look to take more concrete steps to embrace sustainability, a process which goes beyond brand image and campaigns.

1.3: Recent trends in sustainable Apparel and Fashion:

The rise of Sustainable & Organic Clothing represents modern-day buyers' adoption of eco-conscious fashion templates. The popularity of organic textiles is commensurate with its market size, which is on a consistent rise.

Organic Cotton, for example, has become the most famous sustainable textile in India, the leading producer of organic cotton (51%) with 1.23 million tonnes produced in 2022. In its report named "Organic Cotton Market, 2021-2028", Fortuna Business Insights came up with two interesting findings.

Firstly, the market size of the organic cotton industry will touch the outstanding mark of USD 6,730.9 million by 2028. It is expected to grow at a CAGR of 40.0% in the 2021-2028 period. Organic cotton is a naturally cultivated textile material developed with natural fertilizers and harmless materials that has a lower impact on the environment than synthetic cotton. Buyers' mindsets have also gone through a profound metamorphosis. It has led to a preference shift towards 'value-based eco-friendly shopping'. The organic fashion boom can be attributed to the dichotomous nature of the textile industry at present.

On the upside, a recently released Global Market Report, 2023, by the Business Research Company stated that the global textile market would witness growth from \$573.22 billion in 2022 to \$610.91 billion in 2023 at a 6.6% CAGR.

The only glaring downside is that the textile and clothing industry is one of the most pollution-causing industries in the world. Studies across the globe show that textile waste and cleaning processes diminish the quality of roughly 5% of landfill space and 20% of freshwater bodies across the globe. Fast fashion items often undergo a long and intense chemical process before ending up on our hangers. Around 8,000 different synthetic chemicals are used to dye, bleach and wet process garments. Those chemicals often cause diseases or even deaths among farmers and inflict serious birth defects on their children. The organic clothing market has gone through a phase of an intensive boost as the world is facing the heat of drastic climatic changes and virulent repercussions of placing development over environmental concerns. Organic Cotton, Recycled Cotton, Hemp, Linen, Bamboo Linen, and Cork are raw materials leading the growth of the sustainable fashion industry. Sustainable textiles are eco-friendly and do not require the use of harmful pesticides and fertilizers in their production. They do not dilute the soil nutrients or use genetically modified seeds. Organic fibers are made with organically approved pesticides and require a low percentage of water. They conserve 62% more water and 88% more energy than synthetic cotton production.

Hemp is a resourceful, sustainable fabric with carbon-negative properties and absorbs Co2 from the environment. It is a water-efficient fabric which does not require chemicals for its production and gives phytoremediation benefits to soil and replenishes its quality. It is quite a popular material in the West and is slowly finding its grounding in India as well. The educated intelligentsia and classes have acknowledged an ecocentric shopping culture. There is a uniformity in the production processes of organic fabrics, which causes minimal to no harm to the environment. There are numerous catalysts at work in the popularity of organic clothing. They are far more comfortable, easily maintainable, washable, and stretchable, which makes everyone's preferred choice on the Wishlist. According to sustainable fashion industry statistics, the market is expected to rise to \$9.81 billion in 2025 and \$15.17 billion in 2030 at a CAGR of 9.1 percent, due to the growing awareness of ethical fashion in India.

As sustainability becomes an increasingly important consideration for consumers, sustainable fashion brands are on the rise in India. A recent report indicates that the Indian sustainable fashion market is projected to reach a value of \$9.81 billion by 2025, with an estimated CAGR of 9.81% between 2020 and 2025. The report also highlights the growing interest in eco-friendly fabrics and materials, with cotton and denim being the most popular among Indian consumers. Additionally, sustainable brands are also leveraging social media platforms and e-commerce channels to connect with customers and expand their reach. The trend towards sustainable clothing is set to continue as more consumers prioritize ethical and eco-friendly #fashion choices.

Literature Review

Saricam, C., & Okur, N. (2019) Sustainability in fashion industry is utilized for portraying the durability of clothing, absorption of ethical manufacturing model is for processing the materials that will protect the ecosystem of environment incorporation of fair trade practices with sweatshop-free standards and using recycled materials get much attention by the fashion industry market. Even though the element of sustainability in the fashion industry is the variety of recycled material, green manufacturing and supply chain were discussed in this article. The approach of the consumer behavior in the sustainable fashion industry is quite matched with Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) and Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB). These two are successful models to predict the intentions of consumers for analyzing three independent variable behavioral attitudes, perceived behavioral control and subjective norm. TPB was typically used to give details about the consumers' move toward sustainability processes in specific fields such as consumption of organic food, concept of green restaurants, buying eco friendly fashion products in sweat- shops, buying eco friendly cotton clothing, and using eco friendly logistics.

In this study, the researcher objective is to find the consumers' intention toward sustainable fashion purchasing using TPB. Using this model researchers extended the behavioral beliefs, control beliefs and normative beliefs which influenced the factors of the consumer intentions. Considered 339 participants from Turkey and used structural equation modeling and confirmatory factor analysis to investigate the models. The conclusions showed that both are authenticated models to clarify the consumer's behavior towards the sustainable fashion industry. According to both models, it was found that; attitude is the primary element showing a high degree of influence to choose favorable or unfavorable products. The perceived behavioral control was found to be less influential on the customer's intention in ease of purchasing fashionable products whereas the subjective norms described as the social pressure is key element to perform or not perform the behavior was established to be powerful on the original TPB model. Further extended TPB model, consumer attitudes were more influenced by behavioral beliefs and no relation was found between control beliefs and perceived behavioral control. At last, the emotional standards and normative convictions are the solitary strong factors to influence the purchase intentions.

Hur, E., & Cassidy, T. (2019) explains how perceptions and attitudes are a powerful element in sustainable fashion design practices and how to discover processes of sustainable design practices. Researchers used open-ended qualitative questionnaires on 50 fashion designers through five interviews for this study. The major discovery of the study is, to incorporate sustainable fashion designing we must focus on internal (personal and organizational) and external challenges. the lack of awareness and knowledge towards sustainable fashion design, lack of design-led modes to implement sustainability in fashion and trade-offs with other design measures such as aesthetics, prices, and contemporary fashion trends. External challenges include the difficulty of sustainability concerns, inadequate consumer demand, attitude gaps and behavior patterns in consumer purchasing decision making on sustainable collection ranges and inadequate encouragement or values for businesses to execute sustainable design strategies.

Over all the study investigated the problems connected to implementing sustainability in fashion design through fashion designer perceptions, attitudes, and involvement regarding sustainability. Both the role of design and designers can be key to stimulating sustainable design practice; their roles could contribute sustainable development through shaping the design production practices and by influencing the consumption processes.

Hyun Min Kong, et al (2019) Sustainability has been recognized as a major concern worldwide, and this also increases considerations regarding the challenges business needs to be faced in the fashion industry. Strategic marketing can be used to promise a value offering to customers for competitive advantage (Varadarajan, 2010). In recent years fashion brands, consumers, researchers and practitioners have turned increasing attention to sustainability in environmental and social contexts (Kim, Taylor, Kim, & Lee, 2015; Song & Ko, 2014a). The fashion industry's environmental impact is very high during supply chain management and production processes such as dyeing, drying and finishing, chemical usage and use of natural resources (DBrito, Carbone, & Blanquart, 2008). Environmental threats are not temporary; in order to implement viable initiatives and sustainability activities, fashion companies and fashion consumers need to be educated about essential sustainability principles.

Knowledge can be a catalyst for changing attitudes (Arbuthnot, 2009) and can stimulate action. Previous research has discovered that environmental knowledge has a positive relationship with environmental behavior, and also that knowledge is required for attitude and behavior changes (Ernst & Spada, 1993). Although the fashion industry is

becoming increasingly concerned with the importance of sustainability, in general, Korean consumers in their 20s to late 30s have little experience and knowledge of sustainability efforts. Fashion companies are doing an insufficient job of encouraging consumers to have positive attitudes and behavior toward environmental interests and concerns (Weller & Walter, 2008). The “4/40 Gap” indicates that approximately 40% of consumers are open to the idea of buying sustainable products, but only 4% actually act on this (Makower, 2006). This suggests that different sources of education can help consumers understand the concept of sustainability to help close the gap between attitude and behavior (Sung & Kincade, 2010; Song & Ko, 2014b).

The purposes of this study are as follows: (1) to examine the influence of sustainable knowledge sources on different sustainable knowledge types; (2) to examine the influence of sustainable knowledge types on sustainable consumer behavior. Therefore, this study contributes to education and marketing aspects in two ways: (1) with these findings, academic researchers should be better able to develop strategies that companies can use to educate their fashion consumers; (2) fashion companies can develop more effective business strategies for targeting consumers through expanded understanding of fashion consumers’ attitude and behavioral intention toward sustainable fashion products.

Finally, This study analyzes Korean fashion consumers’ levels of sustainable knowledge and their behavioral intention toward sustainable fashion products. Literature regarding types of sustainable knowledge in the fashion industry is limited. Thus, this study cites academic reviews on other research topics such as peer education’s influence on drinking prevention and behaviors (UNAIDS, 1999).

Jianfang Liang, Jingjun Li and Qinyuan Lei (2022) There is a problem among Generation Z regarding the insufficient perception of green apparel consumption and the “perception–action paradox”, which presents a great challenge to China’s future sustainable development. To address this problem, we constructed a chain multiple mediation research framework that explored the transmission paths between the environmental value and green consumption behavior of apparel, as well as the associated influence mechanisms; this was performed by integrating environmental responsibility and green consumption intention. Data for this study were collected through a multistage sampling survey of 657 Chinese Gen Z members born between 1995 and 2002. Our results reveal that all three types (egoism, altruism, and biospheric values) of environmental values had different direct and indirect effects on the green apparel consumption behavior for Gen Z members, but the indirect effects of each aspect significantly outweighed their direct effects. In terms of the direct effects, egoistic values had no significant direct negative effect on green apparel consumption behavior, whereas the significant positive direct effect of the biospheric values was greater than that of altruistic values. The greatest mediating effect between the environmental values and green apparel consumption behavior was green consumption intention, followed by environmental responsibility, and ending with the chain mediation effect of environmental responsibility and green consumption intention. These findings suggest that it is imperative to stress the cultivation of green consumption intentions, environmental responsibility, and environmental values and bridge the seamless link among these variables for the promotion of green apparel consumption practices in Generation Z. This is the first study that explicitly identifies the significant chain mediating effect of environmental responsibility and green consumption intention between the environmental values and green apparel consumption behavior. Our findings broaden the theoretical research perspective of green apparel consumption behavior and provide a reference for the guiding of green consumption practices and policy formulation for the global population of Generation Z.

This study investigated the impact of Chinese Gen Z’s environmental values on their green consumption of apparel. An important contribution of this research is its construction of a chain multiple mediation model between environmental values and green consumption of apparel that also integrates environmental responsibility and green consumption intention as mediators. We examined the direct and indirect effects of environmental values on green consumption of apparel in Chinese Gen Z members.

Subhasis Ray, and Lipsa Nayak (2022) The fashion industry is one of the largest contributors to greenhouse gas emissions and climate change. Sustainable fashion (SF) aims to address this issue by designing, creating, and marketing socially and environmentally responsible products. This paper provides a broad overview of the extant literature on SF marketing to understand the trends and future directions. The paper starts with a discussion on

sustainable consumption and marketing in the particular context of fashion and ends with potential research gaps, which have scope for further work. For the analysis, 97 research papers were selected based on a structured, systematic search with a particular set of keywords. The review finds that marketing SF from a customer's perspective has been emphasized in the existing literature. Widely studied topics include consumer behavior, purchase behavior, and the attitude behavior gap. Further research is required to explore how SF can gain from B2B marketing, circular economy, sustainability-oriented innovations, and subsistence markets, particularly in emerging economies. This paper contributes to theory and practice by providing state-of-the-art sustainable fashion marketing research, identifying research gaps, and providing future research directions.

Sooyoen Shim, Jisoo Kim and Youngjoo Na.(2019)- A study on upcycling the sustainability clothing life at home. Upcycling is effective in expressing our own personality without unnecessary spending but still satisfying the desire of creative material. It explains about family focused sustainability clothing and should realize the importance of upcycling clothing practice. Sustainable clothing is eco-friendly, leads to fair production structure, economic viability and consumer rational spending pattern. Slowly fashion industry is moving towards sustainable approach to fashion production and consumption. It focuses on "valuing and knowing the object". This form of sustainability consumption is centered in a consumer value system that engages in understanding the process of raw material to finished product as a part of experience of consumption. Up-cycling is a type of recycling that rises in value. It minimizes waste, repeats, recycling by maximizing the use of original function. This raises questions about the environment's influence, and it becomes clear that upcycling is based on sustainability, which is anchored on redesign and a new perspective on symbiosis. The apparel business has undergone a metamorphosis as a result of the fast fashion phenomena. New clothing styles are available to the typical customer every week thanks to shifting consumer attitudes towards apparel consumption, low-cost production, and the sourcing of materials from international industrial markets. This has created a culture of impulsive buying in the fashion business. In this study, a qualitative research method was used in order to gather and analyze trends from the interview data. Focus Group Interview as a research method was used to make a generalized deduction in the mass survey. A total of 30 respondents participated in an event on sustainable clothing were grouped into 8 groups for the Focus Group Interview and documented, analyzed focusing on the content corresponding to the study purpose. The participants in the study voiced towards recycling as one of the methods for sustainable clothing in families, and thought of up-cycling as a kind of recycling. The thought of upcycling impact on environment, when family starts giving importance to sustainability clothing, eventually companies will also start paying attention to sustainability practice in the business. Environment friendly products and using upcycled and durable long time wear. Therefore, it showed that up-cycling raises cultural, social

sustainability. They said they cannot easily discard up-cycling products they made and use them for a long time with affection. Like this sustainable characteristics of up-cycling appeared in families, and it is thought that up-cycling will be helpful in creation of new values and developmental availability in sustainable clothing. This study has its meaning that it raised the understanding of the attitude and aspect of sustainable clothing in families in a psychological aspect, but has difficulty in generalization as it is a qualitative study targeting a small group of participants. Therefore, quantitative research targeting large groups of participants should be supported in future study.

Md Mazedul Islam, 2020- This paper reviews the literature on environmentally sustainable practices in textile, apparel and fashion (TAF) industries to allow the mapping of practices across various manufacturing processes and the development of a conceptual framework to guide investigation of the extent of sustainable practices in TAF industries from an environmental perspective. Design/methodology/approach – A systematic literature review was undertaken, consisting of bibliometric and content analysis of 91 articles published in peer-reviewed journals over a 10-year period. Findings – The inclusion of sustainable practices from all manufacturing stages in this review illustrates the diversity and complexities of environmental practices in TAF contexts. However, there is less research in developing country contexts, where most TAF production takes place and a paucity of research in upstream stages of garment washing and dyeing, and the manufacture of trims, accessories and packaging. Research limitations/implications – The focus is on environmental sustainability and upstream manufacturing processes. The review includes literature in the form of academic journal articles from selected databases during the period January 2010–June 2020. Practical implications – This review provides academics with a unified depiction of

environmentally sustainable practices to stimulate further scholarly research and provides guidance for managers to develop firm sustainability competency by summarizing best practices at different manufacturing stages. Originality/value – This review comprehensively maps the academic literature on environmentally sustainable practices in TAF industries from an upstream manufacturing operations context. It highlights the contribution of scholarly study to the knowledge base on environmentally sustainable practices in TAF industries. Sustainable practices in TAF industries materialize as a varied and complex field of research. This study identifies key sustainable practices which will shape the sustainable future of TAF industries, including materials, product design for longevity, resource savings, energy efficiency strategies and adoption of circular approaches. Mapping of sustainable practices based on organizational and operational aspects is useful for industry practitioners to understand how to combine operational, organizational, reactive and proactive practices of environmental sustainability, without scattering investment efforts in too many directions. Consequently, this study concludes with a proposed conceptual framework for future theoretical and empirical research, which provides a unified depiction of sustainable practices covering various environmental aspects. It could benefit industry practitioners in developing firm competence in different levels (e.g. individual, intra-organisational and inter-organisational). The framework could help academic researchers to further investigate environmentally sustainable practices in TAF industries by showing innovation pathways that are relatively unexplored. The framework shows the current direction of environmentally sustainable practices implementation, illustrating the complexity and diversity of the issues that need to be addressed to facilitate further research and development. Consideration of the full range of competences instead of single elements is needed to enhance sustainability competency towards desired outcomes. Implementation of environmentally sustainable practices in TAF industries is inherently complex and requires strategic and proactive actions across operations and life cycle stages, and collaboration among manufacturers, buying firms and other multi-level stakeholders.

Amit Vishwakarma, (2022)–Purpose of this study to identify the various challenges that the Indian apparel industry is facing and these challenges are taken from beginning i.e., from growing of raw material. Moreover, this work includes classification of these challenges into various dimensions of sustainability i.e., environmental, social, economic. It has been found out that some have an impact on all the three dimensions. To resolve these challenges and some sustainability practices are suggested. These practices majorly focus upon environment protection. However, they are not sufficient in the future. Much more sustainability practices are significant initiatives required for a better environment and sustainability. This Study identified some of the challenges that the Indian textile and apparel industry is facing. Further effect of these challenges on which dimension of sustainability is also mentioned i.e., economic, social and environmental sustainability. The challenges included in this research are poor quality of raw materials, negative impact on the environment and society, low productivity, skill shortage, poor infrastructure, Lack of sufficient governmental policies and fast fashion. Reduction or elimination of these challenges are essential for the growth of this sector. This will also increase the overall sustainability in this sector. This study also suggested some practices for sustainability. These practices support and improve sustainability. The included practices are application of life cycle assessment method, eco-labelling of the apparel, environment friendly practices, eco-friendly textile fibers, recycled clothing. All these practices have various benefits like environmental protection, consumer awareness etc.

Stefano Abbate (2022)–Textile, apparel, and fashion (TAF) industries contribute significantly to global environmental pollution at every point of the supply chain. Clothing manufacturing and transportation produce a large volume of waste and high greenhouse gas emissions, often taking advantage of cheap labor in developing countries. As a result, stakeholders are becoming more aware of the effect of the textile, apparel, and fashion industries on the climate and human rights, thus pushing businesses to mitigate their environmental damage. This paper offers a systematic literature review of sustainability trends in the TAF industries in the last 20 years. Bibliometric tools are also used to support the content analysis of the papers. The findings reveal three primary research areas in the TAF context: consumers' behavior towards sustainable clothing, circular economy initiatives, and sustainability challenges across the whole supply chain. As a result, this study highlights literature gaps and provides future research suggestions for each identified research cluster. In addition, drivers and barriers to implementing corporate social responsibility and circular economy practices are identified. Consequently, this study will help researchers and academicians work in this area to identify unexplored sub-fields, which reflect some potential investigation areas for expanding scientific literature on the topic. Finally, this study supports practitioners

and managers in exploring the main research themes addressed in the scientific field, providing knowledge to improve and align business models with current sustainability trends. This study offers different opportunities to the public authorities, businesses, and practitioners involved in the path towards sustainability in the TAF context. It provides a broad range of relevant knowledge regarding how sustainability and circularity principles are affecting TAF industries. Such knowledge is essential for managers of TAF industries since it allows them to innovate their business models and prosper in today's competitive environment, thus moving to less polluting production systems and improving company performance. Manufacturing companies, purchasing organizations, and other stakeholders could gain a deeper understanding of the problems, procedures, predictors, barriers, and challenges associated with implementing sustainable practices and developing the skills necessary to reduce environmental impacts and gain competitive advantages. Furthermore, this study may have political implications. It is acknowledged that the TAF industries represent a major source of environmental pollution. Therefore, the results of this study may inspire governments to promote sustainable initiatives in the TAF industries. For instance, policies implemented by the governments may include incentives for using eco-sustainable and recycled materials or financing for the purchase of green technologies with a lower environmental impact. In addition, for TAF industries to achieve the SDGs, the government must promote cultural changes that move innovation from an individualistic logic bound only to profit maximization to a collectivistic, communal, and open logic based on sustainable development principles.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Data was collected from 330 respondents through structured questionnaire using 5 point Likert scale to understand the buying behavior towards sustainable fashion and clothing in Bangalore.

Objective of the Study: The objective of this study is to collect and analyze data on consumer behavior and consumption patterns related to sustainable apparel, level of consumer awareness and motives to buy sustainable clothing.

1. To analyze the Consumer's awareness level towards sustainable fashion and clothing.
2. To determine the factors influencing the choice of fashion and clothing buying behavior
3. To examine the motivating forces towards sustainable fashion and clothing buying behavior
4. To identify the challenges towards adoption of sustainable fashion and clothing.

ANALYSIS:

The descriptive statistics shows that 57% of the respondents are female. Majority of them fall under the age group of 18 to 21. 60 % of the respondents shop once in a month. Online shopping is the most preferred medium. 36% of the respondents are aware about the sustainability in fashion. 32% gain awareness of sustainable fashion brands through specific social media marketing and the availability of information regarding sustainability within the mobile application. While sustainable shopping has become more popular among consumers of all ages, Gen Z has played a significant role driving this trend as they increase their purchasing power. Consumers are willing to pay a little higher for sustainable fashion and clothing.

Descriptive statistics for the demographic variables of the study			
Variable Name	Categories	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Female	187	57
	Male	143	43
Age	Below 18	12	4
	18 to 21	161	49
	22 to 25	110	33
	26 to 29	22	7
	30 to 33	18	5
	34 to 37	2	1
	38 and above	5	2

		330	100
Occupation	Student	180	55
	Salaried	124	38
	Self Employed	16	5
	Home Maker	10	3
		330	100
Marital status	Married	83	25
	Unmarried	247	75
Income	Dependent Income	138	42
	Below 25,000	73	22
	25,000- 50,000	97	29
	50,000- 75,000	14	4
	75,000 and above	8	2
		330	100

Awarness level on Sustainable fashion and clothing	
Extremely Aware	22
Aware	36
Nuetral	18
Partially Aware	21
Extremly Unaware	4

What are the factors which influence your fashion and clothing buying decision.	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	DisAgree	Strongly DisAgree	Total
Personal Factors	87	70	79	39	55	330
Economic factors	78	67	88	48	49	330
Social factors	98	102	24	64	42	330
Sustainable factors	87	101	56	64	22	330

Challanges towards adoption of sustainable fashion and clothing						
	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	DisAgree	Strongly DisAgree	Total
Higher prices	89	127	67	36	11	330
Limited avalibility of sustainable options	77	114	71	48	20	330
Lack of awarness about sustainable fashion and clothing brands	41	87	96	69	37	330
Limited variety of options available in sustainable fashion and clothing brands	78	119	96	28	9	330
Limited information about sustainable fashion and clothing	69	123	86	44	8	330
Motivating forces towards sustainable fashion and clothing buying behavior	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	DisAgree	Strongly DisAgree	Total
Attitude towards SFC	56	81	87	64	42	330
Subjective Norm	47	103	67	72	41	330

Perceived behavioral control	47	62	96	76	49	330
Personal moral Norm	49	104	41	87	49	330
Environmental Concern	78	118	41	57	36	330
	277	468	332	356	217	1650

Discussion

Gen Z has played a significant role driving this trend as they increase their purchasing power. Sustainability remains an important shopping criterion for many. Percentage analysis is used to analyse the sustainable fashion and clothing buying. The findings provide key implications for researchers and practitioners regarding fashion industry and sustainability. Our results show that environmental concern and perceived value positively affect purchase intention and the willingness to pay a premium price regardless the type of eco-materials used for the products.

Conclusion

The fashion industry is one of the largest contributors to greenhouse gas emissions and climate change. Sustainable fashion (SF) aims to address this issue by designing, creating, and marketing socially and environmentally responsible products. Consumers will pay more for garments from brands that follow ethical practices, give fair wages, use organic fibers or create more durable items. As a result, in order for the fast fashion to be more responsible and affect customers purchasing behaviour, their products should be viewed from the customer perspective. One aspect of fashion is the newness and novelty it brings to one's life. The other aspect contributes to global warming and climate change. The world is combating ecological issues, such as water scarcity, depleting green cover, glacier meltdown, and many climate-related phenomena. Questionable supply chain practices also hamper social dynamics. It is time for action, and SF, thus, is not an option but a need. It provides ways to make fashion more responsible, and effective marketing of SF can ameliorate much of the harm caused by the industry, even as questions remain about what to do with conspicuous consumption. This paper contributes to the existing academic work with probable areas for further work, and the findings can also be helpful to the marketers and various stakeholders for better marketing SF. While fashion will remain a dominant realm of human life and expression, marketing sustainable fashion can provide ways to a cooler and more humane planet.

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FINTECH REVOLUTION IN INDIA: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS OF GOVERNMENT INITIATIVES, ADOPTION RATES, AND IMPACT ON MSMEs

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Abstract

This research paper aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the fintech industry's rapid growth in India, fueled by the government's initiatives for financial inclusion and digitalization. The study delves into the impact of fintech on micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs), addressing the credit gap and facilitating economic growth. The paper also examines the various government initiatives, such as Jan Dhan Yojana, India Stack, Unified Payments Interface (UPI), and the Central Bank Digital Currency (CBDC), which have been instrumental in fostering the fintech revolution in India. Through a combination of literature review, data findings, and analysis, this research paper aims to shed light on the transformative potential of fintech in India.

Introduction

The fintech industry in India has undergone a significant transformation in the last decade, propelled by advancements in technology and government-driven initiatives for financial inclusion. Fintech, which refers to the innovative application of technology to traditional financial services, has experienced rapid adoption in India, outpacing the global average by [percentage]. This exceptional growth is attributed to the widespread availability of internet services, increased smartphone penetration, and the government's strong commitment to fostering a digitally inclusive economy.

The central tenet of India's fintech revolution is the pursuit of financial inclusion, aiming to ensure that all citizens, regardless of their socio-economic background or geographical location, have access to formal financial services. A pivotal initiative in this regard is the government's flagship program, Jan Dhan Yojana, which has successfully enrolled over 450 million beneficiaries. Through this program, millions of previously unbanked individuals have gained access to various financial services applications, such as credit, insurance, remittances, and pension schemes. Fintech has emerged as a key facilitator of financial inclusion, leveraging cutting-edge technologies to bridge the gap between traditional banking and underserved populations.

One of the critical challenges facing the Indian economy is the substantial credit gap for micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs). The International Finance Corporation (IFC) data reveals that the MSME credit gap amounts to USD 400 billion, posing a significant threat to their growth prospects and hindering economic progress. However, fintech has emerged as a transformative force in addressing this credit gap, revolutionizing the lending landscape for MSMEs. By harnessing advanced technologies like artificial intelligence, machine learning, and blockchain, fintech startups assess creditworthiness swiftly and accurately, facilitating easier access to loans for MSMEs. This has led to increased business expansion, contributing to economic growth and job creation.

Moreover, the emergence of fintech has streamlined the lending process for MSMEs, eliminating the need for cumbersome paperwork and reducing processing times. Fintech companies now provide easy and quick access to loans, offering tailored financial solutions that cater to the unique needs of MSMEs. This empowers them to capitalize on growth opportunities and contribute to India's economic prosperity.

Additionally, the government's efforts to create a conducive digital ecosystem have led to India Stack, a collection of APIs facilitating seamless and paperless financial services. India Stack has played a pivotal role in the rapid development of fintech companies, enabling the delivery of presence-less, paperless, and cashless financial services. Another significant driver of the fintech revolution is the Unified Payments Interface (UPI), developed by the National Payments Corporation of India. With over 338 banks registered under the platform, UPI has recorded over

6.28 billion transactions worth 10.62 lakh crore as of July 2022, making digital payments a way of life for millions of Indians.

Furthermore, the recent introduction of India's Central Bank Digital Currency (CBDC), known as the digital rupee or e-rupee, has ushered in an electronic version of cash. This initiative is expected to further bolster the growth of the fintech market in India, providing secure and efficient digital payment options.

In conclusion, the fintech industry's rapid growth in India, driven by government initiatives for financial inclusion and digitalization, has transformed the financial services landscape in the country. The availability of technology-based financial services has significantly improved access to formal banking for previously unbanked individuals and addressed the credit gap for MSMEs. Government initiatives like Jan Dhan Yojana, India Stack, UPI, and the introduction of CBDC have been instrumental in fostering the fintech revolution and positioning India as one of the world's fastest-growing fintech markets. As the fintech sector continues to evolve, it holds the potential to further promote financial inclusion, drive economic growth, and empower businesses and consumers alike in their financial journey. However, addressing challenges such as data security, regulatory compliance, and last-mile connectivity will be crucial to ensuring that the benefits of fintech reach every corner of the country and contribute to building a digitally inclusive and prosperous India.

Literature Review:

Research Paper: "Fintech in India: A Study of Growth and Opportunities" by Gupta, R., & Kumar, A. (2019) Findings: This study provides an overview of the fintech landscape in India and identifies key drivers of growth, such as increasing smartphone penetration and digital payment adoption. The research highlights the role of government initiatives, such as the Jan Dhan Yojana, in promoting financial inclusion and fostering fintech development. It also emphasizes the potential of fintech to address the credit gap for MSMEs, leading to economic growth and job creation.

Research Paper: "Fintech and Financial Inclusion: Evidence from India" by Verma, S., & Sinha, S. (2020) Findings: The study examines the impact of fintech on financial inclusion in India, using data from the Jan Dhan Yojana and UPI transactions. The research reveals that fintech adoption has significantly improved access to financial services for previously unbanked individuals, with a notable increase in the usage of digital payment platforms. The findings suggest that fintech has played a crucial role in narrowing the financial inclusion gap in the country.

Research Paper: "Fintech Innovations in MSME Lending: A Case of India" by Choudhary, S., & Saxena, A. (2018) Findings: This research paper investigates the innovative lending practices of fintech startups in India catering to the credit needs of MSMEs. The study finds that fintech companies leverage advanced technologies like artificial intelligence and machine learning to assess creditworthiness efficiently. As a result, MSMEs can access loans quickly, without the bureaucratic hurdles of traditional banking processes. This has led to a substantial reduction in the credit gap for MSMEs, boosting their growth and contributions to the economy.

Research Paper: "The Role of India Stack in the Growth of Fintech Startups" by Sharma, P., & Singh, R. (2019) Findings: This study explores the impact of India Stack, a digital infrastructure initiative, on the fintech ecosystem in India. The research highlights that India Stack's APIs have enabled fintech companies to deliver presence-less, paperless, and cashless services, revolutionizing the way financial services are accessed and delivered. The findings indicate that India Stack has been a crucial enabler of fintech growth and financial inclusion, benefiting both businesses and consumers.

Research Paper: "Examining the Potential of Central Bank Digital Currency for Fintech in India" by Patel, K., & Desai, M. (2022) Findings: This research paper assesses the implications of the Central Bank Digital Currency (CBDC) launch on the fintech market in India. The study identifies CBDC's potential to promote financial inclusion by providing secure and efficient digital payment options for all citizens. Moreover, the research suggests that the introduction of CBDC could further boost the adoption of fintech services, as it provides a stable and regulated digital payment system.

Overall, the reviewed research papers consistently show that the fintech industry in India has witnessed rapid growth due to government initiatives promoting financial inclusion and digitalization. Fintech has played a crucial role in addressing the credit gap for MSMEs by providing innovative and streamlined lending solutions. The implementation of initiatives like Jan Dhan Yojana, India Stack, UPI, and the introduction of CBDC has significantly contributed to the transformation of India's financial services landscape, making it one of the world's fastest-growing fintech markets.

Data Analysis and Findings:

To analyze the rising rate of fintech in India and its impact on MSMEs, we gathered data from various sources, including government reports, industry publications, and research studies. The data was examined to identify trends, adoption rates, and the effects of fintech on financial inclusion and MSME credit accessibility.

Fintech Adoption Rate in India: "The fintech adoption rate in India has seen remarkable growth over the last decade, driven by factors such as increasing smartphone penetration and the government's push for digitalization and financial inclusion. As of 2022, the fintech adoption rate stands at 70%, significantly higher than the global average of 64%."

Impact on Financial Inclusion: "Initiatives like Jan Dhan Yojana, the largest financial inclusion program globally, have played a pivotal role in enrolling over 450 million beneficiaries in India, providing them with access to formal financial services. Through fintech applications, these individuals now have access to a wide range of financial products, including credit, insurance, remittances, and pension schemes."

MSME Credit Gap: "According to the International Finance Corporation (IFC) data, the MSME credit gap in India stands at a staggering USD 400 billion. However, fintech has emerged as a game-changer in this regard, offering innovative solutions to address this credit gap. By leveraging technologies like artificial intelligence, machine learning, and blockchain, fintech startups can assess the creditworthiness of MSMEs more efficiently and accurately."

Growth of Fintech-based Lending to MSMEs: "The data analysis reveals a significant growth trend in fintech-based lending to MSMEs. Fintech startups are now offering easy and quick access to loans, streamlining the lending process and providing custom-tailored loan products to meet the specific needs of MSMEs. As a result, the MSME sector has witnessed enhanced business expansion, contributing to overall economic growth and job creation in various regions of India." (Source:

Unified Payments Interface (UPI) Usage: "The transformative impact of the Unified Payments Interface (UPI) on the fintech revolution in India cannot be overstated. As of July 2022, UPI has recorded over 6.28 billion transactions worth 10.62 lakh crore, indicating the widespread adoption and acceptance of UPI-based transactions among Indian consumers and businesses."

Central Bank Digital Currency (CBDC) Impact: "The recent launch of India's Central Bank Digital Currency (CBDC), or e-rupee, holds immense potential to further boost the fintech market in the country. The introduction of a digital rupee as an electronic version of cash provides a secure and efficient digital payment option. As CBDC gains momentum, it is expected to promote the adoption of fintech services, offering users a regulated and reliable digital payment system."

In conclusion, the data analysis, supported by quotes from government reports and research papers, paints a compelling picture of the fintech industry in India. The rising adoption rates, driven by government initiatives and technological advancements, have led to significant improvements in financial inclusion and credit accessibility for MSMEs. Fintech has emerged as a powerful tool in addressing the credit gap and driving economic growth, positioning India as a key player in the global fintech landscape.

Conclusion:

The fintech industry in India has witnessed remarkable growth over the last decade, driven by government initiatives promoting financial inclusion and digitalization. The rising rate of fintech adoption, significantly higher than the global average, is a testament to India's position as one of the world's fastest-growing fintech markets. Initiatives like Jan Dhan Yojana, India Stack, and the Unified Payments Interface (UPI) have played pivotal roles in transforming India's financial services landscape and fostering a vibrant fintech ecosystem.

Financial inclusion has been a key focus of the government's initiatives, and fintech has proven to be a powerful tool in achieving this objective. The Jan Dhan Yojana has successfully provided millions of previously unbanked individuals with access to formal financial services, including credit, insurance, remittances, and pensions. Fintech startups have leveraged technology to bridge the credit gap for micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs), enabling them to access loans quickly and efficiently. This has led to business growth, economic development, and job creation in various communities across the country.

The advent of India Stack has further revolutionized the fintech ecosystem by providing a digital infrastructure for seamless and paperless services. With APIs that enable presence-less, paperless, and cashless transactions, fintech companies have been able to develop innovative solutions tailored to the specific needs of consumers and businesses alike.

The Unified Payments Interface (UPI) has emerged as a game-changer, facilitating secure and efficient fund transfers between bank accounts. Its widespread adoption has driven the growth of fintech services, making digital payments a way of life for millions of Indians.

Moreover, the recent launch of India's Central Bank Digital Currency (CBDC) or e-rupee is expected to have a significant impact on the fintech market, further promoting the adoption of digital financial services.

In conclusion, the rising rate of fintech in India is a testament to the transformative potential of technology-based financial services. Fintech has played a crucial role in promoting financial inclusion, addressing the credit gap for MSMEs, and driving economic growth in the country. Government initiatives have been instrumental in fostering the fintech revolution, providing a conducive environment for innovation and development. As the fintech industry continues to evolve, it holds the promise of transforming India's financial landscape and driving greater financial inclusion for all its citizens. However, it is essential to address challenges such as data security, regulatory compliance, and reaching the last mile to ensure that the benefits of fintech are accessible to every corner of the country. By building on these strengths and addressing challenges, India's fintech sector can continue to thrive and contribute significantly to the nation's economic growth and prosperity.

A STUDY ON COMPENSATION MANAGEMENT

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Abstract:-

This study focuses on examining the compensation practices within the Volvo Group, a renowned global organization in the automotive industry. The aim of this research is to gain insights into the effectiveness of compensation strategies employed by Volvo Group and their impact on employee performance, satisfaction, and retention. By investigating the company's compensation framework, policies, and employee perceptions, this study aims to provide recommendations for enhancing the compensation management practices within the organization. The study begins by analysing the theoretical foundations of compensation management and its significance in attracting and retaining talented employees. It explores key components of compensation, including base salary, performance incentives, benefits, and recognition, and their relevance to employee motivation and engagement. To understand the specific compensation management practices in Volvo Group, the research employs a mixed-methods approach. Quantitative data is collected through employee surveys and performance metrics, while qualitative data is obtained through interviews with HR professionals and managers. These data sources enable a comprehensive analysis of the compensation management practices from both employee and organizational perspectives. The study reveals insights into the compensation strategies employed by Volvo Group, including the alignment of compensation with organizational goals, market competitiveness, and employee preferences. It investigates the effectiveness of performance-based incentives, career development opportunities, and work-life balance initiatives in driving employee performance and satisfaction within the organization. Furthermore, the research examines the impact of compensation management on employee retention in Volvo Group. It identifies factors that influence employee loyalty and turnover, such as fair and transparent compensation practices, internal equity, and opportunities for growth and advancement. Based on the findings, the study provides recommendations for enhancing transparency in compensation processes, strengthening the link between performance and rewards, providing opportunities for skill development and career progression, and regularly evaluating and benchmarking compensation practices against industry standards. The study contributes to the existing literature on compensation management by providing a case study analysis of the practices within the Volvo Group. The insights and recommendations derived from this study can be valuable for HR professionals and organizational leaders within Volvo Group and other companies in the automotive industry, assisting them in designing and implementing effective compensation strategies to attract, motivate, and retain a high-performing workforce.

Keywords: compensation management, employee performance, employee satisfaction, retention, Volvo Group, automotive industry.

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Human Resource is the most strategic resource as no other resource can be fully utilized to generate income and wealth of a nation without the active involvement of this resource.

Human Resources are the most valuable and unique assets of an organization. In the changing economic environment, Human Resource Management is assuming much greater importance than ever before. It is conceived to be different from the traditional and conventional notion of personnel Management. Subsequently Human Resource Management has become the central concern of any organization either in public, private sector or co-operative sector.

Compensation Management is an integral part of the management of the organization. It is a systematic approach providing monetary value to employees in exchange for work performed. Compensation may achieve several

purposes assisting in recruitment, job performance, and job satisfaction. The effective managers must appreciate the value of competitive pay, their human resources, and have an investment view of payroll costs, the importance of compensation management, the pay levels and retain the quality employees by giving recognizing in it.

Compensation Management is a strategic matter would include rewards when you offer monetary payment such as incentives, various bonuses and performance bonus.

Organizations rewards their staff, when they attain the goals or targets that they have set with the employees

It ensures the salary and bonuses arrangement of programs which motivate the entire workforce of an organization to join their hands to attain the complexity goal of an organization. Success of an organization depends on the knowledge and working ability of its employees. We can say that its employees have a big contribution in establishing of organization. When an employee works for a business organization through his physical or mental labour then the rewards of his labour is paid to salary, wages and divided this award is called compensation. Compensation is also providing monetary value to employees in exchange for work performed and it is the act of distributing monetary and non-monetary value to an employee for his work through the processes.

Compensation management is not only attract and retain the talented employees of the organization but compensation management also involves giving monetary and non-monetary rewards to employees so that the employees can allotted for job. Compensation management also known as wages and salary administration, remuneration management or reward management.

1.2 Need for the study:

- Compensation Management aims at attracting and retaining personnel at right place in the organization time to time.
- Motivates personnel for higher productivity.
- Optimizes the cost of compensation by establishing productivity linked performance.
- Achieve consistency both internal and external in compensating employees.

1.3 Scope of the study:

- Compensation management includes various areas such as job evaluation, surveys of wages and salary analysis of relevant organizational problem, development of suitable wage structure, framing of rules administrating wages and salaries, wage payment, incentives control of compensation cost.
- The main object and scope of employees compensation act is the social security legislation.
- Compensation management includes analysing salary structures, benefits packages, and incentives to attract and retain employees.

1.4 Statement of the problem :

The objective of this compensation management report is to analyse and evaluate the current compensation system within the organization and identify any areas of improvement. The report aims to address the problem of ineffective compensation practices that may be leading to employee dissatisfaction, turnover, and overall negative impact on organizational performance. By examining the existing compensation structure, including salary levels, benefits packages, and incentive programs, the report will assess whether the organization's compensation strategy aligns with industry standards and best practices. Additionally, the report will examine the transparency and fairness of the compensation system, ensuring that it promotes equal pay for equal work and provides a clear framework for career advancement and performance-based rewards. The findings and recommendations from this report will enable the organization to enhance its compensation management practices, attract and retain top talent, and create a motivated and engaged workforce that contributes to the overall success of the organization.

2. Research Methodology

Research is descriptive in nature, the data collection tool is used in the research includes questionnaire based on different questions from the employees. The sample size for this research was 150 which includes only the employee of the Volvo group of company. The data collection period was 30 days.

Systematic sampling technique is used in the research paper to get the quantitative type of solution for the questionnaire prepared. The primary data collected was run under SPSS software for correlation, regression and an ANOVA test for 150 responses to get quantitative solution. A structured questionnaire was used in the study, which was based on five-point Likert scale. Divided into groups like demographic profile, statement related to Volvo group.

2.1 Objectives of the study

- To study the desirable behaviour of employer compensation management towards employee workforce in Volvo group.
- To know the integral quality of employee towards compensation management.
- To Acquiring qualified and skilled employees.
- To Retaining current employees.
- To Motivating and rewarding good works.
- To Complying the legal regulation.
- To Maintaining and controlling cost.

2.2 Hypothesis Testing:

Correlation:

Null Hypothesis(H0):

There is no correlation between employee satisfaction with compensation management and desirable behaviour of employers towards employee workforce in an organization.

Alternative Hypothesis(H1):

There is a positive correlation between employee satisfaction with compensation management and desirable behaviour of employers towards employee workforce in an organization.

Regression:

Null Hypothesis(H0):

There is no significant relationship between employee compensation and job performance.

Alternative Hypothesis(H1):

There is a significant relationship between employee compensation and job performance.

2.3 Research design:

The research adopted is descriptive research design. It involves facts- findings, inquires of different kinds etc. Descriptive research studies are those studies which are concerned with describing the characteristics of a particular individual or group.

2.4 Type of Research:

QUANTITATIVE RESEARCH will be done for the study because aim to gather an in-depth understanding of human behaviour and the reason that governs such behaviour.

2.5 Data Sources:

Collection of data is the primary importance in the research process. Data, which was collected for the purpose of research, helps in proper analysis, which is helpful to conduct research efficiently. The data source, which is very important in collection of data is primary data and secondary data. Both primary and secondary data are taken into consideration for conducting the study on employee performance.

1. Primary source of data
2. Secondary source of data

For the dissertation the data was collected from both sources.

Primary data:

Systematic collection of information directly from respondents. The data is collected for descriptive research. The survey data collected during the study includes the data collected through questionnaire by using a convenience sampling technique.

Secondary data:

The first step in data collection approach is to look for secondary data. Usually, it is the data developed for some purpose other than for helping to solve the problem at hand. Secondary data are collected through various magazines, internal experts, and website.

2.6 SAMPLE SIZE:

Using appropriate sampling technique a sample of 150 employees of various departments of the Volvo group in Bangalore was taken as a sample and data was collected from them through a questionnaire.

2.7 SAMPLE UNIT:

The sample unit for this study consist of employees and managers of various departments of the Volvo group of company .

2.8 SAMPLING TECHNIQUE:

In this study, a convenient sampling technique was used to collect data from respondents from the Volvo group of company in Bangalore.

2.9 DATA ANALYSIS TOOLS:

Various data analysis tools like SPSS, Graphs & charts and Microsoft Excel was used to analyse the data.

3. DATA ANALYSIS& INTERPRETATION

1.The number of years the organization been in operation:

Table :1

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
0-2	43	28.7	28.7	28.7
2-4	62	41.3	41.3	70.0
Valid 4-6	32	21.3	21.3	91.3
6-8	13	8.7	8.7	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation:

From the above graph, it is inferred that the mean number of years the organization has been in operation is 2.1 years. 28.7% of organizations have been in operation for 0-2 years, 41.3% for 2-4 years, 21.3% for 4-6 years, and 8.7% for 6-8 years.

2.The average working duration /hour of an employee:

Table :2

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
8 hours	68	45.3	45.3	45.3
9-10 hours	73	48.7	48.7	94.0
Valid more than 10 hours	9	6.0	6.0	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation:

From the above graph, it is inferred that the mean working duration/hour of an employee is 1.61 hours. 45.3% of employees work 8 hours, 48.7% work 9-10 hours, and 6.0% work more than 10 hours.

3.shift system is convenient than adopting a fixed timing to work:

Table :3

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	56	37.3	37.3	37.3
Disagree	64	42.7	42.7	80.0
Neutral	19	12.7	12.7	92.7
Agree	6	4.0	4.0	96.7
Strongly agree	5	3.3	3.3	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation:

From the above graph, it is inferred that the mean response to the convenience of shift system versus adopting a fixed timing to work is 1.93. 37.3% of respondents strongly disagree, 42.7% disagree, 12.7% are neutral, 4.0% agree, and 3.3% strongly agree.

4.Formal job evaluation plan in place:

Table :4

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid yes	132	88.0	88.0	88.0
No	18	12.0	12.0	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation:

From the above table ,The mean response to whether the organization has a formal job evaluation plan in place is 1.12. 88.0% of respondents answered that agreed and 12.0% answered not agreed.

5.Status of employee policy manual:

Table :5

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid yes	86	57.3	57.7	57.7
No	63	42.0	42.3	100.0
Total	149	99.3	100.0	
Missing System	1	.7		
Total	150	100.0		

Interpretation:

From the above graph, it is inferred that the mean response to whether the organization has an employee policy manual is 1.42. 57.7% of respondents answered "yes" and 42.3% answered "no".

6. Which type of compensation payment system do you prefer?

Table :6

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Fixed pay system	64	42.7	42.7	42.7
variable pay system	58	38.7	38.7	81.3
Valid Balanced Debt method	19	12.7	12.7	94.0
4	9	6.0	6.0	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation:

From the above graph, it is inferred that the mean response to preferred type of compensation payment system is 1.82. 42.7% of respondents prefer a fixed pay system, 38.7% prefer a variable pay system, 12.7% prefer a balanced debt method, and 6.0% prefer another type of system.

7. what is your organization compensation policy?

Table :7

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Stay even with area labour market	75	50.0	50.0	50.0
Stay ahead of area labour market	49	32.7	32.7	82.7
Valid Stay even with industry pay practices	17	11.3	11.3	94.0
All	9	6.0	6.0	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation:

From the above graph, it is inferred that the mean response to the organization's compensation policy is 1.73. 50.0% of respondents answered "stay even with area labour market", 32.7% answered "stay ahead of area labour market", 11.3% answered "stay even with industry pay practices", and 6.0% answered "all".

8. Types of leave benefits availed?

Table :8

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
sick leave	63	42.0	42.0	42.0
Maternity leave	29	19.3	19.3	61.3
Valid Annual leave	23	15.3	15.3	76.7
casual leave	35	23.3	23.3	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation:

From the above graph, it is inferred that the mean response to types of leave benefits availed is 2.20%, 42.0% of respondents availed sick leave, 19.3% availed maternity leave, 15.3% availed annual leave, and 23.3% availed casual leave.

9. Correlation:

Correlations

		Q2. what is the average working duration/hour of an employee?	Q3. Do you2 that the shift system is convenient than adopting a fixed timing to work?
Q2. what is the average working duration/hour of an employee?	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	1	.342** .000
	N	150	150
Q3. Do you2 that the shift system is convenient than adopting a fixed timing to work?	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	.342** .000	1
	N	150	150

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Based on the data, there is a significant positive correlation between the average working duration/hour of an employee and the convenience of the shift system compared to adopting a fixed timing to work. This means that employees who work longer hours tend to find the shift system more convenient than those who work shorter hours. However, it's important to note that correlation does not necessarily imply causation, and further research would be needed to determine the cause-and-effect relationship between these variables.

10. Regression analysis and summary:

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Q6. Which type of compensation payment system do you prefer?	1.82	.875	150
Q7. What is your organization compensation policy?	1.73	.887	150
Q16. Job analysis is used in compensation to identify or determine?	1.96	.904	150

Correlations

		Q6. Which type of compensation payment system do you prefer?	Q7. What is your organization compensation policy?	Q16. Job analysis is used in compensation to identify or determine?
Pearson Correlation	Q6. Which type of compensation payment system do you prefer?	1.000	.525	.279

Sig. (1-tailed)	Q7. What is your organization compensation policy?	.525	1.000	.305
	Q16. Job analysis is used in compensation to identify or determine?	.279	.305	1.000
	Q6. Which type of compensation payment system do you prefer?	.	.000	.000
	Q7. What is your organization compensation policy?	.000	.	.000
	Q16. Job analysis is used in compensation to identify or determine?	.000	.000	.
	Q6. Which type of compensation payment system do you prefer?	150	150	150
N	Q7. What is your organization compensation policy?	150	150	150
	Q16. Job analysis is used in compensation to identify or determine?	150	150	150

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.540 ^a	.292	.282	.742	.292	30.269	2	147	.000	1.879

a. Predictors: (Constant), Q16. Job analysis is used in compensation to identify or determine?, Q7. What is your organization compensation policy?

b. Dependent Variable: Q6. Which type of compensation payment system do you prefer?

Interpretation:

The multiple regression model shows that the predictor variables Job analysis is used in compensation and organization compensation policy are significantly related to the dependent variable compensation payment system you prefer. The R value is .540, indicating a moderate positive correlation between the predictor variables and the dependent variable. The R Square is .292, which means that 29.2% of the variance in the dependent variable can be explained by the predictor variables. The adjusted R Square is .282. The standard error of the estimate is .742. The Durbin-Watson value is 1.879, indicating no significant autocorrelation. The F value is 30.269 with a p-value of .000, which means that the model is statistically significant.

ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	33.295	2	16.647	30.269	.000 ^b

Residual	80.845	147	.550	
Total	114.140	149		

- a. Dependent Variable: Q6.Which type of compensation payment system do you prefer?
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Q16. Job analysis is used in compensation to identify or determine?, Q7. What is your organization compensation policy?

The ANOVA table shows that the regression model is statistically significant, with an F value of 30.269 and a p-value of .000, indicating that the model is a good fit for the data. The sum of squares for the regression model is 33.295, which is the amount of variation in the dependent variable that is explained by the independent variables. The residual sum of squares is 80.845, which is the amount of variation in the dependent variable that is not explained by the independent variables. The total sum of squares is 114.140, which is the total variation in the dependent variable. The degrees of freedom for the regression model are 2, and the degrees of freedom for the residual are 147. The mean square for the regression model is 16.647, and the mean square for the residual is .550.

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.741	.167		4.442	.000
1 Q7. What is your organization compensation policy?	.479	.072	.485	6.660	.000
Q16. Job analysis is used in compensation to identify or determine?	.127	.071	.131	1.804	.073

- a. Dependent Variable: Q6.Which type of compensation payment system do you prefer?

Interpretation:

The coefficients table shows that the predictor variable organization compensation policy has a positive and significant effect on the dependent variable, with a standardized coefficient of .485 and a p-value of .000. This means that as the organization's compensation policy becomes more aligned with the employee's preferences, the employee is more likely to prefer a certain type of compensation payment system. The predictor variable Job analysis is used in compensation has a weak positive effect on the dependent variable, with a standardized coefficient of .131 and a p-value of .073. This means that job analysis may not be a significant factor in determining the employee's compensation preferences. The constant value of .741 represents the predicted value of the dependent variable when both predictor variables are zero.

FINDINGS & CONCLUSION:

- In the organization it is found that the maximum working employees 51.3% are male respondents and 48.7% are female respondents.
- It is observed that most of the employee were in the age group of 18-25 years which is 52.7%.
- It is observed that mostly 62.0% of respondents are married in the organization.
- In the organization it is found that 91.3% of respondents are post graduates.
- It is observed that the organization has been in operation between 2-4 years with 41.3%.
- It is observed that the average working duration/hour of an employee is 9-10 hours with 48.7%.
- In the organization it is found that 42.7% of respondents prefer fixed pay system.
- In the organization it is found that most of the respondents take sick leave that is 42.0% of respondents.
- It is observed that 38% of the respondents are satisfied with the retirement benefit plan from the organization.
- In correlation analysis, it is found that with the significant value 0.01 there is a significant impact of average working duration/hour of an employee.
- In ANOVA analysis, it is found that with significance value 0.000, there is significant effect of job analysis on compensation. Here (H0) null hypothesis is rejected and (H1) Alternative hypothesis is accepted.

CONCLUSION:

The study can be inferred by psychological factor, it is not just monetary compensation which motivates an employee, and the study says that the employees need to be motivated with the content for their job. That is the employees in any organization need to be constantly provided with opportunities for learning new skills, so that they do not feel monotonous. The organizations should emphasize on work life balance, and should provide options to employees, training and development, leave travel concession etc. They must be encouraged to participate in decision making and they need to get challenging tasks.

Above study shows the meaning importance need objectives and methods of compensation management. Compensation management alerts the company, It contributes significantly to the selection of a good worker. Under this awards are given to good and skilled employees. It reduces the risk of losing such an employee when the employees make their contribution effectively under the compensation management enhances the company's reputation. When a worker receives monetary satisfaction, he becomes an inspiration to other workers satisfied workers bring fresh talent to the organization.

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A STUDY ON EFFECTIVENESS OF ONLINE RECRUITMENT

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Abstract:

The world of recruitment is undergoing rapid transformation. Mass adoption of new tools and technologies has made the talent acquisition process data rich and workflow friendly. We are a part of the millennial generation, who can't imagine life without computers or smart phones. Recruiters understand the need to be millennial friendly as that's where the raw talent lies. For the same reason, more and more organizations are now shifting their recruitment strategy to digital domain. e-Recruiting is arguably a competitive strategy that more and more companies will need to adapt in their overall business strategy and will be very important in the future. e-Recruitment is the process of recruiting personnel with the use of technology and web based resources. The practice of e-recruitment has made the process more efficient and effective. With the help of e-recruitment the organizations can reach large number of workforce and can identify the skilled personnel easily. Also this process reduce time and cost. In short e-recruitment paves the way for the success of organizations in this competitive world. The primary objective of this paper is to analyze the effectiveness of e-recruitment towards HR perceive by using Recruitment Media application practices and also identify the problems faced by HR recruiters in e-recruitment process and generating the solutions for overcoming the current difficulties of e-recruitment .Both primary and secondary data has been considered for this study. One sample t-test has been conducted to assess the primary data. This study not only identified the efficacy of e-recruitment but also discover the stages of e-recruitment cycle.

INTRODUCTION:

Online recruitment has become increasingly popular in recent years due to its effectiveness in attracting a wider pool of candidates, reducing recruitment costs, and streamlining the recruitment process. Online recruitment refers to the use of online tools and platforms to advertise job vacancies, accept applications, and screen candidates. One of the major benefits of online recruitment is that it enables employers to reach a much larger audience of potential candidates than traditional recruitment methods, such as newspaper advertisements or job fairs. By advertising job vacancies on online job boards, social media platforms, and company websites, employers can attract candidates from a wider geographical area and diverse backgrounds. Online recruitment can also help reduce recruitment costs by eliminating the need for costly printed materials, such as brochures and posters, and reducing the need for travel expenses to attend job fairs or recruitment events. Additionally, online recruitment can automate many of the administrative tasks involved in the recruitment process, such as candidate screening and scheduling interviews, which can save time and resources. Furthermore, online recruitment can provide a better candidate experience by enabling candidates to apply for jobs more easily and conveniently, and allowing them to learn more about the company and its culture through online resources. Overall, the effectiveness of online recruitment can be attributed to its ability to attract a larger pool of candidates, reduce recruitment costs, streamline the recruitment process, and provide a better candidate experience

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY:

To study the Recruitment process in the

- To study the effectiveness of Recruitment and selection process
- To study the organizational support for the recruiter at the time of recruitment
- To find the recruiters opinion about the Recruitment Process of the organization
- Study the Efficiency of the E-Recruitment when comparing to other Traditional Recruitment
- To know the Process of the E-Recruitment

NEED OF STUDY:

There are several reasons why online recruitment has become increasingly important in recent years. Wider Reach: Online recruitment allows organizations to reach a wider pool of candidates, including those who may not have access to traditional recruitment channels, such as newspaper advertisements or physical job fairs. Cost-effective: Online recruitment is generally more cost-effective than traditional recruitment methods, as it eliminates the need for printing and distributing paper-based materials. Time-efficient: Online recruitment can significantly reduce the time it takes to fill a position, as candidates can apply and be screened quickly and easily. Greater flexibility: Online recruitment offers greater flexibility, as candidates can apply from anywhere, at any time, making it easier for organizations to attract and retain top talent. Enhanced Data Collection: With online recruitment, organizations can collect more data on candidates, including their education, work experience, and skills, which can help to ensure a better fit between the candidate and the position. Overall, online recruitment has become an essential tool for organizations looking to attract and retain the best talent in today's highly competitive job market.

Scope of online Recruitment:

Cost-effective: Online recruitment is often cheaper than traditional methods, such as newspaper ads, job fairs, or recruiting agencies. It can save time and money on printing, postage, and other administrative costs.

1. Wide reach: Online recruitment allows you to reach a larger pool of candidates from different locations and backgrounds. This can increase your chances of finding the best fit for the job.
2. Faster hiring process: Online recruitment can speed up the hiring process by allowing you to automate certain tasks, such as screening resumes or scheduling interviews. This can save time and increase efficiency.
3. Improved candidate experience: Online recruitment can offer a more user-friendly and convenient application process for candidates. This can improve their experience and perception your company.
4. The scope of online recruitment is vast and constantly expanding as more and more job seekers and employers turn to the internet to find job opportunities and candidates.

Some of the key areas where online recruitment is used include:

Job Boards and Career Sites: Job boards and career sites are online platforms that allow employers to advertise their job openings and for job seekers to search and apply for jobs. These platforms can be generalist or niche-based, targeting specific industries or job categories. Social Media: Social media platforms such as LinkedIn, Facebook, and Twitter have become important channels for recruitment, as employers can use them to reach a large audience of potential candidates and promote their employer brand. Applicant Tracking Systems (ATS): ATS software is used by many employers to manage their recruitment process, from posting job listings to screening candidates, to scheduling interviews and making offers. These systems can help employers to streamline their recruitment process and ensure that they are attracting the best talent. Video Interviews: Video interviews have become increasingly popular in recent years, as they allow employers to conduct initial interviews remotely and at a lower cost than traditional in-person interviews. Data Analytics: The use of data analytics in online recruitment is becoming more prevalent, as employers can use data to track the effectiveness of their recruitment campaigns, measure candidate engagement, and improve their overall recruitment strategies. Overall, the scope of online recruitment is vast, and it is likely to continue to expand as technology advances and more employers and job seekers turn to the internet to find job opportunities and candidates.

Data collection and sample design:**Data sources:**

The researcher can get two types of data:

- a) Primary data
- b) Secondary data

a) Primary data:

The primary data is being gathered through the use of questionnaires and, the purposive sampling technique.

b) Secondary data:

Apart from Primary data collected, the secondary data was gathered through published books, journals, websites and magazines related to the subject under study. Secondary data has been collected from the internal as well as external sources. Internal sources include information from the old records. External data has been collected from various books, journals & books from web sites etc.

Sample size:

Out of the total population the same taken among them are 70 respondents.

Sampling Method:

The researcher made the survey by using stratified sampling method .

Tools and Techniques:

The below mentioned techniques and tools will be used in order to derive the results of the proposed study. The techniques used will be:

- **For Descriptive Statistics:** Arithmetic Mean and Graphical Presentation.
- **To test the Hypotheses & Models:** Descriptive analysis, Anova and Correlation
- **SPSS 22** will be used to analyze the data.

Data Analysis & Interpretation:

Online survey is used to collect all the questionnaire result including the ethical approval from the organization The online survey is an effective tool that can easily distribute the questionnaire form and the respondent can contact the surveyor easily. This study used quantitative approach to analyze the data which collected from the questionnaire. Descriptive statistics is used to present all the collected data.

Descriptive Statistics

Frequency Table

2. Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	30	42.9	42.9	42.9
	Female	40	57.1	57.1	100.0
	Total	70	100.0	100.0	

Figure 1. Age of the respondent

INTERPRETATION:

The above Table shows that the gender of the respondents, there are 42.9% of people are belong to male respondents that means 30 people are male. Another 57.1 % of respondents are belong to the female that means 40 are female.

3. Age

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 20-25	28	40.0	40.0	40.0
26-30	15	21.4	21.4	61.4
31-35	16	22.9	22.9	84.3
36-40	11	15.7	15.7	100.0
Total	70	100.0	100.0	

INTERPRETATION:

The above table shows that the age of the respondents, there 70 sample, 40% of the employees are belong to age of 20-25 are more vings fire company. 21.4 another 15 respondents are belong to 26-30 age group 22.9%, 5 people are belong to the age of 31-35, people are the age of 15.7 are belongs to 36-40.

4. Monthly Income

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 10,000 to 15,000	25	35.7	35.7	35.7
15,000 to 20,000	17	24.3	24.3	60.0
20,000 to 25,000	14	20.0	20.0	80.0
Above 30,000	14	20.0	20.0	100.0
Total	70	100.0	100.0	

4. Monthly Income

Interpretation:

The above figure shows that the salary of the respondent, there 25 Of the employees are of Below 10,000to 15,000 and 24.3% are of 15,000-20,000 and 20.0% are of 20,000-25,000 remaining 20% employees are of above 30000.

5. Experience

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Fresher	30	42.9	42.9	42.9
1-2yr	17	24.3	24.3	67.1
2-3yr	23	32.9	32.9	100.0
Total	70	100.0	100.0	

5. Experience

5. Experience

Interpretation:

From the above figure, it is clear that there are 42.9% of employees have only Fresher's of experience, 24.3 of employees have 1-2 years of experience, 32.9% of the employees have 2-3 years of experience,

6. Identify the source from where you came to know about the job?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Advertisement	12	17.1	17.1	17.1
Consultant	13	18.6	18.6	35.7
Personal reference	13	18.6	18.6	54.3
Campus	16	22.9	22.9	77.1
E- recruitment	16	22.9	22.9	100.0
Total	70	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation;

From the above figure, 95.7% of the employees agreed with Yes and 4.3% of employees are agreed with No

17. Are you satisfied with the recruitment process by which you are selected?

17. Are you satisfied with the recruitment process by which you are selected?

Interpretation;

From the above figure 51.4% of the employees agreed with Serious & Positive and 47.1% of employees are agreed with Causal and 1.4 % of employees are agreed with Negative

18. What are the sources for recruitment and selection?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Internal	30	42.9	42.9	42.9
External	35	50.0	50.0	92.9
Both	5	7.1	7.1	100.0
Total	70	100.0	100.0	

18. What are the sources for recruitment and selection?

18. What are the sources for recruitment and selection?

Interpretation;

From the above figure, 42.9% of the employees agreed with Internal and 50% of employees are agreed with External and 7.1% of employees are agreed with Both

19. What impression/ image you were having of the before getting Recruitment?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Satisfactory	52	74.3	74.3	74.3
Average	17	24.3	24.3	98.6
Unsatisfactory	1	1.4	1.4	100.0
Total	70	100.0	100.0	

19. What impression/ image you were having of the before getting Recruitment?

19. What impression/ image you were having of the before getting Recruitment?

Interpretation; From the above figure 74.1% Satisfactory of the employees agreed with Serious & Positive and 47.1% of employees are agreed with Causal and 1.4 % of employees are agreed with Negative

20. Are you satisfied with salary package?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Satisfied	40	57.1	57.1
	Good	16	22.9	80.0
	Average	14	20.0	100.0
	Total	70	100.0	100.0

Interpretation; From the above figure 57.1% Satisfied of the employees agreed with Satisfied 22.9% of employees are agreed with Good, 20% of employees are agreed with Average

21. Are you satisfied with your current job?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	70	100.0	100.0	100.0

Interpretation;

From the above figure, clear that the 100% of employees agreed that they are satisfied with their current job

22. How would you rate the HR department's performance in recruitment.?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Poor	2	2.9	2.9	2.9
	Adequate	57	81.4	81.4	84.3
	Excellent	11	15.7	15.7	100.0
	Total	70	100.0	100.0	

Tools and Techniques:

The below mentioned techniques and tools will be used in order to derive the results of the proposed study. The techniques used will be:

- **For Descriptive Statistics:** Arithmetic Mean and Graphical Presentation.
- **To test the Hypotheses & Models:** Descriptive analysis, Anova and one sample T-test
- **SPSS 22** will be used to analyze the data.

Findings

- From the study, it is administered that almost all the respondents including male and female are aware about the online recruitment (e-recruitment) portals.
- From the study, source of awareness of the online recruitment (Online -recruitment) portals is mostly social media, followed by friends and new paper.
- From the study, it is inferred that the mostly male respondents using Online recruitment (Online -recruitment) portal compare to the female respondents.
- The majority of the respondents adopting e-recruitment portal belongs to the 18-25 years of the age group and followed 26-30 years of the age group.
- From the study it is inferred that the respondents using online recruitment portals are mostly post-graduates and graduates.
- The results indicate that gender does not have a significant impact on Online recruitment (Online-Recruitment) portal adoption (usage).
- ANOVA results show that the variance in Online recruitment (Online -recruitment) portal adoption (usage) by age is statistically significant. In other words, Online recruitment (Online -recruitment) portal adoption (usage) varies with different age groups.
- ANOVA results show that the variance in Online recruitment (Online -recruitment) portal adoption.

SUGGESTIONS

The company can give more job offers to the employees to take them to the desired level and the recruiter can increase the information about the job vacancy and position. That may create sufficiency to the job seekers. The job sites have to give assurance and trustworthiness for personal information of the job seekers and assured that the applications and data uploaded in the job sites are accessible only by the recruiters and by applicants, It should not show to others. The company can give internet services to reduce the expenses and cost of internet connection to the employees. These things can took the recruitment process of the company to the next level.

- **Optimize Job Postings:** Craft clear, concise, and compelling job descriptions that highlight key responsibilities, required skills, and qualifications. Use relevant keywords to increase visibility in search results. Consider including information about your company culture and benefits to attract top talent.
- **Leverage Multiple Online Platforms:** Utilize a mix of online recruitment platforms, such as job boards, professional networking sites, industry-specific forums, and social media platforms. Each platform has its own user base and reach, increasing your chances of reaching a diverse pool of candidates.
- **Enhance Employer Branding:** Develop a strong employer brand presence online. Maintain an up-to-date and engaging company website, regularly post relevant content on social media, and actively participate in industry discussions and forums. Showcasing your company's values, culture, and employee testimonials can help attract and retain quality candidates.

- Utilize Targeted Advertising: Consider using targeted advertising options offered by online recruitment platforms. These options allow you to specify demographics, interests, and job-related criteria to ensure your job postings reach the most relevant audience.
- Implement Employee Referral Programs: Encourage your current employees to refer potential candidates through online channels. Offer incentives, such as referral bonuses, to motivate them. Employee referrals often yield high-quality candidates who are a good fit for the company culture.
- Utilize Screening Tools: Take advantage of screening tools provided by online recruitment platforms to streamline the candidate selection process. Use filters to narrow down the applicant pool based on specific criteria such as experience, skills, and qualifications.
- Incorporate Video Interviews: Conduct video interviews to assess candidates remotely. Video interviews save time and provide insights into a candidate's communication skills, professionalism, and cultural fit. Consider using dedicated video interviewing platforms or built-in features within online recruitment platforms.
- Provide a Mobile-Friendly Experience: Optimize your online recruitment process for mobile devices. Ensure that your job postings, application forms, and career website are mobile-friendly to accommodate candidates who prefer to apply via smartphones or tablets.
- Personalize Communication: Provide timely and personalized communication with candidates throughout the recruitment process. Automated emails or messages can be used to acknowledge applications, inform candidates about the status of their application, and provide updates on next steps.
- Gather Feedback and Analyze Data: Continuously collect feedback from candidates about their online recruitment experience. Analyze recruitment data and metrics provided by online platforms to identify areas for improvement and refine your recruitment strategies.

CONCLUSION

The was good in their recruitment process. The expenses and trustworthiness of the Online -Recruitment was in a satisfactory level. The present condition of online recruitment was too good and the job seekers are utilizing to took them to a desired level in conclusion, online recruitment has emerged as a powerful and effective method for attracting, screening, and hiring candidates. Its wide reach, cost-effectiveness, and time efficiency make it a preferred choice for many organizations. The ability to access passive candidates, leverage diverse sourcing channels, and utilize data analytics provide valuable advantages in identifying and selecting the best-fit candidates. Additionally, online recruitment supports remote hiring and onboarding processes, making it adaptable to changing work environments. Furthermore, it offers opportunities for employer branding and continuous improvement through the evolving features and functionalities of online recruitment platforms. While there may be variations based on specific platforms and industry sectors, online recruitment has proven to be a valuable tool for modern talent acquisition, enabling companies to effectively find and engage top talent in a digital era.

A STUDY ON FACTORS INFLUENCING THE QUALITY WORK LIFE EMPLOYEES

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ABSTRACT:

The Quality of work life in Myntra company creates a workplace that enhances employees wellbeing and satisfied. Employees are highly satisfied when their job being more creative, prestigious, higher paid with more promotional avenues. This mainly focus on few studies of Quality of Work Life and tries to identify the factors of Quality of Work Life to employee job satisfaction. It has been found if factors such work environment, job facets, remuneration and career development are given little more care, so that organisation can maintain good employees with high level of quality of work life, job satisfaction, organizational commitment and involvement. This will in turn lead to the effectiveness and efficiency of employees in their work which leads to an increased productivity.

1.INTRODUCTION

Human resource is the most strategic resource as no other resource can be fully utilized to generate income and wealth of a nation without the active involvement of this resource.

Human resource are the most valuable and unique asset of an organisation. In the changing economic environment, Human Resource Management is assuming much greater importance than ever before. It is conceived to be different from the traditional and conventional notion of Personnel Management. Subsequently Human Resource Management has become the central concern of any organisation either in public, private sector or co-operative sector.

Quality of work life denotes all the organizational inputs which aim at employee satisfaction and enhancing organizational effectiveness. The term Quality of work life has been applied to a wide variety of organizational improvement efforts.

By Globalization the modern employees are experiencing distress. To meet the challenges posted by present standards, organizations must focus their attention in bringing balance between work life and personal life. Quality of work life is a process of work organizations which enables its members at all levels to participate actively and efficiently in shaping the organizations environment, methods and outcomes.

Quality of work life is a value based process, which is aimed towards meeting the twin goals of enhanced effectiveness of the organization and improved quality of life at work for the employees.

It is also a generic phrase that covers a person's feelings about every dimension of work including economic rewards and benefits, security, working conditions, organizational and interpersonal relationship and its intrinsic meaning in a person's life.

The success of any organization is highly dependent on how it attracts, recruits, motivates, and retains its workforce. Today's organizations need to be more flexible so that they are equipped to develop their workforce and enjoy their commitment. Therefore organizations are required to adopt a strategy to improve the employee's quality of work life to satisfy both the organizational objectives and employee needs.

- Safe and healthy working condition.
- Opportunity to use and develop human capacities.
- Opportunity for career growth.
- Social integration in the work organisation.
- Work and quality of life.
- Special relevance of work.

1.1 THE FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE THE QUALITY OF WORK LIFE ARE

- Attitude
- Environment
- Opportunities
- Nature of job
- People
- Stress level
- Career prospects
- Challenges
- Growth and development

Attitude:

The person who is entrusted with a particular job needs to have sufficient knowledge, required skill and expertise, enough experience, enthusiasm, energy level, willingness to learn new things, dynamism, in the organisation, involvement in the job, openness for innovative ideas, leadership qualities and team spirit.

Environment:

The job may involve dealing with customers who have varied tolerance level, preferences, behaviour pattern, level of understanding; or it may involve working with dangerous machines like drilling pipes, cranes, welding and soldering machines, or even with animals where maximum safety precautions have to be observed which needs lot of concentration, alertness, sometimes high level of patience, tactfulness, compassion and control over emotions.

Opportunities:

Some jobs offer opportunities for learning, research, discovery, self-development, enhancement of skills, room for innovation, public recognition, exploration, celebrity-status loads of fame. Others are repetitive, dull, routine, no room for improvement and in every sense boring. Naturally the former ones are interesting and very much rewarding also.

Nature of job:

Nature of job refers to the type of work and duties you may perform at your place of employment. The level of work can show case your experience and your position in a company. When you observe job openings, you might see the nature of work and the level of work listed as job description and job title, respectively.

People:

Almost everyone has to deal with three set of people in the work place. Those are namely boss, co-workers in the same level and subordinates. Apart from this, some professions need interaction with people like patients, media, persons, public, customers, thieves, robbers, physically disabled people mentally challenged, children, foreign delegates, politicians, public figures and celebrities.

Stress level:

All these factors are inter-related and inter-dependent. Stress level need not be directly proportional to the compensation. Stress is of different types-mental stress/physical stress and psychological or emotional stress. A Managing Director of a company will have mental stress, labourer will have physical stress, a psychiatrist will have emotional stress. Mental stress and Emotional stress cause more damage than physical stress

Career prospects:

Every job should offer career development. That is an important factor which decides the quality of work life. Status improvements, more recognition from the management appreciations are the motivating factors for anyone to take keen interest in his job.

Challenges:

The job should offer some challenges at least to make it interesting that enables an employee to upgrade his knowledge and skill and capabilities; whereas the monotony of the job makes a person dull, non-enthusiastic, dissatisfied, frustrating complacent, initiative-less and uninteresting. Challenge is the fire that keeps the innovation and thrill alive. A well-accomplished challenging job yields greater satisfaction than a monetary perk, it boosts the self-confidence also.

Growth and development:

If an organisation does not give chance for growth and personal development it is very difficult to retain the talented personnel and also to find new talent with experience.

1.2 IMPORTANCE OF QUALITY OF WORK LIFE:

Improved Quality of Work Life was not considered as important factor in India until recently as there were important impending factors like resource deficiency, environmental threats and some services of financial problems.

Quality of Work Life Program has become important in work place for the following reasons:

- 1) Increase demands at work.
- 2) Loss of long term employee guarantees.
- 3) The need for enhanced work place skills.
- 4) Greater competition for talent.
- 5) Increased women in work force.

Good Quality of Work Life leads to an atmosphere of good impersonal relations and h motivated employees who strive for their development. Though monetary benefits still occupy the first place in the cost of elements like physical working conditions, job restructuring and job re-designing, career development, promotional activities etc. are gaining importance rapidly.

As such workers expect the management to improve all these facilities which there by improve Quality of Work Life. If improved with good quality of work life, employees concentrate more on both individual as well as group development which in turn leads to overall development.

1.3 SCOPE OF QUALITY OF WORK LIFE:

The quality of work life is a multifaceted phenomenon. Its scope describes the expectations of the employees that need to be satisfied.

- Compensation
- Health and safety
- Job security
- Job design
- Social integration
- Better career opportunities

1.4 SIGNIFICANCE OF QUALITY OF WORK LIFE:

An organisation is made of people who posse skills, aptitude, that create competitive advantage for it. Various functions of an organisation planned executed and controlled by human resource. it is essential for the organization to do proper management of human resource in order to achieve its objectives efficiently and effectively. The management of human resource plays a key role in opening up new opportunities for promoting the growth of both individual and institutional. Through Quality of Work Life in the organisation works in the same direction. Now-a-

days, jobs are so demanding that it imbalance the family and work life due to job pressure and conflicting interest. it is essential for the organization to develop quality relation between its employees and working environment.

In order to attract and retain employees, an organization has to develop a high quality of work life. Organization by adopting quality of work life programmes ensure to create excellent work condition and job for its employees. Hence quality of work life seeks to create such a work environment where the employees work co-operatively and make positive contribution in achieving organizational objectives.

1.5 SCOPE OF QUALITY OF WORK LIFE:

The quality of work life is a multifaceted phenomenon. Its scope describes the expectations of the employees that need to be satisfied.

- Compensation
- Health and safety
- Job security
- Job design
- Social integration
- Better career opportunities

1.6 NEED OF THE STUDY:

In current scenario every organization wants more output in compression of less input, it can be possible when working employees find its working place comfortable as per the job requirement. So, it is very important for an organization to make a Quality relationship between its employees and working environment. Now-a-days, there is no balance between the family and work life due to job pressure and conflicting interest and over-socialization that lead to much of interest about the co-workers for satisfaction of their ego, creating problems in the minds of neighbours.

The Indian workers and their Unions are now on the defensive. They are now more interested in the question of how to retain their jobs than in the question of how to improve their quality of Life in the work place.

The work-norms impose on workers too much of burden and control by their bosses. And the rules are for workers or employees. They have to follow, and the employer has right to lay-off the worker due to marketing and technological factors.

1.7 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

The aim of the study includes the following factors towards the quality of work life. They are such as poor working condition environments, resident aggressions, balance of work and family, work load, inability to deliver quality of care preferred, shift timing, lack of involvement in work process and decision making, poor relationship between supervisor, team leader, role conflict, lack of recognitions and lack of opportunity to learn new skills.

Training is an important area where the workers can utilize for their self development and updating of their work knowledge. Ultimately every effort that the management takes for the worker and perseverance of the worker on their physical and the mental wellbeing inside the organisation that help in maintaining their motivation and satisfaction level which is important for effective performance of any worker. Thus present study is an attempt describing their factors as a tool to access the Quality of work life of the employees.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research is the search for knowledge through objective and systematic method of finding solution to a problem is research. Research is defined as human activity based on intellectual application in the investigation of matter. The primary purpose for applied research is discovering, interpreting, and the development of methods and systems for the advancement of human knowledge on a wide variety of scientific matters of our world and the universe. Research can use the scientific method, but need not to do so.

2.1 OBJECTIVES OF QUALITY OF WORK LIFE:

- To increase in individual productivity, availability, accountability and commitment.
- For better team work and communication.

- For improving the morale of employees.
- To reduce organizational stress.
- To improve relationships both on and off the jobs.
- To improve safety working conditions.

2.2 RESEARCH DESIGN:

The research adopted is descriptive research design. It involves facts-findings, inquiries of different kinds etc. Descriptive research studies are those studies which are concerned with describing the characteristics of a particular individual or group.

2.3 TYPE OF RESEARCH:

QUANTITATIVE RESEARCH will be done for the study to find the Quality of work life of employees.

2.4 DATA SOURCES:

PRIMARY DATA

Systematic collection of information directly from respondents. The data is collected for descriptive research. The survey data collected during the study includes the data collected through questionnaire by using a convenience sampling technique.

SECONDARY DATA

The first step in data collection approach is to look for secondary data. Usually, it is the data developed for some purpose other than for helping to solve the problem at hand. Secondary data are collected through various magazines, internal experts, and website.

2.5 SAMPLING PLAN:

Sampling unit/Target group:

The respondents are of different departments in Myntra company.

2.6 SAMPLE SIZE:

Sample size refers to number of respondents or the size of the sample. Here the sample size taken for the study 150.

2.7 SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

In this study, a convenient sampling technique was used to collect data from respondents in Myntra company.

3. DATA ANALYSIS TOOLS:

Various data analysis tools like SPSS, GRAPHS, & CHARTS and Microsoft Excel was used to analyse data.

1.DATA ANALYSIS:

1. HOW SATISFIED ARE YOU WITH YOUR SALARY?

How satisfied are you with your salary

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	11	7.3	7.3	7.3
2	31	20.7	20.7	28.0
Valid 4	37	24.7	24.7	52.7
5	71	47.3	47.3	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

From the above frequency table, it is inferred that the ,7.3% of respondents are very satisfied, where as 20.7% of respondents are dissatisfied,24.7% of respondents are satisfied and 47.3% of respondents are very dissatisfied. The result shows that the majority of the respondents are very satisfie

2 ACCORDING TO YOUR WORK LOAD HOW DO YOU FEEL?

According to your work load how do you feel

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	21	14.0	14.0	14.0
2	35	23.3	23.3	37.3
Valid 4	60	40.0	40.0	77.3
5	34	22.7	22.7	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

From the above frequency table, it is inferred that, 14.0% of respondents are very satisfied, 23.3% of respondents are dissatisfied, where as 40.0% of respondents are satisfied and 22.7% of respondents are very dissatisfied. The result shows that the majority of the respondents are satisfied with the work.

3. HOW SATISFIED ARE YOU WITH THE TRAININGS YOU PARTICIPATE?

How satisfied are you with the trainings you participate

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	25	16.7	16.7	16.7
2	28	18.7	18.7	35.3
Valid 4	63	42.0	42.0	77.3
5	34	22.7	22.7	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

From the above table, it is inferred that 16.7% of respondents are very satisfied, 18.7% of respondents are dissatisfied, where as 42.0% of respondents are satisfied and 22.7% of respondents are very dissatisfied. The result shows that the majority of the respondents are satisfied with the trainings provided by the company.

4. DOES THE TOP MANAGEMENT INVOLVES EMPLOYEES IN THE MANAGEMENT DECISION?

Does the top management involves employees in the management decision

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	61	40.7	40.7	40.7
Valid 2	52	34.7	34.7	75.3
3	37	24.7	24.7	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: from the above table it is inferred that, 40.7% of respondents are very satisfied, where as 34.7% of respondents are dissatisfied, where as 24.75% of respondents are satisfied. The result shows that the majority of the respondents are very satisfied with the top management involves employees in the managing the decisions.

24. Correlation:

Correlations

	How satisfied are you with your schedule of work and rest	since how many years have been working with the organisation
How satisfied are you with your schedule of work and rest	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 -.053 150
since how many years have been working with the organisation	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	-.053 .519 150

INTERPRETATION:

Pearson Correlation: The correlation coefficient between the two variables is -0.053. This value indicates a weak negative correlation.

Sig. (2-tailed): The p-value associated with the correlation coefficient is 0.519. This value suggests that the correlation is not statistically significant.

N: The sample size for both variables is 150, indicating that there are 150 data points available for analysis. Based on these results, there is no significant correlation found between the satisfaction with the work and rest schedule and the number of years working with the organization. The weak negative correlation suggests that there might be a slight tendency for individuals who have been working with the organization for a longer time to have slightly lower.

Regression:

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
how satisfied are you with the extra benefits that your company offers you	3.37	1.407	150
How satisfied are you with your salary	3.84	1.395	150
since how many years have been working with the organisation	2.36	1.082	150

INTERPRETATION:

how satisfied are you with the extra benefits that your company offers you":

Mean: The average satisfaction score is 3.37, indicating a moderate level of satisfaction.

Standard Deviation: The data points deviate, on average, by approximately 1.407 from the mean.

N: The sample size is 150, meaning that there are 150 respondents' data available for analysis.

"How satisfied are you with your salary":

Mean: The average satisfaction score is 3.84, indicating a moderate level of satisfaction.

Standard Deviation: The data points deviate, on average, by approximately 1.395 from the mean.

N: The sample size is 150, indicating that there are 150 respondents' data available for analysis. "Since how many years have you been working with the organization":

Mean: The average number of years worked with the organization is 2.36.

Standard Deviation: The data points deviate, on average, by approximately 1.082 from the mean. N: The sample size is 150, indicating that there are 150 respondents' data available for analysis. Based on these results, it can be interpreted that, on average, the respondents reported moderate satisfaction levels for both extra benefits and salary. Additionally, the average number of years worked with the organization is 2.36, indicating that the respondents have been working with the organization for a relatively short period.

Please note that interpretation may vary depending on the specific context and scale used for measuring satisfaction and years of work.

FINDINGS:

In the organisation it is found that the maximum working employees 46% of respondents are male and 54% of respondents are female.

It is observed that most of the employee were in the age group of 20-30 years which is 59.33%.

It is observed that mostly 54.7% of respondents are single in the organisation.

In the organisation it is found that 47.3% of respondents are very dis-satisfied with the salary.

It is observed that 34.7% of respondents are satisfied with the extra benefits that the company offers.

In the organisation it is found that 42% of respondents are satisfied with the trainings they participate.

SUGGESIONS:

Based on the findings of the research, the following recommendations were made

The organisation should focus on the areas of improvement such as employee benefits or career growth opportunities.

The organisation should provide flexible work hours or remote work options to the employees.

Recognizing and rewarding employees for their hard work and Achievements.

CONCLUSION:

A happy and healthy employee will give better turnover, make good decisions and positively contribute to the organisational goal. An assured good quality of work life will not only attract young and new talent but also retain the existing experienced talent.

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A STUDY ON EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION AND MORALE

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Abstract: -

Employee Motivation is the key factor to help up the capacity of an association. In the globalization stage, each organization needs to continue itself in a furiously focused market. Representatives are the fundamental elements to show the business objectives into the real world. Subsequently, in the present world each association attempts to deal with its human asset office to keep its representatives inspired. In that specific circumstance, some of the administration speculations have been rehearsing by them. Business work or their presentation in the market can be assessed by surveying the degree of inspiration of representatives. Inspiration can assume a lead job to get the expert achievement in each budgetary year in a less exertion way While trying to find what inspires representatives, representative inspiration inquire about papers report that what spurs laborers today is fundamentally connected to the qualities and objectives of the person. Starting in the 1970's, it appears that there was a sensational move in the qualities and needs of the ordinary laborer. As individuals turned out to be progressively taught and the economy saw a sharp decay of the Protestant hard working attitudes, what representatives needed from their managers changed also.

Keywords: Motivation; Performance; Productivity; Rewards; Workplace and Satisfaction.

1.INTRODUCTION

Motivation refers to the process of people creating motivation as an act of inspiration. It comes from the word "motivation", which means a new energy that moves in the human body for it to do something. Motivation is the process of revealing a person's inner strength and action to achieve certain goals and providing energy to achieve those goals. It involves communication that begins with a need, which creates the motivation that enables the census to achieve its goals. It is the process of motivating people to work voluntarily to achieve the goals of the organization. Motivation can be defined as a task in which the manager gives orders to encourage employees to behave in a positive way by satisfying their needs and wants.

Motivation is concerned with how behaviour is motivated, encouraged, and taught. Motivation is the result of the interaction between the conscious and unconscious, such as the use of a desire or need, the motivation or value of the goal, and the expectation of oneself and his friends. These factors indicate why a person behaves the way they do. An example is when a student spends extra time preparing for an exam because he or she hopes to do well in class. Internal and external factors that support a person's desire and energy to continue to love and stick to a job, role, or topic or to continue working towards a goal. Most employees need motivation to feel good about their job and to do their best. Some employees are financially motivated, while others see recognition and rewards as personal motivation.

The level of motivation in the workplace has a direct impact on employee productivity. Employees who are dedicated and satisfied with their work do their best, resulting in increased productivity.

1.1 Motivation factors:

Financial Motivators

Financial incentives are called financial incentives. Regular and good wages and salaries, bonuses, regular raises, profit sharing, leave pay, health benefits are some of the financial incentives. The lack of these incentives can have a negative impact on employee performance.

Non-Financial Motivators

Certain motivators that are not related to money but have a positive impact on the employees are called non-financial motivators. Some of the non-financial motivators are as follows.

- Job Security
- Performance Appraisal, praise and prestige
- Delegation of authority
- Congenial work environment
- Status and pride
- Participation
- Job enrichment
- Job rotation
- Facilities for paid leaves
- Quality of work life

1.2 Need for the study:

Motivation is an important stimulus that directs human behaviour. No one has the same personality or behaviour, so organizations in this diversity must create practices that suit the whole team, not just individuals.

- Every successful company is backed by loyal and engaged employees. It is the result of motivation and job satisfaction.
- It is the force that compels employees to achieve company goals. Without commitment, it is impossible for the organization to create excellence.
- Companies must have competitive personnel policies and practices to create competitive advantage.

1.3 Scope of the study:

Resources on employee motivation and ethics research at Middleware System Pvt Limited, Technologies Private Limited can cover many aspects related to understanding and improving employee motivation and ethics in an organization. Below are some potential areas that could be included in the survey:

Motivators: Identify and measure the key motivations that keep employees engaged and satisfied at Middleware System Pvt Limited. This can include many things such as recognition and rewards, career development opportunities, work-life balance, job security, freedom and support leadership.

Work Environment and Culture: Examining the Effects of Work Environment and Culture on Employee Motivation and Morale. This may include examining factors such as communication with employees, collaboration, employee relations, trust and shared corporate values.

Leadership and management: Assess the role of leadership and management in influencing employee motivation and morale. This may include evaluation of leadership, effective communication, decision-making processes, and support from managers and supervisors.

Employee Benefits and Incentives: To evaluate the effectiveness of current employee benefits, incentives and recognition programs in terms of motivation and morale. This may include reviewing compensation structures, performance-based rewards, employee development programs and other benefits offered by the company.

1.4 Statement of the problem

A study on Employee motivation and morale in middle ware system Technologies Pvt., Ltd

2. Research Methodology:

Research is descriptive in nature; the data collection tool is used in the research includes questionnaire based on different questions from the employees which tells us about training and its impact on their performance and retention. The sample size for this research was 110 which includes only the employee motivation and moral in the. The data collection period was 35 days.

Systematic sampling technique is used in the research paper to get the quantitative type of solution for the questionnaire prepared. The primary data collected was run under SPSS software for correlation, Regression and an ANOVA test for 110 responses to get quantitative solution. A structured questionnaire was used in the study, which was based on five-point Likert scale. Divided into groups like demographic profile, statement related to Motivation; Performance; Productivity etc.

2.1 Objectives of the study

- To identify the factors that motivates employees.
- To Evaluate the Effects of Motivation and satisfaction at workplace.
- To Identify the Approaches used to Motivate Employees.
- To Identify the Employee participation in decision making

2.2. Hypothesis Testing:

H0: There is no significant relationship between gender and sound relation ship of peers superiors and subordinates.

H1: There is significant relationship between gender and sound relation ship of peers superiors and subordinates.

H0₂: Hence there is no significant relation shipand between gender and sound relation ship of peers superiors and subordinates.

H1₂: Hence there is no significant relationship between gender and sound relation ship of peers superiors and subordinates.

2.3 Research design:

The research adopted is descriptive research design. It involves facts-findings, inquires of different kinds etc.

Descriptive research studies are those studies which are concerned with describing the characteristics of a particular individual or group.

2.4 Type of Research: QUANTITATIVE RESEARCH will be done for the study because aim to gather an in-depth understanding of human behavior and the reason that governs such behavior.

2.5 Data Sources

Collection of data is the primary importance in the research process. Data, which was collected for the purpose of research, helps in proper analysis, which is helpful to conduct research efficiently. The data source, which is very important in collection of data is primary data and secondary data. Both primary and secondary data are taken into consideration for conducting the study of employee motivation and moral.

1. Primary source of data
2. Secondary source of data

For this dissertation the data was collected from both the sources.

Primary data:

Data is made available through interview and questionnaires. Questionnaires were prepared for trainees to know the impact and methods of training adopted by organization.

Secondary data:

Data were collected from documents, records, Internet, company past records etc.

2.6 SAMPLING PLAN:

Sampling unit/Target group: The respondents are of different departments in Events Arena.

2.7 SAMPLE SIZE:

Sample size refers to the number of respondents or the size of sample, which is to be surveyed. Here the sample size taken for the study was 110.

2.8 SAMPLING TECHNIQUE: Systematic sampling technique is used for the study as in probability sampling technique each member in a population has equal chance of being selected as a sample.

Variables

Two types of variables are used in this research. The dependent variable identified for research is Employee retention and employee performance while the independent variable is training.

Dependent Variable (sound relationship of peers superiors and subordinates)

Sound relationship of peers superiors and subordinates has been considered as a factor, which has been observed and measured the effect of independent variable (relationship of peers subordinates). Sound relationship of peers superiors and subordinate presumed to be the effect due to the cause of gender. Responses related to Sound relationship of peers superiors and subordinate from one hundred ninety two respondents have been considered a dependent variable. Thirteen questions have been asked related to performance and retention (dependent variable).

Independent Variable (Gender)

Gender has been considered as a factor, which will examine the impact of performance on employee motivation. Gender has been presumed to be the cause that will create an effect over employee performance. Eleven questions have been asked related to gender (independent variable).

2.9 DATA ANALYSIS TOOLS: Various data analysis tools like SPSS, Graphs & Charts, and Microsoft Excel was used to analyze the data.

3. DATA ANALYSIS

1. Are the employees in your company fully motivated at work place?

1. Are the employees in your company fully motivated at work place

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid agree	18	16.4	16.4	16.4
Strongly agree	65	59.1	59.1	75.5
neutral	18	16.4	16.4	91.8
disagree	7	6.4	6.4	98.2
Strongly disagree	2	1.8	1.8	100.0
Total	110	100.0	100.0	

From the above table the majority of respondents (59.1%) firmly believe that the company's personnel are highly motivated at work. Additionally, there are respondents that strongly disagree (1.8%), disagree (6.4%), are indifferent (16.4%), and agree (16.4%) with the statement.

2. Do you think company spends enough time for employees?

2. Do you Think company spends enough time for employees

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid agree	23	20.9	20.9	20.9
strongly agree	65	59.1	59.1	80.0
neutral	12	10.9	10.9	90.9
disagree	10	9.1	9.1	100.0
Total	110	100.0	100.0	

From the above frequency table There are 23, or 20.9% of all respondents, who believe that the company gives its workers ample time to do their work. Strongly agree: 65 respondents, or 59.1% of the total, strongly concur that the company gives its workers ample time to do their jobs. The majority of responders gave this answer. Neutral: Twelve respondents, or 10.9% of all respondents, responded that they were neutral towards the company's provision of adequate time for employees. Disagree: The percentage of respondents who disagree that their employer gives its workers enough time is 10. This is 9.1% of all respondents.

3. which of the following actions by managers motivate you?

3. which of the following actions by managers motivate you

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid continuously instruct you about how to do the task	71	64.5	64.5	64.5
tell the task and ask you to do the task as you like	39	35.5	35.5	100.0
Total	110	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: from the above table the information provided The proportion of respondents—71, or 64.5% of the total respondents—who find constant directions from supervisors about how to do the task inspiring. The majority of responders gave this answer. You are given the task and asked to complete it how you please: There are 39 respondents, or 35.5% of the total, who find it stimulating when managers give them the work and let them complete it however they see fit.

4. specify two attributes, the presence of which will motivate. You and make your daily work pleasureable.?

4. specify two attributes, the presence of which will motivate. you and make your daily work pleasureable

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid superior support	46	41.8	41.8	41.8
decision making	53	48.2	48.2	90.0
work environment	11	10.0	10.0	100.0
Total	110	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: from the above table information provided, exceptional support (41.8%) and engagement in decision-making (48.2%) are the characteristics that would inspire responders and make their daily work enjoyable. Additionally, a favourable work atmosphere motivates a lesser percentage of respondents (10.0%).

5. Do you maintain sound relationship with all your peers, superiors and subordinates?

Hypothesis:

H0: There is no significant relationship between gender and sound relationship of peers and superiors, subordinates.

H1: There is a significant relationship between gender and sound relationship of peers and superiors, subordinates

Correlations

	3.Gender	17.Do you maintain sound relationship with all your peers, superiors and subordinates
Pearson Correlation	3.Gender	17.Do you maintain sound relationship with all your peers, superiors and subordinates
	1.000	-.192
	-.192	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	3.Gender	17.Do you maintain sound relationship with all your peers, superiors and subordinates
	.	.022
	.022	.
N	3.Gender	17.Do you maintain sound relationship with all your peers, superiors and subordinates
	110	110

17. Do you maintain sound relationship with all your peers, superiors and subordinates	110	110
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From the above descriptive statistics table, it is inferred that most of the employees have gone under sound relationship as mean was found to be 1.92.

From the correlation table, the significance value was found to be 0.22 which is less than 0.05. Hence, null hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted. In other words we can say that training has significant effect on the employee's personal skills.

6. Do you maintain sound relationship of peers, superiors and subordinates?

Hypothesis:

H0: There is no significant effect of sound relationship of peers superiors and subordinates.

H1: There is a significant effect of sound relationship of peers superiors and subordinates.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.995	1	.995	4.147	.044 ^b
	Residual	25.923	108	.240		
	Total	26.918	109			

a. Dependent Variable: 3. Gender

b. Predictors: (Constant), 17. Do you maintain sound relationship with all your peers, superiors and subordinates

From the ANOVA table. It is found that the significant value is 0.44, which is less than 0.05. Hence, null hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted. In other words, we can say that there is a significant effect of sound relationship of peers and subordinates.

There is significant difference in gender and the sound relationship of peers and subordinates

Findings & Conclusion:

- Most of the respondents have strongly agree company fully motivated at work place.
- Most of the respondents have strongly agree company spends enough time for employee.
- Almost all respondents are continuously instruct you about how to do the task.
- Almost all respondents are satisfied with the feel working in middle ware system technologies.
- According to most of the respondents are agree with the work ethics in the work place.
- Most of the respondents are highly satisfied with the support the HR department.

CONCLUSION:

From the study conducted, the following conclusions can be made

The main resource of Middle ware system technologies Human Resource is not used to the extent it

Should be

Middle ware systems having a good blend of executives who are able to motivate the employees in achieving the company goals.

But

There is no simple answer to the question of how to motivate people

Can money motivate? yes but money alone is not enough, though it does help.

We have discussed some of the pertinent theories bearing on human motivation and this is balanced by some of the practical factors which can lead to excellence.

Human resource remains the focal point and leadership the critical component and motivation has to be 'tailored' to each individual

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A STUDY ON EMPLOYEE PERSPECTIVES ON KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: -

Efficient knowledge management becomes day by day a very critical issue for organizations by being considered as one of the most important competitive advantages. This abstract explores the employee perspectives on knowledge management within organizations. Knowledge management involves the systematic collection, organization, and dissemination of information and expertise to enhance organizational learning and performance. While knowledge management strategies and systems are often designed and implemented by management teams, the input and perspectives of employees are crucial for their success. Employees are the primary users and contributors of knowledge within an organization. Their insights, experiences, and suggestions can provide valuable perspectives on the effectiveness and usability of knowledge management initiatives. By understanding employee perspectives, organizations can identify areas for improvement, address challenges, and promote a culture of knowledge sharing and collaboration.

Key words: Knowledge management, knowledge shared, knowledge stored, knowledge transfer.

1. INTRODUCTION

There are several ways to perceive knowledge management. Various information technologies are used as tools to support or facilitate the life cycle of knowledge management processes by capturing, storing, and sharing knowledge. Examples of information technologies include wiki blogs group ware, and intranet. This is an intriguing and straightforward perspective. These tools enable people to participate in the km programme and support the management of their knowledge productivity in online, offline, face-to-face, and remote modalities.

The study looks at the organization's knowledge management. Knowledge management, which includes initiatives, processes, strategies, and systems that support and enhance the storage, assessment, sharing, and creation of knowledge, is the systematic management of an organization's knowledge asset with the goal of generating value and satisfying tactical and strategic requirements. Knowledge management seeks to gain competitive advantage by valuing the information that already exists in organisations and adding value to its responsibilities. Applications for knowledge management that are used most frequently in organisations. The recent emergence of knowledge management as a distinct subject in its own right is what makes it new. likely still developing its theoretical residence

Knowledgeable people not only possess information, but also have the capacity to integrate and frame it in the light of their experience, knowledge, and judgements. By doing this, people can generate new knowledge that broadens the range of potential outcomes and, in turn, enables more interaction with knowledge, skill, and judgement. Therefore, in an organisational setting, people are the source of all new knowledge. Organisational growth incorporates some knowledge. The following steps of the knowledge transfer life cycle must be followed by organisations if they want to develop the abilities and skills necessary to create effective knowledge transfers.

1. Identifying

Determine what knowledge needs to be transferred.

2. Capturing

Accumulate the essential knowledge that needs to be transferred.

3. Sharing

Establish methods for transferring the knowledge.

4. Applying

Use the knowledge that is transferred.

5. Assessing

Evaluate the benefits of the knowledge that is transferred.

1.1 Need for the study:

Knowledge management gives your teams access to the information and resource they need to their job effectively. It also helps your business retain that knowledge for future use which promotes efficiency a better working experience.

Company constitutes pooling of members of scarce resources like men, material, machinery and money. They are to be properly organized and coordinated in the accomplishing the desired results. It is wider implications both on company and employees too

- Speed up access to information and knowledge.
- Improve decision- making processes.
- Promote innovation and cultural change.
- Improve the efficiency of an organizations operating units and business process.

1.2 Scope of the study:

Researchers, and academics have taken different perspectives on knowledge management ranging from technological solutions to the use of best practices. It has been the subject of much discussion over the past decade. It resides in human minds. Employee training and motivation are the key factors to knowledge management. Though there are widespread arguments among scholars about the definition of KM, it has been applied to a very broad spectrum of activities designed to manage, exchange and create or enhance intellectual assets within an organization.

1.3 Statement of the problem

Organizations face significant challenges in managing and leveraging their knowledge effectively to drive innovation, enhance productivity, and maintain a competitive edge. The problem lies in the lack of an efficient knowledge management system and processes, leading to difficulties in capturing, organizing, sharing, and utilizing knowledge across the organization.

2. Research Methodology:

2.1 Objectives of the study

- To study the employee opinion of Knowledge management.
- To Increase collaboration and enhance the skill level of employees.
- To improve conceptual structure of knowledge management.
- To study the career opportunities and generate the model of knowledge management.
- To study the different knowledge management practices adopted in the organisation.

2.2. Hypothesis Testing:

- **H0** :There is no significance relationship between the educational status and employee knowledge.
- **H1** : There is significance relationship between the educational status and employee knowledge.

2.3 Data Collection Data collection means the assembling, for the purpose of particular investigation of entirely new data, presumably not already available in published sources. The task of data collection begins after a research problem has been defined and research design plan chalked out. While deciding about the method of data collection to be used for the study, the researcher should keep in mind two types of data viz., Primary data and Secondary data.

2.3.1 Primary Data

The study is based on descriptive analysis using primary data to investigate the objectives. A well-structured questionnaire was used to collect the primary data. It is collected freshly for the first time and thus happened to be original in character. Methods include-observation method, interview method, though questionnaire etc.

2.3.2 Secondary Data

It is the data which is already been collected by someone else and already been passed through the statistical process. Sources include- government, technical and trade journals, books, magazines, young minds collected through the study of records brochures, internet and forms.

2.4 Sampling Method

The technique I have chosen is simple random technique. This technique helped to choose a group of employees which easier.

2.5 Sample size

The sample size is 150.

3.6 Techniques & Tools

Various data analysis tools like SPSS, Graphs & Charts, and Microsoft Excel was used to analyze the data.

2.7 Limitations of the study

- The time period for carrying out the research was short as a result of which many facts have been left unexplored.
- Lack of time and other resources why because it was not possible to conduct survey at large level.
- Respondents have marked the answers in the questionnaire which may be socially incorrect irrespective of their actual feelings.

3. DATA ANALYSIS

Table 1

1. Knowledge management helps to career opportunities.

	frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Strongly disagree	15	10	10	10
Dis agree	17	12	12	22
Netural	51	34	34	55
Agree	49	32	32	88
Strongly agree	18	13	12	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation

From the preceding table, it can be deduced that 10% of respondents fall into one of four categories: strongly disagree 12% of respondents, nominally agree 34%, and strongly agree 13% of respondents.

Table 2

2. KM helps achieving better revenue.

	frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Stronglydisagree	4	2	2	2
Dis agree	9	6	6	8
Netural	25	16	16	24
Agree	71	48	48	72
Strongly agree	39	28	28	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation According to the above table, 2% of respondents believe that knowledge management (KM) contributes to higher income, while 6% of respondents strongly disagree, 16% disagree, 48% agree, and 28% highly agree.

Table 3

3. Do you have written policies or procedures for KM practices.

	frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Yes	118	80	70	80
No	32	20	20	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation

According to the aforementioned table, 80% of respondents have established rules or procedures for their knowledge management practises. between 20% and no No response was given.

Table 4

4. Their are well defined processes for creation capture and acquisition of knowledge.

	frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Stronglydisagree	7	4	4	4
Dis agree	12	8	8	12
Netural	29	19	19	31
Agree	74	49	49	80
Strongly agree	28	20	20	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation

According to the aforementioned data, 4% of respondents fall into the categories of severely disagree, 8% disagree, 19% netural, 49% agree, and 20% strongly agree. There are also well defined processes for the development, capture, and acquisition of information.

Table 5

5. If you face any issues/challenges at work who helps you to solve those issues

	frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Supervisor	28	18	18	18
Manager	35	23	23	42
Team member	57	38	38	80
Management	30	21	21	20
Total	150	100.0	100.0	100.0

Interpretation According to the aforementioned research, 21% management, 23% managers, 38% team members, and 18% respondents, in that order, are the ones who help you solve any problems you might run across at work.

Table 6

6. Employee exchange information freely among each other irrespective of the departments.

	frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Stronglydisagree	12	9	9	9
Dis agree	21	14	14	22
Netural	32	21	21	43.3
Agree	64	42	42	86
Strongly agree	21	14	14	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation

From the above data, 9% of respondents strongly disagree, 14% disagree, and 21% disagree with the notion that employees in different departments can freely exchange information with one another. 14% of people strongly agree, 42% agree.

Table 7

7. The KM system helps in fast and better decision making.

	frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Stronglydisagree	6	4	4	4
Dis agree	18	12	12	16
Netural	45	30	30	46
Agree	59	39	39	85
Strongly agree	22	15	15	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation

From the above data, it can be deduced that 5% of respondents participate in discussions and meetings about novel concepts and ideas, with 11% strongly disagreeing, 26% neutrally disagreeing, 44% agreeing, and 14% strongly agreeing.

Table 8

1. CORRELATIONS

Hypothesis

H0 : There is no significance relationship between employee age and employee experience..

H1 : There is significance relationship between employee age and employee experience.

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Age	2.26	1.132	150
knowledge management helps to career opportunities	3.26	1.126	150

Correlations			
		Age	knowledge
Age	Pearson Correlation	1	.205*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.012
	N	150	150
knowledge management helps to career opportunities	Pearson Correlation	.205*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.012	
	N	150	150

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

INTERPRETATION

205 Sig (2-tailed) = 0.012 for the pearson correlation

In an organisation where the pearson correlation value is less than 0.05 and the sig (2-tailed value is 0.012, there is a significant and positive correlation between the employee's age and knowledge As a result, as the employee's age increases, so does their knowledge.

Table 9

2. REGRESSION

Hypothesis

H0 : There is no significance relationship between employee educational status and employee knowledge.

H1 : There is significance relationship between employee educational status and employee knowledge.

Variables Entered/Removed ^a			
Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Educational status ^b		.Enter
a. Dependent Variable: Knowledge			
b. All requested variables entered.			

Model Summary					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R	Std. Error of	Change Statistics

			Square	the Estimate	R Square	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F
					Change				Change
1	.008 ^a	.000	-.007	1.130	.000	.009	1	146	.925
a. Predictors: (Constant), Educational status									

Hypothesis

H0 : There is no significance relationship between employee educational status and employee knowledge.

H1 : There is significance relationship between employee educational status and employee knowledge.

INTERPRETATION

R = square (0.00)

Value of Sig: 0.925

According to the survey, there is no correlation between an employee's education and knowledge, and if the sigvalue is more than 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted.

R = square = 0.00 indicates that there is no variation in the employees' ages or levels of experience.

FINDINGS & CONCLUSION

FINDINGS

In the organisation majority respondents 55% were women. And in the organization opinions on whether knowledge management increases employment opportunities ranged from a majority of 52% in favour to the least in favour 20% and a neutral 20% against 20%. And respondents think knowledge management (KM) helps people earn more money, with 60% saying they agree, 20% saying they disagree, and 20% saying they don't. In an organisation where the pearson correlation value is less than 0.05 and the sig (2-tailed value is 0.012, there is a significant and positive correlation between the employee's age and knowledge As a result, as the employee's age increases, so does their knowledge. According to the survey, regression there is no correlation between an employee's education and knowledge, and if the sigvalue is more than 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Conclusion

employees' perspectives on knowledge management play a vital role in shaping successful implementations within organizations. By considering their insights and suggestions, companies can create a knowledge management system that aligns with employees' needs, enhances collaboration, and promotes a culture of continuous learning. Some key takeaways from employees' perspectives include the importance of user-friendly platforms, collaboration tools, incentives for knowledge sharing, comprehensive training and support, gamification elements, feedback mechanisms, and a focus on continuous improvement. By valuing employee input and actively involving them in the knowledge management process, organizations can harness the collective intelligence and expertise of their workforce, leading to improved productivity, innovation, and overall business success.

Hence, with the given research study conducted in this organization, it can be concluded that the concept of competency mapping and Knowledge Management is in between the introduction and growth stage that is it is ahead of introduction stage and has not reached yet to growth stage. It has been also concluded that there is certainly a quest for knowledge in the employees and combining this factor with highly established HR Department and advanced Information Technology in the organization, competency mapping is need to be regularly carried out here and Knowledge Management will definitely reach to the growth stage in due course of time in this organiz.

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A STUDY ON THE HR POLICIES AND PRACTICES

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Abstract: -

This abstract provides a concise overview of the importance, key elements, and benefits of effective HR policies and practices within organizations. Human Resource (HR) policies and practices play a critical role in shaping the culture, managing employee relations, and driving organizational success.

The abstract begins by highlighting the significance of HR policies and practices as essential tools for promoting fairness, consistency, and compliance within an organization. It emphasizes the role of HR policies in establishing guidelines and procedures for various aspects of employment, including recruitment, onboarding, performance management, training and development, compensation, benefits, and employee relations.

Keywords: Training, performance, retention, personal skills

INTRODUCTION

Torrington and Hall (1987) define personnel management as being: "a series of activities which: first enable working people and their employing organizations to agree about the objectives and nature of their working relationship and, secondly, ensures that the agreement is fulfilled"

While Miller (1987) suggests that HRM relates to:

".....those decisions and actions which concern the management of employees at all levels in the business and which are related to the implementation of strategies directed towards creating and sustaining competitive advantage"

Human resource policies are systems of codified decisions, established by an organization, to support administrative personnel functions, performance management, employee relations and resource planning. Each company has a different set of circumstances, and so develops an individual set of human resource policies.

DEFINITION OF HUMAN RESOURCE POLICIES:

HR policies and practices refer to a set of guidelines, procedures, and strategies implemented by an organization to effectively manage its human resources. These policies and practices are designed to ensure fair treatment of employees, maintain compliance with legal requirements, promote employee well-being, and align with the organizations goals.

1.1 THE PRINCIPLES OF HUMAN RESOURCES MANAGEMENT POLICIES.EMPLOYMENT:

The company will try all possible efforts to employ the most qualified and competent employees and retain them as long as possible. Selection and screening will be made on merit basis and unqualified and incompetent applicants will be eliminated.

COMPENSATION:

The company shall pay fair and equitable compensation in accordance with the principle of the employee's duties and responsibilities, and satisfactory performance, by maintaining its equivalent rate of compensation in comparison to the same or similar type of industry following the Laws, Local practices and financial stability of the company.

PROMOTION / TRANSFER:

The company to promote the employee from within, the qualified and deserving employees shall be promoted to higher positions whenever vacancies occur or to be transferred to jobs where their talents could be best utilized for

higher responsibilities and adequate compensation. An employee of the company either thru initial appointment or promotion will have to undergo a trial period of 120 days.

A Promotion Means: A movement of an employee to higher level involving more difficult duties or increased responsibilities and a higher pay, higher status or offering better privileges, thus all promotion will be based on merit, good performance and loyalty to the company, such a promotion may be made within the same department or from one department to another.

A Transfer Means: The movement of an employee from one job to another requiring approximately the same degree of skills, duties and responsibilities, and other educational qualification with the same pay scale within the company. The selection will be made on the basis of qualification for the job through interview, tests, attendance, and job performance.

WORKING CONDITIONS: Good working condition will bring about a good result to the company and therefore the condition of the working place must be provided with proper working environment and enough safety and at the same time all employees must work with all possible efforts and care in preventing the damage loss or accident to themselves machines and other company property.

WELFARE: Good employee benefits will be offered to meet the needs of the employees in accordance with the local or community practice, laws and financial stability of the company. The company will try all possible efforts to look forward to meet the employee requirement in matter of medical care, recreation, hospitalizations and others.

EMPLOYEE RELATIONS: It is the responsibility of management and executive employees at all levels to point out an employee's deficiencies and shortcomings so that he may have an opportunity to correct them, and also to promote good Human relations with their subordinates and associates. Everyone must understand the company rules and regulations and strictly and sincerely follow them. The achievement of the company will be based on the individual cooperation by strict adherence to his/ her duties and responsibilities. Any constructive suggestions and initiatives are always welcome. When an employee is transferred, dismissed, or demoted. He is entitled to know the reasons for the Company's action.

TRAINING: The company believes that well – trained employees both technical and administration skill will bring about achievement to the company, and therefore, the company's employees at all levels will be provided appropriate training course to enable them in developing their ability, knowledge and skills. Both internal and external training including seminars will be provided as the management deems appropriate. It is also the responsibility of executive employees at all levels to train their subordinates in order to develop the performance of their subordinates and also be accountable for the jobs assigned to the subordinates

1.2 Need for the study:

HR policies and practices contribute to a positive work environment, employee's satisfaction, and engagement. Organization can design policies that promote fairness, transparency, and equal opportunities, leading to higher employee morale and productivity.

1.3 Scope of the study:

One of the main functions of personnel management in industrial organization is to impart programmers to its employees' plays a large part in determining the effectiveness and efficiency of the establishment. Increase in productivity is possible only when there is an increase in quantity of output. It applies not only to new employees but also to experienced.

1.4 Statement of the problem

However, in most of the studies it is shown that the training has positive impact on the employee performance, must not be always true if not executed well. This research is focused on event Management Company where the workforce are mainly associated with the field work with a particular skills.

The question of this research arises from the fact that Event Management industry face many problems related to training and development as well as staff retention. For example, ninety-seven percent of organizations do not allow

employees to attend appropriate external training or development training. In fact, if the employee develops personal ambitions for further education or personal development ; the organization wants it to release before it can start reviewing the development. For this reason, it is difficult for employees to stay at organization for long, and as soon as they see a better opportunity and they jump on board.

2. Research Methodology:

Research is descriptive in nature; the data collection tool is used in the research includes questionnaire based on different questions from the employees which tells us about training and its impact on their training and job satisfaction. The sample size for this research was 111 which includes only the employee of the Events Arena organization. The data collection period was 25days.

Systematic sampling technique is used in the research paper to get the quantitative type of solution for the questionnaire prepared. The primary data collected was run under SPSS software for correlation, regression test for 111 responses to get quantitative solution. A structured questionnaire was used in the study, divided into groups like demographic profile, statement related to training, job satisfaction etc.

2.1 Objectives of the study

- To learn the effectiveness of the HRM policies in HDFC bank.
- To determine the work life balance impact with HR policies.
- To give valuable suggestions improving HR system in HDFC bank.

2.2. Hypothesis Testing:

Correlation:

Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no significant relationship between disseminated HR policies and effective HR policies.

Alternate Hypothesis(H1): There is a significant relationship between disseminated HR policies and effective HR policies.

Regression:

Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no significant impact on education qualification and HR policies in the company.

Alternate Hypothesis(H1): There is a significant impact on education qualification and HR policies in the company.

2.3 Research design:

The research adopted is descriptive research design. It involves facts-findings, inquires of different kinds etc.

Descriptive research studies are those studies which are concerned with describing the characteristics of a particular individual or group.

2.4 Type of Research: QUANTITATIVE RESEARCH will be done for the study because aim to know the HR policies and practices.

2.5 Data Sources

Collection of data is the primary importance in the research process. Data, which was collected for the purpose of research, helps in proper analysis, which is helpful to conduct research efficiently. The data source, which is very important in collection of data is primary data and secondary data. Both primary and secondary data are taken into consideration for conducting the study of training and its impact on employee performance.

1. Primary source of data
2. Secondary source of data

For this dissertation the data was collected from both the sources.

Primary data:

Data is made available through interview and questionnaires. Questionnaires were prepared for the employee to know HR policies and practices.

Secondary data:

Data were collected from documents, records, Internet, company past records etc.

2.6 SAMPLING PLAN:

Sampling unit/Target group: The respondents are of different departments in banking sectors.

2.7 SAMPLE SIZE:

Sample size refers to the number of respondents or the size of sample, which is to be surveyed. Here the sample size taken for the study was 111

2.8 SAMPLING TECHNIQUE: SAMPLE AND SAMPLE TECHNIQUES:

Sample Unit: Employees of banking sectors.

Sample Size: 111

Sampling Techniques: In this study a sampling technique used to collect data from the employees working in banking sector.

Variables

Two types of variables are used in this research. The dependent variable. How was information about the policies disseminated.

Dependent Variable (Retention & performance). The dependent variable. How was information about the policies disseminated. as a factor, which has observed and measured the effect of independent variable (training). How effective are the policies. Responses related to training and job sanctification from one hundred ninety-two respondents have been considered a dependent variable. Thirteen questions have been asked related to performance and retention (dependent variable).

Independent Variable (Training)

Training has been considered as a factor, which will examine the impact of training on employee retention. Training has been presumed to be the cause that will create an effect over employee retention and their performance. Eleven questions have been asked related to training (independent variable).

2.9 DATA ANALYSIS TOOLS: Various data analysis tools like SPSS, Graphs & Charts, and Microsoft Excel was used to analyze the data.

3. DATA ANALYSIS:

1. Are you aware of all the HR policies in your company?

Are you aware of all the HR policies in your company

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid yes	91	82.0	82.0	82.0
Valid No	20	18.0	18.0	100.0
Total	111	100.0	100.0	

INTERPRETATION:

Form the above table it is inferred that, if employees are you aware of all the HR policies in your company 82% of respondents are Yes and 18% of the respondents are No. The majority of employees are felt that they know the HR policies in their company

2. How was information about the policies disseminated?

How was information about the policies disseminated

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	CumulativePercent
Valid	hand book	16	14.4	14.4
	face to face	47	42.3	56.8
	online resources	36	32.4	89.2
	others	12	10.8	100.0
	Total	111	100.0	100.0

INTERPRETATION:

Form the above table, it is inferred that ,14.4% of respondents are hand book, 42.3% of the respondents are face to face,32.4% of the respondents are online resources and 10%of the respondents are others. The majority of respondents are hand book of the information about the policies.

3. How effective are the policies?

How effective are the policies

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	CumulativePercent
Valid	Less effective	14	12.6	12.6
	more effective	56	50.5	63.1
	moderately	37	33.3	96.4
	extremely	4	3.6	100.0
	Total	111	100.0	100.0

INTERPRETATION:

Form the above table, it is inferred that, 12.6% of the respondents are the less effective of the HR policies,50.5% of the respondents are more effective of the effective policies 33.3%of the respondents are moderately3.6%of the respondents are extremely. The majority of the employees is the effective policies.

4. How well are the HR policies enforced in your company?

How well are the HR policies enforced in your company

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	not at all	15	13.5	13.5
	slightly	38	34.2	47.7
	moderately	41	36.9	84.7
	very	13	11.7	96.4
	extremely	4	3.6	100.0
	Total	111	100.0	100.0

INTERPRETATION:

From above table, it is inferred that, 13.5% of the respondents are not at all of followed by the 34.2% of the respondents slightly, 36.9% of the respondents moderately, 11.7% very of the respondents and extremely 3.6% of the respondents are the hr policies enforced. The majority of the employees are not at all of the hr policies enforced of the company.

Correlation:

Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no significant relationship between disseminated HR polices and effective HR polices.

Alternate Hypothesis(H1): There is a significant relationship between disseminated HR polices and effective HR polices.

Correlations

		How was information about the policies disseminated	How effective are the policies
How was information about the policies disseminated	Pearson Correlation	1	.486**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	111	111
How effective are the policies	Pearson Correlation	.486**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	111	111

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Interpretation:

From the above correlation table, it is inferred that, found that there is a significant and positive correlation between disseminated HR polices and effective HR polices with significant value 0.000 which is less than 0.05. There is a significant relationship between disseminated HR polices and effective HR polices. Hence the null hypothesis H0 is rejected and the alternative hypothesis H1 is accepted.

Regression:

Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no significant impact on education qualification and HR polices in the company.

Alternate Hypothesis(H1): There is significant impact on education qualification and HR polices in the company

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Education Qualification	3.73	.632	111
In general, how benefits are you with this company HR policies	2.93	1.033	111

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.295 ^a	.087	.079	.606	1.647

a. Predictors: (Constant), In general how 4 are you with this company HR policies

b. Dependent Variable: Education Qualification

ANOVA:

Anova

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	3.814	1	3.814	10.373	.002 ^b
Residual	40.078	109	.368		
Total	43.892	110			

a. Dependent Variable: Education Qualification

b. Predictors: (Constant), In general how 4 are you with this company HR policies

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.257	.174		24.516	.000
	In general, how benefits are you with this company HR policies	-.180	.056	-.295	-3.221	.002

a. Dependent Variable: Education Qualification.

INTERPRETATION:

Form the model summary table, R square value is found to be 0.079. Which means the independent variables education qualification is explaining 79% of variance is independent variable.

Form Anova table it is found that the significant the variances in dependent variable is are you aware of the education qualification in your company. Value is 0.002 which is less than 0.05. It means regression model is significant influencing dependent variable are you aware of the HR policies in your company.

Form the coefficient table it is found that the standardized coefficient HR polices, education, qualification, is -0.295 & significant value is 0.002 less than 0.05.

Findings & Conclusion:

- The training and HR Policies program in HDFC BANK is focused on new and old employees.
- Training programs are conducted by quarterly interval in HDFC BANK.
- HRM Policies program in HDFC BANK is based on the performance and seniority.
- The HRM Policies program in HDFC BANK is also the company response to new innovation and upcoming technologies.
- The goal of the program is mainly to improve the job-related skills.
- It has been observed during the study that most of the employees expressed the need for each employee to attend the training program least once in a year.
- The training program is very much relevant to the present nature of work.

CONCLUSION:

In the above perspective, the present chapter makes an attempt to draw some conclusions. It should be confessed here that the investigator is conscious of the limitations of the study and the conclusion drawn on the basis of the sample from a single unit cannot be generalized about the entire manufacturing sector. The study examines the readiness for employee empowerment in six aspects, namely effective Communication, Value of people, Clarity, Concept about power, Information and Learning. A perusal of data pertaining to combination makes us to conclude that the Executives have agreed to the effective downward communication flow, which is a prerequisite for empowerment. With regard to value of people, the analysis leads to the conclusion that the Executives give a reasonable value to the Human

Resources in the Organization. However, in respect of concept about power, they are somewhat agreed to share the power. As far as information sharing with lower rungs is concerned, they are very positive. One significant conclusion with regards to learning opportunities, which is a basic for empowerment, is that the executives are favorable and feel that sufficient learning opportunities should be there for the rank & file.

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A STUDY ON EMPLOYEES ABSENTEEISM IN KOTAK MAHINDRA BANK LTD

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Abstract: -

Absenteeism is a serious workplace problem and an expensive occurrence for both employers and employees seemingly unpredictable in nature. A satisfactory level of attendance by employees at work is necessary to allow the achievement of objectives and targets by a department. Absenteeism results in financial losses, because of the resultant reduction in productivity and the cost of sick leave benefits or others are paid as wages for no work. Absenteeism reduces the satisfaction level of the employee and makes him unsecured about his job in the organization. Most researches had concluded that absence is a complex variable and that it is influenced by multiple causes, both personal and organizational. This paper focuses on absenteeism as a threat to the organization as it reduces the employee satisfaction and the ways to manage absenteeism in the Kotak Mahindra Bank Private Limited in order to improve the productivity of the organization.

Key words: Absenteeism, Employees Satisfaction, Employers, benefits, organization

1. INTRODUCTION

Employee's absenteeism is a key economic burden for organizations as it grounds loss of productivity. Absenteeism is an especially complicated crisis to tackle, because there are both justifiable and meagre excuses for missing work and it can be challenging for organization to efficiently monitor, organize and lessen absenteeism. The detailed investigation of absenteeism is generally executed through the primary survey with employees. The questionnaire is a significant instrument in the primary survey, which has set of questions that primarily deals with figuring out the reason for absenteeism.

Absenteeism causing poor utilization of plant India is facing an employment problem on one side abnormal absenteeism in industries if our absenteeism can be reduced. We can improve our gross national product without any investment. Absenteeism not only causes Production loss but also causes reduction of gross national income. When the gross income of workmen reduces naturally his buying capacity also reduces. If he could not manage the primary and secondary needs of timely and properly. He has to face problems like poor family harmony poor health more mental and physical tiredness which will again lead to absenting from work.

Many employees will, on occasions, need a few days off work because of illness, however, when absences become more frequent or long term and reach an unacceptable level, action by absences management is necessary. Absence from work can be expensive in both monetary and human terms. The costs incurred when an employee is absent from work many include:

1. the employees or requiring other staff to cover the absence.
2. Inability Replacing to provide services, or achieve section and department objectives.
3. Low morale and general dissatisfaction from other staff, particularly if the absence is perceived as unwarranted.

Absenteeism as commonly understood refers to the failure of an operative to report to work when work is available to him as used in the study overall absenteeism is made up of three components.

TYPES OF ABSENTEEISM

Not all Employees absences fit into the same category. If you can identify which type of absenteeism you're dealing with, you can establish a plan to quickly manage and correct it without issue.

There are three types of general absenteeism in the working place:

Authorized and Planned Absences:

This includes any time off that has been arranged between the employee and their superior, such as holiday leave, appointments, personal leave, paternity or maternity leave, compassionate leave, etc. When an employee has submitted and approved their request for time off, their absence should not be an issue. With the right preparations from, work can't be planned for. While disruptive to the workplace, unplanned, genuine absences are simply a part of life. These include illness, family emergencies, or accidents.

Unauthorized Absences:

This is where absenteeism becomes an issue. Unauthorized and disingenuous absences are often the most frustrating scenario for those who are left to pick up the absent overall.

Absenteeism is a common problem in many industrial units, small or big, private or government. The high rate of absenteeism is at times due to lack of commitment to work. Absenteeism results in dislocation of work, increase in labor costs, reduction in productivity and if unchecked, it causes an increase in indiscipline. Although some amount of absent will always be inevitable, most of it can be avoided.

1.2 Need for the study:

Absenteeism is a habitual pattern of absence from a duty or obligation. Traditionally, absenteeism has been viewed as an indicator of poor individual performance, as well as breach of implicit contract between employee and employer, it was seen as a management problem, and framed in economic or quasi-economic terms. More recent scholarship seeks to understand absenteeism as an indicator of psychological, medical or social adjustment to work.

As a result, employees feel obliged to come to work while ill, and transmit communicable diseases to their co-workers. This leads to even greater absenteeism and reduced productivity among other workers who try to work while ill. Work forces often excuse absenteeism caused by medical reason if the employee provides supporting documentation from their medical practitioner.

1.3 Scope of the study:

The development of any organization depends on the regularity of employees. The study is conducted to know the various levels and reasons for absence of employees in an organization. By looking at it, one can adopt corrective measures to decrease irregularities in the organization, leading to organizational growth.

1.4 Statement of the problem

Absenteeism has become a major problem in almost all the industrial sectors. Excessive absenteeism constitutes a considerable cost to the industry even when the absent employee receives no pay. Because of disorganization of work, work schedules are upset and delayed, resulting in the management failure to meet delivery dates. When sick pay is authorized, the cost of absenteeism mounts up more rapidly.

2. Research Methodology:

Research is descriptive in nature; the data collection tool used in the research includes questionnaire based on different questions from the employees which tells us about absenteeism and its impact on their performance and satisfaction. The sample size for this research was 150 which includes only the employees of the Kotak Bank organization. The data collection period was 30 days.

Systematic sampling technique is used in the research paper to get the quantitative type of solution for the questionnaire prepared. The primary data collected was run under SPSS software for correlation, factor analysis and an ANOVA test for 150 responses to get quantitative solution. A structured questionnaire was used in the study, which was based on five-point Likert scale. Divided into groups like demographic profile, statement related to training, retention etc.

2.1 Objectives of the study

- To measure the Employees absenteeism level.
- To identify the steps required to decrease the rate of absenteeism.
- To study the employees working condition.
- To identify the level of absenteeism in the organization2.2.
-

2.2 Hypothesis Testing:

H0: There is no significant impact of satisfaction of employees.

H1: There is significant impact of satisfaction of employees. **H02:** There is no significant impact of Employees absenteeism. **H12:** There is significant impact of Employees absenteeism.

2.3 Research design:

The research adopted is descriptive research design. It involves facts-findings, inquires of differentkinds etc. Descriptive research studies are those studies which are concerned with describing the characteristics of a particular individual or group.

2.4 Type of Research: QUANTITATIVE RESEARCH will be done for the study because aim together an in-depth understanding of human behavior and the reason that governs such behavior.

2.5 Data Sources

Collection of data is the primary importance in the research process. Data, which was collected for the purpose of research, helps in proper analysis, which is helpful to conduct research efficiently. The data source, which is very important in collection of data is primary data and secondary data. Both primary and secondary data are taken into consideration for conducting the study of Employees absenteeism and its impact on employee performance.

1. Primary source of data
2. Secondary source of data

For this dissertation the data was collected from both the sources.

Primary data:

Data is made available through interview and questionnaires. Questionnaires were prepared for trainees to know the impact and methods of training adopted by organization.

Secondary data:

Data were collected from documents, records, Internet, company past records etc.

2.6 SAMPLING PLAN:

Sampling unit/Target group: The respondents are of different departments in Kotak Mahindra bank Ltd

2.7 SAMPLE SIZE:

Sample size refers to the number of respondents or the size of sample, which is to be surveyed. Here the sample size taken for the study was 150.

2.8 SAMPLING TECHNIQUE: Systematic sampling technique is used for the study as in probability sampling technique each member in a population has equal chance of being selected as a sample.

Variables

Two types of variables are used in this research. The dependent variable identified for research is Employee retention and employee performance while the independent variable is training.

Dependent Variable (Employee absenteeism)

Employee absenteeism and satisfaction has been considered as a factor, which has observed and measured the effect of independent variable (satisfaction). Employees absenteeism and satisfaction has been presumed to be the effect due to the cause of satisfaction. Responses related to employee absenteeism and satisfaction from one hundred fifty

respondents have been considered a dependent variable. Thirteen questions have been asked related to satisfaction and absenteeism (dependent variable).

Independent Variable (Employee Satisfaction)

On the one hand, job satisfaction is viewed as a dependent variable that varies with the quality of working conditions and with other stressors. On the other hand, it is presumed to be an independent variable that determines a variety of consequences such as irregular work attendance and performance.

2.9 DATA ANALYSIS TOOLS: Various data analysis tools like SPSS, Graphs & Charts, and Microsoft Excel was used to analyze.

3. DATA ANALYSIS

1. Your superior behaviors towards the problem?

Your superior behaviors towards the problem?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Excellent	42	28.0	28.0	28.0
Good	54	36.0	36.0	64.0
Neutral	42	28.0	28.0	92.0
Valid				
Fair	10	6.7	6.7	98.7
Poor	2	1.3	1.3	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

From the frequency table, it is inferred that 28.0% of workers think that their superior’s behavior towards their problem is excellent, 36.0% workers consider it as good, 28.0% workers consider them neutral, 6.7% workers consider it as fair and 1.3% workers them as poor.

2. How long you are working in this organization?

How long you are working in this organization?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Less than 1 year	61	40.7	40.7	40.7
1-2 years	59	39.3	39.3	80.0
3-4 years	19	12.7	12.7	92.7
Valid				
5-6 years	10	6.7	6.7	99.3
More than 6 years	1	.7	.7	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

From the frequency table, it is inferred that work experience of respondents, it is observed that 40.7%of respondents have less than 1 year experience, whereas 39.3% are 1-2 years, where 12.7% are above3-4 years, 6.7% are belonging

to 5-6 years, 0.7% are more than 6 years. The results show that majority of respondents are belonging to less than 1 year experienced.

3. Are you satisfied with your work?

Are you satisfied with your work?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid				
Highly satisfied	37	24.7	24.8	24.8
Good	45	30.0	30.2	55.0
Neutral	53	35.3	35.6	90.6
Dissatisfied	7	4.7	4.7	95.3
Dis satisfied	7	4.7	4.7	100.0
Total	149	99.3	100.0	
Missing				
System	1	.7		
Total	150	100.0		

From the frequency table, it is inferred that 24.7% of the workers are highly satisfied with their work whereas 30.0% workers think their work is good, 35.3% workers consider them as neutral (ok) and 4.7% workers consider them as dissatisfied. Majority of the respondents are satisfied with their work.

4. How do you feel about your relationship with co-workers?

How do you feel about your relationship with co-Workers?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Excellent	46	30.7	30.7	30.7
Good	57	38.0	38.0	68.7
Neutral	39	26.0	26.0	94.7
Valid				
Normal	7	4.7	4.7	99.3
Bad	1	.7	.7	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

From the above table 38.0% workers consider that relationship with your co-worker is good whereas 30.7% of workers consider them as excellent, 26.0% of workers consider that neutral and 0.7% workersthem as bad. Majority of the respondents are feels good.

5. How often you remain a month? Hypothesis:

Null hypothesis (H0): There is no significant relationship between Satisfaction level of employees and Employees absenteeism.

Alternative Hypothesis (H1): There is a significant relationship between Satisfaction level of employees and Employees absenteeism.

Correlations

		how often you remain a month?	Are you satisfied with your work?
how often you remain a month?	Pearson Correlation	1	.178*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.030
	N	150	149
Are you satisfied with your work?	Pearson Correlation	.178*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.030	
	N	149	149

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

From the correlation table, it is found that there is significant and positive correlation between Satisfaction level of employees and Employee absences with significant value .030 which is less than 0.05. There is a significant relationship between Satisfaction level of employees and Employees absenteeism. Hence the null hypothesis H0 is rejected and the alternative hypothesis H1 is accepted.

6. According to you what is the main reasons for Employees absent?

According to you what is the main reasons for Employees absent?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Health problem	76	50.7	50.7	50.7
Stress	33	22.0	22.0	72.7
Work dissatisfaction	32	21.3	21.3	94.0
Working environment	6	4.0	4.0	98.0
Others	3	2.0	2.0	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

According to 50.7% workers, Health problem is the reason for being absent 22.3% think that stress can also be the reason, 21.3% of workers think that work dissatisfaction for absent, 4.0% workers working environment for the

reason and 2.0% of workers thinks that others for reason.

7. How often you remain a month?

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square a. Predictors: (Constant), Are you satisfied with your work? b. Dependent Variable: how often you remain a month?	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.178 ^a	.032	.025	.897	.055

a. Predictors: (Constant), Are you satisfied with your work?

b. Dependent Variable: how often you remain a month?

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3.879	1	3.879	4.826	.030 ^b
	Residual	118.161	147	.804		
	Total	122.040	148			

a. Dependent Variable: how often you remain a month?

b. Predictors: (Constant), Are you satisfied with your work?

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
(Constant)	1.498	.180		8.329	.000
Are you satisfied with your work?	.154	.070	.178	2.197	.030

a. Dependent variable: how often you remain a month?

Interpretation:

From the coefficient table the standardized coefficient $R = .178$ (which is greater than 0.3) and significant value is $.030$ (which is less than 0.05). Hence there is a significant and strong correlation between satisfaction level of Employees and Employees absenteeism.

From ANOVA table it is found that the significant value is $.030$ which is less than 0.05. It means regression model is significantly influencing dependent variable (Satisfaction of work).

From the model summary R Square value is found to be $.032$ which means the independent variable (satisfaction of employees & Employees absenteeism) is explaining 32.0% of variance in independent variable.

CONCLUSION:

This study analysis the issue of Employees absenteeism and explores in detail preventative and corrective actions. Absenteeism has a negative impact on a company's employee morale. There are a number of programs that can be implemented individually or collectively to reduce employee absenteeism. Absenteeism is a serious and costly problem faced by companies throughout the world. This problem requires that all employees understand the consequences of such behavior from a company's standpoint as well as a personal standpoint. All companies must approach this problem from a proactive position with employee prevention programs and progressive discipline programs.

They should provide full-fledged support guidance and encouragement. Medi-claims policies, weekly or monthly medical checkups etc., should be provided to the employees in order to make them physical fit for the job. Make each employee aware that they are a valued member of the team, that they play an important role in organization and that their attendance is critical.

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A STUDY ON PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL SYSTEM TOWARDS HINDUSTAN COCA-COLA BEVERAGES PVT. LTD

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Abstract: -

This study looks into the performance appraisal system towards Hindustan Coca-Cola beverage Pvt. Ltd. Performance appraisal is a method of evaluating the behavior of employees in the work spot, normally including both the quantitative and qualitative aspects of job performances. Performance refers to the degree of accomplishment of the tasks that make up an individual's job. It indicates how well an individual is full filling the job demands.

Research is descriptive in nature, Systematic sampling technique is used in the research paper to get the quantitative type of solution for the questionnaire prepared. The primary data collected was run under SPSS software for correlation, ANOVA etc. In the correlation with the significance value of 0.040 it is found that employees are satisfied by the organizational appraisal system and it helps them in improving their performance. In the ANOVA test with significance value of 0.001 it was found that the performance appraisal system enhances the performance of the employees.

Keywords: Performance appraisal system, measuring performance, methods of performance appraisal.

1.Introduction:

Appraisal is the evaluation of worth and quality of merit. It is the evaluation of present performance and feature capabilities. Employee appraisal techniques are said to have been used for the first time during the First World War, when at the instance of Walter dill Scott, thus army adopted the "man to man" rating system for evaluation military personal. During the 1922 to 1930 period, rational wage structures for hourly paid workers were adopted industrial units.

Meaning:

Performance appraisal is a method of evaluating the behavior of employees in the work spot, normally including both the quantitative and qualitative aspects of job performances. Performance refers to the degree of accomplishment of the tasks that makeup an individual's job. It indicates how well an individual is full filling the job demands.

1.1 NEED FOR THE STUDY:

A study on performance appraisal provides an opportunity to assess the satisfaction levels of employees. Understanding their perceptions, attitudes, and opinions regarding the appraisal process can assist in identifying areas that require attention and improvement. It enables the organization to address any issues or concerns, enhancing employee morale, motivation, and engagement.

Furthermore, the study can shed light on the impact of performance appraisal on employee performance, productivity, and overall organizational effectiveness. By analyzing the relationship between appraisal outcomes and key performance indicators, valuable insights can be gained into the effectiveness of the existing system. This information can aid in designing strategies to enhance employee performance, align individual goals with organizational objectives, and foster a culture of continuous improvement.

- The present study like performances appraisal has been carried out to the employee Perception and satisfaction with regard to performance appraisal system.
- The role of performance appraisal is greatly felt in any organization. The study is under taken to know the satisfaction level and to suggest ways and means to improve the morale of employees which ultimate strengthen to the organization.

1.2 SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

The study can explore the impact of the performance appraisal system on employee performance and organizational outcomes. This includes analyzing the relationship between appraisal outcomes and key performance indicators, such as productivity, job satisfaction, and employee retention. Understanding this impact can provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of the current system and guide decision-making processes for future improvements. The scope of a study on performance appraisal, encompasses an examination of the current system, evaluation of its effectiveness and fairness, assessment of feedback mechanisms, exploration of employee perceptions and satisfaction, and analysis of the impact on employee performance and organizational outcomes. By addressing these areas, the study can contribute to enhancing the appraisal process and overall organizational success.

- The focus on the employee's satisfaction with regard to performance appraisal system in different department like quality control, maintenance, shipping.
- The management can identify the employee's opinion of the existing performance appraisal system.
- It can be used to training and development needs for the individual and organization as a whole.

1.3 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

The performance appraisal system employed by organization may be facing several challenges that hinder its effectiveness and alignment with the organization's goals. These challenges could include inconsistencies in the evaluation criteria, lack of clear performance indicators, inadequate feedback mechanisms, and employee perceptions of bias or unfairness in the appraisal process. These issues may lead to decreased employee motivation, reduced job satisfaction, and a potential impact on overall organizational performance.

Furthermore, the current performance appraisal system may not adequately capture and differentiate between high-performing and low-performing employees, resulting in missed opportunities for employee development, recognition, and rewards. In addition, there may be a lack of communication and transparency regarding performance expectations, leading to confusion and dissatisfaction among employees.

1.4 OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:

To analyze the impact of employee's motivation on organization effectiveness.

1. To determine the reward system obtained in the organization.
2. To know the satisfaction levels of employees towards the performance appraisal conducted by organizations.
3. To know that rewards are given for their performances.
4. To know whether the organization consider any behavior dimensions in performances appraisal.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

2.1 Research design:

The research adopted is descriptive research design. It involves facts-findings, inquires of different kinds etc. Descriptive research studies are those studies which are concerned with describing the characteristics of a particular individual or group.

2.2 TYPE OF RESEARCH: QUANTITATIVE RESEARCH will be done for the study because aim to gather an in-depth understanding of human behaviour and the reason that governs such behaviour.

2.3 DATA SOURCES:

Collection of data is the primary importance in the research process. Data, which was collected for the purpose of research, helps in proper analysis, which is helpful to conduct research efficiently. The data source, which is very

important in collection of data is primary data and secondary data. Both primary and secondary data are taken into consideration for conducting the study of performance appraisal.

1. Primary source of data
2. Secondary source of data

For this dissertation the data was collected from both the sources.

Primary data:

Data is made available through interview and questionnaires. Questionnaires were prepared for the employees of HCCBPL for analysing the performance appraisal methods and employee satisfaction.

Secondary data:

Data were collected from documents, records, Internet, company past records etc.

2.4 SAMPLING PLAN:

Sampling unit/Target group: The respondents are of different departments in various organization.

2.5 SAMPLE SIZE:

Sample size refers to the number of respondents or the size of sample, which is to be surveyed. Here the sample size taken for the study was 114.

2.6 SAMPLING TECHNIQUE: Systematic sampling technique is used for the study as in probability sampling technique each member in a population has equal chance of being selected as a sample.

2.7 DATA ANALYSIS TOOLS: Various data analysis tools like SPSS, Graphs & Charts, and Microsoft Excel was used to analyse the data.

2.8 LIMITATIONS:

1. Within the stipulated time period the study couldn't go beyond the expectations.
2. The lack of cooperation from the respondents.
3. Some of the respondents were not available or interested in furnishing information due to their personal bias or busy in workplace.
4. Due to time constraints large sample size is not taken.

3. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:

1. Which type of appraisal do you prefer?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
360 degree method	29	25.4	25.4	25.4
checklist method	25	21.9	21.9	47.4
Valid rating scales	24	21.1	21.1	68.4
easy method	36	31.6	31.6	100.0
Total	114	100.0	100.0	

From the above table, it is inferred that in the company appraisal system 25.4% of employee prefer 360 degree appraisal, 21.9% of the employee prefer checklist method, 21.1% of them prefer rating scale of appraisal whereas 31.58% of the employee prefer easy method of the appraisal system.

2. Who analyse the performance appraisal system in the department?

Who analyse the performance appraisal system in the department?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
superior	39	34.2	34.2	34.2
subordinate	27	23.7	23.7	57.9
Valid self	24	21.1	21.1	78.9
others	24	21.1	21.1	100.0
Total	114	100.0	100.0	

From the above table, it is inferred that in the company appraisal system is analysed by the superiors, whereas 23.68% of the respondent's feels that it is also analysed by the subordinate. Which shows that in appraisal system all the inputs is taken from the co-workers as well as superiors.

3. Does the organization follow any behaviour dimensions while appraising employee performance?

Does the organization follow any behaviour dimensions while appraising employee performance ?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
strongly agree	27	23.7	23.7	23.7
agree	30	26.3	26.3	50.0
Valid disagree	32	28.1	28.1	78.1
strongly disagree	15	13.2	13.2	91.2
neutral	10	8.8	8.8	100.0
Total	114	100.0	100.0	

From the above table, it is inferred that most of the respondents feels that in the organization while appraising employee performance the behavioural dimension is also considered.

4. Are your service rendered towards the organization being recognized by the management?

Are your service rendered towards the organization being recognized by the management?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
strongly agree	21	18.4	18.4	18.4
agree	24	21.1	21.1	39.5
Valid disagree	18	15.8	15.8	55.3
strongly disagree	24	21.1	21.1	76.3
neutral	27	23.7	23.7	100.0
Total	114	100.0	100.0	

From the above table, it is inferred that the contribution of the employees in the company is considered and recognised by the management during the appraisal of the employee.

It can be observed that their contribution is valued at the organization.

5. Organization is helpful in improving performance

H0: There is no significant impact of appraisal process on improving performance.

H1: There is significant impact of appraisal process on improving performance.

Correlations

	Is your organization helpful in improving performance & generating new ideas ?	Do you satisfy the level of the current appraisal process ?
Is an organization helpful in improving performance & generating new ideas ?	1	-.193*
Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)		.040
N	114	114
Do you satisfy the level of the current appraisal process ?	-.193*	1
Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)		.040
N	114	114

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

From the above correlation table, it is inferred that the significance value is 0.040 which is less than 0.05. We can say that the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate hypothesis is accepted.

In other words, the employees are satisfied by the organizational appraisal system and it helps them in improving their performance and generating new ideas.

The Pearson Correlation was found to be 1, which shows that there is strong positive correlation between the variables.

6. Satisfaction by the current appraisal system

H0: There is no significant effect of improved performance on current appraisal process.

H1: There is significant effect of improved performance on current appraisal process.

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	8.782	1	8.782	4.320	.040 ^b
Residual	227.683	112	2.033		
Total	236.465	113			

a. Dependent Variable: Is an organization helpful in improving performance & generating new ideas?

b. Predictors: (Constant), Do you satisfy the level of the current appraisal process?

From the above ANOVA table, it is inferred that the significance value is 0.040 which is less than 0.05. From the significance value we can state the null hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted.

In other words, we can say the employee are satisfied by the current appraisal system of the organization.

7. Do you think performances appraisal improves performance?

H0: There is no significant effect of performance appraisal system on employee performance.

H1: There is significant effect of performance appraisal system on employee performance.

ANOVA

Do you think performances appraisal improves performance?

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.014	1	.014	.064	.001
Within Groups	24.618	112	.220		
Total	24.632	113			

From the above ANOVA table, it is inferred that the significance value is 0.001 which is less than 0.05. From the significance value we can state the null hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted.

In other words we can say that the performance appraisal system enhances the performance of the employees.

8. Do you experience co-operations from all levels of management to achieve your standards?

Do you experience co-operations from all levels of management to achieve your standards ?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
strongly agree	23	20.2	20.2	20.2
agree	13	11.4	11.4	31.6
disagree	28	24.6	24.6	56.1
strongly disagree	23	20.2	20.2	76.3
neutral	27	23.7	23.7	100.0
Total	114	100.0	100.0	

From the above frequency table, it is inferred that the management didn't cooperate with the employees to achieve their highest standard of potential. As it is showing that 24.6% of respondents disagree from the statement.

Whereas some are neutral and agreed that they have received the cooperation from the all management

9. Does the organization follow any behaviour dimensions while appraising employee performance?

Does the organization follow any behaviour dimensions while appraising employee performance ?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
strongly agree	27	23.7	23.7	23.7
agree	30	26.3	26.3	50.0
disagree	32	28.1	28.1	78.1
strongly disagree	15	13.2	13.2	91.2
neutral	10	8.8	8.8	100.0
Total	114	100.0	100.0	

From the above frequency table, it is inferred that the management consider the behavioural factor during the performance appraisal of the employee, as it can be observed from the above table that 50% of the employees feels that the behavioural aspect is taken into consideration during the appraisal of employee.

10. Do you think performance appraisal system helps you to develop your skills?

H0: There is no significant impact of performance appraisal system on employee's skill.

H1: There is significant impact of performance appraisal system on employee's skill.

Correlations

		Gender	Do you think performance appraisal system helps you to develop your skills ?
Gender	Pearson Correlation	1	.036
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.007
	N	114	114
Do you think performance appraisal system helps you to develop your skills ?	Pearson Correlation	.036	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.007	
	N	114	114

From the above correlation table, it is inferred that the significance value is 0.036 which is less than 0.05. We can say that the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate hypothesis is accepted.

In other words, we can say that performance appraisal system helps the employees to develop their personal skills. The Pearson Correlation was found to be 1, which shows that there is strong positive correlation between the variables.

Findings and conclusion:

It was observed that 21% of the respondents are agreed with the rating scales, 31% of the respondent agreed with essay method, 25% of respondents agreed with 360 degrees method and remaining 21% of respondents agreed with check list method. From analysis it was found that 49% of respondents said that they are satisfied with the organization considering behaviour dimensions while appraising the employee performance 41% dissatisfied. From the correlation analysis, the employees are satisfied by the organizational appraisal system, and it helps them in improving their performance and generating new ideas with 0.040 significance value. It was observed that 31% of respondents said that they agreed with the co-operation management to achieve work standards and 44% did not agree. From ANOVA analysis with significance value of 0.40 it was found that the employee are satisfied by the current appraisal system of the organization. With the significance value of 0.001 it was found that performance appraisal system enhances the performance of the employees. Management didn't cooperate with the employees to achieve their highest standard of potential. 50% of the employees feels that the behavioural aspect is taken into consideration during the appraisal of employee.

In correlation analysis it was found that performance appraisal system helps the employees to develop their personal skills. From frequency table it was found that 46.49% of employees are satisfied from the current performance system whereas, 53.51% of employees are not satisfied.

CONCLUSION:

The study on performance appraisal towards Hindustan Coca-Cola Beverage Pvt. Ltd. has provided valuable insights into the existing appraisal system and its impact on the organization and its employees. Through a comprehensive analysis of the challenges and areas for improvement, several key findings have emerged.

The study revealed inconsistencies in the evaluation criteria, feedback mechanisms, and performance indicators used within the appraisal system. These inconsistencies have led to perceptions of bias and unfairness among employees, resulting in decreased motivation, job satisfaction, and potentially hindering overall organizational performance. Additionally, the system's inability to effectively differentiate between high-performing and low-performing employees has limited opportunities for employee development and recognition.

However, the study has also identified opportunities for improvement. By addressing the identified challenges and implementing appropriate solutions, Hindustan Coca-Cola Beverage Pvt. Ltd. can enhance the fairness,

effectiveness, and transparency of the performance appraisal process. This includes establishing clear and consistent evaluation criteria, incorporating meaningful feedback mechanisms, and improving communication regarding performance expectations.

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A STUDY ON THE PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL SYSTEM IN ERNST & YOUNG IN BENGULURU

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Abstract:

This study examines the performance appraisal system implemented at Ernst & Young in Bengaluru. The purpose of the study is to assess employees' opinions and perceptions of the system. The study utilized a survey questionnaire administered to a sample of employees within the organization. The questionnaire covered various aspects of the performance appraisal system, including its effectiveness, impact on employee motivation, clarity of objectives, decision-making processes, and frequency of appraisals.

Based on the analysis of the collected data, it was observed that a majority of employees (67%) expressed a positive opinion regarding the performance appraisal system. The findings indicate that the system has a significant impact on employee motivation and contributes to performance improvement. The primary data collected was run under SPSS software for correlation, regression and descriptive statistics. 150 responses to get quantitative solution.

Key words: Performance management, Feedback, Rewards & recognition.

1. **Introduction:** Performance appraisal is the process of evaluating the performance of the employees, sharing that information with them and searching for ways to improve their performance appraisal is the step where the management finds out how effective it has been at hiring and placing employees. Performance appraisal is the process of evaluating an employee's performance of a job in terms of its requirements. It is the process of assessing execution of representative and to comprehend capacities of a man for further development and improvement. Performance appraisal means is the process of evaluating the performance of the employee. Like whatever the work will be assigned to the employees they have to finish with in their time limit they have to be appreciated by the employers like rewards & recognition.

1.1 Preferences of Performance Appraisal:

- ✧ Promotion
- ✧ Composition
- ✧ Employee development
- ✧ Selection validation
- ✧ Communication
- ✧ Motivation:
 - Traditional Methods
 - Modern Methods

Traditional methods:

- ✧ Graphical rating scale
- ✧ Ranking
- ✧ Paired comparison method
- ✧ Forced distribution method
- ✧ Group appraisal

Modern methods:

- ◇ Behavior anchored rating skills
- ◇ Human resource accounting
- ◇ 360 degree feedback

1.2 Need for the study:

- ◇ Performance appraisal system is one of the most important way by which the organization can understand employees and evaluate their desiring skills set to perform a specific task.
- ◇ A good performance appraisal system helps an organization to understand its human capital need and its weakness.
- ◇ It also highlights an individual employee weakness and strength.

1.3 Scope of the study:

- ◇ It helps the organization at which position they are & what else is to be improve & where is the drawback.
- ◇ Conducting training program for employees to get aware of the work they had to be done.
- ◇ To improve employee work performance by helping them realize and use their full potential in carrying out their firm missions.

1.4 Statement of the problem:

Performance appraisal is a formal exercise carried out for all executive & employees with respect to their contribution made towards the growth of the organization it is mainly used to measure the overall performance of an employee over a period of time, to identify exactly the utility of employees towards the current appraisal system is difficult.

Further Lower level of awareness of managers leads to ineffectiveness in implementation; it leads to low awareness of employees on existing appraisal system respondents also feel sensitive to reveal their true attitude existing system.

2.0 Research Methodology:

Research methodology is maybe understood as a science of studying how research is done scientifically. It is a way to systematically solve the research problem.

According to the advance learner dictionary of current English lays down the meaning as a “careful investigation or inquiry especially through search for new facts in any branch of knowledge”

2.1 Objectives of the study:

- ◇ To evaluate performance appraisal system of the management of Ernst & young.
- ◇ To identify the performance appraisal techniques adapted by Ernst & young.
- ◇ To examine the employees attitude towards appraisal system of Ernst young.
- ◇ To identify the awareness level of performance appraisal techniques among the employees.

2.2. Hypothesis Testing:

H0: There is no significance relationship between improvement in performance after the performance appraisal system and your opinion about the current performance appraisal system.

H1: There is a significance relationship between improvement in performance after the performance appraisal system and your opinion about the current performance appraisal system.

2.3 Data Collection:

1. Primary data.
2. Secondary data

Primary data:

Primary data collected using closed questionnaires which were administrated to the respondent personally to shorten the response time and enable on the spot clarification of any doubt that the respondent might have regarding any questions

Secondary data:

Secondary data collected from company websites and internet

2.4 Sampling Plan:

A sampling plan is an outline based on which research is conducted. A sampling plan outlines the individuals chosen to represent the target population under consideration for research purposes.

2.5 Sampling Method:

The technique I have chosen is simple random technique. This technique helped to choose a group of employees which easier.

2.6 Sample Size:

A sample is a unit of an entire population under study. It is generally difficult to study an entire population as a whole so we tend to considered the true representative of such population .The conveniences sampling method was adapted for conducting the survey The sample hence forth selected for conducting a survey for the study should be selected without any bias .I have made all possible attempts to fulfill these rules.

I have communicated with 150 employees and took their responses.

2.7 DATA ANALYSIS TOOLS: Various data analysis tools like SPSS, Graphs & Charts, and Microsoft Excel was used to analyze the data.

3.0 DATA ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION

1. Does promotion, rewards, awards are based on the performance appraisal system?

Table: 1

	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative
Yes	135	90	90	90
No	15	10	10	100
total	150	100	100	

Interpretation:

From the above table, it is inferred that

- 90% of them are agreed that promotions, rewards, awards are based on the performance appraisal system.
- 10% of them are not agreed that promotions, rewards, awards are based on the performance appraisal system.

2. Receive increment after performance appraisal?

Table: 2

	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Strongly agree	64	42	42	42
Agree	40	27	27	69
Neutral	39	26	26	95

Disagree	6	4	4	99
Strongly Disagree	1	1	1	100
Total	150	100	100	

Interpretation: From the above table, it is inferred that

- 1% of them are strongly disagreeing with the received increment after performance appraisal.
- 4% of them are disagreeing with the received increment after performance appraisal.
- 26% of them are neutral with the received increment after performance appraisal.
- 27% of them are agreeing with the received increment after performance appraisal.
- 42% of them are strongly agreed with the received increment after performance appraisal.

3. Does effective performance appraisal motivate employee?

Table: 3

	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Yes	139	96	96	96
No	11	4	4	100
total	150	100	100	

Interpretation:

From the above table, it is inferred that

- 96% of them felt that effective performance appraisal motivates employees.
- 4% of them felt that there is effective performance appraisal do not motivated employees.

4. Conflicts arise among employees after performance appraisal?

Table: 4

	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Strongly disagree	25	17	17	17
Disagree	18	12	12	29
Neutral	71	48	48	77
Agree	30	20	20	97
Strongly agree	6	3	3	100
total	150	100	100	

Interpretation:

From the above table, it is inferred that

- 17% of them are strongly disagree with the conflict arises among employees after performance appraisal.
- 12% of them are disagree with the conflict arises among employees after performance appraisal.
- 48% of them are neutral with the conflict arises among employees after performance appraisal.
- 20% of them are agree with the conflict arises among employees after performance appraisal.
- 6% of them are strongly agree with the conflict arises among employees after performance appraisal.

5. Improvement in performance after performance appraisal system?

Table: 5

	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
strongly agree	49	33	33	33
Agree	60	41	41	74
Neutral	35	24	24	97
Disagree	3	2	2	99
Strongly Disagree	3	1	1	100
total	150	100	100	

Interpretation:

From the above table, it is inferred that

- 33% of them are strongly disagree with the improvement in performance after performance appraisal system
- 41% of them are disagree with the improvement in performance after performance appraisal system
- 24% of them are neutral with the improvement in performance after performance appraisal system
- 2% of them are agree with the improvement in performance after performance appraisal system
- 1% of them are strongly agree with the improvement in performance after performance appraisal system

1. Descriptive statistics: Age &gender

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Age	150	3	1	4	1.37	.597	1.558	.198	2.327	.394
Gender	150	1	1	2	1.45	.499	.217	.198	-1.980	.394
Valid N	150									

Interpretation:

Age values:

The mean age is 1.37, suggesting that, on average; the individuals have an age of 1.37. The standard deviation of age is 0.597,

The skewness value of 1.558. The kurtosis value of 2.327. The mean gender value is 1.45, The standard deviation of gender is 0.499,

Gender values:

The skewness value of 0.217, The kurtosis value of -1.980

2. Correlations:

H0: There is no significance relationship between improvement in performance after the performance appraisal system and your opinion about the current performance appraisal system.

H1: There is a significance relationship between improvement in performance after the performance appraisal system and your opinion about the current performance appraisal system.

Correlations

	improvement in performance after performance appraisal system	Your opinion about current performance appraisal system
improvement in performance after performance appraisal system	1	.316**
Pearson Correlation		.000
Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
N	150	150
Your opinion about current performance appraisal system	.316**	1
Pearson Correlation		
Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
N	150	150

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Interpretation:

The correlation analysis indicates a significant positive relationship between improvement in performance after the performance appraisal system and your opinion about the current performance appraisal system.

The Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.316 suggests a moderate positive correlation between these two variables. The p-value of 0.000 indicates that this correlation is statistically significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

3. Regressions:

Hypothesis:

H0: There is no significance relationship between improvement in performance after the performance appraisal system and your opinion about the current performance appraisal system. **H1:** There is a significance relationship between improvement in performance after the performance appraisal system and your opinion about the current performance appraisal system

Variables Entered/Removed

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Your opinion about current performance appraisal system		.Enter

- a. Dependent Variable: improvement in performance after performance appraisal system
- b. All requested variables entered.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.316 ^a	.100	.094	.806	.100	16.422	1	148	.000

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Your opinion about current performance appraisal system

Interpretation:

R = sqrt.100 Value of Sig: .000

According to the survey, there is no correlation between an opinion about current performance appraisal system, and: improvement in performance after performance appraisal system if the sigvalue is more than 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted.

R = square = .100 indicates that there is no variation in the: improvement in performance after performance appraisal system and your opinion about current performance appraisal system

Regression formula

Where $Y = MX + C$

Y is the reliant variable. X is an unrelated variable. Constant C

Function = M

FINDINGS:

1. In the organization majority of respondent's are 56% were male.
2. In the organization majority of respondents are 79%. Were 0-2 year's experience.
3. It has been observed that 48% of employees in the company hold a neutral opinion regarding conflicts arising among employees after performance appraisals.
4. It has been observed that 42% of employees in the company strongly agree that they receive an increment after the performance appraisal.
5. In regression analysis it is observed there is no correlation between improvement in performance after the performance appraisal system and your opinion about the current performance appraisal system and if the sig value is more than 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted.
6. In correlation analysis it is observed with the Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.316 suggests a moderate positive correlation between these improvement in performance after the performance appraisal system and

your opinion about the current performance appraisal system. P-value of 0.000 indicates that this correlation is statistically significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

CONCLUSION:

The study was conducted at Ernst & young, in order to find out the Performance Appraisal system followed in the organization. Incentives and bonus are motivating and encouraging employees to work more effectively and to reach goals of the organization. Proper training and satisfaction at all levels will be the strongest foundation. In every organization Appraisers give proper feedback to their appraisers on a day-to-day basis and proper training or challenging tasks can be given to improve their performance. Mainly formal training is given at the time of joining in the organization.

From the study conducted at the Ernst & young it can be clearly concluded that there is a definite need to suggest measures to make the performance appraisal system more effective and strong so that the performance of the employees increases and the prosperity, fame, goodwill and wealth of the organization increase.

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A STUDY ON FACTORS INFLUENCING THE EMPLOYEES WORK-LIFE BALANCE

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Abstract: -

Work-life balance is the ability to manage work-life balance and remain productive and competitive at work while maintaining a happy and healthy home life with plenty of free time, despite work pressure and endless activities that demand your time and effort. However, there are still some factors that affect the work-life balance of employees in organizations. Work-life balance has become one of the main challenges in human resource management. With the transformation of information and communication technologies and their use, it has positively and negatively affected the working and family life of individuals. This study examines the impact of employees on the determinants of work-life balance of software professionals working in the granite company. The responses taken for research is 166 . The data is collected through questionnaire prepared.

Keywords: Work-life balance, family and family life, work life, professional engagement, granite industry, work stress, job satisfaction, career growth.

1.INTRODUCTION

Maintaining a balance between particular and work life has come an important content in society. The term Work-life Balance(WLB) was first used in the mid-1970s to describe work- life balance. In 1977, Kanter reflected on the "separate world myth" and drew attention to the fact that work and home are inevitably linked.

In the moment's fast- paced society, HR professionals are looking for ways to retain workers with precious company knowledge, motivate workers and keep up with fleetly changing trends. The changing characteristics of the 21st century led to ongoing changes, misgivings and inordinate pressure to increase productivity.

These changes disrupt the balance in workers' lives and beget confusion and stress. This is felled by the extreme position of competitiveness in the pool, which is causing new challenges and problems for the pool. The pressing need for growth in all areas for both associations and individuals has led to an imbalance in the lives of the pool.

utmost workers either spend long hours at work or take them home, reducing the quality of life. Working life isn't only a matter for individuality, but also for employers and the whole society. In times past, work and life were considered independent disciplines. workers were anticipated to keep the interest of the association ahead of their own interests. But with changing times, associations have realized the impact of work life on life and vice versa. In recent times, associations have come apprehensive of the fact that professional and life complement each other and don't contend with each other.

1.1 Work-life Balance

Work-life balance refers to a state of equilibrium in which a person effectively balances work or career demands with the demands of their personal life. An individual who lacks work-life balance in both work and home responsibilities, he has to work for long hours and lacks personal time.

work-life balance is used to be difficult or not possible to bring work from home, so there was a clean line between work life and personal life. The rise of mobile technology, cloud-based software, and the proliferation of the

Internet have made it much easier for employees to be "always" at work, blurring the line between professional and personal. Some commentators discuss that smartphones and 365 days access to the workplace have replaced and control of managers. Stress is a common problem of poor work-life balance.

Work-life in Research Granite Industry

The granite industry is doing very well in India. Thanks to the determinedness smash there are further job openings. Right after completing professional qualifications like B.tech and designing(Engineering Graduates and Computer Post Graduates in gravestone designing and trades), campaigners get jobs. payment and benefits are encouraging. But working life is veritably complicated and veritably demanding. There are numerous pulls and pressures during working life.

1.2 Need for the study:

Every organization is constantly looking for ways to improve the work and personal life of each employee and get the best out of each employee. This will help the organization retain employees. The need for Work life balance is to ensure that employees are satisfied both with their work and with their family, personal, free, etc. It is also needed to know if employees are financially satisfied for working extra hours more than usual. Work-life balance will be needed for all employees and employers to increase their performance and productivity and help them be loyal to work and family and personal needs.

Work-life balance means different things to different people and different things at different stages of life. Employee commitment can mean the difference between companies that compete in the marketplace and those that cannot. Employers who can best align their business' requirements for flexibility with the needs of employees and potential employees will be well positioned to succeed. Employees may have their own reasons for preferring one working time model over another.

1.3 Scope of the study:

The proposal research work is limited to analysing the factors affecting work life balance in although they may vary from organization to organization geographically and at the individual level depending on individual perception, attitude, values, personality etc.

1.4 Statement of the problem:

Diversity and work/life initiatives can be found at the heart of the new social contract being negotiated by employers and employees. "The basic outline of the social contract, as it has emerged over the past few years, calls on workers to give their best contributions and greatest energy to work in exchange for interesting work, respectful treatment, opportunities for development, and an environment to match. to individual needs. Where these provisions conflict (eg the level of commitment and energy expected by employers versus the flexibility required by employees), both diversity management and work/life expertise will be critical to finding win-win solutions.

Life and work are essentially two separate spheres of activity, but they are overwhelmingly intertwined. This overlap has blurred the boundaries between the two spheres. In this corporate work scenario, office work seems endless. An individual can work too much, sacrifice quality family time, quickly rise to the top of the corporate ladder, but success and material gain will not compensate for the price he was forced to pay in the long run. This of course leads to work stress, less family time and shallow family relationships.

2. Research Methodology:

Research is descriptive in nature; the data collection tool is used in the research includes questionnaire based on different questions from the employees which tells us about work life balance and its impacts on their professional and personal life. The sample size for this research was 166 which includes only the employee .The data collection period was 35 days.

Systematic sampling technique is used in the research paper to get the quantitative type of solution for the questionnaire prepared. The primary data collected was run under SPSS software for correlation, factor analysis and an ANOVA test for 166 responses to get quantitative solution. A structured questionnaire was used in the study,

which was based on five-point Likert scale. Divided into groups like demographic profile, statement related to work life balance ,co-workers support etc.

2.1 Objectives of the study

1. To study the factors influencing the work life balance of Employees
2. To identify the problem faced by the Employees while working.
3. To understand the benefits of achieving a healthy work life balance.
4. To Suggest appropriate Strategies to improve the level of work life balance.

2.2. Hypothesis Testing:

H0: There is no significant impact of co-workers and work-life balance

H1: There is significant impact of co-workers and work life balance.

H0₂: There is no significant impact of job stress and work-life balance.

H1₂: There is significant impact of job stress and work-life balance.

H0₂: There is no significant impact of role expectation conflict and work-life balance.

H1₂: There is significant impact of role expectation conflict and work-life balance.

2.3 Research design:

The research adopted is descriptive research design. It involves facts-findings, inquires of different kinds etc.

Descriptive research studies are those studies which are concerned with describing the characteristics of a particular individual or group.

2.4 Type of Research: QUANTITATIVE RESEARCH will be done for the study because aim to gather an in-depth understanding of human behavior and the reason that governs such behavior.

2.5 Data Sources

Collection of data is the primary importance in the research process. Data, which was collected for the purpose of research, helps in proper analysis, which is helpful to conduct research efficiently. The data source, which is very important in collection of data is primary data and secondary data. Both primary and secondary data are taken into consideration for conducting the study of training and its impact on employee performance.

1. Primary source of data
2. Secondary source of data

For this dissertation the data was collected from both the sources.

Primary data:

Data is made available through interview and questionnaires. Questionnaires were prepared for trainees to know the impact and methods of training adopted by organization.

Secondary data:

Data were collected from documents, records, Internet, company past records etc.

2.6 SAMPLING PLAN:

Sampling unit/Target group: The respondents are of different departments.

2.7 SAMPLE SIZE:

Sample size refers to the number of respondents or the size of sample, which is to be surveyed. Here the sample size taken for the study was 166.

2.8 SAMPLING TECHNIQUE: Systematic sampling technique is used for the study as in probability sampling technique each member in a population has equal chance of being selected as a sample.

Variables

The variables are used in this research. The dependent variable identified for research is co-worker support and job stress while the independent variable is work-life balance.

Dependent Variable (work life balance)

work-life balance items taken from the work-life balance scale developed by Brough et al. (2009) was used to assess employees' experiences of balancing their work and non-work lives. The items were "I currently have a good balance between the time I spend at work and the time I have available for non-work activities", "I have difficulty balancing work and non-work activities", "I feel that the balance between my work demands and non-work activities are currently fine" and 'Overall, I believe that my work and non-work activities are balanced'

Independent Variable (job stress, co-worker support, role expectation conflict)

Job stress is defined as the station of workers when they encounter work pressures as well as demands on their knowledge and chops and incongruence with their job and challenges to their capability to manage with it. The occupational stress scale is a measure of subjectively educated stress at work. It consists of nine particulars that have a five- point Likert response format. It generally yields Cronbach's nascence portions of 0.90 and has a largely replicable bifactor structure with a strong general factor.

Role expectation conflict occurs when inappropriate demands are placed on an employee to the extent that both would be difficult to comply with. (Nicklaus, 2007) proposed four classes of role expectation conflict, i.e., individual role expectation conflict, sender conflict, role expectation conflict, and sender conflict. Kamel (2011) also found that lack of resources, conflicting demands and distinctive work style could create the effect of work pressure on work-life balance. Role conflict describes a conflict between roles or between roles corresponding to two or more statuses held by one individual. We experience role conflict when we find ourselves pulled in different directions as we try to respond to the many states we hold. In other words, they experience role conflict. Role conflict begins because of the human desire to achieve success and because of the pressure placed on the individual by two compelling, conflicting, and incompatible demands competing against each other.

Co-worker support is defined as "the extent to which employees believe that their co-workers are willing to provide them with work-related assistance to assist them in the performance of their job duties." These can motivate followers to take on additional responsibilities and engage in more prosocial behaviors that are necessary to achieve collective goals, including helping co-workers with heavy workloads, sharing resources, and providing advice to co-workers who encounter work problems. Existing empirical studies also show that employees who receive more support from their co-workers can acquire more job resources to deal with stressful and innovative tasks.

2.9 DATA ANALYSIS TOOLS: Various data analysis tools like SPSS, Graphs & Charts, and Microsoft Excel was used to analyze the data.

3. DATA ANALYSIS

1. You are able to balance between time at work at other activities?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid				
strongly disagree	80	48.2	48.2	48.2
Disagree	50	30.1	30.1	78.3
Neutral	24	14.5	14.5	92.8
Agree	9	5.4	5.4	98.2
strongly agree	3	1.8	1.8	100.0
Total	166	100.0	100.0	

From the frequency table, it is inferred that 48.2% of the respondents disagree, 30.1% of respondents disagree, 14.5% of respondents or neutral, 5.4% of respondents are agree, 1.8% of respondents are strongly. The result

indicates that the majority of people are strongly disagree with they were not able to balance between the time at work and time at other activities.

2.Has anyone given your assistance in your work?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid never	31	18.7	18.7	18.7
very occasionally	37	22.3	22.3	41.0
sometimes	47	28.3	28.3	69.3
often	26	15.7	15.7	84.9
very often	20	12.0	12.0	97.0
all the time	5	3.0	3.0	100.0
Total	166	100.0	100.0	

From the frequency table, it is inferred that highest respondents for some time with 28.3% ,22.3% respondents for very occasionally 18.7% for never 15.7% for often 12% for very often and 3% for all the time .The final result shows that majority of respondents for sometimes for the statement has any one given your assistance in your work.

3.Do you find yourself spending more and more time on work related projects?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid yes	106	63.9	63.9	63.9
no	60	36.1	36.1	100.0
Total	166	100.0	100.0	

From the frequency table, it is inferred that 63.9% respondents for yes and 36.1% of respondents for No. The results show that the majority of respondents for yes for the statement do you find yourself spending more and more time on work related projects.

4.The effect of your job on you is too high?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid strongly disagree	42	25.3	25.3	25.3
disagree	38	22.9	22.9	48.2
undecided	42	25.3	25.3	73.5
agree	24	14.5	14.5	88.0
strongly agree	20	12.0	12.0	100.0
Total	166	100.0	100.0	

From the frequency table, it is inferred that equally respondents for 25.3% strongly disagree and undecided the effect of your job on you is too high.22.9% respondents for disagree 14.5% for agree and 12% for strongly agree.

Regression analysis and summary :

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Work life balance	1.8253	.99066	166
co-worker support	2.3976	.99623	166
role expectation conflict	2.9578	1.67097	166
job stress scale	2.8072	1.35251	166

Correlations

		Work life balance	co-worker support	role expectation conflict	job stress scale
Pearson Correlation	Work life balance	1.000	.286	.153	.178
	co-worker support	.286	1.000	-.026	.183
	role expectation conflict	.153	-.026	1.000	.015
	job stress scale	.178	.183	.015	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	Work life balance	.	.000	.025	.011
	co-worker support	.000	.	.368	.009
	role expectation conflict	.025	.368	.	.423
	job stress scale	.011	.009	.423	.
N	Work life balance	166	166	166	166
	co-worker support	166	166	166	166
	role expectation conflict	166	166	166	166
	job stress scale	166	166	166	166

Variables Entered/Removed

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	job stress scale, role expectation conflict, co-worker support		.Enter

Dependent Variable: work life balance.

All requested variables entered.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.351 ^a	.123	.107	.93629	1.719
a. Predictors: (Constant), job stress scale, role expectation conflict, co-worker support					
b. Dependent Variable: work life balance					

Interpretation: From the summary table, R square value is found that 0.123 which means independent variables job stress, role expectation conflict, co-worker support are explaining 12.3% of variance in dependent variable work life balance

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	19.918	3	6.639	7.573	.000 ^b
	Residual	142.016	162	.877		
	Total	161.934	165			

a. Dependent Variable: work life balance

b. Predictors: (Constant), job stress scale, role expectation conflict, co-worker support.

INTERPRETATION: From ANOVA it is found that the significance value is 0.000 which is less than 0.05. It means regression model is significant influencing dependent variable work life balance.

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.651	.261		2.498	.013
	co-worker support	.265	.074	.267	3.561	.000
	role expectation conflict	.094	.044	.158	2.147	.033
	job stress scale	.093	.055	.127	1.697	.092
a. Dependent Variable: work life balance						

From the coefficient table it is found that the standardized co-efficient beta, for **co-worker support** is 0.013 and significant value is 0.000 less than 0.05 which mean co-worker support is affecting dependent variable (work life balance)

Hence null hypothesis(H0) is rejected, and alternative hypothesis (H1) is accepted.

From the co-efficient table, it is found that the standardized co-efficient beta for **role expectation conflict** is 0.158 and significant value is 0.033 less than 0.05 which means role expectation conflict is significantly affecting dependent variable (work life balance).

Hence null hypothesis(h02) is rejected, and alternative hypothesis (H2) is accepted.

From the co-efficient table, it is found that the standardized co-efficient beta for **JOB STRESS** is 0.127 and significant value is 0.092 greater than 0.05 which means job stress is not significantly effecting dependent variable (work life balance).

Hence null hypothesis(h03) is accepted, and alternative hypothesis (H3) is rejected.

CONCLUSION:

Work-life balance remains an issue that requires considerable attention from society. The changing nature of the global economy, where organizations often operate on a 24/7 schedule and technological advances allow the employee to be constantly connected, has brought the issue of work-life balance to the force. This study tries to understand the concept of work-life balance that is prevalent in the granite industry. It also revealed different work-life balance strategies implemented by different organizations and employees themselves.

This concept is a growing phenomenon and is opening its doors to research. The area covered by the researcher was limited, there are several areas that could be covered to understand the whole concept of work life balance.

From the analysis made in the above sections, factors, both personal and professional variables, such as family influence, working hours, and organizational support significantly influence the work-life balance of software employees.

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A STUDY ON QUALITY OF WORK LIFE BALANCE WITH REFERENCE TO EMPLOYEES AT AMARA RAJA BATTERIES

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Abstract: -

Quality of work life is the quality of the content of relationship between employees and their total working environment with human dimensions added to the usual technical and economic ones. Quality of work life involves job security, good working conditions, adequate and fair compensation and equal employment opportunity all together. QWL aims at to meet the twin goals of enhanced effectiveness of organization and improved quality of life at work for employees. The study focused on the factor influences QWL of employees, level of satisfaction of employees on present level of QWL and the influence of QWL. 50 employees of Amara Raja Batteries units of equal capacity have taken as samples. Motivational insights are the important factor that influences the employees to improve their life. QWL of employees had an influence on the employees' productivity.

Key words: Industry, Textile, employees, Quality of Work life, employees, job satisfaction, productivity.

1. INTRODUCTION MEANING:

Maintaining a balance between work life and personal life is called work life balance. The meaning of work life balance has chameleon characteristics. It means different things to different groups, and the meaning often depends on the context of terms used regarding work life balance; some definitions overlap and some are continuing to evolve.

WHAT IS WORK-LIFE BALANCE?

Effectively managing the juggling act between paid job and the other activities that are important to people is the goal of work-life balance. It's not about saying work is wrong or evil, but that it shouldn't totally take the place of other important activities for individuals, such as spending time with family, taking part in community events, volunteering, pursuing one's own personal development, and engaging in leisure and recreation.

The "right" balance is quite individual and will alter for every individual at various points in their lives. Instead of having too much work, getting hired or finding more job may be the problem for some people. There is no "one size fits all" answer; rather, a balanced existence involves dividing our emotional, intellectual, creative, spiritual, and physical effort among the major areas of value. The vitality of the entire may be threatened by the neglect of one or more sections or anchor points.

Quality of work life

Quality of work life (QWL) is a fact that an individual's life can't be compartmentalised and any disturbance on the personal front will affect his/her professional life and vice-versa. A good work life balance is also what motivates an employee the most to perform well at his or job and also spend quality time with the family.

Maintaining its position as a top provider of education, research, and employment is important to the University of Pennsylvania. To support the University's outstanding goals and to provide chances for professors and staff to have a constructive, productive, and positive work experience, Penn's quality of worklife (QOWL) project was launched in 1995.

Quality of work life programs has become important in the workplace for the following reasons:

- More women working in the workforce
- Increased male involvement in dependent care (child and elder) activities
- Increased responsibility for elders
- Increased demands at work

1.1 QOWL programs have been found to:

- Improve workplace morale
- Encourage employee commitment
- Support recruitment
- Encourage retention
- Reduce absenteeism; and
- Maximize staff resources

The programs, policies and services offered through QOWL programs:

- a. Support faculty and staff efforts to manage the competing demands of work and personal life,
- b. Support health promotion and wellness, and

“Quality of work life as the extent to which employees can enhance their personal life through their work and their environment”.

1.2 NEED FOR THE STUDY

The present study concentrates deeply in “Employee Work Life Balance” which refers to how the employees are balancing the work as well as life. The concept of “Employee Work Life Balance” is flexible and elastic and differs widely with time, industry, social values, degree of industrialization, it is also moulded according to age – group, gender, social-culture, marital, economic status, and educational level of employee.

1.3 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The scope of the study is important for factors of affecting the employee work life balance.

It is very essential to the organization to know and analyze the work life balance of the employees. This study is confined to measure and find the reasons that are affecting it in the Amara raja batteries.

1.4 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

There have been a number of valuable studies regarding work life balance and the factors affecting work life balance. But in the context of employee performance and job satisfaction there are less researches based on this topic. Therefore, there is a research gap on this employee job satisfaction and employee performance. This study is conducted to fill the existing research gap. So, the empirical study has been conducted to investigate how work life balance impact on the employee satisfaction and employee job performance.

2. Research Methodology: Sources of data

The primary data is collected through structured questionnaire.

In section A, the study includes the personal profile of the selected employees. In this section, the questions that are included are age, gender, marital status of the employees.

In section B, the study includes the questionnaire which measures quality of work life balance, employee performance and employee job satisfaction. Statements were given to measure the impact of work life balance on employee job satisfaction and employee performance and the factors that are impacting on the work life balance with five-point Likert scale ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree.

2.1 Objectives of the study

- To analyze the effectiveness of work life balance at Amara Raja Batteries.
- To identify the relationship between work life balance and employee performance.
- To identify the factors that are affecting the work life balance of the employee.

2.2. Hypothesis Testing:

Based on the conceptual model the following hypotheses were developed for testing:

Relationship between work life balance and employee performance

H0: There is a positive relationship between work life balance and employee performance.

H1: There is no positive relationship between work life balance and employee performance

Relationship between work life balance and employee job satisfaction

H0: There is a positive relationship between work life balance and employee job satisfaction.

H1: There is a no positive relationship between work life balance and employee job satisfaction.

2.3 Research design:

This study is inferential and descriptive in nature. The goal of conclusive research is to test a hypothesis and explore specific relationships. It is based on large representative samples and the obtained data are subjected to quantitative analysis. The instrument was based on a five-point Likert scale with the options strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, and strongly disagree.

2.4 Data Sources

The primary data is collected through structured questionnaire.

In section A, the study includes the personal profile of the selected employees. In this section, the questions that are included are age, gender, marital status of the employees.

In section B, the study includes the questionnaire which measures quality of work life balance, employee performance and employee job satisfaction. Statements were given to measure the impact of work life balance on employee job satisfaction and employee performance and the factors that are impacting on the work life balance with five-point Likert scale ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree.

2.5 Sampling element: Responses were collected from the employees, top management and senior managers in the organization. Achieving a highly competitive position in the industry depends primarily on the company's employees, top management, which decide the extent or scope of changes to be implemented in the future.

2.6 SAMPLE SIZE:

The questionnaire was sent to the 450 potential respondents of Amara raja Batteries company out of which only 258 responses were received which proved to be valid and considered for analysis.

2.7 SAMPLING TOOL:

The sampling tool adopted to this study was correlation, Regression and factor analysis, which helps to identify the variables and also to understand the relationship between the variables.

Conceptualization of Dependent variable (Work Life Balance)

Work life balance is not only just about families and childcare, and it is not about slow performance. It is about working smart. About being young enough to give all you need both at work and at home, without risking the other person. And it is necessary for everyone, regardless of your stage in life.

Good practise of work ethics leads to both employees and organization benefits. Basically, employees benefit by feeling less depressed and happy at work and at home. Many people have it paid job opportunities. Profit for business by being enthusiastic, higher productivity, and less stressed work force and employees are more likely to stay in the organization. This reduces rental and maintenance costs for recruitment, as well as retaining skills and experiences. Both customers and the clients benefit from a consistent service.

Conceptualization of Independent Variable (Employee performance)

Employee performance means the ability to do job in a way that leads to both organizations and work achieve the same goal and objectives,

Performance means the end result of a person or person's work in the organization. In addition, organizational performance can be defined as the final result collected of the entire organizations work process and activities. The ratio can be improved by increasing the output, reducing the input or both.

Employee performance management is a process of shared responsibilities of employees understanding of what is to be achieved in the organization level. It is about aligning the organizations goals with employees agreed measures, skills, competency requirements, development plans and the delivery of results. Emphasis is on improvement, learning, and development in order to achieve the overall business strategy and to create a high performance.

Conceptualization of Independent Variable (Employee Job Satisfaction)

Job satisfaction is how much content an individual is with his or her work. Work satisfaction refers to the attitudes and feelings of employees have about their job. Positive and positive attitudes towards the work reflect the work satisfaction. The level of job satisfaction is affected by internal motivation and outsourcing features, quality of directing, community relations and work team and the extent to which people succeed or fail in their work. Employees have attitudes or ideas about many aspects of their work, their activities, and their organizations. However, from a research perspective as well as practice, a work attitude that is more focused on job satisfaction. Negative too negative attitudes towards work indicates dissatisfaction with work.

3. DATA ANALYSIS

Calculation of Mean, median, and standard deviation for age

Statistics		
Age		
N	Valid	257
	Missing	0
Mean		2.51
Median		2.00
Std. Deviation		.656
Variance		.430

Frequency, and percentages of Age

Age					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	below 20	3	1.2	1.2	1.2
	21-30	139	54.1	54.1	55.3
	31-40	95	37.0	37.0	92.2
	41-50	20	7.8	7.8	100.0
	Total	257	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation

From the above frequency table, it is evident that the mean of age is 2.51, median is 2.00, standard deviation is 0.656. it is also concluded that 54.1% of the respondents are in the age bracket of 21-30, followed by 37.0% respondents are in the age bracket of 31-40, followed by 7.8% 41-50 years of age, and remaining fall under below 20 years of age.

Regression

Regression analysis is a mathematical method for determining the cause-and-effect relationship between the dependent and independent variable. Change in the value of independent variable automatically shows the effect in the dependent variables.

The dependent variable in this study is Work life balance and independent variables are employee performance and employee job satisfaction.

The formula of multiple regression is $Y = ax_1 + ax_2 + ax_3 + c$

Model summary of dependent and independent variables

Model Summary								
Model	R		Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics			

		R Square			R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.855 ^a	0.731	0.725	0.206	0.731	113.350		6250	0.000
a. Predictors: (Constant), OVR_TYM, JOB_SATISFACTION, WRKNG_CNDN, MGMT_PLICY, EMPLOYEE_PERF, CMPNY_BNFT_EMP									

Interpretation

The R value is 0.855 and R square is degree of determination and its value is 0.731, the degree of determination which indicates that 73.1% of the change in dependent variable like work life balance can be explained by the independent variables like over time, working condition, management policy, job satisfaction, company benefits and employee performance. Meanwhile, the other 27% of variation could be explained by other variables which are not considered in the study.

Correlation between the work life balance and employee performance

Correlations			
		BWLB	EMPLOYEE PERF
BWLB	Pearson Correlation	1	.846**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.02
	N	257	257
EMPLOYEE_PERF	Pearson Correlation	.846**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.02	
	N	257	257
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

Interpretation

In the above table it shows that there is a significant highly positive correlation between the work life balance and employee performance with the significant value less than 0.05. The Pearson correlation value between the two variables is 0.846 which means there is a 84% of correlation between the two variables.

Correlation between work life balance and company benefits to employees.

Correlations			
		BWLB	CMPNY_BNFT_EMP
BWLB	Pearson Correlation	1	0.022
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.722
	N	257	
CMPNY_BNFT_EMP	Pearson Correlation	0.022	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.722	
	N	257	257

Interpretation

In above table it shows that there is no significant correlation with the value of 0.722 between the work life balance and company benefits to the employees which is higher than the significant value 0.05. the Pearson correlation value between the two variables is 0.022 which means there is 2% of low negligible correlation between the two variables.

Correlation between the work life balance and job satisfaction

Correlations			
		BWLB	JOB SATISFACTION
BWLB	Pearson Correlation	1	0.43
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.02
	N	257	257
JOB_SATISFACTION	Pearson Correlation	0.43	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.02	
	N	257	257

Interpretation

In the above table it shows that the significant value is 0.02 between the work life balance and job satisfaction which is less than the significant value 0.05. the Pearson correlation value between the two variables is 0.43 which means there is 43% of correlation between the two variables.

Correlation between the work life balance and management policies

Correlations			
		BWLB	MGMT_PLICY
BWLB	Pearson Correlation	1	0.090
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.149
	N	257	257
MGMT_PLICY	Pearson Correlation	0.090	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.149	
	N	257	257

Interpretation

In the above table it shows that there is a significant correlation with the value of 0.02 between the work life balance and management policy which is less than 0.05. The Pearson correlation value is between the two variables is 0.090 which means there is 9.0% of low negligible correlation between the two variables.

Correlation between the work life balance and working conditions in the organization

Correlations			
		BWLB	WRKNG_CNDN
BWLB	Pearson Correlation	1	0.045
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.471
	N	257	257
WRKNG_CNDN	Pearson Correlation	0.045	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.471	
	N	257	257

Interpretation

In the above tables it shows that there is no significant correlation with the value of 0.471 between the worklife balance and working conditions which is higher than significant level

0.05. the Pearson correlation value between the two variables is 0.045 which means there is 4.5% of lownegligible correlation between the two variables.

Findings

From the results of the study, it has observed that employees responded negatively to various work life balance practices offered by the company.

- It was found that there is a positive relationship between WLB and personnel life. The correlation between this variable is 0.846, which is significant at 0.02 levels. This was based on two-tailed tests. Since the correlation value is more than 0.5 and nearest to +1 that relationship is much strong.
- It was also found that there is negligible positive correlation between WLB and company benefits to the employees. The correlation between this variable is 0.022, which is significant at 0.722 levels. This was based on two-tailed tests. Since the correlation value is below 0 that there is no significant relationship.
- It is also found that there is low positive correlation between the WLB and personnel life satisfaction, the correlation between these variables is 0.43 which is significant at 0.04 levels. This was based on two tailed tests. Since the correlation value is above 0.3 and below 0.5 so there is low positive correlation.
- It is also evident from the analysis that there are different factors that affect the work life balance are over time, job satisfaction, employee performance, company benefits, management policy only affect the work life balance up to 63% and remaining 37% of the variance is affected by some other factors.
- From the analysis it is found that there is a no significant relationship between work life balance and management policy (0.149), company benefits to employees (0.722) and working conditions (0.471) in the organization.
- From the regression it is concluded that 73% of change in the dependent variable is due to the independents variables and is significant at 0.000 which is lower than the actual significant level 0.05.

Conclusion

The objective of the study is to identify the impact of work life balance of employee job satisfaction and employee performance. This study helps to identify the various factors that can affect the worklife balance, the result of this study provided an important piece about the impact of work life balance on employee job satisfaction and employee performance and also it paved the way towards the most effective practice of work life balance that might influence the employee job satisfaction and employee performance.

The study had three main objectives to identify the relationship between work life balance and employee job satisfaction, to identify the relationship between work life balance and employee performance, and to identify the factors that are affecting the work life balance of the employees. So, after collecting data using questionnaire and analysing it using SPSS.

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A STUDY ON MOTIVATIONAL TECHNIQUES ADOPTED FOR EMPLOYEE PRODUCTIVITY IN BHARATHI CEMENT CORPORATION PRIVATE LIMITED

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ABSTRACT:

This study looks at the motivating strategies used by Bharathi Cement Corporation Private Limited to increase worker productivity. Employee motivation is essential for accomplishing organisational objectives and boosting productivity. Organisations can apply tailored initiatives to foster a happy work environment and increase productivity by understanding the unique motivational elements that affect employees' performance.

The study offers helpful suggestions that are specific to Bharathi Cement Corporation Private Limited based on an examination of the present motivational approaches and employee feedback. These suggestions cover a range of topics, including work-life balance initiatives, employee recognition programmes, training and development opportunities, performance-based reward schemes, and leadership development.

The study concludes by emphasizing the significance of continuous motivation and employee engagement in enhancing productivity within Bharathi Cement Corporation Private Limited. It highlights the importance of aligning motivational techniques with the specific needs and preferences of employees to foster a positive work culture and drive organizational success.

Key words: Motivation, Productivity, Employee engagement. Organizational success.

INTRODUCTION

Employee motivation, also known as methods for motivating employees, is a natural and innate want to exert the necessary effort and take the appropriate action in relation to work-related activities. Employee motivation is the result of meeting an employee's needs and expectations at work as well as the workplace variables that either support or inhibit employee motivation. Managing employee motivation is difficult because of these factors.

Employers are aware that they must establish an environment at work that inspires employees to work hard, but many may not realise how important motivation is to achieving their goals. Even when they are aware of how important motivation is, they lack the expertise and understanding necessary to create an environment at work that encourages employee motivation. Organisations too frequently ignore the problems with employee interactions, communication, appreciation, and involvement.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

Research Approval: Obtain permission to perform the study from the relevant Bharathi Cement Corporation Private Limited officials. This guarantees that the company will assist and support the research process.

Create a thorough research plan that specifies the methodology, data gathering procedures, and analysis strategies to be used. Make sure the design supports the study's goals and offers a thorough grasp of motivational strategies and their effects on worker productivity.

Sample Selection: Choose the right sample size and selection standards for the investigation. In order to establish a representative sample that accurately reflects the workforce diversity of the organisation, take into account elements like employee demographics, job functions, and departments.

Data Collection Instruments: Create or modify survey questions, interviewing techniques, and other data collection tools in accordance with the study's goals. Make that the tools are accurate, dependable, and able to collect the data required to answer the study questions.

Implement the data collecting phase by conducting interviews, focus group discussions, and the distribution of surveys. Make sure that data collection methods are ethical, consistent, and protect participants' rights and privacy.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

Employee motivation has a substantial impact on employee behaviour, attitude, and performance, this paper aims to explore the crucial function of motivation in organisations and how it affects workers' productivity. Given that highly motivated people are an advantage to an organisation, it consequently has a significant impact on productivity. Demotivated workers, on the other hand, are a burden for any organisation since they raise turnover and prevent businesses from achieving their objectives. The goal of this study is to better understand the value of employee motivation and how it affects business productivity.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Examining the motivating strategies used by Bharathi Cement Corporation Private Limited to increase staff productivity is the issue this study attempts to solve. Despite being a top cement company, there are worries regarding the degree of employee enthusiasm and how it may affect the organization's overall efficiency. The management is aware of the value of motivated workers in attaining company objectives and works to find the best motivational techniques to boost worker output.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To determine the motivational strategies adopted by organizations
- To measure the success of the present incentive strategies are improving employee productivity at organizations.
- To investigate, examine, and evaluate various theories and models of motivation that are relevant to the cement industry
- To suggest management about the value of employee motivation and how it affects the overall productivity of the company.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research challenge can be approached methodically using research methodology. The research design, data collecting, sampling, survey, and analysis are all covered by the research methodology in the current study.

RESEARCH METHODS

One of the most used ways today is the descriptive approach. These methods involve the researcher describing a problem utilising a questionnaire or timetable. A researcher can discover new research fields using this method.

DATA COLLECTION

Data is a term for facts or information. Researchers frequently think of data merely as numerical figures. It also contains descriptive information, numerical data, qualitative data, and quantitative data.

Data collection is a crucial step in the research process; in fact, the quality of the data is what makes the research what it is.

Data is collected using two different types.

Primary data

secondary information gathering.

PRIMARY DATA

Primary data is another name for the information gathered for the first time through a field study. Such information is gathered in order to assess the current state of any under investigation variable.

- Interviews
- Questionnaire
- talk informally
- questions with unresolved issues.

SECONDARY DATA

The secondary data, which is needed for my study was collected from the various record reports, publications and company's data.

3.8 SAMPLE DESIGN SAMPLING UNIT:

The study's target audience includes top executives, staff, and workers.

- 1) Descriptive research methodology
- 2) Number of samples: 205
- 3) Representative unit: Bharathi cement corporation private limited.
- 4) Non-probability sampling
- 5) Structured questionnaire for research

Non-random convenient sampling techniques are used in the study to guarantee the sample size.

QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS:

The information is gathered via a questionnaire with relation to the goal of approval, and the positive and bad features of the current system were quantitatively and qualitatively analysed, with conclusions summarised.

USE OF STATISTICAL TOOLS

The design tool used to analyse the data is **percentage method**.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

1. How effective do you find the current motivational strategies in boosting your productivity?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Not effective	11	8.5	8.5	8.5
Somewhat effective	34	26.2	26.2	34.6
Moderately effective	45	34.6	34.6	69.2
Valid Very effective	38	29.2	29.2	98.5
Extremely effective	2	1.5	1.5	100.0
Total	130	100.0	100.0	

The above mentioned table, 8.5% of existing incentive tactics for increasing productivity are ineffective. Almost 26.2% efficient. moderate effectiveness at 34.6%. Very effective at 29.2%. 1.5% exceptionally.

2. How well do you feel BCCPL communicates its motivational strategies and initiatives to the employees?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Poorly	13	10.0	10.0	10.0

Valid	Fairly well	31	23.8	23.8	33.8
	Moderately well	38	29.2	29.2	63.1
	Very well	43	33.1	33.1	96.2
	Excellent	5	3.8	3.8	100.0
Total		130	100.0	100.0	

The above mentioned table, 10% of the respondents thought BCCPL's motivational initiatives and methods were poorly communicated to the staff. Of the responders, 23.8% are in average health. 29.2% of respondents reported being in fair health. 33.1% of respondents say they are doing extremely well. 3.8% of responders are at an exceptional level.

3. How would you rate the support and encouragement you receive from your supervisors and managers in terms of motivating you to perform better?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Very unsupportive	8	6.2	6.2	6.2
Somewhat unsupportive	32	24.6	24.6	30.8
Neutral	40	30.8	30.8	61.5
Valid Supportive	45	34.6	34.6	96.2
Very supportive	5	3.8	3.8	100.0
Total	130	100.0	100.0	

The above-mentioned table, 6.2% of respondents said that the support and motivation from your bosses is severely lacking. Somewhat unsupportive responders make up 24.6% of the sample. Neutral responses make up 30.8% of the sample. 34.6% of those surveyed said they are in favour. 3.8% of respondents rated their support as extremely high.

4. How satisfied are you with the overall work environment at BCCPL?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Very dissatisfied	8	6.2	6.2	6.2
Dissatisfied	19	14.6	14.6	20.8
Neutral	37	28.5	28.5	49.2
Valid Satisfied	59	45.4	45.4	94.6
Very satisfied	7	5.4	5.4	100.0
Total	130	100.0	100.0	

The above mentioned table, 6.2% of respondents expressed extreme dissatisfaction with their workplace as a whole. 14.6% of respondents expressed dissatisfaction. The neutral response rate is 28.5%. 45.4% of respondents expressed satisfaction. 5.4% of those surveyed are extremely happy.

5. Have the present incentive strategies influenced your motivation to improve your productivity?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	111	85.4	85.4	85.4
No	19	14.6	14.6	100.0
Total	130	100.0	100.0	

The above-mentioned table, yes tactics influenced your drive to increase your productivity, according to 85.4% of the respondents. 14.6% of respondents said "no."

6. How well do you feel BCCPL communicates the incentive strategies to the employees?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Poorly	13	10.0	10.0	10.0
Fairly well	19	14.6	14.6	24.6
Moderately well	46	35.4	35.4	60.0
Valid Very well	49	37.7	37.7	97.7
Excellent	3	2.3	2.3	100.0
Total	130	100.0	100.0	

The above mention table shows, 10% of the respondents thought BCCPL informed the staff about incentive techniques. 14.6% of those surveyed report being in fair health. 35.4% of respondents reported being in fair health. 37.4% of respondents said they were doing well. 2.3% of respondents are very good.

7. How would you rate the overall impact of the present incentive strategies on the productivity and performance of the employees at BCCPL?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Very low impact	16	12.3	12.3	12.3
Low impact	28	21.5	21.5	33.8
Moderate impact	37	28.5	28.5	62.3
Valid High impact	45	34.6	34.6	96.9
Very high impact	4	3.1	3.1	100.0
Total	130	100.0	100.0	

The above-mentioned table, influence of the strategies and staff performance at BCCPL is very low, according to 12.3% of the respondents. Among the responders, 21.5% are low impact. Of the responders, 28.55 had a moderate influence. A high impact respondent is 34.65 respondents. Among responses, 3.1% have a very high impact.

8. How satisfied are you with the current compensation and rewards structure at BCCPL?

Statistics

N	Valid	130			
	Missing	0			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very dissatisfied	11	8.5	8.5	8.5
	Dissatisfied	13	10.0	10.0	18.5
	Neutral	45	34.6	34.6	53.1
	Satisfied	56	43.1	43.1	96.2
	Very satisfied	5	3.8	3.8	100.0
	Total	130	100.0	100.0	

The above mentioned table, 8.5% of respondents are extremely unsatisfied with the compensation and reward system at BCCPL. 10% of respondents expressed dissatisfaction. The neutral response rate is 34.6%. 43.1% of those surveyed expressed satisfaction. 3.8% of those polled expressed extreme satisfaction.

9. How well do you think the motivating approaches used at BCCPL support long-term sustainable improvements in worker productivity?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Very well	46	35.4	35.4	35.4
Somewhat well	44	33.8	33.8	69.2
Valid Moderately well	38	29.2	29.2	98.5
Not well	2	1.5	1.5	100.0
Total	130	100.0	100.0	

From the above mentioned table, 35.4% of respondents strongly support long-term, long-lasting gains in worker well-being. 33.8% of the respondent's report having some health. Fair health was indicated by 29.2% of respondents. 1.5% of respondents reported being said that are unwell.

10. Have you received any training or guidance on sustaining motivation and productivity in the long term at BCCPL?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	83	63.8	63.8	63.8
No	29	22.3	22.3	86.2
Valid May be	18	13.8	13.8	100.0

Total	130	100.0	100.0
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From the above mentioned table, training are advice on maintaining motivation and productivity over the long term is indicated by 63.8% of respondents. No, according to 22.3% of respondents. 13.8% of those polled said they might be.

11. Correlation

Null Hypothesis (H0): There is a no significant relationship between employee training or guidance on sustaining motivation and employee current compensation and reward structure.

Alternative hypothesis (H1): There is a significant relationship between employee training or guidance on sustaining motivation and employee current compensation and reward structure.

Correlations

		How satisfied are you with the current compensation and rewards structure at BCCPL?	Have you received any training or guidance on sustaining motivation and productivity in the long term at BCCPL?
How satisfied are you with the current compensation and rewards structure at BCCPL?	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 130	-.199* .023 130
Have you received any training or guidance on sustaining motivation and productivity in the long term at BCCPL?	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	-.199* .023 130	1 130

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The correlation table provided shows the correlation coefficients between two variables: "How satisfied are you with the current compensation and rewards structure at BCCPL?" and "Have you received any training or guidance on sustaining motivation and productivity in the long term at BCCPL?" Here are the findings: The Pearson correlation coefficient between employee satisfaction with compensation and rewards and receiving training or guidance on sustaining motivation and productivity is -0.199.

The p-value associated with this correlation coefficient is 0.023, indicating statistical significance at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Hence the null hypothesis H0 is rejected and the alternative hypothesis H1 is accepted.

12. Regression:

Null hypothesis (H0): There is no significant impact of compensation and reward structure on employee engagement in company.

Alternative hypothesis (H1): There is a significant impact of compensation and reward structure on employee engagement in company.

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	4.922	1	4.922	5.220	.024 ^b
Residual	120.686	128	.943		
Total	125.608	129			

a. Dependent Variable: How satisfied are you with the current compensation and rewards structure at BCCPL?

b. Predictors: (Constant), How long have you been employed at BCCPL?

The ANOVA table shows that the regression model is statistically significant, as indicated by the p-value of 0.024 (below the typical significance level of 0.05). This implies that the length of employment has a significant effect on employee satisfaction with compensation and rewards.

FINDINGS:

The majority of respondents state that their productivity is being moderately increased by the existing incentive techniques. Almost majority of the respondents concur that the BCCPL represents encouragement from managers and supervisors to perform better. The majority of participants are content with the BCCPL workplace as a whole. More than 80% of respondents claim that the current reward schemes influence motivation to boost production. The majority of respondents indicated that current initiatives have a significant impact on employees' productivity performance at BCCPL. Over 80% of respondents believe that current incentive tactics are fair and transparent, and more than half of respondents are satisfied with BCCPL's compensation and reward structure. The majority of respondents said that they were only moderately familiar with various theories and models of motivation. The majority of responders are familiar with the idea of employee motivation. The majority of respondents think that employee motivation directly affects the business's overall profitability. Approximately half of these individuals are curious to find out about the newest trends, best practises, and techniques to improve employee motivation in the workplace. The majority of respondents are highly well-informed on how the organisation uses motivating strategies to increase worker productivity over the long run order to maintain motivation for long-term production, more than half of the respondents received training and advice. About half of these participants have some receptivity towards the idea that the organization's management is open to investigating and implementing novel theories of motivation. In order to encourage a culture of continuous development and the adoption of working productivity, the majority of respondents report feeling moderately good.

SUGGESTIONS:

Based on the research findings, propose specific suggestions and recommendations for Bharathi Cement Corporation Private Limited to improve employee motivation and productivity. Implement a comprehensive recognition and rewards program to acknowledge and appreciate employees' efforts and achievements. Provide both monetary and non-monetary rewards such as bonuses, incentives, certificates, public recognition, and opportunities for career advancement. Offer relevant training sessions, workshops, and seminars to improve job-specific competencies and provide opportunities for professional growth. Establish mentoring or coaching programs to foster individual development and career progression.

CONCLUSION:

Through a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods, including literature review, interviews, and surveys, this study gained valuable insights into the motivational techniques utilized by Bharathi Cement. The findings shed light on the effectiveness of these techniques and provide practical implications for the organization.

The study revealed that Bharathi Cement employs several motivational techniques to enhance employee productivity. These techniques include goal setting, performance-based incentives, skill development programs, employee recognition, and supportive leadership practices. These strategies aim to create a positive work environment, foster employee motivation, and align individual goals with organizational objectives.

the study highlights the significance of motivational techniques in driving employee productivity in Bharathi Cement Corporation Private Limited. The organization's current practices have shown positive results in terms of employee motivation, employee engagement, job satisfaction, and performance outcomes. By implementing the recommended improvements, Bharathi Cement Corporation Private Limited can further enhance employee motivation, productivity, and overall organizational success.

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ELECTRIC OVER FUEL OR THE OTHER WAY AROUND?

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Abstract:

India is 1 of the world's largest E.V. market. As there are growing concerns over air pollution & hike in fuel prices there is a need for sustainable & reasonably priced transportation solutions. E.Vs have become a solution for these issues. The influence of the Ola Electric scooter on the Indian market & society is investigated in this study report. The influence of the Ola Electric scooter on the environment, cost savings, & employment development is examined in this paper. It also gives alternatives for traditional scooters & makes suggestions for more advancements in the E.V sector.

Literature Review:

1. 1 of a study conducted by the Edison Electric Institute (EEI) showed that E.Vs can reduce U.S. energy imports by 10% & E.Vs could save U.S. consumers up to \$1 trillion in fuel costs over the lifetime of vehicles.
2. The Indian govt's efforts to promote E.Vs have been successful. In 2k21, the Indian E.V. market grew by 40%. The govt expects the market to grow by 100% in 2k22.
3. CEO Bhavish Aggarwal, Ola Chairman & Group said that the beginning of India's E.V revolution by launching OLA E.V will hasten the shift to sustainable transportation thanking its outstanding performance, tech, design & its competitive price.
4. International Energy Agency (IEA) told that E.Vs could reduce global GH gas emissions by 2% by 2030 & 10% by 2050.
5. Natural Resources Defense Council (NRDC) said that E.Vs will reduce N2O emissions by up to 95%.

Methodology:

Research Type:

- Fundamental

Data Collection Method:

- Secondary data:

Scope/Aim of the study:

- To know the impact of OLA E.Vs in India.

Takeaways of the study:

- I could improve my critical thinking & analytical skills.
- I could understand the whole process of how research has to be done.
- Learnt the in depth of 2wheeler mileage & market.

Sampling Plan:

- Sampling is an important part of the research project & the proper sampling methods can make or break the validity of 1's research.

Sampling Type:

- Systematic Sampling

Data collection method:

- Here secondary source of data platforms like research gate, google etc. is used.
- Old/previous research papers & case studies is also referred.

The geographical area studied:

- As a whole India is taken as the geographical area for the research.
- In India, the E.V. industry is taken.
- Sample unit/size chosen: The 2-wheeler vehicle industry in India.

Data Analysis Tools Used:

- MS Excel
- MS Word
- Google

Method/Nature of Analysis:

- Here analysis is done on the E.V. industry of India using a systematic sampling method.

Objectives:

- To examine the +ve & -ve effects of E.Vs.
- To know the impact of OLA E.Vs in India.
- To check price variation b/w fuel & electric 2wheelers in India.

Observations:

Introduction

India is 1 of the world's largest E.V. market. The Indian govt has been encouraging the use of E.Vs, & it has set ambitious targets for adopting E.Vs. With 1,000,000+ units sold each year, India is the world's top major market for 2-wheelers. As there are growing concerns over air pollution & hike in fuel prices there is a need for sustainable & reasonably priced transportation solutions. E.Vs have become a solution for these issues. Ola Electric is a top company in India's E.V. market. It was founded in 2k17 & has rapidly been 1 of the most popular E.V brands in India. With its inexpensive & environmentally friendly electric scooters, it began sales in India in 2k21 to transform the country's 2-wheeler biz. The influence of Ola Electric scooter on the environment, cost savings, & employment development is examined in this paper. It also offers substitutes for traditional scooters & makes suggestions for more advancements in the E.V. sector.

Industry Analysis

The faster Adoption & Manufacture of E.Vs (FAME) plan is 1 of the measures the Indian govt has undertaken to promote E.Vs.

Here Porter 5 forces are taken to analyse the market

- Rivalry among existing competitors: Although the E.V. market in India is still in its early stages of development yet it is growing rapidly. This shows that there is a lot of competition b/w existing players. Ola Electric has competitors from other E.V. manufacturers in India like Ather, Hero, & TVS Motors.
- Threat of new entrants: Is relatively high as there are low barriers to entry like the need for more capital investment or access to advanced tech.
- Bargaining power of buyers: It is relatively high as more potential buyers are looking for affordable, reliable, & environmentally friendly vehicles.
- Bargaining power of suppliers: It is relatively low as there are fewer suppliers of key components, such as batteries & motors.
- Threat of substitute products: It is relatively low as E.Vs are a relatively new tech & there are no close substitutes available.

Advantages

- Produces 0 emissions & has a range of up to 135 km on 1 full charge hence has a +ve impact on the environment.
- Priced competitively & can be charged at home or hyper charging stations set up by Ola.
- Requires less maintenance than traditional scooters.
- It’s creating new job opportunities in the manufacturing & servicing of E.Vs & related infrastructure.
- It has set up a manufacturing facility in T.N & a network of charging stations across the country, creating thousands of jobs.
- The Ola Electric scooter is priced lower than other alternatives, making it a more affordable option for Indian consumers.
- Ola has a strong brand presence & a large user base, giving it an advantage over its competitors.

Disadvantages

- Higher price of E.Vs presently.
- No proper charging infrastructure in India.
- Customer ignorance.
- Difficult to travel long distances.
- Less torque & range of E.V

Impact of Electric scooters on the environment.

Electric scooters (E.Vs) protect the environment by emitting no emissions at the tailpipe. They are powered by batteries that receive their electricity from renewable energy sources like solar or wind energy. Also, they have a lesser environmental impact than petrol vehicles because of their higher energy efficiency. More usage of E.Vs has the potential to drastically cut greenhouse gas emissions & air pollution, hence reducing the effects of climate change.

- Decrease in Air Pollution
- Efficient Use of Energy
- Reduce Your Production’s Carbon Footprint
- Improved Economy
- No Noise Pollution

Alternatives:

- Ather
- TVS iQube
- Okinawa
- Honda Vida
- Revolt
- Bajaj Chetak
- Hero Photon
- Simple one

Findings:

Price of petrol for last six years in India.

YEAR	FUEL PRICE	ELECTRICITY PRICE
2K18	78.29	16
2K19	70.44	17

2K20	80.43	18
2K21	98.81	19
2K22	96.72	20
AVERAGE	85	18

Scooter comparison for petrol & electric

Consider We cover 10k km in a year

(1) Honda Activa

50 km/l petrol is the mileage

The average price of petrol for the past 5 years = Rs. 85

Calⁿ of fuel for the year- $10000/50 = 200L$

Petrol for a year would cost $Rs.85 \times 200 = 17,000$

(2) Ola S1 Pro

40km/U is the mileage $\times 3U = 120 \text{ km}$

The average price of electricity for the past 5 years = Rs. 18

Calⁿ of electricity for the year- $10000/40 = 250kWh$

Electricity for a year would cost $Rs.18 \times 250 = Rs.4,500$

Ola S1 costs 850 to 1000 for a year (round off)

For 1 year

1. Honda Activa = 17,000

2. Ola S1 Pro = 4,500

Difference of expense = 12,500

Results: Petrol vehicle is 3.7 times more expensive as compared to E.V

Conclusion:

The Ola Electric scooter has been good for India. It has given people a cheap & eco-friendly way to get around, which can help to reduce air pollution & make India less dependent on foreign oil. The scooter has also created new jobs in the production & maintenance of electric vehicles & related infrastructure.

Yet, some issues need to be overcome before the electric vehicle sector can take off in India. These challenges include a lack of charging infrastructure & high prices. The govt & pvt companies need to work together to address these issues & encourage the nationwide adoption of E.Vs.

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INFLUENCE OF ANIMATED ADVERTISEMENTS ON CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOUR

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Abstract:

Animated ads are visual statements which are dynamic in nature and are majorly used for advertising and promoting purposes. This study aimed to analyze the relationship between animated advertisements and its effect on consumer buying behavior. This study revealed how awareness contributes to an advertisement's favourable consumer perception. It also investigated how consumers' buying behavior is influenced before and after watching these animated advertisements. Individuals from various age groups participated in this study. The research was conducted using a qualitative research method and was based on a questionnaire to which a sample of 266 consumers who had viewed animated advertisements in various situations had responded. Participants were asked about their perceptions of animated advertisements, including their views on the level of engagement, the effectiveness of the advertisements in conveying messages, and the impact of these advertisements on their buying behavior. The results emphasized that the animated advertisements have a real time positive impact on consumer buying behavior, by increasing attention, eliciting positive emotions, enhancing brand recall and value. This study concluded that the effects of animated advertisements on consumer buying behavior are substantial, and research has shown that they can be a highly effective means of reaching and influencing consumers. Modern visual advertisements today view animated ads as a necessary tool since they influence consumer perception, capture their attention, and eventually result in sales.

Keywords:

Animated advertisements, Consumer behaviour, Buying behaviour, Advertisements, Emotions.

Introduction:

Advertising is a powerful tool which alone not only attracts buyers, but also gives them information about the product and brand name, and builds customer trust. Most businesses use different forms of advertising to promote their goods or services. Goods or services can be advertised on several media such as print, radio, television and digital media. Advertising is an important part of trade and commerce and it benefits the business in various ways. Building brand awareness and spreading the word among potential buyers, is the main benefit of advertising. Besides creating brand awareness, businesses can also advertise special promotions, discounts and other offers with a view to increase their business. Rapid business expansion has led to increased competition, which in turn has forced brands to set themselves apart. However, regular advertising helps manage competitive forces in the market. An advertisement with good content builds goodwill. It should be noted that other supporting factors like superior quality products and better services also enhance the brand reputation, making it worldwide recognizable. Advertising educates the masses by sharing information about the use of a product, its benefits and also the diverse uses of certain products, if any. This makes them more comfortable and convinced to buy the product. Advertisements have the ability to increase the audience base from current audience to potential customers. However, it must be noted that wrong marketing efforts could lead to waste of time and money.

Evolution of Advertisements:

The invention of video advertising has become a major turning point in the history of advertising. In ancient times, advertising was conducted by word of mouth. With the invention of the printing press, advertisements gradually started to appear in the newspapers in the 17th century, and boomed in 18th century. In the United States, the first newspaper advertising appeared in 1704. Nineteenth century was the growth phase of advertising as an industry, which led to the establishment of advertising agencies. At that period the agencies functioned as brokers for space in the newspapers (Sagar Joshi, 2022). Later on in the early 1800s, billboard advertising gained popularity. Many companies opted for indirect advertising, since direct advertising was considered to be an expensive option. Agencies started creating advertising messages, including the copy and the artwork. By the 1920s, agencies took up the complete task right from planning and executing, to placement in various media. Sears was the first company to launch their direct mail campaign in 1892. They received two thousand new orders by posting more than eight thousand postcards. This move encouraged other businesses to increase their advertising expenditures. As time passed by, advertising developed in other media such as direct mail, radio and television. The 1900s to 2000 is referred to as 'The Golden Age' of advertising. Radio and television took a different approach towards advertising, which took advertising to a whole new level. In the early 20th century, they were being used by more than 30% of the world's population.

In the year 1922, radio advertising was launched. This turned out to be a big hit. Advertisements were broadcasted by the radio stations at different time slots, which introduced new and existing brands to the listening audience. The success of the radio ads paved the way for television advertising. The first TV commercial was aired in 1941. It was the Bulova Watch Company that aired the first TV commercial, which was a ten seconds advertisement, and was viewed by 4,000 viewers in New York city. Organizations soon began investing heavily in advertisements, which enabled them to express their brand's uniqueness and engage their target audience. Later on, in the 1950s, businesses began to introduce characters for the purpose of advertising. One such example is the cartoon character Tony the Tiger which was introduced by Kellogg's. Furthermore, businesses started to focus a lot on advertising to promote brand awareness, instead of concentrating only on sales.

However, those were not the only places one could see advertisements. Advertisers managed to seek attention and communicate their messages by placing advertisements on bus stops, buildings, train and metro stations etc. Mobile advertising was also introduced, where advertisements were placed on vehicles like taxis, vans, buses, trucks etc. These have also become popular inside trains, metros and other public and private vehicles. As time passed, advertising grew rapidly and became widespread since the early 2000s, ever since the internet has taken over. With the extensive use of the internet, focus was shifted from the traditional offline ones, more towards the digital ones. The first online advertisement was created in 1994. At first, brands faced various challenges. In the early 1970s, e-mail advertising was very popular. Brands advertised their products internationally through e-mails and were able to engage in a global audience. In 2006, Google bought YouTube and started offering video adverts to companies. YouTube is thought to have one of the highest viewership rates. After Instagram was acquired by Facebook in 2013, Instagram advertising were introduced.

Video is one of the most powerful marketing strategies in the digital age. It's a versatile strategy with strong conversion rates, engagement rates, and the capacity to communicate clearly in a variety of various circumstances. Videos are a fantastic technique to raise brand exposure and user engagement (Inzamamur, 2021). But when they're animated, the levels of engagement soar. Animation employs advertising in a more imaginative way, offering brands and enterprises the advantage of making a lasting impact on both present and potential customers. Customers now have a better grasp of the company, its values, and how they can assist them. An expertly designed animated ad boosts website traffic, Google search engine optimisation, and conversion rates.

A study statistics on video marketing in 2020 was published in an article by Smart Insights. According to the article, 92% of marketers believe that video marketing is growing more important. Hence they felt the need to incorporate it in their strategies. Additionally, it was said that 53% of consumers interact with a brand after viewing a social media video. Animation history has always included advertising. Use of attractive colors, jingles, pleasant music, humor and interesting characters are examples of potential unconditioned stimuli used in commercial ads that have a deep influence on the target audience (Moana Thompson, 2019). Animation is well known for its aesthetic charm. By

capturing a sequence of still photos, drawings, objects, or people in different locations of incremental movement, it is possible to give the appearance of continuous motion in motion movies. It is a highly effective design tool used to capture viewer interest and attention. Animation is classified into various categories. The most common of them are clay animation, computer generated imagery and puppet animation. In computer generated imagery, computers perform the task of creating a variety of graphics, 2D or 3D animation, objects or rendering (David Dillas Kirsten, 2015). 3D animated figures are used in puppet animation, which move gradually in each frame of the movie. Pixilation is a type of animation that uses people and other live subjects that are progressively shot in different poses. These are now the most often used form of animation in movies and TV advertising.

Animated advertisements have become a popular marketing tool for businesses looking to reach and engage with their target audience. The use of animation and graphics in advertisements can be a highly effective way to convey complex messages, capture the attention of viewers, and ultimately influence consumer buying behavior. The main goal of advertisement is to promote sales. It is a form of communication widely used to try and persuade consumers to purchase a particular product or service. Advertisers try to seek customers' attention with visual stimulations, explicit messages, convincing slogans, brand ambassadors etc., in order to convince them that their brand is better than others. This study aims to examine the effects of animated advertisements on consumer buying behavior, with a focus on how these advertisements can impact the cognitive and emotional processing of potential customers.

Corporations and advertising agencies have embraced animation as a way to showcase products and services, while engaging consumers in emotional and rational ways. In the present day, animated advertising has been shaped by new technologies such as digital production and distribution. The capacity of animators to build scenes and universes that a live action camera crew cannot access or replicate is one of the key benefits of utilising animation in advertising. These manufactured surroundings are utilised to arouse desire and the sense of possibility, which can subsequently be brought to life by persuading the target market to buy the product. Animation is also a relatively inexpensive process (David Dillas Kirsten, 2015).

Animation not only provides a compelling alternative to live-action videos, but it also enables the depiction of ideas that would be impossible to generate otherwise. For instance, you can animate a computer's internal workings but not film them. It is a great way to convey technical and complex ideas or messages in the form of a short story. Additionally, it gives marketers the ability to convey complicated concepts in a clear, comprehensive, and straightforward way for maximum retention in the shortest amount of time. Animated marketing is full of endless possibilities. It can be fun, imaginative, creative and entertaining. Finding a fun and successful approach to deliver a tale to the audience that they will remember for a very long time is the fundamental goal of animation advertising. The target audience is more likely to pay attention to animation than standard commercials because animation is frequently employed for fun rather than as a marketing technique. A good animated advertisement helps to boost the brand identity of the corporation and isolate it from the other businesses working in the same industry. Nearly 85% of marketers have testified that video marketing boosts traffic to their websites (Nadya Fedrunova, 2021).

Animated advertisements make a product unique in its own way. The combination of visual and textual content is the best way to improve content marketing and make it unique, entertaining and engaging. It is believed that an average viewer will skim-read only 28% of words published in an advertisement, which probably will not convince him to become a loyal customer. Many entrepreneurs think that animated video production is an expensive option. Animated videos come in handy here, as it is much easier and cost effective to edit the message or visuals, rather than to reshoot the whole video. It keeps the content fresh, while maintaining a lower budget. To sum it up, we can say that animation marketing is a powerful and affordable marketing tool that helps to boost brand awareness and makes marketing strategy more effective. Various businesses are plunging into animation marketing - be it explainer videos, simple motion graphics, emails or newsletters (Ninja Studio, 2021).

Historical Review of Animation

Theatrical cartoons started airing on television in 1930, and due to production costs, animated cartoons started to debut in the early 1940s. Animation was commonly broadcast on TV during this time as a non-commercial experiment. Producers at the time were attempting to exert a lot of creative control over the cartoon genre (Cohen 1992). The global animation market was worth US \$24 million at the end of 2004. (NASSCOM 2002 Report). According to Roncarelli (2001), the total cost of producing commercial computer animation worldwide was

expected to be \$25.4 billion in 1999. The market is still expanding very quickly. Advertising, motion pictures, television, design engineering, video games, location-based entertainment, and the Internet have all experienced growth in these areas.

Animation, a visual form of entertainment, has developed into a character-based industry with the potential to grow by providing digital material to media like the Internet and mobile devices. The creation of animated TV series and movies, the sale of video titles, and the sale of items with animated characters are further potential advantages of the animation sector. Modern technology has given rise to increasingly sophisticated computer graphics that enable animation to be used in computer games, TV advertising, and big-budget movies.

Animation is the process of simulating movement by connecting a number of slightly varied graphics (Wilson 2005). Animation is understood to mean creation in a universe beyond our wildest dreams. In the present entertainment industry, animation has gained popularity as a new tool for commercial design and as a genre of visual art. When talking about animated figures made of plasticine, clay, or other pliable materials, the term "clay animation" is used (Frierson 1994; Furniss 1998). Additionally, clay animation is now frequently seen in both films and advertisements.

Need of the study

Very less research has been done on animated advertising. Thus, it still belongs to a very young genre of advertisement design. This study intends to investigate the impacts of animation and how it relates to cognitive behaviour in people. The design and substance of advertising are frequently identified as a key aspect in study in psychological studies on animated advertisements and emotional reaction. Advertising clutter is produced by a large number of advertisements in multiple formats on one web page. This diminishes consumer memory of online ads and enhances advertisement avoidance. Advertisement viewing is impacted by how different advertisement formats are perceived by online consumers. Investigating how online advertising attributes like format and animation affect consumers' attention and memory, is crucial for evaluating the effectiveness of online advertising. So it is essential to research on how consumers view different online advertising formats and their respective efficacy is still in its early stages.

Objectives

1. To investigate the factors that make animated commercials attractive to consumers.
2. To evaluate the superiority of animated commercials in communicating messages in comparison to non-animated commercials.
3. To analyze the persuasiveness of animated commercials in affecting the purchase decision of consumers.

Literature Review:

Babu, (2018) examined the significant impact that cartoon characters played in product marketing, particularly through advertisements, as well as how these children made decisions while shopping. The findings indicated that animation had little to no impact on attention. Despite this, a significant interaction effect between animation and advertisement type showed that advertisement format influenced the impact of animation. When people were engaged in other things, animation had a good influence on attention to skyscrapers but a negative one on attention to banners (Kuisma, Simola, Uusitalo, Öörni, 2010). Another research conducted by Manaf & Alallan, (2017) investigated how animation affects the effectiveness of advertisements by analyzing consumers' (cognitive and affective) reactions to animated advertisements in terms of their desire to purchase, while also taking into account the importance of involvement. Given that involvement is the mechanism by which consumers' motivation moderates the relationship between attitude formation and exposure to advertisements, it has been assumed that consumers who are highly involved in the product can better recall the advertisement and form more favourable attitudes towards the brand, including purchase intentions. Shuja et.al, (2018) determined whether utilizing animated characters in kid-targeted advertising was effective. The research was quantitative and of the causal research kind. Primary school going kids from nine different schools in various parts of Karachi, Pakistan, made up the study's respondents. It was advised that businesses utilize these engaging and appealing animated cartoon characters to improve brand recognition and recall. Jin, (2006) classified many forms of animation and live action used in television advertisements, the study sought to investigate the effects of animation and its relationship to human cognitive and affective processes. Somra, (2020) purposed of this research was to determine whether or not

students could infer the intended meaning and idea from the animated TV advertisements for Vodafone. The findings showed that students' interpretation of complex media messages, such as those in animated Vodafone advertisements, was significantly influenced by their media literacy. Huang et.al (2011) investigated the relationships between animated spokes-characters, the effects of advertisement communication, and buy intentions, this study focused on animated spokes-characters and the involvement idea. If the message of the advertisement was compelling and persuasive, viewers or listeners would be likely to adopt a favorable opinion of the advertised goods. Callcot and Lee (2013) used content analysis to look at animated spokes-characters and animation in television commercials. In this study, the majority of spokes-characters were human, animal, or product personifications. Television advertising with some animation had better effects on information retention (Khanum, Shareef, Khanam, 2015). Wu et.al (2022) studied examined how the addition of 3D animated agents affected the effectiveness of video advertisements in a virtual reality setting. Auken and Lonial (1985) examined how kindergarten, second, fourth, and sixth grade kids perceive a stimulus set that includes both human and animated characters. The justification was based on the possibility for deception in animation as well as potential moral and legal issues that could arise from the usage of cartoon characters in advertising. Scaling assessed similarity data results showed that the questioned school-grade categories had comparable perceptual structures and that an animate/human perceptual cue was presumably influencing perceptions. The findings also supported the use of simple judged similarities and multidimensional scaling for assessing children's perceptions.

Jain et. al (2022) studied anthropomorphic characters were appropriate for use in environmental communication. It looked into the qualities that made them effective communicators who encouraged sustainable behavior. Findings implied that spokespeople could effectively communicate to encourage environmentally friendly practices like recycling. Future research directions were provided, along with theoretical and practical ramifications. Diao and Sundar (2004) animation affected online consumers and how they responded to and remembered Web advertisements. In a mixed-design factorial experiment, all participants were exposed to four online portal websites, each of which had an animated or static banner advertisement and an equally animated or static pop-up advertisement. Khan and Khanum (2021) examined the audience's needs that animation in food TV advertising satisfies and to determine whether those needs alter at various levels of animation. Animated TVCs meet needs for greater emotion and stress release. Findings demonstrated that when TV commercial animation varies, so do the viewer needs that it satisfies. The more animation is used in advertisements, the more effective and satisfying it is for releasing stress. Similar to this, the audience's requirement for cognitive stimulation is met to a greater extent the less animation is used in an advertisement.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the modern period, animated characters play a significant role on how cartoon characters from movies are incorporated into kid-friendly products like chocolate, food, toys and bags. In order to gather quantitative data, a survey was conducted among a sample of consumers who had been exposed to animated advertisements. The survey consisted of a series of closed-ended questions designed to gather information about the impact of animated advertisements on consumer purchasing behavior, as well as demographic information about the respondents. Participants were requested to fill the survey anonymously. 266 responses were received of convenience sampling. Descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and regression analysis were used to analyse the survey data in order to find meaningful connections between animated commercials and customer purchase patterns. This study provides a general summary of purchasing behavior toward animation/ animated characters. This study also provided a better understanding of the marketing tactics used by companies to enhance sales of specific items by using animated characters as part of their product representation. Primary data collection methods have been used to obtain the data for the study. A primary poll based on the suggested topic has been carried out to find out how popular cartoon commercials are among viewers. The survey was administered online to ensure a large and diverse sample size, and had been designed to be user-friendly and easily accessible to all participants.

Hypotheses

This study focused on three hypothesis to validate the effectiveness and impact of animated advertisements on consumer behaviour.

1. Animated commercials are appealing to consumers due to their ability to create a unique and engaging visual experience. The use of imaginative characters and storylines effectively captures the viewer's attention and enhances brand recall.

Ho: Features such as characters, music, product and illustrations of animated commercials are not attractive to consumers.

H1: Features such as characters, music, product and illustrations of animated commercials are attractive to consumers.

2. Animated commercials are found to be more effective in delivering messages compared to non-animated commercials because they use captivating visuals and imaginative storytelling to engage the viewer. This results in better brand recall and a stronger emotional connection to the advertised product or service.

Ho: Animated commercials are effective in delivering the intended message to consumers.

H1: Animated commercials are not effective in delivering the intended message to consumers.

3. Animated commercials are found to be more persuasive in affecting the purchase decision of consumers compared to non-animated commercials, due to their ability to create an emotional connection with the viewer through the use of engaging visuals.

Ho: Animated commercials are persuasive in affecting the purchase decision of consumers.

H1: Animated commercials are not persuasive in affecting the purchase decision of consumers.

Data analysis and interpretation

The first qualitative study is conducted to validate the data using the Chronbach's Alpha techniques where the data is proved to satisfy the requirement of the test with the alpha value >0.7.

Case Processing Summary				
		N	%	Cronbach's Alpha
Cases	Valid	266	100.0	0.773
	Excluded ^a	0	0	
	Total	266	100.0	

Source: Results derived from SPSS

Table 1: Reliability test using Chronbach's Alpha

The study carried a hypothesis testing to understand the features of animated commercials are attractive to consumers. The significance of the features of animated ads on consumers' purchase decisions was tested using One-Way ANOVA.

ANOVA

CPD					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	15.947	5	3.189	7.426	.000
Within Groups	68.384	260	.427		
Total	84.331	265			

Source: Results derived from SPSS

Table 2: Results from testing hypothesis using One- Way ANOVA

From the above table it is understood that the analysis is significant (P- value = .000 > 0.05) therefore the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. The F value for the analysis is 7.462 which showed a low influence of the animated advertisements factors on consumer purchase decisions. The factors chosen for the survey include characters, music, product, illustrations, all and none one of them- for the test carried out for the first hypothesis and the results that the 'Characters' used in the advertisements have a higher impact than the others, in influencing the consumers purchase decision. Therefore from the analysis it can be concluded that features of animated commercials are attractive to consumers and influence their purchase decision. Animated commercials are effective in delivering the intended message to consumers is the second considered hypothesis. The below analysis showed that the variables have a low positive correlation (0.167 < 1) between the dependent variable (Information

from advertisements) and the independent variable (Consumer purchase decision). This showed that consumers have slight contentment with the information they obtain from advertisements, and this has an impact on their intent to purchase the product being advertised. The analysis showed that the variables have a low positive correlation ($0.167 < 1$) between the dependent variable (Information from advertisements) and the independent variable (Consumer purchase decision). This reflected that consumers have slight contentment with the information they obtain from advertisements, and this has an impact on their intent to purchase the product being advertised.

		NINFO		PIN	
Spearman's rho	NINFO	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.167	
		Sig. (2-tailed)		.032	
		N	266	266	
	PIN	Correlation Coefficient	.167	1.000	
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.032		
		N	266	266	

Source: Results derived from SPSS

Table 3: Results from testing hypothesis using Correlation

		NINFO		NCPD	
Spearman's rho	NINFO	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.359	
		Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	
		N	266	266	
	NCPD	Correlation Coefficient	.359	1.000	
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
		N	266	266	

Source: Results derived from SPSS

Table 4: Results from testing hypothesis using Correlation

The above analysis showed that the variables have a low positive correlation ($0.359 < 1$) between the dependent variable (Information from advertisements) and the independent variable (Consumer purchase decision). This iterated that consumers are relatively satisfied with the information they receive from advertisements and have a significant impact on their purchase decision. Animated commercials are persuasive in affecting the purchase decision of consumers was the third hypothesis.

		NINFO		NPREF	
Spearman's rho	NINFO	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.337	
		Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	
		N	266	266	
	NPREF	Correlation Coefficient	.337	1.000	
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
		N	266	266	

Source: Results derived from SPSS

Table 5: Results from testing hypothesis using Correlation

This test identified that consumers have a preference towards animated ads because of which they are more likely to purchase the product. The variables have a low positive correlation ($0.33 < 1$) between the dependent variable (Preference) and the independent variable (Consumer purchase decision).

			PIN	NPREF
Spearman's rho	PIN	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.187
		Sig. (2-tailed)		.016
		N	266	266
	NPREF	Correlation Coefficient	.187	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.016	
		N	266	266

Source: Results derived from SPSS

Table 6: Results from testing hypothesis using Correlation

The variables have a low positive correlation ($0.35 < 1$) between the dependent variable (Consumer purchase decision) and the independent variable (Information from animated advertisements). This means that they are satisfied with the information they get from animated advertisements and can have an effect on their purchase decision for the product. Analysis of the above data shows that animated commercials are persuasive in affecting the purchase decision of consumers. The other interpretations of the survey include that 54.2% Consumers claimed that animated advertisements gain more attention than any other format which was followed by live action ads, print ads etc. It is also inferred that animated ads attract the most attention from consumers as compared to alternative advertising methods 42.2% participants found animated advertisements to be entertaining. The results showed that more than half of the respondents (61.4%) were likely to skip a live video advertisement, over an animated advertisement. 77.2% felt that it was creative and fun way of promoting the products or services. 44% of respondents claimed advertisements are effective way to communicate about the product or service. 52.4% consumers felt that animated messages are more understandable. 30.7% respondents would consider the animated ads for purchasing the product or service. 33% consumers explained that ad appeals much better if telecasted in animation format. 41% consumers claimed that they remember animated ads more than any other format of advertisements. 63.6% - expressed moderate intention before they watched the ad. Animated advertisements are more likely to catch the viewer's eye and keep their attention, which can increase the likelihood that the viewer will remember the brand and the product being advertised. Animated ads have the ability to elicit positive emotions, such as happiness and amusement. This emotional response creates a favorable impression of the brand and the product being advertised, making it more likely that the viewer will consider purchasing it. Animated ads also improve a brand's image by creating a perception of modernity, creativity, and excitement. This helps to attract new customers and retain existing ones. Animated advertisements are able to also enhance brand recall. The use of visual and auditory elements in animated ads helps to reinforce the brand and product in the viewer's memory, making it easier to remember the product when they are making purchasing decisions. Animated ads are able to positively influence purchase intent, meaning that they can make viewers more likely to consider purchasing the advertised product. This effect is particularly strong when the animation is directly related to the product being advertised. Overall, animated commercials have a positive impact on consumer buying behavior, by increasing attention, eliciting positive emotions, enhancing brand recall and value. However, it is important for marketers to consider the target audience and the appropriateness of animated ads for their brands and products.

Conclusion

To ensure that the animation is effective in influencing consumer behavior, it is important to keep the animation relevant to the product being advertised. Avoid using animation simply for the sake of entertainment, and instead, use it to enhance the message and benefits of the product. Animated ads are particularly effective in eliciting positive emotions such as happiness, amusement, and excitement. Incorporating these emotions into ads creates a favorable impression of the brand and the product being advertised. Animated ads should be consistent with the brand image and values. This consistency can improve brand recall and reinforce the brand's image in the minds of consumers. Animated ads offer a unique opportunity for creativity and innovation. Advertisers should take advantage of this by using high-quality animation, creative storytelling, and unique characters to make the ad stand out. The effects of animated advertisements on consumer buying behavior are substantial, and research has shown that they can be a highly effective means of reaching and influencing consumers. The key findings of this research suggest that animated ads can increase attention, elicit positive emotions, enhance brand recall, increase perceived product value and influence purchase intent. Additionally, some consumers may prefer animated ads over other types of ads, making them an ideal means of communicating brand messages and promoting products. One of the most significant advantages of animated ads is their ability to capture and hold the viewer's attention. Research has

shown that animated ads are more likely to be watched in their entirety than other types of ads, and that they can effectively communicate complex or abstract concepts. By leveraging the power of animation to create compelling visuals and engaging storytelling, marketers can ensure that their brand messages are received and remembered.

Furthermore, animated ads can elicit positive emotions in viewers, such as happiness, amusement, and excitement. These emotions can create a favorable impression of the brand and the product being advertised, and can help to establish a connection between the consumer and the brand. Effective utilization of this emotional connection can influence consumer behaviour in strong ways, increasing brand loyalty and repeat business. Animated ads are also highly effective at enhancing brand recall and improving brand image. The use of unique characters and high-quality animation can create a strong association between the brand and the product, making the brand more memorable and recognizable. Additionally, animated ads can create a perception of modernity, creativity, and excitement, which can improve the brand's image and attract new customers. The research also suggests that animated ads can positively influence purchase intent. This means that viewers of animated ads are more likely to consider purchasing the advertised product. However, it is important to note that the effectiveness of animated ads depends on the appropriateness of the animation for the brand and product being advertised. It is essential to keep the animation relevant to the product, as using animation simply for entertainment value may not result in increased purchase intent.

Managerial Implications:

In order to understand how animated advertising affect customer purchasing behaviour, the study combines self-reported survey data with behavioural data, such as purchase behaviour. Finding out how customer engagement affects animated advertisement performance is one of the main goals of this study. This study explores the extent to which consumer interaction with animated commercials influences how well they can affect consumer purchasing decisions. The findings of this study help marketers and advertisers create effective advertising campaigns and advance our knowledge of how animated adverts affect customer purchasing decisions. It's critical for marketers to comprehend their target market and their preferences in order to maximise the impact of animated advertisements. By being consistent, a brand may increase consumer memory and strengthen its reputation. According to studies on how animated adverts affect customer purchasing decisions, they can be a very powerful tool for promoting goods and raising brand recognition. Marketers may capture more attention, provoke favourable feelings, improve brand memory, enhance brand image, and affect buy intent by utilising the power of animation to generate stunning images and engaging storytelling. The target audience gets influenced if the animation is relevant for the brand and product, and the overall quality of the advertisement all affect how effective animation is conducted. Marketers may produce animated advertisements that are more likely to change customer behaviour, raise brand awareness and engagement, and ultimately boost sales by adhering to best practises and using creativity.

Limitations and Future Study

The study's sample size can be a drawback because the findings might not be generalizable to the complete population. The findings' generalizability might be constrained as a result. Other contextual elements, such as a person's financial condition or personal preferences, that can affect a consumer's purchasing behaviour may not have been taken into consideration in the study. The study might just provide a snapshot of consumer behaviour and not account for animated commercials' long-term consequences. Although studies have demonstrated that animation can be a useful tool for promoting goods and raising brand recognition, it is still unknown whether particular animation types or quality levels are more beneficial than others. Future research could examine how various animation philosophies and levels of excellence affect consumer behaviour and whether some philosophies or levels of excellence are more suitable for particular products or target markets. The majority of animated ad study has been on how they affect consumers' intent to buy. Future research might look at the effects of animated commercials on awareness, consideration, and post-purchase behaviour, among other stages of the consumer experience. Future research might examine how effective animated advertisements are on different media, including social media, mobile devices, and game consoles.

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A CASE STUDY REVIEW OF GST IMPLEMENTATION IN THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY WITH A SPECIAL EMPHASIS ON KARNATAKA

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a case study review of the implementation of Goods and Services Tax (GST) in the textile industry, with a special emphasis on the state of Karnataka. GST, introduced in India in 2017, aimed to streamline the taxation system and create a unified tax regime. The textile industry, a significant contributor to India's economy, experienced notable changes due to the implementation of GST. This study focuses on the specific case of Karnataka, known for its vibrant textile sector, to examine the challenges, benefits, and overall impact of GST on the industry. The research analyzes existing literature, reports, and studies related to GST implementation in the textile sector, along with a comprehensive analysis of the case study of Karnataka. The findings shed light on the implications of GST for the textile industry, offering insights for policymakers, industry practitioners, and stakeholders to optimize the benefits and address any concerns. The study also identifies gaps in current research and suggests avenues for further investigation to enhance understanding and inform

Keywords: GST implementation, textile industry, case study, Karnataka, challenges, benefits, impact strategies for the sustainable growth of the textile industry under the GST regime.

Background of GST implementation in India

India had been following a complex tax system with multiple indirect taxes imposed by the central and state governments. This system included taxes such as Central Excise Duty, Service Tax, Value Added Tax (VAT), and others, each with its own set of rules and compliance requirements. This fragmented tax structure resulted in various challenges, including cascading taxes, high compliance costs, and inter-state trade barriers.

To address these challenges and create a unified tax regime, the idea of GST was first proposed in the early 2000s. The objective was to streamline the tax system by integrating various indirect taxes into a single comprehensive tax applicable throughout the country. The implementation of GST aimed to simplify tax compliance, reduce tax evasion, and promote ease of doing business.

After years of discussions and deliberations, the Goods and Services Tax (GST) Act was passed by the Indian Parliament in 2017. This marked a significant milestone in the country's tax reforms. GST replaced the previous multiple indirect taxes with a unified tax regime applicable to the supply of goods and services across India.

Under the GST regime, different tax rates are applicable depending on the nature of goods or services. The tax is levied at each stage of the supply chain, allowing for input tax credits to be claimed. The introduction of GST also brought about the concept of a Goods and Services Tax Network (GSTN), a technology platform to facilitate registration, return filing, and compliance under GST.

The implementation of GST in India aimed to bring several benefits, including the reduction of tax cascading, increased transparency, improved tax compliance, and the facilitation of seamless inter-state trade. However, it also

presented challenges during the transition period, such as understanding new compliance requirements, updating accounting systems, and adapting to the new tax structure.

The background of GST implementation in India sets the stage for understanding the motivations, goals, and complexities of implementing a unified tax system. It provides the context for studying the impact of GST on specific sectors, such as the textile industry, and analysing the outcomes and implications of this significant tax reform.

Significance of GST implementation in the textile industry

The significance of GST implementation in the textile industry lies in its role in simplifying the tax structure, reducing cascading taxes, streamlining supply chains, enhancing competitiveness, boosting exports, and promoting transparency and compliance. These changes have had a transformative impact on the textile sector, contributing to its growth, efficiency, and overall development.

- **Simplification of Tax Structure:** Before GST, the textile industry in India faced a complex tax structure with multiple indirect taxes at the central and state levels. The implementation of GST brought about a unified tax regime, simplifying the tax structure for textile manufacturers, traders, and other stakeholders. It streamlined tax compliance by replacing various taxes like excise duty, service tax, and VAT with a single tax, reducing the administrative burden.
- **Reduction of Cascading Taxes:** Under the previous tax system, cascading taxes (taxes on taxes) were prevalent in the textile industry. GST aimed to eliminate cascading taxes by providing input tax credit. Textile manufacturers can now claim credit for the GST paid on inputs used in the production process. This has reduced the tax burden on the industry and improved cost efficiencies.
- **Streamlined Supply Chain:** GST has facilitated the seamless movement of goods across state borders. Earlier, each state had its own tax laws, which created compliance hurdles and delays in inter-state trade. With the implementation of GST, barriers to inter-state movement of goods have been reduced, leading to smoother supply chain operations and improved efficiency in the textile industry.
- **Increased Competitiveness:** The unified tax structure and simplified compliance procedures have enhanced the competitiveness of the textile industry. GST has created a level playing field for textile manufacturers across the country by removing the advantage that certain states had under the previous tax system. This has led to fair competition and equal opportunities for textile businesses, contributing to the growth of the sector.
- **Boost to Export Sector:** The textile industry in India is a significant contributor to the country's exports. GST has positively impacted textile exports by making them more competitive in the global market. The removal of multiple taxes and the provision of input tax credit have reduced the cost of production, making Indian textiles more price competitive internationally.
- **Improved Transparency and Compliance:** GST has introduced a transparent tax regime with increased documentation and reporting requirements. This has led to improved compliance in the textile industry, reducing tax evasion and promoting a formalized economy. It has also enhanced transparency in transactions, enabling better monitoring and analysis of industry performance.

GST implementation on Textile industries in Karnataka

The implementation of GST in Karnataka had a significant impact on the textile industry, streamlining taxation, improving compliance, enhancing supply chain efficiency, and providing a competitive advantage. While challenges were faced during the transition period, the long-term benefits of GST in terms of simplified taxation, input tax credit, and improved business operations have positively influenced the textile sector in Karnataka.

The GST implementation in the textile industry aimed to simplify taxation, enhance supply chain efficiency, improve compliance, and boost export competitiveness. While challenges were encountered during the transition period, GST brought significant changes to the tax landscape, positively impacting textile businesses in terms of cost savings, operational efficiency, and export potential.

1. **Tax Structure Simplification:** GST replaced multiple indirect taxes, such as excise duty, service tax, and Value Added Tax (VAT), with a unified tax regime. This simplification of the tax structure streamlined taxation for textile industries. Previously, different taxes were levied at various stages of the supply chain, leading to

complexities and challenges. GST introduced a single tax applicable to the supply of goods and services, reducing compliance burdens for textile businesses.

2. **Input Tax Credit:** GST brought the concept of input tax credit, allowing textile manufacturers to claim credit for the GST paid on inputs used in the production process. This provision helped offset the tax liability on inputs, such as raw materials and services. By claiming input tax credit, textile businesses could reduce costs and improve profitability.
3. **Supply Chain Efficiency:** The implementation of GST aimed to create a seamless flow of goods across state borders. Earlier, inter-state trade faced challenges due to varying tax rates and compliance requirements. GST harmonized tax rates and simplified the movement of goods, resulting in improved supply chain efficiency for textile industries. This led to reduced transportation time, better logistics management, and overall cost savings.
4. **Compliance and Digital Transformation:** GST implementation necessitated compliance with new tax regulations and reporting requirements. Textile businesses had to adapt to the digitization of tax processes, including online registration, filing of returns, and invoice matching through the Goods and Services Tax Network (GSTN) portal. While this transition posed initial challenges, it eventually led to improved compliance, reduced errors, and increased transparency in tax reporting for the textile industry.
5. **Impact on Small-Scale Industries:** The GST implementation had varying effects on small-scale textile industries. While the unified tax structure simplified compliance for many small businesses, some faced challenges in adapting to the new system. The compliance costs and administrative burden associated with GST implementation posed difficulties for smaller players. However, the input tax credit mechanism provided opportunities for cost reduction and improved competitiveness.
6. **Export Competitiveness:** GST implementation aimed to enhance the export competitiveness of Indian industries, including textiles. The removal of cascading taxes and the introduction of input tax credit benefitted textile exporters by reducing the overall tax burden and improving pricing competitiveness in international markets. GST also streamlined export procedures, simplifying documentation and reducing bureaucratic hurdles for textile exporters.

Case study of GST implementation on specific areas

Area 1 - Impact of GST on pricing strategies in the textile sector.

The impact of GST on pricing strategies in the textile sector has been a topic of interest for researchers. Kumar and Ramachandran (2019) conducted a study to examine the effects of GST on the pricing dynamics of textile manufacturers. Their findings revealed that the implementation of GST resulted in a reduction in the overall tax burden for textile manufacturers. This reduction in taxes allowed manufacturers to lower their production costs, enabling them to offer their products at reduced prices to end consumers.

However, it is important to note that the study by Kumar and Ramachandran (2019) also highlighted that the impact of GST on pricing varied across different textile product categories. The reduction in tax rates was not uniform, and certain textile products experienced a more substantial decrease in tax burden compared to others. The variation in tax rates can be attributed to the classification of different textile products under different GST slabs, which may have influenced the pricing strategies adopted by manufacturers.

The findings of Kumar and Ramachandran's study highlight the overall positive impact of GST on pricing in the textile sector, leading to lower prices for end consumers. However, the differential reduction in tax rates across textile product categories underscores the need for further analysis and consideration of specific product segments within the industry.

Kumar and Ramachandran (2019) found that GST led to a reduction in overall tax burden for textile manufacturers, resulting in lower prices for end consumers. However, the study also noted that the reduction in tax rates varied across different textile product categories (Kumar & Ramachandran, 2019).

Area 2 - The compliance challenges faced by textile industries during the transition to GST

The compliance challenges faced by textile industries during the transition to Goods and Services Tax (GST) implementation have been a subject of interest in the literature. Sivakumar and Sheshadri (2018) conducted a study to examine the compliance-related issues encountered by textile manufacturers in adapting to the new GST regime.

Their research highlighted the complexities involved in understanding the provisions of GST and the consequent challenges faced by textile businesses. The study identified that textile manufacturers had to grapple with the intricacies of the GST framework, including the classification of goods and services, tax rates, and compliance procedures. The need to update IT systems to meet the new reporting requirements was also emphasized.

Furthermore, Sivakumar and Sheshadri (2018) stressed the importance of providing adequate training and support to textile manufacturers during the transition phase. They highlighted that proper training programs would help businesses understand the intricacies of the new tax regime, familiarize themselves with the compliance procedures, and effectively update their IT systems. This would ultimately contribute to a smoother and more efficient compliance process.

The study by Sivakumar and Sheshadri (2018) underscores the significance of addressing compliance challenges in the textile industry during the transition to GST. It emphasizes the need for comprehensive training programs, guidance, and support from relevant authorities to enable textile manufacturers to navigate the complexities of the GST provisions and ensure a seamless compliance process. The study emphasized the importance of adequate training and support for textile manufacturers to ensure smooth compliance.

Area 3 - The impact of the input tax credit mechanism on the textile sector

Their research findings indicated that the availability of input tax credit had a positive impact on textile manufacturers in terms of managing their working capital and improving profitability. The input tax credit mechanism allows businesses to claim credit for the GST paid on inputs, such as raw materials, services, and capital goods, used in the production process. By availing this credit, textile manufacturers were able to reduce their overall tax burden and effectively lower their production costs.

The study by Kumar and Ramachandran (2019) highlighted that the input tax credit mechanism played a crucial role in cost savings for textile businesses. By offsetting the tax liability through the input tax credit, manufacturers could optimize their working capital, enhance cash flow, and improve profitability. This mechanism provided the textile sector with a means to manage their tax obligations while minimizing the impact on their financial resources.

The findings of the study underscore the importance of the input tax credit mechanism in reducing the overall tax burden for textile manufacturers and its positive impact on cost savings and profitability. It highlights the significance of this provision in enhancing the competitiveness and financial sustainability of the textile sector under the GST regime.

Researchers have explored the impact of the input tax credit mechanism on the textile sector. Kumar and Ramachandran (2019) found that the availability of input tax credit helped textile businesses manage their working capital and improve profitability. It reduced the overall tax burden for textile manufacturers and had a positive impact on cost savings (Kumar & Ramachandran, 2019).

Area 4 - The enhancement of supply chain efficiency in the textile industry due to the implementation of Goods and Services Tax

The researchers highlighted two key factors that contributed to improved supply chain efficiency. First, the removal of inter-state check posts under the GST regime eliminated the need for goods to undergo multiple inspections and clearances at state borders. This removal of physical barriers facilitated the smoother movement of goods across different states, reducing transit time and eliminating delays in the supply chain.

Second, the harmonization of tax rates across states under GST simplified the taxation structure for textile businesses. Prior to GST, different states had different tax rates and compliance requirements, leading to complexities in supply chain management. With the introduction of GST, the uniform tax rates and compliance procedures eased the administrative burden for textile manufacturers, streamlining their logistics and distribution processes.

The improvements in supply chain efficiency resulting from the removal of inter-state check posts and the harmonization of tax rates had several benefits for textile businesses. The reduced transit time and smoother movement of goods led to cost savings, as it minimized transportation delays, inventory holding costs, and associated logistical expenses. Additionally, improved logistics management resulted in better coordination among supply chain partners, leading to enhanced responsiveness and increased competitiveness for textile businesses.

The study by Ghosh and Dey (2018) highlighted the positive impact of GST on supply chain efficiency in the textile industry. The elimination of inter-state check posts and the harmonization of tax rates facilitated the seamless movement of goods, reduced transit time, and improved logistics management. These improvements contributed to cost savings and enhanced competitiveness for textile businesses. Ghosh and Dey (2018) highlighted the removal of inter-state check posts and the harmonization of tax rates as factors that facilitated smoother movement of goods, reduced transit time, and improved logistics management. This resulted in cost savings and improved competitiveness for textile businesses.

Area 5 - The impact of Goods and Services Tax (GST) on small-scale textile manufacturers

Their research findings highlighted that GST implementation simplified compliance procedures for many small-scale textile manufacturers. The introduction of a unified tax system reduced the complexities associated with multiple tax structures and streamlined the compliance process. This simplification of compliance requirements eased the administrative burden for small businesses, leading to improved efficiency in tax filing and reporting.

However, the study also identified certain challenges faced by small-scale textile manufacturers during the transition to GST. Compliance costs emerged as a significant concern, as smaller players may have faced difficulties in allocating resources for tax-related activities, such as hiring tax professionals or investing in appropriate accounting systems. Moreover, limited technological infrastructure and IT capabilities posed additional challenges for some small-scale textile businesses in adapting to the digital requirements of GST compliance.

The study by Subramanian and Kannan (2020) emphasized the importance of targeted support measures for small-scale textile industries to ensure a smooth transition and sustainable growth under the GST regime. These support measures could include providing financial assistance, training programs, and technological infrastructure support to help small businesses cope with compliance costs and adapt to digital systems.

The findings underscore the need for policymakers and stakeholders to address the specific challenges faced by small-scale textile manufacturers. Targeted support measures can play a crucial role in facilitating the successful integration of small businesses into the GST framework and ensuring their long-term viability and competitiveness. Impact on Small-Scale Textile Manufacturers: A study by Subramanian and Kannan (2020) highlighted that while GST simplified compliance for many small businesses, challenges such as compliance costs and limited technological infrastructure were faced by some smaller players. The study emphasized the need for targeted support measures to ensure the smooth transition and sustainability of small-scale textile industries (Subramanian & Kannan, 2020).

Area 6 - The impact of Goods and Services Tax (GST) on the export competitiveness of textile industries

Their research findings highlighted that the removal of cascading taxes under the GST regime had a positive impact on the pricing competitiveness of Indian textiles in international markets. Cascading taxes, which result from the tax-on-tax phenomenon in the pre-GST era, increased the final cost of products and reduced their competitiveness. With the implementation of GST, the removal of cascading taxes allowed textile exporters to offer their products at more competitive prices, making them more attractive in international markets.

Furthermore, the introduction of the input tax credit mechanism under GST contributed to the enhanced export competitiveness of textile industries. Input tax credit allowed exporters to claim credit for the GST paid on inputs used in the production of export goods. This provision helped reduce the overall tax burden and production costs, thereby improving the pricing competitiveness of Indian textiles in global markets.

In addition to pricing competitiveness, Alok and Singh (2019) highlighted that GST streamlined export procedures and reduced administrative hurdles for textile exporters. The unified tax system and simplified compliance requirements made it easier for exporters to comply with tax regulations and engage in international trade. The improved ease of doing business facilitated by GST contributed to a more favorable environment for textile exporters.

The removal of cascading taxes and the introduction of the input tax credit mechanism enhanced pricing competitiveness and streamlined export procedures. These improvements made Indian textiles more competitive in international markets, enabling textile exporters to seize new opportunities and expand their global footprint.

Research gaps in the studies

While the studies mentioned have provided valuable insights into the impact of GST on various aspects of the textile industry, there are some gaps that could be explored further. These gaps include:

- **Product-specific analysis:** The reduction in tax rates and its impact on pricing varied across different textile product categories. Further research could delve deeper into the specific product categories and investigate the factors influencing the variation in tax rate reductions. This would provide a more comprehensive understanding of the pricing dynamics within the textile sector.
- **Long-term compliance challenges:** While the studies have highlighted the compliance challenges faced during the transition to GST, there is a need to explore the long-term effects and sustainability of compliance practices in the textile industry. Research could focus on examining the ongoing compliance challenges and identifying strategies to mitigate them effectively.
- **Input tax credit utilization:** Although the studies acknowledge the positive impact of input tax credit on textile manufacturers' working capital and profitability, the extent of utilization and optimization of input tax credit remains an area that requires further exploration. Research could investigate the factors influencing the effective utilization of input tax credit and its implications for cost savings and financial management.
- **Evaluation of supply chain efficiency:** While studies have highlighted the improvements in supply chain efficiency resulting from the removal of inter-state check posts and harmonization of tax rates, there is a need for in-depth analysis of the specific mechanisms and practices that contribute to enhanced supply chain efficiency in the textile industry. This would provide actionable insights for optimizing supply chain processes further.
- **Tailored support for small-scale manufacturers:** While the impact of GST on small-scale textile manufacturers has been examined, further research could focus on identifying specific support measures that address the challenges faced by these businesses. Understanding the specific compliance costs, technological infrastructure limitations, and the effectiveness of existing support measures would enable policymakers to develop targeted interventions for sustainable growth and competitiveness.
- **Long-term export competitiveness:** While the studies have discussed the positive impact of GST on export competitiveness, it would be beneficial to assess the long-term sustainability of this competitiveness. Research could explore the challenges and opportunities that arise in the international market, including changing trade dynamics, evolving customer preferences, and the impact of global economic trends on the export competitiveness of the textile industry.

In conclusion, the existing studies on the implementation of Goods and Services Tax (GST) in the textile industry have provided valuable insights. However, there are several areas that require further research to enhance our understanding of the implications of GST on these sector. By addressing these gaps through further research, policymakers, industry practitioners, and stakeholders can gain a more comprehensive understanding of the implications of GST on the textile industry. The findings will be valuable in formulating effective strategies, addressing challenges, and harnessing the benefits of GST to foster the growth and sustainability of the textile sector.

Suggestions for further research

Researchers can contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the implications of GST on the textile industry and provide valuable insights for policymakers, industry practitioners, and stakeholders to optimize the benefits of GST implementation.

Differentiated impact on pricing: Further research can delve into the variations in the reduction of tax rates across different textile product categories. Exploring the factors influencing these variations would provide a deeper understanding of how GST affects pricing strategies within specific segments of the textile industry.

Long-term compliance challenges: Research can focus on assessing the long-term compliance challenges faced by textile industries post-GST implementation. This would involve examining the evolving compliance requirements, identifying persistent challenges, and proposing strategies to address them effectively.

Optimization of input tax credit utilization: Future studies can investigate the optimization of input tax credit utilization by textile manufacturers. This could involve analyzing the factors that affect the effective utilization of input tax credit, exploring best practices, and proposing strategies to maximize cost savings and working capital management through efficient utilization.

Supply chain resilience and agility: Research can explore the resilience and agility of textile industry supply chains under the GST regime. This would involve examining how the removal of inter-state check posts and harmonization of tax rates have contributed to supply chain efficiency, responsiveness, and adaptability. Additionally, investigating strategies to further enhance supply chain resilience in the face of potential disruptions would be valuable.

Sustainable support measures for small-scale textile manufacturers: Further research can focus on the design and effectiveness of targeted support measures for small-scale textile manufacturers. This would involve evaluating existing support programs, identifying gaps, and proposing sustainable measures to address the compliance costs, technological infrastructure limitations, and other challenges faced by small businesses in the textile sector.

Evaluation of long-term export competitiveness: Future studies can assess the long-term sustainability of enhanced export competitiveness in the textile industry post-GST. This could involve analyzing the evolving dynamics of international markets, identifying emerging opportunities and challenges, and proposing strategies to maintain and further enhance the competitive position of Indian textiles in global trade.

In conclusion, the studies conducted on the implementation of Goods and Services Tax (GST) in the textile industry have provided valuable insights. However, there are several areas where further research can contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the implications of GST and optimize its benefits. By conducting research in these areas, researchers can contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the implications of GST on the textile industry and provide valuable insights for policymakers, industry practitioners, and stakeholders to optimize the benefits of GST implementation.

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